

PENNSYLVANIA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION
ARCHAEOLOGICAL PREDICTIVE MODEL SET

$$\begin{matrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{matrix} = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$$

**TASK 2: DESIGNATING MODELING
REGIONS**

CONTRACT #355I01

ARCHAEOLOGICAL PREDICTIVE MODEL SET

Category #05 - Environmental Research

$$\bar{x} = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$$

December 2013

$$(x + a)^n = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} x^k a^{n-k}$$

URS

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ARCHAEOLOGICAL PREDICTIVE MODEL SET
TASK 2: DESIGNATING MODELING REGIONS**

CONTRACT #355I01

Prepared for

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ABSTRACT

This report is the documentation for Task 2 of the Statewide Archaeological Predictive Model Set project sponsored by the Pennsylvania Department of Transportation (PennDOT). This project was solicited under Contract #355I01, Transportation Research, Education, and Technology Transfer ITQ, Category #05 – Environmental Research. The goal of this project is to develop a set of statewide predictive models to assist the planning of transportation projects. PennDOT is developing tools to streamline individual projects and facilitate Linking Planning and NEPA, a federal initiative requiring that NEPA activities be integrated into the planning phases for transportation projects. The purpose of Linking Planning and NEPA is to enhance the ability of planners to predict project schedules and budgets by providing better environmental and cultural resources data and analyses. To that end, PennDOT is sponsoring research to develop a statewide set of predictive models for archaeological resources to help project planners more accurately estimate the need for archaeological studies.

The objective of Task 2 is primarily to define and justify the 10 regions of the Commonwealth for which individual predictive models will be created. The purpose of these divisions serves three main purposes: 1) to reduce the environmental variation within each model; 2) model groups of site locations that are more geographically related; and 3) to better organize the modeling process and computability. The basis for these divisions is physiographic section boundaries and watershed boundaries. These are non-arbitrary and predominately natural landscape divisions that contain more similar environments and presumably had effects on prehistoric settlement choices. Within each of the 10 regions, numerous smaller models will be created within areas defined by watersheds and physiographic sections. The smaller area models will then be aggregated into the larger regions.

This report provides a justification for the segmentation of regions and provides the methods by which the regions were selected, and summarizes the physical character of each region. In addition, this report provides summary tables of the archaeological resources and previous cultural resources surveys within each region.

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INTRODUCTION

Predictive models, even over small areas, require the segmenting of space for reasons of both model fit and computability. The latter is simply that modeling requires millions of raster calculations, and computers have a limited capacity based on available memory and processing power. Study areas require segmenting relative to the available computer resources in order to make the necessary calculations. When segmenting based on computability, the boundaries may be entirely arbitrary so long as the amount of data within each segment fits within the available computer resources. The former type of segmenting, based on model fitting, is a more deliberate task. Through this, the study area landscape is divided into areas to decrease certain sources of environmental variation while at the same time attempting to distribute the known site data points. This form of segmentation is required so that the patterns of environmental factor/site location correlations can be isolated as much as possible to give the best degree of regression model fit and, therefore, model performance. For example, the pattern of site location preference and common landforms in the Glaciated Plateau physiographic section of northwestern Pennsylvania differ substantially from those of the neighboring Central Lowlands section bordering Lake Erie. Attempts to model the sites and landforms of these regions together may result in poor performance because the correlation to environmental variables changes in each region. The process of segmenting the statewide Pennsylvania study area outlined below will balance the needs for computability with the distribution of both natural physiographic landforms and the distribution of known Pennsylvania Archaeological Site Survey (PASS) archaeological sites on file at the Pennsylvania Historical and Museum Commission (PHMC). The result is 10 regions within which numerous smaller models will be created and then mosaicked and validated at the regional level.

DATA AND METHODOLOGY

The division of the study area into 10 regions was performed with the project's Geographic Information System (GIS) and utilized physiographic sections, watersheds, and PASS archaeological site locations. The first step in this division was the creation of areas referred to as *physio-sheds*, which are the combination of physiographic sections and watershed boundaries. These areas capture the range of landforms inherent to each physiographic section, as well as the terrain and hydrologic dynamics specific to each watershed. The second step was to aggregate the physio-sheds into their associated physiographic sections and compare the similarities of each section relative to its size and the density of archaeological sites within it. Physiographic section boundaries were used as the primary modeling region boundary because the variations of landform geomorphology within a section is less than within major watersheds. Watershed boundaries serve as the primary division of individual models within each physiographic section. Finally, each of the 10 regions represents an aggregate of physio-sheds that share similar landforms, are generally confined to major watersheds, contain a relatively even distribution of archaeological sites, and are of reasonable size to make the modeling efforts comparable between regions.

In the next phases of the project, during which the modeling will take place, the physio-sheds will serve as the basis for individual models within each region. Modeling these smaller units will allow for more control over site patterning, outliers, and landform variation. Once successful models of each physio-shed are created, they will be mosaicked into the larger regional model.

DATA

The physical division of modeling regions was based on the Pennsylvania Department of Conservation and Natural Resources (DCNR) Map 13: Physiographic Provinces of Pennsylvania (Sevon 2000) and the Pennsylvania Department of Environmental Protection (DEP) Pennsylvania—104 State Water Plan watersheds (ERRI 1998). These two data sets provide statewide coverage delineating the landscape based on natural features. Such divisions are useful to this project because they are less arbitrary than political divisions, encompass areas of similar hydrology and environmental features, are at scales appropriate for the modeling of archaeological sensitivity, presumably had influence on prehistoric settlement decisions, and are readily available data sets that are commonly used within archaeological studies in Pennsylvania.

Based on Fenneman’s (1917) three-tiered physiographic hierarchy, the DCNR Map 13 (Figure 1) depicts divisions of the state where the underlying bedrock and geologic processes past and present have resulted in geomorphic landforms of similar character and origin. Fenneman’s (1917) work established a nested hierarchy of physiographic divisions, provinces, and sections to describe the range of geomorphic landscapes found across the United States. In Pennsylvania, there are three physiographic regions, six provinces, and 23 sections (Table 1).

Figure 1 - DCNR Map 13: Physiographic Provinces of Pennsylvania.

Table 1 - Physiographic Subdivisions of Pennsylvania

Region	Province	Section
Appalachian Highlands	Appalachian Plateaus	Allegheny Front
		Allegheny Mountain
		Deep Valleys
		Glaciated High Plateau
		Glaciated Low Plateau
		Glaciated Pocono Plateau
		High Plateau
		Northwestern Glaciated Plateau
		Pittsburgh Low Plateau
		Waynesburg Hills
	New England	Reading Prong
	Piedmont	Gettysburg-Newark Lowland
		Piedmont Lowland
		Piedmont Upland
	Ridge and Valley	Anthracite Upland
		Anthracite Valley
		Appalachian Mountain
		Blue Mountain
		Great Valley
South Mountain		
Susquehanna Lowland		
Atlantic Plain	Atlantic Coastal Plain	Lowland and Intermediate Upland
Interior Plains	Central Lowlands	Eastern Lake

Pennsylvania can be divided into eight major watersheds; these are the Delaware River, Susquehanna River, Potomac River, Genesee River, Allegheny River, Ohio River, Monongahela River, and Lake Erie (Figure 2). Combined, these basins drain Pennsylvania’s water into the Delaware and Chesapeake Bays, Mississippi River, Lake Erie, and Lake Ontario. Derived from these basin-level watersheds are the DEP’s 104 State Water Plan Watersheds (Figure 3). The GIS data layer for these watersheds was digitized in 1998 at a source scale of 1:24,000 from earlier 1983 State Water Plan maps.

Figure 2 - Major watersheds of Pennsylvania.

The use of subbasins such as these goes back to the original State Water Plan of the 1970s. For the creation of the original plan, large watersheds were divided into numerous subbasins that were then divided into the specific watersheds used here. The 104 watershed divisions were created as a state-wide planning tool and are commonly used by the PHMC to organize and quantify prehistoric archaeological site locations.

The GIS data representing DCNR Map 13 was created in 2008 by the Pennsylvania Bureau of Topographic and Geologic Survey, Department of Conservation and Natural Resources and available through the Pennsylvania Spatial Data Access (PASDA) site of the Pennsylvania Geospatial Data Clearinghouse (PAGS 2008). Nested within the larger physiographic provinces, these sections were digitized at a scale of 1:50,000 based on 20-foot contour intervals on County topographic maps. These data are not field checked and were developed for statewide and regional planning studies such as the Pennsylvania predictive model set.

Figure 3 - DEP State Water Plan 104 watersheds.

METHODOLOGY

The merging of physiographic sections and the 104 watersheds into a layer of physio-sheds was the primary methodological step in creating the modeling regions. Serving as the basis for the geographical divisions, the remainder of this task involved aggregating the physio-sheds, by physiographic section, into regions of manageable size and logical consistency.

The first step in combining physiographic sections and the 104 watersheds was to compute the geographic union of the two layers within the GIS. Essentially, a union operation is the combination of two or more collections into all of the possible combinations of those collections. Within a geographical framework, this operation results in each of the physiographic sections divided into each of the watersheds that fall within them. Further, the attribute data of each layer (i.e., watershed identification number, section, and province name) are assigned to each of the unique areas created from their union.

This operation works especially well for these two data sets because, in many instances, physiographic section boundaries and watershed boundaries are shared. The topographic ridges that divide some physiographic sections are also ridges that divide watersheds. However, the fact that the two data sets were digitized at different scales leads to some disparity regarding the shared boundaries. Being that the boundaries of watersheds are digitized at a more refined scale than those of the physiographic sections, they are a closer representation of reality. The output from the union operation was visually inspected, and common boundaries between layers were corrected to reflect the more accurate watershed boundaries. Finally, the area of each of the resulting union polygons was calculated and sorted to remove or inspect any small-sized areas for potential errors or uncorrected overlaps. The result of these operations was a layer of 250 physio-sheds representing the division of physiographic sections by the watersheds within them (Figure 4).

Figure 4 - Pennsylvania divided into 250 physio-sheds.

The creation of the final 10 modeling divisions resulted from the aggregation of physio-sheds into physiographic sections and the aggregation of sections into modeling regions. As previously mentioned, the aggregation of physiographic sections into modeling regions was based on combining sections from the same province or that shared similar geomorphic characteristics and attempting to divide the state into roughly equal areas. The exception to this was the assignment

of the Lowland and Intermediate Upland section of the Atlantic Coast Plain province and the Eastern Lake section of the Central Plains province into individual regions. This was done because each of these regions offer geomorphic settings that are quite different from the rest of the state; additionally, the Atlantic Coastal Plain contains much of the highly developed part of Philadelphia County. The final result of this process was the division of the state into 10 main modeling regions, each subdivided by physio-shed (Figure 5). The smaller physio-sheds will serve as the primary modeling units that will then be aggregated into modeling regions.

Figure 5 - Pennsylvania divided into 10 modeling regions and underlain by physio-shed boundaries.

REGIONS OVERVIEW

The 10 modeling regions were created with the intent of segmenting the state into regions that balance similar geomorphology and size comparability, share the same drainage basins, and equally distribute known PASS sites; in order of importance. The sections below synthesize the physical and cultural resources data for each of the 10 modeling regions

PHYSICAL DATA

The 10 modeling regions cover the state of Pennsylvania in a roughly uniform fashion, with the exception of the small Regions 3 and 10, which represent the Central Lowlands and Atlantic Coastal Plain provinces, and the larger Regions 1 and 4. Table 2 depicts the area of each region in square miles and the percent of the state's total area.

Table 2 - Area of Modeling Regions in Square Miles

Region	Square Miles	Percent of Area
1	12,337	27%
2	5101	11%
3	240	1%
4	4612	10%
5	4051	9%
6	5233	12%
7	5258	12%
8	3664	8%
9	4552	10%
10	227	1%
Total	45275	100%

As previously discussed, a major factor guiding the establishment of modeling region boundaries was physiography. The 10 modeling regions encompass the variability in the state's physiography by nesting like physiographic provinces and sections. While the Appalachian Plateaus and Ridge and Valley physiographic province are split between multiple modeling regions, each physiographic section is fully contained within a single region. Table 3 shows the breakdown of physiographic provinces and sections for each modeling region. Similarly, Table 4 depicts the breakdown of major watersheds per modeling region. Table 5 shows the count of physio-sheds per modeling region. Note that with the exception of the smaller Regions 3 and 10, the number of physio-sheds per region ranges from 16 to 40. Finally, Figure 6 graphs the variation of area contained within each physio-shed.

Table 3 - Breakdown of Physiographic Provinces and Sections by Modeling Region

Modeling Region	Physiographic Province	Physiographic Section
1	Appalachian Plateaus	Allegheny Mountain
		Allegheny Front
		Waynesburg Hills
		Pittsburgh Low Plateau
2	Appalachian Plateaus	High Plateau
		Northwestern Glaciated Plateau
3	Central Lowlands	Eastern Lake
4	Ridge and Valley	Appalachian Mountain
5	Ridge and Valley	Susquehanna Lowland
		Anthracite Upland
6	Appalachian Plateaus	Deep Valleys
		Glaciated High Plateau
7	Appalachian Plateaus	Glaciated Pocono Plateau
		Glaciated Low Plateau
	Ridge and Valley	Anthracite Valley
8	Ridge and Valley	Blue Mountain
		Great Valley
		South Mountain
	New England	Reading Prong
9	Piedmont	Gettysburg-Newark Lowland
		Piedmont Upland
		Piedmont Lowland
10	Atlantic Coastal Plain	Lowland and Intermediate Upland

Table 4 - Breakdown of Major Watersheds by Modeling Region

Modeling Region	Major Watersheds
1	Allegheny
	Monongahela
	Ohio
2	Allegheny
	Lake Erie
	Ohio
3	Lake Erie
4	Potomac
	Susquehanna
5	Delaware
	Susquehanna
6	Allegheny
	Genesee
	Susquehanna
7	Delaware
	Susquehanna
8	Delaware
	Susquehanna
	Potomac
9	Delaware
	Susquehanna
	Potomac
10	Delaware

Table 5 - Count of Physio-Sheds by Modeling Region

Modeling Region	Number of Physio-Sheds
1	52
2	16
3	1
4	19
5	28
6	21
7	32
8	36
9	40
10	5
Total	250

Figure 6 - Histogram and cumulative frequency of physio-shed area in square miles.

CULTURAL RESOURCES DATA

The identified archaeological resources of Pennsylvania, as recorded in the PASS database, are not distributed equally. Table 6 shows the distribution of prehistoric PASS sites by region; these include sites with only a prehistoric component as well as those with both prehistoric and historic components. Sites that are exclusively historic are not included in this study. The assignment of these components was derived from the chronology table of the PASS database. PASS sites listed with unknown temporal components were omitted.

Table 6 - Count and Percentage of Prehistoric PASS Sites by Modeling Region

Modeling Region	Number of Prehistoric Sites	Percent of Prehistoric Sites
1	6244	34%
2	1767	10%
3	152	1%
4	1145	6%
5	1265	7%
6	376	2%
7	1024	6%
8	2518	14%
9	3718	20%
10	23	0%
Total	18232	100%

Comparing the number of all archaeological sites per square mile of each region against those with a prehistoric component provides a useful picture of the density of sites and some context for the variability in distribution (Table 7). The colors indicate the range of density within each column, from high (shades of green) to medium (yellow) to low (shades of red). The highest density of all sites is within Region 9, the Piedmont area of southeastern Pennsylvania, and the lowest density is in Region 6, the Deep Valleys and High Glaciated Plateau sections of north-central Pennsylvania. Considering sites with a primarily prehistoric component, the distribution changes quite a bit; most significantly in Region 10. Region 10 contains a large portion of the City of Philadelphia, therefore one would expect a much larger proportion of historic sites over prehistoric. On the other hand, the density of prehistoric sites is much higher across the rest of the Commonwealth.

Table 7 - Density of PASS Sites by Area of Modeling Region

Modeling Region	PASS Sites per Square Mile	Prehistoric Sites per Square Mile
1	0.59	0.51
2	0.45	0.35
3	0.87	0.63
4	0.29	0.25
5	0.37	0.31
6	0.09	0.07
7	0.28	0.19
8	0.79	0.69
9	0.96	0.82
10	0.81	0.10

Finally, Table 8 quantifies the Environmental Review (ER) surveys for each region. This table depicts the number of surveys per region and the total area of surveys per region. Additionally, this table shows the average area of surveys per region, the number of surveys per square miles of the region, and the approximate percent of each region that falls within a survey area. These data do not take into account the level of survey effort per survey area, as recorded in the CRGIS database. Surveys in this database include very large regional sampling surveys as well as very small property-specific surveys.

Table 8 indicates that the most well-surveyed regions are also the smallest—Regions 3 and 10. The least surveyed region is Region 6 in north central Pennsylvania. This region also contains the lowest density of recorded archaeological sites. The columns for surveys per region area and the average size of surveys per region reveal interesting details about survey coverage. While Regions 4 and 9 both have approximately 4% survey area coverage, Region 4 achieved this with fewer surveys of larger area, while Region 9 had, on average, smaller surveys, but more of them. Overall, for most regions, previous ER survey boundaries cover from 2% to 8% of the area.

Table 8 - Count and Density of ER Survey Polygons Intersecting each Modeling Region

Region	Number of ER Surveys	Square Miles of Survey	Average Square Miles per Survey	Number of Surveys per Square Mile	Percent of Region Surveyed
1	3079	817	0.27	0.25	7%
2	490	328	0.67	0.10	6%
3	111	33	0.30	0.46	14%
4	599	218	0.36	0.13	5%
5	652	78	0.12	0.16	2%
6	449	43	0.10	0.09	1%
7	996	124	0.12	0.19	2%
8	1330	212	0.16	0.36	6%
9	1619	180	0.11	0.36	4%
10	178	24	0.13	0.78	11%
Total	9503	2057	-	-	-

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The modeling regions discussed and characterized above were created to help in the statewide modeling effort by consolidating physiographic variation, grouping areas of similar archaeological site density, and partitioning the state into manageably sized regions for modeling logistics. The rationale for using physiographic sections as the primary boundary for modeling region division is centered on the inherent purpose of physiographic sections; that is, to group areas of similar geomorphology, which is the result of millions of years of interaction between geology, hydrology, and climate. Geomorphological development incorporates processes on the scale of tectonics to continental glaciation to regional drainage patterns. It is likely that many of the innumerable physical processes that led to the varied physiography of any region also played some part in the environmental component of settlement decisions made by Native Americans. Undoubtedly these decisions were based on more than just environmental input, but the physical world was clearly a significant influence in daily life. Being that the physiographic sections are the most widely acknowledged and well-studied manner of portioning the state into areas of like physiography, and being that the modeling process that will be used in this project attempts to quantify the environmental component of prehistoric settlement patterns, the use of physiographic sections as modeling division is appropriate. The specific physiographic sections that make up each modeling region are listed in Table 3.

Each of the 10 modeling regions is dissected into numerous smaller areas referred to as physio-sheds. These are the areas within each physiographic section that belongs to one of 104 different watersheds. The purpose of this is to break down modeling regions into smaller and non-arbitrary units that may still have had some bearing on prehistoric settlement patterning. The use of the DEP State Water Plan 104 watersheds is appropriate for its scale, non-arbitrary natural origin, and its use as a planning tool for many state agencies including the PHMC.

Through the construction of physio-sheds, the state was broken down into 250 regions with a unique combination of drainage and physiographic characteristics. The physio-sheds range in area from 0.2 to 890 square miles in area, but the majority are less than 150 square miles in area. They are of appropriate scale to build the individual models that are the building blocks of this project. In addition to the convenience of smaller data sets consistent with computational resources, the smaller areas also lend themselves to a more fine-grained analysis of outliers, regionally connected settlement patterns, and existing survey data, as well as to more efficient model tuning and ultimately model performance. Once acceptable models are created for each physio-shed, they will be mosaicked into their larger regions and presented as single models for each of the 10 regions.

The process by which the modeling regions were derived was relatively simple, reproducible, and based on existing data—data that were created for statewide planning studies such as this. The only customization of the original data sets was the fine-tuning of common boundaries shared between drainage basins and physiographic regions to better reflect the more accurate watershed data. From these regions, the unique physio-sheds were derived and will serve as the primary unit of analysis for this project.

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APPENDIX A

TABLES OF PASS SITES BY REGION

Table A-1. Region 1 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36VE0030	Prehistoric	-79.78833 41.17338	36VE0106	Prehistoric	-79.76781 41.3334
36VE0031	Prehistoric	-79.78755 41.17413	36VE0117	Prehistoric	-79.92079 41.25024
36VE0032	Prehistoric	-79.78655 41.17317	36VE0128	Prehistoric	-79.82029 41.25056
36VE0033	Prehistoric	-79.75051 41.20567	36VE0129	Prehistoric	-79.75379 41.30999
36VE0034	Prehistoric	-79.75194 41.20376	36VE0197	Prehistoric	-79.72674 41.22553
36VE0036	Prehistoric	-79.76968 41.18003	36VE0198	Prehistoric	-79.7274 41.22923
36VE0037	Prehistoric	-79.76097 41.1753	36VE0199	Prehistoric	-79.78333 41.23771
36VE0038	Prehistoric	-79.76511 41.17614	36VE0211	Prehistoric	-79.71268 41.20451
36VE0039	Prehistoric	-79.77583 41.19815	36VE0233	Prehistoric	-79.80606 41.28842
36VE0040	Prehistoric	-79.7747 41.19878	36VE0235	Prehistoric	-79.68471 41.31152
36VE0041	Prehistoric	-79.81061 41.1872	36VE0237	Prehistoric	-79.662 41.31696
36VE0042	Prehistoric	-79.78017 41.21874	36VE0241	Prehistoric	-79.84144 41.23796
36VE0043	Prehistoric	-79.78367 41.20977	36VE0243	Prehistoric	-79.7945 41.22409
36VE0044	Prehistoric	-79.77819 41.21989	36VE0247	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.63226 41.37933
36VE0045	Prehistoric	-79.77725 41.22026	36VE0248	Prehistoric	-79.61755 41.37431
36VE0046	Prehistoric	-79.77626 41.22069	36VE0249	Prehistoric	-79.71425 41.23528
36VE0047	Prehistoric	-79.76799 41.21712	36VE0251	Prehistoric	-79.62868 41.38085
36VE0048	Prehistoric	-79.77705 41.21141	36VE0252	Prehistoric	-79.62851 41.37926
36VE0052	Prehistoric	-79.7251 41.22191	36VE0253	Prehistoric	-79.62982 41.37912
36VE0053	Prehistoric	-79.72535 41.21581	36VE0254	Prehistoric	-79.63059 41.37873
36VE0054	Prehistoric	-79.78663 41.2464	36VE0255	Prehistoric	-79.6299 41.37793
36VE0055	Prehistoric	-79.73266 41.23664	36VE0256	Prehistoric	-79.63059 41.37763
36VE0057	Prehistoric	-79.72531 41.2101	36VE0257	Prehistoric	-79.63142 41.37759
36VE0075	Prehistoric	-79.63499 41.34304	36VE0258	Prehistoric	-79.63034 41.38026
36VE0076	Prehistoric	-79.63241 41.3442	36VE0259	Prehistoric	-79.61541 41.37325
36VE0077	Prehistoric	-79.63376 41.34358	36VE0260	Prehistoric	-79.61618 41.37392
36VE0078	Prehistoric	-79.62988 41.34356	36VE0261	Prehistoric	-79.61402 41.37298
36VE0079	Prehistoric	-79.64851 41.33047	36VE0271	Prehistoric	-79.79731 41.26489
36VE0080	Prehistoric	-79.65024 41.32727	36VE0290	Prehistoric	-79.6983 41.34478
36VE0081	Prehistoric	-79.62653 41.30596	36VE0293	Prehistoric	-79.68285 41.29939
Watershed 29-Appalachian Plateaus-Pittsburgh Low Plateau:					
36CL0012	Prehistoric	-79.58703 41.13299	36CL0060	Prehistoric	-79.59499 41.13332
36CL0013	Prehistoric	-79.64598 41.15895	36CL0061	Prehistoric	-79.55384 41.12172
36CL0018	Prehistoric	-79.66428 41.12303	36CL0062	Prehistoric	-79.56219 41.12241
36CL0019	Prehistoric	-79.62962 41.14231	36CL0063	Prehistoric	-79.41478 41.15141
36CL0022	Prehistoric	-79.66442 41.15463	36CL0064	Prehistoric	-79.24501 41.305
36CL0027	Prehistoric	-79.56578 41.10865	36CL0065	Prehistoric	-79.44663 41.16486
36CL0028	Prehistoric	-79.5098 41.1142	36CL0066	Prehistoric	-79.5269 41.11393
36CL0029	Prehistoric	-79.5121 41.11451	36CL0068	Prehistoric	-79.2706 41.29285
36CL0030	Prehistoric	-79.51543 41.11552	36CL0069	Prehistoric	-79.61383 41.18095
36CL0031	Prehistoric	-79.55329 41.12873	36CL0070	Prehistoric	-79.62189 41.16577
36CL0032	Prehistoric	-79.57049 41.10629	36CL0071	Prehistoric	-79.43419 41.16417
36CL0033	Prehistoric	-79.56669 41.11135	36CL0075	Prehistoric	-79.48656 41.175
36CL0034	Prehistoric	-79.56885 41.10045	36CL0076	Prehistoric	-79.48961 41.17411
36CL0035	Prehistoric	-79.56506 41.10046	36CL0077	Prehistoric	-79.47951 41.16942
36CL0036	Prehistoric	-79.56661 41.10662	36CL0082	Prehistoric	-79.53864 41.23208
36CL0037	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.47861 41.17151	36CL0083	Prehistoric	-79.40456 41.34981
36CL0038	Prehistoric	-79.55213 41.13185	36CL0085	Prehistoric	-79.62241 41.10697
36CL0039	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.55799 41.13144	36CL0089	Prehistoric	-79.24216 41.31625
36CL0042	Prehistoric	-79.53571 41.11716	36CL0090	Prehistoric	-79.32175 41.23425
36CL0043	Prehistoric	-79.56419 41.11756	36CL0091	Prehistoric	-79.37448 41.21625
36CL0044	Prehistoric	-79.56218 41.13587	36CL0106	Prehistoric	-79.4262 41.16239

Table A-1. Region 1 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36AR0440	Prehistoric	-79.23052 41.04006	36JE0017	Prehistoric	-79.11951 41.10446
36AR0441	Prehistoric	-79.33095 40.99534	36JE0018	Prehistoric	-79.11825 41.10662
36AR0458	Prehistoric	-79.62547 41.03481	36JE0019	Prehistoric	-79.1183 41.10822
36AR0459	Prehistoric	-79.62722 41.02947	36JE0022	Prehistoric	-79.13654 41.02456
36AR0472	Prehistoric	-79.25909 41.02951	36JE0035	Prehistoric	-79.1359 41.02679
36AR0473	Prehistoric	-79.25752 41.02864	36JE0036	Prehistoric	-79.13266 41.0262
36AR0482	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.61728 40.99108	36JE0037	Prehistoric	-79.13262 41.0274
36AR0547	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.29792 41.00971	36JE0038	Prehistoric	-79.13187 41.02086
36AR0559	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.29271 41.00967	36JE0039	Prehistoric	-79.15276 41.02617
36BT0032	Prehistoric	-79.70431 41.0791	36JE0040	Prehistoric	-79.15612 41.0295
36BT0033	Prehistoric	-79.70946 41.09274	36JE0041	Prehistoric	-79.16581 41.03343
36BT0034	Prehistoric	-79.76977 41.11789	36JE0042	Prehistoric	-79.16744 41.0329
36BT0035	Prehistoric	-79.73193 41.13013	36JE0043	Prehistoric	-79.16714 41.03492
36BT0036	Prehistoric	-79.71151 41.09783	36JE0044	Prehistoric	-79.17174 41.03793
36BT0037	Prehistoric	-79.70827 41.08714	36JE0045	Prehistoric	-79.17133 41.03518
36BT0038	Prehistoric	-79.77048 41.11574	36JE0046	Prehistoric	-79.17402 41.03551
36BT0039	Prehistoric	-79.73415 41.10507	36JE0047	Prehistoric	-79.09436 41.11624
36BT0183	Prehistoric	-79.69495 41.01085	36JE0048	Prehistoric	-79.14435 41.13481
36BT0196	Prehistoric	-79.71892 41.00567	36JE0049	Prehistoric	-79.14307 41.13639
36BT0258	Prehistoric	-79.77127 41.13688	36JE0050	Prehistoric	-79.13536 41.13229
36BT0285	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.78468 41.06479	36JE0051	Prehistoric	-79.1347 41.02857
36CD0004	Prehistoric	-78.7289 41.0927	36JE0052	Prehistoric	-79.12789 41.0274
36CD0007	Prehistoric	-78.68583 41.16822	36JE0053	Prehistoric	-79.12739 41.01983
36CD0008	Prehistoric	-78.69688 41.07741	36JE0054	Prehistoric	-78.9724 41.16845
36CD0085	Prehistoric	-78.69801 41.04736	36JE0055	Prehistoric	-79.05126 41.15959
36CD0092	Prehistoric	-78.66236 41.10214	36JE0056	Prehistoric	-79.0053 41.13315
36CL0001	Prehistoric	-79.66813 41.08338	36JE0057	Prehistoric	-79.03408 41.14439
36CL0002	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.61909 40.97778	36JE0058	Prehistoric	-79.20248 41.09399
36CL0005	Prehistoric	-79.37325 40.97344	36JE0059	Prehistoric	-79.1842 41.11956
36CL0016	Prehistoric	-79.34663 41.0047	36JE0060	Prehistoric	-79.12912 41.10847
36CL0017	Prehistoric	-79.5181 41.0228	36JE0061	Prehistoric	-79.07206 41.19169
36CL0024	Prehistoric	-79.50197 40.97832	36JE0062	Prehistoric	-79.06152 41.20453
36CL0025	Prehistoric	-79.50384 40.98278	36JE0069	Prehistoric	-79.20791 41.02356
36CL0026	Prehistoric	-79.50892 40.986	36JE0070	Prehistoric	-79.185 41.0359
36CL0078	Prehistoric	-79.2177 41.11633	36JE0075	Prehistoric	-79.09347 41.07967
36CL0079	Prehistoric	-79.21498 41.11013	36JE0076	Prehistoric	-79.18594 41.04118
36CL0081	Prehistoric	-79.65241 41.08165	36JE0077	Prehistoric	-79.16547 41.03032
36CL0084	Prehistoric	-79.65852 41.10212	36JE0078	Prehistoric	-79.08261 41.04567
36CL0086	Prehistoric	-79.2387 41.07464	36JE0079	Prehistoric	-79.11277 41.00329
36CL0087	Prehistoric	-79.23121 41.08453	36JE0080	Prehistoric	-78.88012 41.19541
36CL0088	Prehistoric	-79.24266 41.0359	36JE0081	Prehistoric	-78.96908 41.13705
36CL0092	Prehistoric	-79.29717 41.01355	36JE0082	Prehistoric	-79.06445 41.16993
36CL0093	Prehistoric	-79.29892 41.01269	36JE0083	Prehistoric	-79.04106 41.111
36CL0094	Prehistoric	-79.22174 41.11935	36JE0084	Prehistoric	-79.04984 41.03852
36CL0095	Prehistoric	-79.49348 41.016	36JE0085	Prehistoric	-79.20187 41.10974
36CL0096	Prehistoric	-79.30046 41.01635	36JE0086	Prehistoric	-79.04386 41.0659
36CL0097	Prehistoric	-79.2867 41.0138	36JE0087	Prehistoric	-79.03065 41.06585
36CL0098	Prehistoric	-79.28914 41.01434	36JE0088	Prehistoric	-79.00113 41.06712
36CL0099	Prehistoric	-79.34366 41.03275	36JE0089	Prehistoric	-79.09175 41.11612
36CL0100	Prehistoric	-79.37884 41.02022	36JE0090	Prehistoric	-79.09443 41.11037
36CL0101	Prehistoric	-79.3869 41.03984	36JE0091	Prehistoric	-79.09041 41.11551
36CL0102	Prehistoric	-79.3864 41.03992	36JE0092	Prehistoric	-79.09502 41.11497

Table A-1. Region 1 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36BT0013	Prehistoric	-80.10165 40.80314	36BT0259	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.12231 40.72557
36BT0014	Prehistoric	-79.858 40.82294	36BT0261	Prehistoric	-80.11576 40.80699
36BT0015	Prehistoric	-80.13289 40.80601	36BT0263	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.98341 40.81159
36BT0016	Prehistoric	-80.15074 40.78069	36BT0277	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.10567 40.81889
36BT0017	Prehistoric	-80.15303 40.78051	36BT0280	Prehistoric	-80.0195 40.81165
36BT0018	Prehistoric	-79.90465 41.09635	36BT0281	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.00613 40.8091
36BT0019	Prehistoric	-79.90073 41.13834	36BT0300	Prehistoric	-79.96263 40.82083
36BT0020	Prehistoric	-79.8977 41.13888	36BT0302	Prehistoric	-79.86616 40.79894
36BT0021	Prehistoric	-80.04925 40.80983	36BT0303	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.87261 40.78838
36BT0022	Prehistoric	-80.14641 40.785	36BT0304	Prehistoric	-80.14072 40.72093
36BT0023	Prehistoric	-80.09807 40.68272	36BT0305	Prehistoric	-80.09482 40.68151
36BT0024	Prehistoric	-79.8961 40.70306	36BT0306	Prehistoric	-80.08655 40.68581
36BT0026	Prehistoric	-79.9973 40.76963	36BT0307	Prehistoric	-80.09888 40.67791
36BT0027	Prehistoric	-79.99454 40.80029	36BT0315	Prehistoric	-79.93058 40.81791
36BT0028	Prehistoric	-80.16149 40.94559	36BT0321	Prehistoric	-79.85978 40.77098
36BT0031	Prehistoric	-79.9905 40.79969	36BT0322	Prehistoric	-79.85894 40.77168
36BT0040	Prehistoric	-79.90541 41.13539	36BT0324	Prehistoric	-79.83714 41.08024
36BT0041	Prehistoric	-79.90647 41.13466	36BT0326	Prehistoric	-79.87389 40.93999
36BT0042	Prehistoric	-79.89853 40.78495	36BT0327	Prehistoric	-80.0542 40.73619
36BT0043	Prehistoric	-79.87511 40.86545	36BT0329	Prehistoric	-80.00631 41.13249
36BT0044	Prehistoric	-79.88038 40.75075	36BT0331	Prehistoric	-80.0072 41.13151
36BT0045	Prehistoric	-80.08543 40.95851	36BT0337	Prehistoric	-80.11332 40.67728
36BT0046	Prehistoric	-79.88458 41.02808	36BT0338	Prehistoric	-80.11407 40.68049
36BT0047	Prehistoric	-80.03241 40.77684	36BT0341	Prehistoric	-80.02172 41.0248
36BT0049	Prehistoric	-80.021 40.78276	36BT0360	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.92723 40.96497
36BT0050	Prehistoric	-80.15183 40.80942	36BT0362	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.86793 40.97849
36BT0051	Prehistoric	-80.13652 40.803	36BT0363	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.03969 40.88241
36BT0052	Prehistoric	-80.13892 40.80266	36BT0364	Prehistoric	-80.10791 40.69092
36BT0053	Prehistoric	-80.11768 40.80515	36BT0365	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.09638 40.71668
36BT0054	Prehistoric	-80.08213 40.80447	36BT0371	Prehistoric	-80.13091 40.89634
36BT0055	Prehistoric	-80.01844 40.782	36BT0373	Prehistoric	-79.89681 40.85391
36BT0056	Prehistoric	-80.04765 40.95661	36BT0374	Prehistoric	-80.13457 40.71377
36BT0057	Prehistoric	-80.05543 40.94914	36BT0375	Prehistoric	-80.03903 40.70079
36BT0058	Prehistoric	-80.03759 40.94591	36BT0376	Prehistoric	-80.03654 40.69813
36BT0059	Prehistoric	-80.09457 40.93843	36BT0378	Prehistoric	-80.13666 40.71852
36BT0060	Prehistoric	-80.02118 40.94753	36BT0379	Prehistoric	-80.12865 40.70903
36BT0061	Prehistoric	-80.02616 40.94665	36BT0381	Prehistoric	-80.1443 40.72527
36BT0062	Prehistoric	-79.99769 40.94402	36BT0382	Prehistoric	-80.15022 40.72388
36BT0063	Prehistoric	-79.99712 40.94913	36BT0383	Prehistoric	-80.13652 40.71594
36BT0064	Prehistoric	-80.00487 40.95344	36BT0384	Prehistoric	-80.13324 40.71228
36BT0065	Prehistoric	-80.00875 40.95223	36BT0384	Prehistoric	-80.13316 40.7129
36BT0067	Prehistoric	-80.00605 40.94426	36BT0384	Prehistoric	-80.13385 40.71277
36BT0069	Prehistoric	-79.92541 40.6927	36BT0385	Prehistoric	-80.13188 40.711
36BT0070	Prehistoric	-79.95188 40.70215	36BT0386	Prehistoric	-80.12893 40.70993
36BT0071	Prehistoric	-79.89666 40.74062	36BT0387	Prehistoric	-80.12415 40.70571
36BT0072	Prehistoric	-79.89346 40.69966	36BT0388	Prehistoric	-80.02764 40.87986
36BT0073	Prehistoric	-80.14964 40.72505	36BT0415	Prehistoric	-80.13674 40.70615
36BT0074	Prehistoric	-80.02136 40.78476	36BT0417	Prehistoric	-79.95331 40.69842
36BT0075	Prehistoric	-80.02824 40.77896	36BT0418	Prehistoric	-79.95288 40.69832
36BT0076	Prehistoric	-80.07389 40.82827	36BT0419	Prehistoric	-79.95517 40.69845
36BT0077	Prehistoric	-80.04748 40.80013	36BT0420	Prehistoric	-79.95794 40.69822
36BT0078	Prehistoric	-80.03699 40.779	36BT0421	Prehistoric	-79.9476 40.69748

Table A-1. Region 1 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36BT0079	Prehistoric	-80.06022 40.7343	36BT0423	Prehistoric	-80.1219 40.70312
36BT0080	Prehistoric	-80.12856 40.81784	36BT0428	Prehistoric	-79.95918 40.69351
36BT0085	Prehistoric	-80.13313 40.92458	36BT0430	Prehistoric	-79.86187 41.05097
36BT0086	Prehistoric	-80.12292 40.704	36BV0028	Prehistoric	-80.18173 40.79698
36BT0087	Prehistoric	-80.0979 40.70291	36BV0031	Prehistoric	-80.18041 40.73322
36BT0089	Prehistoric	-80.04387 40.78129	36BV0034	Prehistoric	-80.20037 40.80865
36BT0090	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.11972 40.80923	36BV0062	Prehistoric	-80.21161 40.7479
36BT0091	Prehistoric	-80.07611 40.76001	36BV0063	Prehistoric	-80.20745 40.74711
36BT0092	Prehistoric	-80.08579 40.85559	36BV0064	Prehistoric	-80.18404 40.73654
36BT0094	Prehistoric	-80.14556 40.73186	36BV0065	Prehistoric	-80.15682 40.72689
36BT0095	Prehistoric	-80.13236 40.74255	36BV0066	Prehistoric	-80.2077 40.81418
36BT0096	Prehistoric	-80.12737 40.70627	36BV0067	Prehistoric	-80.24887 40.82139
36BT0097	Prehistoric	-79.87373 40.86394	36BV0072	Prehistoric	-80.22734 40.82297
36BT0098	Prehistoric	-79.9597 40.85157	36BV0136	Prehistoric	-80.18661 40.7996
36BT0103	Prehistoric	-80.0271 40.7914	36BV0140	Prehistoric	-80.20507 40.80636
36BT0104	Prehistoric	-80.02332 40.79337	36BV0141	Prehistoric	-80.25284 40.77404
36BT0105	Prehistoric	-80.0416 40.79982	36BV0142	Prehistoric	-80.2811 40.84209
36BT0109	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.9447 40.7075	36BV0143	Prehistoric	-80.25619 40.83556
36BT0110	Prehistoric	-80.0727 40.67438	36BV0149	Prehistoric	-80.15981 40.82269
36BT0111	Prehistoric	-80.07277 40.67724	36BV0150	Prehistoric	-80.23535 40.78329
36BT0112	Prehistoric	-80.14452 40.71957	36BV0151	Prehistoric	-80.1845 40.82458
36BT0113	Prehistoric	-79.94435 40.7106	36BV0152	Prehistoric	-80.15999 40.81003
36BT0114	Prehistoric	-79.94126 40.70676	36BV0153	Prehistoric	-80.20896 40.74401
36BT0115	Prehistoric	-80.11025 40.80182	36BV0154	Prehistoric	-80.16606 40.73117
36BT0116	Prehistoric	-80.07361 40.79838	36BV0155	Prehistoric	-80.16498 40.72975
36BT0117	Prehistoric	-79.98932 41.1368	36BV0156	Prehistoric	-80.25339 40.81692
36BT0118	Prehistoric	-79.90054 41.0969	36BV0157	Prehistoric	-80.25106 40.82174
36BT0119	Prehistoric	-79.9936 41.10666	36BV0158	Prehistoric	-80.2303 40.81922
36BT0121	Prehistoric	-80.00985 41.10739	36BV0181	Prehistoric	-80.15376 40.72264
36BT0122	Prehistoric	-80.00286 41.1073	36BV0182	Prehistoric	-80.18729 40.71143
36BT0123	Prehistoric	-79.99951 41.10767	36BV0183	Prehistoric	-80.185 40.70907
36BT0126	Prehistoric	-80.03709 41.08495	36BV0184	Prehistoric	-80.17621 40.71485
36BT0127	Prehistoric	-80.00083 41.10662	36BV0185	Prehistoric	-80.17947 40.71529
36BT0134	Prehistoric	-79.80634 40.77523	36BV0186	Prehistoric	-80.18288 40.71464
36BT0140	Prehistoric	-79.83046 40.83833	36BV0187	Prehistoric	-80.16049 40.72774
36BT0144	Prehistoric	-80.01003 41.14043	36BV0188	Prehistoric	-80.20768 40.7415
36BT0146	Prehistoric	-80.00711 41.13543	36BV0190	Prehistoric	-80.20644 40.74497
36BT0152	Prehistoric	-80.13265 40.80279	36BV0215	Prehistoric	-80.1813 40.85252
36BT0160	Prehistoric	-79.9879 40.75185	36BV0226	Prehistoric	-80.18084 40.80148
36BT0161	Prehistoric	-79.9917 40.75325	36BV0227	Prehistoric	-80.15677 40.80273
36BT0162	Prehistoric	-80.14991 40.87392	36BV0244	Prehistoric	-80.17599 40.84574
36BT0165	Prehistoric	-79.98351 41.072	36BV0258	Prehistoric	-80.23844 40.77039
36BT0172	Prehistoric	-80.04109 41.05999	36BV0263	Prehistoric	-80.25107 40.82048
36BT0173	Prehistoric	-80.04234 41.0662	36BV0264	Prehistoric	-80.25325 40.81607
36BT0184	Prehistoric	-80.15393 40.90324	36BV0273	Prehistoric	-80.1815 40.85027
36BT0185	Prehistoric	-80.08719 40.89754	36BV0288	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.26016 40.81847
36BT0186	Prehistoric	-80.08577 40.89762	36BV0289	Prehistoric	-80.25397 40.82087
36BT0187	Prehistoric	-80.07756 40.89794	36BV0290	Prehistoric	-80.25295 40.8207
36BT0188	Prehistoric	-80.01933 40.9115	36BV0291	Prehistoric	-80.25172 40.82045
36BT0189	Prehistoric	-80.01582 40.91462	36BV0292	Prehistoric	-80.25 40.82068
36BT0190	Prehistoric	-80.01608 40.92674	36BV0294	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.24659 40.82063
36BT0191	Prehistoric	-80.01065 40.92477	36BV0295	Prehistoric	-80.1703 40.82856

Table A-1. Region 1 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36BT0192	Prehistoric	-80.00282 40.93107	36BV0359	Prehistoric	-80.25803 40.76459
36BT0193	Prehistoric	-79.99712 40.93586	36LR0006	Prehistoric	-80.21049 40.95628
36BT0194	Prehistoric	-79.99715 40.93693	36LR0019	Prehistoric	-80.18031 40.85585
36BT0195	Prehistoric	-79.99309 40.93673	36LR0079	Prehistoric	-80.17988 40.87075
36BT0197	Prehistoric	-80.12069 40.96815	36LR0083	Prehistoric	-80.17005 40.85889
36BT0198	Prehistoric	-80.11593 40.96713	36LR0084	Prehistoric	-80.17269 40.85453
36BT0199	Prehistoric	-79.95456 41.15043	36LR0136	Prehistoric	-80.27659 40.90179
36BT0200	Prehistoric	-79.96129 41.05388	36LR0137	Prehistoric	-80.26529 40.90255
36BT0201	Prehistoric	-80.01092 41.13136	36LR0138	Prehistoric	-80.17046 40.90498
36BT0202	Prehistoric	-79.92822 40.90061	36LR0139	Prehistoric	-80.28359 40.89464
36BT0204	Prehistoric	-80.02164 41.02382	36LR0140	Prehistoric	-80.2839 40.89532
36BT0205	Prehistoric	-80.01849 41.01707	36LR0141	Prehistoric	-80.28094 40.89532
36BT0206	Prehistoric	-80.02729 41.03795	36LR0142	Prehistoric	-80.27539 40.89029
36BT0207	Prehistoric	-79.87113 40.73143	36LR0143	Prehistoric	-80.28241 40.9
36BT0208	Prehistoric	-79.86841 40.73044	36LR0144	Prehistoric	-80.27544 40.90022
36BT0209	Prehistoric	-80.02934 40.72273	36LR0166	Prehistoric	-80.25505 40.89495
36BT0210	Prehistoric	-80.02734 40.72626	36LR0177	Prehistoric	-80.1716 40.89331
36BT0211	Prehistoric	-79.9571 40.77652	36LR0178	Prehistoric	-80.17384 40.89289
36BT0212	Prehistoric	-79.93306 40.89897	36LR0187	Prehistoric	-80.24832 40.90915
36BT0222	Prehistoric	-79.87414 40.7313	36LR0188	Prehistoric	-80.2483 40.9222
36BT0223	Prehistoric	-79.89452 40.73279	36LR0252	Prehistoric	-80.1712 40.95493
36BT0224	Prehistoric	-80.02606 40.6819	36LR0253	Prehistoric	-80.17101 40.9615
Watershed 39-Appalachian Plateaus-Pittsburgh Low Plateau:					
36CD0084	Prehistoric	-78.35422 40.77349	36CE0504	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.22747 40.90227
36CE0344	Prehistoric	-78.09913 41.11875	36CE0520	Prehistoric	-78.26757 40.84742
Watershed 40-Appalachian Plateaus-Allegheny Front:					
36BL0064	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.15091 40.73666	36CE0447	Prehistoric	-78.03917 40.8137
36CE0056	Prehistoric	-77.95272 40.87389	36CE0449	Prehistoric	-78.04024 40.81358
36CE0057	Prehistoric	-77.95177 40.87294	36CE0451	Prehistoric	-78.08151 40.79152
36CE0097	Prehistoric	-77.84883 40.97873	36CE0453	Prehistoric	-78.02909 40.82311
36CE0098	Prehistoric	-77.85015 40.97907	36CE0456	Prehistoric	-78.07662 40.78846
36CE0099	Prehistoric	-77.84799 40.98015	36CE0457	Prehistoric	-78.07799 40.78901
36CE0100	Prehistoric	-77.85193 40.98025	36CE0460	Prehistoric	-78.06746 40.79156
36CE0201	Prehistoric	-77.72477 41.0426	36CE0492	Prehistoric	-78.07256 40.79781
36CE0212	Prehistoric	-77.65529 41.07153	36CE0532	Prehistoric	-77.9496 40.95897
36CE0213	Prehistoric	-77.7352 41.04926	36CE0533	Prehistoric	-77.94926 40.95923
36CE0214	Prehistoric	-77.67891 41.06061	36CE217a	Prehistoric	-77.72068 41.04272
36CE0215	Prehistoric	-77.72901 41.04458	36CE217b	Prehistoric	-77.71907 41.04191
36CE0216	Prehistoric	-77.7317 41.04406	36CE217c	Prehistoric	-77.71871 41.04135
36CE0217	Prehistoric	-77.71833 41.04092	36CE217d	Prehistoric	-77.71613 41.04111
36CE0218	Prehistoric	-77.72245 41.03982	36CE217e	Prehistoric	-77.71516 41.04043
36CE0219	Prehistoric	-77.72084 41.04379	36CE217f	Prehistoric	-77.71618 41.03995
36CE0220	Prehistoric	-77.69353 41.05363	36CE217g	Prehistoric	-77.71695 41.0395
36CE0221	Prehistoric	-77.68411 41.06004	36CE217h	Prehistoric	-77.7177 41.0401
36CE0222	Prehistoric	-77.68543 41.06149	36CE217i	Prehistoric	-77.7177 41.0409
36CE0223	Prehistoric	-77.68648 41.06244	36CE217j	Prehistoric	-77.71956 41.04044
36CE0224	Prehistoric	-77.688 41.06169	36CE217k	Prehistoric	-77.72074 41.0403
36CE0225	Prehistoric	-77.70036 41.04997	36CE217l	Prehistoric	-77.71992 41.04163
36CE0226	Prehistoric	-77.71639 41.05826	36CE217m	Prehistoric	-77.72094 41.04191
36CE0227	Prehistoric	-77.69709 41.05023	36CE217n	Prehistoric	-77.72057 41.04109
36CE0292	Prehistoric	-77.83993 40.92711	36CN0108	Prehistoric	-77.5965 41.11331

Table A-1. Region 1 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36AR0047	Prehistoric	-79.38015 40.93436	36IN0083	Prehistoric	-79.10306 40.90803
36AR0048	Prehistoric	-79.25544 40.92543	36IN0085	Prehistoric	-79.13998 40.84536
36AR0049	Prehistoric	-79.31857 40.94789	36IN0087	Prehistoric	-79.19576 40.89162
36AR0050	Prehistoric	-79.37317 40.93778	36IN0088	Prehistoric	-79.19807 40.89016
36AR0051	Prehistoric	-79.36588 40.93664	36IN0089	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.14017 40.90079
36AR0073	Prehistoric	-79.37588 40.91822	36IN0090	Prehistoric	-79.13546 40.90245
36AR0074	Prehistoric	-79.3862 40.93643	36IN0091	Prehistoric	-79.18435 40.8777
36AR0075	Prehistoric	-79.38696 40.94132	36IN0092	Prehistoric	-79.1014 40.90629
36AR0076	Prehistoric	-79.38933 40.93254	36IN0093	Prehistoric	-79.09582 40.90548
36AR0077	Prehistoric	-79.39121 40.92839	36IN0094	Prehistoric	-79.19637 40.89577
36AR0078	Prehistoric	-79.40384 40.92806	36IN0144	Prehistoric	-78.94978 40.76155
36AR0079	Prehistoric	-79.46127 40.91557	36IN0195	Prehistoric	-79.20567 40.88746
36AR0080	Prehistoric	-79.4809 40.89178	36IN0196	Prehistoric	-79.19826 40.89209
36AR0081	Prehistoric	-79.41659 40.97064	36IN0197	Prehistoric	-79.14479 40.89595
36AR0082	Prehistoric	-79.31943 40.97087	36IN0198	Prehistoric	-79.1292 40.90311
36AR0083	Prehistoric	-79.31213 40.95713	36IN0199	Prehistoric	-79.0974 40.90166
36AR0085	Prehistoric	-79.46309 40.91932	36IN0200	Prehistoric	-79.10054 40.90252
36AR0106	Prehistoric	-79.51258 40.85312	36IN0203	Prehistoric	-79.15799 40.85511
36AR0107	Prehistoric	-79.49889 40.86434	36IN0204	Prehistoric	-79.1548 40.85857
36AR0108	Prehistoric	-79.4932 40.86797	36IN0205	Prehistoric	-79.1545 40.86098
36AR0111	Prehistoric	-79.50034 40.86157	36IN0206	Prehistoric	-79.17554 40.87203
36AR0112	Prehistoric	-79.50296 40.84915	36IN0207	Prehistoric	-79.16372 40.86368
36AR0118	Prehistoric	-79.48753 40.92732	36IN0208	Prehistoric	-79.16535 40.86151
36AR0156	Prehistoric	-79.21901 40.91185	36IN0253	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.09346 40.886
36AR0191	Prehistoric	-79.27747 40.97229	36IN0294	Prehistoric	-79.0514 40.81571
36AR0192	Prehistoric	-79.3603 40.965	36IN0297	Prehistoric	-78.93834 40.7855
36AR0216	Prehistoric	-79.21757 40.84929	36IN0325	Prehistoric	-78.99154 40.77212
36AR0238	Prehistoric	-79.30163 40.9573	36IN0326	Prehistoric	-78.99246 40.77267
36AR0241	Prehistoric	-79.30282 40.95403	36IN0351	Prehistoric	-79.16577 40.89638
36AR0306	Prehistoric	-79.48038 40.89609	36IN0395	Prehistoric	-79.00344 40.86502
36AR0332	Prehistoric	-79.53604 40.93105	36IN0396	Prehistoric	-78.91665 40.88474
36AR0334	Prehistoric	-79.47933 40.90029	36IN0402	Prehistoric	-79.18216 40.90073
36AR0335	Prehistoric	-79.47877 40.89859	36IN0403	Prehistoric	-79.13298 40.84177
36AR0342	Prehistoric	-79.55459 40.94005	36IN0404	Prehistoric	-79.14155 40.84536
36AR0343	Prehistoric	-79.54235 40.93227	36IN0405	Prehistoric	-79.15834 40.85583
36AR0377	Prehistoric	-79.30967 40.97817	36IN0406	Prehistoric	-79.18303 40.87613
36AR0386	Prehistoric	-79.4847 40.88757	36IN0407	Prehistoric	-79.13436 40.83832
36AR0387	Prehistoric	-79.47249 40.93803	36IN0408	Prehistoric	-79.1394 40.84234
36AR0388	Prehistoric	-79.46794 40.93542	36IN0409	Prehistoric	-79.13987 40.84281
36AR0389	Prehistoric	-79.4819 40.88175	36IN0410	Prehistoric	-79.14143 40.84507
36AR0391	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.54177 40.94287	36IN0411	Prehistoric	-79.14334 40.85048
36AR0407	Prehistoric	-79.51787 40.84338	36IN0412	Prehistoric	-79.14701 40.85074
36AR0408	Prehistoric	-79.51634 40.843	36IN0413	Prehistoric	-79.14893 40.85222
36AR0413	Prehistoric	-79.49619 40.92061	36IN0414	Prehistoric	-79.15389 40.85723
36AR0418	Prehistoric	-79.30904 40.95333	36IN0415	Prehistoric	-79.15512 40.85866
36AR0432	Prehistoric	-79.31656 40.9864	36IN0416	Prehistoric	-79.18125 40.87522
36AR0433	Prehistoric	-79.31072 40.95286	36IN0417	Prehistoric	-79.18275 40.87717
36AR0434	Prehistoric	-79.38811 40.92905	36IN0418	Prehistoric	-79.10369 40.90247
36AR0453	Prehistoric	-79.4691 40.90595	36IN0419	Prehistoric	-79.10324 40.90413
36CD0024	Prehistoric	-78.79269 41.01615	36IN0420	Prehistoric	-79.10481 40.90236
36CD0025	Prehistoric	-78.79041 41.01808	36IN0421	Prehistoric	-79.08044 40.8551
36CD0031	Prehistoric	-78.74802 41.06462	36IN0422	Prehistoric	-79.0858 40.85797

Table A-1. Region 1 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36AR0415	Prehistoric	-79.66824 40.85302	36BT0291	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.72106 40.92138
36AR0416	Prehistoric	-79.64845 40.89904	36BT0292	Prehistoric	-79.72604 40.95858
36AR0417	Prehistoric	-79.6559 40.89409	36BT0293	Prehistoric	-79.71251 40.91879
36AR0419	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.6522 40.85382	36BT0294	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.72066 40.90626
36AR0420	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.67317 40.87745	36BT0295	Prehistoric	-79.7156 40.87762
36AR0421	Prehistoric	-79.65975 40.89605	36BT0296	Prehistoric	-79.71534 40.87713
36AR0422	Prehistoric	-79.6659 40.85598	36BT0297	Prehistoric	-79.71173 40.87719
36AR0423	Prehistoric	-79.66409 40.86026	36BT0298	Prehistoric	-79.71922 40.8885
36AR0431	Prehistoric	-79.64596 40.90941	36BT0299	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.71969 40.89742
36AR0442	Prehistoric	-79.66642 40.87048	36BT0308	Prehistoric	-79.70763 40.7984
36AR0443	Prehistoric	-79.66957 40.88398	36BT0309	Prehistoric	-79.70795 40.79566
36AR0444	Prehistoric	-79.64158 40.90297	36BT0310	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.69262 40.8846
36AR0445	Prehistoric	-79.66372 40.79986	36BT0311	Prehistoric	-79.71927 40.89338
36AR0446	Prehistoric	-79.66496 40.80031	36BT0312	Prehistoric	-79.71945 40.89596
36AR0447	Prehistoric	-79.67828 40.79755	36BT0313	Prehistoric	-79.72095 40.90891
36AR0448	Prehistoric	-79.68292 40.79598	36BT0314	Prehistoric	-79.71863 40.70441
36AR0449	Prehistoric	-79.64911 40.90798	36BT0316	Prehistoric	-79.73292 40.93653
36AR0451	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.65035 40.89006	36BT0317	Prehistoric	-79.72068 40.91192
36AR0485	Prehistoric	-79.65437 40.79748	36BT0318	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.72145 40.90016
36AR0489	Prehistoric	-79.65939 40.93729	36BT0319	Prehistoric	-79.72496 40.92436
36AR0490	Prehistoric	-79.6603 40.93656	36BT0323	Prehistoric	-79.7072 40.90241
36AR0491	Prehistoric	-79.65803 40.93505	36BT0325	Prehistoric	-79.70652 40.87384
36AR0492	Prehistoric	-79.65769 40.93328	36BT0333	Prehistoric	-79.69742 40.90111
36AR0493	Prehistoric	-79.65627 40.93099	36BT0334	Prehistoric	-79.74539 40.91917
36AR0494	Prehistoric	-79.66028 40.94033	36BT0336	Prehistoric	-79.74334 40.94638
36AR0495	Prehistoric	-79.66126 40.941	36BT0389	Prehistoric	-79.70534 40.8745
36AR0496	Prehistoric	-79.65936 40.93967	36BT0390	Prehistoric	-79.72029 40.88758
36AR0497	Prehistoric	-79.6808 40.86792	36BT0391	Prehistoric	-79.7419 40.91872
36AR0498	Prehistoric	-79.69095 40.88987	36BT0392	Prehistoric	-79.74847 40.94933
36AR0499	Prehistoric	-79.67416 40.88011	36BT0393	Prehistoric	-79.72963 40.93248
36AR0500	Prehistoric	-79.68876 40.80147	36BT0394	Prehistoric	-79.72323 40.92011
36AR0501	Prehistoric	-79.65653 40.84586	36BT0395	Prehistoric	-79.72193 40.91736
36AR0502	Prehistoric	-79.64625 40.84255	36BT0396	Prehistoric	-79.73165 40.91307
36AR0503	Prehistoric	-79.64704 40.84189	36BT0397	Prehistoric	-79.76407 40.90637
36AR0504	Prehistoric	-79.64414 40.84541	36BT0398	Prehistoric	-79.76496 40.90713
36AR0505	Prehistoric	-79.69085 40.88606	36BT0399	Prehistoric	-79.76658 40.90893
36AR0506	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.69108 40.89105	36BT0400	Prehistoric	-79.76349 40.9029
36AR0507	Prehistoric	-79.63408 40.90075	36BT0401	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.70939 40.89709
36AR0508	Prehistoric	-79.65098 40.9141	36BT0402	Prehistoric	-79.71177 40.8867
36AR0509	Prehistoric	-79.64933 40.91259	36BT0403	Prehistoric	-79.71548 40.88279
36AR0510	Prehistoric	-79.64932 40.90428	36BT0404	Prehistoric	-79.76825 40.84299
36AR0511	Prehistoric	-79.64724 40.90448	36BT0405	Prehistoric	-79.7706 40.8406
36AR0512	Prehistoric	-79.65321 40.91627	36BT0406	Prehistoric	-79.77217 40.83987
36AR0513	Prehistoric	-79.62812 40.90791	36BT0407	Prehistoric	-79.7716 40.83907
36AR0514	Prehistoric	-79.62989 40.911	36BT0408	Prehistoric	-79.76952 40.84017
36AR0515	Prehistoric	-79.65508 40.81161	36BT0409	Prehistoric	-79.71584 40.88168
36AR0525	Prehistoric	-79.64367 40.83592	36BT0410	Prehistoric	-79.71718 40.88813
36AR0526	Prehistoric	-79.65381 40.81686	36BT0411	Prehistoric	-79.71558 40.87884
36AR0527	Prehistoric	-79.65828 40.81716	36BT0412	Prehistoric	-79.6923 40.88538
36AR0528	Prehistoric	-79.6574 40.81623	36BT0413	Prehistoric	-79.73084 40.92835
36AR0529	Prehistoric	-79.65197 40.81289	36BT0424	Prehistoric	-79.7225 40.93626
36BT0029	Prehistoric	-79.69471 40.88759	36BT0425	Prehistoric	-79.72116 40.90427

Table A-1. Region 1 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36AR0089	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.40341 40.84277	36AR0429	Prehistoric	-79.58651 40.7119
36AR0090	Prehistoric	-79.35604 40.8791	36AR0430	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.5711 40.84325
36AR0091	Prehistoric	-79.37025 40.87209	36AR0450	Prehistoric	-79.47169 40.81474
36AR0092	Prehistoric	-79.37912 40.87371	36AR0452	Prehistoric	-79.4827 40.77333
36AR0093	Prehistoric	-79.38657 40.87807	36AR0460	Prehistoric	-79.36791 40.80276
36AR0094	Prehistoric	-79.38422 40.88029	36AR0461	Prehistoric	-79.26952 40.79165
36AR0103	Prehistoric	-79.5185 40.80418	36AR0463	Prehistoric	-79.61198 40.75883
36AR0109	Prehistoric	-79.32871 40.86787	36AR0464	Prehistoric	-79.61153 40.75499
36AR0113	Prehistoric	-79.5405 40.74574	36AR0465	Prehistoric	-79.61024 40.75378
36AR0114	Prehistoric	-79.60403 40.70322	36AR0466	Prehistoric	-79.61296 40.75473
36AR0120	Prehistoric	-79.51278 40.80707	36AR0468	Prehistoric	-79.61731 40.75078
36AR0121	Prehistoric	-79.32439 40.67098	36AR0471	Prehistoric	-79.37409 40.80071
36AR0122	Prehistoric	-79.27829 40.7274	36AR0474	Prehistoric	-79.61277 40.69061
36AR0123	Prehistoric	-79.29209 40.72396	36AR0475	Prehistoric	-79.50723 40.7225
36AR0124	Prehistoric	-79.30518 40.71812	36AR0476	Prehistoric	-79.50766 40.72306
36AR0125	Prehistoric	-79.32539 40.69742	36AR0477	Prehistoric	-79.50798 40.72336
36AR0126	Prehistoric	-79.32127 40.66697	36AR0478	Prehistoric	-79.50914 40.72371
36AR0127	Prehistoric	-79.31926 40.68472	36AR0483	Prehistoric	-79.58948 40.72837
36AR0128	Prehistoric	-79.6363 40.69388	36AR0484	Prehistoric	-79.6066 40.70257
36AR0129	Prehistoric	-79.6406 40.69287	36AR0486	Prehistoric	-79.46741 40.81005
36AR0132	Prehistoric	-79.51931 40.78239	36AR0488	Prehistoric	-79.28926 40.79203
36AR0138	Prehistoric	-79.32851 40.66425	36AR0530	Prehistoric	-79.47074 40.7174
36AR0140	Prehistoric	-79.29216 40.79364	36AR0531	Prehistoric	-79.5305 40.7317
36AR0141	Prehistoric	-79.36393 40.80324	36AR0532	Prehistoric	-79.59279 40.8299
36AR0142	Prehistoric	-79.30024 40.79491	36AR0533	Prehistoric	-79.30553 40.71018
36AR0143	Prehistoric	-79.32688 40.79232	36AR0534	Prehistoric	-79.30608 40.70957
36AR0144	Prehistoric	-79.26716 40.79559	36AR0535	Prehistoric	-79.59621 40.70541
36AR0145	Prehistoric	-79.26423 40.79961	36AR0536	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.5966 40.70536
36AR0146	Prehistoric	-79.25441 40.80485	36AR0539	Prehistoric	-79.39773 40.87697
36AR0147	Prehistoric	-79.3681 40.79895	36IN0007	Prehistoric	-79.08594 40.71656
36AR0148	Prehistoric	-79.36526 40.78516	36IN0022	Prehistoric	-79.27626 40.65461
36AR0149	Prehistoric	-79.36875 40.78391	36IN0023	Prehistoric	-79.28033 40.64989
36AR0150	Prehistoric	-79.257 40.79401	36IN0024	Prehistoric	-79.23962 40.66331
36AR0154	Prehistoric	-79.64129 40.69552	36IN0025	Prehistoric	-79.25423 40.66217
36AR0157	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.32681 40.66641	36IN0026	Prehistoric	-79.26804 40.65832
36AR0158	Prehistoric	-79.32674 40.66769	36IN0027	Prehistoric	-79.21591 40.64578
36AR0159	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.32361 40.66873	36IN0028	Prehistoric	-79.31535 40.65362
36AR0160	Prehistoric	-79.28069 40.727	36IN0029	Prehistoric	-79.20981 40.66947
36AR0161	Prehistoric	-79.28236 40.72693	36IN0030	Prehistoric	-79.20633 40.67374
36AR0162	Prehistoric	-79.29248 40.72498	36IN0033	Prehistoric	-79.3158 40.65571
36AR0163	Prehistoric	-79.35116 40.64565	36IN0035	Prehistoric	-79.28671 40.65561
36AR0164	Prehistoric	-79.35211 40.64659	36IN0061	Prehistoric	-79.2085 40.675
36AR0165	Prehistoric	-79.35371 40.64683	36IN0062	Prehistoric	-79.20721 40.6772
36AR0166	Prehistoric	-79.35241 40.64758	36IN0063	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.23135 40.66117
36AR0167	Prehistoric	-79.35035 40.64793	36IN0064	Prehistoric	-79.21672 40.72759
36AR0168	Prehistoric	-79.35091 40.64896	36IN0065	Prehistoric	-79.21198 40.72735
36AR0169	Prehistoric	-79.35252 40.65048	36IN0073	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.0766 40.66497
36AR0170	Prehistoric	-79.3488 40.65385	36IN0095	Prehistoric	-79.31424 40.65448
36AR0171	Prehistoric	-79.33286 40.68982	36IN0096	Prehistoric	-79.31286 40.65479
36AR0172	Prehistoric	-79.36082 40.65442	36IN0097	Prehistoric	-79.31002 40.65581
36AR0173	Prehistoric	-79.29709 40.72285	36IN0098	Prehistoric	-79.31042 40.65717
36AR0174	Prehistoric	-79.30104 40.71766	36IN0099	Prehistoric	-79.30801 40.6565

Table A-1. Region 1 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36AR0175	Prehistoric	-79.33207 40.67019	36IN0100	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.30785 40.65771
36AR0176	Prehistoric	-79.30443 40.71095	36IN0101	Prehistoric	-79.30565 40.658
36AR0177	Prehistoric	-79.30825 40.71877	36IN0102	Prehistoric	-79.30284 40.65308
36AR0178	Prehistoric	-79.30704 40.71838	36IN0103	Prehistoric	-79.32485 40.65919
36AR0179	Prehistoric	-79.33375 40.65948	36IN0104	Prehistoric	-79.32232 40.65758
36AR0180	Prehistoric	-79.32878 40.66216	36IN0115	Prehistoric	-79.10959 40.67035
36AR0181	Prehistoric	-79.32805 40.66092	36IN0134	Prehistoric	-79.24119 40.72161
36AR0182	Prehistoric	-79.23971 40.77151	36IN0135	Prehistoric	-79.24769 40.63251
36AR0183	Prehistoric	-79.27447 40.79435	36IN0136	Prehistoric	-79.09322 40.71943
36AR0184	Prehistoric	-79.22839 40.80075	36IN0137	Prehistoric	-79.11198 40.71838
36AR0187	Prehistoric	-79.2465 40.81728	36IN0138	Prehistoric	-79.23183 40.65878
36AR0188	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.52135 40.79507	36IN0142	Prehistoric	-79.17271 40.76801
36AR0189	Prehistoric	-79.39945 40.63511	36IN0186	Prehistoric	-79.0736 40.71348
36AR0198	Prehistoric	-79.54555 40.7642	36IN0187	Prehistoric	-79.08662 40.66362
36AR0199	Prehistoric	-79.54584 40.76373	36IN0201	Prehistoric	-79.18135 40.82666
36AR0200	Prehistoric	-79.54598 40.76333	36IN0202	Prehistoric	-79.20999 40.77886
36AR0201	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.54754 40.76221	36IN0209	Prehistoric	-79.2761 40.65783
36AR0204	Prehistoric	-79.26232 40.79362	36IN0210	Prehistoric	-79.27563 40.65919
36AR0205	Prehistoric	-79.27648 40.83229	36IN0211	Prehistoric	-79.2718 40.66037
36AR0206	Prehistoric	-79.36803 40.80441	36IN0212	Prehistoric	-79.27406 40.65696
36AR0207	Prehistoric	-79.27771 40.72879	36IN0227	Prehistoric	-79.17556 40.63941
36AR0208	Prehistoric	-79.28019 40.72823	36IN0228	Prehistoric	-79.23579 40.6637
36AR0209	Prehistoric	-79.29506 40.7217	36IN0229	Prehistoric	-79.21824 40.67066
36AR0210	Prehistoric	-79.29875 40.72283	36IN0230	Prehistoric	-79.21426 40.66853
36AR0211	Prehistoric	-79.30006 40.72185	36IN0231	Prehistoric	-79.21033 40.67294
36AR0212	Prehistoric	-79.29639 40.71939	36IN0232	Prehistoric	-79.18969 40.68446
36AR0213	Prehistoric	-79.31453 40.70728	36IN0233	Prehistoric	-79.18784 40.684
36AR0217	Prehistoric	-79.28452 40.82963	36IN0234	Prehistoric	-79.18442 40.68592
36AR0218	Prehistoric	-79.32757 40.69884	36IN0235	Prehistoric	-79.17149 40.70017
36AR0219	Prehistoric	-79.32738 40.69721	36IN0236	Prehistoric	-79.14351 40.71338
36AR0220	Prehistoric	-79.33056 40.69556	36IN0237	Prehistoric	-79.14195 40.71346
36AR0221	Prehistoric	-79.32684 40.66903	36IN0239	Prehistoric	-79.1644 40.7204
36AR0222	Prehistoric	-79.33703 40.66881	36IN0240	Prehistoric	-79.1259 40.71169
36AR0223	Prehistoric	-79.32404 40.67627	36IN0241	Prehistoric	-79.1264 40.7084
36AR0224	Prehistoric	-79.32211 40.68218	36IN0242	Prehistoric	-79.13375 40.73479
36AR0225	Prehistoric	-79.31803 40.70481	36IN0243	Prehistoric	-79.1305 40.73347
36AR0226	Prehistoric	-79.30594 40.71088	36IN0244	Prehistoric	-79.12882 40.73458
36AR0227	Prehistoric	-79.28385 40.72501	36IN0245	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.12674 40.73338
36AR0228	Prehistoric	-79.30646 40.72117	36IN0246	Prehistoric	-79.18766 40.72973
36AR0229	Prehistoric	-79.29952 40.7196	36IN0247	Prehistoric	-79.19522 40.73492
36AR0230	Prehistoric	-79.29493 40.71923	36IN0248	Prehistoric	-79.20031 40.72996
36AR0231	Prehistoric	-79.30192 40.79489	36IN0249	Prehistoric	-79.20109 40.73073
36AR0232	Prehistoric	-79.35556 40.80294	36IN0250	Prehistoric	-79.21501 40.72719
36AR0233	Prehistoric	-79.6653 40.69102	36IN0251	Prehistoric	-79.20851 40.72849
36AR0244	Prehistoric	-79.26602 40.87118	36IN0252	Prehistoric	-79.21378 40.66711
36AR0245	Prehistoric	-79.25145 40.84603	36IN0254	Prehistoric	-79.05833 40.70856
36AR0246	Prehistoric	-79.53603 40.72491	36IN0255	Prehistoric	-79.05608 40.70662
36AR0247	Prehistoric	-79.51614 40.70429	36IN0256	Prehistoric	-79.05387 40.70416
36AR0257	Prehistoric	-79.48204 40.81248	36IN0257	Prehistoric	-79.05283 40.70502
36AR0258	Prehistoric	-79.64269 40.69382	36IN0258	Prehistoric	-79.05184 40.70258
36AR0260	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.51622 40.71444	36IN0259	Prehistoric	-79.06243 40.66091
36AR0261	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.51617 40.71592	36IN0260	Prehistoric	-79.0658 40.66288

Table A-1. Region 1 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36IN0105	Prehistoric	-79.2075 40.60354	36WM0284	Prehistoric	-79.31112 40.39268
36IN0106	Prehistoric	-79.14876 40.59216	36WM0285	Prehistoric	-79.3162 40.38736
36IN0107	Prehistoric	-79.14307 40.59074	36WM0286	Prehistoric	-79.31387 40.38723
36IN0108	Prehistoric	-79.16756 40.53888	36WM0287	Prehistoric	-79.27155 40.36703
36IN0111	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.16768 40.53981	36WM0288	Prehistoric	-79.27483 40.36607
36IN0113	Prehistoric	-79.18921 40.55386	36WM0289	Prehistoric	-79.27373 40.3654
36IN0114	Prehistoric	-79.18975 40.55518	36WM0310	Prehistoric	-79.2765 40.40425
36IN0116	Prehistoric	-79.16451 40.54974	36WM0311	Prehistoric	-79.28681 40.40724
36IN0117	Prehistoric	-79.16242 40.55023	36WM0312	Prehistoric	-79.28608 40.41158
36IN0119	Prehistoric	-79.16924 40.55448	36WM0313	Prehistoric	-79.28587 40.41455
36IN0120	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.18371 40.55171	36WM0314	Prehistoric	-79.2772 40.41275
36IN0121	Prehistoric	-79.18742 40.55308	36WM0315	Prehistoric	-79.2738 40.4142
36IN0122	Prehistoric	-79.16579 40.5451	36WM0316	Prehistoric	-79.2787 40.41467
36IN0123	Prehistoric	-79.18324 40.54863	36WM0317	Prehistoric	-79.28108 40.41556
36IN0124	Prehistoric	-79.19476 40.56243	36WM0318	Prehistoric	-79.27882 40.41686
36IN0125	Prehistoric	-79.1884 40.55612	36WM0319	Prehistoric	-79.27945 40.40019
36IN0126	Prehistoric	-79.18088 40.50493	36WM0320	Prehistoric	-79.28433 40.38944
36IN0127	Prehistoric	-79.17589 40.52297	36WM0321	Prehistoric	-79.26498 40.41495
36IN0128	Prehistoric	-79.21974 40.55878	36WM0330	Prehistoric	-79.28268 40.37292
36IN0129	Prehistoric	-79.21792 40.55635	36WM0331	Prehistoric	-79.28286 40.37229
36IN0131	Prehistoric	-79.17245 40.5166	36WM0332	Prehistoric	-79.27895 40.37117
36IN0132	Prehistoric	-79.1702 40.51629	36WM0333	Prehistoric	-79.27689 40.36998
36IN0133	Prehistoric	-79.19079 40.62158	36WM0334	Prehistoric	-79.29336 40.35575
36IN0139	Prehistoric	-79.18045 40.53154	36WM0335	Prehistoric	-79.30063 40.35653
36IN0140	Prehistoric	-78.95169 40.67468	36WM0336	Prehistoric	-79.28821 40.35295
36IN0141	Prehistoric	-78.94815 40.67378	36WM0345	Prehistoric	-79.25301 40.41551
36IN0145	Prehistoric	-79.17928 40.60295	36WM0346	Prehistoric	-79.25057 40.41787
36IN0178	Prehistoric	-79.00989 40.58134	36WM0347	Prehistoric	-79.24814 40.40835
36IN0185	Prehistoric	-79.05961 40.62635	36WM0348	Prehistoric	-79.24582 40.408
36IN0188	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.29545 40.4558	36WM0349	Prehistoric	-79.23937 40.42668
36IN0213	Prehistoric	-79.22982 40.45018	36WM0350	Prehistoric	-79.25902 40.41265
36IN0214	Prehistoric	-79.22751 40.45173	36WM0351	Prehistoric	-79.26029 40.40952
36IN0215	Prehistoric	-79.212 40.46791	36WM0352	Prehistoric	-79.25885 40.40136
36IN0216	Prehistoric	-79.20643 40.4761	36WM0353	Prehistoric	-79.26116 40.39932
36IN0217	Prehistoric	-79.20497 40.47769	36WM0354	Prehistoric	-79.33036 40.45009
36IN0218	Prehistoric	-79.19734 40.49598	36WM0355	Prehistoric	-79.33334 40.45661
36IN0219	Prehistoric	-79.19511 40.49832	36WM0356	Prehistoric	-79.28684 40.39628
36IN0220	Prehistoric	-79.19716 40.49762	36WM0357	Prehistoric	-79.28582 40.3973
36IN0221	Prehistoric	-79.19761 40.49957	36WM0358	Prehistoric	-79.28736 40.39792
36IN0285	Prehistoric	-79.20073 40.50254	36WM0359	Prehistoric	-79.28893 40.3998
36IN0286	Prehistoric	-79.17299 40.60908	36WM0360	Prehistoric	-79.29033 40.39943
36IN0287	Prehistoric	-79.20584 40.46594	36WM0361	Prehistoric	-79.28852 40.39705
36IN0288	Prehistoric	-79.20347 40.46876	36WM0388	Prehistoric	-79.30842 40.43457
36IN0298	Prehistoric	-78.99108 40.76258	36WM0390	Prehistoric	-79.31495 40.39649
36IN0308	Prehistoric	-79.32175 40.47108	36WM0393	Prehistoric	-79.30057 40.36237
36IN0309	Prehistoric	-79.32736 40.46399	36WM0394	Prehistoric	-79.30203 40.36191
36IN0310	Prehistoric	-79.32607 40.46292	36WM0395	Prehistoric	-79.29729 40.36076
36IN0311	Prehistoric	-79.32328 40.46064	36WM0423	Prehistoric	-79.28582 40.35984
36IN0312	Prehistoric	-79.31848 40.47165	36WM0424	Prehistoric	-79.28026 40.36969
36IN0313	Prehistoric	-79.31743 40.47293	36WM0425	Prehistoric	-79.27834 40.36646
36IN0314	Prehistoric	-79.34373 40.48	36WM0426	Prehistoric	-79.29438 40.34173
36IN0315	Prehistoric	-79.34274 40.4786	36WM0427	Prehistoric	-79.31258 40.36435

Table A-1. Region 1 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36IN0316	Prehistoric	-79.2869 40.45289	36WM0433	Prehistoric	-79.28545 40.36865
36IN0318	Prehistoric	-79.29345 40.45725	36WM0437	Prehistoric	-79.27684 40.41922
36IN0319	Prehistoric	-79.27947 40.4819	36WM0438	Prehistoric	-79.32016 40.4006
36IN0320	Prehistoric	-79.27395 40.48872	36WM0439	Prehistoric	-79.30117 40.39329
36IN0321	Prehistoric	-79.27115 40.47503	36WM0443	Prehistoric	-79.29461 40.35083
36IN0322	Prehistoric	-79.20791 40.47423	36WM0450	Prehistoric	-79.30514 40.36469
36IN0323	Prehistoric	-79.2034 40.48057	36WM0466	Prehistoric	-79.27344 40.3692
36IN0330	Prehistoric	-79.18753 40.59115	36WM0473	Prehistoric	-79.30977 40.36224
36IN0331	Prehistoric	-79.19994 40.59589	36WM0474	Prehistoric	-79.30784 40.36315
36IN0334	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.19647 40.59724	36WM0477	Prehistoric	-79.30724 40.3669
36IN0336	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.29751 40.57573	36WM0487	Prehistoric	-79.28847 40.35616
36IN0339	Prehistoric	-79.22372 40.53375	36WM0488	Prehistoric	-79.30033 40.39122
36IN0340	Prehistoric	-79.23526 40.45485	36WM0515	Prehistoric	-79.28366 40.40241
36IN0341	Prehistoric	-79.23187 40.45607	36WM0519	Prehistoric	-79.2913 40.35466
36IN0342	Prehistoric	-79.23178 40.45374	36WM0523	Prehistoric	-79.28685 40.40597
36IN0343	Prehistoric	-79.23003 40.45522	36WM0524	Prehistoric	-79.32547 40.45015
36IN0344	Prehistoric	-79.24283 40.45116	36WM0530	Prehistoric	-79.32139 40.45005
36IN0345	Prehistoric	-79.24648 40.45078	36WM0649	Prehistoric	-79.33386 40.37857
36IN0347	Prehistoric	-79.30036 40.43688	36WM0650	Prehistoric	-79.33225 40.37804
36IN0358	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.25323 40.45255	36WM0651	Prehistoric	-79.33288 40.38314
36IN0359	Prehistoric	-79.20503 40.59841	36WM0652	Prehistoric	-79.27652 40.39272
36IN0360	Prehistoric	-79.19775 40.56315	36WM0653	Prehistoric	-79.2732 40.39001
36IN0362	Prehistoric	-79.19515 40.47933	36WM0654	Prehistoric	-79.33096 40.40034
36IN0364	Prehistoric	-79.19088 40.49439	36WM0655	Prehistoric	-79.29182 40.40214
36IN0365	Prehistoric	-79.19131 40.49272	36WM0656	Prehistoric	-79.30172 40.39037
36IN0371	Prehistoric	-79.24436 40.44148	36WM0657	Prehistoric	-79.30558 40.38348
36IN0372	Prehistoric	-79.23299 40.44657	36WM0658	Prehistoric	-79.28531 40.41735
36IN0373	Prehistoric	-79.23493 40.44635	36WM0688	Prehistoric	-79.28983 40.40275
36IN0374	Prehistoric	-79.2409 40.43901	36WM0689	Prehistoric	-79.28271 40.43994
36IN0375	Prehistoric	-79.22815 40.45074	36WM0691	Prehistoric	-79.28957 40.42783
36IN0376	Prehistoric	-79.2343 40.44001	36WM0692	Prehistoric	-79.28876 40.43202
36IN0377	Prehistoric	-79.23685 40.43906	36WM0693	Prehistoric	-79.29038 40.43296
36IN0378	Prehistoric	-79.23574 40.43803	36WM0722	Prehistoric	-79.2617 40.37072
36IN0379	Prehistoric	-79.2332 40.44963	36WM0744	Prehistoric	-79.2964 40.39824
36IN0380	Prehistoric	-79.21457 40.45634	36WM0745	Prehistoric	-79.29512 40.39942
36IN0381	Prehistoric	-79.21964 40.45745	36WM0767	Prehistoric	-79.3058 40.38719
36IN0383	Prehistoric	-79.19482 40.4866	36WM0782	Prehistoric	-79.26521 40.3763
36IN0384	Prehistoric	-79.20269 40.48241	36WM0790	Prehistoric	-79.36268 40.47241
36IN0385	Prehistoric	-79.20553 40.47917	36WM0791	Prehistoric	-79.36389 40.47259
36IN0386	Prehistoric	-79.20678 40.47975	36WM0817	Prehistoric	-79.30948 40.36797
36IN0387	Prehistoric	-79.21036 40.47909	36WM0820	Prehistoric	-79.27503 40.36765
36IN0388	Prehistoric	-79.20819 40.4783	36WM0824	Prehistoric	-79.26937 40.37888
36IN0389	Prehistoric	-79.20996 40.47479	36WM0825	Prehistoric	-79.26845 40.37877
36IN0398	Prehistoric	-79.18564 40.49734	36WM0826	Prehistoric	-79.2684 40.38113
36IN0399	Prehistoric	-79.27158 40.49095	36WM0827	Prehistoric	-79.26835 40.38054
36IN0400	Prehistoric	-79.35737 40.48062	36WM0842	Prehistoric	-79.27507 40.37651
36IN0401	Prehistoric	-79.29525 40.46211	36WM0867	Prehistoric	-79.26707 40.41519
36IN0429	Prehistoric	-79.19407 40.48809	36WM0868	Prehistoric	-79.25491 40.41452
36IN0430	Prehistoric	-79.19249 40.49088	36WM0870	Prehistoric	-79.25882 40.38516
36IN0431	Prehistoric	-79.19355 40.48964	36WM0871	Prehistoric	-79.25851 40.38375
36IN0432	Prehistoric	-79.1905 40.55435	36WM0873	Prehistoric	-79.2589 40.38234
36IN0433	Prehistoric	-79.22712 40.45427	36WM1023	Prehistoric	-79.29682 40.35558

Table A-1. Region 1 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36AL0177	Prehistoric	-79.98794 40.5932	36AL0529	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.00153 40.44846
36AL0178	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.01752 40.60802	36AL0535	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.98014 40.46361
36AL0179	Prehistoric	-80.0169 40.60891	36AL0543	Prehistoric	-79.91076 40.633
36AL0180	Prehistoric	-79.97704 40.58006	36AL0592	Prehistoric	-80.0251 40.61857
36AL0181	Prehistoric	-80.02992 40.61527	36AL0622	Prehistoric	-79.77984 40.52839
36AL0182	Prehistoric	-79.99841 40.59796	36AR0003	Prehistoric	-79.67771 40.67374
36AL0183	Prehistoric	-80.04195 40.61784	36BT0068	Prehistoric	-79.90905 40.67785
36AL0184	Prehistoric	-80.03142 40.62317	36BT0154	Prehistoric	-79.80302 40.70301
36AL0185	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.03339 40.62358	36BT0155	Prehistoric	-79.80418 40.6997
36AL0186	Prehistoric	-80.03552 40.62464	36BT0213	Prehistoric	-79.8047 40.70752
36AL0187	Prehistoric	-80.02726 40.62639	36BT0214	Prehistoric	-79.80654 40.7099
36AL0188	Prehistoric	-80.01233 40.61495	36BT0215	Prehistoric	-79.80579 40.70897
36AL0189	Prehistoric	-79.99976 40.59542	36BT0218	Prehistoric	-79.75649 40.68637
36AL0190	Prehistoric	-80.009 40.62547	36BT0219	Prehistoric	-79.7563 40.68861
36AL0191	Prehistoric	-79.9761 40.57485	36BT0220	Prehistoric	-79.84766 40.67843
36AL0192	Prehistoric	-80.0475 40.58968	36BT0221	Prehistoric	-79.82492 40.71641
36AL0193	Prehistoric	-80.03569 40.58705	36BT0427	Prehistoric	-79.69323 40.66968
36AL0194	Prehistoric	-79.98265 40.64374	36WM0025	Prehistoric	-79.76573 40.58712
36AL0195	Prehistoric	-79.98307 40.64088	36WM0026	Prehistoric	-79.706 40.62245
36AL0196	Prehistoric	-80.0353 40.58623	36WM0027	Prehistoric	-79.76059 40.55391
36AL0197	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.04544 40.61838	36WM0030	Prehistoric	-79.69251 40.66167
36AL0205	Prehistoric	-79.79632 40.54006	36WM0031	Prehistoric	-79.77093 40.5797
36AL0206	Prehistoric	-80.03139 40.58619	36WM0032	Prehistoric	-79.75411 40.5932
36AL0207	Prehistoric	-79.77387 40.49727	36WM0700	Prehistoric	-79.6674 40.67764
36AL0208	Prehistoric	-79.90889 40.59548	36WM0784	Prehistoric	-79.68065 40.59776
36AL0209	Prehistoric	-79.88827 40.54668	36WM0804	Prehistoric	-79.65144 40.5328
36AL0212	Prehistoric	-80.03665 40.66293	36WM0869	Prehistoric	-79.70062 40.59882
36AL0213	Prehistoric	-79.95295 40.62743	36WM0908	Prehistoric	-79.66078 40.58194
36AL0214	Prehistoric	-79.98134 40.58183	36WM0909	Prehistoric	-79.66037 40.58353
36AL0252	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.08377 40.63206	36WM0910	Prehistoric	-79.65955 40.58482
36AL0262	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.99947 40.44302	36WM0911	Prehistoric	-79.68071 40.61829
36AL0278	Prehistoric	-79.90766 40.48974	36WM0912	Prehistoric	-79.67859 40.61654
36AL0279	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.9822 40.50929	36WM0913	Prehistoric	-79.68783 40.61005
36AL0280	Prehistoric	-79.98207 40.51708	36WM0928	Prehistoric	-79.67647 40.61764
36AL0281	Prehistoric	-79.97584 40.51857	36WM0929	Prehistoric	-79.68188 40.62019
36AL0282	Prehistoric	-79.97709 40.51957	36WM0930	Prehistoric	-79.68343 40.64007
36AL0288	Prehistoric	-79.85244 40.65662	36WM0931	Prehistoric	-79.68081 40.63444
36AL0289	Prehistoric	-79.80462 40.6539	36WM0932	Prehistoric	-79.68584 40.6401
36AL0290	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.77569 40.6407	36WM0933	Prehistoric	-79.68433 40.63953
36AL0291	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.78412 40.64695	36WM0934	Prehistoric	-79.68294 40.63933
36AL0292	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.79961 40.62334	36WM0935	Prehistoric	-79.68627 40.63877
36AL0300	Prehistoric	-79.83395 40.635	36WM0947	Prehistoric	-79.69116 40.66721
36AL0301	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.82209 40.63198	36WM1464	Prehistoric	-79.66461 40.49741
36AL0302	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.81947 40.63115	36WM1465	Prehistoric	-79.64305 40.48975
36AL0303	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.84559 40.62845	36WM1466	Prehistoric	-79.64152 40.48955
36AL0304	Prehistoric	-79.84532 40.62531	36WM1467	Prehistoric	-79.63539 40.48771
36AL0305	Prehistoric	-79.84783 40.65561			
Watershed 66-Appalachian Plateaus-Pittsburgh Low Plateau:					
36AR0008	Prehistoric	-79.58024 40.6314	36WM0495	Prehistoric	-79.45685 40.52509
36AR0202	Prehistoric	-79.4298 40.55386	36WM0496	Prehistoric	-79.45521 40.52603
36AR0252	Prehistoric	-79.53757 40.5524	36WM0497	Prehistoric	-79.4542 40.52732
36AR0313	Prehistoric	-79.46708 40.60314	36WM0498	Prehistoric	-79.45045 40.52763

Table A-1. Region 1 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36AR0326	Prehistoric	-79.48916 40.54999	36WM0499	Prehistoric	-79.45168 40.52912
36AR0329	Prehistoric	-79.58321 40.629	36WM0500	Prehistoric	-79.46615 40.51291
36AR0330	Prehistoric	-79.58168 40.68038	36WM0501	Prehistoric	-79.45733 40.50852
36AR0393	Prehistoric	-79.58246 40.60779	36WM0527	Prehistoric	-79.53856 40.38763
36AR0394	Prehistoric	-79.55486 40.59777	36WM0533	Prehistoric	-79.50963 40.43583
36AR0395	Prehistoric	-79.58077 40.63244	36WM0534	Prehistoric	-79.45592 40.50712
36AR0396	Prehistoric	-79.57602 40.63225	36WM0585	Prehistoric	-79.45786 40.50703
36AR0397	Prehistoric	-79.57897 40.6331	36WM0592	Prehistoric	-79.55649 40.4587
36AR0455	Prehistoric	-79.60167 40.6691	36WM0593	Prehistoric	-79.55693 40.45968
36AR0456	Prehistoric	-79.60249 40.66807	36WM0707	Prehistoric	-79.61347 40.48912
36AR0519	Prehistoric	-79.57739 40.68219	36WM0732	Prehistoric	-79.47944 40.52732
36AR0520	Prehistoric	-79.57742 40.68319	36WM0755	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.63077 40.62696
36AR0521	Prehistoric	-79.57971 40.68431	36WM0772	Prehistoric	-79.53895 40.43325
36AR0522	Prehistoric	-79.57916 40.68621	36WM0775	Prehistoric	-79.53248 40.42897
36AR0523	Prehistoric	-79.57805 40.6857	36WM0778	Prehistoric	-79.53686 40.43116
36AR0524	Prehistoric	-79.58232 40.67815	36WM0785	Prehistoric	-79.64041 40.57658
36IN0055	Prehistoric	-79.45212 40.49828	36WM0787	Prehistoric	-79.64561 40.57177
36IN0143	Prehistoric	-79.4536 40.52147	36WM0794	Prehistoric	-79.55759 40.40115
36IN0148	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.45333 40.5017	36WM0863	Prehistoric	-79.58918 40.60676
36IN0307	Prehistoric	-79.45541 40.52174	36WM0864	Prehistoric	-79.58932 40.6075
36IN0390	Prehistoric	-79.4519 40.49628	36WM0882	Prehistoric	-79.63082 40.57555
36WM0014	Prehistoric	-79.45655 40.4956	36WM0883	Prehistoric	-79.63621 40.57487
36WM0028	Prehistoric	-79.59926 40.61887	36WM0894	Prehistoric	-79.55529 40.39847
36WM0029	Prehistoric	-79.58812 40.61264	36WM0903	Prehistoric	-79.55966 40.53447
36WM0084	Prehistoric	-79.45579 40.50484	36WM0904	Prehistoric	-79.56017 40.5344
36WM0107	Prehistoric	-79.6633 40.67713	36WM0948	Prehistoric	-79.60763 40.54852
36WM0133	Prehistoric	-79.59832 40.57041	36WM0949	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.60947 40.54668
36WM0145	Prehistoric	-79.45692 40.50178	36WM0951	Prehistoric	-79.61861 40.5381
36WM0414	Prehistoric	-79.56213 40.40059	36WM0952	Prehistoric	-79.62282 40.53383
36WM0415	Prehistoric	-79.58747 40.46439	36WM0953	Prehistoric	-79.61987 40.53554
36WM0416	Prehistoric	-79.59877 40.44059	36WM0954	Prehistoric	-79.62983 40.52122
36WM0418	Prehistoric	-79.55573 40.40142	36WM0955	Prehistoric	-79.6157 40.53027
36WM0420	Prehistoric	-79.57843 40.45733	36WM0956	Prehistoric	-79.62817 40.51751
36WM0421	Prehistoric	-79.5981 40.46371	36WM0957	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.62358 40.53326
36WM0494	Prehistoric	-79.46039 40.52684	36WM0981	Prehistoric	-79.56039 40.52593
Watershed 67-Appalachian Plateaus-Pittsburgh Low Plateau:					
36BV0003	Prehistoric	-80.42774 40.6242	36BV0172	Prehistoric	-80.30074 40.57528
36BV0013	Prehistoric	-80.35406 40.5184	36BV0173	Prehistoric	-80.30418 40.57189
36BV0014	Prehistoric	-80.33985 40.51926	36BV0174	Prehistoric	-80.30231 40.5512
36BV0015	Prehistoric	-80.32944 40.52908	36BV0175	Prehistoric	-80.30272 40.55215
36BV0016	Prehistoric	-80.33768 40.52408	36BV0176	Prehistoric	-80.30191 40.55318
36BV0017	Prehistoric	-80.32479 40.53867	36BV0177	Prehistoric	-80.32666 40.54495
36BV0018	Prehistoric	-80.32439 40.53535	36BV0178	Prehistoric	-80.33556 40.56264
36BV0019	Prehistoric	-80.31582 40.54839	36BV0179	Prehistoric	-80.31598 40.5686
36BV0020	Prehistoric	-80.30301 40.54877	36BV0180	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.3121 40.56529
36BV0021	Prehistoric	-80.31308 40.56753	36BV0191	Prehistoric	-80.34779 40.64746
36BV0022	Prehistoric	-80.31267 40.58944	36BV0192	Prehistoric	-80.34123 40.64425
36BV0023	Prehistoric	-80.30391 40.59815	36BV0193	Prehistoric	-80.34056 40.62644
36BV0024	Prehistoric	-80.30383 40.606	36BV0202	Prehistoric	-80.299 40.55694
36BV0025	Prehistoric	-80.31242 40.61282	36BV0203	Prehistoric	-80.31251 40.54747
36BV0026	Prehistoric	-80.30126 40.61121	36BV0204	Prehistoric	-80.32113 40.54672
36BV0027	Prehistoric	-80.42125 40.63246	36BV0205	Prehistoric	-80.32794 40.54138

Table A-1. Region 1 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36BV0121	Prehistoric	-80.33482 40.52652	36WH0560	Prehistoric	-80.51462 40.43216
36BV0122	Prehistoric	-80.36451 40.5164	36WH0561	Prehistoric	-80.51645 40.43262
36BV0123	Prehistoric	-80.36527 40.50969	36WH0562	Prehistoric	-80.51285 40.42788
36BV0124	Prehistoric	-80.32366 40.54122	36WH0563	Prehistoric	-80.51371 40.43252
36BV0125	Prehistoric	-80.32186 40.53541	36WH0565	Prehistoric	-80.49088 40.423
36BV0129	Prehistoric	-80.38226 40.64226	36WH0566	Prehistoric	-80.49128 40.42395
36BV0130	Prehistoric	-80.50879 40.63419	36WH0567	Prehistoric	-80.4891 40.42352
36BV0132	Prehistoric	-80.5072 40.62899	36WH0569	Prehistoric	-80.51392 40.47444
36BV0133	Prehistoric	-80.49626 40.63368	36WH0585	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.45688 40.46946
36BV0134	Prehistoric	-80.51395 40.6347	36WH0608	Prehistoric	-80.28728 40.41078
36BV0137	Prehistoric	-80.36 40.49101	36WH0616	Prehistoric	-80.31433 40.39745
36BV0138	Prehistoric	-80.36129 40.47991	36WH0756	Prehistoric	-80.35899 40.43666
36BV0145	Prehistoric	-80.51289 40.63179	36WH0757	Prehistoric	-80.36389 40.43841
36BV0159	Prehistoric	-80.31275 40.59131	36WH0758	Prehistoric	-80.36191 40.4393
36BV0160	Prehistoric	-80.30816 40.59525	36WH0800	Prehistoric	-80.28213 40.40725
36BV0161	Prehistoric	-80.31784 40.58715	36WH1028	Prehistoric	-80.36139 40.46194
36BV0162	Prehistoric	-80.30949 40.61041	36WH1036	Prehistoric	-80.37322 40.39645
36BV0163	Prehistoric	-80.2935 40.60566	36WH1045	Prehistoric	-80.35717 40.43057
36BV0164	Prehistoric	-80.29101 40.60795	36WH1083	Prehistoric	-80.36246 40.46544
36BV0165	Prehistoric	-80.30816 40.61516	36WH1097	Prehistoric	-80.36876 40.47579
36BV0166	Prehistoric	-80.29997 40.60679	36WH1182	Prehistoric	-80.35258 40.37917
36BV0168	Prehistoric	-80.29957 40.57768	36WH1315	Prehistoric	-80.36676 40.44231
36BV0169	Prehistoric	-80.30159 40.57801	36WH1319	Prehistoric	-80.4975 40.40079
36BV0170	Prehistoric	-80.29765 40.57611	36WH1440	Prehistoric	-80.30438 40.40462
36BV0171	Prehistoric	-80.30422 40.57005	36WH1462	Prehistoric	-80.37461 40.38925
Watershed 67-Appalachian Plateaus-Waynesburg Hills:					
36WH0038	Prehistoric	-80.37357 40.33755	36WH0506	Prehistoric	-80.416 40.34155
36WH0039	Prehistoric	-80.33163 40.24898	36WH0507	Prehistoric	-80.45078 40.3391
36WH0077	Prehistoric	-80.41435 40.29331	36WH0508	Prehistoric	-80.45133 40.33744
36WH0078	Prehistoric	-80.33264 40.34147	36WH0509	Prehistoric	-80.44801 40.33103
36WH0089	Prehistoric	-80.33479 40.25201	36WH0510	Prehistoric	-80.43316 40.32793
36WH0106	Prehistoric	-80.36017 40.31256	36WH0511	Prehistoric	-80.43017 40.3273
36WH0107	Prehistoric	-80.34709 40.33542	36WH0512	Prehistoric	-80.43272 40.3324
36WH0108	Prehistoric	-80.33054 40.34206	36WH0513	Prehistoric	-80.43084 40.33643
36WH0109	Prehistoric	-80.31962 40.32187	36WH0514	Prehistoric	-80.42006 40.33817
36WH0110	Prehistoric	-80.36809 40.32221	36WH0515	Prehistoric	-80.42258 40.33709
36WH0112	Prehistoric	-80.39801 40.35425	36WH0516	Prehistoric	-80.42154 40.33931
36WH0117	Prehistoric	-80.34129 40.27944	36WH0517	Prehistoric	-80.4235 40.33449
36WH0119	Prehistoric	-80.34325 40.26503	36WH0518	Prehistoric	-80.43466 40.29348
36WH0120	Prehistoric	-80.35017 40.26271	36WH0519	Prehistoric	-80.38891 40.27099
36WH0121	Prehistoric	-80.35109 40.27152	36WH0520	Prehistoric	-80.46031 40.28076
36WH0122	Prehistoric	-80.35088 40.27448	36WH0521	Prehistoric	-80.46513 40.3372
36WH0123	Prehistoric	-80.35913 40.25929	36WH0522	Prehistoric	-80.40312 40.32862
36WH0124	Prehistoric	-80.34978 40.24507	36WH0523	Prehistoric	-80.40335 40.32674
36WH0126	Prehistoric	-80.39229 40.25019	36WH0524	Prehistoric	-80.41374 40.30226
36WH0127	Prehistoric	-80.38988 40.2515	36WH0525	Prehistoric	-80.37664 40.2866
36WH0128	Prehistoric	-80.38891 40.25305	36WH0526	Prehistoric	-80.37651 40.25946
36WH0129	Prehistoric	-80.3939 40.25398	36WH0527	Prehistoric	-80.44399 40.31235
36WH0130	Prehistoric	-80.35382 40.2641	36WH0528	Prehistoric	-80.42497 40.33821
36WH0131	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.39438 40.25711	36WH0529	Prehistoric	-80.38261 40.29812
36WH0132	Prehistoric	-80.39071 40.25831	36WH0530	Prehistoric	-80.5008 40.35793
36WH0133	Prehistoric	-80.35449 40.25769	36WH0607	Prehistoric	-80.35255 40.25675

Table A-1. Region 1 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36WH0134	Prehistoric	-80.35423 40.27419	36WH0654	Prehistoric	-80.32847 40.25403
36WH0135	Prehistoric	-80.35635 40.27161	36WH0667	Prehistoric	-80.34064 40.25193
36WH0136	Prehistoric	-80.35035 40.25346	36WH0668	Prehistoric	-80.32321 40.3252
36WH0170	Prehistoric	-80.35564 40.2545	36WH0687	Prehistoric	-80.34504 40.25741
36WH0181	Prehistoric	-80.32559 40.32766	36WH0688	Prehistoric	-80.34657 40.25454
36WH0183	Prehistoric	-80.34868 40.35373	36WH0689	Prehistoric	-80.35189 40.25134
36WH0184	Prehistoric	-80.35145 40.35567	36WH0709	Prehistoric	-80.48515 40.29105
36WH0187	Prehistoric	-80.37042 40.31285	36WH0720	Prehistoric	-80.32957 40.26315
36WH0195	Prehistoric	-80.33156 40.24711	36WH0796	Prehistoric	-80.3705 40.24652
36WH0197	Prehistoric	-80.34452 40.33126	36WH0797	Prehistoric	-80.37876 40.24556
36WH0223	Prehistoric	-80.41522 40.28937	36WH0821	Prehistoric	-80.36925 40.29191
36WH0224	Prehistoric	-80.31434 40.30363	36WH0843	Prehistoric	-80.38669 40.24326
36WH0227	Prehistoric	-80.29788 40.30907	36WH0859	Prehistoric	-80.36878 40.24491
36WH0230	Prehistoric	-80.28718 40.31175	36WH0982	Prehistoric	-80.34029 40.2438
36WH0232	Prehistoric	-80.31563 40.3006	36WH0983	Prehistoric	-80.33702 40.24054
36WH0233	Prehistoric	-80.34202 40.32679	36WH0984	Prehistoric	-80.34052 40.24473
36WH0243	Prehistoric	-80.3537 40.25236	36WH0985	Prehistoric	-80.34751 40.24874
36WH0244	Prehistoric	-80.32482 40.32247	36WH0986	Prehistoric	-80.34318 40.24377
36WH0245	Prehistoric	-80.39681 40.25449	36WH0987	Prehistoric	-80.34205 40.24408
36WH0246	Prehistoric	-80.39554 40.25398	36WH0992	Prehistoric	-80.34691 40.253
36WH0252	Prehistoric	-80.35892 40.35981	36WH0993	Prehistoric	-80.34933 40.255
36WH0253	Prehistoric	-80.35087 40.35666	36WH1000	Prehistoric	-80.29794 40.32983
36WH0290	Prehistoric	-80.44057 40.29183	36WH1002	Prehistoric	-80.35392 40.33681
36WH0291	Prehistoric	-80.4387 40.29245	36WH1007	Prehistoric	-80.29946 40.33077
36WH0293	Prehistoric	-80.40076 40.25502	36WH1019	Prehistoric	-80.30001 40.32845
36WH0294	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.41301 40.25093	36WH1031	Prehistoric	-80.32941 40.31155
36WH0295	Prehistoric	-80.43732 40.28291	36WH1032	Prehistoric	-80.37081 40.31121
36WH0296	Prehistoric	-80.35075 40.26116	36WH1037	Prehistoric	-80.38355 40.25875
36WH0297	Prehistoric	-80.49104 40.28637	36WH1038	Prehistoric	-80.33702 40.24723
36WH0311	Prehistoric	-80.4363 40.27782	36WH1043	Prehistoric	-80.40846 40.29283
36WH0312	Prehistoric	-80.51917 40.28249	36WH1046	Prehistoric	-80.37087 40.2706
36WH0313	Prehistoric	-80.51649 40.2831	36WH1073	Prehistoric	-80.40712 40.24297
36WH0314	Prehistoric	-80.51135 40.28763	36WH1088	Prehistoric	-80.34047 40.24104
36WH0315	Prehistoric	-80.35695 40.24687	36WH1093	Prehistoric	-80.37071 40.2541
36WH0316	Prehistoric	-80.39727 40.26009	36WH1095	Prehistoric	-80.3566 40.33404
36WH0317	Prehistoric	-80.41855 40.25528	36WH1096	Prehistoric	-80.33868 40.24086
36WH0318	Prehistoric	-80.41544 40.25298	36WH1104	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.4061 40.25957
36WH0319	Prehistoric	-80.41385 40.25315	36WH1111	Prehistoric	-80.37578 40.24787
36WH0320	Prehistoric	-80.41745 40.25391	36WH1112	Prehistoric	-80.35178 40.3374
36WH0321	Prehistoric	-80.40997 40.25464	36WH1115	Prehistoric	-80.33328 40.24749
36WH0322	Prehistoric	-80.41127 40.25664	36WH1118	Prehistoric	-80.34642 40.24972
36WH0323	Prehistoric	-80.41303 40.25609	36WH1119	Prehistoric	-80.35083 40.24984
36WH0324	Prehistoric	-80.4072 40.25259	36WH1121	Prehistoric	-80.36599 40.24867
36WH0325	Prehistoric	-80.40152 40.25597	36WH1147	Prehistoric	-80.35602 40.25369
36WH0326	Prehistoric	-80.40731 40.25359	36WH1148	Prehistoric	-80.35672 40.25439
36WH0327	Prehistoric	-80.40438 40.25551	36WH1150	Prehistoric	-80.3582 40.25349
36WH0328	Prehistoric	-80.39941 40.25397	36WH1151	Prehistoric	-80.35107 40.25084
36WH0329	Prehistoric	-80.39807 40.25315	36WH1152	Prehistoric	-80.34006 40.25401
36WH0330	Prehistoric	-80.38634 40.25582	36WH1155	Prehistoric	-80.34557 40.24058
36WH0331	Prehistoric	-80.38919 40.25505	36WH1156	Prehistoric	-80.34284 40.23983
36WH0332	Prehistoric	-80.38999 40.25368	36WH1157	Prehistoric	-80.36786 40.24937
36WH0333	Prehistoric	-80.39182 40.25374	36WH1158	Prehistoric	-80.33656 40.24316

Table A-1. Region 1 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36WH0401	Prehistoric	-80.48478 40.27853	36WH1353	Prehistoric	-80.31514 40.3204
36WH0404	Prehistoric	-80.40975 40.31657	36WH1354	Prehistoric	-80.31828 40.3225
36WH0405	Prehistoric	-80.41564 40.32236	36WH1355	Prehistoric	-80.31917 40.32414
36WH0407	Prehistoric	-80.44367 40.30164	36WH1356	Prehistoric	-80.32185 40.32472
36WH0408	Prehistoric	-80.35755 40.31502	36WH1357	Prehistoric	-80.32211 40.32676
36WH0409	Prehistoric	-80.36261 40.31415	36WH1358	Prehistoric	-80.32273 40.32842
36WH0410	Prehistoric	-80.36569 40.3117	36WH1359	Prehistoric	-80.32266 40.3297
36WH0415	Prehistoric	-80.46065 40.27888	36WH1360	Prehistoric	-80.34721 40.28814
36WH0420	Prehistoric	-80.36149 40.25589	36WH1361	Prehistoric	-80.34615 40.25051
36WH0421	Prehistoric	-80.35241 40.25538	36WH1362	Prehistoric	-80.33074 40.25783
36WH0422	Prehistoric	-80.37152 40.25312	36WH1363	Prehistoric	-80.36829 40.25914
36WH0431	Prehistoric	-80.44403 40.31071	36WH1364	Prehistoric	-80.36785 40.26143
36WH0432	Prehistoric	-80.44491 40.31483	36WH1365	Prehistoric	-80.36694 40.26461
36WH0445	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.41327 40.25215	36WH1366	Prehistoric	-80.36472 40.26078
36WH0475	Prehistoric	-80.35684 40.25263	36WH1367	Prehistoric	-80.36504 40.26203
36WH0492	Prehistoric	-80.33937 40.30497	36WH1386	Prehistoric	-80.37811 40.28517
36WH0493	Prehistoric	-80.34241 40.28575	36WH1482	Prehistoric	-80.35568 40.25691
36WH0494	Prehistoric	-80.33664 40.28581	36WH1483	Prehistoric	-80.34211 40.33455
36WH0495	Prehistoric	-80.35373 40.29841	36WH1484	Prehistoric	-80.34613 40.33128
36WH0496	Prehistoric	-80.36503 40.28873	36WH1485	Prehistoric	-80.34977 40.32309
36WH0497	Prehistoric	-80.35207 40.29726	36WH1517	Prehistoric	-80.37885 40.28304
36WH0498	Prehistoric	-80.3368 40.29072	36WH1518	Prehistoric	-80.37921 40.284
36WH0499	Prehistoric	-80.34651 40.27396	36WH1521	Prehistoric	-80.37141 40.31139
36WH0500	Prehistoric	-80.37272 40.2883	36WH1524	Prehistoric	-80.41846 40.37231
36WH0501	Prehistoric	-80.37979 40.2755	36WH1532	Prehistoric	-80.36802 40.25282
36WH0502	Prehistoric	-80.41766 40.29278	36WH1540	Prehistoric	-80.36943 40.314
36WH0503	Prehistoric	-80.44952 40.2843	36WH1555	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.4719 40.25663
36WH0504	Prehistoric	-80.42407 40.31531	36WH1559	Prehistoric	-80.35419 40.24256
36WH0505	Prehistoric	-80.41749 40.34292			
Watershed 68-Appalachian Plateaus-Allegheny Mountain:					
36WM0009	Prehistoric	-79.2049 40.25937	36WM0337	Prehistoric	-79.39326 40.21119
36WM0033	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.22894 40.25351	36WM0338	Prehistoric	-79.38841 40.21161
36WM0037	Prehistoric	-79.18381 40.13666	36WM0362	Prehistoric	-79.32762 40.31133
36WM0038	Prehistoric	-79.11412 40.22511	36WM0372	Prehistoric	-79.15584 40.26727
36WM0041	Prehistoric	-79.28264 40.26277	36WM0373	Prehistoric	-79.23837 40.27089
36WM0043	Prehistoric	-79.29047 40.2279	36WM0374	Prehistoric	-79.2417 40.26807
36WM0044	Prehistoric	-79.21081 40.26077	36WM0375	Prehistoric	-79.15197 40.2688
36WM0045	Prehistoric	-79.20796 40.26177	36WM0378	Prehistoric	-79.29775 40.22221
36WM0046	Prehistoric	-79.19987 40.26332	36WM0379	Prehistoric	-79.29553 40.22669
36WM0053	Prehistoric	-79.2576 40.13689	36WM0384	Prehistoric	-79.21836 40.22217
36WM0054	Prehistoric	-79.36866 40.10405	36WM0385	Prehistoric	-79.21545 40.2193
36WM0056	Prehistoric	-79.27726 40.17395	36WM0386	Prehistoric	-79.2077 40.21609
36WM0057	Prehistoric	-79.2726 40.17036	36WM0387	Prehistoric	-79.20582 40.21676
36WM0072	Prehistoric	-79.23159 40.23395	36WM0396	Prehistoric	-79.31168 40.30857
36WM0073	Prehistoric	-79.23011 40.23001	36WM0397	Prehistoric	-79.32268 40.31198
36WM0094	Prehistoric	-79.24689 40.25118	36WM0398	Prehistoric	-79.31801 40.31115
36WM0097	Prehistoric	-79.21594 40.24236	36WM0401	Prehistoric	-79.21881 40.2233
36WM0098	Prehistoric	-79.21951 40.22057	36WM0403	Prehistoric	-79.22304 40.29643
36WM0105	Prehistoric	-79.29826 40.15531	36WM0404	Prehistoric	-79.21844 40.29865
36WM0114	Prehistoric	-79.22896 40.23923	36WM0405	Prehistoric	-79.21941 40.29628
36WM0116	Prehistoric	-79.25584 40.2175	36WM0471	Prehistoric	-79.25943 40.23157
36WM0117	Prehistoric	-79.26078 40.21537	36WM0472	Prehistoric	-79.26226 40.22806

Table A-1. Region 1 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36WM0119	Prehistoric	-79.26199 40.25098	36WM0475	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.36827 40.25827
36WM0121	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.20813 40.25585	36WM0503	Prehistoric	-79.18979 40.28702
36WM0122	Prehistoric	-79.24526 40.29763	36WM0632	Prehistoric	-79.27991 40.30455
36WM0123	Prehistoric	-79.24247 40.23674	36WM0633	Prehistoric	-79.27689 40.31099
36WM0124	Prehistoric	-79.12425 40.24479	36WM0667	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.3896 40.23304
36WM0134	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.17562 40.20745	36WM0671	Prehistoric	-79.23588 40.33245
36WM0146	Prehistoric	-79.2437 40.23484	36WM0713	Prehistoric	-79.23818 40.25584
36WM0171	Prehistoric	-79.25803 40.21615	36WM0752	Prehistoric	-79.23894 40.25739
36WM0175	Prehistoric	-79.3601 40.13539	36WM0810	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.23925 40.33626
36WM0183	Prehistoric	-79.23599 40.25057	36WM0811	Prehistoric	-79.27687 40.30516
36WM0184	Prehistoric	-79.23712 40.25144	36WM0812	Prehistoric	-79.2769 40.30575
36WM0185	Prehistoric	-79.23332 40.25053	36WM0813	Prehistoric	-79.27746 40.30553
36WM0186	Prehistoric	-79.23466 40.25614	36WM0814	Prehistoric	-79.28034 40.30424
36WM0187	Prehistoric	-79.22751 40.25234	36WM0815	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.26285 40.31754
36WM0188	Prehistoric	-79.22258 40.2534	36WM0818	Prehistoric	-79.28987 40.30978
36WM0189	Prehistoric	-79.22297 40.2555	36WM0819	Prehistoric	-79.28768 40.30837
36WM0190	Prehistoric	-79.22418 40.25531	36WM0821	Prehistoric	-79.37443 40.25818
36WM0191	Prehistoric	-79.18684 40.2573	36WM0822	Prehistoric	-79.2926 40.3036
36WM0192	Prehistoric	-79.1878 40.25537	36WM0823	Prehistoric	-79.29226 40.30056
36WM0193	Prehistoric	-79.23892 40.23535	36WM0835	Prehistoric	-79.37984 40.21027
36WM0196	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.24261 40.2328	36WM0839	Prehistoric	-79.21758 40.22271
36WM0214	Prehistoric	-79.22627 40.15272	36WM0840	Prehistoric	-79.30854 40.2333
36WM0243	Prehistoric	-79.32262 40.21604	36WM0856	Prehistoric	-79.34401 40.15958
36WM0248	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.35688 40.13268	36WM0857	Prehistoric	-79.34507 40.16027
36WM0249	Prehistoric	-79.32683 40.21834	36WM0858	Prehistoric	-79.33829 40.16089
36WM0250	Prehistoric	-79.32364 40.21754	36WM0859	Prehistoric	-79.34142 40.16041
36WM0252	Prehistoric	-79.27062 40.22384	36WM0862	Prehistoric	-79.36187 40.11092
36WM0253	Prehistoric	-79.26169 40.24954	36WM0902	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.23962 40.24208
36WM0254	Prehistoric	-79.26647 40.25077	36WM0915	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.28302 40.21818
36WM0255	Prehistoric	-79.26072 40.24837	36WM0937	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.28664 40.25128
36WM0256	Prehistoric	-79.28399 40.25656	36WM0941	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.23946 40.24004
36WM0307	Prehistoric	-79.24633 40.24449	36WM0942	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.21967 40.22234
36WM0308	Prehistoric	-79.21358 40.25745	36WM1004	Prehistoric	-79.39016 40.23313
36WM0323	Prehistoric	-79.28641 40.25806			
Watershed 68-Appalachian Plateaus-Pittsburgh Low Plateau:					
36AR0203	Prehistoric	-79.43122 40.5535	36WM0448	Prehistoric	-79.50183 40.3533
36IN0021	Prehistoric	-79.36502 40.55028	36WM0449	Prehistoric	-79.3885 40.27961
36IN0147	Prehistoric	-79.44861 40.52238	36WM0460	Prehistoric	-79.44072 40.39768
36IN0149	Prehistoric	-79.41719 40.51271	36WM0462	Prehistoric	-79.35506 40.3426
36IN0150	Prehistoric	-79.41014 40.51021	36WM0463	Prehistoric	-79.39628 40.2942
36IN0151	Prehistoric	-79.41075 40.5107	36WM0464	Prehistoric	-79.33685 40.33064
36IN0152	Prehistoric	-79.41347 40.51246	36WM0465	Prehistoric	-79.34111 40.36873
36IN0153	Prehistoric	-79.41071 40.51241	36WM0467	Prehistoric	-79.5022 40.37493
36IN0154	Prehistoric	-79.42734 40.50747	36WM0468	Prehistoric	-79.50516 40.37503
36IN0155	Prehistoric	-79.40708 40.51418	36WM0469	Prehistoric	-79.44429 40.37983
36IN0156	Prehistoric	-79.40563 40.51387	36WM0470	Prehistoric	-79.44529 40.37762
36IN0157	Prehistoric	-79.40488 40.51552	36WM0478	Prehistoric	-79.32843 40.33765
36IN0158	Prehistoric	-79.40249 40.51685	36WM0489	Prehistoric	-79.36953 40.39713
36IN0159	Prehistoric	-79.40118 40.51544	36WM0490	Prehistoric	-79.46992 40.47229
36IN0160	Prehistoric	-79.40139 40.51892	36WM0491	Prehistoric	-79.47086 40.47355
36IN0392	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.44624 40.52282	36WM0492	Prehistoric	-79.47116 40.47121
36IN0428	Prehistoric	-79.39891 40.51944	36WM0493	Prehistoric	-79.46995 40.46946

Table A-1. Region 1 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36WM0295	Prehistoric	-79.4074 40.297	36WM0677	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.42428 40.26364
36WM0296	Prehistoric	-79.39972 40.29587	36WM0678	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.42199 40.26708
36WM0297	Prehistoric	-79.41248 40.29816	36WM0679	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.42417 40.26714
36WM0298	Prehistoric	-79.39769 40.28843	36WM0680	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.41768 40.26611
36WM0299	Prehistoric	-79.3976 40.28771	36WM0681	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.41059 40.27318
36WM0300	Prehistoric	-79.41254 40.29447	36WM0694	Prehistoric	-79.43749 40.42764
36WM0301	Prehistoric	-79.42321 40.29387	36WM0695	Prehistoric	-79.43621 40.42717
36WM0302	Prehistoric	-79.4042 40.30223	36WM0696	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.44052 40.4302
36WM0303	Prehistoric	-79.42049 40.31786	36WM0697	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.4423 40.42889
36WM0304	Prehistoric	-79.39496 40.3044	36WM0698	Prehistoric	-79.44284 40.42867
36WM0324	Prehistoric	-79.32886 40.33426	36WM0699	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.44326 40.42834
36WM0325	Prehistoric	-79.33155 40.33252	36WM0727	Prehistoric	-79.47749 40.32316
36WM0326	Prehistoric	-79.36107 40.33838	36WM0729	Prehistoric	-79.35558 40.30076
36WM0327	Prehistoric	-79.35948 40.33846	36WM0793	Prehistoric	-79.46487 40.33447
36WM0328	Prehistoric	-79.36056 40.33591	36WM0805	Prehistoric	-79.41636 40.26191
36WM0329	Prehistoric	-79.36269 40.33992	36WM0806	Prehistoric	-79.42924 40.28522
36WM0363	Prehistoric	-79.33453 40.31073	36WM0807	Prehistoric	-79.44069 40.30913
36WM0364	Prehistoric	-79.33466 40.30798	36WM0808	Prehistoric	-79.44335 40.34785
36WM0365	Prehistoric	-79.34657 40.29099	36WM0809	Prehistoric	-79.40345 40.26919
36WM0366	Prehistoric	-79.33921 40.33927	36WM0833	Prehistoric	-79.4075 40.2432
36WM0367	Prehistoric	-79.3283 40.35129	36WM0834	Prehistoric	-79.40789 40.24248
36WM0368	Prehistoric	-79.3287 40.3491	36WM0838	Prehistoric	-79.42075 40.24914
36WM0369	Prehistoric	-79.32514 40.34934	36WM0843	Prehistoric	-79.33429 40.33645
36WM0370	Prehistoric	-79.4848 40.34813	36WM0851	Prehistoric	-79.42004 40.24634
36WM0371	Prehistoric	-79.42659 40.37827	36WM0884	Prehistoric	-79.36508 40.28597
36WM0376	Prehistoric	-79.38618 40.28139	36WM0891	Prehistoric	-79.38356 40.28189
36WM0389	Prehistoric	-79.40743 40.29886	36WM0896	Prehistoric	-79.42464 40.26509
36WM0391	Prehistoric	-79.32647 40.34348	36WM0897	Prehistoric	-79.42395 40.26871
36WM0392	Prehistoric	-79.3264 40.34081	36WM0898	Prehistoric	-79.42505 40.26882
36WM0399	Prehistoric	-79.37858 40.3509	36WM0899	Prehistoric	-79.42489 40.27067
36WM0400	Prehistoric	-79.40433 40.29882	36WM0900	Prehistoric	-79.42162 40.26845
36WM0428	Prehistoric	-79.3257 40.36529	36WM0901	Prehistoric	-79.42881 40.26635
36WM0436	Prehistoric	-79.4811 40.35194	36WM0907	Prehistoric	-79.3893 40.34488
36WM0440	Prehistoric	-79.33632 40.34273	36WM0914	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.44386 40.28747
36WM0441	Prehistoric	-79.33437 40.34004	36WM0971	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.44221 40.44186
36WM0442	Prehistoric	-79.35106 40.33595	36WM0972	Prehistoric	-79.43969 40.44055
36WM0444	Prehistoric	-79.36277 40.3476	36WM0973	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.43446 40.44104
36WM0445	Prehistoric	-79.33568 40.35688	36WM1001	Prehistoric	-79.39993 40.24795
36WM0446	Prehistoric	-79.33802 40.33734	36WM1002	Prehistoric	-79.40195 40.24293
36WM0447	Prehistoric	-79.34149 40.33791			
Watershed 73-Appalachian Plateaus-Allegheny Front:					
36SO0031	Prehistoric	-78.69089 40.19339	36SO0207	Prehistoric	-78.801 40.05097
Watershed 73-Appalachian Plateaus-Allegheny Mountain:					
36CB0006	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.03969 40.29669	36SO0161	Prehistoric	-79.0475 40.04341
36CB0007	Prehistoric	-79.04372 40.29287	36SO0162	Prehistoric	-79.03808 40.05221
36CB0018	Prehistoric	-79.04201 40.28647	36SO0163	Prehistoric	-79.03879 40.0541
36CB0029	Prehistoric	-78.92405 40.28602	36SO0164	Prehistoric	-79.03978 40.05282
36CB0144	Prehistoric	-78.76398 40.31845	36SO0165	Prehistoric	-79.04113 40.05452
36CB0177	Prehistoric	-78.91513 40.31133	36SO0167	Prehistoric	-79.04497 40.0546
36CB0178	Prehistoric	-78.82903 40.28676	36SO0168	Prehistoric	-79.04609 40.05767
36CB0179	Prehistoric	-78.82847 40.28695	36SO0169	Prehistoric	-79.04891 40.05759

Table A-1. Region 1 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36CB0180	Prehistoric	-78.82542 40.28799	36SO0170	Prehistoric	-79.04875 40.05863
36SO/070	Prehistoric	-78.95143 40.04326	36SO0171	Prehistoric	-79.04351 40.05979
36SO/071	Prehistoric	-78.96049 40.04311	36SO0172	Prehistoric	-79.04326 40.05928
36SO0011	Prehistoric	-78.87253 40.1329	36SO0173	Prehistoric	-79.04183 40.06149
36SO0012	Prehistoric	-78.87402 40.13487	36SO0176	Prehistoric	-79.05708 40.05631
36SO0015	Prehistoric	-78.9307 40.19775	36SO0177	Prehistoric	-79.05415 40.05471
36SO0016	Prehistoric	-78.92948 40.1413	36SO0178	Prehistoric	-79.08526 40.1361
36SO0017	Prehistoric	-78.94204 40.18781	36SO0179	Prehistoric	-79.03436 40.18062
36SO0018	Prehistoric	-78.93221 40.19562	36SO0180	Prehistoric	-79.03233 40.18356
36SO0023	Prehistoric	-78.97519 40.1633	36SO0196	Prehistoric	-78.86161 40.07152
36SO0024	Prehistoric	-78.93497 40.19797	36SO0199	Prehistoric	-78.9603 39.93521
36SO0025	Prehistoric	-78.92919 40.19896	36SO0202	Prehistoric	-79.00449 40.04301
36SO0026	Prehistoric	-78.92592 40.19655	36SO0203	Prehistoric	-79.05909 40.19273
36SO0033	Prehistoric	-78.96968 40.15022	36SO0204	Prehistoric	-78.87176 40.15594
36SO0034	Prehistoric	-78.97159 40.15416	36SO0216	Prehistoric	-78.9619 40.20309
36SO0035	Prehistoric	-78.95756 40.17314	36SO0222	Prehistoric	-79.08132 40.07076
36SO0036	Prehistoric	-78.97214 40.15053	36SO0271	Prehistoric	-78.95005 40.07375
36SO0037	Prehistoric	-78.94402 40.1779	36SO0272	Prehistoric	-78.9399 40.07882
36SO0038	Prehistoric	-78.97413 40.15229	36SO0273	Prehistoric	-78.945 40.09075
36SO0039	Prehistoric	-78.84602 40.23252	36SO0275	Prehistoric	-78.95744 40.10984
36SO0042	Prehistoric	-78.95711 40.17468	36SO0276	Prehistoric	-78.98166 40.1136
36SO0048	Prehistoric	-78.8766 40.12979	36SO0277	Prehistoric	-78.98985 40.10876
36SO0078	Prehistoric	-78.936 40.2006	36SO0278	Prehistoric	-78.91605 40.14736
36SO0079	Prehistoric	-78.93411 40.20107	36SO0279	Prehistoric	-79.02661 40.15687
36SO0080	Prehistoric	-78.93205 40.20295	36SO0288	Prehistoric	-79.02688 40.15716
36SO0082	Prehistoric	-78.92839 40.1976	36SO0290	Prehistoric	-78.91638 39.9898
36SO0083	Prehistoric	-78.9199 40.19589	36SO0291	Prehistoric	-78.98703 40.08759
36SO0084	Prehistoric	-78.93725 40.19851	36SO0292	Prehistoric	-78.99242 40.08814
36SO0085	Prehistoric	-78.93984 40.19894	36SO0293	Prehistoric	-78.95688 40.09505
36SO0086	Prehistoric	-78.94072 40.1963	36SO0294	Prehistoric	-78.95743 40.09424
36SO0087	Prehistoric	-78.93806 40.1991	36SO0295	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.96101 40.09116
36SO0088	Prehistoric	-78.93834 40.19731	36SO0296	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.96187 40.09126
36SO0089	Prehistoric	-78.96592 40.20074	36SO0297	Prehistoric	-78.95931 40.09135
36SO0090	Prehistoric	-78.94577 40.14138	36SO0298	Prehistoric	-78.96243 40.0912
36SO0091	Prehistoric	-78.93817 40.14184	36SO0299	Prehistoric	-78.96957 40.09732
36SO0092	Prehistoric	-78.87562 40.12565	36SO0300	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.95761 40.09259
36SO0093	Prehistoric	-79.03548 40.27485	36SO0304	Prehistoric	-78.95327 40.09384
36SO0094	Prehistoric	-79.0293 40.27965	36SO0305	Prehistoric	-78.9446 40.09183
36SO0099	Prehistoric	-79.10536 40.17759	36SO0306	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.95222 40.07532
36SO0101	Prehistoric	-78.97604 40.01149	36SO0307	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.9449 40.09505
36SO0103	Prehistoric	-78.92192 40.0754	36SO0345	Prehistoric	-78.94767 39.9839
36SO0104	Prehistoric	-78.92048 40.01459	36SO0346	Prehistoric	-78.95065 39.98572
36SO0105	Prehistoric	-78.98819 40.07304	36SO0347	Prehistoric	-78.93896 39.9696
36SO0146	Prehistoric	-78.9197 40.02611	36SO0348	Prehistoric	-78.93909 39.96741
36SO0147	Prehistoric	-79.10407 40.20031	36SO0350	Prehistoric	-78.93288 39.98168
36SO0148	Prehistoric	-79.10702 40.19447	36SO0353	Prehistoric	-78.94221 39.977
36SO0149	Prehistoric	-79.05572 40.26604	36SO0354	Prehistoric	-78.94775 39.97357
36SO0150	Prehistoric	-78.92971 40.14258	36SO0355	Prehistoric	-78.9461 39.96987
36SO0151	Prehistoric	-79.15129 40.15648	36SO0356	Prehistoric	-78.94739 39.96585
36SO0153	Prehistoric	-79.15714 40.14924	36SO0357	Prehistoric	-78.94966 39.96484
36SO0157	Prehistoric	-79.16309 40.13728	36SO0358	Prehistoric	-78.94264 39.96493
36SO0158	Prehistoric	-79.04251 40.04585	36SO0381	Prehistoric	-78.89488 40.02149

Table A-1. Region 1 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36AL0111	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.0817 40.43013	36AL0594	Prehistoric	-80.21696 40.41922
36AL0119	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.0557 40.46274	36AL0595	Prehistoric	-80.21945 40.4181
36AL0121	Prehistoric	-80.09607 40.45609	36AL0596	Prehistoric	-80.21702 40.41883
36AL0122	Prehistoric	-80.08287 40.45694	36WH0024	Prehistoric	-80.25378 40.36326
36AL0123	Prehistoric	-80.07287 40.46463	36WH0043	Prehistoric	-80.24795 40.36472
36AL0137	Prehistoric	-80.05935 40.46181	36WH0086	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.25098 40.36415
36AL0321	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.10329 40.41649	36WH0240	Prehistoric	-80.24267 40.37406
36AL0385	Prehistoric	-80.21591 40.42223	36WH1310	Prehistoric	-80.2621 40.35985
Watershed 75-Appalachian Plateaus-Waynesburg Hills:					
36AL0014	Prehistoric	-80.11651 40.36879	36WH0456	Prehistoric	-80.13637 40.17908
36AL0015	Prehistoric	-80.11123 40.36775	36WH0457	Prehistoric	-80.1319 40.20382
36AL0028	Prehistoric	-80.11676 40.36194	36WH0458	Prehistoric	-80.12757 40.20252
36AL0029	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.09626 40.3798	36WH0459	Prehistoric	-80.13798 40.12732
36AL0038	Prehistoric	-80.11167 40.32146	36WH0461	Prehistoric	-80.05526 40.28549
36AL0039	Prehistoric	-80.11458 40.3194	36WH0465	Prehistoric	-80.15657 40.2274
36AL0040	Prehistoric	-80.1149 40.31684	36WH0466	Prehistoric	-80.15658 40.2266
36AL0041	Prehistoric	-80.11387 40.31458	36WH0467	Prehistoric	-80.13643 40.21771
36AL0042	Prehistoric	-80.11909 40.31323	36WH0468	Prehistoric	-80.13777 40.21571
36AL0045	Prehistoric	-80.11885 40.31519	36WH0469	Prehistoric	-80.13126 40.27246
36AL0046	Prehistoric	-80.11883 40.31763	36WH0470	Prehistoric	-80.13947 40.26122
36AL0048	Prehistoric	-80.12143 40.31692	36WH0586	Prehistoric	-80.18102 40.28421
36AL0049	Prehistoric	-80.11805 40.31961	36WH0587	Prehistoric	-80.22664 40.25039
36AL0050	Prehistoric	-80.12105 40.3152	36WH0588	Prehistoric	-80.23841 40.32143
36AL0051	Prehistoric	-80.10775 40.32101	36WH0606	Prehistoric	-80.11765 40.15659
36AL0052	Prehistoric	-80.10603 40.32002	36WH0609	Prehistoric	-80.31873 40.23505
36AL0053	Prehistoric	-80.11216 40.33231	36WH0610	Prehistoric	-80.28737 40.16765
36AL0054	Prehistoric	-80.10296 40.33355	36WH0613	Prehistoric	-80.21206 40.20345
36AL0055	Prehistoric	-80.09664 40.32919	36WH0619	Prehistoric	-80.32806 40.22894
36AL0056	Prehistoric	-80.1159 40.3676	36WH0620	Prehistoric	-80.29529 40.17634
36AL0062	Prehistoric	-80.11859 40.36862	36WH0621	Prehistoric	-80.29329 40.17687
36AL0063	Prehistoric	-80.11348 40.37062	36WH0622	Prehistoric	-80.29218 40.17721
36AL0064	Prehistoric	-80.1076 40.37398	36WH0623	Prehistoric	-80.13763 40.27701
36AL0065	Prehistoric	-80.11079 40.33058	36WH0624	Prehistoric	-80.1352 40.25694
36AL0071	Prehistoric	-80.09956 40.3387	36WH0625	Prehistoric	-80.13701 40.22338
36AL0073	Prehistoric	-80.11164 40.32395	36WH0626	Prehistoric	-80.13792 40.24246
36AL0081	Prehistoric	-80.11822 40.33258	36WH0627	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.13325 40.22444
36AL0082	Prehistoric	-80.10476 40.33522	36WH0628	Prehistoric	-80.16714 40.23777
36AL0085	Prehistoric	-80.11353 40.34145	36WH0629	Prehistoric	-80.14061 40.2306
36AL0086	Prehistoric	-80.11624 40.31982	36WH0630	Prehistoric	-80.13753 40.23805
36AL0095	Prehistoric	-80.10378 40.37921	36WH0631	Prehistoric	-80.13707 40.22954
36AL0097	Prehistoric	-80.10624 40.31857	36WH0632	Prehistoric	-80.13558 40.23733
36AL0106	Prehistoric	-80.11118 40.33453	36WH0633	Prehistoric	-80.1355 40.24103
36AL0107	Prehistoric	-80.17041 40.33912	36WH0634	Prehistoric	-80.13221 40.23417
36AL0108	Prehistoric	-80.11963 40.3596	36WH0635	Prehistoric	-80.15224 40.18882
36AL0109	Prehistoric	-80.07753 40.4114	36WH0636	Prehistoric	-80.15527 40.18835
36AL0112	Prehistoric	-80.17862 40.37308	36WH0637	Prehistoric	-80.17753 40.20426
36AL0113	Prehistoric	-80.16273 40.35784	36WH0638	Prehistoric	-80.17499 40.20347
36AL0114	Prehistoric	-80.08528 40.35991	36WH0639	Prehistoric	-80.17074 40.19965
36AL0115	Prehistoric	-80.20932 40.36353	36WH0640	Prehistoric	-80.14101 40.18702
36AL0116	Prehistoric	-80.21603 40.36691	36WH0641	Prehistoric	-80.1295 40.1575
36AL0117	Prehistoric	-80.05464 40.33786	36WH0642	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.13929 40.18454
36AL0118	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.05991 40.32644	36WH0643	Prehistoric	-80.1361 40.23146

Table A-1. Region 1 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36FA0368	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.91899 39.81381	36GR0220	Prehistoric	-79.9387 39.76903
36FA0388	Prehistoric	-79.83632 39.76244	36GR0240	Prehistoric	-79.91175 39.79916
36FA0389	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.83398 39.80603	36GR0320	Prehistoric	-79.9311 39.85463
Watershed 103-Appalachian Plateaus-Waynesburg Hills:					
36FA0013	Prehistoric	-79.92171 39.91663	36GR0125	Prehistoric	-80.0351 39.74701
36FA0075	Prehistoric	-79.91876 39.92192	36GR0181	Prehistoric	-80.09087 39.72816
36GR/008	Prehistoric	-80.17048 39.83876	36GR0194	Prehistoric	-80.07565 39.80847
36GR0005	Prehistoric	-79.96313 39.82649	36GR0199	Prehistoric	-80.28376 39.73725
36GR0007	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.94285 39.90099	36GR0208	Prehistoric	-80.09225 39.72841
36GR0018	Prehistoric	-80.06244 39.73728	36GR0221	Prehistoric	-79.93127 39.92396
36GR0024	Prehistoric	-79.95004 39.84332	36GR0226	Prehistoric	-79.94162 39.90537
36GR0030	Prehistoric	-79.93487 39.92632	36GR0256	Prehistoric	-79.93155 39.80418
36GR0031	Prehistoric	-79.933 39.91664	36GR0257	Prehistoric	-80.09149 39.79256
36GR0032	Prehistoric	-80.03822 39.80646	36GR0259	Prehistoric	-80.05918 39.74555
36GR0035	Prehistoric	-79.92577 39.88413	36GR0260	Prehistoric	-80.05524 39.74601
36GR0056	Prehistoric	-80.25828 39.72462	36GR0276	Prehistoric	-79.9936 39.82126
36GR0060	Prehistoric	-79.98807 39.78155	36GR0282	Prehistoric	-79.92768 39.89466
36GR0091	Prehistoric	-79.93459 39.86663	36GR0360	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.13311 39.85785
36GR0092	Prehistoric	-79.96673 39.80478	36GR0361	Prehistoric	-80.34191 39.77102
36GR0093	Prehistoric	-79.95898 39.80221	36GR0370	Prehistoric	-80.34944 39.72422
36GR0109	Prehistoric	-80.12375 39.82641	36GR0381	Prehistoric	-80.14814 39.83942
36GR0115	Prehistoric	-80.04432 39.754	36GR0382	Prehistoric	-80.14955 39.82666
36GR0121	Prehistoric	-80.05052 39.74466			

Table A-2. Region 2 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36WA0121	Prehistoric	-79.5422 41.89098	36WA0268	Prehistoric	-79.59234 41.92401
36WA0122	Prehistoric	-79.5534 41.92275	36WA0328	Prehistoric	-79.1356 41.94169
36WA0123	Prehistoric	-79.5891 41.92244	36WA0329	Prehistoric	-79.1374 41.96438
36WA0124	Prehistoric	-79.5885 41.91666	36WA0330	Prehistoric	-79.1285 41.968
36WA0125	Prehistoric	-79.5918 41.9299	36WA0331	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.13304 41.95968
36WA0126	Prehistoric	-79.5957 41.91719	36WA0333	Prehistoric	-79.13144 41.94869
36WA0127	Prehistoric	-79.5942 41.91541	36WA0334	Prehistoric	-79.13218 41.94189
36WA0135	Prehistoric	-79.3432 41.9849	36WA0335	Prehistoric	-79.13292 41.93936
36WA0151	Prehistoric	-79.3285 41.97156	36WA0340	Prehistoric	-79.13916 41.89887
36WA0158	Prehistoric	-79.1382 41.9795	36WA0383	Prehistoric	-79.15166 41.90492
36WA0159	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.1391 41.98066	36WA0388	Prehistoric	-79.13706 41.89486
36WA0160	Prehistoric	-79.3012 41.92653	36WA0389	Prehistoric	-79.1515 41.90596
36WA0164	Prehistoric	-79.3193 41.94479	36WA0391	Prehistoric	-79.5972 41.91769
36WA0165	Prehistoric	-79.3088 41.9908	36WA0410	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.42493 41.89611
36WA0166	Prehistoric	-79.3287 41.97592	36WA0411	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.42267 41.89521
36WA0172	Prehistoric	-79.1449 41.89487	36WA0412	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.42223 41.89766
36WA0185	Prehistoric	-79.1483 41.89899	36WA0413	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.4197 41.89565
Watershed 12-Appalachian Plateaus-High Plateau:					
36VE0125	Prehistoric	-79.9155 41.40225	36VE0166	Prehistoric	-79.79177 41.54739
36VE0126	Prehistoric	-79.8594 41.39852	36VE0167	Prehistoric	-79.79367 41.5474
36VE0160	Prehistoric	-79.8437 41.52139	36VE0173	Prehistoric	-79.79898 41.58759
36VE0161	Prehistoric	-79.7959 41.51059	36VE0184	Prehistoric	-79.87372 41.43566
36VE0162	Prehistoric	-79.7854 41.54855	36VE0219	Prehistoric	-79.82757 41.41425
36VE0164	Prehistoric	-79.7869 41.54697	36VE0300	Prehistoric	-79.85808 41.45992
36VE0165	Prehistoric	-79.7897 41.5463			
Watershed 12-Appalachian Plateaus-Northwestern Glaciated Plateau:					
36CW0001	Prehistoric	-80.0448 41.51238	36CW0260	Prehistoric	-80.18447 41.52035
36CW0005	Prehistoric	-80.1492 41.59223	36CW0261	Prehistoric	-80.18451 41.52162
36CW0006	Prehistoric	-80.1692 41.68551	36CW0262	Prehistoric	-80.18387 41.52163
36CW0007	Prehistoric	-80.1749 41.67334	36CW0263	Prehistoric	-80.16796 41.52233
36CW0008	Prehistoric	-80.1598 41.62329	36CW0264	Prehistoric	-80.17659 41.52144
36CW0009	Prehistoric	-80.1525 41.60176	36CW0265	Prehistoric	-80.18181 41.52719
36CW0010	Prehistoric	-80.1588 41.60749	36CW0266	Prehistoric	-80.18221 41.5286
36CW0011	Prehistoric	-80.1413 41.58958	36CW0267	Prehistoric	-80.13922 41.52668
36CW0012	Prehistoric	-80.1474 41.58633	36CW0268	Prehistoric	-80.19567 41.53853
36CW0013	Prehistoric	-80.1348 41.58263	36CW0269	Prehistoric	-80.17416 41.56873
36CW0014	Prehistoric	-80.1207 41.56857	36CW0270	Prehistoric	-80.16561 41.56125
36CW0015	Prehistoric	-80.0798 41.52984	36CW0271	Prehistoric	-80.14937 41.58854
36CW0016	Prehistoric	-80.1074 41.54573	36CW0272	Prehistoric	-80.1271 41.53585
36CW0017	Prehistoric	-80.1086 41.53973	36CW0273	Prehistoric	-80.16428 41.61394
36CW0018	Prehistoric	-80.1034 41.53632	36CW0274	Prehistoric	-80.23907 41.55479
36CW0019	Prehistoric	-80.0603 41.52264	36CW0275	Prehistoric	-80.21368 41.58748
36CW0020	Prehistoric	-80.0359 41.50316	36CW0276	Prehistoric	-80.17267 41.65865
36CW0021	Prehistoric	-80.2 41.57255	36CW0277	Prehistoric	-80.16676 41.6156
36CW0028	Prehistoric	-80.3089 41.64378	36CW0278	Prehistoric	-80.166 41.61784
36CW0029	Prehistoric	-80.3044 41.64385	36CW0279	Prehistoric	-80.15356 41.61742
36CW0030	Prehistoric	-80.3079 41.61895	36CW0280	Prehistoric	-80.20565 41.58783
36CW0031	Prehistoric	-80.3024 41.59714	36CW0281	Prehistoric	-80.29181 41.58646
36CW0032	Prehistoric	-80.2622 41.58063	36CW0282	Prehistoric	-80.2921 41.59345
36CW0033	Prehistoric	-80.2665 41.58402	36CW0283	Prehistoric	-80.30337 41.60586
36CW0034	Prehistoric	-80.2685 41.57792	36CW0284	Prehistoric	-80.26402 41.57929

Table A-2. Region 2 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36CW0035	Prehistoric	-80.2209 41.59265	36CW0285	Prehistoric	-80.26217 41.57895
36CW0036	Prehistoric	-80.2206 41.59063	36CW0286	Prehistoric	-80.26256 41.58027
36CW0037	Prehistoric	-80.2169 41.5885	36CW0287	Prehistoric	-80.26675 41.58161
36CW0038	Prehistoric	-80.2189 41.58675	36CW0288	Prehistoric	-80.26724 41.58052
36CW0040	Prehistoric	-80.0692 41.5256	36CW0289	Prehistoric	-80.26852 41.58097
36CW0041	Prehistoric	-80.0778 41.5264	36CW0290	Prehistoric	-80.26811 41.57717
36CW0042	Prehistoric	-80.105 41.53818	36CW0291	Prehistoric	-80.26849 41.57656
36CW0058	Prehistoric	-80.0412 41.50562	36CW0292	Prehistoric	-80.26866 41.57581
36CW0061	Prehistoric	-80.2845 41.58777	36CW0293	Prehistoric	-80.27029 41.57575
36CW0062	Prehistoric	-80.2858 41.59161	36CW0295	Prehistoric	-80.29234 41.60541
36CW0063	Prehistoric	-80.2975 41.60039	36CW0296	Prehistoric	-80.2915 41.6044
36CW0076	Prehistoric	-80.3617 41.63748	36CW0297	Prehistoric	-80.30467 41.61246
36CW0106	Prehistoric	-80.3556 41.62993	36CW0300	Prehistoric	-80.26358 41.59225
36CW0107	Prehistoric	-80.3598 41.63908	36CW0301	Prehistoric	-80.26255 41.59149
36CW0108	Prehistoric	-80.3583 41.63875	36CW0302	Prehistoric	-80.2612 41.59099
36CW0109	Prehistoric	-80.3323 41.6621	36CW0303	Prehistoric	-80.26026 41.59044
36CW0110	Prehistoric	-80.3067 41.65835	36CW0304	Prehistoric	-80.26073 41.57803
36CW0111	Prehistoric	-80.3046 41.65671	36CW0305	Prehistoric	-80.26601 41.58315
36CW0112	Prehistoric	-80.3251 41.66261	36CW0306	Prehistoric	-80.26783 41.5778
36CW0113	Prehistoric	-80.309 41.66056	36CW0317	Prehistoric	-80.26266 41.59846
36CW0114	Prehistoric	-80.3033 41.66274	36CW0318	Prehistoric	-80.30708 41.55057
36CW0115	Prehistoric	-80.2937 41.66311	36CW0320	Prehistoric	-80.30671 41.61775
36CW0116	Prehistoric	-80.3335 41.63119	36CW0326	Prehistoric	-80.24394 41.59485
36CW0117	Prehistoric	-80.3552 41.62131	36CW0327	Prehistoric	-80.35055 41.66354
36CW0118	Prehistoric	-80.0609 41.5697	36CW0328	Prehistoric	-80.32293 41.66151
36CW0119	Prehistoric	-80.0619 41.57255	36CW0329	Prehistoric	-80.3215 41.65798
36CW0120	Prehistoric	-80.0586 41.57575	36CW0330	Prehistoric	-80.30084 41.63135
36CW0121	Prehistoric	-80.1124 41.59932	36CW0331	Prehistoric	-80.30135 41.63229
36CW0122	Prehistoric	-80.1116 41.60224	36CW0349	Prehistoric	-80.31249 41.62514
36CW0123	Prehistoric	-80.1073 41.60116	36CW0350	Prehistoric	-80.08422 41.53216
36CW0124	Prehistoric	-80.101 41.60244	36CW0352	Prehistoric	-80.06773 41.52656
36CW0125	Prehistoric	-80.0608 41.56693	36CW0355	Prehistoric	-80.31074 41.54953
36CW0126	Prehistoric	-80.0592 41.56876	36CW0356	Prehistoric	-80.32863 41.65621
36CW0127	Prehistoric	-80.0496 41.5697	36CW0357	Prehistoric	-80.3245 41.6563
36CW0128	Prehistoric	-80.0497 41.57051	36CW0358	Prehistoric	-80.29858 41.65219
36CW0129	Prehistoric	-80.0514 41.57067	36CW0359	Prehistoric	-80.30343 41.65716
36CW0130	Prehistoric	-80.053 41.57113	36CW0360	Prehistoric	-80.11869 41.52957
36CW0131	Prehistoric	-80.0536 41.57275	36CW0361	Prehistoric	-80.11725 41.5352
36CW0132	Prehistoric	-80.0538 41.572	36CW0365	Prehistoric	-80.32515 41.59103
36CW0133	Prehistoric	-80.0539 41.57046	36CW0366	Prehistoric	-80.32598 41.59022
36CW0134	Prehistoric	-80.0558 41.5243	36CW0369	Prehistoric	-80.16053 41.61637
36CW0135	Prehistoric	-80.0618 41.52864	36CW0370	Prehistoric	-80.16006 41.61843
36CW0136	Prehistoric	-80.0724 41.52606	36CW0371	Prehistoric	-80.13968 41.52761
36CW0137	Prehistoric	-80.1157 41.54864	36CW0372	Prehistoric	-80.12875 41.52537
36CW0138	Prehistoric	-80.1069 41.56409	36CW0373	Prehistoric	-80.2873 41.57562
36CW0139	Prehistoric	-80.1041 41.56504	36CW0374	Prehistoric	-80.31716 41.65088
36CW0140	Prehistoric	-80.0376 41.50228	36CW0375	Prehistoric	-80.31619 41.65386
36CW0141	Prehistoric	-80.0433 41.52423	36CW0376	Prehistoric	-80.31084 41.64772
36CW0142	Prehistoric	-80.0576 41.56749	36CW0378	Prehistoric	-80.23799 41.75957
36CW0143	Prehistoric	-80.0576 41.56593	36CW0379	Prehistoric	-80.31303 41.62679
36CW0144	Prehistoric	-80.0596 41.57799	36CW0383	Prehistoric	-80.22641 41.66605
36CW0145	Prehistoric	-80.0495 41.61216	36CW0384	Prehistoric	-80.21682 41.57652

Table A-2. Region 2 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36CW0146	Prehistoric	-80.0529 41.60518	36CW0389	Prehistoric	-80.08102 41.5311
36CW0147	Prehistoric	-80.0519 41.58617	36CW0391	Prehistoric	-79.96342 41.62042
36CW0148	Prehistoric	-80.0491 41.59497	36CW0409	Prehistoric	-80.20484 41.57586
36CW0149	Prehistoric	-80.0415 41.50645	36CW0410	Prehistoric	-80.24799 41.78007
36CW0150	Prehistoric	-80.0389 41.50497	36CW0411	Prehistoric	-80.25042 41.61653
36CW0151	Prehistoric	-80.0433 41.56556	36CW0413	Prehistoric	-80.23551 41.55329
36CW0152	Prehistoric	-80.045 41.59277	36CW0414	Prehistoric	-80.20013 41.58071
36CW0153	Prehistoric	-80.1003 41.53231	36CW0415	Prehistoric	-80.22031 41.5872
36CW0154	Prehistoric	-80.0987 41.52931	36CW0416	Prehistoric	-80.22023 41.58485
36CW0155	Prehistoric	-80.1051 41.5327	36CW0417	Prehistoric	-80.2195 41.5825
36CW0156	Prehistoric	-80.0962 41.52445	36CW0418	Prehistoric	-80.20065 41.54796
36CW0157	Prehistoric	-80.0931 41.52457	36CW0419	Prehistoric	-80.25158 41.5911
36CW0158	Prehistoric	-80.0907 41.52443	36CW0420	Prehistoric	-80.23151 41.56593
36CW0159	Prehistoric	-80.0907 41.55743	36CW0421	Prehistoric	-80.20788 41.58957
36CW0160	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.0892 41.55622	36CW0422	Prehistoric	-80.22333 41.56115
36CW0161	Prehistoric	-80.0556 41.58654	36CW0423	Prehistoric	-80.19384 41.57457
36CW0162	Prehistoric	-80.1335 41.58172	36CW0466	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.98366 41.58197
36CW0163	Prehistoric	-80.1288 41.57721	36CW0467	Prehistoric	-80.16489 41.61843
36CW0164	Prehistoric	-80.1343 41.58453	36CW0468	Prehistoric	-80.16636 41.61857
36CW0165	Prehistoric	-80.1378 41.5818	36CW0473	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.04899 41.52283
36CW0166	Prehistoric	-80.1248 41.58424	36CW0475	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.32083 41.64666
36CW0167	Prehistoric	-80.1267 41.59769	36CW0476	Prehistoric	-80.31778 41.64592
36CW0168	Prehistoric	-80.1294 41.5991	36CW0477	Prehistoric	-80.31288 41.6499
36CW0169	Prehistoric	-80.1421 41.59111	36CW0478	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.21593 41.59104
36CW0170	Prehistoric	-80.1465 41.58939	36CW0479	Prehistoric	-80.21346 41.59125
36CW0171	Prehistoric	-80.1441 41.52602	36ME0057	Prehistoric	-80.00053 41.46169
36CW0172	Prehistoric	-80.1387 41.52709	36ME0103	Prehistoric	-80.02549 41.48318
36CW0189	Prehistoric	-80.1639 41.66655	36ME0154	Prehistoric	-80.04132 41.4628
36CW0190	Prehistoric	-80.1705 41.67859	36ME0161	Prehistoric	-80.00773 41.44264
36CW0214	Prehistoric	-79.9627 41.58103	36ME0256	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.01797 41.47179
36CW0215	Prehistoric	-80.2378 41.76093	36VE0016	Prehistoric	-79.95143 41.43228
36CW0222	Prehistoric	-80.1496 41.61278	36VE0018	Prehistoric	-79.89407 41.4213
36CW0223	Prehistoric	-80.1508 41.6102	36VE0019	Prehistoric	-79.89237 41.42277
36CW0225	Prehistoric	-80.0497 41.59307	36VE0023	Prehistoric	-79.8874 41.42034
36CW0226	Prehistoric	-80.0481 41.59266	36VE0025	Prehistoric	-79.91812 41.43905
36CW0227	Prehistoric	-80.0464 41.59334	36VE0049	Prehistoric	-79.89307 41.45968
36CW0228	Prehistoric	-80.046 41.59394	36VE0157	Prehistoric	-79.91483 41.53709
36CW0229	Prehistoric	-80.102 41.53513	36VE0158	Prehistoric	-79.91622 41.53678
36CW0230	Prehistoric	-80.0644 41.5846	36VE0159	Prehistoric	-79.91621 41.52492
36CW0231	Prehistoric	-80.1063 41.54654	36VE0168	Prehistoric	-79.86312 41.52438
36CW0235	Prehistoric	-80.0164 41.60762	36VE0169	Prehistoric	-79.86538 41.51539
36CW0240	Prehistoric	-80.3366 41.63329	36VE0170	Prehistoric	-79.86494 41.57532
36CW0241	Prehistoric	-80.3256 41.65596	36VE0171	Prehistoric	-79.86203 41.56543
36CW0242	Prehistoric	-80.3356 41.64734	36VE0172	Prehistoric	-79.86318 41.56513
36CW0244	Prehistoric	-80.3196 41.65506	36VE0176	Prehistoric	-79.87421 41.49145
36CW0245	Prehistoric	-80.3201 41.65101	36VE0177	Prehistoric	-79.87499 41.48615
36CW0246	Prehistoric	-80.3318 41.66354	36VE0178	Prehistoric	-79.87687 41.48006
36CW0247	Prehistoric	-80.1813 41.55117	36VE0179	Prehistoric	-79.89771 41.48323
36CW0248	Prehistoric	-80.1883 41.55675	36VE0180	Prehistoric	-79.90147 41.47386
36CW0249	Prehistoric	-80.2099 41.5548	36VE0181	Prehistoric	-79.96955 41.44582
36CW0250	Prehistoric	-80.1835 41.54086	36VE0182	Prehistoric	-79.89258 41.43922
36CW0251	Prehistoric	-80.1803 41.53663	36VE0183	Prehistoric	-79.88283 41.43371

Table A-2. Region 2 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36CW0252	Prehistoric	-80.1791 41.53487	36VE0201	Prehistoric	-79.93166 41.43162
36CW0253	Prehistoric	-80.1786 41.53552	36VE0203	Prehistoric	-79.91487 41.54216
36CW0254	Prehistoric	-80.1682 41.53412	36VE0204	Prehistoric	-79.91977 41.54006
36CW0255	Prehistoric	-80.1674 41.53471	36VE0205	Prehistoric	-79.91989 41.53604
36CW0256	Prehistoric	-80.1668 41.53371	36VE0206	Prehistoric	-79.91653 41.52692
36CW0257	Prehistoric	-80.1563 41.52521	36VE0207	Prehistoric	-79.91886 41.52449
36CW0258	Prehistoric	-80.181 41.52091	36VE0208	Prehistoric	-79.90455 41.50344
36CW0259	Prehistoric	-80.1824 41.51895			
Watershed 16-Appalachian Plateaus-High Plateau:					
36CW0056	Prehistoric	-79.6546 41.61939	36VE0175	Prehistoric	-79.6535 41.60718
36FO0084	Prehistoric	-79.4659 41.46133	36VE0185	Prehistoric	-79.69308 41.48201
36FO0085	Prehistoric	-79.4665 41.46882	36VE0186	Prehistoric	-79.64336 41.45174
36FO0086	Prehistoric	-79.4648 41.4689	36VE0187	Prehistoric	-79.64525 41.46101
36VE0002	Prehistoric	-79.5585 41.44748	36VE0188	Prehistoric	-79.78072 41.39365
36VE0003	Prehistoric	-79.5736 41.44978	36VE0191	Prehistoric	-79.61058 41.49437
36VE0011	Prehistoric	-79.8208 41.39427	36VE0192	Prehistoric	-79.61277 41.49583
36VE0012	Prehistoric	-79.5921 41.52656	36VE0193	Prehistoric	-79.61178 41.49548
36VE0014	Prehistoric	-79.7869 41.40809	36VE0194	Prehistoric	-79.60965 41.49559
36VE0050	Prehistoric	-79.674 41.42158	36VE0195	Prehistoric	-79.61503 41.49584
36VE0056	Prehistoric	-79.6608 41.43146	36VE0202	Prehistoric	-79.60773 41.37778
36VE0058	Prehistoric	-79.6918 41.51574	36VE0209	Prehistoric	-79.71224 41.5158
36VE0059	Prehistoric	-79.5903 41.52245	36VE0210	Prehistoric	-79.70887 41.52292
36VE0060	Prehistoric	-79.5569 41.48548	36VE0216	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.68089 41.51846
36VE0062	Prehistoric	-79.5404 41.47262	36VE0224	Prehistoric	-79.68419 41.41707
36VE0064	Prehistoric	-79.5691 41.45871	36VE0225	Prehistoric	-79.68276 41.42029
36VE0065	Prehistoric	-79.5681 41.45762	36VE0226	Prehistoric	-79.68443 41.41985
36VE0066	Prehistoric	-79.5575 41.45018	36VE0242	Prehistoric	-79.68097 41.41508
36VE0067	Prehistoric	-79.6011 41.48058	36VE0244	Prehistoric	-79.63436 41.44161
36VE0068	Prehistoric	-79.6034 41.45861	36VE0246	Prehistoric	-79.63431 41.4383
36VE0069	Prehistoric	-79.61 41.45725	36VE0264	Prehistoric	-79.67413 41.42289
36VE0070	Prehistoric	-79.624 41.46228	36VE0265	Prehistoric	-79.65557 41.40568
36VE0071	Prehistoric	-79.6262 41.46648	36VE0266	Prehistoric	-79.64627 41.46517
36VE0072	Prehistoric	-79.7264 41.41302	36VE0267	Prehistoric	-79.64624 41.46398
36VE0073	Prehistoric	-79.7297 41.41038	36VE0268	Prehistoric	-79.64688 41.46218
36VE0074	Prehistoric	-79.6674 41.42767	36VE0274	Prehistoric	-79.79409 41.40993
36VE0130	Prehistoric	-79.8197 41.39997	36VE0294	Prehistoric	-79.57852 41.44663
36VE0163	Prehistoric	-79.7748 41.51251	36VE0295	Prehistoric	-79.53959 41.42794
Watershed 16-Appalachian Plateaus-Northwestern Glaciated Plateau:					
36CW0002	Prehistoric	-79.7034 41.84948	36CW0392	Prehistoric	-79.84969 41.81368
36CW0004	Prehistoric	-79.8415 41.80416	36CW0393	Prehistoric	-79.83062 41.80771
36CW0307	Prehistoric	-79.723 41.6919	36CW0394	Prehistoric	-79.83863 41.82949
36CW0308	Prehistoric	-79.7163 41.69231	36CW0395	Prehistoric	-79.8296 41.80867
36CW0309	Prehistoric	-79.7149 41.7034	36CW0396	Prehistoric	-79.84115 41.80768
36CW0310	Prehistoric	-79.7722 41.73948	36CW0397	Prehistoric	-79.81677 41.78901
36CW0311	Prehistoric	-79.7969 41.77672	36CW0398	Prehistoric	-79.83669 41.80762
36CW0347	Prehistoric	-79.7945 41.78082	36CW0399	Prehistoric	-79.83531 41.81434
36CW0354	Prehistoric	-79.7842 41.69965	36CW0400	Prehistoric	-79.83677 41.81272
36CW0380	Prehistoric	-79.7783 41.7041	36CW0412	Prehistoric	-79.64911 41.75492
36CW0385	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.7297 41.65382	36ER0016	Prehistoric	-79.66987 41.8619
36CW0390	Prehistoric	-79.7941 41.70307			

Table A-2. Region 2 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
Watershed 19-Appalachian Plateaus-High Plateau:					
36EL0001	Prehistoric	-78.878 41.60441	36WA0100	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.26814 41.82759
36EL0002	Prehistoric	-78.8979 41.58509	36WA0101	Prehistoric	-79.26963 41.82534
36EL0017	Prehistoric	-78.8785 41.59266	36WA0102	Prehistoric	-79.26559 41.83227
36EL0065	Prehistoric	-78.8704 41.60132	36WA0128	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.27043 41.82981
36EL0067	Prehistoric	-78.8973 41.58658	36WA0132	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.25757 41.83822
36EL0068	Prehistoric	-78.8786 41.60285	36WA0136	Prehistoric	-79.45333 41.75948
36EL0092	Prehistoric	-78.9449 41.61878	36WA0137	Prehistoric	-79.45284 41.76065
36EL0093	Prehistoric	-78.8856 41.60411	36WA0168	Prehistoric	-79.24691 41.75331
36EL0094	Prehistoric	-78.9126 41.59488	36WA0169	Prehistoric	-79.2036 41.76452
36EL0102	Prehistoric	-78.9296 41.6166	36WA0170	Prehistoric	-79.21787 41.77109
36FO0001	Prehistoric	-79.416 41.56328	36WA0177	Prehistoric	-79.24703 41.79121
36FO0002	Prehistoric	-79.5066 41.47587	36WA0178	Prehistoric	-79.27455 41.7537
36FO0003	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.4353 41.53879	36WA0180	Prehistoric	-79.01386 41.68956
36FO0004	Prehistoric	-79.4511 41.51389	36WA0182	Prehistoric	-79.0263 41.66926
36FO0005	Prehistoric	-79.434 41.55265	36WA0183	Prehistoric	-79.03135 41.68292
36FO0006	Prehistoric	-79.4504 41.50835	36WA0184	Prehistoric	-79.28886 41.76171
36FO0007	Prehistoric	-79.4558 41.48514	36WA0189	Prehistoric	-79.30277 41.75289
36FO0008	Prehistoric	-79.4196 41.47661	36WA0209	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.37025 41.68337
36FO0009	Prehistoric	-79.4073 41.58742	36WA0214	Prehistoric	-79.26358 41.72661
36FO0010	Prehistoric	-79.4039 41.57876	36WA0215	Prehistoric	-79.25555 41.83361
36FO0011	Prehistoric	-79.4552 41.49051	36WA0218	Prehistoric	-79.27494 41.82087
36FO0012	Prehistoric	-79.3893 41.61603	36WA0220	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.30628 41.6366
36FO0013	Prehistoric	-79.1476 41.62638	36WA0247	Prehistoric	-79.25576 41.83148
36FO0014	Prehistoric	-79.3255 41.54107	36WA0248	Prehistoric	-79.25391 41.83363
36FO0015	Prehistoric	-79.3996 41.56646	36WA0249	Prehistoric	-79.24915 41.83911
36FO0016	Prehistoric	-79.3957 41.57283	36WA0253	Prehistoric	-79.2634 41.83106
36FO0017	Prehistoric	-79.3971 41.62014	36WA0254	Prehistoric	-79.26636 41.8287
36FO0018	Prehistoric	-79.4532 41.48529	36WA0256	Prehistoric	-79.26887 41.82931
36FO0019	Prehistoric	-79.3562 41.49267	36WA0257	Prehistoric	-79.26614 41.83771
36FO0027	Prehistoric	-79.4263 41.56607	36WA0269	Prehistoric	-79.14331 41.62959
36FO0028	Prehistoric	-79.4247 41.56543	36WA0270	Prehistoric	-79.14513 41.63679
36FO0029	Prehistoric	-79.4236 41.56458	36WA0271	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.14017 41.6394
36FO0030	Prehistoric	-79.4232 41.56528	36WA0272	Prehistoric	-79.14017 41.643
36FO0031	Prehistoric	-79.4229 41.5649	36WA0273	Prehistoric	-79.14018 41.64667
36FO0032	Prehistoric	-79.4222 41.56477	36WA0274	Prehistoric	-79.13671 41.63441
36FO0033	Prehistoric	-79.4225 41.56433	36WA0275	Prehistoric	-79.13422 41.63199
36FO0034	Prehistoric	-79.4219 41.5635	36WA0276	Prehistoric	-79.15978 41.63385
36FO0037	Prehistoric	-79.4229 41.56404	36WA0277	Prehistoric	-79.1573 41.63525
36FO0039	Prehistoric	-79.1616 41.62658	36WA0278	Prehistoric	-79.15736 41.63433
36FO0047	Prehistoric	-79.2606 41.60008	36WA0279	Prehistoric	-79.15699 41.70448
36FO0048	Prehistoric	-79.0726 41.56427	36WA0280	Prehistoric	-79.164 41.70675
36FO0049	Prehistoric	-79.055 41.54653	36WA0281	Prehistoric	-79.21186 41.63851
36FO0054	Prehistoric	-79.229 41.61668	36WA0282	Prehistoric	-79.2328 41.65773
36FO0055	Prehistoric	-78.9837 41.5933	36WA0283	Prehistoric	-79.16036 41.64004
36FO0056	Prehistoric	-78.9753 41.58249	36WA0284	Prehistoric	-79.16907 41.6302
36FO0058	Prehistoric	-79.4038 41.57012	36WA0285	Prehistoric	-79.16557 41.64738
36FO0065	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.4966 41.47019	36WA0286	Prehistoric	-79.15418 41.63186
36FO0066	Prehistoric	-79.4955 41.46976	36WA0287	Prehistoric	-79.18438 41.66384
36FO0067	Prehistoric	-79.4937 41.46842	36WA0288	Prehistoric	-79.18562 41.66479
36FO0069	Prehistoric	-79.4041 41.56925	36WA0289	Prehistoric	-79.18633 41.66593
36FO0071	Prehistoric	-79.1569 41.61902	36WA0290	Prehistoric	-79.18744 41.66769

Table A-2. Region 2 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36FO0072	Prehistoric	-79.1574 41.6205	36WA0291	Prehistoric	-79.18762 41.66917
36FO0073	Prehistoric	-79.1582 41.6208	36WA0292	Prehistoric	-79.18835 41.67122
36FO0074	Prehistoric	-79.1582 41.62113	36WA0293	Prehistoric	-79.19055 41.67073
36FO0083	Prehistoric	-79.4774 41.46821	36WA0294	Prehistoric	-79.19196 41.66883
36FO0118	Prehistoric	-79.3803 41.59518	36WA0295	Prehistoric	-79.19349 41.66904
36FO0119	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.4435 41.47973	36WA0296	Prehistoric	-79.19581 41.67067
36FO0136	Prehistoric	-79.1511 41.60664	36WA0297	Prehistoric	-79.19746 41.67253
36FO0138	Prehistoric	-79.4271 41.4737	36WA0298	Prehistoric	-79.21202 41.69624
36FO0142	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.2905 41.52884	36WA0299	Prehistoric	-79.21483 41.70243
36FO0143	Prehistoric	-79.2907 41.52576	36WA0300	Prehistoric	-79.21257 41.70366
36FO0144	Prehistoric	-79.2912 41.52531	36WA0301	Prehistoric	-79.20994 41.70507
36FO0149	Prehistoric	-79.1981 41.57117	36WA0302	Prehistoric	-79.2089 41.70663
36FO0151	Prehistoric	-79.2383 41.5139	36WA0306	Prehistoric	-78.96089 41.69531
36FO0159	Prehistoric	-79.2071 41.49693	36WA0307	Prehistoric	-78.96789 41.68447
36FO0169	Prehistoric	-79.2192 41.51103	36WA0308	Prehistoric	-78.97221 41.68432
36FO0171	Prehistoric	-79.2042 41.49659	36WA0309	Prehistoric	-78.97855 41.68225
36FO0172	Prehistoric	-79.2074 41.49459	36WA0310	Prehistoric	-78.96323 41.69066
36FO0175	Prehistoric	-79.5022 41.47161	36WA0311	Prehistoric	-78.97323 41.68665
36FO0178	Prehistoric	-79.178 41.501	36WA0312	Prehistoric	-79.09249 41.74183
36FO0179	Prehistoric	-79.2067 41.49656	36WA0313	Prehistoric	-79.05247 41.69362
36FO0180	Prehistoric	-79.212 41.49457	36WA0314	Prehistoric	-79.05013 41.68535
36MC0035	Prehistoric	-78.9534 41.68831	36WA0315	Prehistoric	-79.10305 41.63632
36MC0040	Prehistoric	-78.9171 41.71831	36WA0321	Prehistoric	-79.22814 41.75729
36MC0041	Prehistoric	-78.9218 41.72187	36WA0322	Prehistoric	-79.25476 41.70856
36MC0042	Prehistoric	-78.9193 41.72166	36WA0323	Prehistoric	-79.25657 41.70238
36MC0043	Prehistoric	-78.9176 41.6898	36WA0325	Prehistoric	-79.29319 41.72027
36MC0044	Prehistoric	-78.9376 41.70922	36WA0326	Prehistoric	-79.2828 41.7267
36MC0045	Prehistoric	-78.9476 41.722	36WA0341	Prehistoric	-79.26924 41.71361
36VE0001	Prehistoric	-79.5583 41.4598	36WA0342	Prehistoric	-79.24994 41.70988
36VE0061	Prehistoric	-79.5173 41.4816	36WA0351	Prehistoric	-79.25641 41.84119
36VE0063	Prehistoric	-79.542 41.472	36WA0365	Prehistoric	-79.17683 41.62971
36VE0250	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.5504 41.47056	36WA0367	Prehistoric	-79.17867 41.63401
36WA0029	Prehistoric	-79.2635 41.83036	36WA0368	Prehistoric	-79.18311 41.64641
36WA0033	Prehistoric	-79.25 41.83805	36WA0369	Prehistoric	-79.18109 41.65395
36WA0034	Prehistoric	-79.2865 41.78332	36WA0370	Prehistoric	-79.18247 41.64519
36WA0038	Prehistoric	-79.2405 41.79496	36WA0371	Prehistoric	-79.1838 41.64772
36WA0041	Prehistoric	-79.222 41.6876	36WA0372	Prehistoric	-79.18141 41.64597
36WA0043	Prehistoric	-79.2924 41.74593	36WA0373	Prehistoric	-79.18592 41.64851
36WA0047	Prehistoric	-79.1846 41.72385	36WA0374	Prehistoric	-79.18799 41.64922
36WA0048	Prehistoric	-79.191 41.75158	36WA0375	Prehistoric	-79.18952 41.65117
36WA0049	Prehistoric	-79.1789 41.72652	36WA0376	Prehistoric	-79.19397 41.65563
36WA0051	Prehistoric	-79.2413 41.7982	36WA0377	Prehistoric	-79.17971 41.64895
36WA0055	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.4077 41.68761	36WA0378	Prehistoric	-79.19916 41.66949
36WA0060	Prehistoric	-79.0721 41.77666	36WA0379	Prehistoric	-79.18469 41.65835
36WA0069	Prehistoric	-79.4077 41.68229	36WA0380	Prehistoric	-79.18327 41.66065
36WA0072	Prehistoric	-79.4236 41.65161	36WA0381	Prehistoric	-79.18628 41.66379
36WA0073	Prehistoric	-79.3573 41.73365	36WA0382	Prehistoric	-79.1779 41.67155
36WA0074	Prehistoric	-79.4457 41.66805	36WA0393	Prehistoric	-79.0889 41.70758
36WA0075	Prehistoric	-79.4454 41.66623	36WA0398	Prehistoric	-78.97877 41.64526
36WA0076	Prehistoric	-79.392 41.68629	36WA0399	Prehistoric	-78.95587 41.68318
36WA0077	Prehistoric	-79.4044 41.68226	36WA0400	Prehistoric	-79.01017 41.62767
36WA0078	Prehistoric	-79.3468 41.70557	36WA0401	Prehistoric	-78.9742 41.68614

Table A-2. Region 2 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36CW0088	Prehistoric	-80.4497 41.73589	36ME0050	Prehistoric	-80.35176 41.32908
36CW0089	Prehistoric	-80.4521 41.73805	36ME0051	Prehistoric	-80.44715 41.29948
36CW0090	Prehistoric	-80.4594 41.73433	36ME0052	Prehistoric	-80.44839 41.29619
36CW0091	Prehistoric	-80.4706 41.72947	36ME0053	Prehistoric	-80.44694 41.29757
36CW0092	Prehistoric	-80.3862 41.63374	36ME0054	Prehistoric	-80.39333 41.35549
36CW0093	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.3978 41.63414	36ME0055	Prehistoric	-80.47326 41.32005
36CW0094	Prehistoric	-80.39 41.63397	36ME0056	Prehistoric	-80.28516 41.2407
36CW0095	Prehistoric	-80.388 41.63312	36ME0060	Prehistoric	-80.39058 41.2954
36CW0096	Prehistoric	-80.3892 41.63341	36ME0061	Prehistoric	-80.50953 41.18829
36CW0097	Prehistoric	-80.3982 41.64933	36ME0062	Prehistoric	-80.44712 41.30726
36CW0098	Prehistoric	-80.423 41.67845	36ME0063	Prehistoric	-80.42985 41.30152
36CW0099	Prehistoric	-80.4862 41.68464	36ME0064	Prehistoric	-80.12923 41.21467
36CW0100	Prehistoric	-80.4293 41.63702	36ME0065	Prehistoric	-80.12893 41.21318
36CW0101	Prehistoric	-80.4095 41.69225	36ME0066	Prehistoric	-80.13217 41.2186
36CW0102	Prehistoric	-80.51 41.71833	36ME0067	Prehistoric	-80.13144 41.22054
36CW0103	Prehistoric	-80.3766 41.60279	36ME0068	Prehistoric	-80.1379 41.22657
36CW0104	Prehistoric	-80.3923 41.58389	36ME0069	Prehistoric	-80.14001 41.22557
36CW0105	Prehistoric	-80.4012 41.60305	36ME0070	Prehistoric	-80.13989 41.2273
36CW0216	Prehistoric	-80.4381 41.66222	36ME0071	Prehistoric	-80.13262 41.22234
36CW0217	Prehistoric	-80.464 41.72744	36ME0072	Prehistoric	-80.39141 41.29072
36CW0218	Prehistoric	-80.3843 41.63295	36ME0073	Prehistoric	-80.38953 41.28994
36CW0219	Prehistoric	-80.3863 41.63264	36ME0074	Prehistoric	-80.38571 41.28593
36CW0220	Prehistoric	-80.4362 41.62655	36ME0075	Prehistoric	-80.38367 41.28855
36CW0221	Prehistoric	-80.4461 41.6336	36ME0076	Prehistoric	-80.38189 41.28938
36CW0233	Prehistoric	-80.4279 41.64204	36ME0077	Prehistoric	-80.38028 41.28907
36CW0234	Prehistoric	-80.4292 41.63599	36ME0078	Prehistoric	-80.38031 41.28986
36CW0236	Prehistoric	-80.5034 41.60368	36ME0079	Prehistoric	-80.37892 41.2898
36CW0237	Prehistoric	-80.3886 41.62512	36ME0080	Prehistoric	-80.38444 41.28783
36CW0238	Prehistoric	-80.5067 41.63393	36ME0081	Prehistoric	-80.4416 41.2957
36CW0239	Prehistoric	-80.4558 41.61738	36ME0082	Prehistoric	-80.3873 41.29414
36CW0294	Prehistoric	-80.3405 41.56396	36ME0083	Prehistoric	-80.37649 41.28742
36CW0298	Prehistoric	-80.3555 41.53778	36ME0084	Prehistoric	-80.41507 41.29144
36CW0299	Prehistoric	-80.3574 41.5382	36ME0085	Prehistoric	-80.44505 41.29868
36CW0312	Prehistoric	-80.5046 41.58968	36ME0086	Prehistoric	-80.44265 41.29499
36CW0319	Prehistoric	-80.3368 41.56389	36ME0087	Prehistoric	-80.44462 41.29551
36CW0321	Prehistoric	-80.3676 41.58419	36ME0088	Prehistoric	-80.4637 41.30874
36CW0322	Prehistoric	-80.3563 41.52324	36ME0089	Prehistoric	-80.46628 41.30995
36CW0323	Prehistoric	-80.359 41.52165	36ME0090	Prehistoric	-80.46872 41.30797
36CW0324	Prehistoric	-80.3629 41.50524	36ME0091	Prehistoric	-80.47604 41.31438
36CW0325	Prehistoric	-80.3649 41.55423	36ME0092	Prehistoric	-80.46032 41.3093
36CW0332	Prehistoric	-80.5058 41.63023	36ME0093	Prehistoric	-80.47628 41.31634
36CW0333	Prehistoric	-80.4444 41.6475	36ME0094	Prehistoric	-80.47372 41.31712
36CW0334	Prehistoric	-80.4845 41.66113	36ME0095	Prehistoric	-80.47983 41.31857
36CW0335	Prehistoric	-80.439 41.63468	36ME0096	Prehistoric	-80.39363 41.29176
36CW0336	Prehistoric	-80.4351 41.63961	36ME0097	Prehistoric	-80.39702 41.29176
36CW0337	Prehistoric	-80.3865 41.62517	36ME0098	Prehistoric	-80.39169 41.28935
36CW0338	Prehistoric	-80.435 41.6425	36ME0099	Prehistoric	-80.3936 41.28972
36CW0339	Prehistoric	-80.4428 41.634	36ME0100	Prehistoric	-80.38986 41.29297
36CW0340	Prehistoric	-80.4756 41.63164	36ME0101	Prehistoric	-80.39093 41.29235
36CW0341	Prehistoric	-80.4491 41.6504	36ME0102	Prehistoric	-80.39163 41.29296
36CW0342	Prehistoric	-80.4355 41.64597	36ME0107	Prehistoric	-80.19761 41.21194
36CW0343	Prehistoric	-80.4512 41.64333	36ME0108	Prehistoric	-80.19791 41.21019

Table A-2. Region 2 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36CW0344	Prehistoric	-80.4476 41.63489	36ME0109	Prehistoric	-80.14957 41.21953
36CW0345	Prehistoric	-80.4586 41.65418	36ME0110	Prehistoric	-80.16779 41.22292
36CW0346	Prehistoric	-80.48 41.63964	36ME0111	Prehistoric	-80.16783 41.23891
36CW0362	Prehistoric	-80.3549 41.53963	36ME0112	Prehistoric	-80.1316 41.22325
36CW0363	Prehistoric	-80.3553 41.54173	36ME0113	Prehistoric	-80.13105 41.21857
36CW0364	Prehistoric	-80.3581 41.53735	36ME0114	Prehistoric	-80.1289 41.21402
36CW0367	Prehistoric	-80.394 41.63927	36ME0115	Prehistoric	-80.18996 41.24258
36CW0368	Prehistoric	-80.3936 41.63861	36ME0116	Prehistoric	-80.18272 41.23277
36CW0382	Prehistoric	-80.5144 41.65331	36ME0117	Prehistoric	-80.13379 41.21856
36CW0386	Prehistoric	-80.4619 41.65705	36ME0118	Prehistoric	-80.21334 41.13813
36CW0387	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.5013 41.60823	36ME0119	Prehistoric	-80.21534 41.1358
36CW0388	Prehistoric	-80.4715 41.50934	36ME0120	Prehistoric	-80.21312 41.13574
36CW0401	Prehistoric	-80.3969 41.64048	36ME0121	Prehistoric	-80.23799 41.20759
36CW0406	Prehistoric	-80.3364 41.53584	36ME0122	Prehistoric	-80.13348 41.20108
36CW0407	Prehistoric	-80.3361 41.53409	36ME0124	Prehistoric	-80.12787 41.2147
36CW0408	Prehistoric	-80.4652 41.66212	36ME0125	Prehistoric	-80.14957 41.24263
36CW0426	Prehistoric	-80.3707 41.55407	36ME0126	Prehistoric	-80.17518 41.25216
36LR0002	Prehistoric	-80.4302 41.1189	36ME0129	Prehistoric	-80.32372 41.13517
36LR0007	Prehistoric	-80.2829 41.04505	36ME0130	Prehistoric	-80.32191 41.13376
36LR0009	Prehistoric	-80.3918 41.07952	36ME0131	Prehistoric	-80.31196 41.15316
36LR0010	Prehistoric	-80.3015 41.05153	36ME0132	Prehistoric	-80.37042 41.28619
36LR0013	Prehistoric	-80.2371 41.09524	36ME0133	Prehistoric	-80.3712 41.28588
36LR0014	Prehistoric	-80.2855 41.09569	36ME0134	Prehistoric	-80.37178 41.286
36LR0015	Prehistoric	-80.3206 41.09418	36ME0135	Prehistoric	-80.36908 41.28593
36LR0016	Prehistoric	-80.3174 41.12125	36ME0138	Prehistoric	-80.445 41.39489
36LR0020	Prehistoric	-80.2328 41.05093	36ME0143	Prehistoric	-80.15561 41.22025
36LR0022	Prehistoric	-80.3062 41.06077	36ME0144	Prehistoric	-80.43635 41.40213
36LR0023	Prehistoric	-80.3118 41.09009	36ME0146	Prehistoric	-80.42878 41.45054
36LR0024	Prehistoric	-80.3085 41.05315	36ME0147	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.42874 41.45213
36LR0025	Prehistoric	-80.3065 41.05197	36ME0148	Prehistoric	-80.29347 41.47157
36LR0026	Prehistoric	-80.3036 41.04931	36ME0150	Prehistoric	-80.50646 41.3282
36LR0027	Prehistoric	-80.3058 41.07732	36ME0151	Prehistoric	-80.50954 41.34335
36LR0028	Prehistoric	-80.3207 41.10926	36ME0152	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.51094 41.3458
36LR0029	Prehistoric	-80.3112 41.11815	36ME0153	Prehistoric	-80.17753 41.16895
36LR0030	Prehistoric	-80.4333 41.11082	36ME0158	Prehistoric	-80.23436 41.21426
36LR0031	Prehistoric	-80.4156 41.10665	36ME0160	Prehistoric	-80.3679 41.28585
36LR0032	Prehistoric	-80.387 41.07525	36ME0162	Prehistoric	-80.49061 41.18603
36LR0033	Prehistoric	-80.3984 41.0355	36ME0163	Prehistoric	-80.44701 41.14543
36LR0034	Prehistoric	-80.3871 41.07126	36ME0164	Prehistoric	-80.44407 41.13847
36LR0040	Prehistoric	-80.4093 41.09591	36ME0165	Prehistoric	-80.44358 41.16803
36LR0041	Prehistoric	-80.3932 41.10814	36ME0166	Prehistoric	-80.47242 41.13698
36LR0042	Prehistoric	-80.3076 41.10779	36ME0168	Prehistoric	-80.43823 41.2927
36LR0043	Prehistoric	-80.3063 41.06545	36ME0169	Prehistoric	-80.39627 41.29841
36LR0044	Prehistoric	-80.3106 41.06041	36ME0170	Prehistoric	-80.44869 41.30554
36LR0049	Prehistoric	-80.4178 41.10233	36ME0171	Prehistoric	-80.45161 41.30775
36LR0050	Prehistoric	-80.4138 41.09982	36ME0172	Prehistoric	-80.44268 41.29686
36LR0051	Prehistoric	-80.4209 41.10015	36ME0173	Prehistoric	-80.35533 41.43864
36LR0052	Prehistoric	-80.417 41.09647	36ME0174	Prehistoric	-80.416 41.29555
36LR0053	Prehistoric	-80.3881 41.08024	36ME0175	Prehistoric	-80.14174 41.2681
36LR0054	Prehistoric	-80.3822 41.07917	36ME0176	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.46818 41.19444
36LR0055	Prehistoric	-80.4036 41.07764	36ME0178	Prehistoric	-80.38776 41.28769
36LR0056	Prehistoric	-80.3829 41.07332	36ME0179	Prehistoric	-80.21825 41.13121

Table A-2. Region 2 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LR0057	Prehistoric	-80.3828 41.06981	36ME0180	Prehistoric	-80.21546 41.12736
36LR0058	Prehistoric	-80.3811 41.06409	36ME0181	Prehistoric	-80.20439 41.13415
36LR0059	Prehistoric	-80.3974 41.05421	36ME0182	Prehistoric	-80.23945 41.30403
36LR0061	Prehistoric	-80.4001 41.04288	36ME0183	Prehistoric	-80.23962 41.30505
36LR0062	Prehistoric	-80.4051 41.03702	36ME0184	Prehistoric	-80.24239 41.30346
36LR0063	Prehistoric	-80.3841 41.03181	36ME0185	Prehistoric	-80.24302 41.31914
36LR0064	Prehistoric	-80.377 41.04898	36ME0186	Prehistoric	-80.21796 41.22632
36LR0065	Prehistoric	-80.3175 41.05988	36ME0187	Prehistoric	-80.21499 41.22879
36LR0066	Prehistoric	-80.4346 41.10072	36ME0188	Prehistoric	-80.23263 41.17112
36LR0067	Prehistoric	-80.309 41.11945	36ME0189	Prehistoric	-80.23377 41.31051
36LR0068	Prehistoric	-80.303 41.11642	36ME0190	Prehistoric	-80.2301 41.28049
36LR0069	Prehistoric	-80.3038 41.11534	36ME0192	Prehistoric	-80.49493 41.33022
36LR0073	Prehistoric	-80.3776 41.09111	36ME0193	Prehistoric	-80.46082 41.31267
36LR0086	Prehistoric	-80.3006 41.12093	36ME0194	Prehistoric	-80.45429 41.30294
36LR0087	Prehistoric	-80.4365 41.10168	36ME0196	Prehistoric	-80.44845 41.29979
36LR0088	Prehistoric	-80.4385 41.1027	36ME0197	Prehistoric	-80.44379 41.29822
36LR0089	Prehistoric	-80.4377 41.10397	36ME0198	Prehistoric	-80.4367 41.29558
36LR0090	Prehistoric	-80.4376 41.10518	36ME0200	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.38658 41.28973
36LR0091	Prehistoric	-80.4378 41.1054	36ME0201	Prehistoric	-80.39436 41.35351
36LR0092	Prehistoric	-80.4387 41.1056	36ME0202	Prehistoric	-80.49079 41.27148
36LR0093	Prehistoric	-80.4296 41.09415	36ME0203	Prehistoric	-80.23409 41.21033
36LR0156	Prehistoric	-80.2836 41.01773	36ME0204	Prehistoric	-80.23346 41.20616
36LR0157	Prehistoric	-80.2859 41.01713	36ME0205	Prehistoric	-80.23014 41.21087
36LR0158	Prehistoric	-80.2883 41.02073	36ME0206	Prehistoric	-80.42689 41.2949
36LR0159	Prehistoric	-80.2854 41.02355	36ME0211	Prehistoric	-80.24844 41.32143
36LR0161	Prehistoric	-80.3173 41.1162	36ME0212	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.24677 41.3235
36LR0162	Prehistoric	-80.3127 41.11766	36ME0213	Prehistoric	-80.23628 41.33796
36LR0174	Prehistoric	-80.2154 41.09071	36ME0214	Prehistoric	-80.45728 41.19975
36LR0179	Prehistoric	-80.2742 41.06992	36ME0215	Prehistoric	-80.44541 41.29707
36LR0182	Prehistoric	-80.2265 41.10032	36ME0216	Prehistoric	-80.35707 41.46183
36LR0191	Prehistoric	-80.2363 40.97566	36ME0217	Prehistoric	-80.35262 41.46183
36LR0192	Prehistoric	-80.2404 40.99343	36ME0218	Prehistoric	-80.11158 41.2238
36LR0198	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.3946 41.01703	36ME0220	Prehistoric	-80.21706 41.36785
36LR0239	Prehistoric	-80.3653 41.07862	36ME0223	Prehistoric	-80.1943 41.27926
36LR0240	Prehistoric	-80.3671 41.07816	36ME0224	Prehistoric	-80.17368 41.27854
36LR0241	Prehistoric	-80.3648 41.07681	36ME0225	Prehistoric	-80.17166 41.27858
36LR0243	Prehistoric	-80.4509 41.07754	36ME0235	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.40915 41.15105
36LR0244	Prehistoric	-80.3735 41.07923	36ME0236	Prehistoric	-80.4491 41.23884
36LR0250	Prehistoric	-80.347 41.09852	36ME0237	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.4497 41.25106
36LR0251	Prehistoric	-80.3431 41.11347	36ME0238	Prehistoric	-80.18382 41.20504
36LR0257	Prehistoric	-80.3741 41.05253	36ME0242	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.39919 41.42273
36LR0258	Prehistoric	-80.3747 41.0522	36ME0248	Prehistoric	-80.37674 41.36755
36LR0282	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.3641 41.08141	36ME0249	Prehistoric	-80.35279 41.38161
36LR0283	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.3662 41.08093	36ME0251	Prehistoric	-80.27095 41.16138
36LR0285	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.3036 40.98405	36ME0252	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.2641 41.16176
36LR0287	Prehistoric	-80.3699 40.98622	36ME0257	Prehistoric	-80.21374 41.27206
36ME0004	Prehistoric	-80.2845 41.2154	36ME0258	Prehistoric	-80.20813 41.27122
36ME0005	Prehistoric	-80.2822 41.21204			
Watershed 23-Appalachian Plateaus-High Plateau:					
36EL0003	Prehistoric	-78.7792 41.31889	36EL0091	Prehistoric	-78.70715 41.41244
36EL0004	Prehistoric	-78.7718 41.32318	36EL0096	Prehistoric	-78.83128 41.38521
36EL0005	Prehistoric	-78.7964 41.33564	36EL0097	Prehistoric	-78.75878 41.36155

Table A-2. Region 2 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36EL0006	Prehistoric	-78.7185 41.40495	36EL0098	Prehistoric	-78.76388 41.3595
36EL0007	Prehistoric	-78.8286 41.33602	36EL0099	Prehistoric	-78.85429 41.33887
36EL0009	Prehistoric	-78.7513 41.38604	36EL0100	Prehistoric	-78.90359 41.48726
36EL0010	Prehistoric	-78.7504 41.38152	36EL0101	Prehistoric	-78.73078 41.41912
36EL0011	Prehistoric	-78.8294 41.3806	36EL0103	Prehistoric	-78.74823 41.56421
36EL0014	Prehistoric	-78.6848 41.39178	36EL0104	Prehistoric	-78.74397 41.56896
36EL0018	Prehistoric	-78.8828 41.40009	36EL0106	Prehistoric	-78.75852 41.35515
36EL0019	Prehistoric	-78.5451 41.56648	36EL0107	Prehistoric	-78.80656 41.33285
36EL0020	Prehistoric	-78.5865 41.55497	36EL0108	Prehistoric	-78.69243 41.39964
36EL0022	Prehistoric	-78.7308 41.38973	36EL0110	Prehistoric	-78.92238 41.41664
36EL0023	Prehistoric	-78.7285 41.38975	36EL0119	Prehistoric	-78.64715 41.46896
36EL0030	Prehistoric	-78.6397 41.41871	36EL0206	Prehistoric	-78.78948 41.34979
36EL0034	Prehistoric	-78.6851 41.55563	36EL0207	Prehistoric	-78.7673 41.34194
36EL0035	Prehistoric	-78.6645 41.43185	36EL0208	Prehistoric	-78.76812 41.34204
36EL0044	Prehistoric	-78.9328 41.40156	36FO0040	Prehistoric	-78.96397 41.49052
36EL0049	Prehistoric	-78.7281 41.38861	36FO0041	Prehistoric	-78.96279 41.48805
36EL0066	Prehistoric	-78.8133 41.34492	36FO0042	Prehistoric	-78.9994 41.49581
36EL0070	Prehistoric	-78.7688 41.3312	36FO0043	Prehistoric	-78.98721 41.49594
36EL0071	Prehistoric	-78.7641 41.3316	36FO0044	Prehistoric	-78.98364 41.48736
36EL0072	Prehistoric	-78.7603 41.32968	36FO0045	Prehistoric	-78.97177 41.48251
36EL0073	Prehistoric	-78.7846 41.31244	36FO0046	Prehistoric	-78.96919 41.48239
36EL0074	Prehistoric	-78.7848 41.31151	36FO0050	Prehistoric	-79.02497 41.54519
36EL0077	Prehistoric	-78.9042 41.41866	36FO0051	Prehistoric	-79.01403 41.4865
36EL0078	Prehistoric	-78.9025 41.41527	36FO0052	Prehistoric	-79.00031 41.48641
36EL0081	Prehistoric	-78.9065 41.40589	36FO0053	Prehistoric	-79.01918 41.47994
36EL0083	Prehistoric	-78.8621 41.56512	36FO0061	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.02354 41.46848
36EL0084	Prehistoric	-78.8528 41.56318	36FO0063	Prehistoric	-79.01438 41.46658
36EL0089	Prehistoric	-78.7999 41.39424	36FO0106	Prehistoric	-79.00007 41.49431
36EL0090	Prehistoric	-78.7264 41.42259	36FO0177	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.98044 41.4951
Watershed 27-Appalachian Plateaus-High Plateau:					
36VE0004	Prehistoric	-79.8477 41.3244	36VE0131	Prehistoric	-79.84819 41.31468
36VE0005	Prehistoric	-79.8403 41.3268	36VE0132	Prehistoric	-79.87902 41.3351
36VE0006	Prehistoric	-79.8888 41.31601	36VE0133	Prehistoric	-79.84548 41.29165
36VE0007	Prehistoric	-79.84 41.30766	36VE0155	Prehistoric	-79.85077 41.29015
36VE0008	Prehistoric	-79.8442 41.33478	36VE0156	Prehistoric	-79.84287 41.32606
36VE0009	Prehistoric	-79.8397 41.33477	36VE0189	Prehistoric	-79.70681 41.3526
36VE0024	Prehistoric	-79.9453 41.31135	36VE0190	Prehistoric	-79.74045 41.37325
36VE0026	Prehistoric	-79.8228 41.3301	36VE0200	Prehistoric	-79.89557 41.34358
36VE0027	Prehistoric	-79.8155 41.35592	36VE0215	Prehistoric	-79.8501 41.32348
36VE0035	Prehistoric	-79.9027 41.3696	36VE0221	Prehistoric	-79.85677 41.31435
36VE0051	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.9001 41.35613	36VE0222	Prehistoric	-79.8477 41.30665
36VE0096	Prehistoric	-79.8167 41.29016	36VE0223	Prehistoric	-79.86621 41.2764
36VE0097	Prehistoric	-79.8128 41.30194	36VE0227	Prehistoric	-79.94878 41.29261
36VE0098	Prehistoric	-79.812 41.29706	36VE0228	Prehistoric	-79.91553 41.29307
36VE0099	Prehistoric	-79.8516 41.31453	36VE0229	Prehistoric	-79.91691 41.295
36VE0100	Prehistoric	-79.8344 41.3263	36VE0231	Prehistoric	-79.8492 41.28467
36VE0101	Prehistoric	-79.8532 41.32255	36VE0232	Prehistoric	-79.82721 41.28612
36VE0102	Prehistoric	-79.8398 41.33355	36VE0239	Prehistoric	-79.84925 41.32205
36VE0103	Prehistoric	-79.837 41.33745	36VE0270	Prehistoric	-79.87525 41.36678
36VE0104	Prehistoric	-79.842 41.34208	36VE0273	Prehistoric	-79.94864 41.31427
36VE0105	Prehistoric	-79.8424 41.34085	36VE0275	Prehistoric	-79.90955 41.36001
36VE0107	Prehistoric	-79.7717 41.3428	36VE0279	Prehistoric	-79.90076 41.3622

Table A-2. Region 2 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36VE0108	Prehistoric	-79.7719 41.33642	36VE0280	Prehistoric	-79.90099 41.36095
36VE0109	Prehistoric	-79.7723 41.33357	36VE0281	Prehistoric	-79.90053 41.35965
36VE0110	Prehistoric	-79.8073 41.35217	36VE0282	Prehistoric	-79.89948 41.35895
36VE0111	Prehistoric	-79.8577 41.35457	36VE0283	Prehistoric	-79.90104 41.35753
36VE0112	Prehistoric	-79.8576 41.35331	36VE0285	Prehistoric	-79.95207 41.38938
36VE0113	Prehistoric	-79.8583 41.3513	36VE0286	Prehistoric	-79.94071 41.38897
36VE0114	Prehistoric	-79.8786 41.34737	36VE0287	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.93796 41.38594
36VE0115	Prehistoric	-79.8771 41.34222	36VE0288	Prehistoric	-79.93647 41.38711
36VE0116	Prehistoric	-79.889 41.33314	36VE0291	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.94203 41.38121
36VE0118	Prehistoric	-79.9391 41.2941	36VE0292	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.95535 41.39506
36VE0119	Prehistoric	-79.9504 41.2919	36VE0296	Prehistoric	-79.91011 41.36384
36VE0120	Prehistoric	-79.953 41.29185	36VE0301	Prehistoric	-79.78066 41.32725
36VE0122	Prehistoric	-79.9543 41.34255	36VE0302	Prehistoric	-79.78919 41.3276
36VE0124	Prehistoric	-79.9127 41.36232	36VE0303	Prehistoric	-79.80871 41.29129
36VE0127	Prehistoric	-79.8271 41.31174			
Watershed 27-Appalachian Plateaus-Northwestern Glaciated Plateau:					
36ME0001	Prehistoric	-80.0631 41.33245	36ME0210	Prehistoric	-80.16032 41.43565
36ME0002	Prehistoric	-80.0563 41.33592	36ME0221	Prehistoric	-80.11143 41.40577
36ME0003	Prehistoric	-80.0556 41.32177	36ME0222	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.11057 41.40776
36ME0058	Prehistoric	-80.0042 41.33598	36ME0228	Prehistoric	-80.09921 41.33165
36ME0104	Prehistoric	-80.116 41.41026	36ME0244	Prehistoric	-80.10387 41.39363
36ME0105	Prehistoric	-80.1138 41.40603	36ME0245	Prehistoric	-80.11011 41.39907
36ME0106	Prehistoric	-80.119 41.40338	36ME0246	Prehistoric	-80.10974 41.39864
36ME0127	Prehistoric	-80.1391 41.42103	36ME0247	Prehistoric	-80.13132 41.41011
36ME0128	Prehistoric	-80.1422 41.42242	36ME0250	Prehistoric	-80.031 41.40008
36ME0149	Prehistoric	-80.1945 41.46511	36VE0010	Prehistoric	-79.97162 41.32878
36ME0177	Prehistoric	-80.0962 41.37479	36VE0121	Prehistoric	-79.97595 41.33804
36ME0191	Prehistoric	-80.1583 41.43026	36VE0123	Prehistoric	-79.97536 41.35865
36ME0195	Prehistoric	-80.1177 41.41173	36VE0298	Prehistoric	-79.97513 41.35759
36ME0199	Prehistoric	-80.0912 41.38909			
Watershed 29-Appalachian Plateaus-High Plateau:					
36CL0023	Prehistoric	-79.2097 41.33177	36EL0136	Prehistoric	-79.06754 41.38383
36CL0139	Prehistoric	-79.2122 41.32067	36EL0138	Prehistoric	-79.07503 41.38105
36CL0140	Prehistoric	-79.2336 41.31685	36EL0139	Prehistoric	-78.98253 41.38689
36CL0141	Prehistoric	-79.2272 41.3209	36EL0140	Prehistoric	-78.96336 41.38198
36CL0142	Prehistoric	-79.2217 41.3197	36EL0141	Prehistoric	-78.96394 41.38356
36CL0143	Prehistoric	-79.2335 41.31791	36EL0142	Prehistoric	-78.96095 41.38562
36EL0008	Prehistoric	-78.8649 41.3891	36EL0143	Prehistoric	-78.95978 41.38554
36EL0012	Prehistoric	-78.8221 41.36701	36EL0144	Prehistoric	-78.96068 41.38589
36EL0015	Prehistoric	-78.9963 41.36685	36EL0203	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.00677 41.35974
36EL0021	Prehistoric	-78.6814 41.47788	36EL0204	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.07091 41.35493
36EL0028	Prehistoric	-78.8349 41.38137	36EL0209	Prehistoric	-79.01299 41.43606
36EL0032	Prehistoric	-78.9901 41.40454	36EL0216	Prehistoric	-79.0039 41.35938
36EL0033	Prehistoric	-78.989 41.39927	36EL0221	Prehistoric	-78.99221 41.36891
36EL0075	Prehistoric	-78.9479 41.38602	36EL0222	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.00222 41.36029
36EL0076	Prehistoric	-78.9494 41.38837	36EL0232	Prehistoric	-78.9968 41.39931
36EL0079	Prehistoric	-78.9263 41.4043	36EL0235	Prehistoric	-78.97054 41.39531
36EL0080	Prehistoric	-78.8808 41.39257	36EL0237	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.97082 41.39669
36EL0082	Prehistoric	-78.8764 41.39807	36EL0246	Prehistoric	-79.01772 41.42579
36EL0085	Prehistoric	-79.0189 41.43833	36EL0247	Prehistoric	-79.03774 41.37007
36EL0086	Prehistoric	-79.0516 41.42198	36FO0068	Prehistoric	-79.14211 41.34578

Table A-2. Region 2 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36EL0087	Prehistoric	-79.0914 41.38078	36FO0117	Prehistoric	-79.11171 41.33156
36EL0088	Prehistoric	-78.998 41.36739	36FO0145	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.0979 41.4748
36EL0095	Prehistoric	-78.8215 41.37697	36FO0157	Prehistoric	-79.07442 41.48181
36EL0109	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.0586 41.3829	36JE0023	Prehistoric	-78.96477 41.36854
36EL0116	Prehistoric	-79.0712 41.35626	36JE0024	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.97189 41.37461
36EL0117	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.0727 41.35422	36JE0068	Prehistoric	-79.10332 41.3329
36EL0121	Prehistoric	-78.9364 41.38405	36JE0102	Prehistoric	-79.20428 41.31809
36EL0122	Prehistoric	-79.0063 41.44345	36JE0103	Prehistoric	-78.97794 41.34191
36EL0123	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.0532 41.37248	36JE0104	Prehistoric	-78.9625 41.36247
36EL0124	Prehistoric	-79.044 41.37359	36JE0120	Prehistoric	-78.981 41.341
36EL0125	Prehistoric	-79.0435 41.3727	36JE0121	Prehistoric	-78.97857 41.33563
36EL0126	Prehistoric	-79.0432 41.38174	36JE0122	Prehistoric	-78.96576 41.33194
36EL0127	Prehistoric & Historic	-79.0443 41.38133	36JE0125	Prehistoric	-78.97538 41.3211
36EL0128	Prehistoric	-79.0522 41.37423	36JE0127	Prehistoric	-79.01664 41.31802
36EL0129	Prehistoric	-79.0584 41.38204	36JE0128	Prehistoric	-78.96184 41.31792
36EL0130	Prehistoric	-79.0618 41.37917	36JE0132	Prehistoric	-78.99358 41.35856
36EL0131	Prehistoric	-79.0641 41.36573	36JE0134	Prehistoric	-79.01066 41.35052
36EL0133	Prehistoric	-79.0601 41.36947	36JE0138	Prehistoric	-79.13069 41.32942
36EL0134	Prehistoric	-79.0647 41.38509	36JE0146	Prehistoric	-79.07433 41.35192
36EL0135	Prehistoric	-79.0643 41.38516			
Watershed 35-Appalachian Plateaus-Northwestern Glaciated Plateau:					
36BT0004	Prehistoric	-80.1387 41.02496	36LR0085	Prehistoric	-80.1768 41.08145
36BT0005	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.1291 41.03369	36LR0095	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.14276 41.0355
36BT0007	Prehistoric	-80.0552 41.10704	36LR0152	Prehistoric	-80.15394 41.08835
36BT0025	Prehistoric	-80.07 41.06812	36LR0153	Prehistoric	-80.16631 41.09085
36BT0082	Prehistoric	-80.0874 41.06094	36LR0154	Prehistoric	-80.17438 41.08674
36BT0083	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.0899 41.06224	36LR0155	Prehistoric	-80.17655 41.09572
36BT0099	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.0951 41.04263	36LR0160	Prehistoric	-80.17136 40.98139
36BT0100	Prehistoric	-80.0971 41.04223	36LR0167	Prehistoric	-80.16383 41.02922
36BT0102	Prehistoric	-80.1027 41.04991	36LR0170	Prehistoric	-80.18094 40.99214
36BT0120	Prehistoric	-80.0024 41.15773	36LR0171	Prehistoric	-80.18181 40.99079
36BT0124	Prehistoric	-80.0866 41.04608	36LR0172	Prehistoric	-80.17301 40.98866
36BT0125	Prehistoric	-80.0475 41.05217	36LR0183	Prehistoric	-80.16916 41.06776
36BT0128	Prehistoric	-80.0557 41.11089	36LR0184	Prehistoric	-80.14815 41.03073
36BT0129	Prehistoric	-80.0853 41.04398	36LR0185	Prehistoric	-80.15192 41.03228
36BT0130	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.107 41.04245	36LR0189	Prehistoric	-80.24735 40.93071
36BT0131	Prehistoric	-80.0561 41.06501	36LR0190	Prehistoric	-80.24475 40.94939
36BT0132	Prehistoric	-80.0343 41.12797	36LR0217	Prehistoric	-80.1323 41.0337
36BT0153	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.0679 41.08861	36LR0218	Prehistoric	-80.13389 41.03367
36BT0168	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.0742 41.07808	36LR0219	Prehistoric	-80.13463 41.03328
36BT0171	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.1117 41.04055	36LR0220	Prehistoric	-80.13352 41.03283
36BT0230	Prehistoric	-80.1061 41.04705	36LR0221	Prehistoric	-80.13351 41.0313
36BT0236	Prehistoric	-80.0634 41.08499	36LR0222	Prehistoric	-80.13746 41.03405
36BT0238	Prehistoric	-80.0656 41.06898	36LR0223	Prehistoric	-80.13677 41.03302
36BT0240	Prehistoric	-80.0422 41.09021	36LR0224	Prehistoric	-80.13663 41.02986
36BT0255	Prehistoric	-80.0331 41.13284	36LR0225	Prehistoric	-80.13763 41.03128
36BT0256	Prehistoric	-80.0353 41.13141	36LR0226	Prehistoric	-80.13437 41.03473
36BT0260	Prehistoric	-80.1256 41.03649	36LR0227	Prehistoric	-80.13515 41.03041
36BT0320	Prehistoric	-80.0997 41.04277	36LR0229	Prehistoric	-80.14203 41.03386
36BT0328	Prehistoric	-80.0977 41.04293	36LR0242	Prehistoric	-80.18459 40.99074
36BT0339	Prehistoric	-80.108 41.03567	36LR0254	Prehistoric	-80.18502 40.99675
36BT0340	Prehistoric	-80.1097 41.03687	36LR0255	Prehistoric	-80.18606 40.99568

Table A-2. Region 2 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36BT0343	Prehistoric	-80.1333 41.03027	36LR0284	Prehistoric	-80.18515 40.99187
36BT0344	Prehistoric	-80.1318 41.02981	36ME0034	Prehistoric	-80.13196 41.12857
36BT0345	Prehistoric	-80.1293 41.0308	36ME0041	Prehistoric	-80.06794 41.10892
36BT0346	Prehistoric	-80.1326 41.03004	36ME0042	Prehistoric	-80.11708 41.13065
36BT0347	Prehistoric	-80.1335 41.02901	36ME0044	Prehistoric	-80.08298 41.11654
36BT0348	Prehistoric	-80.1324 41.02912	36ME0123	Prehistoric	-80.13884 41.18909
36BT0349	Prehistoric	-80.1318 41.03205	36ME0136	Prehistoric	-80.05307 41.16136
36BT0350	Prehistoric	-80.1344 41.02781	36ME0137	Prehistoric	-80.05527 41.15832
36BT0351	Prehistoric	-80.1342 41.02736	36ME0139	Prehistoric	-80.06102 41.14471
36BT0352	Prehistoric	-80.1321 41.02678	36ME0140	Prehistoric	-80.0186 41.17244
36BT0353	Prehistoric	-80.1329 41.02579	36ME0141	Prehistoric	-80.06254 41.17212
36BT0354	Prehistoric	-80.1338 41.02642	36ME0142	Prehistoric	-80.05368 41.15835
36BT0355	Prehistoric	-80.1339 41.02546	36ME0155	Prehistoric	-80.13826 41.12481
36BT0356	Prehistoric	-80.1345 41.0255	36ME0156	Prehistoric	-80.068 41.16956
36BT0357	Prehistoric	-80.1352 41.02646	36ME0157	Prehistoric	-80.07582 41.14834
36BT0358	Prehistoric	-80.1312 41.03048	36ME0159	Prehistoric	-80.08484 41.17036
36BT0359	Prehistoric	-80.1318 41.03112	36ME0207	Prehistoric	-80.09114 41.12251
36BT0414	Prehistoric	-80.1097 41.04109	36ME0208	Prehistoric	-80.07318 41.108
36LR0080	Prehistoric	-80.152 41.03048	36ME0209	Prehistoric	-80.11853 41.13212
Watershed 44-Appalachian Plateaus-Northwestern Glaciated Plateau:					
36BV0077	Prehistoric	-80.4082 40.81938	36LR0130	Prehistoric	-80.34263 40.90274
36BV0199	Prehistoric	-80.406 40.82039	36LR0131	Prehistoric	-80.31628 40.90069
36BV0200	Prehistoric	-80.4128 40.83415	36LR0132	Prehistoric	-80.31394 40.89801
36BV0243	Prehistoric	-80.4195 40.81784	36LR0133	Prehistoric	-80.31251 40.90089
36LR0001	Prehistoric	-80.3718 40.92996	36LR0134	Prehistoric	-80.30674 40.8994
36LR0003	Prehistoric	-80.4439 41.01646	36LR0135	Prehistoric	-80.30602 40.90046
36LR0004	Prehistoric	-80.4323 40.95412	36LR0145	Prehistoric	-80.28564 40.9202
36LR0005	Prehistoric	-80.37 40.92132	36LR0146	Prehistoric	-80.38527 40.91348
36LR0008	Prehistoric	-80.3638 40.91578	36LR0147	Prehistoric	-80.38576 40.91914
36LR0011	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.4293 41.01097	36LR0148	Prehistoric	-80.38617 40.92037
36LR0012	Prehistoric	-80.5096 41.0324	36LR0150	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.39483 40.98372
36LR0017	Prehistoric	-80.4111 41.00089	36LR0151	Prehistoric	-80.39245 40.87306
36LR0018	Prehistoric	-80.4055 40.94619	36LR0163	Prehistoric	-80.43485 41.02416
36LR0021	Prehistoric	-80.4502 41.01963	36LR0164	Prehistoric	-80.32717 40.94047
36LR0035	Prehistoric	-80.4282 41.0176	36LR0165	Prehistoric	-80.44009 41.01711
36LR0036	Prehistoric	-80.4943 41.0239	36LR0168	Prehistoric	-80.43543 41.02252
36LR0037	Prehistoric	-80.4523 41.02021	36LR0173	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.46643 40.93309
36LR0038	Prehistoric	-80.4728 41.02112	36LR0175	Prehistoric	-80.41338 40.92149
36LR0039	Prehistoric	-80.4883 41.04153	36LR0176	Prehistoric	-80.41534 40.92598
36LR0045	Prehistoric	-80.4207 41.0166	36LR0180	Prehistoric	-80.39896 40.85707
36LR0046	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.4535 41.02364	36LR0181	Prehistoric	-80.40107 40.85908
36LR0047	Prehistoric	-80.3834 40.97055	36LR0186	Prehistoric	-80.45976 41.03563
36LR0048	Prehistoric	-80.3767 40.9364	36LR0193	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.46283 41.00567
36LR0070	Prehistoric	-80.46 41.02432	36LR0194	Prehistoric	-80.39044 40.8641
36LR0071	Prehistoric	-80.4907 41.02217	36LR0195	Prehistoric	-80.38958 40.85934
36LR0072	Prehistoric	-80.4812 41.01965	36LR0196	Prehistoric	-80.48849 40.98537
36LR0074	Prehistoric	-80.4061 40.99422	36LR0197	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.46929 40.97897
36LR0075	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.4181 40.9989	36LR0199	Prehistoric	-80.4677 40.88824
36LR0076	Prehistoric	-80.376 40.92718	36LR0200	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.46428 40.88799
36LR0077	Prehistoric	-80.4627 41.02069	36LR0201	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.45871 40.88794
36LR0078	Prehistoric	-80.5184 41.03305	36LR0202	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.44456 40.88748
36LR0081	Prehistoric	-80.35 40.90533	36LR0203	Prehistoric	-80.44088 40.88865

Table A-2. Region 2 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LR0106	Prehistoric	-80.4965 40.88505	36LR0204	Prehistoric	-80.44204 40.88766
36LR0107	Prehistoric	-80.4943 40.88519	36LR0205	Prehistoric	-80.42329 40.88805
36LR0108	Prehistoric	-80.4918 40.88535	36LR0206	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.50608 40.8876
36LR0109	Prehistoric	-80.4707 40.88857	36LR0207	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.50035 40.88635
36LR0110	Prehistoric	-80.4604 40.8881	36LR0208	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.5111 40.88466
36LR0111	Prehistoric	-80.45 40.88838	36LR0209	Prehistoric	-80.49872 40.88617
36LR0112	Prehistoric	-80.4462 40.88837	36LR0210	Prehistoric	-80.49518 40.8857
36LR0113	Prehistoric	-80.4215 40.88686	36LR0211	Prehistoric	-80.34586 40.90219
36LR0114	Prehistoric	-80.4087 40.88776	36LR0214	Prehistoric	-80.51005 40.88791
36LR0115	Prehistoric	-80.407 40.88849	36LR0215	Prehistoric	-80.50409 40.88541
36LR0116	Prehistoric	-80.4054 40.88934	36LR0216	Prehistoric	-80.4467 40.88776
36LR0117	Prehistoric	-80.3908 40.89431	36LR0228	Prehistoric	-80.41523 40.99676
36LR0118	Prehistoric	-80.3869 40.89365	36LR0230	Prehistoric	-80.3956 40.89009
36LR0119	Prehistoric	-80.3856 40.89257	36LR0231	Prehistoric	-80.3953 40.89051
36LR0120	Prehistoric	-80.3846 40.89381	36LR0232	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.39413 40.89097
36LR0121	Prehistoric	-80.3835 40.89396	36LR0233	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.39377 40.89124
36LR0122	Prehistoric	-80.3752 40.89501	36LR0234	Prehistoric	-80.39335 40.89123
36LR0123	Prehistoric	-80.3718 40.89522	36LR0235	Prehistoric	-80.39136 40.89126
36LR0124	Prehistoric	-80.3687 40.89539	36LR0236	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.38946 40.89143
36LR0125	Prehistoric	-80.3656 40.89555	36LR0237	Prehistoric	-80.38619 40.8922
36LR0126	Prehistoric	-80.3636 40.89587	36LR0238	Prehistoric & Historic	-80.38337 40.89458
36LR0127	Prehistoric	-80.3616 40.89649	36LR0247	Prehistoric	-80.46159 40.88842
36LR0128	Prehistoric	-80.3582 40.89652	36LR0249	Prehistoric	-80.3699 40.89049
36LR0129	Prehistoric	-80.353 40.89728	36LR0286	Prehistoric	-80.44381 41.01448

Table A-3. Region 3 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates		Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	
Watershed 2-Central Lowlands-Eastern Lake:							
36ER0003	Prehistoric	-80.44006	41.94569	36ER0135	Prehistoric	-80.25094	42.03166
36ER0004	Prehistoric	-80.40653	41.97134	36ER0136	Prehistoric	-80.24616	42.02635
36ER0006	Prehistoric	-79.99387	42.11765	36ER0137	Prehistoric	-80.16853	42.10429
36ER0008	Prehistoric	-79.78185	42.24882	36ER0138	Prehistoric	-80.24582	42.02748
36ER0009	Prehistoric	-80.31356	42.04149	36ER0139	Prehistoric	-80.24557	42.02668
36ER0010	Prehistoric	-79.76286	42.23284	36ER0140	Prehistoric	-80.24497	42.0263
36ER0011	Prehistoric	-80.46005	41.96313	36ER0141	Prehistoric	-80.24419	42.02608
36ER0013	Prehistoric	-80.03961	42.12292	36ER0143	Prehistoric	-80.36606	42.02511
36ER0014	Prehistoric	-80.114	42.1085	36ER0146	Prehistoric	-80.23639	42.06911
36ER0018	Prehistoric	-80.01157	42.14261	36ER0147	Prehistoric	-80.21605	42.05716
36ER0052	Prehistoric	-80.27662	42.04399	36ER0150	Prehistoric	-80.27601	42.03836
36ER0053	Prehistoric	-80.36804	42.02083	36ER0151	Prehistoric	-80.16287	42.0787
36ER0054	Prehistoric	-80.36121	42.02303	36ER0152	Prehistoric	-79.89384	42.19806
36ER0055	Prehistoric	-80.35651	42.0262	36ER0153	Prehistoric	-80.1466	42.11395
36ER0056	Prehistoric	-80.35432	42.01881	36ER0154	Prehistoric	-80.14651	42.11276
36ER0057	Prehistoric	-80.37718	42.01667	36ER0155	Prehistoric	-80.145	42.11289
36ER0058	Prehistoric	-80.30333	42.0361	36ER0156	Prehistoric	-80.14515	42.11092
36ER0061	Prehistoric	-80.20031	42.07977	36ER0157	Prehistoric	-80.14472	42.11045
36ER0062	Prehistoric	-80.1942	42.08075	36ER0160	Prehistoric	-80.37402	42.02363
36ER0063	Prehistoric	-79.91357	42.21128	36ER0161	Prehistoric	-80.37465	42.02321

Table A-4. Region 4 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
Watershed 25-Ridge and Valley-Appalachian Mountain:					
36LY0172	Prehistoric	-77.21906 41.15943			
Watershed 40-Ridge and Valley-Appalachian Mountain:					
36CE0001	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.91832 40.87824	36CE0354	Prehistoric	-77.88205 40.85687
36CE0002	Prehistoric	-77.80882 40.85925	36CE0355	Prehistoric	-77.88174 40.8633
36CE0003	Prehistoric	-77.83316 40.82006	36CE0356	Prehistoric	-77.60385 41.06037
36CE0004	Prehistoric	-77.81006 40.8595	36CE0357	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.71866 40.8781
36CE0005	Prehistoric	-78.01493 40.82883	36CE0358	Prehistoric	-77.71739 40.87562
36CE0006	Prehistoric	-78.01638 40.82795	36CE0359	Prehistoric	-77.91622 40.85262
36CE0007	Prehistoric	-78.0205 40.82647	36CE0361	Prehistoric	-77.76731 40.95192
36CE0008	Prehistoric	-78.02731 40.82349	36CE0362	Prehistoric	-77.79531 40.90369
36CE0009	Prehistoric	-77.83901 40.80739	36CE0363	Prehistoric	-77.64054 40.99393
36CE0010	Prehistoric	-77.98495 40.84294	36CE0365	Prehistoric	-77.88733 40.86512
36CE0011	Prehistoric	-78.03044 40.81845	36CE0366	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.88723 40.86752
36CE0012	Prehistoric	-78.07043 40.78586	36CE0369	Prehistoric	-77.87702 40.85889
36CE0013	Prehistoric	-77.9351 40.86608	36CE0370	Prehistoric	-77.87805 40.86223
36CE0014	Prehistoric	-77.93394 40.86789	36CE0371	Prehistoric	-77.87553 40.86063
36CE0015	Prehistoric	-77.94999 40.85851	36CE0372	Prehistoric	-77.87765 40.85887
36CE0016	Prehistoric	-77.95756 40.85494	36CE0373	Prehistoric	-77.87898 40.85728
36CE0017	Prehistoric	-77.96101 40.85381	36CE0375	Prehistoric	-77.83981 40.85063
36CE0018	Prehistoric	-77.96707 40.85027	36CE0377	Prehistoric	-77.66511 41.01944
36CE0024	Prehistoric	-77.5835 41.0651	36CE0378	Prehistoric	-77.66208 41.01816
36CE0026	Prehistoric	-77.5789 41.06394	36CE0379	Prehistoric	-77.66048 41.02039
36CE0027	Prehistoric	-78.02165 40.82588	36CE0380	Prehistoric	-77.67057 41.01411
36CE0028	Prehistoric	-77.87525 40.74367	36CE0381	Prehistoric	-77.67821 41.00312
36CE0029	Prehistoric	-77.82063 40.84192	36CE0382	Prehistoric	-77.68295 41.00207
36CE0030	Prehistoric	-77.81863 40.83485	36CE0383	Prehistoric	-77.96808 40.84927
36CE0031	Prehistoric	-77.61918 41.04077	36CE0384	Prehistoric	-77.68924 40.99921
36CE0032	Prehistoric	-77.59595 41.05982	36CE0385	Prehistoric	-77.83843 40.92283
36CE0033	Prehistoric	-77.57523 41.06237	36CE0387	Prehistoric	-78.04623 40.80544
36CE0034	Prehistoric	-77.86674 40.90889	36CE0388	Prehistoric	-78.06351 40.79147
36CE0035	Prehistoric	-77.82826 40.92736	36CE0390	Prehistoric	-77.88526 40.86946
36CE0036	Prehistoric	-78.02196 40.82527	36CE0392	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.95804 40.82759
36CE0037	Prehistoric	-78.02298 40.8243	36CE0393	Prehistoric	-78.07944 40.78235
36CE0038	Prehistoric	-77.78906 40.94232	36CE0399	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.11084 40.7592
36CE0039	Prehistoric	-78.02386 40.82485	36CE0402	Prehistoric	-77.80726 40.8414
36CE0040	Prehistoric	-78.02311 40.82546	36CE0403	Prehistoric	-77.78683 40.8548
36CE0041	Prehistoric	-78.023 40.82639	36CE0404	Prehistoric	-77.78379 40.86196
36CE0042	Prehistoric	-78.02445 40.82576	36CE0405	Prehistoric	-77.76246 40.88158
36CE0043	Prehistoric	-78.00212 40.8367	36CE0406	Prehistoric	-77.76051 40.88131
36CE0044	Prehistoric	-77.89257 40.89558	36CE0407	Prehistoric	-77.75898 40.88104
36CE0045	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.9789 40.84495	36CE0408	Prehistoric	-77.75036 40.88288
36CE0046	Prehistoric	-78.06952 40.78787	36CE0416	Prehistoric	-77.83281 40.82145
36CE0047	Prehistoric	-77.99698 40.84017	36CE0418	Prehistoric	-77.79542 40.78143
36CE0048	Prehistoric	-77.99627 40.84102	36CE0419	Prehistoric	-77.81995 40.83613
36CE0049	Prehistoric	-77.99439 40.84188	36CE0420	Prehistoric	-77.8184 40.83612
36CE0050	Prehistoric	-77.99307 40.84118	36CE0421	Prehistoric	-77.81718 40.83559
36CE0051	Prehistoric	-77.98968 40.8409	36CE0422	Prehistoric	-77.80586 40.84158
36CE0052	Prehistoric	-77.99347 40.83928	36CE0423	Prehistoric	-77.83593 40.83616
36CE0053	Prehistoric	-77.97118 40.84825	36CE0424	Prehistoric	-77.82532 40.84371
36CE0054	Prehistoric	-77.96926 40.84798	36CE0425	Prehistoric	-77.82209 40.84373

Table A-4. Region 4 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36CE0055	Prehistoric	-78.01009 40.83238	36CE0426	Prehistoric	-77.82015 40.84335
36CE0058	Prehistoric	-77.84155 40.767	36CE0427	Prehistoric	-77.81853 40.84556
36CE0059	Prehistoric	-77.831 40.77161	36CE0428	Prehistoric	-77.82234 40.84248
36CE0060	Prehistoric	-77.79478 40.79455	36CE0429	Prehistoric	-77.83035 40.83865
36CE0061	Prehistoric	-77.76114 40.7955	36CE0430	Prehistoric	-77.81615 40.84562
36CE0062	Prehistoric	-77.81592 40.80265	36CE0431	Prehistoric	-77.81295 40.84753
36CE0063	Prehistoric	-77.82152 40.8097	36CE0432	Prehistoric	-77.77945 40.87219
36CE0064	Prehistoric	-77.819 40.81772	36CE0433	Prehistoric	-77.77908 40.8735
36CE0065	Prehistoric	-77.83382 40.81539	36CE0434	Prehistoric	-77.82347 40.84123
36CE0066	Prehistoric	-77.8994 40.8871	36CE0435	Prehistoric	-77.75534 40.87447
36CE0067	Prehistoric	-77.88768 40.89695	36CE0436	Prehistoric	-77.75657 40.87388
36CE0068	Prehistoric	-77.87276 40.90478	36CE0437	Prehistoric	-77.75638 40.87309
36CE0069	Prehistoric	-77.85869 40.91294	36CE0441	Prehistoric	-78.0665 40.78979
36CE0070	Prehistoric	-77.86293 40.91127	36CE0442	Prehistoric	-78.06713 40.78932
36CE0071	Prehistoric	-77.7832 40.943	36CE0443	Prehistoric	-78.03934 40.81113
36CE0072	Prehistoric	-77.77097 40.94935	36CE0444	Prehistoric	-78.03843 40.81299
36CE0073	Prehistoric	-77.70758 40.98474	36CE0445	Prehistoric	-78.02098 40.8277
36CE0074	Prehistoric	-77.69511 40.99284	36CE0446	Prehistoric	-78.02086 40.82854
36CE0075	Prehistoric	-77.68704 40.99762	36CE0448	Prehistoric	-78.03955 40.80996
36CE0076	Prehistoric	-77.65531 41.02552	36CE0450	Prehistoric	-78.04444 40.80816
36CE0077	Prehistoric	-77.66083 41.02486	36CE0452	Prehistoric	-78.07309 40.78555
36CE0078	Prehistoric	-77.64572 41.0244	36CE0454	Prehistoric	-78.12287 40.75052
36CE0079	Prehistoric	-77.63856 41.02184	36CE0455	Prehistoric	-78.07309 40.78619
36CE0080	Prehistoric	-77.64763 41.01887	36CE0458	Prehistoric	-77.96709 40.83138
36CE0081	Prehistoric	-77.65015 41.02601	36CE0459	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.94168 40.82566
36CE0082	Prehistoric	-77.60597 41.04935	36CE0461	Prehistoric	-78.06683 40.78955
36CE0083	Prehistoric	-78.0812 40.77967	36CE0463	Prehistoric	-77.73252 40.93511
36CE0084	Prehistoric	-77.6599 41.01954	36CE0464	Prehistoric	-77.7355 40.93492
36CE0085	Prehistoric	-77.65404 41.02026	36CE0465	Prehistoric	-77.72949 40.93761
36CE0086	Prehistoric	-77.65308 41.01822	36CE0466	Prehistoric	-77.73245 40.94478
36CE0087	Prehistoric	-77.64858 41.02508	36CE0467	Prehistoric	-77.72046 40.94607
36CE0088	Prehistoric	-77.65062 41.02339	36CE0468	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.72202 40.94377
36CE0089	Prehistoric	-77.78639 40.93435	36CE0469	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.72383 40.94385
36CE0090	Prehistoric	-77.59335 41.02302	36CE0470	Prehistoric	-78.02729 40.82245
36CE0091	Prehistoric	-77.59591 41.02494	36CE0471	Prehistoric	-78.02699 40.82271
36CE0092	Prehistoric	-77.59607 41.02247	36CE0472	Prehistoric	-78.03769 40.8134
36CE0093	Prehistoric	-77.6015 41.01789	36CE0473	Prehistoric	-78.03682 40.81337
36CE0094	Prehistoric	-77.60158 41.01554	36CE0474	Prehistoric	-78.03706 40.81395
36CE0095	Prehistoric	-77.60101 41.0149	36CE0475	Prehistoric	-78.03639 40.81453
36CE0096	Prehistoric	-77.59989 41.018	36CE0476	Prehistoric	-78.03541 40.81441
36CE0101	Prehistoric	-77.82819 40.92947	36CE0477	Prehistoric	-78.03476 40.81477
36CE0102	Prehistoric	-77.82918 40.92706	36CE0478	Prehistoric	-78.10338 40.76356
36CE0103	Prehistoric	-77.83076 40.92728	36CE0479	Prehistoric	-78.1026 40.76422
36CE0104	Prehistoric	-77.82581 40.93132	36CE0480	Prehistoric	-78.10239 40.76365
36CE0105	Prehistoric	-77.82281 40.93167	36CE0481	Prehistoric	-78.10178 40.76442
36CE0106	Prehistoric	-77.82862 40.92832	36CE0482	Prehistoric	-78.10656 40.76143
36CE0107	Prehistoric	-77.8314 40.928	36CE0483	Prehistoric	-78.07369 40.78371
36CE0108	Prehistoric	-77.82484 40.93132	36CE0484	Prehistoric	-78.07331 40.78445
36CE0109	Prehistoric	-77.82385 40.93147	36CE0485	Prehistoric	-78.07409 40.78469
36CE0110	Prehistoric	-77.75663 40.96295	36CE0486	Prehistoric	-78.04505 40.80537
36CE0111	Prehistoric	-77.75444 40.9667	36CE0488	Prehistoric	-78.04555 40.80406
36CE0112	Prehistoric	-77.75384 40.96847	36CE0489	Prehistoric	-78.04956 40.80018

Table A-4. Region 4 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36CE0113	Prehistoric	-77.7931 40.88438	36CE0490	Prehistoric	-78.0444 40.80128
36CE0114	Prehistoric	-77.83329 40.81623	36CE0491	Prehistoric	-78.05267 40.80184
36CE0115	Prehistoric	-77.83243 40.81903	36CE0494	Prehistoric	-77.86398 40.8664
36CE0116	Prehistoric	-77.83213 40.81203	36CE0496	Prehistoric	-78.00138 40.83513
36CE0117	Prehistoric	-77.83254 40.81569	36CE0498	Prehistoric	-77.86294 40.86841
36CE0118	Prehistoric	-77.83518 40.82144	36CE0501	Prehistoric	-77.78155 40.87235
36CE0119	Prehistoric	-77.83471 40.82324	36CE0502	Prehistoric	-77.82506 40.84631
36CE0120	Prehistoric	-77.83004 40.81997	36CE0503	Prehistoric	-77.79629 40.90269
36CE0121	Prehistoric	-77.82788 40.81827	36CE0505	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.83746 40.81319
36CE0122	Prehistoric	-77.83458 40.81697	36CE0507	Prehistoric	-77.93488 40.86502
36CE0123	Prehistoric	-77.8355 40.81618	36CE0508	Prehistoric	-77.98949 40.84206
36CE0124	Prehistoric	-77.83097 40.81249	36CE0510	Prehistoric	-78.06617 40.78918
36CE0125	Prehistoric	-77.8367 40.81658	36CE0511	Prehistoric	-77.8229 40.81893
36CE0126	Prehistoric	-77.83686 40.81753	36CE0518	Prehistoric	-77.76401 40.95388
36CE0127	Prehistoric	-77.8367 40.81869	36CE0519	Prehistoric	-77.71793 40.87497
36CE0128	Prehistoric	-77.83658 40.81509	36CE0521	Prehistoric	-77.83104 40.81966
36CE0129	Prehistoric	-77.82544 40.82028	36CE0522	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.89256 40.85271
36CE0130	Prehistoric	-77.82702 40.82037	36CE0523	Prehistoric	-77.76141 40.79657
36CE0131	Prehistoric	-77.8263 40.81963	36CE0524	Prehistoric	-77.64243 41.02734
36CE0132	Prehistoric	-77.83096 40.82194	36CE0525	Prehistoric	-77.85138 40.75669
36CE0133	Prehistoric	-77.85434 40.77127	36CE0530	Prehistoric	-77.83363 40.78869
36CE0134	Prehistoric	-77.85167 40.77269	36CN0016	Prehistoric	-77.41085 41.13163
36CE0135	Prehistoric	-77.84413 40.7606	36CN0046	Prehistoric	-77.41811 41.12953
36CE0136	Prehistoric	-77.84227 40.76488	36CN0047	Prehistoric	-77.47957 41.12593
36CE0137	Prehistoric	-77.84331 40.76618	36CN0051	Prehistoric	-77.48391 41.11733
36CE0138	Prehistoric	-77.8429 40.76662	36CN0098	Prehistoric	-77.48423 41.12583
36CE0139	Prehistoric	-77.84243 40.76703	36CN0099	Prehistoric	-77.48402 41.1224
36CE0140	Prehistoric	-77.84373 40.75414	36CN0100	Prehistoric	-77.49384 41.12345
36CE0141	Prehistoric	-77.84858 40.75178	36CN0101	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.50254 41.11565
36CE0142	Prehistoric	-77.85021 40.75902	36CN0102	Prehistoric	-77.50353 41.11295
36CE0143	Prehistoric	-77.78378 40.79347	36CN0103	Prehistoric	-77.5349 41.08958
36CE0144	Prehistoric	-77.78149 40.79364	36CN0104	Prehistoric	-77.56809 41.0679
36CE0145	Prehistoric	-77.77808 40.80179	36CN0106	Prehistoric	-77.4752 41.12383
36CE0146	Prehistoric	-77.79427 40.79542	36CN0112	Prehistoric	-77.52602 41.08998
36CE0147	Prehistoric	-77.79089 40.79664	36CN0113	Prehistoric	-77.52932 41.08935
36CE0148	Prehistoric	-77.78503 40.79212	36CN0114	Prehistoric	-77.53095 41.08893
36CE0149	Prehistoric	-77.75876 40.8031	36CN0115	Prehistoric	-77.53043 41.08703
36CE0150	Prehistoric	-77.76573 40.80101	36CN0116	Prehistoric	-77.52969 41.08716
36CE0151	Prehistoric	-77.75749 40.80837	36CN0117	Prehistoric	-77.53774 41.09349
36CE0152	Prehistoric	-77.75322 40.80686	36CN0118	Prehistoric	-77.53638 41.08667
36CE0153	Prehistoric	-77.75374 40.80376	36CN0119	Prehistoric	-77.53719 41.08598
36CE0154	Prehistoric	-77.75139 40.8035	36CN0120	Prehistoric	-77.53718 41.0851
36CE0155	Prehistoric	-77.76018 40.80579	36CN0121	Prehistoric	-77.53517 41.08416
36CE0156	Prehistoric	-77.76136 40.80915	36CN0122	Prehistoric	-77.52635 41.08906
36CE0157	Prehistoric	-77.83545 40.92422	36CN0123	Prehistoric	-77.53038 41.08576
36CE0158	Prehistoric	-77.88013 40.90161	36CN0124	Prehistoric	-77.52975 41.08594
36CE0175	Prehistoric	-77.71666 40.8447	36CN0125	Prehistoric	-77.52892 41.08596
36CE0191	Prehistoric	-77.68305 40.83727	36CN0126	Prehistoric	-77.52641 41.08741
36CE0192	Prehistoric	-77.71672 40.81459	36CN0127	Prehistoric	-77.52514 41.08862
36CE0193	Prehistoric	-77.70954 40.82326	36CN0129	Prehistoric	-77.53196 41.08878
36CE0194	Prehistoric	-77.70998 40.82146	36CN0130	Prehistoric	-77.52563 41.10261
36CE0195	Prehistoric	-77.68917 40.82381	36CN0131	Prehistoric	-77.51607 41.0932

Table A-4. Region 4 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36CE0196	Prehistoric	-77.6676 40.82158	36CN0132	Prehistoric	-77.51695 41.09523
36CE0197	Prehistoric	-77.74282 40.80788	36CN0133	Prehistoric	-77.51765 41.09622
36CE0198	Prehistoric	-77.74135 40.80925	36CN0134	Prehistoric	-77.51549 41.09682
36CE0199	Prehistoric	-77.73883 40.81109	36CN0135	Prehistoric	-77.51519 41.10102
36CE0200	Prehistoric	-77.73818 40.81179	36CN0136	Prehistoric	-77.5092 41.09617
36CE0205	Prehistoric	-77.72446 40.81182	36CN0137	Prehistoric	-77.51068 41.09545
36CE0228	Prehistoric	-77.78856 40.81052	36CN0138	Prehistoric	-77.51689 41.09191
36CE0229	Prehistoric	-77.75559 40.8112	36CN0139	Prehistoric	-77.52204 41.0549
36CE0230	Prehistoric	-77.76872 40.77931	36CN0140	Prehistoric	-77.5163 41.0579
36CE0231	Prehistoric	-77.8334 40.77364	36CN0141	Prehistoric	-77.51561 41.05428
36CE0232	Prehistoric	-77.80966 40.80079	36CN0142	Prehistoric	-77.52319 41.04984
36CE0233	Prehistoric	-77.81074 40.80075	36CN0143	Prehistoric	-77.51227 41.01672
36CE0234	Prehistoric	-77.81188 40.80183	36CN0144	Prehistoric	-77.51295 41.01761
36CE0235	Prehistoric	-77.81491 40.80145	36CN0145	Prehistoric	-77.5138 41.01665
36CE0236	Prehistoric	-77.81393 40.8082	36CN0146	Prehistoric	-77.51295 41.01686
36CE0237	Prehistoric	-77.82386 40.81008	36CN0147	Prehistoric	-77.51356 41.01719
36CE0238	Prehistoric	-77.85203 40.81673	36CN0148	Prehistoric	-77.52246 41.02208
36CE0239	Prehistoric	-77.76614 40.77692	36CN0149	Prehistoric	-77.5245 41.02374
36CE0240	Prehistoric	-77.77018 40.77672	36CN0150	Prehistoric	-77.50938 41.01716
36CE0241	Prehistoric	-77.77 40.77611	36CN0151	Prehistoric	-77.50608 41.02006
36CE0242	Prehistoric	-77.7702 40.77546	36CN0152	Prehistoric	-77.50322 41.02133
36CE0243	Prehistoric	-77.77002 40.7751	36CN0153	Prehistoric	-77.5043 41.02246
36CE0244	Prehistoric	-77.77029 40.77814	36CN0154	Prehistoric	-77.51729 41.01539
36CE0245	Prehistoric	-77.77044 40.78026	36CN0155	Prehistoric	-77.46001 40.98234
36CE0246	Prehistoric	-77.76579 40.78173	36CN0156	Prehistoric	-77.45978 40.98783
36CE0247	Prehistoric	-77.76361 40.78165	36CN0157	Prehistoric	-77.42369 40.99424
36CE0248	Prehistoric	-77.76481 40.78186	36CN0158	Prehistoric	-77.42278 40.99386
36CE0249	Prehistoric	-77.76359 40.78082	36CN0159	Prehistoric	-77.42186 40.99369
36CE0250	Prehistoric	-77.76419 40.78018	36CN0160	Prehistoric	-77.42729 40.98755
36CE0251	Prehistoric	-77.76535 40.77869	36CN0161	Prehistoric	-77.42886 40.9934
36CE0252	Prehistoric	-77.66193 40.97088	36CN0162	Prehistoric	-77.42734 40.99435
36CE0255	Prehistoric	-77.68927 40.92781	36CN0163	Prehistoric	-77.42611 40.99475
36CE0256	Prehistoric	-77.74266 40.89994	36CN0167	Prehistoric	-77.41506 41.13085
36CE0257	Prehistoric	-77.76619 40.7777	36CN0168	Prehistoric	-77.42121 41.13073
36CE0258	Prehistoric	-77.8308 40.7759	36CN0169	Prehistoric	-77.43962 41.12668
36CE0259	Prehistoric	-77.77059 40.77944	36CN0171	Prehistoric	-77.42684 41.13076
36CE0260	Prehistoric	-77.77236 40.78092	36CN0172	Prehistoric	-77.43319 41.12961
36CE0261	Prehistoric	-77.76688 40.77682	36CN0173	Prehistoric	-77.43478 41.12681
36CE0262	Prehistoric	-77.75436 40.78464	36CN0174	Prehistoric	-77.44185 41.12601
36CE0263	Prehistoric	-77.75278 40.78501	36CN0176	Prehistoric	-77.43988 41.12509
36CE0264	Prehistoric	-77.7682 40.78527	36CN0177	Prehistoric	-77.44379 41.12358
36CE0265	Prehistoric	-77.76585 40.78521	36CN0182	Prehistoric	-77.52883 41.08711
36CE0266	Prehistoric	-77.83409 40.77466	36CN0183	Prehistoric	-77.45372 41.1201
36CE0267	Prehistoric	-77.83359 40.77531	36CN0192	Prehistoric	-77.43284 41.12591
36CE0268	Prehistoric	-77.81204 40.80082	36CN0194	Prehistoric	-77.42951 41.0509
36CE0270	Prehistoric	-77.81526 40.80718	36CN0195	Prehistoric	-77.47387 41.05555
36CE0271	Prehistoric	-77.83028 40.81744	36CN0196	Prehistoric	-77.45766 41.05009
36CE0272	Prehistoric	-77.814 40.80532	36CN0197	Prehistoric	-77.46581 41.06521
36CE0273	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.83939 40.81407	36CN0200	Prehistoric	-77.49821 41.11064
36CE0274	Prehistoric	-77.84062 40.8133	36CN0203	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.47385 41.12294
36CE0275	Prehistoric	-77.84202 40.81309	36CN0204	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.3064 41.02892
36CE0278	Prehistoric	-77.75263 40.77275	36CN0206	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.47397 41.05927

Table A-4. Region 4 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36CE0279	Prehistoric	-77.75788 40.77708	36CN0207	Prehistoric	-77.47247 41.0579
36CE0280	Prehistoric	-77.85714 40.81675	36CN0210	Prehistoric	-77.41842 41.13384
36CE0281	Prehistoric	-77.87002 40.82126	36CN0211	Prehistoric	-77.41953 41.13376
36CE0287	Prehistoric	-77.81133 40.81004	36CN0212	Prehistoric	-77.40381 41.13528
36CE0288	Prehistoric	-77.81081 40.80164	36CN0215	Prehistoric	-77.46087 41.05832
36CE0289	Prehistoric	-77.7927 40.75373	36CN0216	Prehistoric	-77.47528 41.06145
36CE0290	Prehistoric	-77.87296 40.74575	36CE0159	Prehistoric	-77.41229 40.96517
36CE0291	Prehistoric	-77.87184 40.7475	36CE0162	Prehistoric	-77.46936 40.94665
36CE0293	Prehistoric	-77.82676 40.93263	36CE0163	Prehistoric	-77.45162 40.95056
36CE0294	Prehistoric	-77.82793 40.92407	36CE0164	Prehistoric	-77.39464 40.95255
36CE0295	Prehistoric	-77.86104 40.86841	36CE0165	Prehistoric	-77.47325 40.93462
36CE0296	Prehistoric	-77.86545 40.86689	36CE0166	Prehistoric	-77.46955 40.93517
36CE0297	Prehistoric	-77.86381 40.86697	36CE0168	Prehistoric	-77.41432 40.89733
36CE0298	Prehistoric	-77.83652 40.82317	36CE0169	Prehistoric	-77.39877 40.89734
36CE0299	Prehistoric	-77.83852 40.82373	36CE0170	Prehistoric	-77.4009 40.89654
36CE0300	Prehistoric	-77.84336 40.8256	36CE0172	Prehistoric	-77.41966 40.8811
36CE0301	Prehistoric	-77.8335 40.82605	36CE0173	Prehistoric	-77.41815 40.88264
36CE0302	Prehistoric	-77.83687 40.82417	36CE0174	Prehistoric	-77.41752 40.89092
36CE0303	Prehistoric	-77.83927 40.8245	36CE0176	Prehistoric	-77.66048 40.8484
36CE0304	Prehistoric	-77.83961 40.82103	36CE0177	Prehistoric	-77.66328 40.84671
36CE0305	Prehistoric	-77.76357 40.80819	36CE0178	Prehistoric	-77.66591 40.8534
36CE0306	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.7627 40.80781	36CE0179	Prehistoric	-77.64876 40.84337
36CE0307	Prehistoric	-77.75662 40.79839	36CE0180	Prehistoric	-77.65424 40.84244
36CE0308	Prehistoric	-77.75553 40.79955	36CE0181	Prehistoric	-77.65186 40.84342
36CE0309	Prehistoric	-77.75892 40.79773	36CE0182	Prehistoric	-77.66188 40.84262
36CE0310	Prehistoric	-77.76107 40.80271	36CE0183	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.67009 40.83843
36CE0311	Prehistoric	-77.75177 40.80171	36CE0184	Prehistoric	-77.66721 40.84041
36CE0312	Prehistoric	-77.75521 40.81277	36CE0185	Prehistoric	-77.6727 40.84119
36CE0313	Prehistoric	-77.75688 40.81442	36CE0186	Prehistoric	-77.66884 40.84429
36CE0314	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.75804 40.81319	36CE0187	Prehistoric	-77.66604 40.84565
36CE0315	Prehistoric	-77.75845 40.81509	36CE0188	Prehistoric	-77.67866 40.82894
36CE0316	Prehistoric	-77.75802 40.81607	36CE0189	Prehistoric	-77.67367 40.83164
36CE0317	Prehistoric	-77.76024 40.8156	36CE0190	Prehistoric	-77.67401 40.83825
36CE0318	Prehistoric	-77.75902 40.8158	36CE0202	Prehistoric	-77.63634 40.80189
36CE0319	Prehistoric	-77.76608 40.8116	36CE0203	Prehistoric	-77.64221 40.8014
36CE0320	Prehistoric	-77.75853 40.81436	36CE0204	Prehistoric	-77.64529 40.80164
36CE0321	Prehistoric	-77.75895 40.81358	36CE0207	Prehistoric	-77.65099 40.79296
36CE0322	Prehistoric	-77.75647 40.81324	36CE0208	Prehistoric	-77.62675 40.81073
36CE0323	Prehistoric	-77.75773 40.81253	36CE0209	Prehistoric	-77.64357 40.79378
36CE0324	Prehistoric	-77.7631 40.80895	36CE0211	Prehistoric	-77.66115 40.79507
36CE0325	Prehistoric	-77.76674 40.81206	36CE0286	Prehistoric	-77.66163 40.79981
36CE0326	Prehistoric	-77.75884 40.81165	36CE0340	Prehistoric	-77.52554 40.84887
36CE0327	Prehistoric	-77.76201 40.80107	36CE0367	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.47565 40.89463
36CE0328	Prehistoric	-77.76261 40.80161	36CE0368	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.47586 40.89596
36CE0329	Prehistoric	-77.75869 40.80868	36CE0389	Prehistoric	-77.55953 40.86004
36CE0330	Prehistoric	-77.76473 40.81441	36CE0439	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.67181 40.83616
36CE0331	Prehistoric	-77.75904 40.81673	36CE0440	Prehistoric	-77.67088 40.83856
36CE0332	Prehistoric	-77.75995 40.81631	36SN0038	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.22491 40.76287
36CE0333	Prehistoric	-77.75527 40.80181	36SN0049	Prehistoric	-77.13342 40.76647
36CE0334	Prehistoric	-77.76148 40.80852	36SN0050	Prehistoric	-77.13139 40.76978
36CE0335	Prehistoric	-77.76502 40.79676	36SN0051	Prehistoric	-77.13395 40.77177
36CE0336	Prehistoric	-77.86551 40.82248	36SN0052	Prehistoric	-77.1305 40.77149

Table A-4. Region 4 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36CE0337	Prehistoric	-77.86889 40.82299	36SN0054	Prehistoric	-77.14929 40.77323
36CE0338	Prehistoric	-77.80695 40.80021	36SN0056	Prehistoric	-77.14323 40.77475
36CE0339	Prehistoric	-77.79922 40.77657	36SN0086	Prehistoric	-77.17541 40.75519
36CE0341	Prehistoric	-77.85533 40.91654	36SN0095	Prehistoric	-77.09645 40.7702
36CE0342	Prehistoric	-77.76404 40.95249	36SN0134	Prehistoric	-77.20666 40.75819
36CE0345	Prehistoric	-77.62311 41.03573	36SN0158	Prehistoric	-77.03614 40.77676
36CE0346	Prehistoric	-77.61513 41.04107	36SN0159	Prehistoric	-77.0061 40.79455
36CE0347	Prehistoric	-77.60787 41.04492	36SN0205	Prehistoric	-77.22641 40.75938
36CE0348	Prehistoric	-77.6201 41.03815	36SN0206	Prehistoric	-77.21078 40.76225
36CE0349	Prehistoric	-77.62941 41.04805	36SN0207	Prehistoric	-77.20092 40.763
36CE0350	Prehistoric	-77.62663 41.04001	36SN0261	Prehistoric	-77.14199 40.77539
36CE0351	Prehistoric	-77.88895 40.86659	36SN0272	Prehistoric	-77.16363 40.7709
36CE0352	Prehistoric	-77.88927 40.86842	36SN0273	Prehistoric	-77.28508 40.72804
36CE0353	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.88511 40.85523	36SN0274	Prehistoric	-77.3172 40.70985
Watershed 55-Ridge and Valley-Appalachian Mountain:					
36BL0001	Prehistoric	-78.29771 40.43077	36BL0079	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.25926 40.43491
36BL0002	Prehistoric	-78.44812 40.31526	36BL0080	Prehistoric	-78.27761 40.40047
36BL0003	Prehistoric	-78.41033 40.39579	36BL0081	Prehistoric	-78.25353 40.43539
36BL0004	Prehistoric	-78.36011 40.42847	36BL0088	Prehistoric	-78.22562 40.44537
36BL0005	Prehistoric	-78.21899 40.66208	36BL0089	Prehistoric	-78.2393 40.44019
36BL0006	Prehistoric	-78.21829 40.65829	36BL0090	Prehistoric	-78.16438 40.72641
36BL0007	Prehistoric	-78.40769 40.39628	36BL0091	Prehistoric	-78.35725 40.42739
36BL0008	Prehistoric	-78.40713 40.39521	36BL0092	Prehistoric	-78.3253 40.60111
36BL0009	Prehistoric	-78.40675 40.39312	36BL0093	Prehistoric	-78.45331 40.29503
36BL0010	Prehistoric	-78.40038 40.39564	36BL0094	Prehistoric	-78.21174 40.7033
36BL0011	Prehistoric	-78.37041 40.42352	36BL0097	Prehistoric	-78.19927 40.70905
36BL0012	Prehistoric	-78.37261 40.43465	36BL0098	Prehistoric	-78.20031 40.71154
36BL0013	Prehistoric	-78.33782 40.44565	36BL0099	Prehistoric	-78.46434 40.28128
36BL0014	Prehistoric	-78.32971 40.43987	36BL0100	Prehistoric	-78.29844 40.62263
36BL0015	Prehistoric	-78.2812 40.47078	36BL0101	Prehistoric	-78.29705 40.62283
36BL0016	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.28111 40.47199	36BL0102	Prehistoric	-78.29758 40.62217
36BL0017	Prehistoric	-78.33501 40.50725	36BL0103	Prehistoric	-78.29674 40.62203
36BL0019	Prehistoric	-78.3185 40.60881	36BL0104	Prehistoric	-78.29788 40.62428
36BL0020	Prehistoric	-78.31579 40.60899	36BL0105	Prehistoric	-78.2969 40.62388
36BL0021	Prehistoric	-78.31249 40.60869	36BL0106	Prehistoric	-78.46223 40.27271
36BL0022	Prehistoric	-78.31372 40.60749	36BL0109	Prehistoric	-78.41944 40.37771
36BL0023	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.29591 40.6282	36BL0112	Prehistoric	-78.31548 40.60668
36BL0024	Prehistoric	-78.17271 40.6164	36CE0269	Prehistoric	-77.91827 40.71918
36BL0025	Prehistoric	-78.43691 40.32701	36CE0282	Prehistoric	-77.97506 40.70321
36BL0026	Prehistoric	-78.34249 40.32526	36CE0283	Prehistoric	-77.975 40.7021
36BL0027	Prehistoric	-78.43349 40.35758	36CE0284	Prehistoric	-77.97214 40.70383
36BL0028	Prehistoric	-78.42873 40.39037	36CE0285	Prehistoric	-77.97113 40.70461
36BL0029	Prehistoric	-78.42997 40.39042	36CE0360	Prehistoric	-77.95379 40.70698
36BL0030	Prehistoric	-78.42989 40.39244	36CE0497	Prehistoric	-78.01842 40.79476
36BL0036	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.45477 40.26693	36CE0512	Prehistoric	-78.04237 40.76667
36BL0038	Prehistoric	-78.30062 40.62779	36HU0065	Prehistoric	-78.10596 40.639
36BL0039	Prehistoric	-78.30202 40.62811	36HU0066	Prehistoric	-78.11712 40.56464
36BL0040	Prehistoric	-78.30304 40.62843	36HU0067	Prehistoric	-78.07017 40.56509
36BL0041	Prehistoric	-78.31177 40.62773	36HU0072	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.11564 40.65583
36BL0042	Prehistoric	-78.30672 40.6299	36HU0076	Prehistoric	-78.1371 40.71026
36BL0043	Prehistoric	-78.30576 40.63072	36HU0086	Prehistoric	-78.06865 40.5663
36BL0044	Prehistoric	-78.30663 40.6307	36HU0097	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.0656 40.56772

Table A-4. Region 4 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36BL0045	Prehistoric	-78.29433 40.62674	36HU0101	Prehistoric	-78.02465 40.69615
36BL0046	Prehistoric	-78.33623 40.5652	36HU0113	Prehistoric	-78.07633 40.53875
36BL0047	Prehistoric	-78.33859 40.56552	36HU0115	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.08956 40.64528
36BL0048	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.33543 40.59444	36HU0152	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.14965 40.56557
36BL0049	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.3347 40.59503	36HU0153	Prehistoric	-78.14262 40.57921
36BL0050	Prehistoric	-78.3001 40.6259	36HU0155	Prehistoric	-78.07901 40.5373
36BL0051	Prehistoric	-78.30316 40.62552	36HU0181	Prehistoric	-78.11109 40.71456
36BL0052	Prehistoric	-78.32332 40.5836	36HU0182	Prehistoric	-78.10986 40.71545
36BL0053	Prehistoric	-78.32049 40.59392	36HU0184	Prehistoric	-78.17052 40.61212
36BL0054	Prehistoric	-78.31888 40.59552	36HU0185	Prehistoric	-78.16978 40.61064
36BL0055	Prehistoric	-78.31895 40.59896	36HU0187	Prehistoric	-78.15721 40.59585
36BL0056	Prehistoric	-78.28374 40.63247	36HU0188	Prehistoric	-78.1527 40.59191
36BL0057	Prehistoric	-78.33093 40.56388	36HU0189	Prehistoric	-78.14058 40.57223
36BL0058	Prehistoric	-78.3607 40.42966	36HU0191	Prehistoric	-78.13893 40.57211
36BL0060	Prehistoric	-78.2787 40.47367	36HU0215	Prehistoric	-78.1082 40.55855
36BL0062	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.27221 40.47455	36HU0216	Prehistoric	-78.09601 40.55354
36BL0065	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.18306 40.72334	36HU0217	Prehistoric	-78.08615 40.53845
36BL0069	Prehistoric	-78.47645 40.2726	36HU0218	Prehistoric	-78.0817 40.53577
36BL0070	Prehistoric	-78.47623 40.26948	36HU0219	Prehistoric	-78.08956 40.53469
36BL0071	Prehistoric	-78.16277 40.73171	36HU0220	Prehistoric	-78.08843 40.53451
36BL0072	Prehistoric	-78.17642 40.72069	36HU0221	Prehistoric	-78.08875 40.53613
36BL0074	Prehistoric	-78.18717 40.6113			
Watershed 56-Ridge and Valley-Appalachian Mountain:					
36HU0043	Prehistoric	-77.83589 40.36562	36MI0050	Prehistoric	-77.65368 40.55222
36HU0044	Prehistoric	-77.85647 40.3632	36MI0051	Prehistoric	-77.74487 40.53219
36HU0073	Prehistoric	-77.85297 40.36285	36MI0052	Prehistoric	-77.65646 40.54009
36JU0101	Prehistoric	-77.46533 40.60676	36MI0053	Prehistoric	-77.6573 40.53427
36JU0102	Prehistoric	-77.46911 40.60505	36MI0054	Prehistoric	-77.65374 40.53776
36JU0103	Prehistoric	-77.47073 40.60477	36MI0055	Prehistoric	-77.71497 40.5162
36JU0104	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.47306 40.60492	36MI0056	Prehistoric	-77.70153 40.52316
36JU0105	Prehistoric	-77.48434 40.60261	36MI0057	Prehistoric	-77.69725 40.52192
36JU0106	Prehistoric	-77.4242 40.58663	36MI0058	Prehistoric	-77.70006 40.52089
36MI0001	Prehistoric	-77.86243 40.37361	36MI0059	Prehistoric	-77.69583 40.51877
36MI0002	Prehistoric	-77.85644 40.36665	36MI0060	Prehistoric	-77.65457 40.52617
36MI0003	Prehistoric	-77.73954 40.60458	36MI0061	Prehistoric	-77.65886 40.51601
36MI0004	Prehistoric	-77.73732 40.60317	36MI0062	Prehistoric	-77.6546 40.51897
36MI0005	Prehistoric	-77.69829 40.60117	36MI0065	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.5929 40.71244
36MI0006	Prehistoric	-77.73152 40.62892	36MI0068	Prehistoric	-77.5982 40.69638
36MI0007	Prehistoric	-77.73484 40.50169	36MI0069	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.60217 40.69091
36MI0008	Prehistoric	-77.72877 40.50624	36MI0070	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.60701 40.683
36MI0009	Prehistoric	-77.76 40.57855	36MI0071	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.60701 40.68167
36MI0010	Prehistoric	-77.77221 40.56179	36MI0072	Prehistoric	-77.59767 40.68486
36MI0011	Prehistoric	-77.79426 40.57355	36MI0073	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.60139 40.67773
36MI0012	Prehistoric	-77.8152 40.54635	36MI0074	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.60363 40.67411
36MI0014	Prehistoric	-77.73539 40.49703	36MI0076	Prehistoric	-77.58678 40.5584
36MI0015	Prehistoric	-77.73541 40.47554	36MI0077	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.83423 40.39034
36MI0016	Prehistoric	-77.73028 40.47881	36MI0079	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.59146 40.59231
36MI0017	Prehistoric	-77.73601 40.47915	36MI0080	Prehistoric	-77.65312 40.56279
36MI0018	Prehistoric	-77.85181 40.36707	36MI0081	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.69799 40.53338
36MI0020	Prehistoric	-77.55406 40.74687	36MI0082	Prehistoric	-77.70329 40.52922
36MI0021	Prehistoric	-77.59881 40.72783	36MI0083	Prehistoric	-77.68645 40.54487
36MI0022	Prehistoric	-77.52965 40.72662	36MI0084	Prehistoric	-77.59346 40.5916

Table A-4. Region 4 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36MI0023	Prehistoric	-77.54824 40.65529	36MI0088	Prehistoric	-77.60359 40.67728
36MI0024	Prehistoric	-77.54624 40.73108	36MI0090	Prehistoric	-77.57612 40.61622
36MI0025	Prehistoric	-77.53247 40.70982	36MI0091	Prehistoric	-77.53684 40.57991
36MI0026	Prehistoric	-77.55943 40.68859	36MI0092	Prehistoric	-77.5412 40.57915
36MI0027	Prehistoric	-77.61937 40.66709	36MI0093	Prehistoric	-77.5251 40.58491
36MI0028	Prehistoric	-77.52382 40.6427	36MI0094	Prehistoric	-77.67525 40.50898
36MI0029	Prehistoric	-77.52634 40.64581	36MI0095	Prehistoric	-77.50507 40.63172
36MI0031	Prehistoric	-77.57301 40.7435	36MI0096	Prehistoric	-77.5229 40.61814
36MI0033	Prehistoric	-77.59818 40.67389	36MI0098	Prehistoric	-77.53134 40.61409
36MI0034	Prehistoric	-77.73493 40.60615	36MI0099	Prehistoric	-77.77109 40.58383
36MI0035	Prehistoric	-77.69942 40.60395	36MI0100	Prehistoric	-77.50722 40.6296
36MI0036	Prehistoric	-77.67687 40.61613	36MI0101	Prehistoric	-77.53192 40.61309
36MI0037	Prehistoric	-77.74165 40.59591	36MI0103	Prehistoric	-77.67082 40.51288
36MI0038	Prehistoric	-77.64049 40.59743	36MI0105	Prehistoric	-77.7053 40.6042
36MI0039	Prehistoric	-77.66871 40.57561	36MI0106	Prehistoric	-77.60411 40.56986
36MI0040	Prehistoric	-77.66805 40.57856	36MI0107	Prehistoric	-77.69033 40.56484
36MI0041	Prehistoric	-77.7066 40.5635	36MI0108	Prehistoric	-77.7353 40.60445
36MI0042	Prehistoric	-77.68003 40.56633	36MI0109	Prehistoric	-77.8529 40.3751
36MI0043	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.68291 40.56595	36MI0110	Prehistoric	-77.83651 40.39113
36MI0045	Prehistoric	-77.68001 40.56397	36MI0111	Prehistoric	-77.81987 40.36196
36MI0046	Prehistoric	-77.72256 40.54725	36MI0112	Prehistoric	-77.85115 40.36978
36MI0047	Prehistoric	-77.70441 40.55289	36MI0113	Prehistoric	-77.8318 40.39373
36MI0048	Prehistoric	-77.70824 40.55355	36MI0115	Prehistoric	-77.59285 40.56931
36MI0049	Prehistoric	-77.64638 40.54961	36MI0116	Prehistoric	-77.78777 40.47381
Watershed 61-Ridge and Valley-Appalachian Mountain:					
36HU0042	Prehistoric	-77.80799 40.66392	36HU0124	Prehistoric	-78.05709 40.46261
36HU0045	Prehistoric	-78.02363 40.49236	36HU0125	Prehistoric	-78.05199 40.46442
36HU0047	Prehistoric	-77.85081 40.61536	36HU0126	Prehistoric	-78.05522 40.46264
36HU0061	Prehistoric	-77.85362 40.61242	36HU0127	Prehistoric	-78.05349 40.46484
36HU0062	Prehistoric	-77.85082 40.61432	36HU0128	Prehistoric	-78.05522 40.46866
36HU0068	Prehistoric	-78.04949 40.56823	36HU0138	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.00755 40.47818
36HU0075	Prehistoric	-77.97568 40.61409	36HU0164	Prehistoric	-78.06098 40.46401
36HU0089	Prehistoric	-77.89017 40.57963	36HU0193	Prehistoric	-78.11742 40.42803
36HU0090	Prehistoric	-77.88899 40.57866	36HU0194	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.84617 40.63629
36HU0098	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.06293 40.5689	36HU0201	Prehistoric	-77.88978 40.6915
36HU0099	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.01904 40.48768	36HU0202	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.00143 40.48454
36HU0114	Prehistoric	-77.85749 40.62372	36HU0207	Prehistoric	-77.86916 40.59219
36HU0121	Prehistoric	-78.0814 40.45064	36HU0208	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.93309 40.66367
36HU0122	Prehistoric	-78.08126 40.44791	36HU0211	Prehistoric	-77.95865 40.5543
36HU0123	Prehistoric	-78.05941 40.46191			
Watershed 64-Ridge and Valley-Appalachian Mountain:					
36JU0001	Prehistoric	-77.4987 40.48065	36JU0072	Prehistoric	-77.41884 40.51828
36JU0005	Prehistoric	-77.50118 40.47366	36JU0073	Prehistoric	-77.50139 40.47927
36JU0011	Prehistoric	-77.3945 40.52584	36JU0074	Prehistoric	-77.51194 40.46439
36JU0014	Prehistoric	-77.65882 40.32992	36JU0075	Prehistoric	-77.51467 40.46883
36JU0015	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.42102 40.51677	36JU0076	Prehistoric	-77.53799 40.47233
36JU0016	Prehistoric	-77.4669 40.47299	36JU0077	Prehistoric	-77.55408 40.44578
36JU0017	Prehistoric	-77.66226 40.32714	36JU0078	Prehistoric	-77.54291 40.4529
36JU0018	Prehistoric	-77.4642 40.46976	36JU0079	Prehistoric	-77.55677 40.4431
36JU0019	Prehistoric	-77.5733 40.39129	36JU0080	Prehistoric	-77.55469 40.45236
36JU0021	Prehistoric	-77.54766 40.45058	36JU0081	Prehistoric	-77.56027 40.45467

Table A-4. Region 4 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36JU0024	Prehistoric	-77.46211 40.46857	36JU0082	Prehistoric	-77.57655 40.43647
36JU0025	Prehistoric	-77.46579 40.46853	36JU0083	Prehistoric	-77.58309 40.44309
36JU0027	Prehistoric	-77.46091 40.47048	36JU0085	Prehistoric	-77.53727 40.41901
36JU0031	Prehistoric	-77.18788 40.56379	36JU0086	Prehistoric	-77.57257 40.39612
36JU0039	Prehistoric	-77.18384 40.56408	36JU0087	Prehistoric	-77.5716 40.40224
36JU0061	Prehistoric	-77.63232 40.35445	36JU0088	Prehistoric	-77.55987 40.40789
36JU0062	Prehistoric	-77.63045 40.35444	36JU0089	Prehistoric	-77.58427 40.38355
36JU0063	Prehistoric	-77.6229 40.35521	36JU0108	Prehistoric	-77.55156 40.44675
36JU0065	Prehistoric	-77.4815 40.53868	36JU0109	Prehistoric	-77.52749 40.46488
36JU0066	Prehistoric	-77.44069 40.55425	36JU0110	Prehistoric	-77.6093 40.43707
36JU0067	Prehistoric	-77.41904 40.5466	36JU0112	Prehistoric	-77.64307 40.34634
36JU0068	Prehistoric	-77.44963 40.50256	36JU0113	Prehistoric	-77.41894 40.51634
36JU0069	Prehistoric	-77.42521 40.51087	36JU0114	Prehistoric	-77.69675 40.29132
36JU0070	Prehistoric	-77.41963 40.51484	36JU0115	Prehistoric	-77.65984 40.33075
36JU0071	Prehistoric	-77.41783 40.51566			
Watershed 71-Ridge and Valley-Appalachian Mountain:					
36FU0001	Prehistoric	-77.94495 40.06529	36HU0094	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.87442 40.30171
36FU0002	Prehistoric	-77.96667 40.0652	36HU0095	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.87281 40.30487
36FU0003	Prehistoric	-77.96617 40.06843	36HU0096	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.87105 40.31605
36FU0004	Prehistoric	-77.96057 40.05823	36HU0100	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.89848 40.24918
36FU0029	Prehistoric	-78.04522 40.12495	36HU0102	Prehistoric	-77.86295 40.18435
36FU0038	Prehistoric	-77.96892 40.07144	36HU0103	Prehistoric	-78.00893 40.21196
36FU0039	Prehistoric	-77.8918 40.08062	36HU0104	Prehistoric	-77.98307 40.19295
36FU0040	Prehistoric	-77.89264 40.07972	36HU0132	Prehistoric	-77.87494 40.23281
36FU0041	Prehistoric	-77.95292 40.06472	36HU0133	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.88711 40.2379
36FU0043	Prehistoric	-77.9492 40.06277	36HU0134	Prehistoric	-77.87597 40.28606
36FU0048	Prehistoric	-78.09833 40.0445	36HU0135	Prehistoric	-77.887 40.27125
36FU0049	Prehistoric	-78.04643 40.12489	36HU0137	Prehistoric	-77.92946 40.43038
36HU0039	Prehistoric	-77.96785 40.44906	36HU0139	Prehistoric	-77.94436 40.44239
36HU0040	Prehistoric	-77.9164 40.26127	36HU0141	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.87467 40.28868
36HU0041	Prehistoric	-77.96641 40.44809	36HU0154	Prehistoric	-77.87932 40.28233
36HU0048	Prehistoric	-77.97823 40.45683	36HU0158	Prehistoric	-77.92154 40.2927
36HU0063	Prehistoric	-77.89699 40.2753	36HU0160	Prehistoric	-77.83568 40.36152
36HU0064	Prehistoric	-77.91514 40.2579	36HU0165	Prehistoric	-77.9142 40.25427
36HU0069	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.96907 40.45095	36HU0166	Prehistoric	-77.8334 40.36138
36HU0070	Prehistoric	-77.94246 40.44106	36HU0198	Prehistoric	-77.92175 40.45069
36HU0071	Prehistoric	-77.94367 40.39967	36HU0199	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.8847 40.2367
36HU0074	Prehistoric	-77.83502 40.36254	36HU0200	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.88593 40.23735
36HU0091	Prehistoric	-77.99385 40.47203	36HU0209	Prehistoric	-77.83696 40.36278
36HU0092	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.8682 40.32446	36HU0210	Prehistoric	-77.88816 40.30331
36HU0093	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.87363 40.30254	36MI0013	Prehistoric	-77.81981 40.51859
Watershed 78-Ridge and Valley-Appalachian Mountain:					
36BD0020	Prehistoric	-78.40355 40.01527	36HU0021	Prehistoric	-78.20587 40.33002
36BD0036	Prehistoric	-78.25933 40.21779	36HU0022	Prehistoric	-78.17065 40.31476
36BD0037	Prehistoric	-78.26052 40.21748	36HU0023	Prehistoric	-78.17768 40.31189
36BD0038	Prehistoric	-78.25922 40.21324	36HU0024	Prehistoric	-78.18033 40.3104
36BD0039	Prehistoric	-78.26609 40.21681	36HU0025	Prehistoric	-78.18676 40.30262
36BD0040	Prehistoric	-78.27455 40.21449	36HU0026	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.18557 40.29893
36BD0050	Prehistoric	-78.43982 40.01188	36HU0027	Prehistoric	-78.22092 40.29901
36BD0052	Prehistoric	-78.30937 40.04713	36HU0028	Prehistoric	-78.18926 40.29501
36BD0090	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.50938 40.03955	36HU0029	Prehistoric	-78.19686 40.28085

Table A-4. Region 4 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36BD0098	Prehistoric	-78.31044 40.00703	36HU0030	Prehistoric	-78.16578 40.27177
36BD0099	Prehistoric	-78.32196 40.01311	36HU0031	Prehistoric	-78.2109 40.25634
36BD0100	Prehistoric	-78.48912 40.01841	36HU0032	Prehistoric	-78.14349 40.37101
36BD0152	Prehistoric	-78.25026 40.21009	36HU0033	Prehistoric	-78.14568 40.37015
36BD0155	Prehistoric	-78.37779 40.17046	36HU0034	Prehistoric	-78.19185 40.29504
36BD0156	Prehistoric	-78.37689 40.17265	36HU0035	Prehistoric	-78.14221 40.34502
36BD0158	Prehistoric	-78.37539 40.16736	36HU0036	Prehistoric	-78.11908 40.35781
36BD0159	Prehistoric	-78.37541 40.16684	36HU0037	Prehistoric	-78.13123 40.35198
36BD0160	Prehistoric	-78.37484 40.16707	36HU0038	Prehistoric	-78.11914 40.2854
36BD0177	Prehistoric	-78.37805 40.16956	36HU0049	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.97914 40.456
36BD0178	Prehistoric	-78.4458 40.01741	36HU0050	Prehistoric	-77.97917 40.44886
36BD0179	Prehistoric	-78.44772 40.0183	36HU0051	Prehistoric	-78.04512 40.38208
36BD0180	Prehistoric	-78.44642 40.01665	36HU0052	Prehistoric	-78.04785 40.38227
36BD0183	Prehistoric	-78.39219 40.14665	36HU0053	Prehistoric	-78.06221 40.38066
36BD0184	Prehistoric	-78.39355 40.14585	36HU0054	Prehistoric	-78.11214 40.36371
36BD0190	Prehistoric	-78.26839 40.21423	36HU0055	Prehistoric	-78.11532 40.35982
36BD0222	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.48462 40.02045	36HU0056	Prehistoric	-78.08416 40.36928
36BD0225	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.47015 40.01349	36HU0057	Prehistoric	-78.14357 40.37173
36BD0226	Prehistoric	-78.46669 40.01495	36HU0058	Prehistoric	-78.09061 40.36648
36BD0227	Prehistoric	-78.45339 40.02531	36HU0059	Prehistoric	-78.20319 40.32935
36BD0245	Prehistoric	-78.40777 40.17312	36HU0060	Prehistoric	-78.13023 40.31933
36BD0246	Prehistoric	-78.37605 40.16251	36HU0077	Prehistoric	-78.07554 40.26875
36BD0262	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.29456 40.09116	36HU0088	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.98608 40.45207
36BD0263	Prehistoric	-78.29601 40.09104	36HU0105	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.19583 40.33052
36BD0267	Prehistoric	-78.2722 40.13861	36HU0106	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.20157 40.33273
36BD0269	Prehistoric	-78.46595 40.00955	36HU0107	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.20078 40.33233
36BD0288	Prehistoric	-78.49297 40.01848	36HU0108	Prehistoric	-78.20163 40.33356
36HU0001	Prehistoric	-78.06039 40.39632	36HU0109	Prehistoric	-78.20227 40.33383
36HU0002	Prehistoric	-78.00703 40.42452	36HU0110	Prehistoric	-78.20363 40.33488
36HU0003	Prehistoric	-78.01001 40.42179	36HU0111	Prehistoric	-78.1217 40.28653
36HU0004	Prehistoric	-78.01556 40.42479	36HU0112	Prehistoric	-78.22172 40.21797
36HU0005	Prehistoric	-78.05686 40.39473	36HU0129	Prehistoric	-78.15387 40.30079
36HU0006	Prehistoric	-78.0568 40.38522	36HU0143	Prehistoric	-78.16187 40.29236
36HU0007	Prehistoric	-78.08526 40.37343	36HU0144	Prehistoric	-78.17202 40.27859
36HU0008	Prehistoric	-78.10743 40.37154	36HU0145	Prehistoric	-78.17359 40.27516
36HU0009	Prehistoric	-78.12844 40.35918	36HU0146	Prehistoric	-78.1794 40.26662
36HU0010	Prehistoric	-78.13182 40.36338	36HU0147	Prehistoric	-78.19743 40.24908
36HU0011	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.13962 40.36455	36HU0148	Prehistoric	-78.21901 40.22291
36HU0012	Prehistoric	-78.14303 40.36929	36HU0149	Prehistoric	-78.20074 40.20572
36HU0013	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.14954 40.36962	36HU0157	Prehistoric	-78.04727 40.28077
36HU0014	Prehistoric	-78.1449 40.39513	36HU0178	Prehistoric	-78.02715 40.29988
36HU0015	Prehistoric	-78.14772 40.39655	36HU0180	Prehistoric	-78.18209 40.30249
36HU0017	Prehistoric	-78.13553 40.3553	36HU0204	Prehistoric	-78.00499 40.37569
36HU0018	Prehistoric	-78.13771 40.35283	36HU0205	Prehistoric	-78.00006 40.38208
36HU0019	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.13971 40.34389	36HU0206	Prehistoric	-77.98844 40.40024
36HU0020	Prehistoric	-78.20439 40.33247			
Watershed 82-Ridge and Valley-Appalachian Mountain:					
36BD0026	Prehistoric	-78.52832 40.10374	36BD0182	Prehistoric	-78.47665 40.03097
36BD0048	Prehistoric	-78.52178 40.09575	36BD0193	Prehistoric	-78.38659 39.92425
36BD0049	Prehistoric	-78.5272 40.0999	36BD0197	Prehistoric	-78.51824 40.17167
36BD0051	Prehistoric	-78.5141 40.0932	36BD0198	Prehistoric	-78.51957 40.16767
36BD0076	Prehistoric	-78.51145 40.09441	36BD0203	Prehistoric	-78.52331 40.10349

Table A-4. Region 4 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36BD0077	Prehistoric	-78.51465 40.09881	36BD0204	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.59358 40.00477
36BD0151	Prehistoric	-78.57007 39.93545	36BD0209	Prehistoric	-78.51889 40.0948
36BD0161	Prehistoric	-78.51602 40.08765	36BD0210	Prehistoric	-78.51818 40.09412
36BD0162	Prehistoric	-78.51668 40.08836	36BD0211	Prehistoric	-78.51703 40.09369
36BD0163	Prehistoric	-78.51397 40.08428	36BD0218	Prehistoric	-78.51298 40.09144
36BD0164	Prehistoric	-78.51654 40.08668	36BD0219	Prehistoric	-78.51778 40.09575
36BD0165	Prehistoric	-78.51974 40.08915	36BD0240	Prehistoric	-78.40231 40.01817
36BD0166	Prehistoric	-78.51521 40.08397	36BD0241	Prehistoric	-78.40151 40.01896
36BD0167	Prehistoric	-78.5171 40.08725	36BD0243	Prehistoric	-78.40076 40.0171
36BD0168	Prehistoric	-78.51981 40.08838	36BD0259	Prehistoric	-78.39332 39.97368
36BD0169	Prehistoric	-78.51872 40.08813	36BD0271	Prehistoric	-78.48649 40.03367
36BD0170	Prehistoric	-78.50994 40.08799	36BD0272	Prehistoric	-78.48489 40.03397
36BD0171	Prehistoric	-78.51173 40.0867	36BD0273	Prehistoric	-78.4828 40.03459
36BD0172	Prehistoric	-78.51271 40.08586	36BD0286	Prehistoric	-78.50456 40.09221
36BD0173	Prehistoric	-78.51415 40.0878	36BD0287	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.50449 39.99854
36BD0174	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.51471 40.08806	36BD0305	Prehistoric	-78.48928 39.93117
36BD0175	Prehistoric	-78.50466 40.08275	36BD0307	Prehistoric	-78.53173 39.92942
36BD0176	Prehistoric	-78.50411 40.08245	36BD0311	Prehistoric	-78.52774 40.10086
Watershed 84-Ridge and Valley-Appalachian Mountain:					
36CU0211	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.13248 40.29465			
Watershed 91-Ridge and Valley-Appalachian Mountain:					
36FR0044	Prehistoric	-77.86315 40.03117	36FR0065	Prehistoric	-77.78304 40.10041
36FR0061	Prehistoric	-77.76836 40.129	36FR0155	Prehistoric	-77.90101 39.74428
36FR0062	Prehistoric	-77.76885 40.13155	36FR0194	Prehistoric	-77.84561 40.05004
36FR0063	Prehistoric	-77.77296 40.12945	36FR0195	Prehistoric	-77.8452 40.04592
36FR0064	Prehistoric	-77.77273 40.11394	36FR0408	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.92776 39.89397
Watershed 100-Ridge and Valley-Appalachian Mountain:					
36BD0187	Prehistoric	-78.40293 39.79978	36FU0018	Prehistoric	-78.04876 39.84259
36BD0220	Prehistoric	-78.3274 39.8657	36FU0019	Prehistoric	-78.03426 39.84244
36BD0290	Prehistoric	-78.34175 39.88474	36FU0020	Prehistoric	-78.08225 39.78079
36BD0291	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.34208 39.88373	36FU0021	Prehistoric	-78.06513 40.00549
36BD0292	Prehistoric	-78.34147 39.88356	36FU0022	Prehistoric	-78.06435 40.00173
36BD0293	Prehistoric	-78.34134 39.88432	36FU0023	Prehistoric	-78.05975 39.98887
36BD0294	Prehistoric	-78.34248 39.88451	36FU0024	Prehistoric	-78.06115 39.98686
36BD0295	Prehistoric	-78.34612 39.88176	36FU0025	Prehistoric	-78.06376 39.98119
36BD0296	Prehistoric	-78.34691 39.88168	36FU0026	Prehistoric	-78.08326 39.94695
36BD0298	Prehistoric	-78.35365 39.88741	36FU0027	Prehistoric	-78.07866 39.94778
36BD0299	Prehistoric	-78.34851 39.89007	36FU0028	Prehistoric	-78.07711 39.94565
36BD0301	Prehistoric	-78.35072 39.89782	36FU0030	Prehistoric	-78.1402 39.83894
36BD0302	Prehistoric	-78.34515 39.87975	36FU0031	Prehistoric	-78.16781 39.75759
36BD0303	Prehistoric	-78.35148 39.88808	36FU0032	Prehistoric	-78.16382 39.75531
36BD0304	Prehistoric	-78.33062 39.89528	36FU0033	Prehistoric	-78.18508 39.75512
36FR0119	Prehistoric	-78.08706 39.7279	36FU0034	Prehistoric	-78.18254 39.7551
36FR0120	Prehistoric	-78.08608 39.7258	36FU0035	Prehistoric	-78.18279 39.75286
36FR0121	Prehistoric	-78.08539 39.73044	36FU0036	Prehistoric	-78.08629 39.73623
36FR0122	Prehistoric	-78.06481 39.72589	36FU0037	Prehistoric	-78.10189 39.84853
36FR0123	Prehistoric	-78.05435 39.72619	36FU0044	Prehistoric	-77.97298 40.01402
36FR0124	Prehistoric	-78.04833 39.7259	36FU0045	Prehistoric	-77.97148 40.01494
36FR0125	Prehistoric	-78.05742 39.72263	36FU0046	Prehistoric	-77.98447 40.00755
36FR0126	Prehistoric	-78.05105 39.72311	36FU0047	Prehistoric	-78.0551 39.99548

Table A-4. Region 4 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36FR0127	Prehistoric	-78.05092 39.72544	36FU0050	Prehistoric	-77.96283 39.99658
36FR0128	Prehistoric	-78.05429 39.72393	36FU0051	Prehistoric	-78.16305 39.83332
36FR0129	Prehistoric	-78.08508 39.73341	36FU0052	Prehistoric	-78.09489 39.8661
36FR0302	Prehistoric	-78.06676 39.72686	36FU0053	Prehistoric	-78.09251 39.79525
36FU0005	Prehistoric	-77.9611 40.0098	36FU0054	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.09063 39.7907
36FU0006	Prehistoric	-77.99149 39.94716	36FU0055	Prehistoric	-78.06689 39.97307
36FU0007	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.98601 39.8948	36FU0056	Prehistoric	-78.06734 39.97231
36FU0008	Prehistoric	-78.00904 39.91493	36FU0057	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.98765 39.89496
36FU0009	Prehistoric	-78.0075 39.91399	36FU0058	Prehistoric	-77.99134 39.89553
36FU0010	Prehistoric	-78.01195 39.90986	36FU0059	Prehistoric	-78.32024 39.72335
36FU0011	Prehistoric	-77.9967 39.92436	36FU0060	Prehistoric	-78.18099 39.75078
36FU0012	Prehistoric	-78.01421 39.91057	36FU0061	Prehistoric	-78.0036 39.89686
36FU0013	Prehistoric	-78.01404 39.90599	36FU0062	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.01948 39.89712
36FU0014	Prehistoric	-78.01485 39.8751	36FU0063	Prehistoric	-77.99413 39.92647
36FU0015	Prehistoric	-78.0266 39.87882	36FU0064	Prehistoric	-77.99409 39.92459
36FU0016	Prehistoric	-78.02577 39.88079	36FU0065	Prehistoric	-77.99958 39.9252
36FU0017	Prehistoric	-78.02846 39.88071	36FU0068	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.05887 39.98765
Watershed 102-Ridge and Valley-Appalachian Mountain:					
36BD0053	Prehistoric	-78.51466 39.83619	36BD0135	Prehistoric	-78.71442 39.83226
36BD0134	Prehistoric	-78.6963 39.871	36BD0136	Prehistoric	-78.714 39.83835

Table A-5. Region 5 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
Watershed 13-Ridge and Valley-Susquehanna Lowland:					
36CN0017	Prehistoric	-77.28607 41.18171	36CN0205	Prehistoric	-77.27917 41.17808
36CN0020	Prehistoric	-77.29414 41.18396	36CN0219	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.2794 41.18002
36CN0021	Prehistoric	-77.29564 41.18934	36LY0139	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.27044 41.17706
36CN0023	Prehistoric	-77.27855 41.17657	36LY0276	Prehistoric	-77.29003 41.18613
36CN0179	Prehistoric	-77.2746 41.17686			
Watershed 24-Ridge and Valley-Susquehanna Lowland:					
36CN0002	Prehistoric	-77.41441 41.1404	36CN0037	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.35948 41.1685
36CN0003	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.4113 41.14463	36CN0038	Prehistoric	-77.36566 41.16261
36CN0004	Prehistoric	-77.40133 41.14356	36CN0039	Prehistoric	-77.36687 41.16157
36CN0005	Prehistoric	-77.4018 41.14135	36CN0040	Prehistoric	-77.37028 41.15892
36CN0006	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.30793 41.16847	36CN0041	Prehistoric	-77.37178 41.15819
36CN0007	Prehistoric	-77.40387 41.14616	36CN0042	Prehistoric	-77.37541 41.15234
36CN0008	Prehistoric	-77.40223 41.14622	36CN0043	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.3798 41.15453
36CN0009	Prehistoric	-77.3982 41.14576	36CN0044	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.38724 41.14319
36CN0010	Prehistoric	-77.36896 41.16531	36CN0045	Prehistoric	-77.39817 41.13857
36CN0011	Prehistoric	-77.29253 41.16891	36CN0052	Prehistoric	-77.40527 41.14387
36CN0012	Prehistoric	-77.36233 41.16464	36CN0053	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.36666 41.16702
36CN0013	Prehistoric	-77.36466 41.16927	36CN0105	Prehistoric	-77.41278 41.1412
36CN0015	Prehistoric	-77.37859 41.15764	36CN0107	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.44204 41.13798
36CN0024	Prehistoric	-77.29783 41.17235	36CN0164	Prehistoric	-77.41762 41.13856
36CN0025	Prehistoric	-77.30299 41.17375	36CN0178	Prehistoric	-77.30533 41.17681
36CN0026	Prehistoric	-77.30548 41.17341	36CN0180	Prehistoric	-77.29646 41.17034
36CN0027	Prehistoric	-77.31112 41.17284	36CN0181	Prehistoric	-77.34324 41.17648
36CN0028	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.3171 41.17152	36CN0189	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.34498 41.16107
36CN0029	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.33281 41.16899	36CN0201	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.32565 41.16347
36CN0033	Prehistoric	-77.3039 41.16931	36CN0213	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.30788 41.17886
36CN0034	Prehistoric	-77.31421 41.16819	36CN0214	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.30612 41.17874
36CN0035	Prehistoric	-77.32347 41.1641	36CN0223	Prehistoric	-77.27221 41.17104
36CN0036	Prehistoric	-77.34793 41.17312			
Watershed 25-Ridge and Valley-Susquehanna Lowland:					
36LY0028	Prehistoric	-77.04227 41.26074	36LY0129	Prehistoric	-77.24443 41.20919
36LY0029	Prehistoric	-77.04713 41.2713	36LY0130	Prehistoric	-77.2429 41.20773
36LY0031	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.03849 41.22636	36LY0131	Prehistoric	-77.23976 41.20401
36LY0036	Prehistoric	-77.07212 41.30692	36LY0132	Prehistoric	-77.24044 41.21056
36LY0038	Prehistoric	-77.08086 41.31576	36LY0133	Prehistoric	-77.23557 41.18849
36LY0040	Prehistoric	-77.08621 41.31626	36LY0134	Prehistoric	-77.24512 41.19396
36LY0041	Prehistoric	-77.09026 41.32113	36LY0135	Prehistoric	-77.24432 41.19213
36LY0042	Prehistoric	-77.09528 41.32098	36LY0136	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.24334 41.18968
36LY0059	Prehistoric	-77.05593 41.22583	36LY0137	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.26092 41.17344
36LY0060	Prehistoric	-77.06263 41.22448	36LY0138	Prehistoric	-77.26758 41.17424
36LY0061	Prehistoric	-77.07212 41.22148	36LY0141	Prehistoric	-77.11155 41.22286
36LY0062	Prehistoric	-77.07429 41.22131	36LY0142	Prehistoric	-77.12233 41.22525
36LY0063	Prehistoric	-77.0919 41.23276	36LY0153	Prehistoric	-77.04296 41.22321
36LY0064	Prehistoric	-77.14266 41.23005	36LY0154	Prehistoric	-77.24087 41.20042
36LY0065	Prehistoric	-77.15647 41.218	36LY0155	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.06277 41.28361
36LY0066	Prehistoric	-77.15701 41.21631	36LY0157	Prehistoric	-77.06417 41.29141
36LY0067	Prehistoric	-77.21164 41.21518	36LY0158	Prehistoric	-77.06657 41.29116
36LY0068	Prehistoric	-77.21762 41.21891	36LY0159	Prehistoric	-77.08959 41.28973
36LY0069	Prehistoric	-77.22413 41.21681	36LY0161	Prehistoric	-77.09782 41.29495
36LY0070	Prehistoric	-77.19143 41.19861	36LY0162	Prehistoric	-77.11178 41.29195

Table A-5. Region 5 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LY0071	Prehistoric	-77.10836 41.22246	36LY0163	Prehistoric	-77.11354 41.29209
36LY0072	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.24487 41.20115	36LY0164	Prehistoric	-77.12273 41.29407
36LY0073	Prehistoric	-77.25471 41.17901	36LY0165	Prehistoric	-77.12635 41.29285
36LY0074	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.26549 41.1773	36LY0166	Prehistoric	-77.1416 41.29599
36LY0075	Prehistoric	-77.23738 41.19314	36LY0170	Prehistoric	-77.05256 41.22485
36LY0076	Prehistoric	-77.23867 41.18937	36LY0171	Prehistoric	-77.13829 41.23833
36LY0079	Prehistoric	-77.15148 41.21316	36LY0180	Prehistoric	-77.05571 41.29893
36LY0082	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.07767 41.2245	36LY0182	Prehistoric	-77.23665 41.19982
36LY0083	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.24698 41.20531	36LY0220	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.06336 41.28563
36LY0084	Prehistoric	-77.24267 41.19852	36LY0221	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.06044 41.28569
36LY0085	Prehistoric	-77.2342 41.21501	36LY0228	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.09554 41.31993
36LY0086	Prehistoric	-77.22992 41.21603	36LY0229	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.09535 41.32254
36LY0087	Prehistoric	-77.16475 41.20342	36LY0230	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.09381 41.32268
36LY0088	Prehistoric	-77.16203 41.2089	36LY0234	Prehistoric	-77.05761 41.29778
36LY0089	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.16064 41.21114	36LY0235	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.14907 41.22648
36LY0090	Prehistoric	-77.15829 41.21412	36LY0242	Prehistoric	-77.11696 41.2302
36LY0091	Prehistoric	-77.15501 41.20939	36LY0243	Prehistoric	-77.2149 41.21766
36LY0092	Prehistoric	-77.14834 41.21913	36LY0244	Prehistoric	-77.23937 41.21534
36LY0093	Prehistoric	-77.13181 41.23133	36LY0245	Prehistoric	-77.07675 41.3083
36LY0094	Prehistoric	-77.12368 41.22987	36LY0246	Prehistoric	-77.08022 41.30986
36LY0098	Prehistoric	-77.06067 41.30076	36LY0256	Prehistoric	-77.05057 41.27273
36LY0101	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.26157 41.17831	36LY0257	Prehistoric	-77.05397 41.27173
36LY0102	Prehistoric	-77.10434 41.22667	36LY0258	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.10041 41.2685
36LY0103	Prehistoric	-77.0613 41.28012	36LY0259	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.10407 41.26825
36LY0104	Prehistoric	-77.01908 41.22739	36LY0260	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.11501 41.26801
36LY0123	Prehistoric	-77.07255 41.22333	36LY0261	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.14782 41.26564
36LY0124	Prehistoric	-77.14643 41.22152	36LY0262	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.19157 41.2625
36LY0125	Prehistoric	-77.20821 41.20793	36LY0304	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.10573 41.23172
36LY0126	Prehistoric	-77.22012 41.21265	36LY0305	Prehistoric	-77.11954 41.22968
36LY0127	Prehistoric	-77.22564 41.21336	36LY0308	Prehistoric	-77.01902 41.23383
36LY0128	Prehistoric	-77.22926 41.21233	36LY0317	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.04172 41.2244
Watershed 26-Ridge and Valley-Susquehanna Lowland:					
36LY0013	Prehistoric	-76.93204 41.24764	36LY0173	Prehistoric	-76.91061 41.29783
36LY0014	Prehistoric	-76.93934 41.24615	36LY0178	Prehistoric	-76.93125 41.25536
36LY0020	Prehistoric	-76.91925 41.26989	36LY0222	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.95669 41.27755
36LY0035	Prehistoric	-76.93087 41.24147	36LY0223	Prehistoric	-76.93239 41.27908
36LY0039	Prehistoric	-77.05441 41.29825	36LY0224	Prehistoric	-76.90819 41.28044
36LY0045	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.91381 41.28885	36LY0225	Prehistoric	-76.91909 41.26034
36LY0046	Prehistoric	-76.90605 41.29111	36LY0252	Prehistoric	-76.915 41.28043
36LY0047	Prehistoric	-76.9146 41.31782	36LY0253	Prehistoric	-76.97991 41.27533
36LY0077	Prehistoric	-77.03618 41.31518	36LY0255	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.02483 41.27408
36LY0078	Prehistoric	-77.0251 41.3189	36LY0275	Prehistoric	-76.9425 41.23787
36LY0146	Prehistoric	-76.91298 41.30569	36LY0288	Prehistoric	-76.94157 41.23959
36LY0147	Prehistoric	-76.92128 41.31895	36LY0309	Prehistoric	-76.94171 41.24158
Watershed 31-Ridge and Valley-Susquehanna Lowland:					
36CO0012	Prehistoric	-76.56509 41.08669	36MO0052	Prehistoric	-76.6645 41.05297
36LY0002	Prehistoric	-76.81924 41.23018	36MO0053	Prehistoric	-76.66501 41.05389
36LY0004	Prehistoric	-76.83592 41.23441	36MO0054	Prehistoric	-76.66568 41.05462
36LY0005	Prehistoric	-76.84195 41.23711	36MO0055	Prehistoric	-76.66596 41.05548
36LY0006	Prehistoric	-76.8404 41.23524	36MO0056	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.6654 41.05657
36LY0009	Prehistoric	-76.79616 41.21486	36MO0057	Prehistoric	-76.66562 41.0576
36LY0010	Prehistoric	-76.86511 41.2354	36MO0058	Prehistoric	-76.70261 41.086

Table A-5. Region 5 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LY0015	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.83031 41.23588	36MO0059	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.65741 41.05842
36LY0016	Prehistoric	-76.83744 41.23678	36MO0060	Prehistoric	-76.72979 41.01721
36LY0021	Prehistoric	-76.74555 41.20534	36MO0061	Prehistoric	-76.68002 41.08419
36LY0022	Prehistoric	-76.75482 41.2124	36MO0062	Prehistoric	-76.69968 41.02553
36LY0023	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.79054 41.21088	36MO0063	Prehistoric	-76.70085 41.02513
36LY0081	Prehistoric	-76.78296 41.21825	36MO0064	Prehistoric	-76.6817 41.08804
36LY0109	Prehistoric	-76.79741 41.21195	36MO0065	Prehistoric	-76.65855 41.08413
36LY0110	Prehistoric	-76.80196 41.21363	36MO0066	Prehistoric	-76.66978 41.0819
36LY0111	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.80513 41.22102	36MO0067	Prehistoric	-76.66776 41.08465
36LY0112	Prehistoric	-76.81086 41.22374	36MO0068	Prehistoric	-76.723 41.11328
36LY0113	Prehistoric	-76.81239 41.22495	36MO0069	Prehistoric	-76.6794 41.03827
36LY0115	Prehistoric	-76.86169 41.23283	36MO0070	Prehistoric	-76.68157 41.04069
36LY0116	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.87263 41.23624	36MO0071	Prehistoric	-76.68396 41.03963
36LY0144	Prehistoric	-76.8699 41.23928	36MO0072	Prehistoric	-76.72802 41.01785
36LY0183	Prehistoric	-76.6323 41.198	36MO0073	Prehistoric	-76.77256 40.98727
36LY0185	Prehistoric	-76.66351 41.18777	36MO0075	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.66077 41.06481
36LY0186	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.68032 41.1782	36MO0076	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.66319 41.06232
36LY0187	Prehistoric	-76.67026 41.18633	36MO0077	Prehistoric	-76.77243 40.98767
36LY0188	Prehistoric	-76.6737 41.17757	36MO0078	Prehistoric	-76.77381 40.98841
36LY0189	Prehistoric	-76.69657 41.18532	36MO0079	Prehistoric	-76.69096 41.08369
36LY0190	Prehistoric	-76.80205 41.21612	36MO0080	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.65689 41.06843
36LY0191	Prehistoric	-76.80136 41.21802	36MO0081	Prehistoric	-76.66394 41.05436
36LY0192	Prehistoric	-76.8031 41.21786	36MO0083	Prehistoric	-76.72113 41.08903
36LY0196	Prehistoric	-76.79026 41.20918	36MO0084	Prehistoric	-76.68288 41.0744
36LY0200	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.79578 41.20722	36MO0085	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.68116 41.0745
36LY0202	Prehistoric	-76.77589 41.19889	36MO0086	Prehistoric	-76.67653 41.0734
36LY0203	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.75878 41.21356	36NB0001	Prehistoric	-76.84713 40.91869
36LY0207	Prehistoric	-76.85764 41.23489	36NB0003	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.88687 41.10896
36LY0214	Prehistoric	-76.75804 41.21014	36NB0013	Prehistoric	-76.86878 40.94994
36LY0215	Prehistoric	-76.76112 41.2152	36NB0014	Prehistoric	-76.87844 41.0984
36LY0216	Prehistoric	-76.80165 41.21281	36NB0018	Prehistoric	-76.86242 41.00029
36LY0217	Prehistoric	-76.80243 41.21443	36NB0019	Prehistoric	-76.87047 40.98366
36LY0218	Prehistoric	-76.79893 41.21425	36NB0020	Prehistoric	-76.87434 40.97701
36LY0219	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.79444 41.2144	36NB0021	Prehistoric	-76.8598 40.93603
36LY0238	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.71569 41.25788	36NB0022	Prehistoric	-76.84079 40.91438
36LY0241	Prehistoric	-76.90316 41.23454	36NB0023	Prehistoric	-76.85078 40.92214
36LY0249	Prehistoric	-76.79779 41.27767	36NB0024	Prehistoric	-76.85658 40.93022
36LY0250	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.86786 41.27908	36NB0025	Prehistoric	-76.87061 40.9586
36LY0264	Prehistoric	-76.73488 41.22276	36NB0026	Prehistoric	-76.86606 40.98932
36LY0265	Prehistoric	-76.73474 41.22374	36NB0028	Prehistoric	-76.86454 40.94463
36LY0266	Prehistoric	-76.73632 41.22472	36NB0029	Prehistoric	-76.86206 40.94357
36LY0267	Prehistoric	-76.67737 41.17757	36NB0032	Prehistoric	-76.85659 40.9325
36LY0268	Prehistoric	-76.81231 41.22606	36NB0033	Prehistoric	-76.85839 40.93348
36LY0272	Prehistoric	-76.82359 41.23676	36NB0034	Prehistoric	-76.85604 40.93506
36LY0273	Prehistoric	-76.82149 41.23809	36NB0035	Prehistoric	-76.85227 40.93573
36LY0274	Prehistoric	-76.81952 41.23681	36NB0036	Prehistoric	-76.85653 40.93714
36LY0277	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.87278 41.23713	36NB0037	Prehistoric	-76.78127 40.98189
36LY0278	Prehistoric	-76.80884 41.22174	36NB0038	Prehistoric	-76.78054 40.98477
36LY0279	Prehistoric	-76.80823 41.22194	36NB0039	Prehistoric	-76.77699 41.00096
36LY0280	Prehistoric	-76.80682 41.22433	36NB0040	Prehistoric	-76.80615 40.97361
36LY0281	Prehistoric	-76.80589 41.22442	36NB0041	Prehistoric	-76.81681 40.96856
36LY0282	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.80592 41.22344	36NB0042	Prehistoric	-76.81351 40.96718
36LY0283	Prehistoric	-76.87067 41.23458	36NB0043	Prehistoric	-76.80859 40.96866

Table A-5. Region 5 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LY0284	Prehistoric	-76.87599 41.23853	36NB0044	Prehistoric	-76.78089 40.99192
36LY0285	Prehistoric	-76.87516 41.23812	36NB0045	Prehistoric	-76.77734 40.99152
36LY0286	Prehistoric	-76.87614 41.23774	36NB0048	Prehistoric	-76.85412 40.9319
36LY0289	Prehistoric	-76.73674 41.22268	36NB0069	Prehistoric	-76.8452 40.9125
36LY0290	Prehistoric	-76.73593 41.22237	36NB0106	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.79612 41.10207
36LY0291	Prehistoric	-76.73653 41.22223	36NB0107	Prehistoric	-76.79581 41.10461
36LY0292	Prehistoric	-76.82406 41.27914	36NB0109	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.88373 41.10955
36LY0298	Prehistoric	-76.76 41.21167	36NB0113	Prehistoric	-76.86061 41.01743
36LY0299	Prehistoric	-76.7628 41.2135	36NB0115	Prehistoric	-76.8754 40.96636
36LY0300	Prehistoric	-76.75652 41.21297	36NB0123	Prehistoric	-76.85213 41.07474
36LY0307	Prehistoric	-76.7479 41.21537	36NB0124	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.85278 41.0717
36LY0312	Prehistoric	-76.64583 41.31378	36NB0125	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.8085 41.09246
36MO0001	Prehistoric	-76.77443 40.98655	36NB0126	Prehistoric	-76.83305 41.07575
36MO0002	Prehistoric	-76.77302 40.99728	36NB0127	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.85491 41.10506
36MO0003	Prehistoric	-76.76939 41.001	36NB0128	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.86365 41.11657
36MO0004	Prehistoric	-76.7645 41.00343	36NB0129	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.86407 41.11715
36MO0005	Prehistoric	-76.76722 41.00568	36NB0131	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.85445 40.94028
36MO0006	Prehistoric	-76.70786 41.02522	36NB0132	Prehistoric	-76.84586 41.03495
36MO0007	Prehistoric	-76.69993 41.03324	36NB0133	Prehistoric	-76.85699 40.934
36MO0008	Prehistoric	-76.69764 41.03253	36NB0134	Prehistoric	-76.85338 40.93778
36MO0009	Prehistoric	-76.67777 41.03948	36NB0135	Prehistoric	-76.8667 40.97942
36MO0010	Prehistoric	-76.67646 41.0466	36NB0136	Prehistoric	-76.86416 40.99123
36MO0011	Prehistoric	-76.68016 41.05588	36NB0142	Prehistoric	-76.85472 40.93538
36MO0012	Prehistoric	-76.6799 41.05995	36NB0143	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.85124 40.9366
36MO0013	Prehistoric	-76.68387 41.06712	36NB0144	Prehistoric	-76.87417 40.9738
36MO0014	Prehistoric	-76.68463 41.07346	36NB0145	Prehistoric	-76.8236 40.95267
36MO0015	Prehistoric	-76.68008 41.07211	36NB0146	Prehistoric	-76.805 40.97495
36MO0016	Prehistoric	-76.6808 41.07319	36NB0147	Prehistoric	-76.78387 40.9827
36MO0017	Prehistoric	-76.68468 41.07662	36NB0148	Prehistoric	-76.85387 40.92896
36MO0018	Prehistoric	-76.69302 41.0845	36NB0149	Prehistoric	-76.86894 40.95625
36MO0019	Prehistoric	-76.69532 41.08523	36NB0150	Prehistoric	-76.84592 41.04841
36MO0020	Prehistoric	-76.69782 41.08633	36NB0151	Prehistoric	-76.87581 40.9717
36MO0021	Prehistoric	-76.68197 41.08243	36NB0152	Prehistoric	-76.87418 40.96614
36MO0022	Prehistoric	-76.68019 41.08509	36NB0153	Prehistoric	-76.87031 40.97309
36MO0023	Prehistoric	-76.67475 41.07637	36NB0154	Prehistoric	-76.79137 41.11653
36MO0024	Prehistoric	-76.67331 41.07791	36NB0172	Prehistoric	-76.85049 40.97495
36MO0025	Prehistoric	-76.67213 41.08011	36NB0181	Prehistoric	-76.79974 40.97496
36MO0026	Prehistoric	-76.66759 41.08068	36NB0187	Prehistoric	-76.79157 41.10671
36MO0027	Prehistoric	-76.6653 41.08146	36NB0188	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.87168 41.09055
36MO0028	Prehistoric	-76.66358 41.08253	36UN0011	Prehistoric	-76.88338 40.97259
36MO0029	Prehistoric	-76.66631 41.08225	36UN0012	Prehistoric	-76.879 40.97989
36MO0030	Prehistoric	-76.66275 41.0861	36UN0013	Prehistoric	-76.86945 40.99596
36MO0031	Prehistoric	-76.65571 41.08337	36UN0015	Prehistoric	-76.84983 40.91078
36MO0032	Prehistoric	-76.65291 41.08415	36UN0016	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.83472 40.89854
36MO0033	Prehistoric	-76.6474 41.05923	36UN0018	Prehistoric	-76.86053 40.92439
36MO0034	Prehistoric	-76.67382 41.06821	36UN0023	Prehistoric	-76.86811 41.00922
36MO0035	Prehistoric	-76.68422 41.04202	36UN0133	Prehistoric	-76.88262 40.97422
36MO0036	Prehistoric	-76.6825 41.04315	36UN0134	Prehistoric	-76.88078 40.9757
36MO0037	Prehistoric	-76.68074 41.04455	36UN0135	Prehistoric	-76.87514 40.98637
36MO0038	Prehistoric	-76.72409 41.02685	36UN0136	Prehistoric	-76.88294 40.98068
Watershed 32-Ridge and Valley-Susquehanna Lowland:					
36LU0007	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.05391 41.2674	36LU0093	Prehistoric	-75.95635 41.11552

Table A-5. Region 5 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LU0179	Prehistoric	-75.97286 40.96897	36LU0196	Prehistoric	-75.93069 41.06071
36LU0184	Prehistoric	-75.92183 41.06555	36LU0197	Prehistoric	-75.96627 41.02071
36LU0185	Prehistoric	-75.91151 41.07552	36LU0198	Prehistoric	-75.95886 41.0355
36LU0189	Prehistoric	-76.00299 40.9635	36LU0199	Prehistoric	-75.92822 41.05281
36LU0190	Prehistoric	-76.0254 40.96993	36LU0266	Prehistoric	-75.85662 40.99425
Watershed 42-Ridge and Valley-Susquehanna Lowland:					
36CO0001	Prehistoric	-76.34634 41.02213	36CO0025	Prehistoric	-76.43073 40.99768
36CO0002	Prehistoric	-76.23324 41.04886	36CO0028	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.26864 41.07111
36CO0010	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.44075 40.99399	36CO0031	Prehistoric	-76.27161 41.04063
36CO0014	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.45933 40.98588	36CO0033	Prehistoric	-76.32927 41.03036
36CO0015	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.31495 41.03822	36CO0034	Prehistoric	-76.3285 41.02987
36CO0016	Prehistoric	-76.31456 41.03663	36CO0035	Prehistoric	-76.32289 41.02668
36CO0017	Prehistoric	-76.3107 41.03806	36CO0036	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.46266 40.9835
36CO0018	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.30862 41.03408	36CO0037	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.46602 40.98055
36CO0019	Prehistoric	-76.2842 41.045	36LU0282	Prehistoric	-76.16673 41.08711
36CO0020	Prehistoric	-76.43353 40.99709	36LU0301	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.17073 41.08517
36CO0024	Prehistoric	-76.42806 40.99893			
Watershed 46-Ridge and Valley-Anthracite Upland:					
36SC0049	Prehistoric	-76.15122 40.86014	36SC0067	Prehistoric	-76.16368 40.93615
Watershed 46-Ridge and Valley-Susquehanna Lowland:					
36CO0004	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.52586 40.93729	36NB0079	Prehistoric	-76.72346 40.92723
36CO0006	Prehistoric	-76.43599 40.93264	36NB0080	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.72218 40.92799
36CO0009	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.47009 40.95491	36NB0081	Prehistoric	-76.67621 40.95073
36MO0039	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.55666 40.93573	36NB0082	Prehistoric	-76.68186 40.94691
36MO0040	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.54646 40.93488	36NB0083	Prehistoric	-76.68295 40.94614
36MO0041	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.54495 40.93487	36NB0084	Prehistoric	-76.69242 40.94102
36MO0042	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.52792 40.93677	36NB0085	Prehistoric	-76.69339 40.94064
36MO0043	Prehistoric	-76.63293 40.96722	36NB0086	Prehistoric	-76.69566 40.93903
36MO0044	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.62985 40.96582	36NB0087	Prehistoric	-76.69708 40.93831
36MO0045	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.58146 40.94723	36NB0088	Prehistoric	-76.69911 40.93793
36MO0046	Prehistoric	-76.60161 40.94753	36NB0089	Prehistoric	-76.70394 40.93648
36MO0047	Prehistoric	-76.59383 40.945	36NB0090	Prehistoric	-76.70277 40.93683
36MO0048	Prehistoric	-76.55732 40.9415	36NB0091	Prehistoric	-76.70738 40.93615
36MO0049	Prehistoric	-76.54938 40.94011	36NB0092	Prehistoric	-76.72228 40.93197
36MO0050	Prehistoric	-76.64077 40.96999	36NB0093	Prehistoric	-76.72309 40.93135
36MO0051	Prehistoric	-76.6272 41.00408	36NB0094	Prehistoric	-76.72348 40.93067
36NB0004	Prehistoric	-76.7701 40.90335	36NB0095	Prehistoric	-76.7365 40.91968
36NB0027	Prehistoric	-76.77621 40.89326	36NB0096	Prehistoric	-76.73744 40.91942
36NB0063	Prehistoric	-76.77161 40.90162	36NB0097	Prehistoric	-76.73875 40.91878
36NB0064	Prehistoric	-76.768 40.90398	36NB0098	Prehistoric	-76.74976 40.91431
36NB0065	Prehistoric	-76.76536 40.9064	36NB0099	Prehistoric	-76.73927 40.91948
36NB0066	Prehistoric	-76.76241 40.9078	36NB0100	Prehistoric	-76.74092 40.91817
36NB0067	Prehistoric	-76.75924 40.90855	36NB0101	Prehistoric	-76.74233 40.91779
36NB0068	Prehistoric	-76.74534 40.91333	36NB0102	Prehistoric	-76.78098 40.89638
36NB0070	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.78975 40.89035	36NB0103	Prehistoric	-76.72534 40.92712
36NB0072	Prehistoric	-76.57808 40.92268	36NB0114	Prehistoric	-76.72563 40.9238
36NB0073	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.55956 40.9372	36NB0117	Prehistoric	-76.72754 40.92053
36NB0074	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.58456 40.93808	36NB0118	Prehistoric	-76.71686 40.92911
36NB0075	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.59054 40.93755	36NB0120	Prehistoric	-76.72936 40.91702
36NB0076	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.59457 40.93846	36NB0159	Prehistoric	-76.58665 40.91895
36NB0077	Prehistoric	-76.63779 40.96279	36NB0184	Prehistoric	-76.78475 40.87851

Table A-5. Region 5 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36SN0135	Prehistoric	-77.19576 40.76889	36UN0042	Prehistoric	-77.15677 40.87915
36SN0136	Prehistoric	-77.19131 40.77283	36UN0043	Prehistoric	-77.1434 40.87868
36SN0137	Prehistoric	-77.18918 40.77686	36UN0044	Prehistoric	-77.13133 40.87908
36SN0138	Prehistoric	-77.18635 40.77787	36UN0045	Prehistoric	-76.99388 40.87521
36SN0139	Prehistoric	-77.05774 40.7827	36UN0046	Prehistoric	-77.13511 40.88192
36SN0140	Prehistoric	-77.0684 40.82376	36UN0047	Prehistoric	-77.1573 40.87673
36SN0141	Prehistoric	-77.05954 40.84731	36UN0049	Prehistoric	-77.11745 40.87483
36SN0142	Prehistoric	-77.04572 40.86526	36UN0050	Prehistoric	-77.0485 40.86909
36SN0143	Prehistoric	-77.05224 40.86682	36UN0054	Prehistoric	-77.17059 40.87299
36SN0144	Prehistoric	-77.05135 40.86515	36UN0055	Prehistoric	-77.13757 40.88189
36SN0145	Prehistoric	-77.05407 40.86426	36UN0056	Prehistoric	-77.01711 40.86058
36SN0146	Prehistoric	-77.05494 40.85681	36UN0057	Prehistoric	-77.1776 40.87673
36SN0147	Prehistoric	-77.03184 40.86238	36UN0058	Prehistoric	-77.1392 40.88159
36SN0148	Prehistoric	-77.03321 40.86089	36UN0087	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.15259 40.90147
36SN0149	Prehistoric	-77.03042 40.86013	36UN0088	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.14838 40.90158
36SN0150	Prehistoric	-77.01234 40.86024	36UN0089	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.15159 40.90106
36SN0151	Prehistoric	-77.04682 40.79702	36UN0095	Prehistoric	-77.15263 40.89852
36SN0152	Prehistoric	-77.0551 40.81676	36UN0098	Prehistoric	-76.9937 40.87746
36SN0153	Prehistoric	-77.04195 40.7899	36UN0105	Prehistoric	-77.01124 40.86954
36SN0154	Prehistoric	-77.03516 40.79161	36UN0106	Prehistoric	-77.03714 40.86608
36SN0155	Prehistoric	-77.02969 40.79343	36UN0107	Prehistoric	-77.04002 40.86428
36SN0156	Prehistoric	-77.02724 40.79344	36UN0108	Prehistoric	-77.10146 40.87479
36SN0157	Prehistoric	-77.0196 40.79395	36UN0109	Prehistoric	-77.00867 40.87111
36SN0160	Prehistoric	-77.00441 40.79666	36UN0111	Prehistoric	-77.21814 40.86359
36SN0161	Prehistoric	-77.00088 40.79958	36UN0112	Prehistoric	-77.18865 40.87233
36SN0162	Prehistoric	-76.99131 40.80538	36UN0113	Prehistoric	-77.12391 40.88311
36SN0163	Prehistoric	-76.98603 40.80202	36UN0121	Prehistoric	-77.03113 40.88034
36SN0164	Prehistoric	-76.98351 40.80318	36UN0122	Prehistoric	-77.15235 40.88659
36SN0165	Prehistoric	-76.97987 40.80374	36UN0123	Prehistoric	-77.15482 40.88369
36SN0166	Prehistoric	-76.9821 40.80565	36UN0124	Prehistoric	-77.14959 40.88602
36SN0167	Prehistoric	-76.98094 40.80728	36UN0125	Prehistoric	-77.14082 40.88866
36SN0168	Prehistoric	-76.98815 40.80749	36UN0126	Prehistoric	-77.13847 40.88899
36SN0169	Prehistoric	-76.97116 40.80425	36UN0127	Prehistoric	-77.17476 40.87867
36SN0170	Prehistoric	-76.96815 40.8067	36UN0128	Prehistoric	-76.97391 40.87833
36SN0171	Prehistoric	-76.95873 40.80665	36UN0131	Prehistoric	-76.9922 40.87598
36SN0172	Prehistoric	-76.99526 40.8711	36UN0137	Prehistoric	-77.02173 40.85952
36SN0173	Prehistoric	-76.99072 40.87409	36UN0138	Prehistoric	-77.01312 40.86714
36SN0174	Prehistoric	-76.96755 40.87605			
Watershed 52-Ridge and Valley-Anthracite Upland:					
36SC0001	Prehistoric	-76.27894 40.68068	36SC0007	Prehistoric	-76.25725 40.66514
36SC0002	Prehistoric	-76.27008 40.64424	36SC0046	Prehistoric	-76.19929 40.66965
36SC0003	Prehistoric	-76.23654 40.68361	36SC0065	Prehistoric	-76.02448 40.82092
36SC0006	Prehistoric	-76.25159 40.69624	36SC0069	Prehistoric	-76.26925 40.65906
Watershed 53-Ridge and Valley-Anthracite Upland:					
36NB0108	Prehistoric	-76.54753 40.74084			
Watershed 53-Ridge and Valley-Susquehanna Lowland:					
36NB0051	Prehistoric	-76.83828 40.72216	36SN0014	Prehistoric	-76.86008 40.7795
36NB0052	Prehistoric	-76.84806 40.71778	36SN0015	Prehistoric	-76.85954 40.77433
36NB0053	Prehistoric	-76.83598 40.73357	36SN0016	Prehistoric	-76.85968 40.7692
36NB0054	Prehistoric	-76.84006 40.72731	36SN0018	Prehistoric	-76.85903 40.76386
36NB0055	Prehistoric	-76.83944 40.75468	36SN0019	Prehistoric	-76.8578 40.7545

Table A-5. Region 5 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36DA0043	Prehistoric	-76.93735 40.60426	36PE0045	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.95258 40.48864
36DA0044	Prehistoric	-76.94821 40.6146	36PE0046	Prehistoric	-76.99015 40.44099
36DA0045	Prehistoric	-77.00237 40.41835	36PE0051	Prehistoric	-76.95772 40.46093
36DA0046	Prehistoric	-77.00189 40.40955	36PE0052	Prehistoric	-76.99124 40.44116
36DA0047	Prehistoric	-76.9937 40.41636	36PE0054	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.96714 40.49524
36DA0049	Prehistoric	-76.99004 40.436	36PE0060	Prehistoric	-76.98188 40.57953
36DA0112	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.00691 40.40316	36PE0061	Prehistoric	-76.95349 40.61483
36DA0122	Prehistoric	-76.93116 40.48614	36PE0079	Prehistoric	-76.99581 40.56775
36DA0126	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.01037 40.40204	36SC0056	Prehistoric	-76.68796 40.66087
36DA0140	Prehistoric	-76.83418 40.4928	36SN0024	Prehistoric	-76.90972 40.67135
36DA0141	Prehistoric	-76.83084 40.48605	36SN0025	Prehistoric	-76.91709 40.66406
36DA0147	Prehistoric	-76.93302 40.48209	36SN0026	Prehistoric	-76.91964 40.66007
36DA0153	Prehistoric	-76.82365 40.48022	36SN0027	Prehistoric	-76.92119 40.65535
36DA0154	Prehistoric	-76.81336 40.47999	36SN0029	Prehistoric	-76.92775 40.64728
36JU0004	Prehistoric	-76.94076 40.63789	36SN0030	Prehistoric	-76.93491 40.64209
36JU0040	Prehistoric	-76.94803 40.63162	36SN0039	Prehistoric	-76.94067 40.64883
36JU0090	Prehistoric	-76.94752 40.64268	36SN0197	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.9246 40.65217
36JU0093	Prehistoric	-76.94501 40.63771	36SN0220	Prehistoric	-76.91173 40.66815
36JU0094	Prehistoric	-76.94158 40.64024	36SN0221	Prehistoric	-76.92919 40.6489
36JU0095	Prehistoric	-76.94025 40.64114	36SN0222	Prehistoric	-76.93033 40.64948
36JU0097	Prehistoric	-77.10914 40.68994	36SN0226	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.889 40.68315
36JU0098	Prehistoric	-77.10778 40.69024	36SN0227	Prehistoric	-76.93752 40.64306
36NB0002	Prehistoric	-76.88764 40.67112	36SN0228	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.93562 40.64461
36NB0049	Prehistoric	-76.93272 40.62453	36SN0229	Prehistoric	-76.87085 40.69829
36NB0050	Prehistoric	-76.88414 40.672	36SN0230	Prehistoric	-76.86807 40.70151
36NB0138	Prehistoric	-76.90791 40.64844	36SN0237	Prehistoric	-77.11809 40.69369
36NB0141	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.90687 40.6495	36SN0238	Prehistoric	-77.11815 40.69295
36NB0160	Prehistoric	-76.90637 40.64693	36SN0239	Prehistoric	-77.11756 40.69133
36NB0161	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.93979 40.63411	36SN0240	Prehistoric	-77.1027 40.69038
36NB0162	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.93203 40.63737	36SN0241	Prehistoric	-77.10256 40.69264
36NB0163	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.91439 40.64569	36SN0263	Prehistoric	-77.0177 40.727
36NB0164	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.91787 40.65436	36SN0268	Prehistoric	-76.87028 40.69999
36NB0165	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.91695 40.65798	36SN0271	Prehistoric	-77.10099 40.68942
Watershed 64-Ridge and Valley-Susquehanna Lowland:					
36JU0002	Prehistoric	-77.32855 40.52534	36JU0046	Prehistoric	-77.28327 40.53927
36JU0003	Prehistoric	-77.20526 40.56946	36JU0047	Prehistoric	-77.28413 40.5406
36JU0006	Prehistoric	-77.24414 40.55397	36JU0048	Prehistoric	-77.27869 40.54046
36JU0007	Prehistoric	-77.28153 40.54046	36JU0049	Prehistoric	-77.27986 40.5411
36JU0008	Prehistoric	-77.22269 40.56062	36JU0050	Prehistoric	-77.25441 40.54989
36JU0009	Prehistoric	-77.23586 40.55569	36JU0051	Prehistoric	-77.25453 40.55095
36JU0010	Prehistoric	-77.19891 40.56339	36JU0052	Prehistoric	-77.2509 40.55208
36JU0012	Prehistoric	-77.34645 40.53352	36JU0053	Prehistoric	-77.22812 40.55752
36JU0013	Prehistoric	-77.38968 40.54735	36JU0054	Prehistoric	-77.21339 40.56733
36JU0020	Prehistoric	-77.36785 40.53059	36JU0055	Prehistoric	-77.21321 40.56843
36JU0022	Prehistoric	-77.29597 40.56546	36JU0056	Prehistoric	-77.2073 40.56458
36JU0023	Prehistoric	-77.23223 40.55741	36JU0057	Prehistoric	-77.20137 40.56339
36JU0026	Prehistoric	-77.20549 40.57022	36JU0064	Prehistoric	-77.38119 40.53277
36JU0028	Prehistoric	-77.32554 40.55408	36JU0100	Prehistoric	-77.23706 40.55506
36JU0029	Prehistoric	-77.33561 40.52981	36JU0111	Prehistoric	-77.38359 40.53511
36JU0030	Prehistoric	-77.20275 40.57071	36JU0119	Prehistoric	-77.39849 40.56401
36JU0032	Prehistoric	-77.29921 40.53639	36JU0120	Prehistoric	-77.3986 40.56324
36JU0033	Prehistoric	-77.36622 40.53046	36JU0121	Prehistoric	-77.39788 40.56324

Table A-5. Region 5 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36JU0034	Prehistoric	-77.39004 40.5283	36JU0122	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.40196 40.56606
36JU0035	Prehistoric	-77.38585 40.52785	36PE0019	Prehistoric	-77.14752 40.53807
36JU0036	Prehistoric	-77.38456 40.53017	36PE0020	Prehistoric	-77.13058 40.516
36JU0037	Prehistoric	-77.39198 40.54443	36PE0021	Prehistoric	-77.09361 40.4897
36JU0038	Prehistoric	-77.38951 40.54238	36PE0022	Prehistoric	-77.01643 40.42794
36JU0041	Prehistoric	-77.32405 40.52622	36PE0023	Prehistoric	-77.11514 40.47125
36JU0042	Prehistoric	-77.3153 40.5306	36PE0025	Prehistoric	-77.13783 40.52643
36JU0043	Prehistoric	-77.29101 40.53817	36PE0026	Prehistoric	-77.14601 40.53645
36JU0044	Prehistoric	-77.2986 40.53558	36PE0027	Prehistoric	-77.1441 40.55369
36JU0045	Prehistoric	-77.2994 40.53737			
Watershed 70-Ridge and Valley-Anthracite Upland:					
36DA0019	Prehistoric	-77.00495 40.3598	36DA0175	Prehistoric	-77.00575 40.37923
36DA0021	Prehistoric	-76.94394 40.3589	36DA0176	Prehistoric	-77.00153 40.37777
36DA0030	Prehistoric	-76.97318 40.35925	36DA0177	Prehistoric	-77.00291 40.37758
36DA0031	Prehistoric	-76.99211 40.36951	36DA0178	Prehistoric	-76.99603 40.37466
36DA0114	Prehistoric	-76.99391 40.37038	36DA0179	Prehistoric	-76.95977 40.37061
36DA0115	Prehistoric	-76.99371 40.37126	36DA0180	Prehistoric	-76.94891 40.36905
36DA0116	Prehistoric	-76.95245 40.37705	36DA0181	Prehistoric	-76.92935 40.36538
36DA0130	Prehistoric	-76.9965 40.37067	36DA0195	Prehistoric	-76.95606 40.36917
36DA0131	Prehistoric	-76.99769 40.37157	36DA0234	Prehistoric	-76.68802 40.45283
36DA0132	Prehistoric	-76.99759 40.37323	36PE0036	Prehistoric	-77.02394 40.36582
36DA0134	Prehistoric	-76.93621 40.36627	36PE0073	Prehistoric	-76.97925 40.35645
36DA0158	Prehistoric	-76.94052 40.36881	36PE0074	Prehistoric	-76.9858 40.35639
36DA0167	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.92834 40.36415	36PE0075	Prehistoric	-77.00406 40.35617
Watershed 77-Ridge and Valley-Susquehanna Lowland:					
36PE0001	Prehistoric	-77.31255 40.3697	36PE0030	Prehistoric	-77.26862 40.31554
36PE0002	Prehistoric	-77.22748 40.34265	36PE0031	Prehistoric	-77.50454 40.34735
36PE0003	Prehistoric	-77.3082 40.341	36PE0032	Prehistoric	-77.37356 40.35355
36PE0004	Prehistoric	-77.27111 40.31714	36PE0033	Prehistoric	-77.36823 40.35402
36PE0006	Prehistoric	-77.23062 40.33806	36PE0034	Prehistoric	-77.4301 40.35731
36PE0007	Prehistoric	-77.21345 40.34976	36PE0035	Prehistoric	-77.48949 40.33158
36PE0008	Prehistoric	-77.19174 40.34482	36PE0036	Prehistoric	-77.47767 40.33117
36PE0009	Prehistoric	-77.18273 40.3327	36PE0039	Prehistoric	-77.42716 40.35722
36PE0012	Prehistoric	-77.31525 40.36212	36PE0040	Prehistoric	-77.33897 40.38353
36PE0013	Prehistoric	-77.31552 40.35002	36PE0041	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.31256 40.34274
36PE0014	Prehistoric	-77.28791 40.32773	36PE0068	Prehistoric	-77.52748 40.32714
36PE0018	Prehistoric	-77.11035 40.44415	36PE0069	Prehistoric	-77.53709 40.33392
36PE0024	Prehistoric	-77.27433 40.32299	36PE0071	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.16972 40.32304
36PE0028	Prehistoric	-77.27603 40.3206	36PE0072	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.16881 40.32242
36PE0029	Prehistoric	-77.27283 40.31444			

Table A-6. Region 6 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36WA0016	Prehistoric	-78.95213 41.88122	36WA0305	Prehistoric	-78.92775 41.9922
36WA0017	Prehistoric	-78.95101 41.88267	36WA0324	Prehistoric	-78.99266 41.85904
36WA0018	Prehistoric	-78.95628 41.88462	36WA0344	Prehistoric	-78.93284 41.87991
36WA0019	Prehistoric	-78.95515 41.88539	36WA0348	Prehistoric	-78.95416 41.81409
36WA0020	Prehistoric	-78.95118 41.88524	36WA0359	Prehistoric	-78.94449 41.89766
Watershed 8-Appalachian Plateaus-Deep Valleys:					
36TI0039	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.01939 41.91954	36TI0101	Prehistoric	-77.29291 41.8557
Watershed 8-Appalachian Plateaus-Glaciaded High Plateau:					
36PO0029	Prehistoric	-77.64415 41.93846	36TI0031	Prehistoric	-77.2106 41.98076
36TI0005	Prehistoric	-77.40962 41.9617	36TI0032	Prehistoric	-77.22537 41.97667
36TI0009	Prehistoric	-77.47849 41.93635	36TI0033	Prehistoric	-77.20628 41.97806
36TI0010	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.46634 41.95233	36TI0034	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.2028 41.9775
36TI0011	Prehistoric	-77.461 41.95263	36TI0035	Prehistoric	-77.22732 41.97643
36TI0012	Prehistoric	-77.44653 41.96365	36TI0036	Prehistoric	-77.22697 41.97922
36TI0013	Prehistoric	-77.44358 41.96239	36TI0037	Prehistoric	-77.20802 41.97763
36TI0014	Prehistoric	-77.46967 41.98357	36TI0038	Prehistoric	-77.23994 41.97605
36TI0015	Prehistoric	-77.42139 41.95539	36TI0047	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.23583 41.97545
36TI0016	Prehistoric	-77.35492 41.97725	36TI0059	Prehistoric	-77.60383 41.90854
36TI0017	Prehistoric	-77.33105 41.98195	36TI0078	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.52313 41.87158
36TI0018	Prehistoric	-77.32834 41.98455	36TI0104	Prehistoric	-77.07382 41.67364
36TI0019	Prehistoric	-77.32428 41.98431	36TI0129	Prehistoric	-77.13774 41.99182
36TI0026	Prehistoric	-77.2805 41.98863	36TI0130	Prehistoric	-77.13799 41.99245
36TI0028	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.13885 41.99434	36TI0131	Prehistoric	-77.25661 41.9795
36TI0028	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.13897 41.99335	36TI0136	Prehistoric	-77.13465 41.99886
36TI0030	Prehistoric	-77.26177 41.98506			
Watershed 9-Appalachian Plateaus-Deep Valleys:					
36MC0009	Prehistoric	-78.76276 41.98268	36PO0007	Prehistoric	-78.06065 41.84572
36MC0013	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.72556 41.84976	36PO0008	Prehistoric	-78.0479 41.76018
36MC0014	Prehistoric	-78.68212 41.8738	36PO0009	Prehistoric	-77.99749 41.87631
36MC0017	Prehistoric	-78.66079 41.95486	36PO0011	Prehistoric	-78.20184 41.97009
36MC0033	Prehistoric	-78.38538 41.96356	36PO0012	Prehistoric	-78.2005 41.97029
36MC0056	Prehistoric	-78.39025 41.74617	36PO0013	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.19912 41.97047
36MC0057	Prehistoric	-78.43017 41.8129	36PO0014	Prehistoric	-78.20128 41.97064
36MC0058	Prehistoric	-78.45284 41.93678	36PO0016	Prehistoric	-78.20544 41.97404
36MC0059	Prehistoric	-78.28756 41.91186	36PO0019	Prehistoric	-78.20028 41.78598
36MC0060	Prehistoric	-78.28319 41.80764	36PO0025	Prehistoric	-77.98656 41.76781
36MC0061	Prehistoric	-78.28221 41.80768	36PO0030	Prehistoric	-77.97743 41.76638
36MC0062	Prehistoric	-78.29216 41.81353	36PO0031	Prehistoric	-78.04117 41.76006
36MC0070	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.3993 41.97546	36PO0034	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.20544 41.97192
36MC0092	Prehistoric & Historic	-78.2353 41.97853	36PO0048	Prehistoric	-78.04275 41.76178
36MC0093	Prehistoric	-78.23633 41.97901			
Watershed 10-Appalachian Plateaus-Deep Valleys:					
36PO0006	Prehistoric	-77.86336 41.99405	36PO0015	Prehistoric	-77.92101 41.89839
36PO0010	Prehistoric	-77.80619 41.87434			
Watershed 13-Appalachian Plateaus-Deep Valleys:					
36LY0097	Prehistoric	-77.32524 41.25213	36PO0038	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.76283 41.85002
36LY0148	Prehistoric	-77.35184 41.30163	36PO0039	Prehistoric	-77.76385 41.84395
36LY0149	Prehistoric	-77.33566 41.23881	36PO0040	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.71041 41.87621
36LY0150	Prehistoric	-77.32636 41.24462	36TI0008	Prehistoric	-77.43212 41.74606

Table A-6. Region 6 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
Watershed 24-Appalachian Plateaus-Deep Valleys:					
36CN0018	Prehistoric	-77.52836 41.16544	36CN0077	Prehistoric	-77.77535 41.32357
36CN0019	Prehistoric	-77.54743 41.17728	36CN0078	Prehistoric	-77.779 41.3232
36CN0022	Prehistoric	-77.54512 41.17464	36CN0081	Prehistoric	-77.63432 41.31395
36CN0057	Prehistoric	-77.5346 41.16765	36CN0082	Prehistoric	-77.63695 41.32708
36CN0058	Prehistoric	-77.53964 41.17032	36CN0083	Prehistoric	-77.76112 41.32674
36CN0059	Prehistoric	-77.63493 41.30934	36CN0084	Prehistoric	-77.78594 41.31971
36CN0060	Prehistoric	-77.63408 41.30722	36CN0085	Prehistoric	-77.78706 41.31707
36CN0061	Prehistoric	-77.59184 41.2634	36CN0088	Prehistoric	-77.93006 41.37776
36CN0062	Prehistoric	-77.70135 41.34314	36CN0089	Prehistoric	-77.92496 41.39639
36CN0063	Prehistoric	-77.69253 41.34619	36CN0090	Prehistoric	-77.91659 41.40067
36CN0064	Prehistoric	-77.69533 41.3476	36CN0091	Prehistoric	-77.91923 41.4248
36CN0065	Prehistoric	-77.69405 41.34766	36CN0092	Prehistoric	-77.91234 41.42662
36CN0066	Prehistoric	-77.7059 41.33966	36CN0093	Prehistoric	-77.90181 41.4318
36CN0067	Prehistoric	-77.63479 41.32053	36CN0094	Prehistoric	-77.87111 41.44661
36CN0068	Prehistoric	-77.64045 41.32871	36CN0095	Prehistoric	-77.90934 41.41776
36CN0069	Prehistoric	-77.6446 41.33056	36CN0096	Prehistoric	-77.84028 41.29726
36CN0070	Prehistoric	-77.70392 41.34111	36CN0165	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.9216 41.40291
36CN0071	Prehistoric	-77.70313 41.34418	36CN0185	Prehistoric	-77.48168 41.17681
36CN0072	Prehistoric	-77.49023 41.17434	36CN0199	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.91975 41.40337
36CN0073	Prehistoric	-77.70058 41.34556	36CN0209	Prehistoric	-77.89288 41.43883
36CN0074	Prehistoric	-77.70718 41.3363	36CN0218	Prehistoric	-77.6855 41.33953
36CN0075	Prehistoric	-77.5918 41.26908	36PO0003	Prehistoric	-77.68042 41.51603
36CN0076	Prehistoric	-77.59676 41.26253	36PO0032	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.78635 41.49264
Watershed 25-Appalachian Plateaus-Deep Valleys:					
36LY0043	Prehistoric	-77.02797 41.42099	36LY0167	Prehistoric	-77.04895 41.39145
36LY0044	Prehistoric	-77.04023 41.41405	36LY0168	Prehistoric	-77.0469 41.39235
36LY0049	Prehistoric	-77.08153 41.35214	36LY0169	Prehistoric	-77.04254 41.39977
36LY0050	Prehistoric	-77.06883 41.37004	36LY0176	Prehistoric	-76.97719 41.47798
36LY0051	Prehistoric	-77.05729 41.38266	36LY0184	Prehistoric	-77.02616 41.42476
36LY0052	Prehistoric	-77.05332 41.38194	36LY0231	Prehistoric	-76.97544 41.46384
36LY0053	Prehistoric	-77.05031 41.38603	36LY0232	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.97537 41.45322
36LY0054	Prehistoric	-77.04686 41.38913	36LY0233	Prehistoric	-76.97662 41.45129
36LY0055	Prehistoric	-77.04219 41.40497	36LY0247	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.02693 41.42304
36LY0156	Prehistoric	-77.06243 41.37876	36LY0254	Prehistoric	-77.09574 41.35089
36LY0160	Prehistoric	-76.94958 41.50733	36LY0332	Prehistoric	-77.13427 41.43553
Watershed 25-Appalachian Plateaus-Glaciated High Plateau:					
36LY0318	Prehistoric	-76.89181 41.57499			
Watershed 26-Appalachian Plateaus-Deep Valleys:					
36LY0030	Prehistoric	-76.79672 41.4	36SU0004	Prehistoric	-76.72275 41.47027
36LY0048	Prehistoric	-76.91393 41.33262	36SU0006	Prehistoric	-76.70677 41.44099
36LY0100	Prehistoric	-76.90094 41.39212	36SU0007	Prehistoric	-76.71674 41.44132
36LY0145	Prehistoric	-76.81356 41.38263	36SU0009	Prehistoric	-76.59461 41.5006
36SU0001	Prehistoric	-76.70922 41.41421	36SU0010	Prehistoric	-76.69739 41.44698
36SU0002	Prehistoric	-76.46626 41.50736	36SU0011	Prehistoric	-76.71688 41.44347
36SU0003	Prehistoric	-76.61786 41.49203			
Watershed 26-Appalachian Plateaus-Glaciated High Plateau:					
36SU0012	Prehistoric	-76.38586 41.49652	36SU0013	Prehistoric	-76.37757 41.4772

Table A-6. Region 6 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Province and Section

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
Watershed 31-Appalachian Plateaus-Deep Valleys:					
36SU0005	Prehistoric	-76.58888 41.33749	36SU0008	Prehistoric	-76.58327 41.42204
Watershed 39-Appalachian Plateaus-Deep Valleys:					
36CE0020	Prehistoric	-77.91971 41.22945	36CE0023	Prehistoric	-78.00007 41.14701
36CE0021	Prehistoric	-77.92824 41.22594	36CN0086	Prehistoric	-77.902 41.25992
36CE0022	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.98852 41.16135	36CN0097	Prehistoric	-77.91811 41.23676

Table A-7. Region 7 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36BR0143	Prehistoric	-76.44878 41.73824	36BR0271	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.46726 41.72193
36BR0149	Prehistoric	-76.73469 41.77485	36BR0275	Prehistoric	-76.35175 41.555
36BR0151	Prehistoric	-76.51176 41.69943	36BR0289	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.45742 41.73603
36BR0152	Prehistoric	-76.52376 41.69945	36BR0308	Prehistoric	-76.65724 41.82614
36BR0154	Prehistoric	-76.66074 41.7165	36BR0309	Prehistoric	-76.7682 41.68498
36BR0158	Prehistoric	-76.54525 41.77818			
Watershed 15-Appalachian Plateaus-Glaciated Low Plateau:					
36LW0001	Prehistoric	-75.71145 41.61243	36WO0011	Prehistoric	-75.7651 41.63028
36LW0002	Prehistoric	-75.74286 41.61291	36WO0012	Prehistoric	-75.79456 41.61775
36LW0011	Prehistoric	-75.65745 41.57685	36WO0013	Prehistoric	-75.79571 41.61908
36LW0012	Prehistoric	-75.73169 41.58219	36WO0014	Prehistoric	-75.7861 41.62147
36LW0013	Prehistoric	-75.64736 41.63672	36WO0015	Prehistoric	-75.76724 41.62214
36LW0018	Prehistoric	-75.74031 41.49403	36WO0016	Prehistoric	-75.7639 41.62401
36LW0030	Prehistoric	-75.66102 41.59068	36WO0017	Prehistoric	-75.75933 41.62199
36LW0031	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.55157 41.63889	36WO0026	Prehistoric	-75.75062 41.62447
36LW0035	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.62226 41.52847	36WO0027	Prehistoric	-75.76909 41.62215
36LW0054	Prehistoric	-75.74751 41.60154	36WO0028	Prehistoric	-75.92141 41.55141
36SQ0005	Prehistoric	-75.58331 41.71275	36WO0040	Prehistoric	-75.95035 41.60898
36SQ0006	Prehistoric	-75.53469 41.69463	36WO0041	Prehistoric	-75.89543 41.61171
36SQ0046	Prehistoric	-75.85121 41.65157	36WO0042	Prehistoric	-75.91845 41.58331
36SQ0047	Prehistoric	-75.81079 41.72845	36WO0043	Prehistoric	-75.95816 41.56289
36SQ0048	Prehistoric	-75.82576 41.68416	36WO0044	Prehistoric	-75.94485 41.55584
36SQ0053	Prehistoric	-75.69631 41.64854	36WO0045	Prehistoric	-75.89018 41.56396
36SQ0054	Prehistoric	-75.67002 41.65551	36WO0046	Prehistoric	-75.87509 41.56644
36SQ0055	Prehistoric	-75.64316 41.68632	36WO0047	Prehistoric	-75.74563 41.63529
36SQ0056	Prehistoric	-75.71512 41.66611	36WO0049	Prehistoric	-75.76833 41.62746
36SQ0057	Prehistoric	-75.69239 41.66834	36WO0050	Prehistoric	-75.82175 41.52817
36SQ0058	Prehistoric	-75.6778 41.65992	36WO0051	Prehistoric	-75.76256 41.63007
36SQ0059	Prehistoric	-75.64319 41.67854	36WO0052	Prehistoric	-75.89588 41.5532
36SQ0060	Prehistoric	-75.67154 41.70789	36WO0053	Prehistoric	-75.76628 41.59813
36SQ0061	Prehistoric	-75.64694 41.70433	36WO0055	Prehistoric	-75.94029 41.5366
36SQ0062	Prehistoric	-75.67213 41.70301	36WO0062	Prehistoric	-75.79202 41.61978
36SQ0063	Prehistoric	-75.69449 41.68439	36WO0063	Prehistoric	-75.78935 41.61992
36SQ0064	Prehistoric	-75.69793 41.68015	36WO0067	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.9303 41.53728
36SQ0065	Prehistoric	-75.71147 41.67212	36WO0068	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.93236 41.5368
36SQ0066	Prehistoric	-75.71559 41.64675	36WO0077	Prehistoric	-75.93696 41.54058
36SQ0067	Prehistoric	-75.71731 41.6431	36WO0078	Prehistoric	-75.93555 41.54059
36SQ0068	Prehistoric	-75.71031 41.65862	36WO0080	Prehistoric	-75.89365 41.55812
36SQ0069	Prehistoric	-75.69091 41.65888	36WO0081	Prehistoric	-75.89126 41.55927
36SQ0070	Prehistoric	-75.68236 41.67364	36WO0082	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.89328 41.55709
36SQ0145	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.71112 41.79329	36WO0083	Prehistoric	-75.89123 41.55734
36WO0001	Prehistoric	-75.87158 41.55908	36WO0085	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.89783 41.55326
36WO0010	Prehistoric	-75.76338 41.63005			
Watershed 17-Appalachian Plateaus-Glaciated Low Plateau:					
36LW0010	Prehistoric	-75.64827 41.51899	36LW0034	Prehistoric	-75.6291 41.52646
36LW0019	Prehistoric	-75.4629 41.35981	36SQ0007	Prehistoric	-75.51614 41.74706
36LW0032	Prehistoric	-75.58253 41.3273			
Watershed 17-Ridge and Valley-Anthracite Valley:					
36LU0012	Prehistoric	-75.79967 41.34415	36LW0009	Prehistoric	-75.66488 41.4242
36LU0055	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.79243 41.34543	36LW0016	Prehistoric	-75.66246 41.42258

Table A-7. Region 7 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LU0058	Prehistoric	-75.79662 41.3481	36LW0017	Prehistoric	-75.66235 41.43305
36LU0080	Prehistoric	-75.7899 41.34224	36LW0020	Prehistoric	-75.53246 41.49748
36LU0083	Prehistoric	-75.79954 41.35788	36LW0036	Prehistoric	-75.58231 41.48169
36LU0123	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.80235 41.3457	36LW0039	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.69841 41.38196
36LU0169	Prehistoric	-75.79716 41.3494	36LW0044	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.51013 41.56374
36LU0170	Prehistoric	-75.7823 41.3501	36LW0055	Prehistoric	-75.61171 41.48192
36LU0210	Prehistoric	-75.79748 41.33871	36WY0153	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.46334 41.70082
36LW0008	Prehistoric	-75.63898 41.39951			
Watershed 18-Appalachian Plateaus-Glaciated Low Plateau:					
36LU0028	Prehistoric	-75.83278 41.41358	36WO0025	Prehistoric	-75.981 41.55589
36LU0063	Prehistoric	-75.91118 41.39937	36WO0029	Prehistoric	-76.00292 41.62074
36LU0084	Prehistoric	-75.83149 41.39493	36WO0030	Prehistoric	-76.04018 41.56965
36LU0085	Prehistoric	-75.82582 41.38957	36WO0031	Prehistoric	-76.08677 41.56173
36LU0215	Prehistoric	-75.83373 41.40699	36WO0032	Prehistoric	-76.06134 41.57859
36LU0300	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.79921 41.38037	36WO0033	Prehistoric	-76.04641 41.60577
36LW0003	Prehistoric	-75.83016 41.42738	36WO0034	Prehistoric	-76.05749 41.56926
36LW0004	Prehistoric	-75.81284 41.38821	36WO0036	Prehistoric	-76.05095 41.61391
36LW0005	Prehistoric	-75.80281 41.38646	36WO0039	Prehistoric	-76.01622 41.53525
36LW0006	Prehistoric	-75.8004 41.38544	36WO0048	Prehistoric	-75.84086 41.43346
36LW0007	Prehistoric	-75.82802 41.39565	36WO0054	Prehistoric	-75.85084 41.44749
36LW0015	Prehistoric	-75.75308 41.46968	36WO0056	Prehistoric	-75.85468 41.46154
36LW0053	Prehistoric	-75.79424 41.38083	36WO0057	Prehistoric	-75.94358 41.62868
36LW0061	Prehistoric	-75.79894 41.38503	36WO0058	Prehistoric	-75.9458 41.62935
36LW0062	Prehistoric	-75.79628 41.38337	36WO0059	Prehistoric	-75.87188 41.44193
36SQ0049	Prehistoric	-75.85778 41.68551	36WO0064	Prehistoric	-76.00099 41.47239
36WO0002	Prehistoric	-75.89238 41.46529	36WO0065	Prehistoric	-76.05047 41.60152
36WO0003	Prehistoric	-75.85716 41.44918	36WO0069	Prehistoric	-75.97009 41.54278
36WO0004	Prehistoric	-75.94608 41.51442	36WO0070	Prehistoric	-75.96822 41.54092
36WO0006	Prehistoric	-75.94174 41.52171	36WO0071	Prehistoric	-75.96447 41.53818
36WO0009	Prehistoric	-75.94041 41.52939	36WO0073	Prehistoric	-76.06055 41.58478
36WO0018	Prehistoric	-75.90686 41.5112	36WO0075	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.95822 41.53627
36WO0019	Prehistoric	-75.91506 41.51277	36WO0076	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.96063 41.53659
36WO0020	Prehistoric	-75.91096 41.51507	36WO0079	Prehistoric	-75.90034 41.50839
36WO0022	Prehistoric	-76.05545 41.59953	36WO0084	Prehistoric	-75.85637 41.44171
36WO0023	Prehistoric	-76.0312 41.54935	36WO0087	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.94868 41.5242
36WO0024	Prehistoric	-75.98672 41.56097	36WO0100	Prehistoric	-76.11284 41.56092
Watershed 18-Ridge and Valley-Anthracite Valley:					
36LU0027	Prehistoric	-75.8002 41.36321	36LU0211	Prehistoric	-75.80818 41.36143
Watershed 20-Appalachian Plateaus-Glaciated Low Plateau:					
36PI0068	Prehistoric	-75.06787 41.49801	36WY0005	Prehistoric	-75.2439 41.5035
36PI0069	Prehistoric	-75.07391 41.45075	36WY0007	Prehistoric	-75.43593 41.54896
36PI0070	Prehistoric	-75.07645 41.46542	36WY0008	Prehistoric	-75.26498 41.61471
36PI0071	Prehistoric	-75.07583 41.45089	36WY0011	Prehistoric	-75.24647 41.48856
36PI0218	Prehistoric	-75.09758 41.50504	36WY0012	Prehistoric	-75.24386 41.49072
36PI0219	Prehistoric	-75.09736 41.50395	36WY0013	Prehistoric	-75.24241 41.48852
36PI0228	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.09056 41.505	36WY0014	Prehistoric	-75.24864 41.49828
36PI0229	Prehistoric	-75.09175 41.50497	36WY0015	Prehistoric	-75.26466 41.48566
36PI0230	Prehistoric	-75.08872 41.50349	36WY0016	Prehistoric	-75.2521 41.49352
36PI0241	Prehistoric	-75.00497 41.48022	36WY0134	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.41541 41.71884
36PI0252	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.08678 41.50527	36WY0152	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.19518 41.49325

Table A-7. Region 7 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
Watershed 28-Appalachian Plateaus-Glaciated Low Plateau:					
36MR0032	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.09547 41.10909	36PI0108	Prehistoric	-74.97317 41.42271
36MR0047	Prehistoric	-75.15012 41.2092	36PI0109	Prehistoric	-74.98984 41.42147
36MR0063	Prehistoric	-75.03546 41.08712	36PI0110	Prehistoric	-74.94755 41.4256
36MR0070	Prehistoric	-75.10545 41.06298	36PI0111	Prehistoric	-74.96823 41.3988
36MR0071	Prehistoric	-75.10407 41.06013	36PI0112	Prehistoric	-74.98061 41.41436
36MR0161	Prehistoric	-75.0967 41.07889	36PI0113	Prehistoric	-74.97719 41.41708
36MR0162	Prehistoric	-75.09811 41.07931	36PI0114	Prehistoric	-74.97623 41.4195
36MR0163	Prehistoric	-75.09915 41.07794	36PI0115	Prehistoric	-74.96803 41.38601
36MR032D	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.09494 41.1102	36PI0116	Prehistoric	-74.8134 41.41668
36PI0001	Prehistoric	-75.00782 41.09281	36PI0117	Prehistoric	-74.82985 41.425
36PI0002	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.77805 41.32589	36PI0118	Prehistoric	-74.86217 41.42878
36PI0003	Prehistoric	-74.8152 41.29893	36PI0119	Prehistoric	-74.85511 41.43357
36PI0004	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.83216 41.28694	36PI0120	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.86049 41.44296
36PI0005	Prehistoric	-74.88283 41.18549	36PI0121	Prehistoric	-74.82414 41.4307
36PI0006	Prehistoric	-74.91361 41.15478	36PI0122	Prehistoric	-74.8065 41.44116
36PI0007	Prehistoric	-74.91554 41.14736	36PI0123	Prehistoric	-74.80263 41.43687
36PI0008	Prehistoric	-74.92864 41.14017	36PI0124	Prehistoric	-74.79258 41.42056
36PI0009	Prehistoric	-74.95201 41.12423	36PI0125	Prehistoric	-74.79634 41.40678
36PI0010	Prehistoric	-74.88277 41.18849	36PI0126	Prehistoric	-74.74337 41.41749
36PI0011	Prehistoric	-74.89615 41.17448	36PI0127	Prehistoric	-74.74812 41.41404
36PI0012	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.94867 41.12826	36PI0128	Prehistoric	-74.74403 41.41102
36PI0013	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.95793 41.12016	36PI0129	Prehistoric	-74.74376 41.40894
36PI0014	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.85304 41.25373	36PI0130	Prehistoric	-74.71551 41.3514
36PI0015	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.95052 41.12656	36PI0131	Prehistoric	-74.71456 41.35259
36PI0016	Prehistoric	-74.8252 41.29382	36PI0132	Prehistoric	-74.81766 41.29669
36PI0019	Prehistoric	-74.82966 41.29048	36PI0133	Prehistoric	-74.75726 41.34643
36PI0020	Prehistoric	-74.98902 41.10063	36PI0135	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.79588 41.30998
36PI0022	Prehistoric	-74.99219 41.09729	36PI0136	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.86097 41.21866
36PI0023	Prehistoric	-74.99063 41.09894	36PI0137	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.86229 41.21939
36PI0024	Prehistoric	-74.9893 41.0987	36PI0138	Prehistoric	-75.03242 41.0872
36PI0025	Prehistoric	-74.97105 41.11493	36PI0139	Prehistoric	-75.03323 41.0876
36PI0026	Prehistoric	-74.95041 41.12327	36PI0140	Prehistoric	-74.83685 41.28353
36PI0027	Prehistoric	-74.90614 41.15871	36PI0141	Prehistoric	-74.84791 41.27049
36PI0028	Prehistoric	-74.83615 41.28178	36PI0142	Prehistoric	-74.84867 41.27228
36PI0029	Prehistoric	-74.81406 41.30097	36PI0143	Prehistoric	-74.85094 41.2755
36PI0030	Prehistoric	-74.98558 41.10489	36PI0144	Prehistoric	-74.84135 41.30237
36PI0031	Prehistoric	-74.9894 41.10701	36PI0145	Prehistoric	-74.83634 41.28654
36PI0032	Prehistoric	-74.92679 41.13899	36PI0146	Prehistoric	-74.83696 41.28544
36PI0033	Prehistoric	-74.90179 41.16736	36PI0147	Prehistoric	-74.84385 41.28111
36PI0034	Prehistoric	-74.9438 41.1315	36PI0148	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.98413 41.10761
36PI0035	Prehistoric	-74.90838 41.15598	36PI0149	Prehistoric	-74.98564 41.10572
36PI0036	Prehistoric	-74.79423 41.31406	36PI0150	Prehistoric	-75.02997 41.10925
36PI0037	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.78321 41.32575	36PI0151	Prehistoric	-75.03068 41.10831
36PI0038	Prehistoric	-74.77075 41.32852	36PI0152	Prehistoric	-75.02995 41.11879
36PI0039	Prehistoric	-74.89647 41.17317	36PI0156	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.92422 41.15998
36PI0040	Prehistoric	-74.87715 41.19982	36PI0157	Prehistoric	-74.96349 41.13438
36PI0041	Prehistoric	-74.72199 41.35022	36PI0158	Prehistoric	-74.9202 41.16792
36PI0042	Prehistoric	-74.76774 41.33141	36PI0159	Prehistoric	-74.90803 41.18341
36PI0043	Prehistoric	-74.90052 41.16888	36PI0160	Prehistoric	-74.86843 41.21349
36PI0044	Prehistoric	-74.94203 41.18761	36PI0161	Prehistoric	-74.86722 41.2242
36PI0045	Prehistoric	-74.94311 41.18079	36PI0162	Prehistoric	-74.87067 41.22416

Table A-7. Region 7 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36PI0046	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.81225 41.2995	36PI0164	Prehistoric	-75.02345 41.17806
36PI0072	Prehistoric	-74.97312 41.37472	36PI0165	Prehistoric	-75.02053 41.1821
36PI0073	Prehistoric	-74.97571 41.37472	36PI0166	Prehistoric	-75.0201 41.18161
36PI0074	Prehistoric	-74.93997 41.34179	36PI0167	Prehistoric	-75.0316 41.17444
36PI0078	Prehistoric	-75.01097 41.35499	36PI0169	Prehistoric	-74.9137 41.47496
36PI0079	Prehistoric	-75.01196 41.35548	36PI0172	Prehistoric	-74.81513 41.32388
36PI0080	Prehistoric	-75.01182 41.35445	36PI0198	Prehistoric	-74.81722 41.32906
36PI0081	Prehistoric	-75.0805 41.29103	36PI0202	Prehistoric	-75.04732 41.152
36PI0082	Prehistoric	-75.01567 41.35497	36PI0220	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.91725 41.20065
36PI0083	Prehistoric	-75.06755 41.36608	36PI0223	Prehistoric	-74.69734 41.35917
36PI0099	Prehistoric	-74.98764 41.48373	36PI0224	Prehistoric	-74.77402 41.3274
36PI0100	Prehistoric	-74.98798 41.47654	36PI0233	Prehistoric	-74.90197 41.16558
36PI0101	Prehistoric	-74.99092 41.47377	36PI0234	Prehistoric	-74.84801 41.26244
36PI0102	Prehistoric	-74.94809 41.47958	36PI0235	Prehistoric	-74.89633 41.20754
36PI0103	Prehistoric	-74.91222 41.47338	36PI0236	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.95519 41.12649
36PI0104	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.91951 41.46995	36PI0238	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.72727 41.3485
36PI0105	Prehistoric	-74.92668 41.44978	36PI0244	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.00259 41.09375
36PI0106	Prehistoric	-74.89251 41.45142	36PI0249	Prehistoric	-75.05356 41.143
36PI0107	Prehistoric	-74.89846 41.44323	36PI0250	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.09529 41.24459
Watershed 28-Appalachian Plateaus-Glaciaded Pocono Plateau:					
36PI0075	Prehistoric	-75.14958 41.33579	36PI0077	Prehistoric	-75.14381 41.35984
36PI0076	Prehistoric	-75.16869 41.35341			
Watershed 30-Appalachian Plateaus-Glaciaded Low Plateau:					
36PI0047	Prehistoric	-75.18128 41.4482	36WY0022	Prehistoric	-75.2015 41.44074
36PI0048	Prehistoric	-75.17647 41.44059	36WY0023	Prehistoric	-75.21195 41.44071
36PI0049	Prehistoric	-75.18429 41.42896	36WY0024	Prehistoric	-75.21791 41.43471
36PI0050	Prehistoric	-75.19213 41.42925	36WY0025	Prehistoric	-75.20996 41.43475
36PI0051	Prehistoric	-75.2068 41.41839	36WY0026	Prehistoric	-75.22323 41.4306
36PI0052	Prehistoric	-75.21132 41.41698	36WY0027	Prehistoric	-75.22425 41.42761
36PI0053	Prehistoric	-75.21467 41.41804	36WY0028	Prehistoric	-75.23511 41.42772
36PI0054	Prehistoric	-75.22698 41.41756	36WY0029	Prehistoric	-75.23724 41.42502
36PI0055	Prehistoric	-75.22931 41.41368	36WY0030	Prehistoric	-75.24378 41.42234
36PI0056	Prehistoric	-75.24068 41.40722	36WY0031	Prehistoric	-75.25119 41.42249
36PI0057	Prehistoric	-75.24751 41.39775	36WY0032	Prehistoric	-75.2556 41.4211
36PI0058	Prehistoric	-75.2454 41.38875	36WY0033	Prehistoric	-75.25053 41.41605
36PI0059	Prehistoric	-75.24002 41.38643	36WY0034	Prehistoric	-75.25488 41.41195
36PI0060	Prehistoric	-75.25537 41.37967	36WY0035	Prehistoric	-75.25479 41.40423
36PI0061	Prehistoric	-75.25935 41.3796	36WY0036	Prehistoric	-75.2588 41.39995
36PI0062	Prehistoric	-75.2562 41.37358	36WY0037	Prehistoric	-75.26997 41.38334
36PI0063	Prehistoric	-75.26145 41.37163	36WY0038	Prehistoric	-75.27157 41.38194
36PI0064	Prehistoric	-75.26439 41.37043	36WY0039	Prehistoric	-75.27752 41.37555
36PI0065	Prehistoric	-75.27024 41.37106	36WY0040	Prehistoric	-75.30989 41.37639
36PI0066	Prehistoric	-75.29684 41.36492	36WY0041	Prehistoric	-75.2699 41.37342
36PI0067	Prehistoric	-75.29917 41.36619	36WY0042	Prehistoric	-75.27232 41.37386
36PI0221	Prehistoric	-75.22757 41.4097	36WY0043	Prehistoric	-75.28522 41.37324
36WY0017	Prehistoric	-75.31248 41.4697	36WY0044	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.29026 41.37214
36WY0018	Prehistoric	-75.30084 41.46605	36WY0045	Prehistoric	-75.29485 41.37094
36WY0019	Prehistoric	-75.18919 41.45643	36WY0046	Prehistoric	-75.29626 41.37255
36WY0020	Prehistoric	-75.19727 41.44546	36WY0047	Prehistoric	-75.30323 41.37238
36WY0021	Prehistoric	-75.1949 41.44196	36WY0125	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.28027 41.38975

Table A-7. Region 7 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
Watershed 30-Appalachian Plateaus-Glaciaded Pocono Plateau:					
36PI0163	Prehistoric	-75.28183 41.26506	36WY0048	Prehistoric	-75.3205 41.31591
Watershed 30-Ridge and Valley-Anthracite Valley:					
36LW0014	Prehistoric	-75.51292 41.43013			
Watershed 32-Appalachian Plateaus-Glaciaded Low Plateau:					
36LU0005	Prehistoric	-75.8936 41.3348	36LU0069	Prehistoric	-75.97639 41.32083
36LU0006	Prehistoric	-75.89507 41.33212	36LU0070	Prehistoric	-75.98073 41.32283
36LU0008	Prehistoric	-76.03361 41.28003	36LU0071	Prehistoric	-75.98487 41.32172
36LU0066	Prehistoric	-75.93067 41.29973	36LU0072	Prehistoric	-75.99135 41.32252
36LU0067	Prehistoric	-75.97165 41.31426	36LU0073	Prehistoric	-75.98277 41.31319
36LU0068	Prehistoric	-75.97164 41.31537	36LU0074	Prehistoric	-75.9872 41.30872
Watershed 32-Ridge and Valley-Anthracite Valley:					
36LU0001	Prehistoric	-75.97132 41.21073	36LU0047	Prehistoric	-75.84404 41.30495
36LU0002	Prehistoric	-75.88513 41.25137	36LU0054	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.93603 41.24134
36LU0003	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.86631 41.28198	36LU0059	Prehistoric	-75.97023 41.21398
36LU0004	Prehistoric	-75.86314 41.28448	36LU0060	Prehistoric	-75.873 41.262
36LU0009	Prehistoric	-75.95801 41.22557	36LU0075	Prehistoric	-75.87351 41.29454
36LU0010	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.86474 41.28348	36LU0076	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.8678 41.2904
36LU0011	Prehistoric	-75.97288 41.2107	36LU0077	Prehistoric	-75.8596 41.29319
36LU0013	Prehistoric	-75.86585 41.28788	36LU0082	Prehistoric	-75.84068 41.29857
36LU0014	Prehistoric	-75.8603 41.28352	36LU0086	Prehistoric	-75.85768 41.28777
36LU0026	Prehistoric	-75.80312 41.32198	36LU0101	Prehistoric	-76.07078 41.20127
36LU0030	Prehistoric	-75.77841 41.22711	36LU0103	Prehistoric	-75.80071 41.28604
36LU0032	Prehistoric	-75.86688 41.28928	36LU0110	Prehistoric	-75.83618 41.30343
36LU0033	Prehistoric	-76.1055 41.18064	36LU0121	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.82818 41.30748
36LU0034	Prehistoric	-76.11037 41.1789	36LU0122	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.79224 41.33105
36LU0035	Prehistoric	-76.10818 41.18018	36LU0125	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.82939 41.30875
36LU0036	Prehistoric	-76.10708 41.18009	36LU0128	Prehistoric	-75.95265 41.23627
36LU0037	Prehistoric	-76.08361 41.1892	36LU0132	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.14454 41.14589
36LU0038	Prehistoric	-75.97564 41.2213	36LU0175	Prehistoric	-75.97969 41.21568
36LU0039	Prehistoric	-75.97549 41.21583	36LU0182	Prehistoric	-75.92746 41.24592
36LU0040	Prehistoric	-75.96269 41.22277	36LU0186	Prehistoric	-76.0841 41.18802
36LU0041	Prehistoric	-75.9581 41.22257	36LU0237	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.91565 41.23491
36LU0042	Prehistoric	-76.14765 41.14808	36LU0271	Prehistoric	-75.91767 41.24887
36LU0044	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.85666 41.29371	36LU0276	Prehistoric	-75.95905 41.20102
36LU0045	Prehistoric	-75.84905 41.29727	36LU0305	Prehistoric	-75.85458 41.29571
36LU0046	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.94306 41.23194	36LU0306	Prehistoric	-75.8483 41.2097
Watershed 36-Appalachian Plateaus-Glaciaded Pocono Plateau:					
36CR0030	Prehistoric	-75.71378 41.1123	36LU0145	Prehistoric	-75.70125 41.12847
36CR0036	Prehistoric	-75.65717 41.11576	36LU0146	Prehistoric	-75.69293 41.13177
36CR0037	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.64874 41.12103	36LU0148	Prehistoric	-75.68578 41.13104
36CR0068	Prehistoric	-75.68135 41.13142	36LU0151	Prehistoric	-75.65073 41.12293
36CR0069	Prehistoric	-75.59406 41.08021	36LU0171	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.65598 41.1168
36CR0070	Prehistoric	-75.6394 41.07646	36LU0172	Prehistoric	-75.7231 41.1522
36CR0071	Prehistoric	-75.65075 41.07829	36LU0173	Prehistoric	-75.71962 41.15579
36CR0072	Prehistoric	-75.66137 41.09053	36LW0021	Prehistoric	-75.63521 41.20961
36CR0073	Prehistoric	-75.65278 41.09467	36LW0022	Prehistoric	-75.63616 41.21258
36CR0074	Prehistoric	-75.65096 41.09915	36LW0023	Prehistoric	-75.62907 41.21428
36CR0075	Prehistoric	-75.67674 41.13218	36LW0024	Prehistoric	-75.62587 41.21524

Table A-7. Region 7 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36CR0076	Prehistoric	-75.65086 41.11954	36LW0025	Prehistoric	-75.61452 41.21393
36CR0079	Prehistoric	-75.6618 41.12831	36LW0026	Prehistoric	-75.59752 41.20086
36CR0080	Prehistoric	-75.65903 41.1178	36LW0027	Prehistoric	-75.57124 41.19264
36CR0081	Prehistoric	-75.65916 41.11859	36LW0028	Prehistoric	-75.57691 41.18811
36CR0082	Prehistoric	-75.65897 41.11953	36LW0029	Prehistoric	-75.57665 41.18269
36CR0084	Prehistoric	-75.64739 41.11936	36LW0056	Prehistoric	-75.58968 41.17267
36CR0085	Prehistoric	-75.62269 41.1069	36MR0031	Prehistoric	-75.64806 41.12384
36CR0118	Prehistoric	-75.66099 41.10054	36MR0035	Prehistoric	-75.45517 41.02873
36CR0124	Prehistoric	-75.62603 41.10916	36MR0036	Prehistoric	-75.44938 41.02882
36CR0126	Prehistoric	-75.61783 41.07416	36MR0037	Prehistoric	-75.51391 41.09879
36CR0127	Prehistoric	-75.61286 41.07683	36MR0073	Prehistoric	-75.53168 41.09697
36CR0147	Prehistoric	-75.6923 41.13054	36MR0074	Prehistoric	-75.57332 41.09049
36LU0061	Prehistoric	-75.65946 41.1291	36MR0075	Prehistoric	-75.51144 41.11188
36LU0078	Prehistoric	-75.71256 41.13364	36MR0076	Prehistoric	-75.51952 41.1063
36LU0095	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.71247 41.16412	36MR0077	Prehistoric	-75.51364 41.10093
36LU0098	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.62818 41.13026	36MR0078	Prehistoric	-75.51067 41.10067
36LU0111	Prehistoric	-75.69052 41.13216	36MR0079	Prehistoric	-75.50343 41.10142
36LU0112	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.72208 41.1557	36MR0080	Prehistoric	-75.51009 41.10282
36LU0113	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.66152 41.13009	36MR0081	Prehistoric	-75.53216 41.09818
36LU0138	Prehistoric	-75.71187 41.14095	36MR0082	Prehistoric	-75.52686 41.09758
36LU0139	Prehistoric	-75.72116 41.15485	36MR0083	Prehistoric	-75.53633 41.09589
36LU0140	Prehistoric	-75.72308 41.15104	36MR0084	Prehistoric	-75.5302 41.09604
36LU0141	Prehistoric	-75.72015 41.14449	36MR0085	Prehistoric	-75.47666 41.01518
36LU0142	Prehistoric	-75.71742 41.14246	36MR0086	Prehistoric	-75.64805 41.12384
36LU0144	Prehistoric	-75.70868 41.12369	36MR0089	Prehistoric	-75.64609 41.11354
Watershed 37-Appalachian Plateaus-Glaciated Low Plateau:					
36MR0033	Prehistoric	-75.26896 41.0397	36MR0096	Prehistoric	-75.12928 41.04732
36MR0056	Prehistoric	-75.18894 41.03863	36MR0099	Prehistoric	-75.12967 41.05049
36MR0090	Prehistoric	-75.31418 41.05006	36MR0220	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.32204 41.06367
Watershed 37-Appalachian Plateaus-Glaciated Pocono Plateau:					
36MR0217	Prehistoric	-75.37397 41.10696			
Watershed 42-Appalachian Plateaus-Glaciated Pocono Plateau:					
36LU0106	Prehistoric	-75.79929 41.14573			
Watershed 47-Appalachian Plateaus-Glaciated Pocono Plateau:					
36CR0046	Prehistoric	-75.59654 40.95842	36CR0049	Prehistoric	-75.59438 40.95798
36CR0047	Prehistoric	-75.57055 40.96186	36CR0119	Prehistoric	-75.61654 40.97726
36CR0048	Prehistoric	-75.60903 40.96082	36MR0166	Prehistoric	-75.50539 40.97914

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
Watershed 28-Ridge and Valley-Blue Mountain:					
36MR0001	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.08453 41.01811	36MR0123	Prehistoric	-75.11825 41.04505
36MR0002	Prehistoric	-75.07419 41.02029	36MR0126	Prehistoric	-75.10863 41.04954
36MR0003	Prehistoric	-75.06777 41.02198	36MR0128	Prehistoric	-75.12038 41.04671
36MR0004	Prehistoric	-75.06108 41.02509	36MR0129	Prehistoric	-75.1211 41.04721
36MR0005	Prehistoric	-75.05281 41.029	36MR0130	Prehistoric	-75.11461 41.04735
36MR0006	Prehistoric	-75.04197 41.03356	36MR0131	Prehistoric	-75.11424 41.04779
36MR0007	Prehistoric	-75.02854 41.04159	36MR0132	Prehistoric	-75.11289 41.04762
36MR0008	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.01921 41.05734	36MR0142	Prehistoric	-75.12503 41.04343
36MR0009	Prehistoric	-75.00595 41.07049	36MR0164	Prehistoric	-75.0942 41.05579
36MR0010	Prehistoric	-75.03829 41.03746	36MR0182	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.03093 41.08361
36MR0011	Prehistoric	-75.0331 41.03993	36MR0192	Prehistoric	-75.11567 41.04468
36MR0012	Prehistoric	-75.04772 41.03161	36MR0193	Prehistoric	-75.11513 41.04829
36MR0013	Prehistoric	-74.9826 41.08095	36MR0202	Prehistoric	-75.10173 41.0292
36MR0014	Prehistoric	-75.07156 41.06458	36MR0203	Prehistoric	-75.10076 41.02931
36MR0015	Prehistoric	-74.9758 41.09157	36MR0204	Prehistoric	-75.10014 41.02978
36MR0042	Prehistoric	-75.07933 41.02202	36MR0205	Prehistoric	-75.1035 41.02637
36MR0045	Prehistoric	-75.09948 41.011	36MR0206	Prehistoric	-75.10425 41.02782
36MR0046	Prehistoric	-74.98896 41.08749	36MR0207	Prehistoric	-75.10432 41.02848
36MR0048	Prehistoric	-75.05064 41.0512	36MR0208	Prehistoric	-75.10481 41.03054
36MR0059	Prehistoric	-74.97069 41.08865	36MR0209	Prehistoric	-75.09781 41.03546
36MR0060	Prehistoric	-75.00091 41.07512	36MR0223	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.09169 41.01684
36MR0061	Prehistoric	-75.00457 41.0789	36MR0224	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.02556 41.08124
36MR0062	Prehistoric	-74.9938 41.08207	36MR0226	Prehistoric	-75.0051 41.07545
36MR0064	Prehistoric	-75.03267 41.08293	36MR0227	Prehistoric	-75.01035 41.07652
36MR0066	Prehistoric	-75.03743 41.0694	36MR0228	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.01014 41.07737
36MR0067	Prehistoric	-75.0427 41.06738	36MR0230	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.01076 41.07872
36MR0072	Prehistoric	-75.04881 41.05225	36MR0231	Prehistoric	-75.01442 41.0767
36MR0102	Prehistoric	-75.11657 41.04334	36PI0017	Prehistoric	-75.02079 41.0853
36MR0112	Prehistoric	-75.11729 41.04376	36PI0018	Prehistoric	-75.03065 41.08469
36MR0118	Prehistoric	-75.09291 41.05664	36PI0021	Prehistoric	-74.99209 41.09523
36MR0122	Prehistoric	-75.12131 41.04468	36PI0245	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.00816 41.08825
Watershed 37-Ridge and Valley-Blue Mountain:					
36MR0016	Prehistoric	-75.13726 40.98956	36MR0135	Prehistoric	-75.12643 41.02953
36MR0017	Prehistoric	-75.13108 40.99864	36MR0136	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.1313 41.04545
36MR0018	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.13239 40.9972	36MR0137	Prehistoric	-75.13084 41.04203
36MR0021	Prehistoric	-75.12735 41.00093	36MR0138	Prehistoric	-75.13078 41.04314
36MR0022	Prehistoric	-75.12572 41.00313	36MR0139	Prehistoric	-75.13443 41.04619
36MR0023	Prehistoric	-75.14 40.97718	36MR0140	Prehistoric	-75.13352 41.04534
36MR0024	Prehistoric	-75.14171 40.97936	36MR0141	Prehistoric	-75.12828 41.0423
36MR0025	Prehistoric	-75.12111 41.00032	36MR0143	Prehistoric	-75.12509 41.04044
36MR0026	Prehistoric	-75.23306 40.97375	36MR0144	Prehistoric	-75.12927 41.04414
36MR0027	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.13871 40.99576	36MR0145	Prehistoric	-75.12885 41.04209
36MR0028	Prehistoric	-75.14033 40.99729	36MR0146	Prehistoric	-75.12938 41.04193
36MR0029	Prehistoric	-75.13957 40.99186	36MR0147	Prehistoric	-75.12989 41.04379
36MR0030	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.1851 41.01821	36MR0148	Prehistoric	-75.12791 41.03981
36MR0039	Prehistoric	-75.32285 40.93826	36MR0150	Prehistoric	-75.12941 41.04475
36MR0041	Prehistoric	-75.31313 40.9309	36MR0151	Prehistoric	-75.12862 41.04612
36MR0043	Prehistoric	-75.13329 40.99257	36MR0152	Prehistoric	-75.19945 41.0285
36MR0044	Prehistoric	-75.14282 41	36MR0153	Prehistoric	-75.27857 40.95997
36MR0057	Prehistoric	-75.20194 41.016	36MR0154	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.15651 40.95732

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36MR0091	Prehistoric	-75.12366 41.04169	36MR0155	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.15598 40.95854
36MR0092	Prehistoric	-75.12317 41.04204	36MR0156	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.15666 40.9545
36MR0093	Prehistoric	-75.12525 41.03097	36MR0157	Prehistoric	-75.15638 40.95614
36MR0094	Prehistoric	-75.13035 41.04485	36MR0159	Prehistoric	-75.3482 40.96409
36MR0095	Prehistoric	-75.13057 41.04686	36MR0160	Prehistoric	-75.2778 40.95903
36MR0097	Prehistoric	-75.12876 41.04682	36MR0168	Prehistoric	-75.28735 40.95283
36MR0098	Prehistoric	-75.12524 41.03557	36MR0169	Prehistoric	-75.12122 41.03941
36MR0100	Prehistoric	-75.1286 41.04271	36MR0170	Prehistoric	-75.12179 41.04109
36MR0101	Prehistoric	-75.11766 41.04011	36MR0171	Prehistoric	-75.12107 41.04132
36MR0103	Prehistoric	-75.13206 41.04185	36MR0172	Prehistoric	-75.12142 41.04135
36MR0104	Prehistoric	-75.13166 41.04315	36MR0173	Prehistoric	-75.121 41.04363
36MR0105	Prehistoric	-75.13232 41.04273	36MR0174	Prehistoric	-75.12159 41.04414
36MR0106	Prehistoric	-75.13351 41.04407	36MR0179	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.13128 40.99341
36MR0107	Prehistoric	-75.12436 41.03566	36MR0183	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.15909 40.97269
36MR0108	Prehistoric	-75.12304 41.03529	36MR0184	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.15676 41.00167
36MR0109	Prehistoric	-75.12255 41.03623	36MR0185	Prehistoric	-75.15654 41.00243
36MR0110	Prehistoric	-75.12193 41.03446	36MR0186	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.15987 40.97397
36MR0111	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.12212 41.03509	36MR0187	Prehistoric	-75.15617 41.00325
36MR0113	Prehistoric	-75.12158 41.03998	36MR0188	Prehistoric	-75.13373 41.0308
36MR0114	Prehistoric	-75.1215 41.0397	36MR0189	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.12719 41.04028
36MR0115	Prehistoric	-75.12079 41.04002	36MR0190	Prehistoric	-75.12072 41.04144
36MR0116	Prehistoric	-75.12165 41.03942	36MR0191	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.11752 41.04307
36MR0117	Prehistoric	-75.12123 41.03928	36MR0194	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.16113 40.97584
36MR0119	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.12319 41.04036	36MR0195	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.16155 40.97648
36MR0120	Prehistoric	-75.12421 41.03046	36MR0196	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.16189 40.97698
36MR0121	Prehistoric	-75.11789 41.04229	36MR0198	Prehistoric	-75.15775 40.99358
36MR0124	Prehistoric	-75.11767 41.04266	36MR0199	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.15146 40.99901
36MR0125	Prehistoric	-75.11934 41.03819	36MR0200	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.15836 40.98849
36MR0127	Prehistoric	-75.11822 41.03862	36MR0221	Prehistoric	-75.22714 40.95793
36MR0133	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.12252 41.04064	36MR0235	Prehistoric	-75.28533 40.95957
36MR0134	Prehistoric	-75.12676 41.04269	36MR0236	Prehistoric	-75.28539 40.959
Watershed 47-Ridge and Valley-Blue Mountain:					
36CR0003	Prehistoric	-75.82535 40.78595	36CR0058	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.61528 40.89499
36CR0005	Prehistoric	-75.57076 40.81935	36CR0061	Prehistoric	-75.60696 40.88748
36CR0006	Prehistoric	-75.76837 40.80722	36CR0062	Prehistoric	-75.60687 40.88104
36CR0007	Prehistoric	-75.7575 40.80885	36CR0063	Prehistoric	-75.55426 40.91328
36CR0008	Prehistoric	-75.63573 40.80524	36CR0064	Prehistoric	-75.5503 40.90807
36CR0009	Prehistoric	-75.63427 40.7899	36CR0065	Prehistoric	-75.54533 40.96481
36CR0010	Prehistoric	-75.63299 40.79032	36CR0066	Prehistoric	-75.54476 40.96383
36CR0011	Prehistoric	-75.6648 40.79462	36CR0067	Prehistoric	-75.54434 40.96313
36CR0012	Prehistoric	-75.62745 40.79131	36CR0078	Prehistoric	-75.52601 40.82126
36CR0013	Prehistoric	-75.55616 40.80513	36CR0083	Prehistoric	-75.52335 40.82371
36CR0014	Prehistoric	-75.60987 40.79492	36CR0087	Prehistoric	-75.59781 40.8055
36CR0015	Prehistoric	-75.6111 40.79579	36CR0092	Prehistoric	-75.60812 40.86868
36CR0016	Prehistoric	-75.61339 40.79466	36CR0094	Prehistoric	-75.58991 40.87099
36CR0017	Prehistoric	-75.60409 40.79761	36CR0095	Prehistoric	-75.5748 40.87403
36CR0018	Prehistoric	-75.60013 40.80098	36CR0099	Prehistoric	-75.5555 40.88264
36CR0019	Prehistoric	-75.6044 40.79952	36CR0100	Prehistoric	-75.56224 40.8855
36CR0020	Prehistoric	-75.62342 40.79476	36CR0101	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.57908 40.87613
36CR0021	Prehistoric	-75.64391 40.78993	36CR0102	Prehistoric	-75.55426 40.88153
36CR0022	Prehistoric	-75.66293 40.79328	36CR0115	Prehistoric	-75.5975 40.86885
36CR0023	Prehistoric	-75.66795 40.79141	36CR0116	Prehistoric	-75.58278 40.8739

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36CR0024	Prehistoric	-75.69139 40.78746	36CR0117	Prehistoric	-75.52762 40.82132
36CR0025	Prehistoric	-75.52912 40.81759	36CR0131	Prehistoric	-75.60645 40.8106
36CR0026	Prehistoric	-75.5224 40.81957	36CR0132	Prehistoric	-75.58189 40.81693
36CR0027	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.5242 40.8209	36CR0133	Prehistoric	-75.56926 40.81841
36CR0028	Prehistoric	-75.52448 40.82251	36CR0134	Prehistoric	-75.54649 40.82415
36CR0029	Prehistoric	-75.51992 40.8248	36CR0135	Prehistoric	-75.65945 40.78368
36CR0031	Prehistoric	-75.55706 40.81518	36CR0136	Prehistoric	-75.63724 40.79939
36CR0032	Prehistoric	-75.65724 40.79215	36CR0137	Prehistoric	-75.63776 40.78748
36CR0033	Prehistoric	-75.63143 40.7905	36CR0138	Prehistoric	-75.64376 40.78752
36CR0034	Prehistoric	-75.632 40.80161	36CR0139	Prehistoric	-75.61964 40.79066
36CR0035	Prehistoric	-75.7574 40.81231	36MR0038	Prehistoric	-75.56618 40.94595
36CR0039	Prehistoric	-75.6214 40.79801	36MR0055	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.34455 40.88689
36CR0040	Prehistoric	-75.52915 40.82132	36MR0087	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.42792 40.96571
36CR0041	Prehistoric	-75.69262 40.84772	36MR0167	Prehistoric	-75.50866 40.97568
36CR0042	Prehistoric	-75.61835 40.85988	36MR0176	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.50687 40.97727
36CR0043	Prehistoric	-75.59807 40.86764	36MR0197	Prehistoric	-75.50369 40.89892
36CR0044	Prehistoric	-75.62267 40.86458	36MR0212	Prehistoric	-75.33676 40.85882
36CR0045	Prehistoric	-75.61363 40.85747	36MR0216	Prehistoric	-75.48724 40.89984
36CR0050	Prehistoric	-75.58778 40.94794	36SC0010	Prehistoric	-75.84274 40.70182
36CR0051	Prehistoric	-75.58597 40.9458	36SC0011	Prehistoric	-75.85162 40.71087
36CR0052	Prehistoric	-75.58541 40.94465	36SC0013	Prehistoric	-75.8875 40.7023
36CR0053	Prehistoric	-75.58475 40.9419	36SC0018	Prehistoric	-75.87852 40.70354
36CR0054	Prehistoric	-75.58302 40.94181	36SC0019	Prehistoric	-75.88314 40.76599
36CR0055	Prehistoric	-75.56543 40.94153	36SC0020	Prehistoric	-75.89733 40.76935
36CR0056	Prehistoric	-75.62426 40.89088	36SC0021	Prehistoric	-75.88031 40.76677
36CR0057	Prehistoric	-75.62293 40.89085	36SC0048	Prehistoric	-75.92032 40.75641
Watershed 49-Ridge and Valley-Great Valley:					
36NM0001	Prehistoric	-75.07677 40.90027	36NM0122	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.27021 40.81368
36NM0002	Prehistoric	-75.07916 40.89828	36NM0123	Prehistoric	-75.27878 40.81925
36NM0003	Prehistoric	-75.08973 40.91833	36NM0124	Prehistoric	-75.27266 40.81533
36NM0004	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.08224 40.91207	36NM0141	Prehistoric	-75.21746 40.77097
36NM0005	Prehistoric	-75.07073 40.88136	36NM0150	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.20192 40.76641
36NM0006	Prehistoric	-75.09054 40.85335	36NM0151	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.21114 40.75472
36NM0007	Prehistoric	-75.09324 40.85195	36NM0162	Prehistoric	-75.2881 40.68726
36NM0008	Prehistoric	-75.08662 40.82521	36NM0163	Prehistoric	-75.28113 40.71201
36NM0009	Prehistoric	-75.13442 40.77522	36NM0165	Prehistoric	-75.25614 40.72181
36NM0010	Prehistoric	-75.15996 40.78048	36NM0167	Prehistoric	-75.22629 40.76203
36NM0011	Prehistoric	-75.2624 40.75899	36NM0169	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.24495 40.73528
36NM0012	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.18759 40.75857	36NM0170	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.24599 40.73327
36NM0013	Prehistoric	-75.07846 40.90473	36NM0171	Prehistoric	-75.23612 40.74814
36NM0014	Prehistoric	-75.17625 40.77657	36NM0172	Prehistoric	-75.22529 40.76467
36NM0015	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.21092 40.76996	36NM0181	Prehistoric	-75.24407 40.73776
36NM0016	Prehistoric	-75.30815 40.78252	36NM0193	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.17924 40.7753
36NM0017	Prehistoric	-75.29621 40.79116	36NM0195	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.22154 40.77025
36NM0018	Prehistoric	-75.27805 40.75563	36NM0197	Prehistoric	-75.19931 40.80563
36NM0019	Prehistoric	-75.278 40.75936	36NM0199	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.19703 40.81198
36NM0020	Prehistoric	-75.25287 40.75882	36NM0200	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.1982 40.81454
36NM0021	Prehistoric	-75.30593 40.75389	36NM0201	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.17047 40.84236
36NM0022	Prehistoric	-75.30188 40.75415	36NM0202	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.16958 40.84368
36NM0023	Prehistoric	-75.30188 40.75664	36NM0203	Prehistoric	-75.16272 40.85864
36NM0024	Prehistoric	-75.29965 40.75647	36NM0204	Prehistoric	-75.16143 40.86196
36NM0025	Prehistoric	-75.292 40.75296	36NM0205	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.16109 40.87176

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36NM0029	Prehistoric	-75.15838 40.87278	36NM0208	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.16093 40.87378
36NM0031	Prehistoric	-75.26478 40.82588	36NM0209	Prehistoric	-75.16088 40.87916
36NM0032	Prehistoric	-75.11061 40.94346	36NM0220	Prehistoric	-75.21769 40.83966
36NM0035	Prehistoric	-75.23481 40.76541	36NM0222	Prehistoric	-75.15748 40.94366
36NM0037	Prehistoric	-75.26831 40.83291	36NM0244	Prehistoric	-75.05505 40.86893
36NM0038	Prehistoric	-75.27702 40.81633	36NM0254	Prehistoric	-75.18489 40.77539
36NM0039	Prehistoric	-75.26623 40.81854	36NM0255	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.15826 40.89617
36NM0040	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.28213 40.82356	36NM0256	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.15938 40.91108
36NM0041	Prehistoric	-75.24449 40.72966	36NM0258	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.19683 40.80865
36NM0042	Prehistoric	-75.24978 40.7465	36NM0259	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.16407 40.85537
36NM0043	Prehistoric	-75.24431 40.7461	36NM0260	Prehistoric	-75.16232 40.85978
36NM0044	Prehistoric	-75.2466 40.69171	36NM0261	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.16047 40.86437
36NM0051	Prehistoric	-75.21524 40.76668	36NM0262	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.15991 40.88625
36NM0052	Prehistoric	-75.23995 40.69131	36NM0263	Prehistoric	-75.15822 40.88896
36NM0053	Prehistoric	-75.24372 40.757	36NM0264	Prehistoric	-75.15687 40.89107
36NM0054	Prehistoric	-75.23921 40.69295	36NM0265	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.1571 40.89349
36NM0055	Prehistoric	-75.28866 40.78572	36NM0266	Prehistoric	-75.15851 40.89719
36NM0056	Prehistoric	-75.25345 40.71794	36NM0267	Prehistoric	-75.1602 40.90604
36NM0057	Prehistoric	-75.11818 40.79016	36NM0268	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.16116 40.87556
36NM0058	Prehistoric	-75.11902 40.79136	36NM0269	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.15888 40.9308
36NM0060	Prehistoric	-75.31979 40.80206	36NM0270	Prehistoric	-75.15724 40.9423
36NM0061	Prehistoric	-75.32058 40.80036	36NM0271	Prehistoric	-75.15662 40.89406
36NM0062	Prehistoric	-75.25143 40.68607	36NM0272	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.15809 40.88724
36NM0063	Prehistoric	-75.13035 40.81136	36NM0297	Prehistoric	-75.15919 40.9174
36NM0064	Prehistoric	-75.1286 40.80857	36NM0298	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.15823 40.90293
36NM0065	Prehistoric	-75.26132 40.79012	36NM0299	Prehistoric	-75.16974 40.84023
36NM0066	Prehistoric	-75.25373 40.71163	36NM0300	Prehistoric	-75.16948 40.84127
36NM0069	Prehistoric	-75.27823 40.82575	36NM0301	Prehistoric	-75.30846 40.68005
36NM0070	Prehistoric	-75.29018 40.80883	36NM0303	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.12855 40.95132
36NM0106	Prehistoric	-75.30402 40.7862	36NM0304	Prehistoric	-75.12897 40.94891
36NM0107	Prehistoric	-75.14684 40.87825	36NM0306	Prehistoric	-75.33216 40.81201
36NM0108	Prehistoric	-75.24547 40.81724	36NM0307	Prehistoric	-75.33314 40.81114
36NM0120	Prehistoric	-75.24794 40.74248	36NM0309	Prehistoric	-75.29364 40.74485
36NM0121	Prehistoric	-75.25488 40.74614	36NM0312	Prehistoric	-75.27837 40.75358
Watershed 52-Ridge and Valley-Blue Mountain:					
36SC0005	Prehistoric	-76.12708 40.63603	36SC0033	Prehistoric	-76.03288 40.66715
36SC0012	Prehistoric	-75.99596 40.6658	36SC0034	Prehistoric	-76.00854 40.66414
36SC0014	Prehistoric	-75.99674 40.681	36SC0035	Prehistoric	-76.01288 40.67927
36SC0015	Prehistoric	-75.99415 40.68722	36SC0036	Prehistoric	-76.00322 40.68793
36SC0016	Prehistoric	-75.9812 40.68899	36SC0037	Prehistoric	-75.99407 40.65101
36SC0017	Prehistoric	-75.98501 40.67994	36SC0038	Prehistoric	-75.99871 40.66978
36SC0022	Prehistoric	-75.92758 40.67853	36SC0039	Prehistoric	-76.01787 40.62319
36SC0023	Prehistoric	-75.96269 40.67995	36SC0040	Prehistoric	-76.03053 40.61183
36SC0024	Prehistoric	-75.95875 40.68088	36SC0041	Prehistoric	-76.03298 40.60724
36SC0025	Prehistoric	-76.07178 40.65067	36SC0057	Prehistoric	-76.19933 40.61731
36SC0026	Prehistoric	-76.05716 40.63899	36SC0071	Prehistoric	-76.05891 40.61987
36SC0027	Prehistoric	-76.02376 40.63264	36SC0072	Prehistoric	-76.05733 40.61969
36SC0028	Prehistoric	-76.0229 40.63667	36SC0073	Prehistoric	-76.05746 40.61965
36SC0029	Prehistoric	-76.01764 40.63533	36SC0080	Prehistoric	-76.13187 40.65042
36SC0030	Prehistoric	-76.01521 40.64535	36SC0081	Prehistoric	-76.06782 40.64456
36SC0031	Prehistoric	-76.01859 40.6496	36SC0082	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.05907 40.6398
36SC0032	Prehistoric	-76.0252 40.6668	36SC0083	Prehistoric	-76.02808 40.65016

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
Watershed 54-New England-Reading Prong:					
36BK0479	Prehistoric	-75.68393 40.49056	36LH0128	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.51019 40.50529
36BK0480	Prehistoric	-75.71828 40.48708	36LH0129	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.50717 40.50339
36BK0481	Prehistoric	-75.61814 40.5006	36LH0130	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.50525 40.50447
36BK0483	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.62293 40.50124	36LH0138	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.46122 40.52311
36BK0511	Prehistoric	-75.64306 40.49279	36LH0143	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.46092 40.52374
36BK0554	Prehistoric	-75.66623 40.47961	36LH0150	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.50795 40.50397
36LH0012	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.50112 40.50872	36LH0177	Prehistoric	-75.55025 40.50588
36LH0013	Prehistoric	-75.44572 40.56491	36LH0229	Prehistoric	-75.41149 40.53311
36LH0036	Prehistoric	-75.53142 40.50945	36LH0235	Prehistoric	-75.41017 40.52948
36LH0037	Prehistoric	-75.43883 40.52551	36NM0076	Prehistoric	-75.27162 40.62743
36LH0052	Prehistoric	-75.52938 40.50581	36NM0087	Prehistoric	-75.25837 40.60238
36LH0053	Prehistoric	-75.52627 40.50628	36NM0089	Prehistoric	-75.2887 40.62218
36LH0054	Prehistoric	-75.52395 40.50736	36NM0113	Prehistoric	-75.30701 40.60378
36LH0055	Prehistoric	-75.52249 40.50778	36NM0114	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.29163 40.61561
36LH0059	Prehistoric	-75.47681 40.50861	36NM0115	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.27983 40.6279
36LH0063	Prehistoric	-75.48816 40.50521	36NM0143	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.26675 40.60989
36LH0073	Prehistoric	-75.45641 40.50989	36NM0173	Prehistoric	-75.29647 40.61522
36LH0076	Prehistoric	-75.49434 40.49622	36NM0221	Prehistoric	-75.28068 40.63041
36LH0109	Prehistoric	-75.44136 40.56907	36NM0275	Prehistoric	-75.33191 40.62314
36LH0110	Prehistoric	-75.4614 40.50319			
Watershed 54-Ridge and Valley-Blue Mountain:					
36CR0038	Prehistoric	-75.61688 40.787	36LH0255	Prehistoric	-75.69239 40.76348
36LH0104	Prehistoric	-75.69526 40.76328	36NM0102	Prehistoric	-75.60456 40.78467
36LH0254	Prehistoric	-75.69305 40.764	36NM0103	Prehistoric	-75.60412 40.78601
Watershed 54-Ridge and Valley-Great Valley:					
36BK0014	Prehistoric	-75.63932 40.48596	36LH0236	Prehistoric	-75.56596 40.56591
36BK0239	Prehistoric	-75.64786 40.49126	36LH0237	Prehistoric	-75.45003 40.50565
36BK0478	Prehistoric	-75.62821 40.49086	36LH0238	Prehistoric	-75.44942 40.50165
36BK0508	Prehistoric	-75.67331 40.49168	36LH0239	Prehistoric	-75.44851 40.50494
36BK0509	Prehistoric	-75.67413 40.49079	36LH0241	Prehistoric	-75.59305 40.56596
36BK0510	Prehistoric	-75.64932 40.48723	36LH0244	Prehistoric	-75.54983 40.63686
36BK0517	Prehistoric	-75.64448 40.49893	36LH0245	Prehistoric	-75.5457 40.63581
36BK0553	Prehistoric	-75.66261 40.48831	36LH0249	Prehistoric	-75.44755 40.50399
36BK0746	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.64579 40.492	36LH0250	Prehistoric	-75.44733 40.50466
36LH0001	Prehistoric	-75.40753 40.53415	36LH0251	Prehistoric	-75.45138 40.50571
36LH0002	Prehistoric	-75.45718 40.49997	36LH0252	Prehistoric	-75.44884 40.50451
36LH0003	Prehistoric	-75.62486 40.56533	36LH0253	Prehistoric	-75.39863 40.56695
36LH0004	Prehistoric	-75.50044 40.55235	36LH0256	Prehistoric	-75.64918 40.69535
36LH0005	Prehistoric	-75.60062 40.66732	36LH0265	Prehistoric	-75.45341 40.61835
36LH0006	Prehistoric	-75.53243 40.53253	36LH0266	Prehistoric	-75.60262 40.53599
36LH0007	Prehistoric	-75.5381 40.53378	36LH0267	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.60765 40.55683
36LH0008	Prehistoric	-75.5365 40.53421	36LH0269	Prehistoric	-75.53516 40.6759
36LH0009	Prehistoric	-75.53908 40.53963	36LH0272	Prehistoric	-75.59718 40.50164
36LH0010	Prehistoric	-75.5643 40.54232	36LH0273	Prehistoric	-75.45057 40.58385
36LH0011	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.54379 40.50936	36LH0274	Prehistoric	-75.45019 40.58323
36LH0014	Prehistoric	-75.41762 40.61447	36LH0275	Prehistoric	-75.65034 40.65108
36LH0015	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.42531 40.55753	36LH0276	Prehistoric	-75.58791 40.51043
36LH0016	Prehistoric	-75.49983 40.553	36LH0277	Prehistoric	-75.57928 40.51148
36LH0017	Prehistoric	-75.50692 40.56007	36LH0281	Prehistoric	-75.63162 40.53714

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LH0018	Prehistoric	-75.50099 40.55581	36LH0282	Prehistoric	-75.38691 40.61499
36LH0019	Prehistoric	-75.54741 40.61732	36LH0284	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.52478 40.67398
36LH0020	Prehistoric	-75.60501 40.53568	36LH0285	Prehistoric	-75.41924 40.60855
36LH0021	Prehistoric	-75.5432 40.54297	36LH0286	Prehistoric	-75.4149 40.61254
36LH0022	Prehistoric	-75.58349 40.54134	36LH0287	Prehistoric	-75.45811 40.6257
36LH0023	Prehistoric	-75.56996 40.53628	36LH0288	Prehistoric	-75.41521 40.55588
36LH0024	Prehistoric	-75.57719 40.65424	36LH0289	Prehistoric	-75.41071 40.56244
36LH0025	Prehistoric	-75.5864 40.65546	36LH0290	Prehistoric	-75.4117 40.56327
36LH0026	Prehistoric	-75.61997 40.64611	36LH0291	Prehistoric	-75.41549 40.56149
36LH0027	Prehistoric	-75.58948 40.6568	36LH0292	Prehistoric	-75.41472 40.55792
36LH0028	Prehistoric	-75.55963 40.62939	36LH0293	Prehistoric	-75.41475 40.56003
36LH0029	Prehistoric	-75.55924 40.62854	36LH0294	Prehistoric	-75.62993 40.54776
36LH0030	Prehistoric	-75.55672 40.62931	36LH0295	Prehistoric	-75.62836 40.54796
36LH0031	Prehistoric	-75.5554 40.62875	36LH0296	Prehistoric	-75.62189 40.54518
36LH0032	Prehistoric	-75.56485 40.62815	36LH0297	Prehistoric	-75.62231 40.54463
36LH0033	Prehistoric	-75.5637 40.62818	36LH0298	Prehistoric	-75.62397 40.54745
36LH0034	Prehistoric	-75.55828 40.62729	36LH0299	Prehistoric	-75.62787 40.54502
36LH0035	Prehistoric	-75.55535 40.62767	36LH0300	Prehistoric	-75.62719 40.54509
36LH0039	Prehistoric	-75.63358 40.55135	36LH0301	Prehistoric	-75.62657 40.54811
36LH0040	Prehistoric	-75.6356 40.54132	36LH0302	Prehistoric	-75.62891 40.54916
36LH0041	Prehistoric	-75.6407 40.56015	36LH0303	Prehistoric	-75.4519 40.61865
36LH0042	Prehistoric	-75.64199 40.54774	36LH0305	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.42212 40.54739
36LH0043	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.55392 40.57882	36LH0306	Prehistoric	-75.42105 40.5478
36LH0044	Prehistoric	-75.54977 40.57938	36LH0307	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.42029 40.54832
36LH0045	Prehistoric	-75.53945 40.57536	36LH0308	Prehistoric	-75.41823 40.54978
36LH0046	Prehistoric	-75.53678 40.57599	36LH0309	Prehistoric	-75.65034 40.55506
36LH0047	Prehistoric	-75.53499 40.57793	36LH0310	Prehistoric	-75.64997 40.55528
36LH0048	Prehistoric	-75.62422 40.54806	36LH0311	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.6485 40.55571
36LH0049	Prehistoric	-75.53269 40.53407	36LH0313	Prehistoric	-75.64787 40.55696
36LH0050	Prehistoric	-75.53983 40.53678	36LH0315	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.46561 40.49664
36LH0051	Prehistoric	-75.51617 40.5162	36LH0321	Prehistoric	-75.51285 40.5226
36LH0056	Prehistoric	-75.53666 40.53287	36LH0322	Prehistoric	-75.51106 40.52104
36LH0058	Prehistoric	-75.47998 40.5098	36LH0323	Prehistoric	-75.50946 40.51951
36LH0060	Prehistoric	-75.42389 40.55014	36LH0324	Prehistoric	-75.50888 40.51895
36LH0061	Prehistoric	-75.42401 40.53442	36LH0325	Prehistoric	-75.50901 40.51791
36LH0062	Prehistoric	-75.40897 40.5643	36LH0327	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.57713 40.62124
36LH0064	Prehistoric	-75.46479 40.52636	36LH0328	Prehistoric	-75.57514 40.60675
36LH0065	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.45757 40.52765	36LH0329	Prehistoric	-75.57668 40.60988
36LH0066	Prehistoric	-75.45398 40.54583	36LH0333	Prehistoric	-75.6918 40.67959
36LH0067	Prehistoric	-75.45177 40.54778	36LH0334	Prehistoric	-75.48338 40.65463
36LH0068	Prehistoric	-75.4493 40.54683	36LH0335	Prehistoric	-75.51058 40.66858
36LH0069	Prehistoric	-75.44636 40.55029	36LH0336	Prehistoric	-75.53147 40.67629
36LH0070	Prehistoric	-75.44157 40.55566	36LH0337	Prehistoric	-75.53515 40.52786
36LH0071	Prehistoric	-75.43371 40.5332	36LH0338	Prehistoric	-75.52303 40.51307
36LH0072	Prehistoric	-75.4693 40.52186	36NM0026	Prehistoric	-75.33157 40.74347
36LH0074	Prehistoric	-75.42202 40.55776	36NM0027	Prehistoric	-75.33518 40.74576
36LH0077	Prehistoric	-75.43238 40.5275	36NM0028	Prehistoric	-75.33925 40.73853
36LH0095	Prehistoric	-75.75832 40.61522	36NM0033	Prehistoric	-75.31268 40.6326
36LH0103	Prehistoric	-75.60453 40.76343	36NM0034	Prehistoric	-75.23966 40.66835
36LH0105	Prehistoric	-75.60659 40.77742	36NM0036	Prehistoric	-75.37959 40.77317
36LH0106	Prehistoric	-75.65883 40.76143	36NM0046	Prehistoric	-75.3402 40.74202
36LH0107	Prehistoric	-75.67925 40.75264	36NM0047	Prehistoric	-75.34457 40.74052

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LH0108	Prehistoric	-75.6791 40.64599	36NM0048	Prehistoric	-75.34425 40.73799
36LH0111	Prehistoric	-75.40859 40.55018	36NM0049	Prehistoric	-75.34109 40.73802
36LH0112	Prehistoric	-75.4212 40.54983	36NM0050	Prehistoric	-75.34379 40.73345
36LH0113	Prehistoric	-75.4223 40.55097	36NM0059	Prehistoric	-75.38052 40.65314
36LH0114	Prehistoric	-75.39017 40.53849	36NM0067	Prehistoric	-75.50307 40.72282
36LH0115	Prehistoric	-75.44977 40.52804	36NM0068	Prehistoric	-75.50484 40.72443
36LH0116	Prehistoric	-75.53973 40.51734	36NM0072	Prehistoric	-75.31549 40.6289
36LH0117	Prehistoric	-75.52598 40.51603	36NM0073	Prehistoric	-75.26027 40.64065
36LH0119	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.63 40.56837	36NM0074	Prehistoric	-75.2586 40.64564
36LH0120	Prehistoric	-75.61876 40.56416	36NM0075	Prehistoric	-75.28294 40.63454
36LH0121	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.60232 40.5643	36NM0077	Prehistoric	-75.33404 40.63283
36LH0122	Prehistoric	-75.59287 40.56286	36NM0078	Prehistoric	-75.32619 40.63135
36LH0123	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.57331 40.54495	36NM0091	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.35386 40.59305
36LH0124	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.56522 40.53763	36NM0093	Prehistoric	-75.38733 40.57926
36LH0125	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.56565 40.53455	36NM0094	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.3881 40.57568
36LH0126	Prehistoric	-75.54488 40.52921	36NM0095	Prehistoric	-75.3897 40.57732
36LH0127	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.54513 40.52557	36NM0096	Prehistoric	-75.60261 40.77876
36LH0131	Prehistoric	-75.50326 40.50368	36NM0097	Prehistoric	-75.60017 40.76473
36LH0132	Prehistoric	-75.4982 40.5025	36NM0098	Prehistoric	-75.58177 40.73664
36LH0133	Prehistoric	-75.49529 40.5042	36NM0099	Prehistoric	-75.5509 40.72539
36LH0134	Prehistoric	-75.48965 40.50638	36NM0100	Prehistoric	-75.60199 40.76027
36LH0135	Prehistoric	-75.47415 40.51116	36NM0101	Prehistoric	-75.604 40.77342
36LH0136	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.47063 40.51305	36NM0104	Prehistoric	-75.30786 40.6338
36LH0137	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.46705 40.51641	36NM0105	Prehistoric	-75.36018 40.55786
36LH0139	Prehistoric	-75.45732 40.53026	36NM0109	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.36795 40.59095
36LH0140	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.42718 40.54646	36NM0110	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.36668 40.5909
36LH0141	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.4465 40.53739	36NM0111	Prehistoric	-75.36112 40.59329
36LH0142	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.43063 40.5437	36NM0112	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.34914 40.59612
36LH0144	Prehistoric	-75.42646 40.54879	36NM0116	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.27512 40.63577
36LH0145	Prehistoric	-75.42867 40.54892	36NM0117	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.26821 40.64059
36LH0146	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.42499 40.55184	36NM0118	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.22498 40.6685
36LH0147	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.41265 40.56485	36NM0119	Prehistoric	-75.3594 40.61842
36LH0148	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.43704 40.53903	36NM0126	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.38173 40.66195
36LH0149	Prehistoric	-75.57102 40.54263	36NM0127	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.38589 40.66319
36LH0151	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.5825 40.58596	36NM0140	Prehistoric	-75.27778 40.64263
36LH0152	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.57116 40.58387	36NM0142	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.54257 40.73236
36LH0153	Prehistoric	-75.56885 40.58335	36NM0149	Prehistoric	-75.48163 40.7888
36LH0154	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.56595 40.58107	36NM0157	Prehistoric	-75.29242 40.67331
36LH0155	Prehistoric	-75.43737 40.53231	36NM0158	Prehistoric	-75.29669 40.67103
36LH0156	Prehistoric	-75.45102 40.59574	36NM0159	Prehistoric	-75.2972 40.67011
36LH0157	Prehistoric	-75.47335 40.61944	36NM0164	Prehistoric	-75.29316 40.63565
36LH0158	Prehistoric	-75.57414 40.62555	36NM0168	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.36081 40.70971
36LH0159	Prehistoric	-75.59744 40.62624	36NM0175	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.35921 40.70975
36LH0160	Prehistoric	-75.58276 40.61608	36NM0176	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.35631 40.71202
36LH0161	Prehistoric	-75.45806 40.62723	36NM0177	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.38248 40.7037
36LH0162	Prehistoric	-75.57693 40.67284	36NM0178	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.37864 40.7043
36LH0163	Prehistoric	-75.58285 40.67694	36NM0184	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.296 40.6409
36LH0164	Prehistoric	-75.57372 40.66817	36NM0210	Prehistoric	-75.36234 40.67175
36LH0165	Prehistoric	-75.5737 40.67488	36NM0211	Prehistoric	-75.35929 40.67197
36LH0166	Prehistoric	-75.56526 40.72034	36NM0212	Prehistoric	-75.4515 40.70181
36LH0167	Prehistoric	-75.59752 40.66832	36NM0215	Prehistoric	-75.37741 40.73025
36LH0168	Prehistoric	-75.66964 40.75412	36NM0217	Prehistoric	-75.37652 40.73021

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LH0169	Prehistoric	-75.63961 40.75307	36NM0218	Prehistoric	-75.37813 40.73153
36LH0172	Prehistoric	-75.61191 40.7796	36NM0223	Prehistoric	-75.45889 40.68039
36LH0173	Prehistoric	-75.64207 40.67542	36NM0229	Prehistoric	-75.45055 40.70079
36LH0174	Prehistoric	-75.63493 40.74851	36NM0230	Prehistoric	-75.42078 40.66083
36LH0175	Prehistoric	-75.62948 40.72179	36NM0231	Prehistoric	-75.41937 40.66098
36LH0176	Prehistoric	-75.53901 40.5135	36NM0232	Prehistoric	-75.41909 40.6605
36LH0178	Prehistoric	-75.69413 40.56666	36NM0233	Prehistoric	-75.41986 40.66021
36LH0179	Prehistoric	-75.55212 40.50966	36NM0234	Prehistoric	-75.35494 40.59167
36LH0182	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.45785 40.59949	36NM0235	Prehistoric	-75.35361 40.59156
36LH0188	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.60971 40.50754	36NM0236	Prehistoric	-75.3521 40.59156
36LH0189	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.38917 40.54136	36NM0237	Prehistoric	-75.3575 40.59133
36LH0190	Prehistoric	-75.42013 40.55177	36NM0238	Prehistoric	-75.35125 40.59435
36LH0191	Prehistoric	-75.62512 40.54552	36NM0239	Prehistoric	-75.35074 40.59521
36LH0192	Prehistoric	-75.60885 40.55332	36NM0240	Prehistoric	-75.39934 40.70597
36LH0193	Prehistoric	-75.57895 40.56503	36NM0243	Prehistoric	-75.34252 40.56096
36LH0194	Prehistoric	-75.6848 40.56133	36NM0246	Prehistoric	-75.32368 40.61711
36LH0195	Prehistoric	-75.62304 40.54309	36NM0251	Prehistoric	-75.46428 40.67877
36LH0196	Prehistoric	-75.63524 40.53995	36NM0252	Prehistoric	-75.46446 40.67726
36LH0197	Prehistoric	-75.6315 40.53966	36NM0253	Prehistoric	-75.4661 40.67582
36LH0198	Prehistoric	-75.65166 40.54146	36NM0273	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.31052 40.58181
36LH0199	Prehistoric	-75.6682 40.54488	36NM0274	Prehistoric	-75.32985 40.63399
36LH0200	Prehistoric	-75.58092 40.55619	36NM0276	Prehistoric	-75.34278 40.67922
36LH0201	Prehistoric	-75.6484 40.693	36NM0277	Prehistoric	-75.38286 40.65052
36LH0205	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.46881 40.64823	36NM0278	Prehistoric	-75.34953 40.68819
36LH0206	Prehistoric	-75.64942 40.54046	36NM0279	Prehistoric	-75.35072 40.67655
36LH0208	Prehistoric	-75.61596 40.55323	36NM0280	Prehistoric	-75.3384 40.6218
36LH0209	Prehistoric	-75.61462 40.55265	36NM0281	Prehistoric	-75.30787 40.63261
36LH0210	Prehistoric	-75.61572 40.55481	36NM0282	Prehistoric	-75.31772 40.6355
36LH0211	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.61648 40.55399	36NM0283	Prehistoric	-75.32284 40.63345
36LH0212	Prehistoric	-75.6105 40.56016	36NM0284	Prehistoric	-75.32396 40.63471
36LH0213	Prehistoric	-75.58655 40.56171	36NM0285	Prehistoric	-75.33086 40.63451
36LH0215	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.4023 40.62893	36NM0286	Prehistoric	-75.31801 40.63351
36LH0216	Prehistoric	-75.5283 40.51508	36NM0287	Prehistoric	-75.32553 40.63432
36LH0218	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.42201 40.54937	36NM0288	Prehistoric	-75.32814 40.63515
36LH0221	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.53702 40.5147	36NM0289	Prehistoric	-75.32681 40.63467
36LH0222	Prehistoric	-75.60187 40.53131	36NM0290	Prehistoric	-75.31679 40.6347
36LH0223	Prehistoric	-75.58077 40.56212	36NM0291	Prehistoric	-75.28498 40.64008
36LH0224	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.574 40.5635	36NM0292	Prehistoric	-75.31381 40.62955
36LH0225	Prehistoric	-75.63178 40.56312	36NM0293	Prehistoric	-75.31512 40.62969
36LH0226	Prehistoric	-75.51357 40.52606	36NM0294	Prehistoric	-75.27877 40.64241
36LH0230	Prehistoric	-75.40255 40.55067	36NM0295	Prehistoric	-75.39012 40.69581
36LH0232	Prehistoric	-75.3968 40.54756	36NM0296	Prehistoric	-75.33875 40.74168
36LH0233	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.39984 40.54993			
Watershed 60-New England-Reading Prong:					
36BK0015	Prehistoric	-75.74171 40.47473	36BK0482	Prehistoric	-75.80928 40.43371
36BK0240	Prehistoric	-75.74466 40.47565	36BK0500	Prehistoric	-75.7626 40.46687
36BK0410	Prehistoric	-75.73219 40.47296	36BK0501	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.76254 40.4651
36BK0471	Prehistoric	-75.80185 40.43374	36BK0684	Prehistoric	-75.79518 40.43605
36BK0472	Prehistoric	-75.80074 40.43485			
Watershed 60-Ridge and Valley-Great Valley:					
36BK0016	Prehistoric	-75.87305 40.51701	36BK0436	Prehistoric	-75.87512 40.52218

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36BK0180	Prehistoric	-75.99878 40.45445	36BK0437	Prehistoric	-75.87665 40.52159
36BK0181	Prehistoric	-75.97231 40.49868	36BK0438	Prehistoric	-75.87821 40.51882
36BK0182	Prehistoric	-75.97822 40.45964	36BK0439	Prehistoric	-75.8753 40.51842
36BK0183	Prehistoric	-75.97587 40.45515	36BK0440	Prehistoric	-75.87979 40.51602
36BK0184	Prehistoric	-75.97003 40.44749	36BK0441	Prehistoric	-75.87739 40.5155
36BK0185	Prehistoric	-75.96944 40.43211	36BK0442	Prehistoric	-75.87752 40.51386
36BK0186	Prehistoric	-75.97401 40.43115	36BK0443	Prehistoric	-75.90102 40.51647
36BK0187	Prehistoric	-75.96976 40.43043	36BK0444	Prehistoric	-75.88384 40.50733
36BK0188	Prehistoric	-75.96239 40.42941	36BK0445	Prehistoric	-75.87194 40.50965
36BK0189	Prehistoric	-75.96053 40.42802	36BK0446	Prehistoric	-75.81541 40.53574
36BK0191	Prehistoric	-75.94777 40.42525	36BK0447	Prehistoric	-75.81724 40.50878
36BK0194	Prehistoric	-75.88962 40.46029	36BK0448	Prehistoric	-75.81252 40.50895
36BK0195	Prehistoric	-75.89432 40.44839	36BK0449	Prehistoric	-75.78509 40.52582
36BK0196	Prehistoric	-75.88263 40.44826	36BK0451	Prehistoric	-75.7947 40.51443
36BK0197	Prehistoric	-75.90232 40.44515	36BK0452	Prehistoric	-75.79256 40.51276
36BK0198	Prehistoric	-75.87861 40.43843	36BK0453	Prehistoric	-75.79225 40.50944
36BK0199	Prehistoric	-75.92919 40.42819	36BK0454	Prehistoric	-75.79397 40.52005
36BK0200	Prehistoric	-75.92685 40.42589	36BK0455	Prehistoric	-75.75496 40.55236
36BK0201	Prehistoric	-75.84486 40.49502	36BK0456	Prehistoric	-75.75582 40.54949
36BK0202	Prehistoric	-75.87164 40.44931	36BK0457	Prehistoric	-75.76087 40.54769
36BK0203	Prehistoric	-75.86623 40.45185	36BK0458	Prehistoric	-75.74608 40.53696
36BK0204	Prehistoric	-75.86507 40.45136	36BK0459	Prehistoric	-75.74921 40.53894
36BK0205	Prehistoric	-75.86163 40.44933	36BK0460	Prehistoric	-75.74869 40.53589
36BK0206	Prehistoric	-75.86245 40.44853	36BK0461	Prehistoric	-75.72764 40.55049
36BK0207	Prehistoric	-75.86071 40.44829	36BK0462	Prehistoric	-75.72222 40.5486
36BK0208	Prehistoric	-75.84006 40.45286	36BK0463	Prehistoric	-75.72251 40.54783
36BK0209	Prehistoric	-75.83938 40.45161	36BK0464	Prehistoric	-75.72085 40.54066
36BK0210	Prehistoric	-75.83348 40.46128	36BK0465	Prehistoric	-75.71856 40.54127
36BK0211	Prehistoric	-75.81037 40.46365	36BK0466	Prehistoric	-75.73394 40.55004
36BK0212	Prehistoric	-75.79965 40.46405	36BK0473	Prehistoric	-75.98557 40.42362
36BK0213	Prehistoric	-75.7949 40.46662	36BK0476	Prehistoric	-75.72224 40.55186
36BK0230	Prehistoric	-75.74436 40.48936	36BK0477	Prehistoric	-75.72083 40.54925
36BK0231	Prehistoric	-75.73969 40.48418	36BK0484	Prehistoric	-75.85492 40.63145
36BK0232	Prehistoric	-75.73492 40.48083	36BK0485	Prehistoric	-75.84489 40.63276
36BK0233	Prehistoric	-75.73427 40.47693	36BK0486	Prehistoric	-75.85076 40.64741
36BK0241	Prehistoric	-75.99857 40.52417	36BK0487	Prehistoric	-75.83934 40.63315
36BK0242	Prehistoric	-75.99835 40.51735	36BK0488	Prehistoric	-75.95276 40.63895
36BK0243	Prehistoric	-75.98902 40.55017	36BK0489	Prehistoric	-75.95083 40.63494
36BK0244	Prehistoric	-75.98794 40.54937	36BK0490	Prehistoric	-75.8965 40.62505
36BK0245	Prehistoric	-75.95725 40.51194	36BK0491	Prehistoric	-75.89056 40.63126
36BK0246	Prehistoric	-75.93866 40.51684	36BK0492	Prehistoric	-75.90079 40.6271
36BK0247	Prehistoric	-75.87492 40.54968	36BK0493	Prehistoric	-75.90355 40.63149
36BK0248	Prehistoric	-75.87641 40.52415	36BK0494	Prehistoric	-75.89238 40.6303
36BK0249	Prehistoric	-75.87871 40.52227	36BK0495	Prehistoric	-75.8592 40.62321
36BK0250	Prehistoric	-75.88072 40.52118	36BK0496	Prehistoric	-75.94071 40.64138
36BK0251	Prehistoric	-75.88732 40.50557	36BK0497	Prehistoric	-75.9202 40.62849
36BK0263	Prehistoric	-76.07991 40.46683	36BK0499	Prehistoric	-75.76318 40.47242
36BK0264	Prehistoric	-76.07143 40.46921	36BK0512	Prehistoric	-75.92334 40.42724
36BK0265	Prehistoric	-76.06691 40.47055	36BK0524	Prehistoric	-75.97215 40.50422
36BK0266	Prehistoric	-76.06423 40.45878	36BK0525	Prehistoric	-75.97115 40.50515
36BK0273	Prehistoric	-76.00797 40.43303	36BK0526	Prehistoric	-75.98577 40.50722
36BK0274	Prehistoric	-76.04015 40.48762	36BK0527	Prehistoric	-75.97703 40.50126

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36BK0275	Prehistoric	-76.04722 40.47949	36BK0528	Prehistoric	-75.9744 40.5044
36BK0276	Prehistoric	-76.04506 40.4753	36BK0529	Prehistoric	-75.78855 40.51136
36BK0277	Prehistoric	-76.02523 40.48086	36BK0532	Prehistoric	-75.97463 40.49968
36BK0278	Prehistoric	-76.02203 40.48323	36BK0533	Prehistoric	-75.88402 40.44416
36BK0279	Prehistoric	-76.01907 40.48175	36BK0534	Prehistoric	-75.88663 40.44516
36BK0282	Prehistoric	-76.01606 40.44387	36BK0535	Prehistoric	-75.96846 40.44657
36BK0283	Prehistoric	-76.0702 40.52565	36BK0536	Prehistoric	-75.92977 40.43916
36BK0284	Prehistoric	-76.05483 40.54659	36BK0537	Prehistoric	-75.93223 40.42819
36BK0285	Prehistoric	-76.057 40.50709	36BK0539	Prehistoric	-75.96298 40.44463
36BK0286	Prehistoric	-76.04032 40.55276	36BK0540	Prehistoric	-75.96457 40.44594
36BK0287	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.00758 40.53387	36BK0541	Prehistoric	-75.97499 40.49784
36BK0288	Prehistoric	-76.02251 40.50756	36BK0542	Prehistoric	-75.95953 40.42701
36BK0346	Prehistoric	-75.73184 40.54102	36BK0544	Prehistoric	-75.95886 40.43319
36BK0349	Prehistoric	-75.72153 40.56324	36BK0545	Prehistoric	-75.95901 40.43083
36BK0350	Prehistoric	-75.71423 40.56177	36BK0547	Prehistoric	-75.88105 40.54192
36BK0351	Prehistoric	-75.71883 40.55885	36BK0548	Prehistoric	-75.89614 40.62477
36BK0352	Prehistoric	-75.7233 40.55689	36BK0549	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.9472 40.42107
36BK0353	Prehistoric	-75.73088 40.5521	36BK0550	Prehistoric	-75.75191 40.53756
36BK0354	Prehistoric	-75.72067 40.55147	36BK0551	Prehistoric	-76.00369 40.47955
36BK0355	Prehistoric	-75.73165 40.54625	36BK0552	Prehistoric	-76.03312 40.49488
36BK0356	Prehistoric	-75.73977 40.53822	36BK0556	Prehistoric	-75.92561 40.42426
36BK0357	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.74308 40.53685	36BK0557	Prehistoric	-75.95118 40.42045
36BK0358	Prehistoric	-75.73973 40.55748	36BK0558	Prehistoric	-75.95475 40.4222
36BK0359	Prehistoric	-75.74871 40.55824	36BK0564	Prehistoric	-75.99706 40.51214
36BK0360	Prehistoric	-75.76432 40.54653	36BK0590	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.00057 40.53184
36BK0361	Prehistoric	-75.71855 40.54302	36BK0595	Prehistoric	-76.01255 40.53222
36BK0362	Prehistoric	-75.75964 40.5502	36BK0600	Prehistoric	-75.97935 40.45844
36BK0363	Prehistoric	-75.75401 40.53311	36BK0651	Prehistoric	-75.92144 40.42773
36BK0364	Prehistoric	-75.75766 40.5303	36BK0652	Prehistoric	-75.87818 40.45117
36BK0365	Prehistoric	-75.78076 40.52698	36BK0656	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.99916 40.52138
36BK0366	Prehistoric	-75.79004 40.52732	36BK0686	Prehistoric	-76.02886 40.50515
36BK0367	Prehistoric	-75.78793 40.52003	36BK0687	Prehistoric	-75.97421 40.45636
36BK0368	Prehistoric	-75.76969 40.52049	36BK0708	Prehistoric	-75.87805 40.44116
36BK0369	Prehistoric	-75.78636 40.53317	36BK0709	Prehistoric	-75.92458 40.42513
36BK0370	Prehistoric	-75.8105 40.53298	36BK0710	Prehistoric	-75.93665 40.42545
36BK0371	Prehistoric	-75.81032 40.53821	36BK0711	Prehistoric	-75.8851 40.4496
36BK0372	Prehistoric	-75.81776 40.5338	36BK0713	Prehistoric	-75.76484 40.51605
36BK0373	Prehistoric	-75.8274 40.53515	36BK0717	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.98722 40.42368
36BK0374	Prehistoric	-75.83705 40.53822	36BK0721	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.87407 40.5248
36BK0375	Prehistoric	-75.85026 40.53394	36BK0722	Prehistoric	-75.95197 40.56712
36BK0376	Prehistoric	-75.85073 40.53075	36BK0724	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.90445 40.42761
36BK0377	Prehistoric	-75.85728 40.53442	36BK0729	Prehistoric	-75.76681 40.51727
36BK0378	Prehistoric	-75.85619 40.53162	36BK0730	Prehistoric	-75.76477 40.51751
36BK0379	Prehistoric	-75.85638 40.52879	36BK0731	Prehistoric	-75.76358 40.51708
36BK0380	Prehistoric	-75.86107 40.52615	36BK0732	Prehistoric	-75.7651 40.5167
36BK0381	Prehistoric	-75.86985 40.5279	36BK0736	Prehistoric	-75.96953 40.48951
36BK0382	Prehistoric	-75.86817 40.52381	36BK0737	Prehistoric	-75.96347 40.49044
36BK0383	Prehistoric	-75.86994 40.51729	36BK0739	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.78859 40.51083
36BK0384	Prehistoric	-75.88257 40.56604	36BK0740	Prehistoric	-75.7922 40.51169
36BK0385	Prehistoric	-75.88852 40.55828	36BK0741	Prehistoric	-75.7891 40.51185
36BK0386	Prehistoric	-75.8785 40.55086	36BK0742	Prehistoric	-75.79076 40.5136
36BK0387	Prehistoric	-75.87557 40.5433	36BK0743	Prehistoric	-75.79371 40.51312

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36BK0388	Prehistoric	-75.87601 40.53823	36BK0749	Prehistoric	-75.76075 40.51726
36BK0389	Prehistoric	-75.87644 40.5312	36BK0859	Prehistoric	-75.74882 40.48444
36BK0390	Prehistoric	-75.88036 40.5314	36BK0864	Prehistoric	-75.87665 40.57327
36BK0391	Prehistoric	-75.8829 40.51843	36BK0866	Prehistoric	-75.80433 40.57865
36BK0392	Prehistoric	-75.88371 40.51354	36BK0872	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.93698 40.42808
36BK0393	Prehistoric	-75.87929 40.50897	36BK0894	Prehistoric	-75.9262 40.42465
36BK0394	Prehistoric	-75.88032 40.50472	36BK0911	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.9402 40.5311
36BK0395	Prehistoric	-75.86855 40.526	36BK0913	Prehistoric	-75.92828 40.4245
36BK0396	Prehistoric	-75.82837 40.50745	36BK0914	Prehistoric	-75.9241 40.42387
36BK0397	Prehistoric	-75.85484 40.52216	36LH0079	Prehistoric	-75.78395 40.70253
36BK0398	Prehistoric	-75.85805 40.52349	36LH0080	Prehistoric	-75.84402 40.64865
36BK0399	Prehistoric	-75.87938 40.5111	36LH0081	Prehistoric	-75.78451 40.69509
36BK0400	Prehistoric	-75.88131 40.50657	36LH0082	Prehistoric	-75.77497 40.65568
36BK0401	Prehistoric	-75.86873 40.53015	36LH0083	Prehistoric	-75.84818 40.66934
36BK0402	Prehistoric	-75.74628 40.54488	36LH0084	Prehistoric	-75.84628 40.67244
36BK0403	Prehistoric	-75.78094 40.52139	36LH0085	Prehistoric	-75.78356 40.67683
36BK0404	Prehistoric	-75.82656 40.49231	36LH0086	Prehistoric	-75.78423 40.65205
36BK0405	Prehistoric	-75.83171 40.49655	36LH0087	Prehistoric	-75.79049 40.64381
36BK0406	Prehistoric	-75.84667 40.49636	36LH0088	Prehistoric	-75.77973 40.63729
36BK0407	Prehistoric	-75.77602 40.5441	36LH0089	Prehistoric	-75.84602 40.65909
36BK0408	Prehistoric	-75.74494 40.48499	36LH0090	Prehistoric	-75.84411 40.65351
36BK0409	Prehistoric	-75.74278 40.48348	36LH0091	Prehistoric	-75.78274 40.62757
36BK0416	Prehistoric	-75.74011 40.47888	36LH0092	Prehistoric	-75.78979 40.63117
36BK0421	Prehistoric	-75.72556 40.5447	36LH0093	Prehistoric	-75.778 40.70713
36BK0422	Prehistoric	-75.72473 40.54355	36LH0094	Prehistoric	-75.75049 40.60801
36BK0423	Prehistoric	-75.86427 40.62247	36LH0096	Prehistoric	-75.74113 40.61534
36BK0424	Prehistoric	-75.86826 40.61932	36LH0097	Prehistoric	-75.78745 40.64493
36BK0425	Prehistoric	-75.86965 40.61339	36LH0098	Prehistoric	-75.84319 40.65643
36BK0428	Prehistoric	-75.84161 40.49651	36LH0099	Prehistoric	-75.85851 40.66976
36BK0429	Prehistoric	-75.82785 40.49438	36LH0100	Prehistoric	-75.85902 40.67427
36BK0430	Prehistoric	-75.83675 40.49588	36LH0101	Prehistoric	-75.85427 40.67459
36BK0431	Prehistoric	-75.88232 40.54347	36LH0102	Prehistoric	-75.84974 40.67313
36BK0432	Prehistoric	-75.8752 40.54067	36LH0170	Prehistoric	-75.788 40.67497
36BK0433	Prehistoric	-75.87809 40.52722	36LH0171	Prehistoric	-75.76692 40.716
36BK0434	Prehistoric	-75.87363 40.51434	36LH0234	Prehistoric	-75.80465 40.67394
36BK0435	Prehistoric	-75.87288 40.51969			
Watershed 63-New England-Reading Prong:					
36BU0026	Prehistoric	-75.2101 40.57545	36NM0081	Prehistoric	-75.18426 40.67061
36BU0113	Prehistoric	-75.2043 40.57172	36NM0082	Prehistoric	-75.18494 40.66757
36BU0114	Prehistoric	-75.19567 40.57398	36NM0084	Prehistoric	-75.22796 40.64811
36BU0116	Prehistoric	-75.20388 40.56937	36NM0085	Prehistoric	-75.22569 40.63613
36BU0217	Prehistoric	-75.20723 40.57477	36NM0086	Prehistoric	-75.25691 40.61597
36NM0079	Prehistoric	-75.18392 40.67844	36NM0088	Prehistoric	-75.2563 40.61986
36NM0080	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.17968 40.67426	36NM0090	Prehistoric	-75.25758 40.62114
Watershed 63-Ridge and Valley-Great Valley:					
36BU0004	Prehistoric	-75.19695 40.58057	36BU0315	Prehistoric	-75.19474 40.5859
36BU0112	Prehistoric	-75.1918 40.58941	36BU0359	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.30379 40.54565
36BU0115	Prehistoric	-75.19452 40.5976	36BU0403	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.19234 40.59372
36BU0119	Prehistoric	-75.1963 40.58352	36NM0045	Prehistoric	-75.20447 40.68981
36BU0120	Prehistoric	-75.19815 40.58299	36NM0071	Prehistoric	-75.22999 40.61139
36BU0121	Prehistoric	-75.2114 40.58667	36NM0083	Prehistoric	-75.20396 40.64729

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36BU0122	Prehistoric	-75.21455 40.59013	36NM0092	Prehistoric	-75.19662 40.62145
36BU0123	Prehistoric	-75.20691 40.58991	36NM0138	Prehistoric	-75.23202 40.6149
36BU0169	Prehistoric	-75.19733 40.6058	36NM0227	Prehistoric	-75.20209 40.61937
36BU0171	Prehistoric	-75.27152 40.5559	36NM0228	Prehistoric	-75.20363 40.61759
36BU0196	Prehistoric	-75.19792 40.58131	36NM0241	Prehistoric	-75.19055 40.62648
Watershed 65-Ridge and Valley-Blue Mountain:					
36LE0056	Prehistoric	-76.6056 40.4459	36LE0416	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.61735 40.45888
36LE0057	Prehistoric	-76.62131 40.44686	36SC0009	Prehistoric	-76.37855 40.52234
36LE0058	Prehistoric	-76.62993 40.45175	36SC0042	Prehistoric	-76.46409 40.52197
36LE0059	Prehistoric	-76.58953 40.4596	36SC0043	Prehistoric	-76.37811 40.55464
36LE0095	Prehistoric	-76.63412 40.41831	36SC0044	Prehistoric	-76.38321 40.55971
36LE0405	Prehistoric	-76.61962 40.46022	36SC0045	Prehistoric	-76.3862 40.53818
36LE0407	Prehistoric	-76.64638 40.43683	36SC0060	Prehistoric	-76.37723 40.53767
36LE0414	Prehistoric	-76.59843 40.46417	36SC0061	Prehistoric	-76.37843 40.53874
36LE0415	Prehistoric	-76.60036 40.46313			
Watershed 65-Ridge and Valley-Great Valley:					
36BK0003	Prehistoric	-76.34455 40.46509	36LE0079	Prehistoric	-76.61513 40.36799
36BK0004	Prehistoric	-76.34684 40.45524	36LE0080	Prehistoric	-76.61631 40.3668
36BK0005	Prehistoric	-76.3836 40.47287	36LE0081	Prehistoric	-76.62323 40.3921
36BK0006	Prehistoric	-76.34859 40.4843	36LE0082	Prehistoric	-76.62419 40.39621
36BK0007	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.33452 40.44458	36LE0083	Prehistoric	-76.62533 40.40158
36BK0008	Prehistoric	-76.37215 40.46834	36LE0084	Prehistoric	-76.62685 40.40919
36BK0009	Prehistoric	-76.38577 40.47306	36LE0085	Prehistoric	-76.61392 40.39816
36BK0043	Prehistoric	-76.284 40.45568	36LE0086	Prehistoric	-76.61249 40.39983
36BK0044	Prehistoric	-76.29264 40.46503	36LE0087	Prehistoric	-76.61463 40.39561
36BK0045	Prehistoric	-76.27847 40.46598	36LE0088	Prehistoric	-76.61465 40.38703
36BK0046	Prehistoric	-76.27143 40.47256	36LE0089	Prehistoric	-76.63292 40.38904
36BK0047	Prehistoric	-76.2648 40.47226	36LE0090	Prehistoric	-76.6334 40.39112
36BK0048	Prehistoric	-76.25448 40.45379	36LE0091	Prehistoric	-76.64247 40.39673
36BK0049	Prehistoric	-76.26381 40.44443	36LE0092	Prehistoric	-76.64433 40.41163
36BK0050	Prehistoric	-76.29707 40.43282	36LE0093	Prehistoric	-76.64029 40.41398
36BK0051	Prehistoric	-76.29264 40.43329	36LE0094	Prehistoric	-76.63471 40.41393
36BK0052	Prehistoric	-76.29156 40.4322	36LE0096	Prehistoric	-76.6309 40.41816
36BK0053	Prehistoric	-76.2677 40.42539	36LE0097	Prehistoric	-76.62808 40.41531
36BK0054	Prehistoric	-76.26136 40.41357	36LE0098	Prehistoric	-76.62396 40.41942
36BK0055	Prehistoric	-76.27273 40.41089	36LE0099	Prehistoric	-76.62086 40.42048
36BK0056	Prehistoric	-76.26761 40.40511	36LE0100	Prehistoric	-76.61862 40.41857
36BK0057	Prehistoric	-76.26443 40.40932	36LE0101	Prehistoric	-76.61848 40.41575
36BK0058	Prehistoric	-76.26037 40.41059	36LE0102	Prehistoric	-76.64239 40.40813
36BK0059	Prehistoric	-76.27089 40.4075	36LE0103	Prehistoric	-76.62657 40.37033
36BK0060	Prehistoric	-76.26177 40.40734	36LE0104	Prehistoric	-76.61705 40.36265
36BK0061	Prehistoric	-76.24852 40.49614	36LE0105	Prehistoric	-76.62338 40.35944
36BK0062	Prehistoric	-76.2429 40.48237	36LE0106	Prehistoric	-76.61732 40.35446
36BK0063	Prehistoric	-76.24249 40.48081	36LE0107	Prehistoric	-76.61755 40.34845
36BK0064	Prehistoric	-76.23672 40.48017	36LE0108	Prehistoric	-76.61438 40.35114
36BK0065	Prehistoric	-76.22511 40.47871	36LE0109	Prehistoric	-76.61065 40.35402
36BK0066	Prehistoric	-76.2081 40.48772	36LE0110	Prehistoric	-76.61024 40.35742
36BK0067	Prehistoric	-76.23067 40.4745	36LE0111	Prehistoric	-76.60621 40.35702
36BK0068	Prehistoric	-76.20652 40.47485	36LE0112	Prehistoric	-76.60888 40.35369
36BK0070	Prehistoric	-76.2379 40.46154	36LE0113	Prehistoric	-76.59874 40.35371
36BK0305	Prehistoric	-76.3554 40.44829	36LE0114	Prehistoric	-76.59448 40.36281

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36BK0306	Prehistoric	-76.35401 40.45019	36LE0115	Prehistoric	-76.59072 40.36021
36BK0307	Prehistoric	-76.34853 40.45392	36LE0116	Prehistoric	-76.58882 40.3561
36BK0308	Prehistoric	-76.34392 40.47153	36LE0117	Prehistoric	-76.59425 40.35808
36BK0309	Prehistoric	-76.34351 40.47775	36LE0118	Prehistoric	-76.59272 40.35425
36BK0310	Prehistoric	-76.34741 40.48006	36LE0119	Prehistoric	-76.6129 40.34557
36BK0311	Prehistoric	-76.34714 40.49916	36LE0120	Prehistoric	-76.60743 40.34696
36BK0312	Prehistoric	-76.33211 40.48475	36LE0121	Prehistoric	-76.61843 40.34284
36BK0313	Prehistoric	-76.33565 40.44705	36LE0122	Prehistoric	-76.61533 40.34172
36BK0314	Prehistoric	-76.33106 40.44495	36LE0123	Prehistoric	-76.60857 40.34287
36BK0315	Prehistoric	-76.32805 40.44497	36LE0124	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.6044 40.31905
36BK0316	Prehistoric	-76.33162 40.45979	36LE0125	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.59745 40.31877
36BK0317	Prehistoric	-76.32336 40.46405	36LE0126	Prehistoric	-76.59774 40.32215
36BK0318	Prehistoric	-76.31548 40.46735	36LE0127	Prehistoric	-76.59022 40.32138
36BK0319	Prehistoric	-76.34993 40.44371	36LE0128	Prehistoric	-76.56357 40.32923
36BK0320	Prehistoric	-76.33908 40.43717	36LE0129	Prehistoric	-76.57105 40.34782
36BK0321	Prehistoric	-76.33653 40.44026	36LE0130	Prehistoric	-76.53927 40.35612
36BK0322	Prehistoric	-76.32363 40.44135	36LE0131	Prehistoric	-76.5514 40.30938
36BK0323	Prehistoric	-76.31346 40.43884	36LE0132	Prehistoric	-76.5544 40.29498
36BK0324	Prehistoric	-76.31774 40.43528	36LE0136	Prehistoric	-76.52238 40.27579
36BK0325	Prehistoric	-76.30327 40.43458	36LE0139	Prehistoric	-76.5106 40.33748
36BK0326	Prehistoric	-76.28943 40.43919	36LE0140	Prehistoric	-76.52715 40.34352
36BK0327	Prehistoric	-76.28273 40.4472	36LE0141	Prehistoric	-76.49931 40.32931
36BK0328	Prehistoric	-76.27886 40.45103	36LE0142	Prehistoric	-76.49094 40.33229
36BK0329	Prehistoric	-76.28798 40.44653	36LE0143	Prehistoric	-76.48656 40.33293
36BK0330	Prehistoric	-76.29035 40.45032	36LE0144	Prehistoric	-76.48946 40.33121
36BK0573	Prehistoric	-76.26907 40.42169	36LE0145	Prehistoric	-76.47269 40.33267
36BK0575	Prehistoric	-76.25867 40.41392	36LE0146	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.46256 40.33725
36BK0576	Prehistoric	-76.33007 40.49522	36LE0147	Prehistoric	-76.4711 40.34861
36BK0577	Prehistoric	-76.33276 40.49769	36LE0148	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.47645 40.35316
36BK0578	Prehistoric	-76.31117 40.49554	36LE0149	Prehistoric	-76.5956 40.43278
36BK0591	Prehistoric	-76.38651 40.47407	36LE0150	Prehistoric	-76.49455 40.39509
36BK0751	Prehistoric	-76.28104 40.43864	36LE0151	Prehistoric	-76.49723 40.40244
36BK0752	Prehistoric	-76.25116 40.45314	36LE0152	Prehistoric	-76.48219 40.40704
36BK0753	Prehistoric	-76.25789 40.45201	36LE0153	Prehistoric	-76.48405 40.41722
36BK0754	Prehistoric	-76.31021 40.4821	36LE0154	Prehistoric	-76.48708 40.4363
36BK0756	Prehistoric	-76.27237 40.48343	36LE0155	Prehistoric	-76.49467 40.44286
36BK0757	Prehistoric	-76.32148 40.48629	36LE0156	Prehistoric	-76.51097 40.44784
36BK0758	Prehistoric	-76.29061 40.45141	36LE0157	Prehistoric	-76.51656 40.47332
36BK0759	Prehistoric	-76.27623 40.48525	36LE0158	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.50912 40.47503
36BK0760	Prehistoric	-76.33271 40.48813	36LE0159	Prehistoric	-76.49667 40.47012
36BK0763	Prehistoric	-76.35387 40.44426	36LE0160	Prehistoric	-76.49168 40.47615
36BK0764	Prehistoric	-76.34838 40.44606	36LE0161	Prehistoric	-76.47616 40.47991
36BK0765	Prehistoric	-76.29628 40.40917	36LE0162	Prehistoric	-76.46797 40.48103
36BK0766	Prehistoric	-76.27658 40.4615	36LE0163	Prehistoric	-76.42598 40.46337
36BK0767	Prehistoric	-76.26587 40.41421	36LE0164	Prehistoric	-76.42714 40.41022
36BK0768	Prehistoric	-76.33232 40.45563	36LE0165	Prehistoric	-76.4385 40.41299
36BK0769	Prehistoric	-76.28697 40.48062	36LE0166	Prehistoric	-76.43572 40.41644
36BK0770	Prehistoric	-76.2773 40.469	36LE0167	Prehistoric	-76.42999 40.42539
36BK0771	Prehistoric	-76.33253 40.48013	36LE0168	Prehistoric	-76.43248 40.43575
36BK0772	Prehistoric	-76.25147 40.46296	36LE0169	Prehistoric	-76.41632 40.44215
36BK0776	Prehistoric	-76.30764 40.496	36LE0170	Prehistoric	-76.39079 40.4483
36BK0777	Prehistoric	-76.28258 40.44502	36LE0171	Prehistoric	-76.52365 40.4689

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36BK0778	Prehistoric	-76.35204 40.44859	36LE0172	Prehistoric	-76.35549 40.43694
36BK0779	Prehistoric	-76.35655 40.48281	36LE0173	Prehistoric	-76.36572 40.43032
36BK0780	Prehistoric	-76.2923 40.48939	36LE0174	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.36301 40.42695
36BK0781	Prehistoric	-76.29002 40.43582	36LE0175	Prehistoric	-76.36577 40.42412
36DA0016	Prehistoric	-76.6274 40.32733	36LE0176	Prehistoric	-76.3745 40.42734
36DA0061	Prehistoric	-76.63349 40.3103	36LE0177	Prehistoric	-76.36979 40.42563
36DA0062	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.62945 40.31384	36LE0178	Prehistoric	-76.37389 40.42343
36DA0063	Prehistoric	-76.62688 40.32003	36LE0179	Prehistoric	-76.3844 40.42604
36DA0064	Prehistoric	-76.62607 40.3226	36LE0180	Prehistoric	-76.40163 40.42277
36DA0065	Prehistoric	-76.62345 40.32669	36LE0181	Prehistoric	-76.39559 40.41658
36DA0066	Prehistoric	-76.61946 40.31754	36LE0182	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.40907 40.41008
36DA0067	Prehistoric	-76.64278 40.31939	36LE0183	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.4114 40.40509
36DA0068	Prehistoric	-76.64543 40.32204	36LE0184	Prehistoric	-76.41772 40.41071
36DA0069	Prehistoric	-76.64671 40.32631	36LE0185	Prehistoric	-76.40935 40.40236
36DA0071	Prehistoric	-76.64082 40.32653	36LE0186	Prehistoric	-76.41129 40.39761
36DA0072	Prehistoric	-76.67018 40.30614	36LE0187	Prehistoric	-76.40698 40.39492
36DA0073	Prehistoric	-76.67253 40.29793	36LE0188	Prehistoric	-76.4101 40.39495
36DA0074	Prehistoric	-76.63158 40.31733	36LE0189	Prehistoric	-76.41645 40.39741
36DA0075	Prehistoric	-76.63636 40.31294	36LE0190	Prehistoric	-76.4112 40.38509
36DA0076	Prehistoric	-76.6661 40.29926	36LE0191	Prehistoric	-76.41403 40.38252
36DA0077	Prehistoric	-76.64954 40.36085	36LE0192	Prehistoric	-76.41345 40.37992
36DA0078	Prehistoric	-76.64727 40.29008	36LE0193	Prehistoric	-76.43449 40.36212
36DA0079	Prehistoric	-76.6587 40.31638	36LE0194	Prehistoric	-76.38485 40.33199
36DA0080	Prehistoric	-76.6308 40.32339	36LE0195	Prehistoric	-76.49513 40.3646
36DA0081	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.66186 40.36992	36LE0200	Prehistoric	-76.47982 40.27021
36DA0082	Prehistoric	-76.65201 40.32747	36LE0201	Prehistoric	-76.48289 40.27574
36DA0083	Prehistoric	-76.69937 40.39108	36LE0202	Prehistoric	-76.48725 40.27816
36DA0084	Prehistoric	-76.68132 40.33272	36LE0205	Prehistoric	-76.46648 40.27187
36DA0108	Prehistoric	-76.72843 40.27142	36LE0206	Prehistoric	-76.46429 40.26927
36DA0109	Prehistoric	-76.69787 40.28609	36LE0207	Prehistoric	-76.45745 40.27032
36DA0117	Prehistoric	-76.65985 40.38304	36LE0208	Prehistoric	-76.45417 40.27209
36DA0118	Prehistoric	-76.64387 40.27687	36LE0209	Prehistoric	-76.45982 40.2842
36DA0119	Prehistoric	-76.66096 40.37881	36LE0210	Prehistoric	-76.46044 40.29652
36DA0120	Prehistoric	-76.72438 40.26409	36LE0211	Prehistoric	-76.48781 40.32899
36DA0121	Prehistoric	-76.72351 40.27356	36LE0213	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.43226 40.27714
36DA0127	Prehistoric	-76.62828 40.3175	36LE0215	Prehistoric	-76.43001 40.2951
36DA0135	Prehistoric	-76.65247 40.32273	36LE0218	Prehistoric	-76.41768 40.38694
36DA0136	Prehistoric	-76.6596 40.31604	36LE0220	Prehistoric	-76.43889 40.3884
36DA0137	Prehistoric	-76.65837 40.31817	36LE0235	Prehistoric	-76.58212 40.37119
36DA0142	Prehistoric	-76.68056 40.28655	36LE0236	Prehistoric	-76.507 40.44144
36DA0155	Prehistoric	-76.66821 40.29749	36LE0237	Prehistoric	-76.5021 40.44278
36DA0164	Prehistoric	-76.66953 40.30524	36LE0238	Prehistoric	-76.5035 40.44405
36DA0172	Prehistoric	-76.65888 40.3712	36LE0240	Prehistoric	-76.35262 40.44103
36DA0174	Prehistoric	-76.72303 40.26948	36LE0241	Prehistoric	-76.57827 40.34135
36DA0182	Prehistoric	-76.72802 40.33128	36LE0243	Prehistoric	-76.45945 40.41668
36DA0183	Prehistoric	-76.72718 40.33066	36LE0244	Prehistoric	-76.6261 40.34282
36DA0194	Prehistoric	-76.73462 40.35218	36LE0246	Prehistoric	-76.41988 40.40328
36DA0196	Prehistoric	-76.78664 40.33846	36LE0247	Prehistoric	-76.60703 40.36324
36DA0197	Prehistoric	-76.76043 40.32938	36LE0254	Prehistoric	-76.56411 40.36463
36DA0199	Prehistoric	-76.72691 40.25641	36LE0255	Prehistoric	-76.5629 40.40772
36DA0200	Prehistoric	-76.73626 40.25506	36LE0256	Prehistoric	-76.51533 40.32501
36DA0201	Prehistoric	-76.73296 40.25763	36LE0257	Prehistoric	-76.3874 40.33587

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36DA0208	Prehistoric	-76.65256 40.36189	36LE0258	Prehistoric	-76.45724 40.27396
36DA0209	Prehistoric	-76.63029 40.27112	36LE0259	Prehistoric	-76.40982 40.36096
36DA0210	Prehistoric	-76.63141 40.26235	36LE0280	Prehistoric	-76.43395 40.4108
36DA0219	Prehistoric	-76.74246 40.28789	36LE0281	Prehistoric	-76.3941 40.41218
36DA0221	Prehistoric	-76.75384 40.34374	36LE0282	Prehistoric	-76.38962 40.43701
36DA0233	Prehistoric	-76.67912 40.28732	36LE0283	Prehistoric	-76.38988 40.40678
36DA0239	Prehistoric	-76.69609 40.34591	36LE0284	Prehistoric	-76.3827 40.41305
36LE0001	Prehistoric	-76.58438 40.36694	36LE0285	Prehistoric	-76.41083 40.38673
36LE0002	Prehistoric	-76.5281 40.28071	36LE0286	Prehistoric	-76.37979 40.43385
36LE0003	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.525 40.27403	36LE0287	Prehistoric	-76.45654 40.44718
36LE0004	Prehistoric	-76.61731 40.32466	36LE0288	Prehistoric	-76.41193 40.45502
36LE0005	Prehistoric	-76.58038 40.36735	36LE0289	Prehistoric	-76.48864 40.44174
36LE0006	Prehistoric	-76.57733 40.36805	36LE0290	Prehistoric	-76.48764 40.43227
36LE0007	Prehistoric	-76.57588 40.3696	36LE0291	Prehistoric	-76.40262 40.41526
36LE0008	Prehistoric	-76.57451 40.37142	36LE0292	Prehistoric	-76.38787 40.43237
36LE0009	Prehistoric	-76.56848 40.37813	36LE0293	Prehistoric	-76.34505 40.42342
36LE0010	Prehistoric	-76.56311 40.38246	36LE0294	Prehistoric	-76.36772 40.4094
36LE0011	Prehistoric	-76.57004 40.3949	36LE0295	Prehistoric	-76.37314 40.40562
36LE0012	Prehistoric	-76.56985 40.3994	36LE0296	Prehistoric	-76.36265 40.40049
36LE0013	Prehistoric	-76.53836 40.37314	36LE0297	Prehistoric	-76.36318 40.38675
36LE0014	Prehistoric	-76.53368 40.3662	36LE0306	Prehistoric	-76.33105 40.42012
36LE0015	Prehistoric	-76.52985 40.36574	36LE0307	Prehistoric	-76.32237 40.41872
36LE0016	Prehistoric	-76.51357 40.36441	36LE0308	Prehistoric	-76.33377 40.41585
36LE0017	Prehistoric	-76.52342 40.36828	36LE0309	Prehistoric	-76.34118 40.40529
36LE0018	Prehistoric	-76.51812 40.37929	36LE0310	Prehistoric	-76.33806 40.40716
36LE0019	Prehistoric	-76.51989 40.38261	36LE0338	Prehistoric	-76.49388 40.43407
36LE0020	Prehistoric	-76.51689 40.38645	36LE0339	Prehistoric	-76.50548 40.47169
36LE0021	Prehistoric	-76.50176 40.39081	36LE0340	Prehistoric	-76.56432 40.38967
36LE0022	Prehistoric	-76.5049 40.38907	36LE0341	Prehistoric	-76.55014 40.39931
36LE0023	Prehistoric	-76.54798 40.39527	36LE0343	Prehistoric	-76.37337 40.37968
36LE0024	Prehistoric	-76.55186 40.39668	36LE0353	Prehistoric	-76.57153 40.38152
36LE0025	Prehistoric	-76.55009 40.40126	36LE0354	Prehistoric	-76.57097 40.38217
36LE0026	Prehistoric	-76.56045 40.39991	36LE0358	Prehistoric	-76.49418 40.42443
36LE0027	Prehistoric	-76.55393 40.40767	36LE0359	Prehistoric	-76.51353 40.47405
36LE0028	Prehistoric	-76.5542 40.40465	36LE0360	Prehistoric	-76.5495 40.4097
36LE0029	Prehistoric	-76.55299 40.41346	36LE0361	Prehistoric	-76.57094 40.4236
36LE0030	Prehistoric	-76.55476 40.41441	36LE0362	Prehistoric	-76.59551 40.30771
36LE0031	Prehistoric	-76.5507 40.42447	36LE0363	Prehistoric	-76.64137 40.38592
36LE0032	Prehistoric	-76.55409 40.42121	36LE0364	Prehistoric	-76.39774 40.38909
36LE0033	Prehistoric	-76.55233 40.42017	36LE0366	Prehistoric	-76.50139 40.40083
36LE0034	Prehistoric	-76.5521 40.42715	36LE0368	Prehistoric	-76.32727 40.40326
36LE0035	Prehistoric	-76.53308 40.43506	36LE0371	Prehistoric	-76.39111 40.41743
36LE0036	Prehistoric	-76.55003 40.44928	36LE0377	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.42919 40.30611
36LE0037	Prehistoric	-76.53676 40.45369	36LE0378	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.4296 40.3122
36LE0038	Prehistoric	-76.53909 40.45616	36LE0379	Prehistoric	-76.41776 40.27998
36LE0039	Prehistoric	-76.54267 40.456	36LE0380	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.41674 40.27619
36LE0040	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.52148 40.46974	36LE0384	Prehistoric	-76.43301 40.27717
36LE0041	Prehistoric	-76.56994 40.40618	36LE0385	Prehistoric	-76.47173 40.35175
36LE0042	Prehistoric	-76.57267 40.40689	36LE0389	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.49369 40.36472
36LE0043	Prehistoric	-76.5678 40.40761	36LE0400	Prehistoric	-76.61743 40.35105
36LE0044	Prehistoric	-76.56942 40.40863	36LE0401	Prehistoric	-76.56712 40.39565
36LE0045	Prehistoric	-76.55439 40.41158	36LE0406	Prehistoric	-76.59513 40.35723

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LE0046	Prehistoric	-76.55575 40.40635	36LE0420	Prehistoric	-76.52537 40.44915
36LE0047	Prehistoric	-76.57695 40.40637	36LE0421	Prehistoric	-76.52494 40.45027
36LE0048	Prehistoric	-76.579 40.40957	36LE0425	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.53681 40.46152
36LE0049	Prehistoric	-76.56856 40.41257	36LE0427	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.5573 40.45267
36LE0050	Prehistoric	-76.58152 40.41057	36LE0428	Prehistoric	-76.55781 40.45257
36LE0051	Prehistoric	-76.57883 40.41672	36LE0436	Prehistoric	-76.6165 40.36622
36LE0052	Prehistoric	-76.57243 40.42079	36LE0437	Prehistoric	-76.48926 40.4813
36LE0053	Prehistoric	-76.55976 40.42575	36LE0438	Prehistoric	-76.6045 40.35787
36LE0054	Prehistoric	-76.58323 40.41178	36LE0439	Prehistoric	-76.61146 40.36853
36LE0055	Prehistoric	-76.59455 40.42976	36LE0440	Prehistoric	-76.61212 40.35288
36LE0060	Prehistoric	-76.51996 40.4706	36LE0443	Prehistoric	-76.50723 40.46733
36LE0061	Prehistoric	-76.51939 40.46601	36LE0446	Prehistoric	-76.3719 40.42968
36LE0062	Prehistoric	-76.5838 40.40346	36LE0447	Prehistoric	-76.3607 40.42176
36LE0063	Prehistoric	-76.57997 40.40486	36LE0449	Prehistoric	-76.359 40.43799
36LE0064	Prehistoric	-76.58323 40.40591	36LE0451	Prehistoric	-76.35114 40.43184
36LE0065	Prehistoric	-76.59225 40.41671	36LE0453	Prehistoric	-76.35272 40.40485
36LE0066	Prehistoric	-76.58915 40.41466	36LE0455	Prehistoric	-76.35619 40.40482
36LE0067	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.59798 40.4163	36LE0456	Prehistoric	-76.35435 40.42309
36LE0068	Prehistoric	-76.60139 40.41859	36LE0457	Prehistoric	-76.33231 40.40417
36LE0069	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.60507 40.41919	36LE0458	Prehistoric	-76.32789 40.40466
36LE0070	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.60134 40.4287	36LE0464	Prehistoric	-76.33548 40.40656
36LE0071	Prehistoric	-76.57735 40.39525	36LE0467	Prehistoric	-76.61536 40.36042
36LE0072	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.5868 40.36838	36LE0468	Prehistoric	-76.43561 40.41913
36LE0073	Prehistoric	-76.58889 40.36564	36LE0478	Prehistoric	-76.50565 40.44333
36LE0074	Prehistoric	-76.59797 40.36851	36LE0482	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.59106 40.43574
36LE0075	Prehistoric	-76.60191 40.37004	36LE0485	Prehistoric	-76.58454 40.27541
36LE0076	Prehistoric	-76.60521 40.36973	36LE0513	Prehistoric	-76.58281 40.41091
36LE0077	Prehistoric	-76.60333 40.37163	36LE0517	Prehistoric	-76.56111 40.42265
36LE0078	Prehistoric	-76.61032 40.36967	36LE0521	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.458 40.33811
Watershed 69-New England-Reading Prong:					
36BK0229	Prehistoric	-75.86167 40.41795	36BK0585	Prehistoric	-75.99809 40.30291
36BK0270	Prehistoric	-76.15256 40.34766	36BK0606	Prehistoric	-75.99784 40.30198
36BK0584	Prehistoric	-76.00002 40.3	36BK0723	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.89539 40.41774
Watershed 69-Ridge and Valley-Great Valley:					
36BK0010	Prehistoric	-76.02721 40.3344	36BK0574	Prehistoric	-76.25484 40.39813
36BK0019	Prehistoric	-76.04107 40.38257	36BK0592	Prehistoric	-76.21141 40.40628
36BK0020	Prehistoric	-76.04092 40.3838	36BK0593	Prehistoric	-76.20756 40.39402
36BK0021	Prehistoric	-76.04656 40.38586	36BK0594	Prehistoric	-76.10607 40.36579
36BK0022	Prehistoric	-76.04607 40.38172	36BK0596	Prehistoric	-76.13823 40.34732
36BK0023	Prehistoric	-76.00297 40.35475	36BK0603	Prehistoric	-76.18971 40.39977
36BK0024	Prehistoric	-76.04387 40.38074	36BK0604	Prehistoric	-76.23176 40.399
36BK0025	Prehistoric	-76.03344 40.37059	36BK0611	Prehistoric	-75.94653 40.38454
36BK0026	Prehistoric	-76.04489 40.37717	36BK0613	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.01428 40.37703
36BK0027	Prehistoric	-76.03849 40.37067	36BK0616	Prehistoric	-75.99097 40.36683
36BK0028	Prehistoric	-76.04511 40.36916	36BK0617	Prehistoric	-75.98831 40.36306
36BK0029	Prehistoric	-76.04266 40.37074	36BK0621	Prehistoric	-75.95136 40.34462
36BK0030	Prehistoric	-76.04662 40.37527	36BK0630	Prehistoric	-76.00912 40.38402
36BK0031	Prehistoric	-76.05556 40.39366	36BK0631	Prehistoric	-76.01209 40.34672
36BK0032	Prehistoric	-76.04906 40.37254	36BK0632	Prehistoric	-75.98261 40.35229
36BK0033	Prehistoric	-76.0367 40.36857	36BK0633	Prehistoric	-75.9886 40.36007
36BK0034	Prehistoric	-76.04838 40.39471	36BK0634	Prehistoric	-76.01823 40.3822

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36BK0035	Prehistoric	-76.05317 40.38178	36BK0639	Prehistoric	-76.19335 40.36853
36BK0036	Prehistoric	-76.03656 40.38547	36BK0640	Prehistoric	-76.19588 40.36878
36BK0037	Prehistoric	-76.09109 40.41595	36BK0642	Prehistoric	-76.0607 40.3703
36BK0038	Prehistoric	-76.09119 40.42187	36BK0643	Prehistoric	-76.05513 40.37199
36BK0039	Prehistoric	-76.07304 40.39419	36BK0644	Prehistoric	-76.07848 40.40419
36BK0040	Prehistoric	-76.11828 40.43484	36BK0654	Prehistoric	-76.02049 40.33635
36BK0041	Prehistoric	-76.07878 40.38134	36BK0655	Prehistoric	-76.13447 40.34638
36BK0042	Prehistoric	-76.08659 40.41127	36BK0667	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.99208 40.36562
36BK0069	Prehistoric	-76.18827 40.48676	36BK0668	Prehistoric	-75.95549 40.40877
36BK0071	Prehistoric	-76.20505 40.46644	36BK0670	Prehistoric	-75.95223 40.40891
36BK0072	Prehistoric	-76.20166 40.45628	36BK0692	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.99241 40.36281
36BK0073	Prehistoric	-76.18405 40.45709	36BK0693	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.01594 40.37218
36BK0074	Prehistoric	-76.17723 40.45966	36BK0694	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.04422 40.39848
36BK0075	Prehistoric	-76.16504 40.4651	36BK0696	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.9945 40.36323
36BK0076	Prehistoric	-76.23065 40.43905	36BK0706	Prehistoric	-76.05885 40.30727
36BK0077	Prehistoric	-76.24893 40.40858	36BK0707	Prehistoric	-76.05522 40.30816
36BK0078	Prehistoric	-76.23869 40.40704	36BK0712	Prehistoric	-75.96957 40.393
36BK0079	Prehistoric	-76.23373 40.40863	36BK0718	Prehistoric	-75.97115 40.31234
36BK0080	Prehistoric	-76.22956 40.40792	36BK0719	Prehistoric	-75.97203 40.31161
36BK0081	Prehistoric	-76.21908 40.40667	36BK0720	Prehistoric	-75.97507 40.32275
36BK0082	Prehistoric	-76.21445 40.40581	36BK0744	Prehistoric	-75.96907 40.39182
36BK0083	Prehistoric	-76.21675 40.41023	36BK0755	Prehistoric	-76.25767 40.38677
36BK0084	Prehistoric	-76.24575 40.38851	36BK0761	Prehistoric	-76.2553 40.39182
36BK0085	Prehistoric	-76.24336 40.38627	36BK0762	Prehistoric	-76.2652 40.39915
36BK0086	Prehistoric	-76.21578 40.3818	36BK0773	Prehistoric	-76.26614 40.39686
36BK0087	Prehistoric	-76.21157 40.38042	36BK0782	Prehistoric	-76.28427 40.4008
36BK0088	Prehistoric	-76.20841 40.37761	36BK0846	Prehistoric	-76.03045 40.33076
36BK0089	Prehistoric	-76.24711 40.3804	36BK0847	Prehistoric	-76.02955 40.3325
36BK0090	Prehistoric	-76.23816 40.37909	36BK0848	Prehistoric	-76.03762 40.34077
36BK0091	Prehistoric	-76.23018 40.37705	36BK0849	Prehistoric	-76.03269 40.33136
36BK0092	Prehistoric	-76.2275 40.37595	36BK0850	Prehistoric	-76.03176 40.33224
36BK0093	Prehistoric	-76.2146 40.37546	36BK0851	Prehistoric	-76.02953 40.33427
36BK0094	Prehistoric	-76.21227 40.3767	36BK0852	Prehistoric	-76.03276 40.33495
36BK0095	Prehistoric	-76.20673 40.37553	36BK0853	Prehistoric	-76.03139 40.33732
36BK0096	Prehistoric	-76.22346 40.43558	36BK0854	Prehistoric	-76.03357 40.33685
36BK0097	Prehistoric	-76.19179 40.43731	36BK0855	Prehistoric	-76.0345 40.33719
36BK0098	Prehistoric	-76.16823 40.43459	36BK0856	Prehistoric	-76.0329 40.33922
36BK0099	Prehistoric	-76.14222 40.45223	36BK0857	Prehistoric	-76.03379 40.33998
36BK0100	Prehistoric	-76.12544 40.43899	36BK0858	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.03453 40.33515
36BK0101	Prehistoric	-76.16888 40.41935	36BK0870	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.93881 40.41495
36BK0102	Prehistoric	-76.1655 40.42059	36BK0874	Prehistoric	-75.93769 40.41007
36BK0103	Prehistoric	-76.15889 40.42134	36BK0875	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.95366 40.37141
36BK0104	Prehistoric	-76.15705 40.42094	36BK0876	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.98491 40.38359
36BK0105	Prehistoric	-76.15218 40.42492	36BK0877	Prehistoric	-75.98597 40.3826
36BK0106	Prehistoric	-76.14184 40.42312	36BK0886	Prehistoric	-75.96292 40.38627
36BK0107	Prehistoric	-76.1373 40.42609	36BK0901	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.01841 40.41024
36BK0108	Prehistoric	-76.13109 40.42319	36BK0912	Prehistoric	-75.9302 40.42421
36BK0109	Prehistoric	-76.14059 40.41965	36LE0196	Prehistoric	-76.37373 40.37291
36BK0110	Prehistoric	-76.20522 40.42055	36LE0197	Prehistoric	-76.34394 40.38913
36BK0111	Prehistoric	-76.20297 40.41914	36LE0198	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.31646 40.36934
36BK0112	Prehistoric	-76.20732 40.41704	36LE0199	Prehistoric	-76.34719 40.36413
36BK0113	Prehistoric	-76.13879 40.41658	36LE0217	Prehistoric	-76.19485 40.35114

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36BK0114	Prehistoric	-76.18616 40.39977	36LE0219	Prehistoric	-76.21052 40.33568
36BK0115	Prehistoric	-76.17798 40.39547	36LE0260	Prehistoric	-76.37591 40.37339
36BK0116	Prehistoric	-76.18663 40.39134	36LE0261	Prehistoric	-76.35646 40.36506
36BK0117	Prehistoric	-76.17382 40.38659	36LE0262	Prehistoric	-76.32841 40.36661
36BK0118	Prehistoric	-76.16924 40.38175	36LE0263	Prehistoric	-76.27603 40.34392
36BK0119	Prehistoric	-76.1689 40.38017	36LE0264	Prehistoric	-76.34279 40.37149
36BK0120	Prehistoric	-76.17289 40.37932	36LE0265	Prehistoric	-76.2947 40.37479
36BK0121	Prehistoric	-76.18251 40.37772	36LE0266	Prehistoric	-76.29725 40.36967
36BK0122	Prehistoric	-76.13982 40.37781	36LE0267	Prehistoric	-76.29557 40.36948
36BK0141	Prehistoric	-75.86584 40.34921	36LE0268	Prehistoric	-76.31641 40.36761
36BK0155	Prehistoric	-75.9959 40.36121	36LE0269	Prehistoric	-76.27444 40.3726
36BK0156	Prehistoric	-75.97968 40.36669	36LE0270	Prehistoric	-76.25684 40.31376
36BK0158	Prehistoric	-76.101 40.37519	36LE0271	Prehistoric	-76.36672 40.36301
36BK0159	Prehistoric	-76.09137 40.37174	36LE0272	Prehistoric	-76.2508 40.32885
36BK0160	Prehistoric	-76.1233 40.36907	36LE0273	Prehistoric	-76.37408 40.37098
36BK0161	Prehistoric	-76.00999 40.37176	36LE0274	Prehistoric	-76.28426 40.37469
36BK0162	Prehistoric	-76.1188 40.35136	36LE0275	Prehistoric	-76.31556 40.3701
36BK0163	Prehistoric	-76.10666 40.35283	36LE0276	Prehistoric	-76.32166 40.36609
36BK0164	Prehistoric	-76.08568 40.34938	36LE0277	Prehistoric	-76.34233 40.36773
36BK0165	Prehistoric	-76.08423 40.34788	36LE0279	Prehistoric	-76.33611 40.36711
36BK0166	Prehistoric	-76.09543 40.3372	36LE0298	Prehistoric	-76.35635 40.37804
36BK0167	Prehistoric	-76.0928 40.33847	36LE0299	Prehistoric	-76.34357 40.37948
36BK0168	Prehistoric	-76.05175 40.33988	36LE0300	Prehistoric	-76.34066 40.38535
36BK0169	Prehistoric	-76.01788 40.35605	36LE0301	Prehistoric	-76.33874 40.38684
36BK0170	Prehistoric	-76.01194 40.35886	36LE0302	Prehistoric	-76.32334 40.37605
36BK0171	Prehistoric	-76.00447 40.35608	36LE0303	Prehistoric	-76.32463 40.37716
36BK0172	Prehistoric	-76.005 40.35182	36LE0304	Prehistoric	-76.31648 40.37812
36BK0173	Prehistoric	-76.01563 40.3421	36LE0305	Prehistoric	-76.31501 40.3789
36BK0174	Prehistoric	-76.01672 40.33604	36LE0311	Prehistoric	-76.32874 40.39451
36BK0175	Prehistoric	-76.09896 40.33315	36LE0312	Prehistoric	-76.3226 40.39429
36BK0176	Prehistoric	-76.09426 40.33192	36LE0313	Prehistoric	-76.32214 40.39317
36BK0177	Prehistoric	-76.092 40.32848	36LE0314	Prehistoric	-76.3053 40.39399
36BK0178	Prehistoric	-76.05785 40.30398	36LE0315	Prehistoric	-76.30215 40.39375
36BK0190	Prehistoric	-75.98594 40.39656	36LE0316	Prehistoric	-76.29151 40.39561
36BK0192	Prehistoric	-75.9479 40.40868	36LE0317	Prehistoric	-76.28513 40.39065
36BK0193	Prehistoric	-75.9504 40.40841	36LE0318	Prehistoric	-76.28859 40.3859
36BK0252	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.08779 40.41266	36LE0319	Prehistoric	-76.29265 40.38112
36BK0253	Prehistoric	-76.04281 40.32252	36LE0320	Prehistoric	-76.29733 40.38302
36BK0254	Prehistoric	-76.07646 40.4021	36LE0321	Prehistoric	-76.29542 40.37753
36BK0255	Prehistoric	-76.08425 40.38879	36LE0322	Prehistoric	-76.29252 40.37647
36BK0256	Prehistoric	-76.07765 40.3931	36LE0323	Prehistoric	-76.25772 40.38177
36BK0257	Prehistoric	-76.0517 40.3707	36LE0324	Prehistoric	-76.24569 40.36316
36BK0258	Prehistoric	-76.05463 40.39485	36LE0325	Prehistoric	-76.24442 40.33574
36BK0259	Prehistoric	-76.04575 40.38364	36LE0326	Prehistoric	-76.24913 40.33036
36BK0260	Prehistoric	-76.1126 40.48353	36LE0327	Prehistoric	-76.22413 40.33652
36BK0261	Prehistoric	-76.11947 40.44905	36LE0328	Prehistoric	-76.21985 40.33527
36BK0262	Prehistoric	-76.10483 40.45542	36LE0329	Prehistoric	-76.21739 40.33709
36BK0267	Prehistoric	-76.07426 40.44131	36LE0330	Prehistoric	-76.21432 40.33783
36BK0268	Prehistoric	-76.10656 40.42743	36LE0331	Prehistoric	-76.24545 40.31951
36BK0269	Prehistoric	-76.08775 40.42573	36LE0332	Prehistoric	-76.24712 40.317
36BK0271	Prehistoric	-76.03827 40.42156	36LE0333	Prehistoric	-76.24311 40.31478
36BK0272	Prehistoric	-76.03288 40.41954	36LE0334	Prehistoric	-76.23535 40.32067

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36BK0280	Prehistoric	-76.04114 40.43337	36LE0335	Prehistoric	-76.22425 40.30239
36BK0281	Prehistoric	-76.03242 40.43858	36LE0344	Prehistoric	-76.35763 40.38282
36BK0289	Prehistoric	-76.18958 40.37448	36LE0345	Prehistoric	-76.32027 40.38679
36BK0290	Prehistoric	-76.17918 40.37273	36LE0346	Prehistoric	-76.29102 40.38571
36BK0291	Prehistoric	-76.19335 40.3727	36LE0347	Prehistoric	-76.2271 40.35256
36BK0292	Prehistoric	-76.18993 40.37221	36LE0348	Prehistoric	-76.22894 40.35464
36BK0293	Prehistoric	-76.19306 40.37059	36LE0349	Prehistoric	-76.2235 40.33928
36BK0294	Prehistoric	-76.19646 40.37057	36LE0350	Prehistoric	-76.22337 40.33732
36BK0295	Prehistoric	-76.18158 40.35336	36LE0351	Prehistoric	-76.23209 40.34521
36BK0296	Prehistoric	-76.143 40.36345	36LE0352	Prehistoric	-76.24422 40.30878
36BK0331	Prehistoric	-76.07942 40.41717	36LE0365	Prehistoric	-76.23108 40.31886
36BK0332	Prehistoric	-76.06983 40.42084	36LE0367	Prehistoric	-76.28719 40.38846
36BK0333	Prehistoric	-76.0626 40.42243	36LE0369	Prehistoric	-76.286 40.384
36BK0334	Prehistoric	-76.01374 40.34356	36LE0370	Prehistoric	-76.28311 40.39382
36BK0335	Prehistoric	-76.0571 40.30554	36LE0373	Prehistoric	-76.36223 40.36851
36BK0336	Prehistoric	-76.05303 40.30925	36LE0374	Prehistoric	-76.20368 40.33654
36BK0343	Prehistoric	-76.04867 40.37876	36LE0376	Prehistoric	-76.25391 40.32835
36BK0344	Prehistoric	-76.05261 40.39013	36LE0381	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.31238 40.36975
36BK0345	Prehistoric	-76.05284 40.39253	36LE0383	Prehistoric	-76.23989 40.34149
36BK0347	Prehistoric	-76.07587 40.39808	36LE0444	Prehistoric	-76.32967 40.3927
36BK0348	Prehistoric	-76.07585 40.40674	36LE0445	Prehistoric	-76.30161 40.38936
36BK0420	Prehistoric	-76.05094 40.45224	36LE0448	Prehistoric	-76.27528 40.39157
36BK0426	Prehistoric	-76.19782 40.40855	36LE0450	Prehistoric	-76.32738 40.37873
36BK0427	Prehistoric	-76.18862 40.37654	36LE0452	Prehistoric	-76.33484 40.38947
36BK0469	Prehistoric	-75.96619 40.36149	36LE0454	Prehistoric	-76.29071 40.38384
36BK0470	Prehistoric	-76.20086 40.38006	36LE0459	Prehistoric	-76.28165 40.39454
36BK0475	Prehistoric	-76.082 40.40815	36LE0460	Prehistoric	-76.29198 40.38662
36BK0506	Prehistoric	-76.06812 40.31748	36LE0462	Prehistoric	-76.29199 40.3839
36BK0514	Prehistoric	-75.99405 40.36583	36LE0463	Prehistoric	-76.28999 40.39867
36BK0538	Prehistoric	-75.90533 40.38152	36LE0465	Prehistoric	-76.34472 40.37634
36BK0543	Prehistoric	-75.95216 40.40826	36LE0466	Prehistoric	-76.31848 40.38605
36BK0570	Prehistoric	-76.1712 40.38014			
Watershed 70-Ridge and Valley-Blue Mountain:					
36DA0159	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.909 40.34078	36DA0237	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.90692 40.33858
Watershed 70-Ridge and Valley-Great Valley:					
36DA0085	Prehistoric	-76.81622 40.35427	36DA0206	Prehistoric	-76.84341 40.25197
36DA0087	Prehistoric	-76.85383 40.22903	36DA0207	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.84397 40.25013
36DA0144	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.86424 40.29936	36YO0337	Prehistoric	-76.84242 40.22141
36DA0185	Prehistoric	-76.86835 40.29277			
Watershed 72-New England-Reading Prong:					
36BK0304	Prehistoric	-75.56668 40.44673	36BK0342	Prehistoric	-75.62535 40.44388
36BK0339	Prehistoric	-75.59999 40.46878	36BK0661	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.65011 40.44153
36BK0340	Prehistoric	-75.60674 40.46767	36BK0878	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.60389 40.47096
36BK0341	Prehistoric	-75.61151 40.46149			
Watershed 76-New England-Reading Prong:					
36BK0214	Prehistoric	-75.77012 40.44837	36BK0502	Prehistoric	-75.76209 40.46232
36BK0215	Prehistoric	-75.76578 40.45542	36BK0503	Prehistoric	-75.76193 40.46037
36BK0216	Prehistoric	-75.76164 40.45834	36BK0504	Prehistoric	-75.76059 40.44707
36BK0217	Prehistoric	-75.75283 40.46268	36BK0505	Prehistoric	-75.75923 40.44038
36BK0234	Prehistoric	-75.74794 40.46213	36BK0522	Prehistoric	-75.7629 40.45923

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36BK0235	Prehistoric	-75.74894 40.43294	36BK0555	Prehistoric	-75.77058 40.41242
36BK0411	Prehistoric	-75.81125 40.34443			
Watershed 76-Ridge and Valley-Great Valley:					
36BK0124	Prehistoric	-75.73491 40.31555	36BK0302	Prehistoric	-75.74319 40.34861
36BK0132	Prehistoric	-75.81881 40.37323	36BK0412	Prehistoric	-75.8087 40.34311
36BK0133	Prehistoric	-75.81571 40.36711	36BK0413	Prehistoric	-75.80566 40.34384
36BK0134	Prehistoric	-75.81444 40.35469	36BK0417	Prehistoric	-75.75014 40.39964
36BK0135	Prehistoric	-75.80827 40.35001	36BK0418	Prehistoric	-75.75555 40.40707
36BK0136	Prehistoric	-75.80732 40.34728	36BK0419	Prehistoric	-75.74407 40.35425
36BK0137	Prehistoric	-75.7909 40.33493	36BK0518	Prehistoric	-75.74138 40.36194
36BK0138	Prehistoric	-75.77414 40.33592	36BK0519	Prehistoric	-75.74259 40.34593
36BK0139	Prehistoric	-75.76448 40.32596	36BK0520	Prehistoric	-75.77324 40.37876
36BK0140	Prehistoric	-75.75107 40.32394	36BK0521	Prehistoric	-75.81311 40.37808
36BK0142	Prehistoric	-75.82847 40.33311	36BK0523	Prehistoric	-75.81151 40.37568
36BK0151	Prehistoric	-75.75159 40.31931	36BK0530	Prehistoric	-75.67488 40.41668
36BK0152	Prehistoric	-75.74984 40.31992	36BK0559	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.75936 40.41164
36BK0218	Prehistoric	-75.75967 40.40794	36BK0560	Prehistoric	-75.75817 40.4117
36BK0219	Prehistoric	-75.76798 40.40252	36BK0563	Prehistoric	-75.76569 40.38469
36BK0220	Prehistoric	-75.76815 40.40039	36BK0579	Prehistoric	-75.8143 40.36907
36BK0221	Prehistoric	-75.76255 40.3991	36BK0638	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.73973 40.33903
36BK0222	Prehistoric	-75.79185 40.38507	36BK0700	Prehistoric	-75.73462 40.31382
36BK0223	Prehistoric	-75.79104 40.38119	36BK0701	Prehistoric	-75.73661 40.31436
36BK0224	Prehistoric	-75.78239 40.37713	36BK0702	Prehistoric	-75.73641 40.31624
36BK0225	Prehistoric	-75.77124 40.37818	36BK0704	Prehistoric	-75.79123 40.38316
36BK0226	Prehistoric	-75.76922 40.38407	36BK0895	Prehistoric	-75.7524 40.35137
36BK0227	Prehistoric	-75.76103 40.38033	36BK0896	Prehistoric	-75.7468 40.38867
36BK0228	Prehistoric	-75.75805 40.38522	36BK0897	Prehistoric	-75.74076 40.39508
36BK0236	Prehistoric	-75.7432 40.40317	36BK0898	Prehistoric	-75.73933 40.39763
36BK0237	Prehistoric	-75.72753 40.3914	36BK0905	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.7457 40.38436
36BK0238	Prehistoric	-75.74118 40.37755			
Watershed 84-Ridge and Valley-Great Valley:					
36CU0003	Prehistoric	-77.52784 40.13386	36CU0123	Prehistoric	-77.3898 40.17721
36CU0004	Prehistoric	-77.52241 40.13536	36CU0124	Prehistoric	-77.381 40.19283
36CU0005	Prehistoric	-77.54903 40.12154	36CU0125	Prehistoric	-77.17664 40.21077
36CU0006	Prehistoric	-77.51851 40.14094	36CU0130	Prehistoric	-76.92939 40.27642
36CU0007	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.51611 40.14483	36CU0134	Prehistoric	-76.91487 40.27212
36CU0008	Prehistoric	-77.50594 40.15124	36CU0136	Prehistoric	-77.42756 40.19108
36CU0009	Prehistoric	-77.52202 40.13867	36CU0137	Prehistoric	-77.41015 40.18375
36CU0010	Prehistoric	-77.49586 40.15281	36CU0138	Prehistoric	-77.33846 40.23102
36CU0011	Prehistoric	-77.49149 40.15457	36CU0144	Prehistoric	-77.5027 40.1477
36CU0012	Prehistoric	-77.48398 40.15778	36CU0145	Prehistoric	-77.49314 40.1529
36CU0013	Prehistoric	-77.47989 40.15667	36CU0147	Prehistoric	-76.97608 40.29295
36CU0014	Prehistoric	-77.47233 40.15628	36CU0160	Prehistoric	-77.4399 40.22727
36CU0015	Prehistoric	-77.472 40.15919	36CU0161	Prehistoric	-77.43612 40.22785
36CU0016	Prehistoric	-77.4579 40.15948	36CU0170	Prehistoric	-77.11204 40.26041
36CU0017	Prehistoric	-77.46403 40.16509	36CU0171	Prehistoric	-77.11354 40.2594
36CU0018	Prehistoric	-77.463 40.17448	36CU0172	Prehistoric	-77.51599 40.06463
36CU0019	Prehistoric	-77.47516 40.18189	36CU0181	Prehistoric	-77.54649 40.12164
36CU0020	Prehistoric	-77.45931 40.17892	36CU0182	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.50714 40.16254
36CU0021	Prehistoric	-77.44108 40.18465	36CU0186	Prehistoric	-77.49568 40.05939
36CU0022	Prehistoric	-77.46306 40.14803	36CU0187	Prehistoric	-77.4977 40.05986

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36CU0023	Prehistoric	-77.41824 40.19169	36CU0190	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.25728 40.23629
36CU0024	Prehistoric	-77.40726 40.18313	36CU0195	Prehistoric	-76.97714 40.27382
36CU0025	Prehistoric	-77.50707 40.03157	36CU0196	Prehistoric	-77.00859 40.25294
36CU0026	Prehistoric	-77.51522 40.04061	36CU0197	Prehistoric	-77.54254 40.08354
36CU0027	Prehistoric	-77.51652 40.042	36CU0200	Prehistoric	-77.01508 40.19749
36CU0028	Prehistoric	-77.55684 40.09601	36CU0206	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.51725 40.14406
36CU0029	Prehistoric	-77.02726 40.25474	36DA0011	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.90621 40.30597
36CU0030	Prehistoric	-77.31977 40.21314	36DA0138	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.91919 40.29104
36CU0031	Prehistoric	-77.25548 40.21761	36DA0162	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.90701 40.3046
36CU0042	Prehistoric	-77.40746 40.12743	36FR0002	Prehistoric	-77.59667 40.02897
36CU0043	Prehistoric	-77.55668 40.11549	36FR0003	Prehistoric	-77.61854 40.06093
36CU0044	Prehistoric	-77.51985 40.14235	36FR0004	Prehistoric	-77.61146 40.06728
36CU0045	Prehistoric	-77.52753 40.13892	36FR0005	Prehistoric	-77.61329 40.06918
36CU0046	Prehistoric	-77.52546 40.12911	36FR0006	Prehistoric	-77.61176 40.0702
36CU0047	Prehistoric	-77.38936 40.18868	36FR0007	Prehistoric	-77.60804 40.02012
36CU0048	Prehistoric	-77.44647 40.10362	36FR0008	Prehistoric	-77.60984 40.0193
36CU0049	Prehistoric	-77.44623 40.10259	36FR0009	Prehistoric	-77.60783 40.02341
36CU0050	Prehistoric	-77.44558 40.10179	36FR0010	Prehistoric	-77.61502 40.02125
36CU0051	Prehistoric	-77.44715 40.10135	36FR0011	Prehistoric	-77.61669 40.01945
36CU0078	Prehistoric	-77.363 40.20582	36FR0017	Prehistoric	-77.63389 40.03359
36CU0081	Prehistoric	-77.34842 40.20998	36FR0018	Prehistoric	-77.63251 40.03509
36CU0082	Prehistoric	-77.31068 40.216	36FR0019	Prehistoric	-77.63593 40.03717
36CU0083	Prehistoric	-77.30723 40.21717	36FR0020	Prehistoric	-77.64652 40.06989
36CU0084	Prehistoric	-77.27168 40.20877	36FR0021	Prehistoric	-77.64454 40.07199
36CU0085	Prehistoric	-77.41512 40.18978	36FR0022	Prehistoric	-77.64921 40.09085
36CU0086	Prehistoric	-77.34528 40.21004	36FR0023	Prehistoric	-77.6534 40.04915
36CU0087	Prehistoric	-77.30631 40.21481	36FR0024	Prehistoric	-77.64257 40.03717
36CU0090	Prehistoric	-77.26898 40.22058	36FR0025	Prehistoric	-77.64473 40.07656
36CU0098	Prehistoric	-77.0445 40.26193	36FR0026	Prehistoric	-77.64179 40.06309
36CU0100	Prehistoric	-77.31409 40.16279	36FR0027	Prehistoric	-77.51361 40.00716
36CU0101	Prehistoric	-76.91764 40.27032	36FR0028	Prehistoric	-77.5212 40.03461
36CU0102	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.99122 40.25637	36FR0029	Prehistoric	-77.52047 40.04373
36CU0103	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.99053 40.25568	36FR0030	Prehistoric	-77.56931 40.09884
36CU0104	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.98933 40.2555	36FR0045	Prehistoric	-77.61267 40.01981
36CU0105	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.98744 40.25124	36FR0046	Prehistoric	-77.61941 40.06011
36CU0106	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.00011 40.26634	36FR0047	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.59778 40.07162
36CU0108	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.99342 40.25741	36FR0052	Prehistoric	-77.58005 40.11645
36CU0109	Prehistoric	-77.40958 40.13032	36FR0053	Prehistoric	-77.57205 40.09412
36CU0110	Prehistoric	-77.4203 40.16241	36FR0054	Prehistoric	-77.60054 40.08173
36CU0111	Prehistoric	-77.42111 40.16068	36FR0055	Prehistoric	-77.59688 40.07433
36CU0112	Prehistoric	-77.39158 40.18791	36FR0056	Prehistoric	-77.60517 40.06972
36CU0113	Prehistoric	-77.39083 40.19085	36FR0057	Prehistoric	-77.59232 40.06531
36CU0114	Prehistoric	-77.33457 40.21654	36FR0058	Prehistoric	-77.6213 40.06081
36CU0115	Prehistoric	-77.35015 40.21391	36FR0059	Prehistoric	-77.59842 40.07054
36CU0116	Prehistoric	-77.34283 40.21615	36FR0060	Prehistoric	-77.59357 40.04126
36CU0117	Prehistoric	-77.40541 40.18762	36FR0069	Prehistoric	-77.6637 40.10757
36CU0118	Prehistoric	-77.40273 40.17971	36FR0113	Prehistoric	-77.6573 40.03082
36CU0119	Prehistoric	-77.40527 40.16389	36FR0114	Prehistoric	-77.64568 40.01455
36CU0120	Prehistoric	-77.40119 40.16501	36FR0196	Prehistoric	-77.61275 40.15483
36CU0121	Prehistoric	-77.39439 40.17123	36FR0412	Prehistoric	-77.63989 40.02961
36CU0122	Prehistoric	-77.41357 40.16051			

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
Watershed 85-Ridge and Valley-Great Valley:					
36LE0278	Prehistoric	-76.25448 40.30263	36LE0396	Prehistoric	-76.31621 40.28684
36LE0342	Prehistoric	-76.24507 40.29863	36LE0399	Prehistoric	-76.25919 40.29911
36LE0391	Prehistoric	-76.25272 40.29867	36LE0469	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.30198 40.29111
36LE0392	Prehistoric	-76.33539 40.28771	36LE0471	Prehistoric	-76.31178 40.28836
36LE0393	Prehistoric	-76.35836 40.2831	36LE0472	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.30957 40.28701
36LE0395	Prehistoric	-76.31988 40.28487	36LE0473	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.30545 40.29524
Watershed 87-Ridge and Valley-Great Valley:					
36CU0032	Prehistoric	-77.40916 40.06412	36CU0080	Prehistoric	-77.03809 40.15231
36CU0033	Prehistoric	-77.41242 40.08755	36CU0088	Prehistoric	-77.04917 40.1482
36CU0034	Prehistoric	-77.36296 40.09503	36CU0089	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.02149 40.14856
36CU0035	Prehistoric	-77.35907 40.09642	36CU0091	Prehistoric	-77.03195 40.14877
36CU0036	Prehistoric	-77.35353 40.09642	36CU0092	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.0401 40.14814
36CU0037	Prehistoric	-77.32001 40.10666	36CU0093	Prehistoric	-77.15141 40.13837
36CU0038	Prehistoric	-77.33646 40.10084	36CU0094	Prehistoric	-77.09342 40.149
36CU0039	Prehistoric	-77.39216 40.09446	36CU0095	Prehistoric	-77.09156 40.14608
36CU0040	Prehistoric	-77.38712 40.09401	36CU0096	Prehistoric	-77.06661 40.14518
36CU0041	Prehistoric	-77.37603 40.09458	36CU0097	Prehistoric	-77.03441 40.14884
36CU0052	Prehistoric	-77.33143 40.10304	36CU0132	Prehistoric	-76.97608 40.165
36CU0053	Prehistoric	-77.33012 40.10526	36CU0143	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.9202 40.22905
36CU0054	Prehistoric	-77.12158 40.14474	36CU0146	Prehistoric	-76.85945 40.22591
36CU0055	Prehistoric	-77.20408 40.12868	36CU0148	Prehistoric	-77.08187 40.14741
36CU0056	Prehistoric	-77.19645 40.13685	36CU0153	Prehistoric	-77.02487 40.1482
36CU0057	Prehistoric	-77.1748 40.14806	36CU0154	Prehistoric	-77.02405 40.1476
36CU0058	Prehistoric	-77.14886 40.13868	36CU0155	Prehistoric	-77.02466 40.14871
36CU0059	Prehistoric	-77.14976 40.1373	36CU0156	Prehistoric	-77.02531 40.14882
36CU0060	Prehistoric	-77.14931 40.13082	36CU0157	Prehistoric	-77.02039 40.14856
36CU0061	Prehistoric	-77.13214 40.14112	36CU0158	Prehistoric	-77.01876 40.14914
36CU0062	Prehistoric	-77.1316 40.13742	36CU0159	Prehistoric	-77.01746 40.14956
36CU0063	Prehistoric	-77.34214 40.09867	36CU0175	Prehistoric	-76.99874 40.17145
36CU0064	Prehistoric	-77.30216 40.10629	36CU0176	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.09711 40.15929
36CU0065	Prehistoric	-77.28511 40.10958	36CU0178	Prehistoric	-77.11721 40.14734
36CU0066	Prehistoric	-77.27138 40.11254	36CU0179	Prehistoric	-77.116 40.14283
36CU0067	Prehistoric	-77.27101 40.11069	36CU0188	Prehistoric	-76.86244 40.21896
36CU0068	Prehistoric	-77.23842 40.11903	36CU0189	Prehistoric	-77.23426 40.12819
36CU0069	Prehistoric	-77.24069 40.12508	36CU0193	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.03004 40.14771
36CU0070	Prehistoric	-77.22694 40.1253	36CU0194	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.88551 40.24661
36CU0071	Prehistoric	-77.21817 40.12561	36CU0198	Prehistoric	-77.02372 40.1467
36CU0072	Prehistoric	-77.2127 40.12573	36CU0199	Prehistoric	-77.02303 40.1469
36CU0073	Prehistoric	-77.20751 40.12789	36DA0012	Prehistoric	-76.88903 40.25692
36CU0074	Prehistoric	-77.19516 40.13316	36DA0014	Prehistoric	-76.89664 40.26838
36CU0075	Prehistoric	-77.16857 40.1458	36DA0015	Prehistoric	-76.89475 40.26556
36CU0076	Prehistoric	-77.16056 40.14247	36YO0064	Prehistoric	-77.03592 40.13843
36CU0077	Prehistoric	-77.14372 40.13886	36YO0173	Prehistoric	-77.03058 40.1402
36CU0079	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.03564 40.15323	36YO0357	Prehistoric	-77.01972 40.14712
Watershed 87-Ridge and Valley-South Mountain:					
36CU0173	Prehistoric	-77.27024 40.04201			
Watershed 91-Ridge and Valley-Great Valley:					
36FR0001	Prehistoric	-77.56987 39.97611	36FR0216	Prehistoric	-77.72357 39.75369
36FR0012	Prehistoric	-77.86763 39.89083	36FR0217	Prehistoric	-77.72988 39.76279

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36FR0013	Prehistoric	-77.86636 39.89184	36FR0218	Prehistoric	-77.73093 39.76351
36FR0014	Prehistoric	-77.56317 39.73513	36FR0219	Prehistoric	-77.72968 39.76516
36FR0015	Prehistoric	-77.57954 39.80927	36FR0220	Prehistoric	-77.7323 39.76635
36FR0016	Prehistoric	-77.57343 39.82459	36FR0221	Prehistoric	-77.73567 39.7653
36FR0031	Prehistoric	-77.88569 39.89504	36FR0222	Prehistoric	-77.7334 39.76433
36FR0032	Prehistoric	-77.62304 39.97399	36FR0223	Prehistoric	-77.7215 39.77734
36FR0033	Prehistoric	-77.61946 39.97191	36FR0224	Prehistoric	-77.69417 39.78477
36FR0034	Prehistoric	-77.64762 39.96492	36FR0225	Prehistoric	-77.71528 39.79293
36FR0035	Prehistoric	-77.65199 39.95624	36FR0226	Prehistoric	-77.71683 39.79348
36FR0036	Prehistoric	-77.65399 39.95116	36FR0227	Prehistoric	-77.70022 39.79644
36FR0037	Prehistoric	-77.69292 39.90464	36FR0228	Prehistoric	-77.69685 39.79637
36FR0038	Prehistoric	-77.70212 39.90035	36FR0229	Prehistoric	-77.69413 39.79729
36FR0039	Prehistoric	-77.74393 39.9177	36FR0230	Prehistoric	-77.69188 39.80063
36FR0040	Prehistoric	-77.71845 39.78	36FR0231	Prehistoric	-77.69389 39.79983
36FR0041	Prehistoric	-77.86355 39.881	36FR0232	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.69569 39.79846
36FR0042	Prehistoric	-77.86764 39.89257	36FR0233	Prehistoric	-77.69799 39.79771
36FR0043	Prehistoric	-77.78546 39.96048	36FR0234	Prehistoric	-77.69875 39.79851
36FR0048	Prehistoric	-77.65543 39.96104	36FR0235	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.68611 39.8093
36FR0049	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.76276 39.95435	36FR0236	Prehistoric	-77.69908 39.81224
36FR0050	Prehistoric	-77.59106 39.97527	36FR0237	Prehistoric	-77.69616 39.82695
36FR0051	Prehistoric	-77.76445 39.9624	36FR0238	Prehistoric	-77.69845 39.827
36FR0066	Prehistoric	-77.58203 39.96242	36FR0239	Prehistoric	-77.69987 39.82901
36FR0067	Prehistoric	-77.58213 39.95851	36FR0240	Prehistoric	-77.69945 39.83078
36FR0068	Prehistoric	-77.55736 39.95047	36FR0241	Prehistoric	-77.69828 39.83172
36FR0070	Prehistoric	-77.60539 39.97635	36FR0242	Prehistoric	-77.69536 39.83357
36FR0071	Prehistoric	-77.59968 39.97711	36FR0243	Prehistoric	-77.69517 39.83223
36FR0072	Prehistoric	-77.58041 39.97261	36FR0244	Prehistoric	-77.68552 39.83826
36FR0073	Prehistoric	-77.577 39.97211	36FR0245	Prehistoric	-77.68684 39.8391
36FR0074	Prehistoric	-77.57937 39.97138	36FR0246	Prehistoric	-77.66665 39.81917
36FR0075	Prehistoric	-77.57805 39.96965	36FR0247	Prehistoric	-77.67047 39.81973
36FR0076	Prehistoric	-77.57985 39.96891	36FR0248	Prehistoric	-77.73897 39.84524
36FR0077	Prehistoric	-77.58315 39.96516	36FR0249	Prehistoric	-77.71093 39.87251
36FR0078	Prehistoric	-77.58508 39.95041	36FR0250	Prehistoric	-77.70459 39.87257
36FR0079	Prehistoric	-77.58526 39.941	36FR0251	Prehistoric	-77.70179 39.87268
36FR0080	Prehistoric	-77.58127 39.93676	36FR0252	Prehistoric	-77.6573 39.78543
36FR0081	Prehistoric	-77.5863 39.93445	36FR0253	Prehistoric	-77.5711 39.73768
36FR0082	Prehistoric	-77.58235 39.93138	36FR0254	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.56808 39.74005
36FR0083	Prehistoric	-77.58167 39.92945	36FR0255	Prehistoric	-77.56473 39.73903
36FR0084	Prehistoric	-77.5804 39.92936	36FR0256	Prehistoric	-77.5599 39.73622
36FR0085	Prehistoric	-77.57997 39.92798	36FR0257	Prehistoric	-77.55108 39.73159
36FR0086	Prehistoric	-77.57582 39.9266	36FR0258	Prehistoric	-77.5485 39.73078
36FR0087	Prehistoric	-77.57527 39.9246	36FR0259	Prehistoric	-77.5381 39.73124
36FR0088	Prehistoric	-77.57775 39.92302	36FR0260	Prehistoric	-77.5344 39.7324
36FR0089	Prehistoric	-77.57719 39.92112	36FR0261	Prehistoric	-77.86255 39.83569
36FR0090	Prehistoric	-77.5773 39.91641	36FR0262	Prehistoric	-77.86305 39.84589
36FR0091	Prehistoric	-77.55784 39.92432	36FR0263	Prehistoric	-77.80082 39.75703
36FR0092	Prehistoric	-77.53995 39.91112	36FR0264	Prehistoric	-77.79678 39.75641
36FR0093	Prehistoric	-77.53471 39.90949	36FR0265	Prehistoric	-77.79766 39.7588
36FR0094	Prehistoric	-77.6524 39.98108	36FR0266	Prehistoric	-77.75263 39.79243
36FR0095	Prehistoric	-77.6317 39.96989	36FR0267	Prehistoric	-77.75605 39.79528
36FR0096	Prehistoric	-77.627 39.96879	36FR0268	Prehistoric	-77.75352 39.79573
36FR0097	Prehistoric	-77.63254 39.96701	36FR0269	Prehistoric	-77.75473 39.79697

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36FR0098	Prehistoric	-77.63023 39.9656	36FR0270	Prehistoric	-77.75903 39.79698
36FR0099	Prehistoric	-77.63687 39.96042	36FR0271	Prehistoric	-77.76088 39.79915
36FR0100	Prehistoric	-77.64066 39.96379	36FR0272	Prehistoric	-77.75475 39.79914
36FR0101	Prehistoric	-77.64442 39.96684	36FR0273	Prehistoric	-77.76209 39.80945
36FR0102	Prehistoric	-77.6533 39.96585	36FR0274	Prehistoric	-77.77253 39.81687
36FR0103	Prehistoric	-77.64915 39.96324	36FR0275	Prehistoric	-77.79903 39.84785
36FR0104	Prehistoric	-77.65243 39.95908	36FR0276	Prehistoric	-77.70778 39.8782
36FR0105	Prehistoric	-77.57058 39.9274	36FR0277	Prehistoric	-77.60489 39.76256
36FR0106	Prehistoric	-77.58444 39.93961	36FR0278	Prehistoric	-77.58906 39.77321
36FR0112	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.75409 40.00804	36FR0279	Prehistoric	-77.58826 39.77761
36FR0115	Prehistoric	-77.73524 39.9247	36FR0280	Prehistoric	-77.58276 39.77907
36FR0116	Prehistoric	-77.75795 39.79781	36FR0281	Prehistoric	-77.57975 39.77935
36FR0117	Prehistoric	-77.8831 39.89384	36FR0282	Prehistoric	-77.57738 39.78077
36FR0118	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.88465 39.90219	36FR0283	Prehistoric	-77.57926 39.786
36FR0130	Prehistoric	-77.8248 39.91825	36FR0284	Prehistoric	-77.57884 39.78794
36FR0131	Prehistoric	-77.80101 39.95087	36FR0285	Prehistoric	-77.57519 39.82165
36FR0132	Prehistoric	-77.80956 39.95024	36FR0286	Prehistoric	-77.65181 39.7445
36FR0133	Prehistoric	-77.81674 39.91442	36FR0287	Prehistoric	-77.66604 39.72866
36FR0134	Prehistoric	-77.80512 39.91636	36FR0288	Prehistoric	-77.66346 39.7291
36FR0135	Prehistoric	-77.73478 39.93582	36FR0289	Prehistoric	-77.66756 39.72332
36FR0136	Prehistoric	-77.89287 39.73162	36FR0290	Prehistoric	-77.69079 39.73336
36FR0137	Prehistoric	-77.89031 39.73351	36FR0291	Prehistoric	-77.69267 39.73004
36FR0138	Prehistoric	-77.88096 39.74298	36FR0292	Prehistoric	-77.69198 39.72757
36FR0139	Prehistoric	-77.88988 39.7529	36FR0293	Prehistoric	-77.68163 39.74712
36FR0140	Prehistoric	-77.88704 39.75139	36FR0294	Prehistoric	-77.68652 39.74447
36FR0141	Prehistoric	-77.88362 39.75326	36FR0295	Prehistoric	-77.61382 39.73668
36FR0142	Prehistoric	-77.89584 39.76921	36FR0296	Prehistoric	-77.57207 39.79002
36FR0143	Prehistoric	-77.91509 39.78133	36FR0297	Prehistoric	-77.5961 39.76927
36FR0144	Prehistoric	-77.91082 39.78466	36FR0298	Prehistoric	-77.60449 39.75351
36FR0145	Prehistoric	-77.94612 39.7699	36FR0299	Prehistoric	-77.86779 39.82882
36FR0146	Prehistoric	-77.87872 39.77461	36FR0300	Prehistoric	-77.86862 39.83155
36FR0147	Prehistoric	-77.88031 39.77183	36FR0303	Prehistoric	-77.56358 39.74054
36FR0148	Prehistoric	-77.86931 39.75795	36FR0304	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.56147 39.74126
36FR0149	Prehistoric	-77.86712 39.76066	36FR0306	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.53312 39.90175
36FR0150	Prehistoric	-77.93157 39.77858	36FR0307	Prehistoric	-77.65853 39.89177
36FR0151	Prehistoric	-77.92696 39.77837	36FR0308	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.74115 39.89169
36FR0152	Prehistoric	-77.93856 39.77677	36FR0308	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.74216 39.89209
36FR0153	Prehistoric	-77.93458 39.77601	36FR0309	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.66254 39.89203
36FR0154	Prehistoric	-77.93263 39.77612	36FR0310	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.87917 39.88922
36FR0156	Prehistoric	-77.89869 39.74601	36FR0312	Prehistoric	-77.78053 39.89036
36FR0157	Prehistoric	-77.89721 39.74542	36FR0314	Prehistoric	-77.9064 39.83283
36FR0158	Prehistoric	-77.92508 39.76076	36FR0315	Prehistoric	-77.57434 39.9186
36FR0159	Prehistoric	-77.92231 39.76128	36FR0316	Prehistoric	-77.86765 39.82705
36FR0160	Prehistoric	-77.89083 39.8625	36FR0317	Prehistoric	-77.91547 39.83455
36FR0161	Prehistoric	-77.93852 39.76875	36FR0318	Prehistoric	-77.91331 39.83412
36FR0162	Prehistoric	-77.92794 39.77599	36FR0319	Prehistoric	-77.91246 39.83289
36FR0163	Prehistoric	-77.92358 39.83816	36FR0320	Prehistoric	-77.90856 39.83316
36FR0164	Prehistoric	-77.89357 39.7691	36FR0321	Prehistoric	-77.90907 39.83117
36FR0165	Prehistoric	-77.88655 39.76906	36FR0322	Prehistoric	-77.88852 39.83657
36FR0166	Prehistoric	-77.94719 39.77562	36FR0323	Prehistoric	-77.88631 39.83649
36FR0167	Prehistoric	-77.94776 39.7722	36FR0324	Prehistoric	-77.90904 39.83019
36FR0168	Prehistoric	-77.88161 39.78429	36FR0326	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.89398 39.89564

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36FR0169	Prehistoric	-77.90426 39.75562	36FR0327	Prehistoric	-77.89704 39.89592
36FR0170	Prehistoric	-77.92773 39.77082	36FR0328	Prehistoric	-77.88941 39.89509
36FR0171	Prehistoric	-77.87188 39.75377	36FR0329	Prehistoric	-77.8839 39.85919
36FR0172	Prehistoric	-77.93086 39.83669	36FR0330	Prehistoric	-77.58501 39.94344
36FR0173	Prehistoric	-77.88865 39.73769	36FR0331	Prehistoric	-77.74023 39.94228
36FR0174	Prehistoric	-77.88549 39.73823	36FR0332	Prehistoric	-77.57703 39.919
36FR0175	Prehistoric	-77.86575 39.83528	36FR0336	Prehistoric	-77.78034 39.99304
36FR0176	Prehistoric	-77.86805 39.83355	36FR0337	Prehistoric	-77.58622 39.94947
36FR0177	Prehistoric	-77.89216 39.77073	36FR0338	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.8744 39.85793
36FR0178	Prehistoric	-77.88942 39.77094	36FR0339	Prehistoric	-77.65838 39.9589
36FR0179	Prehistoric	-77.77553 39.87846	36FR0340	Prehistoric	-77.65717 39.95787
36FR0180	Prehistoric	-77.86002 39.89791	36FR0345	Prehistoric	-77.57466 39.81513
36FR0181	Prehistoric	-77.9319 39.7739	36FR0346	Prehistoric	-77.70012 39.87096
36FR0182	Prehistoric	-77.92248 39.77784	36FR0347	Prehistoric	-77.69878 39.8742
36FR0183	Prehistoric	-77.9414 39.77998	36FR0348	Prehistoric	-77.69481 39.87767
36FR0184	Prehistoric	-77.94146 39.77773	36FR0357	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.51285 39.76719
36FR0185	Prehistoric	-77.94403 39.77286	36FR0364	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.52785 39.76542
36FR0186	Prehistoric	-77.79467 39.90011	36FR0367	Prehistoric	-77.73201 39.76477
36FR0187	Prehistoric	-77.79417 39.89831	36FR0368	Prehistoric	-77.55208 39.73535
36FR0188	Prehistoric	-77.78758 39.89507	36FR0369	Prehistoric	-77.55087 39.73666
36FR0189	Prehistoric	-77.87393 39.74765	36FR0371	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.58983 39.9525
36FR0190	Prehistoric	-77.91625 39.83699	36FR0381	Prehistoric	-77.71621 39.78242
36FR0191	Prehistoric	-77.82538 39.77196	36FR0382	Prehistoric	-77.71806 39.78321
36FR0192	Prehistoric	-77.93255 39.76735	36FR0383	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.67057 39.92563
36FR0193	Prehistoric	-77.93117 39.76849	36FR0396	Prehistoric	-77.57009 39.83627
36FR0197	Prehistoric	-77.87621 39.76299	36FR0397	Prehistoric	-77.65649 39.95921
36FR0198	Prehistoric	-77.88775 39.90101	36FR0398	Prehistoric	-77.65461 39.95524
36FR0199	Prehistoric	-77.8851 39.89737	36FR0399	Prehistoric	-77.58315 39.93923
36FR0200	Prehistoric	-77.66256 39.72807	36FR0400	Prehistoric	-77.57614 39.92892
36FR0201	Prehistoric	-77.66468 39.73006	36FR0402	Prehistoric	-77.57417 39.78965
36FR0202	Prehistoric	-77.68918 39.73468	36FR0406	Prehistoric	-77.61893 39.91737
36FR0203	Prehistoric	-77.69671 39.7385	36FR0407	Prehistoric	-77.62134 39.91721
36FR0204	Prehistoric	-77.69955 39.73946	36FR0410	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.68245 39.9132
36FR0205	Prehistoric	-77.73363 39.74469	36FR0413	Prehistoric	-77.61828 39.9774
36FR0206	Prehistoric	-77.73143 39.74598	36FR0414	Prehistoric	-77.58713 39.93918
36FR0207	Prehistoric	-77.73706 39.74622	36FR0415	Prehistoric	-77.58603 39.93933
36FR0208	Prehistoric	-77.72114 39.74859	36FR0416	Prehistoric	-77.58048 39.96839
36FR0209	Prehistoric	-77.78275 39.86766	36FR0419	Prehistoric	-77.56032 39.84559
36FR0210	Prehistoric	-77.73867 39.74304	36FR0421	Prehistoric	-77.73206 39.76034
36FR0211	Prehistoric	-77.7408 39.74612	36FR0422	Prehistoric	-77.84602 39.89086
36FR0212	Prehistoric	-77.74023 39.74933	36FR0423	Prehistoric	-77.84275 39.89094
36FR0213	Prehistoric	-77.74503 39.74593	36FR0426	Prehistoric	-77.55883 39.89901
36FR0214	Prehistoric	-77.73532 39.75351	36FR0434	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.55226 39.75396
36FR0215	Prehistoric	-77.73524 39.75483	36FR0437	Prehistoric	-77.66823 39.81964
Watershed 91-Ridge and Valley-South Mountain:					
36AD0001	Prehistoric	-77.45029 39.89229	36FR0301	Prehistoric	-77.48355 39.84911
36AD0030	Prehistoric	-77.45196 39.886	36FR0305	Prehistoric	-77.47218 39.90187
36AD0119	Prehistoric	-77.4485 39.87776	36FR0311	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.4778 39.90406
36AD0142	Prehistoric	-77.45385 39.90009	36FR0344	Prehistoric	-77.46763 39.88345
36AD0153	Prehistoric	-77.45961 39.88266	36FR0349	Prehistoric	-77.46932 39.88814
36AD0154	Prehistoric	-77.45468 39.88916	36FR0350	Prehistoric	-77.46992 39.88494

Table A-8. Region 8 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36AD0200	Prehistoric	-77.45568 39.89397	36FR0351	Prehistoric	-77.46732 39.868
36AD0201	Prehistoric	-77.46463 39.86917	36FR0352	Prehistoric	-77.4737 39.86407
36AD0202	Prehistoric	-77.45811 39.86624	36FR0353	Prehistoric	-77.47326 39.86802
36AD0485	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.45694 39.87966	36FR0354	Prehistoric	-77.4736 39.87302
Watershed 93-Ridge and Valley-South Mountain:					
36AD0120	Prehistoric	-77.31823 39.93507			
Watershed 104-Ridge and Valley-South Mountain:					
36AD0046	Prehistoric	-77.42125 39.7714	36AD0498	Prehistoric	-77.35977 39.89859
36AD0116	Prehistoric	-77.43082 39.72082			

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
Watershed 54-Piedmont-Gettysburg-Newark Lowland:					
36LH0078	Prehistoric	-75.39286 40.52142			
Watershed 63-Piedmont-Gettysburg-Newark Lowland:					
36BU0001	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.18236 40.56573	36BU0144	Prehistoric	-75.21547 40.47538
36BU0002	Prehistoric	-75.06567 40.42844	36BU0145	Prehistoric	-75.21656 40.47645
36BU0003	Prehistoric	-75.18721 40.56559	36BU0146	Prehistoric	-75.19045 40.49045
36BU0005	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.14405 40.57265	36BU0147	Prehistoric	-75.19295 40.49317
36BU0007	Prehistoric	-75.35292 40.46792	36BU0148	Prehistoric	-75.08397 40.41404
36BU0008	Prehistoric	-75.30748 40.42022	36BU0159	Prehistoric	-75.33606 40.4521
36BU0017	Prehistoric	-75.10036 40.44207	36BU0160	Prehistoric	-75.30297 40.4971
36BU0020	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.31501 40.4409	36BU0161	Prehistoric	-75.06871 40.50184
36BU0021	Prehistoric	-75.07067 40.42003	36BU0165	Prehistoric	-75.32099 40.50261
36BU0022	Prehistoric	-75.06247 40.42074	36BU0167	Prehistoric	-75.18074 40.3707
36BU0023	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.06025 40.41848	36BU0176	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.10222 40.56663
36BU0025	Prehistoric	-75.32921 40.44742	36BU0180	Prehistoric	-75.33243 40.4054
36BU0035	Prehistoric	-75.33975 40.40299	36BU0183	Prehistoric	-75.31904 40.44252
36BU0039	Prehistoric	-75.17827 40.46799	36BU0191	Prehistoric	-75.10293 40.56665
36BU0042	Prehistoric	-75.22636 40.46507	36BU0199	Prehistoric	-75.37047 40.4078
36BU0048	Prehistoric	-75.14361 40.4914	36BU0213	Prehistoric	-75.33959 40.4037
36BU0062	Prehistoric	-75.26788 40.47225	36BU0229	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.14976 40.4004
36BU0063	Prehistoric	-75.29082 40.45679	36BU0230	Prehistoric	-75.31896 40.37614
36BU0064	Prehistoric	-75.31598 40.40767	36BU0254	Prehistoric	-75.35244 40.46362
36BU0065	Prehistoric	-75.33613 40.41716	36BU0255	Prehistoric	-75.35352 40.46499
36BU0066	Prehistoric	-75.30447 40.46622	36BU0256	Prehistoric	-75.35138 40.46321
36BU0067	Prehistoric	-75.27245 40.43486	36BU0258	Prehistoric	-75.34954 40.46327
36BU0068	Prehistoric	-75.29895 40.4402	36BU0260	Prehistoric	-75.06981 40.51661
36BU0069	Prehistoric	-75.31017 40.48769	36BU0261	Prehistoric	-75.06905 40.52086
36BU0070	Prehistoric	-75.27968 40.45514	36BU0262	Prehistoric	-75.06872 40.52923
36BU0072	Prehistoric	-75.30411 40.44764	36BU0263	Prehistoric	-75.06934 40.53361
36BU0073	Prehistoric	-75.33294 40.43543	36BU0265	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.17714 40.51376
36BU0074	Prehistoric	-75.30792 40.44229	36BU0266	Prehistoric	-75.27108 40.46265
36BU0075	Prehistoric	-75.32953 40.40631	36BU0280	Prehistoric	-75.36325 40.42703
36BU0076	Prehistoric	-75.34851 40.4491	36BU0305	Prehistoric	-75.27245 40.46237
36BU0077	Prehistoric	-75.34105 40.46097	36BU0309	Prehistoric	-75.10442 40.56427
36BU0078	Prehistoric	-75.31994 40.41175	36BU0314	Prehistoric	-75.32291 40.43209
36BU0079	Prehistoric	-75.30959 40.42507	36BU0335	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.32275 40.40604
36BU0080	Prehistoric	-75.33681 40.45395	36BU0336	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.33291 40.40397
36BU0094	Prehistoric	-75.27416 40.41721	36BU0337	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.31058 40.40809
36BU0117	Prehistoric	-75.18888 40.56279	36BU0353	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.32046 40.42169
36BU0118	Prehistoric	-75.17634 40.56298	36BU0391	Prehistoric	-75.16104 40.46349
36BU0124	Prehistoric	-75.36894 40.46807	36BU0392	Prehistoric	-75.15984 40.46456
36BU0125	Prehistoric	-75.11915 40.43035	36BU0393	Prehistoric	-75.13792 40.43604
36BU0126	Prehistoric	-75.32368 40.44519	36BU0394	Prehistoric	-75.13679 40.4366
36BU0127	Prehistoric	-75.32774 40.4607	36BU0395	Prehistoric	-75.13423 40.43689
36BU0128	Prehistoric	-75.3581 40.4287	36BU0396	Prehistoric	-75.13245 40.44315
36BU0129	Prehistoric	-75.17144 40.40532	36BU0397	Prehistoric	-75.13877 40.44064
36BU0130	Prehistoric	-75.14363 40.49142	36BU0398	Prehistoric	-75.13905 40.43696
36BU0131	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.13992 40.43772	36BU0400	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.13894 40.43627
36BU0134	Prehistoric	-75.11992 40.43481			

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
Watershed 65-Piedmont-Gettysburg-Newark Lowland:					
36DA0029	Prehistoric	-76.66312 40.26311	36LE0134	Prehistoric	-76.55816 40.26561
36DA0056	Prehistoric	-76.62045 40.23497	36LE0135	Prehistoric	-76.55615 40.26778
36DA0113	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.73362 40.18634	36LE0138	Prehistoric	-76.59235 40.26945
36DA0143	Prehistoric	-76.64039 40.25058	36LE0203	Prehistoric	-76.49311 40.26485
36DA0202	Prehistoric	-76.71481 40.19778	36LE0204	Prehistoric	-76.49683 40.26102
36DA0203	Prehistoric	-76.7127 40.20308	36LE0212	Prehistoric	-76.43669 40.27392
36DA0204	Prehistoric	-76.72302 40.21898	36LE0242	Prehistoric	-76.58477 40.25732
36DA0205	Prehistoric	-76.72152 40.21733	36LE0245	Prehistoric	-76.52541 40.27144
36DA0212	Prehistoric	-76.65805 40.23155	36LE0475	Prehistoric	-76.43544 40.27185
36LE0133	Prehistoric	-76.55959 40.2707			
Watershed 69-Piedmont-Gettysburg-Newark Lowland:					
36BK0002	Prehistoric	-75.88514 40.29735	36BK0583	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.01861 40.27675
36BK0017	Prehistoric	-75.90716 40.3	36BK0615	Prehistoric	-75.91387 40.29947
36BK0018	Prehistoric	-75.90463 40.30983	36BK0647	Prehistoric	-75.86389 40.28345
36BK0123	Prehistoric	-75.92175 40.2392	36BK0648	Prehistoric	-75.85966 40.28566
36BK0157	Prehistoric	-75.90832 40.25451	36BK0649	Prehistoric	-75.85146 40.28011
36BK0179	Prehistoric	-76.02841 40.29791	36BK0650	Prehistoric	-75.84516 40.27652
36BK0300	Prehistoric	-75.83561 40.27493	36BK0657	Prehistoric	-75.83212 40.27638
36BK0338	Prehistoric	-75.86932 40.2879	36BK0671	Prehistoric	-75.85 40.29942
36BK0468	Prehistoric	-75.89162 40.29629	36BK0680	Prehistoric	-75.9181 40.24788
36BK0531	Prehistoric	-75.89737 40.30314	36BK0716	Prehistoric	-75.89298 40.29674
36BK0561	Prehistoric	-75.91971 40.2451	36BK0733	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.90574 40.29569
36BK0562	Prehistoric	-75.894 40.29621	36BK0889	Prehistoric	-75.92318 40.25894
Watershed 70-Piedmont-Gettysburg-Newark Lowland:					
36DA0022	Prehistoric	-76.82295 40.20589	36DA0220	Prehistoric	-76.80037 40.2093
36DA0048	Prehistoric	-76.7688 40.19686	36DA0238	Prehistoric	-76.8009 40.20889
36DA0088	Prehistoric	-76.82258 40.20407	36YO0260	Prehistoric	-76.79871 40.19917
36DA0089	Prehistoric	-76.80653 40.20557	36YO0261	Prehistoric	-76.82731 40.20395
36DA0090	Prehistoric	-76.73996 40.18028	36YO0262	Prehistoric	-76.82103 40.20141
36DA0125	Prehistoric	-76.74322 40.17669	36YO0263	Prehistoric	-76.80457 40.19579
36DA0133	Prehistoric	-76.74095 40.19272	36YO0265	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.81183 40.19608
36DA0145	Prehistoric	-76.82496 40.20472			
Watershed 72-Piedmont-Gettysburg-Newark Lowland:					
36BK0126	Prehistoric	-75.69757 40.30738	36MG0107	Prehistoric	-75.43881 40.32576
36BK0127	Prehistoric	-75.69507 40.30524	36MG0108	Prehistoric	-75.38061 40.23787
36BK0128	Prehistoric	-75.68516 40.31121	36MG0109	Prehistoric	-75.41882 40.19343
36BK0129	Prehistoric	-75.68815 40.3098	36MG0110	Prehistoric	-75.38049 40.22089
36BK0131	Prehistoric	-75.69964 40.3108	36MG0111	Prehistoric	-75.309 40.23105
36BK0303	Prehistoric	-75.55608 40.44498	36MG0113	Prehistoric	-75.53506 40.27673
36BK0474	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.56476 40.4207	36MG0117	Prehistoric	-75.37605 40.33149
36BK0674	Prehistoric	-75.67791 40.29355	36MG0118	Prehistoric	-75.37961 40.32994
36BK0675	Prehistoric	-75.66561 40.29861	36MG0119	Prehistoric	-75.38505 40.3311
36BK0676	Prehistoric	-75.66914 40.29676	36MG0120	Prehistoric	-75.39797 40.30723
36BK0677	Prehistoric	-75.61809 40.35024	36MG0121	Prehistoric	-75.40119 40.30484
36BK0681	Prehistoric	-75.58731 40.38465	36MG0122	Prehistoric	-75.3527 40.32149
36BK0682	Prehistoric	-75.59422 40.38714	36MG0123	Prehistoric	-75.38056 40.29511
36BK0683	Prehistoric	-75.59273 40.38524	36MG0124	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.41032 40.28245
36BK0728	Prehistoric	-75.60118 40.39616	36MG0125	Prehistoric	-75.41893 40.29689
36BK0735	Prehistoric	-75.54028 40.43479	36MG0126	Prehistoric	-75.42241 40.3022

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36BK0747	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.60015 40.3849	36MG0127	Prehistoric	-75.42812 40.30567
36BK0862	Prehistoric	-75.59845 40.3884	36MG0128	Prehistoric	-75.43268 40.30596
36BU0006	Prehistoric	-75.38934 40.37622	36MG0129	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.45394 40.25414
36BU0013	Prehistoric	-75.31402 40.34135	36MG0130	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.45683 40.25196
36BU0014	Prehistoric	-75.313 40.34659	36MG0131	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.45559 40.25585
36BU0015	Prehistoric	-75.3135 40.35285	36MG0132	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.46147 40.25719
36BU0027	Prehistoric	-75.40108 40.4061	36MG0133	Prehistoric	-75.46069 40.25497
36BU0028	Prehistoric	-75.42202 40.44873	36MG0144	Prehistoric	-75.48893 40.20014
36BU0029	Prehistoric	-75.41898 40.39346	36MG0145	Prehistoric	-75.46511 40.21492
36BU0030	Prehistoric	-75.39376 40.43169	36MG0146	Prehistoric	-75.45909 40.21508
36BU0031	Prehistoric	-75.42313 40.41096	36MG0147	Prehistoric	-75.4094 40.20804
36BU0032	Prehistoric	-75.39473 40.42054	36MG0148	Prehistoric	-75.39687 40.21059
36BU0033	Prehistoric	-75.39262 40.37645	36MG0149	Prehistoric	-75.38551 40.21084
36BU0034	Prehistoric	-75.40319 40.41284	36MG0150	Prehistoric	-75.44298 40.21432
36BU0036	Prehistoric	-75.37249 40.38907	36MG0151	Prehistoric	-75.38553 40.21275
36BU0037	Prehistoric	-75.34603 40.37842	36MG0152	Prehistoric	-75.3347 40.21083
36BU0038	Prehistoric	-75.4003 40.37333	36MG0161	Prehistoric	-75.38868 40.21062
36BU0040	Prehistoric	-75.40677 40.37691	36MG0165	Prehistoric	-75.55379 40.32262
36BU0041	Prehistoric	-75.40336 40.37186	36MG0168	Prehistoric	-75.50199 40.3858
36BU0071	Prehistoric	-75.36657 40.39329	36MG0169	Prehistoric	-75.50256 40.38627
36BU0082	Prehistoric	-75.42042 40.44759	36MG0193	Prehistoric	-75.50078 40.3783
36BU0083	Prehistoric	-75.40956 40.39778	36MG0194	Prehistoric	-75.49966 40.3756
36BU0084	Prehistoric	-75.41884 40.46766	36MG0195	Prehistoric	-75.50043 40.37366
36BU0086	Prehistoric	-75.41817 40.40209	36MG0196	Prehistoric	-75.44595 40.22543
36BU0087	Prehistoric	-75.40328 40.43048	36MG0198	Prehistoric	-75.38059 40.26608
36BU0088	Prehistoric	-75.41784 40.42968	36MG0202	Prehistoric	-75.43266 40.2179
36BU0089	Prehistoric	-75.41296 40.43171	36MG0210	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.56028 40.32249
36BU0090	Prehistoric	-75.37636 40.43415	36MG0212	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.38108 40.25613
36BU0091	Prehistoric	-75.38331 40.41672	36MG0213	Prehistoric	-75.38424 40.25603
36BU0101	Prehistoric	-75.32583 40.34836	36MG0214	Prehistoric	-75.3829 40.254
36BU0102	Prehistoric	-75.44421 40.4483	36MG0220	Prehistoric	-75.44753 40.22393
36BU0103	Prehistoric	-75.4161 40.38379	36MG0221	Prehistoric	-75.4479 40.22509
36BU0104	Prehistoric	-75.37575 40.37851	36MG0223	Prehistoric	-75.44355 40.2261
36BU0105	Prehistoric	-75.42373 40.42028	36MG0224	Prehistoric	-75.43903 40.24141
36BU0135	Prehistoric	-75.42223 40.41161	36MG0225	Prehistoric	-75.43366 40.24092
36BU0136	Prehistoric	-75.39181 40.37459	36MG0226	Prehistoric	-75.43555 40.24242
36BU0137	Prehistoric	-75.27499 40.34862	36MG0227	Prehistoric	-75.44984 40.22147
36BU0138	Prehistoric	-75.26906 40.36584	36MG0228	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.44555 40.22725
36BU0162	Prehistoric	-75.39788 40.42675	36MG0229	Prehistoric	-75.44147 40.23719
36BU0168	Prehistoric	-75.27814 40.35153	36MG0230	Prehistoric	-75.4324 40.23718
36BU0170	Prehistoric	-75.23996 40.3913	36MG0232	Prehistoric	-75.43868 40.24244
36BU0177	Prehistoric	-75.25074 40.35206	36MG0245	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.31244 40.24522
36BU0181	Prehistoric	-75.34385 40.37842	36MG0246	Prehistoric	-75.58433 40.29521
36BU0192	Prehistoric	-75.3571 40.37597	36MG0247	Prehistoric	-75.54459 40.29117
36BU0200	Prehistoric	-75.34019 40.37948	36MG0248	Prehistoric	-75.54944 40.2807
36BU0204	Prehistoric	-75.31656 40.35323	36MG0249	Prehistoric	-75.60446 40.34319
36BU0332	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.23473 40.38465	36MG0250	Prehistoric	-75.6034 40.34102
36BU0408	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.39865 40.43948	36MG0251	Prehistoric	-75.6017 40.33939
36BU0410	Prehistoric	-75.29813 40.36211	36MG0252	Prehistoric	-75.36277 40.22936
36LH0038	Prehistoric	-75.42127 40.48162	36MG0253	Prehistoric	-75.57677 40.38471
36LH0118	Prehistoric	-75.42331 40.48462	36MG0257	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.37795 40.23546
36LH0207	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.46532 40.47093	36MG0258	Prehistoric	-75.57124 40.32841

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LH0279	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.49835 40.45429	36MG0259	Prehistoric	-75.57237 40.32898
36LH0280	Prehistoric	-75.49915 40.45481	36MG0260	Prehistoric	-75.57448 40.32959
36MG0003	Prehistoric	-75.45964 40.12095	36MG0261	Prehistoric	-75.58018 40.32437
36MG0004	Prehistoric	-75.45401 40.1182	36MG0262	Prehistoric	-75.48443 40.27518
36MG0005	Prehistoric	-75.44333 40.12954	36MG0263	Prehistoric	-75.36867 40.24633
36MG0006	Prehistoric	-75.44787 40.1501	36MG0265	Prehistoric	-75.45136 40.33859
36MG0019	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.4226 40.36979	36MG0276	Prehistoric	-75.41431 40.27306
36MG0020	Prehistoric	-75.4164 40.34508	36MG0278	Prehistoric	-75.4203 40.33964
36MG0021	Prehistoric	-75.47852 40.33135	36MG0279	Prehistoric	-75.44178 40.34179
36MG0022	Prehistoric	-75.47269 40.32924	36MG0293	Prehistoric	-75.4255 40.34998
36MG0023	Prehistoric	-75.47743 40.33066	36MG0294	Prehistoric	-75.48811 40.33597
36MG0024	Prehistoric	-75.48184 40.32919	36MG0304	Prehistoric	-75.38712 40.20528
36MG0025	Prehistoric	-75.48569 40.32405	36MG0306	Prehistoric	-75.45427 40.14838
36MG0026	Prehistoric	-75.43771 40.3349	36MG0308	Prehistoric	-75.44269 40.16181
36MG0040	Prehistoric	-75.57942 40.33221	36MG0310	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.51045 40.3979
36MG0043	Prehistoric	-75.54208 40.34545	36MG0311	Prehistoric	-75.48526 40.26921
36MG0046	Prehistoric	-75.50558 40.36715	36MG0312	Prehistoric	-75.48572 40.26568
36MG0047	Prehistoric	-75.50656 40.37307	36MG0313	Prehistoric	-75.49627 40.26268
36MG0048	Prehistoric	-75.51183 40.36609	36MG0314	Prehistoric	-75.50557 40.26087
36MG0049	Prehistoric	-75.51647 40.37246	36MG0319	Prehistoric	-75.31907 40.19945
36MG0050	Prehistoric	-75.51066 40.38576	36MG0330	Prehistoric	-75.53781 40.43319
36MG0051	Prehistoric	-75.50578 40.37996	36MG0331	Prehistoric	-75.5343 40.43111
36MG0052	Prehistoric	-75.50914 40.37974	36MG0332	Prehistoric	-75.53768 40.43179
36MG0053	Prehistoric	-75.51067 40.37814	36MG0333	Prehistoric	-75.53916 40.43326
36MG0054	Prehistoric	-75.51671 40.4359	36MG0334	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.5395 40.4295
36MG0055	Prehistoric	-75.52174 40.41726	36MG0351	Prehistoric	-75.46975 40.38081
36MG0056	Prehistoric	-75.52152 40.40656	36MG0352	Prehistoric	-75.46924 40.38004
36MG0057	Prehistoric	-75.58286 40.31837	36MG0375	Prehistoric	-75.52534 40.42445
36MG0058	Prehistoric	-75.56903 40.32745	36MG0376	Prehistoric	-75.52639 40.42433
36MG0059	Prehistoric	-75.56916 40.32385	36MG0377	Prehistoric	-75.35012 40.26098
36MG0060	Prehistoric	-75.56521 40.32409	36MG0378	Prehistoric	-75.34787 40.26254
36MG0061	Prehistoric	-75.56671 40.32532	36MG0379	Prehistoric	-75.34637 40.26394
36MG0062	Prehistoric	-75.56457 40.32718	36MG0380	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.31713 40.29046
36MG0063	Prehistoric	-75.56242 40.32791	36MG0381	Prehistoric	-75.34818 40.26293
36MG0064	Prehistoric	-75.56297 40.3297	36MG0383	Prehistoric	-75.35497 40.25592
36MG0065	Prehistoric	-75.47071 40.38194	36MG0387	Prehistoric	-75.40838 40.24761
36MG0066	Prehistoric	-75.47059 40.37791	36MG0388	Prehistoric	-75.41224 40.24641
36MG0067	Prehistoric	-75.46978 40.37701	36MG0389	Prehistoric	-75.41498 40.24905
36MG0068	Prehistoric	-75.52053 40.41463	36MG0390	Prehistoric	-75.41924 40.2506
36MG0075	Prehistoric	-75.4303 40.14631	36MG0398	Prehistoric	-75.4264 40.28772
36MG0076	Prehistoric	-75.42328 40.36893	36MG0401	Prehistoric	-75.33283 40.29782
36MG0079	Prehistoric	-75.43597 40.34371	36MG0405	Prehistoric	-75.41513 40.29833
36MG0080	Prehistoric	-75.43362 40.34964	36MG0406	Prehistoric	-75.41555 40.29722
36MG0081	Prehistoric	-75.42545 40.35841	36MG0407	Prehistoric	-75.41442 40.29702
36MG0082	Prehistoric	-75.42754 40.35675	36MG0408	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.34592 40.24719
36MG0083	Prehistoric	-75.5515 40.41799	36MG0409	Prehistoric	-75.44843 40.18051
36MG0085	Prehistoric	-75.40363 40.29046	36MG0410	Prehistoric	-75.4475 40.19147
36MG0086	Prehistoric	-75.44235 40.27611	36MG0411	Prehistoric	-75.45126 40.21897
36MG0087	Prehistoric	-75.41678 40.29336	36MG0415	Prehistoric	-75.4175 40.20743
36MG0088	Prehistoric	-75.45967 40.29928	36MG0417	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.35178 40.26138
36MG0089	Prehistoric	-75.41957 40.28945	36MG0418	Prehistoric	-75.35316 40.26443
36MG0090	Prehistoric	-75.37105 40.3368	36MG0419	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.28165 40.23964

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36MG0091	Prehistoric	-75.43988 40.32723	36MG0420	Prehistoric	-75.30819 40.20266
36MG0092	Prehistoric	-75.44788 40.32554	36MG0423	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.45429 40.24121
36MG0093	Prehistoric	-75.45083 40.27697	36MG0424	Prehistoric	-75.41959 40.30227
36MG0094	Prehistoric	-75.44861 40.27749	36MG0431	Prehistoric	-75.35209 40.25987
36MG0095	Prehistoric	-75.3902 40.20687	36MG0432	Prehistoric	-75.35295 40.26187
36MG0096	Prehistoric	-75.4163 40.1882	36MG0433	Prehistoric	-75.34576 40.21379
36MG0097	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.42666 40.17394	36MG0439	Prehistoric	-75.45586 40.17192
36MG0098	Prehistoric	-75.57744 40.29645	36MG0443	Prehistoric	-75.42489 40.23318
36MG0099	Prehistoric	-75.58093 40.29935	36MG0444	Prehistoric	-75.42285 40.2254
36MG0100	Prehistoric	-75.57156 40.30248	36MG0445	Prehistoric	-75.42336 40.23013
36MG0104	Prehistoric	-75.45704 40.11736	36MG0446	Prehistoric	-75.42407 40.23173
36MG0105	Prehistoric	-75.36702 40.33762	36MG0447	Prehistoric	-75.42364 40.23347
36MG0106	Prehistoric	-75.42881 40.28448	36MG0448	Prehistoric	-75.42067 40.23142
Watershed 76-Piedmont-Gettysburg-Newark Lowland:					
36BK0011	Prehistoric	-75.77421 40.27077	36CH0440	Prehistoric	-75.56977 40.14198
36BK0012	Prehistoric	-75.73296 40.25273	36CH0442	Prehistoric	-75.61294 40.14577
36BK0013	Prehistoric	-75.76561 40.2582	36CH0443	Prehistoric	-75.59748 40.14093
36BK0125	Prehistoric	-75.73515 40.31281	36CH0450	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.5299 40.14527
36BK0130	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.72699 40.30199	36CH0451	Prehistoric	-75.59856 40.14537
36BK0143	Prehistoric	-75.81583 40.3233	36CH0452	Prehistoric	-75.59843 40.16447
36BK0144	Prehistoric	-75.79225 40.32881	36CH0454	Prehistoric	-75.6197 40.14831
36BK0145	Prehistoric	-75.81574 40.32051	36CH0458	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.52255 40.1449
36BK0146	Prehistoric	-75.78733 40.31651	36CH0460	Prehistoric	-75.51805 40.14495
36BK0147	Prehistoric	-75.7894 40.31433	36CH0461	Prehistoric	-75.51061 40.14544
36BK0148	Prehistoric	-75.78779 40.31477	36CH0489	Prehistoric	-75.77584 40.17961
36BK0149	Prehistoric	-75.78657 40.31242	36CH0491	Prehistoric	-75.68879 40.17117
36BK0150	Prehistoric	-75.7888 40.31246	36CH0492	Prehistoric	-75.71799 40.17327
36BK0153	Prehistoric	-75.75138 40.31629	36CH0493	Prehistoric	-75.73622 40.18645
36BK0154	Prehistoric	-75.77951 40.27158	36CH0551	Prehistoric	-75.59319 40.14444
36BK0297	Prehistoric	-75.70047 40.24241	36CH0557	Prehistoric	-75.56943 40.18782
36BK0298	Prehistoric	-75.70943 40.24395	36CH0579	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.54109 40.15437
36BK0299	Prehistoric	-75.75914 40.25897	36CH0580	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.55759 40.15639
36BK0301	Prehistoric	-75.72159 40.30903	36CH0581	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.53783 40.15245
36BK0337	Prehistoric	-75.78348 40.27185	36CH0583	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.53449 40.15518
36BK0415	Prehistoric	-75.78319 40.30908	36CH0632	Prehistoric	-75.62207 40.22874
36BK0498	Prehistoric	-75.72908 40.25667	36CH0633	Prehistoric	-75.58263 40.20602
36BK0507	Prehistoric	-75.82515 40.17559	36CH0634	Prehistoric	-75.58295 40.20435
36BK0513	Prehistoric	-75.82434 40.18031	36CH0635	Prehistoric	-75.58209 40.20252
36BK0515	Prehistoric	-75.82746 40.17986	36CH0641	Prehistoric	-75.59979 40.15178
36BK0516	Prehistoric	-75.82615 40.17728	36CH0642	Prehistoric	-75.58517 40.14369
36BK0546	Prehistoric	-75.82737 40.17431	36CH0643	Prehistoric	-75.58008 40.14016
36BK0565	Prehistoric	-75.72226 40.22949	36CH0821	Prehistoric	-75.66423 40.17087
36BK0566	Prehistoric	-75.73885 40.24799	36CH0822	Prehistoric	-75.66469 40.17139
36BK0567	Prehistoric	-75.74015 40.23543	36CH0823	Prehistoric	-75.66965 40.17112
36BK0568	Prehistoric	-75.74059 40.24659	36CH0824	Prehistoric	-75.67062 40.17065
36BK0569	Prehistoric	-75.73687 40.2318	36CH0825	Prehistoric	-75.66932 40.17197
36BK0571	Prehistoric	-75.74908 40.23902	36CH0826	Prehistoric	-75.66825 40.17131
36BK0572	Prehistoric	-75.78876 40.25832	36CH0827	Prehistoric	-75.66514 40.17014
36BK0605	Prehistoric	-75.73111 40.26355	36CH0828	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.66086 40.24035
36BK0607	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.76795 40.20601	36CH0841	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.68707 40.17526
36BK0635	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.67194 40.27526	36CH0892	Prehistoric	-75.67611 40.24118
36BK0637	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.73138 40.27535	36CH0893	Prehistoric	-75.64233 40.23424

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36BK0691	Prehistoric	-75.72875 40.24762	36CH0894	Prehistoric	-75.67283 40.24211
36BK0698	Prehistoric	-75.73972 40.31375	36CH0895	Prehistoric	-75.67436 40.242
36BK0699	Prehistoric	-75.72892 40.31115	36CH0896	Prehistoric	-75.60427 40.23442
36BK0725	Prehistoric	-75.71815 40.31055	36CH0898	Prehistoric	-75.70989 40.18887
36BK0726	Prehistoric	-75.71122 40.30977	36CH0899	Prehistoric	-75.62931 40.23172
36BK0727	Prehistoric	-75.71477 40.31049	36CH0900	Prehistoric	-75.63556 40.23336
36BK0863	Prehistoric	-75.71592 40.30811	36MG0001	Prehistoric	-75.56618 40.20848
36BK0879	Prehistoric	-75.71852 40.24518	36MG0002	Prehistoric	-75.47438 40.13018
36BK0880	Prehistoric	-75.71649 40.2405	36MG0011	Prehistoric	-75.51403 40.1601
36BK0885	Prehistoric	-75.77863 40.26033	36MG0012	Prehistoric	-75.49813 40.16381
36CH0035	Prehistoric	-75.68281 40.23663	36MG0013	Prehistoric	-75.52627 40.17632
36CH0036	Prehistoric	-75.59994 40.21955	36MG0014	Prehistoric	-75.54405 40.19206
36CH0037	Prehistoric	-75.59918 40.22117	36MG0015	Prehistoric	-75.55161 40.20255
36CH0038	Prehistoric	-75.59532 40.22612	36MG0016	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.60952 40.23672
36CH0039	Prehistoric	-75.59391 40.20762	36MG0036	Prehistoric	-75.60725 40.24026
36CH0040	Prehistoric	-75.55871 40.18781	36MG0037	Prehistoric	-75.58581 40.21478
36CH0041	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.55401 40.18639	36MG0038	Prehistoric	-75.55614 40.20882
36CH0042	Prehistoric	-75.60165 40.22636	36MG0039	Prehistoric	-75.54851 40.19544
36CH0043	Prehistoric	-75.55509 40.19858	36MG0041	Prehistoric	-75.56727 40.20277
36CH0044	Prehistoric	-75.60448 40.21795	36MG0042	Prehistoric	-75.51758 40.15707
36CH0045	Prehistoric	-75.60421 40.21623	36MG0044	Prehistoric	-75.51357 40.1636
36CH0046	Prehistoric	-75.53778 40.16391	36MG0045	Prehistoric	-75.50088 40.1645
36CH0047	Prehistoric	-75.53064 40.15967	36MG0069	Prehistoric	-75.51524 40.15989
36CH0053	Prehistoric	-75.51202 40.15067	36MG0071	Prehistoric	-75.64296 40.26999
36CH0054	Prehistoric	-75.50489 40.15517	36MG0073	Prehistoric	-75.50219 40.14924
36CH0055	Prehistoric	-75.58069 40.19476	36MG0078	Prehistoric	-75.47486 40.13566
36CH0056	Prehistoric	-75.57688 40.19499	36MG0101	Prehistoric	-75.50121 40.16184
36CH0070	Prehistoric	-75.62485 40.1503	36MG0112	Prehistoric	-75.49819 40.15404
36CH0071	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.65826 40.23617	36MG0134	Prehistoric	-75.52071 40.16168
36CH0084	Prehistoric	-75.56173 40.12558	36MG0135	Prehistoric	-75.52031 40.1681
36CH0101	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.61903 40.22642	36MG0136	Prehistoric	-75.52101 40.16951
36CH0102	Prehistoric	-75.59575 40.2281	36MG0137	Prehistoric	-75.50092 40.18898
36CH0103	Prehistoric	-75.59321 40.22277	36MG0138	Prehistoric	-75.57044 40.20706
36CH0104	Prehistoric	-75.59957 40.22316	36MG0139	Prehistoric	-75.52471 40.16906
36CH0105	Prehistoric	-75.59336 40.21023	36MG0140	Prehistoric	-75.5239 40.16685
36CH0106	Prehistoric	-75.58541 40.20936	36MG0141	Prehistoric	-75.52253 40.16335
36CH0107	Prehistoric	-75.58414 40.1987	36MG0142	Prehistoric	-75.51943 40.15009
36CH0108	Prehistoric	-75.58271 40.19382	36MG0143	Prehistoric	-75.49601 40.19306
36CH0109	Prehistoric	-75.53539 40.167	36MG0162	Prehistoric	-75.52368 40.156
36CH0110	Prehistoric	-75.51765 40.14671	36MG0163	Prehistoric	-75.52739 40.16907
36CH0111	Prehistoric	-75.55352 40.19509	36MG0173	Prehistoric	-75.48266 40.1295
36CH0112	Prehistoric	-75.54554 40.16914	36MG0178	Prehistoric	-75.52436 40.21639
36CH0113	Prehistoric	-75.55005 40.16873	36MG0179	Prehistoric	-75.50681 40.21388
36CH0114	Prehistoric	-75.50406 40.15336	36MG0187	Prehistoric	-75.50234 40.16661
36CH0115	Prehistoric	-75.60159 40.22734	36MG0205	Prehistoric	-75.54087 40.1923
36CH0144	Prehistoric	-75.50999 40.10815	36MG0264	Prehistoric	-75.52955 40.17622
36CH0148	Prehistoric	-75.72363 40.16992	36MG0292	Prehistoric	-75.52559 40.17075
36CH0260	Prehistoric	-75.75448 40.19615	36MG0303	Prehistoric	-75.60385 40.2394
36CH0269	Prehistoric	-75.51957 40.11022	36MG0305	Prehistoric	-75.6064 40.23886
36CH0278	Prehistoric	-75.59725 40.23492	36MG0337	Prehistoric	-75.50964 40.17726
36CH0279	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.69605 40.23811	36MG0341	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.50454 40.1475
36CH0318	Prehistoric	-75.7412 40.1867	36MG0343	Prehistoric	-75.56698 40.25111

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36CH0321	Prehistoric	-75.76153 40.19157	36MG0344	Prehistoric	-75.5657 40.2515
36CH0322	Prehistoric	-75.75945 40.19532	36MG0345	Prehistoric	-75.56187 40.2478
36CH0323	Prehistoric	-75.7529 40.19329	36MG0346	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.5635 40.24789
36CH0324	Prehistoric	-75.61879 40.17081	36MG0347	Prehistoric	-75.5643 40.24755
36CH0325	Prehistoric	-75.71405 40.19034	36MG0348	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.56761 40.24801
36CH0363	Prehistoric	-75.59302 40.16186	36MG0350	Prehistoric	-75.50086 40.15216
36CH0364	Prehistoric	-75.59233 40.21883	36MG0353	Prehistoric	-75.67341 40.24467
36CH0380	Prehistoric	-75.6788 40.1751	36MG0354	Prehistoric	-75.66801 40.24558
36CH0382	Prehistoric	-75.59737 40.221	36MG0355	Prehistoric	-75.50001 40.1583
36CH0383	Prehistoric	-75.53008 40.16512	36MG0369	Prehistoric	-75.48474 40.13589
36CH0384	Prehistoric	-75.46883 40.12185	36MG0393	Prehistoric	-75.62391 40.23219
36CH0435	Prehistoric	-75.75709 40.18958	36MG0395	Prehistoric	-75.67611 40.2433
36CH0439	Prehistoric	-75.56777 40.14023	36MG0456	Prehistoric	-75.68795 40.23704
Watershed 76-Piedmont-Piedmont Upland:					
36CH0075	Prehistoric	-75.54847 40.10201	36CH0733	Prehistoric	-75.80153 40.15293
36CH0121	Prehistoric	-75.63696 40.09262	36CH0734	Prehistoric	-75.80699 40.15205
36CH0122	Prehistoric	-75.6802 40.08318	36CH0735	Prehistoric	-75.8145 40.14481
36CH0123	Prehistoric	-75.67668 40.08017	36CH0736	Prehistoric	-75.81074 40.14411
36CH0124	Prehistoric	-75.683 40.08327	36CH0737	Prehistoric	-75.65519 40.06401
36CH0125	Prehistoric	-75.68326 40.08089	36CH0744	Prehistoric	-75.81342 40.14074
36CH0127	Prehistoric	-75.6626 40.06839	36CH0766	Prehistoric	-75.68499 40.07798
36CH0143	Prehistoric	-75.57048 40.09398	36CH0767	Prehistoric	-75.68768 40.08349
36CH0193	Prehistoric	-75.5751 40.11228	36CH0769	Prehistoric	-75.68779 40.0862
36CH0194	Prehistoric	-75.56988 40.11266	36CH0770	Prehistoric	-75.68837 40.08651
36CH0199	Prehistoric	-75.60919 40.06166	36CH0771	Prehistoric	-75.68657 40.08733
36CH0211	Prehistoric	-75.61716 40.07077	36CH0773	Prehistoric	-75.67931 40.08046
36CH0381	Prehistoric	-75.67038 40.16573	36CH0818	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.68055 40.09141
36CH0436	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.60417 40.07226	36CH0836	Prehistoric	-75.67987 40.08954
36CH0437	Prehistoric	-75.61098 40.07216	36CH0837	Prehistoric	-75.67299 40.0904
36CH0441	Prehistoric	-75.62333 40.12728	36CH0838	Prehistoric	-75.66782 40.08838
36CH0453	Prehistoric	-75.6209 40.14656	36CH0839	Prehistoric	-75.66217 40.08661
36CH0456	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.62443 40.10011	36CH0840	Prehistoric	-75.68031 40.09576
36CH0490	Prehistoric	-75.80065 40.15916	36CH0848	Prehistoric	-75.66924 40.08885
36CH0510	Prehistoric	-75.68661 40.11886	36CH0849	Prehistoric	-75.66923 40.08813
36CH0622	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.64103 40.09275	36CH0850	Prehistoric	-75.66761 40.08658
36CH0640	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.49142 40.10256	36CH0868	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.68479 40.14614
36CH0677	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.64411 40.0811	36CH0922	Prehistoric	-75.66235 40.06622
36CH0691	Prehistoric	-75.65906 40.07982			
Watershed 79-Piedmont-Gettysburg-Newark Lowland:					
36BU0016	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.93147 40.3242	36BU0304	Prehistoric	-75.07274 40.36647
36BU0044	Prehistoric	-74.82088 40.23745	36BU0308	Prehistoric	-75.0035 40.40678
36BU0149	Prehistoric	-74.88591 40.30558	36BU0310	Prehistoric	-74.99512 40.35494
36BU0150	Prehistoric	-74.96587 40.3207	36BU0319	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.93558 40.32926
36BU0151	Prehistoric	-74.97582 40.32378	36BU0320	Prehistoric	-74.88287 40.26384
36BU0152	Prehistoric	-74.92549 40.32655	36BU0333	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.87036 40.29454
36BU0153	Prehistoric	-74.92784 40.32664	36BU0334	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.87112 40.29493
36BU0154	Prehistoric	-74.93559 40.33269	36BU0362	Prehistoric	-74.92135 40.3146
36BU0155	Prehistoric	-74.94292 40.33806	36BU0363	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.9181 40.31267
36BU0156	Prehistoric	-74.92538 40.3244	36BU0364	Prehistoric	-74.92023 40.31365
36BU0157	Prehistoric	-74.94378 40.33167	36BU0367	Prehistoric	-74.90932 40.26832
36BU0166	Prehistoric	-75.01464 40.31534	36BU0370	Prehistoric	-74.99064 40.35523

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36BU0187	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.93269 40.33051	36BU0371	Prehistoric	-74.89725 40.27113
36BU0188	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.8713 40.29332	36BU0378	Prehistoric	-74.85233 40.25643
36BU0190	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.86942 40.294	36BU0379	Prehistoric	-74.85016 40.2573
36BU0269	Prehistoric	-74.92881 40.31616	36BU0382	Prehistoric	-75.0071 40.36339
36BU0278	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.86986 40.2945	36BU0407	Prehistoric	-74.87761 40.29783
36BU0286	Prehistoric	-75.0414 40.40737	36BU0418	Prehistoric	-74.90146 40.2686
36BU0287	Prehistoric	-75.04156 40.40798	36BU0422	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.90271 40.27037
36BU0302	Prehistoric	-75.07142 40.3658	36BU0423	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.89877 40.26784
36BU0303	Prehistoric	-75.07045 40.36559			
Watershed 79-Piedmont-Piedmont Upland:					
36BU0322	Prehistoric	-74.87303 40.1946	36BU0323	Prehistoric	-74.86868 40.20067
Watershed 80-Piedmont-Gettysburg-Newark Lowland:					
36BU0009	Prehistoric	-75.19337 40.3472	36BU0226	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.08309 40.23779
36BU0010	Prehistoric	-75.20931 40.30573	36BU0227	Prehistoric	-75.08682 40.23845
36BU0011	Prehistoric	-75.13851 40.28477	36BU0228	Prehistoric	-75.08946 40.23333
36BU0012	Prehistoric	-75.17252 40.28996	36BU0233	Prehistoric	-75.15531 40.23279
36BU0024	Prehistoric	-75.09829 40.29014	36BU0234	Prehistoric	-75.11895 40.37604
36BU0043	Prehistoric	-75.00612 40.24685	36BU0235	Prehistoric	-75.11893 40.37271
36BU0045	Prehistoric	-75.04733 40.21331	36BU0236	Prehistoric	-75.02546 40.25974
36BU0046	Prehistoric	-75.05737 40.23323	36BU0239	Prehistoric	-75.1555 40.29009
36BU0047	Prehistoric	-75.04873 40.23886	36BU0240	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.16424 40.2861
36BU0049	Prehistoric	-75.09332 40.27657	36BU0241	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.18181 40.28018
36BU0050	Prehistoric	-75.0114 40.2522	36BU0242	Prehistoric	-75.20242 40.26834
36BU0051	Prehistoric	-75.00746 40.2503	36BU0243	Prehistoric	-75.1844 40.2768
36BU0052	Prehistoric	-75.00743 40.25113	36BU0268	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.96036 40.22515
36BU0053	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.24106 40.28201	36BU0273	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.17411 40.28344
36BU0054	Prehistoric	-75.24119 40.28012	36BU0274	Prehistoric	-75.17603 40.28263
36BU0055	Prehistoric	-75.23326 40.28182	36BU0275	Prehistoric	-75.17797 40.28205
36BU0056	Prehistoric	-75.22618 40.28473	36BU0276	Prehistoric	-75.15258 40.28999
36BU0059	Prehistoric	-75.03484 40.25043	36BU0277	Prehistoric	-75.15048 40.28996
36BU0061	Prehistoric	-74.97072 40.2352	36BU0281	Prehistoric	-75.0842 40.23275
36BU0081	Prehistoric	-75.05097 40.23692	36BU0289	Prehistoric	-75.18126 40.26599
36BU0092	Prehistoric	-75.00392 40.25067	36BU0290	Prehistoric	-75.18778 40.27215
36BU0093	Prehistoric	-75.09559 40.27767	36BU0292	Prehistoric	-75.04903 40.30531
36BU0096	Prehistoric	-75.07286 40.22034	36BU0293	Prehistoric	-75.04876 40.30388
36BU0097	Prehistoric	-75.07391 40.2191	36BU0294	Prehistoric	-75.04651 40.29905
36BU0098	Prehistoric	-75.07473 40.22042	36BU0296	Prehistoric	-75.06524 40.34471
36BU0099	Prehistoric	-75.07087 40.22544	36BU0297	Prehistoric	-75.06359 40.35044
36BU0100	Prehistoric	-75.10773 40.23354	36BU0299	Prehistoric	-75.13429 40.22938
36BU0106	Prehistoric	-75.1368 40.22324	36BU0300	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.13341 40.22889
36BU0107	Prehistoric	-74.98444 40.24639	36BU0301	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.09223 40.23615
36BU0108	Prehistoric	-74.98375 40.24693	36BU0306	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.0627 40.26409
36BU0109	Prehistoric	-75.09975 40.27485	36BU0316	Prehistoric	-75.15467 40.22408
36BU0110	Prehistoric	-75.07206 40.23486	36BU0317	Prehistoric	-75.21556 40.28729
36BU0111	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.94493 40.19717	36BU0321	Prehistoric	-75.13298 40.30176
36BU0132	Prehistoric	-75.07696 40.26968	36BU0339	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.10411 40.23444
36BU0133	Prehistoric	-75.12121 40.23151	36BU0340	Prehistoric	-75.17313 40.33353
36BU0139	Prehistoric	-74.97757 40.24338	36BU0372	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.89826 40.26455
36BU0140	Prehistoric	-74.97729 40.23704	36BU0374	Prehistoric	-75.08025 40.23449
36BU0141	Prehistoric	-74.96958 40.23279	36BU0383	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.1903 40.27177
36BU0142	Prehistoric	-74.98484 40.22498	36BU0384	Prehistoric	-75.07263 40.298

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36BU0143	Prehistoric	-74.97537 40.2239	36BU0385	Prehistoric	-75.07755 40.29854
36BU0163	Prehistoric	-75.003 40.2494	36BU0386	Prehistoric	-75.08053 40.30071
36BU0164	Prehistoric	-74.93169 40.24646	36BU0402	Prehistoric	-75.17321 40.28271
36BU0174	Prehistoric	-75.11041 40.22036	36BU0425	Prehistoric	-75.1394 40.2905
36BU0182	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.1135 40.21839	36BU0426	Prehistoric	-75.14126 40.28757
36BU0185	Prehistoric	-75.2043 40.2924	36MG0072	Prehistoric	-75.19972 40.19362
36BU0193	Prehistoric	-75.0689 40.31076	36MG0167	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.15325 40.21679
36BU0194	Prehistoric	-75.05481 40.32404	36MG0189	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.16102 40.2182
36BU0195	Prehistoric	-75.05658 40.32022	36MG0222	Prehistoric	-75.25273 40.25796
36BU0197	Prehistoric	-75.14277 40.22482	36MG0244	Prehistoric	-75.24635 40.22933
36BU0201	Prehistoric	-74.92584 40.19159	36MG0254	Prehistoric	-75.19476 40.19548
36BU0202	Prehistoric	-74.93019 40.18864	36MG0266	Prehistoric	-75.23066 40.2387
36BU0205	Prehistoric	-74.9668 40.23882	36MG0267	Prehistoric	-75.23275 40.23995
36BU0208	Prehistoric	-75.04252 40.24466	36MG0268	Prehistoric	-75.23481 40.23385
36BU0212	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.02027 40.28238	36MG0287	Prehistoric	-75.19742 40.21795
36BU0218	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.09752 40.3462	36MG0295	Prehistoric	-75.24 40.23044
36BU0219	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.09874 40.34581	36MG0296	Prehistoric	-75.23913 40.23057
36BU0220	Prehistoric	-75.05234 40.30928	36MG0297	Prehistoric	-75.23549 40.23266
36BU0222	Prehistoric	-75.07239 40.23817	36MG0298	Prehistoric	-75.23715 40.23152
36BU0223	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.07341 40.23333	36MG0299	Prehistoric	-75.21621 40.24877
36BU0224	Prehistoric	-75.0713 40.232	36MG0307	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.2393 40.22837
36BU0225	Prehistoric	-75.07897 40.23724			
Watershed 80-Piedmont-Piedmont Upland:					
36BU0057	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.97469 40.16488	36BU0341	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.04158 40.15383
36BU0058	Prehistoric	-74.96668 40.17206	36BU0365	Prehistoric	-74.95304 40.14616
36BU0173	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.96662 40.17053	36BU0366	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.95052 40.14726
36BU0214	Prehistoric	-74.96836 40.16993	36BU0433	Prehistoric	-74.96803 40.17317
Watershed 85-Piedmont-Gettysburg-Newark Lowland:					
36BK0580	Prehistoric	-75.88234 40.16501	36LA0904	Prehistoric	-76.24597 40.24368
36BK0582	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.03205 40.26401	36LA0906	Prehistoric	-76.18435 40.24643
36BK0587	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.88993 40.16285	36LA0919	Prehistoric	-76.17855 40.27373
36BK0588	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.88668 40.16811	36LA0922	Prehistoric	-76.13102 40.16823
36BK0589	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.88987 40.16476	36LA0926	Prehistoric	-76.11085 40.20051
36BK0597	Prehistoric	-75.88632 40.16489	36LA0928	Prehistoric	-76.09112 40.2109
36BK0601	Prehistoric	-75.95365 40.20338	36LA0942	Prehistoric	-76.01734 40.21198
36BK0602	Prehistoric	-75.94484 40.18627	36LA0946	Prehistoric	-76.17837 40.16638
36BK0619	Prehistoric	-75.89568 40.16975	36LA0947	Prehistoric	-76.14103 40.16927
36BK0620	Prehistoric	-75.90141 40.16815	36LA0950	Prehistoric	-76.2558 40.24209
36BK0653	Prehistoric	-75.88395 40.16246	36LA0953	Prehistoric	-76.11435 40.17545
36BK0663	Prehistoric	-76.03065 40.25527	36LA0954	Prehistoric	-76.15997 40.27801
36BK0664	Prehistoric	-76.03208 40.25426	36LA0965	Prehistoric	-76.07914 40.16409
36BK0665	Prehistoric	-76.03502 40.24958	36LA0966	Prehistoric	-76.14192 40.26337
36BK0697	Prehistoric	-76.03487 40.25049	36LA0996	Prehistoric	-76.10016 40.18096
36LA0073	Prehistoric	-76.19181 40.16519	36LA1001	Prehistoric	-76.13747 40.24318
36LA0078	Prehistoric	-76.17341 40.15874	36LA1009	Prehistoric	-76.12507 40.28678
36LA0083	Prehistoric	-76.12254 40.17036	36LA1010	Prehistoric	-76.15429 40.16668
36LA0094	Prehistoric	-76.01216 40.16941	36LA1027	Prehistoric	-76.00979 40.18098
36LA0095	Prehistoric	-76.06973 40.21926	36LA1028	Prehistoric	-76.00213 40.18914
36LA0131	Prehistoric	-76.08839 40.2083	36LA1031	Prehistoric	-76.09472 40.16947
36LA0132	Prehistoric	-76.09343 40.17943	36LA1032	Prehistoric	-76.09095 40.16826
36LA0134	Prehistoric	-76.12004 40.16986	36LA1033	Prehistoric	-76.09484 40.17198

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LA0135	Prehistoric	-76.14226 40.24235	36LA1039	Prehistoric	-76.06902 40.15768
36LA0163	Prehistoric	-76.08533 40.25854	36LA1040	Prehistoric	-76.06713 40.15587
36LA0164	Prehistoric	-76.0325 40.23882	36LA1105	Prehistoric	-76.0235 40.18653
36LA0165	Prehistoric	-76.05035 40.19936	36LA1149	Prehistoric	-76.13623 40.24387
36LA0335	Prehistoric	-76.03673 40.18134	36LA1150	Prehistoric	-76.13934 40.24289
36LA0336	Prehistoric	-76.08963 40.20235	36LA1187	Prehistoric	-76.09672 40.2297
36LA0337	Prehistoric	-76.08858 40.20123	36LA1188	Prehistoric	-76.09931 40.22982
36LA0338	Prehistoric	-76.08648 40.19875	36LA1189	Prehistoric	-76.09763 40.23136
36LA0339	Prehistoric	-76.02749 40.17512	36LA1190	Prehistoric	-76.10093 40.22861
36LA0344	Prehistoric	-76.04948 40.17638	36LA1191	Prehistoric	-76.10194 40.22733
36LA0345	Prehistoric	-76.20449 40.27248	36LA1192	Prehistoric	-76.09672 40.22829
36LA0346	Prehistoric	-76.1914 40.27161	36LA1194	Prehistoric	-76.18844 40.16039
36LA0347	Prehistoric	-76.17479 40.27697	36LA1237	Prehistoric	-76.13254 40.16765
36LA0348	Prehistoric	-76.21678 40.2504	36LA1242	Prehistoric	-76.0924 40.20213
36LA0349	Prehistoric	-76.21481 40.27034	36LA1243	Prehistoric	-76.08561 40.20621
36LA0352	Prehistoric	-76.07485 40.24065	36LA1244	Prehistoric	-76.07738 40.18819
36LA0353	Prehistoric	-76.08711 40.17061	36LA1247	Prehistoric	-76.08226 40.17161
36LA0353	Prehistoric	-76.08712 40.17102	36LA1405	Prehistoric	-76.03337 40.17542
36LA0354	Prehistoric	-76.14445 40.25977	36LA1406	Prehistoric	-76.01926 40.18819
36LA0355	Prehistoric	-76.21081 40.27407	36LA1407	Prehistoric	-75.97522 40.15425
36LA0365	Prehistoric	-76.19001 40.16174	36LA1408	Prehistoric	-76.11084 40.25444
36LA0366	Prehistoric	-76.13294 40.18044	36LA1411	Prehistoric	-76.22061 40.28637
36LA0367	Prehistoric	-76.1249 40.18059	36LA1412	Prehistoric	-76.22214 40.2841
36LA0380	Prehistoric	-76.11866 40.17812	36LA1413	Prehistoric	-76.22338 40.2864
36LA0382	Prehistoric	-76.07518 40.17749	36LA1414	Prehistoric	-76.20989 40.28898
36LA0383	Prehistoric	-76.05307 40.17557	36LA1415	Prehistoric	-76.21165 40.28031
36LA0384	Prehistoric	-76.11789 40.17224	36LA1474	Prehistoric	-76.06632 40.19224
36LA0385	Prehistoric	-76.0573 40.17943	36LA1477	Prehistoric	-76.12931 40.16604
36LA0388	Prehistoric	-76.09807 40.18181	36LE0216	Prehistoric	-76.28306 40.26959
36LA0389	Prehistoric	-76.08393 40.18064	36LE0336	Prehistoric	-76.24651 40.28976
36LA0390	Prehistoric	-76.09325 40.18164	36LE0337	Prehistoric	-76.2421 40.28257
36LA0392	Prehistoric	-76.0566 40.1981	36LE0356	Prehistoric	-76.21994 40.29623
36LA0881	Prehistoric	-76.07182 40.17895	36LE0372	Prehistoric	-76.28782 40.27161
36LA0882	Prehistoric	-76.04285 40.18266	36LE0394	Prehistoric	-76.28904 40.27161
36LA0899	Prehistoric	-76.13254 40.17207	36LE0397	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.30539 40.28407
36LA0902	Prehistoric	-76.23953 40.23963	36LE0398	Prehistoric	-76.25389 40.29518
36LA0903	Prehistoric	-76.24404 40.24399			
Watershed 85-Piedmont-Piedmont Lowland:					
36BK0581	Prehistoric	-75.88098 40.16107	36LA0709	Prehistoric	-76.30317 40.1161
36BK0626	Prehistoric	-75.88546 40.16076	36LA0710	Prehistoric	-76.30466 40.11556
36BK0627	Prehistoric	-75.88978 40.16209	36LA0711	Prehistoric	-76.30467 40.11661
36BK0628	Prehistoric	-75.88891 40.16217	36LA0712	Prehistoric	-76.30627 40.11622
36BK0629	Prehistoric	-75.88603 40.16189	36LA0713	Prehistoric	-76.30815 40.11598
36BK0869	Prehistoric	-75.88206 40.14594	36LA0714	Prehistoric	-76.31036 40.11665
36LA/92	Prehistoric	-76.24585 40.05816	36LA0715	Prehistoric	-76.31198 40.11599
36LA0001	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.38417 39.9444	36LA0716	Prehistoric	-76.31305 40.11538
36LA0024	Prehistoric	-75.92255 40.13547	36LA0717	Prehistoric	-76.31467 40.11581
36LA0025	Prehistoric	-75.90529 40.1387	36LA0718	Prehistoric	-76.31449 40.11492
36LA0026	Prehistoric	-75.95408 40.13004	36LA0719	Prehistoric	-76.31367 40.11415
36LA0044	Prehistoric	-75.97533 40.12876	36LA0720	Prehistoric	-76.31487 40.11379
36LA0049	Prehistoric	-76.36748 39.96077	36LA0721	Prehistoric	-76.31572 40.11342
36LA0052	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.405 39.96275	36LA0722	Prehistoric	-76.31633 40.11504

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LA0053	Prehistoric	-76.41339 39.96556	36LA0723	Prehistoric	-76.31763 40.1135
36LA0055	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.39709 39.95231	36LA0724	Prehistoric	-76.31282 40.11342
36LA0058	Prehistoric	-76.30632 39.99958	36LA0725	Prehistoric	-76.31037 40.11458
36LA0059	Prehistoric	-75.97214 40.13948	36LA0726	Prehistoric	-76.30798 40.11444
36LA0071	Prehistoric	-75.99066 40.1061	36LA0727	Prehistoric	-76.30743 40.11314
36LA0072	Prehistoric	-76.11298 40.15491	36LA0728	Prehistoric	-76.30597 40.11264
36LA0074	Prehistoric	-76.08862 40.14771	36LA0729	Prehistoric	-76.30855 40.11249
36LA0075	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.96741 40.13861	36LA0730	Prehistoric	-76.30964 40.11298
36LA0077	Prehistoric	-76.22569 40.09429	36LA0731	Prehistoric	-76.31051 40.11336
36LA0079	Prehistoric	-76.17562 40.13701	36LA0732	Prehistoric	-76.31104 40.11227
36LA0080	Prehistoric	-76.15778 40.14187	36LA0733	Prehistoric	-76.30988 40.11212
36LA0081	Prehistoric	-76.11179 40.16119	36LA0734	Prehistoric	-76.30688 40.1115
36LA0082	Prehistoric	-76.0066 40.11213	36LA0735	Prehistoric	-76.30706 40.10963
36LA0085	Prehistoric	-76.10757 40.16327	36LA0736	Prehistoric	-76.30639 40.10818
36LA0086	Prehistoric	-76.10843 40.16491	36LA0737	Prehistoric	-76.30693 40.10642
36LA0087	Prehistoric	-76.10792 40.15975	36LA0738	Prehistoric	-76.30924 40.10625
36LA0088	Prehistoric	-76.18247 40.12945	36LA0739	Prehistoric	-76.30827 40.10755
36LA0089	Prehistoric	-75.95988 40.15003	36LA0740	Prehistoric	-76.30937 40.10996
36LA0090	Prehistoric	-75.96274 40.1391	36LA0741	Prehistoric	-76.30863 40.11106
36LA0096	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.28477 40.01883	36LA0742	Prehistoric	-76.30992 40.1113
36LA0100	Prehistoric	-76.20144 40.17935	36LA0743	Prehistoric	-76.31148 40.11052
36LA0104	Prehistoric	-76.16058 40.14178	36LA0744	Prehistoric	-76.31098 40.11142
36LA0105	Prehistoric	-76.31303 39.99931	36LA0745	Prehistoric	-76.31082 40.10728
36LA0106	Prehistoric	-76.12652 40.14145	36LA0746	Prehistoric	-76.31101 40.10893
36LA0108	Prehistoric	-76.11923 40.15414	36LA0747	Prehistoric	-76.31344 40.10879
36LA0109	Prehistoric	-76.00915 40.10942	36LA0748	Prehistoric	-76.31262 40.10797
36LA0110	Prehistoric	-76.13795 40.15195	36LA0749	Prehistoric	-76.31372 40.10644
36LA0112	Prehistoric	-76.11766 40.15934	36LA0750	Prehistoric	-76.31416 40.10726
36LA0113	Prehistoric	-76.20285 40.1654	36LA0751	Prehistoric	-76.31584 40.10896
36LA0114	Prehistoric	-76.20327 40.16885	36LA0752	Prehistoric	-76.31208 40.11127
36LA0116	Prehistoric	-76.21824 40.1131	36LA0753	Prehistoric	-76.314 40.11242
36LA0119	Prehistoric	-76.19652 40.18518	36LA0754	Prehistoric	-76.31553 40.11236
36LA0125	Prehistoric	-76.1368 40.19216	36LA0755	Prehistoric	-76.31705 40.11213
36LA0126	Prehistoric	-76.15819 40.1581	36LA0756	Prehistoric	-76.3137 40.11126
36LA0127	Prehistoric	-76.17623 40.11663	36LA0757	Prehistoric	-76.31676 40.11088
36LA0128	Prehistoric	-76.15206 40.1199	36LA0758	Prehistoric	-76.31791 40.11037
36LA0129	Prehistoric	-76.00375 40.10491	36LA0759	Prehistoric	-76.3172 40.10888
36LA0130	Prehistoric	-76.07853 40.14518	36LA0760	Prehistoric	-76.31844 40.11143
36LA0133	Prehistoric	-76.08189 40.13374	36LA0761	Prehistoric	-76.32005 40.11041
36LA0151	Prehistoric	-76.26618 40.05798	36LA0761	Prehistoric	-76.31515 40.10652
36LA0152	Prehistoric	-76.2674 40.0562	36LA0762	Prehistoric	-76.31647 40.10726
36LA0153	Prehistoric	-76.26871 40.04475	36LA0763	Prehistoric	-76.3144 40.10515
36LA0154	Prehistoric	-76.27778 40.0158	36LA0764	Prehistoric	-76.31583 40.10537
36LA0155	Prehistoric	-76.23038 40.0706	36LA0765	Prehistoric	-76.31714 40.1059
36LA0156	Prehistoric	-76.22593 40.07056	36LA0766	Prehistoric	-76.31769 40.10713
36LA0157	Prehistoric	-76.24837 40.05661	36LA0767	Prehistoric	-76.3183 40.10784
36LA0158	Prehistoric	-76.24677 40.05652	36LA0768	Prehistoric	-76.31944 40.10818
36LA0159	Prehistoric	-76.24533 40.0591	36LA0769	Prehistoric	-76.32022 40.10909
36LA0160	Prehistoric	-76.22871 40.05043	36LA0770	Prehistoric	-76.32179 40.1098
36LA0161	Prehistoric	-76.20253 40.07485	36LA0771	Prehistoric	-76.32127 40.10882
36LA0166	Prehistoric	-76.00636 40.14857	36LA0772	Prehistoric	-76.32079 40.10794
36LA0167	Prehistoric	-76.16301 40.13694	36LA0773	Prehistoric	-76.32252 40.10864

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LA0171	Prehistoric	-76.2673 40.04814	36LA0774	Prehistoric	-76.32205 40.10762
36LA0177	Prehistoric	-76.36844 40.06053	36LA0775	Prehistoric	-76.32097 40.1069
36LA0193	Prehistoric	-76.27091 40.04984	36LA0776	Prehistoric	-76.31908 40.10634
36LA0194	Prehistoric	-76.25677 40.0578	36LA0778	Prehistoric	-76.27096 40.02918
36LA0195	Prehistoric	-76.26788 40.05473	36LA0779	Prehistoric	-76.27068 40.02777
36LA0196	Prehistoric	-76.26967 40.05484	36LA0780	Prehistoric	-76.26952 40.02748
36LA0197	Prehistoric	-76.26822 40.05806	36LA0781	Prehistoric	-76.26864 40.02678
36LA0198	Prehistoric	-76.26368 40.05649	36LA0782	Prehistoric	-76.26728 40.02599
36LA0199	Prehistoric	-76.26478 40.05349	36LA0783	Prehistoric	-76.26761 40.02679
36LA0206	Prehistoric	-76.42564 39.95926	36LA0784	Prehistoric	-76.26841 40.02577
36LA0207	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.35316 39.98636	36LA0785	Prehistoric	-76.26942 40.02548
36LA0208	Prehistoric	-76.30157 40.00369	36LA0786	Prehistoric	-76.27051 40.02528
36LA0222	Prehistoric	-76.25015 40.05879	36LA0787	Prehistoric	-76.27195 40.02465
36LA0223	Prehistoric	-76.25028 40.05698	36LA0788	Prehistoric	-76.27382 40.02347
36LA0224	Prehistoric	-76.2649 40.06158	36LA0789	Prehistoric	-76.26887 40.02386
36LA0240	Prehistoric	-76.22989 40.11396	36LA0790	Prehistoric	-76.26657 40.02422
36LA0243	Prehistoric	-76.27228 40.0431	36LA0791	Prehistoric	-76.26625 40.02327
36LA0247	Prehistoric	-76.29079 40.20447	36LA0792	Prehistoric	-76.25918 40.03958
36LA0248	Prehistoric	-76.40825 39.95591	36LA0793	Prehistoric	-76.25873 40.03827
36LA0252	Prehistoric	-76.37911 39.9454	36LA0794	Prehistoric	-76.25642 40.0389
36LA0257	Prehistoric	-76.19171 40.13199	36LA0795	Prehistoric	-76.2573 40.0379
36LA0258	Prehistoric	-76.20101 40.23577	36LA0796	Prehistoric	-76.25632 40.03712
36LA0277	Prehistoric	-75.97942 40.12504	36LA0797	Prehistoric	-76.20735 40.06887
36LA0280	Prehistoric	-76.25224 40.05654	36LA0798	Prehistoric	-76.20843 40.06958
36LA0281	Prehistoric	-76.24986 40.05378	36LA0799	Prehistoric	-76.20676 40.0708
36LA0282	Prehistoric	-76.25167 40.0506	36LA0800	Prehistoric	-76.20726 40.07187
36LA0283	Prehistoric	-76.24914 40.05525	36LA0801	Prehistoric	-76.2082 40.07506
36LA0284	Prehistoric	-76.25482 40.0563	36LA0802	Prehistoric	-76.20962 40.07234
36LA0285	Prehistoric	-76.25289 40.05457	36LA0803	Prehistoric	-76.21007 40.07055
36LA0286	Prehistoric	-76.25309 40.05945	36LA0804	Prehistoric	-76.21144 40.07143
36LA0287	Prehistoric	-76.25133 40.06558	36LA0805	Prehistoric	-76.21155 40.07337
36LA0288	Prehistoric	-76.25055 40.06044	36LA0806	Prehistoric	-76.21283 40.07461
36LA0289	Prehistoric	-76.30162 40.11207	36LA0807	Prehistoric	-76.21305 40.07347
36LA0290	Prehistoric	-76.2707 40.05811	36LA0808	Prehistoric	-76.21333 40.07143
36LA0291	Prehistoric	-76.27101 40.05498	36LA0809	Prehistoric	-76.2126 40.06942
36LA0292	Prehistoric	-76.27739 40.02226	36LA0810	Prehistoric	-76.21451 40.06794
36LA0293	Prehistoric	-76.27099 40.053	36LA0811	Prehistoric	-76.21502 40.07013
36LA0294	Prehistoric	-76.26853 40.05365	36LA0812	Prehistoric	-76.21547 40.07189
36LA0295	Prehistoric	-76.25869 40.05487	36LA0813	Prehistoric	-76.21456 40.07394
36LA0296	Prehistoric	-76.27828 40.05095	36LA0814	Prehistoric	-76.21692 40.07245
36LA0297	Prehistoric	-76.24698 40.10452	36LA0815	Prehistoric	-76.21767 40.07394
36LA0298	Prehistoric	-76.13342 40.07492	36LA0816	Prehistoric	-76.21894 40.0753
36LA0299	Prehistoric	-76.20802 40.05205	36LA0817	Prehistoric	-76.2224 40.07315
36LA0300	Prehistoric	-76.17298 40.09931	36LA0876	Prehistoric	-75.96777 40.14725
36LA0301	Prehistoric	-76.22306 40.06148	36LA0892	Prehistoric	-76.24895 39.99817
36LA0302	Prehistoric	-76.2395 40.02986	36LA0893	Prehistoric	-76.24721 39.99106
36LA0303	Prehistoric	-76.1563 40.06145	36LA0894	Prehistoric	-76.26221 40.00003
36LA0304	Prehistoric	-76.24603 40.06185	36LA0895	Prehistoric	-76.26523 39.99786
36LA0305	Prehistoric	-76.24712 40.06428	36LA0896	Prehistoric	-76.26872 39.98864
36LA0306	Prehistoric	-76.22129 40.0531	36LA0897	Prehistoric	-76.26433 39.98281
36LA0307	Prehistoric	-76.22343 40.04949	36LA0898	Prehistoric	-76.27746 40.0341
36LA0308	Prehistoric	-76.24794 40.05197	36LA0900	Prehistoric	-76.12994 40.2013

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LA0309	Prehistoric	-76.28223 40.19837	36LA0901	Prehistoric	-76.2193 40.17024
36LA0310	Prehistoric	-75.96718 40.13002	36LA0905	Prehistoric	-76.24004 40.18473
36LA0311	Prehistoric	-75.93876 40.14746	36LA0907	Prehistoric	-76.23949 40.17869
36LA0312	Prehistoric	-75.91624 40.15382	36LA0908	Prehistoric	-76.14661 40.14253
36LA0313	Prehistoric	-75.94836 40.14526	36LA0909	Prehistoric	-76.24618 40.20272
36LA0314	Prehistoric	-75.93438 40.15122	36LA0910	Prehistoric	-76.17095 40.13557
36LA0315	Prehistoric	-75.90595 40.13743	36LA0911	Prehistoric	-76.17228 40.1405
36LA0316	Prehistoric	-75.93737 40.13399	36LA0914	Prehistoric	-76.23443 40.12285
36LA0317	Prehistoric	-75.91508 40.15575	36LA0915	Prehistoric	-76.20613 40.09716
36LA0318	Prehistoric	-76.09021 40.07926	36LA0916	Prehistoric	-76.22694 40.10948
36LA0319	Prehistoric	-76.07883 40.10907	36LA0917	Prehistoric	-76.0089 40.10561
36LA0320	Prehistoric	-76.09187 40.10545	36LA0921	Prehistoric	-76.21401 40.14376
36LA0321	Prehistoric	-76.01334 40.11237	36LA0923	Prehistoric	-76.16149 40.13635
36LA0323	Prehistoric	-76.0139 40.11751	36LA0927	Prehistoric	-76.11467 40.16386
36LA0324	Prehistoric	-76.00754 40.10421	36LA0944	Prehistoric	-76.19525 40.1757
36LA0325	Prehistoric	-76.05519 40.12463	36LA0945	Prehistoric	-76.168 40.18795
36LA0326	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.06553 40.09235	36LA0948	Prehistoric	-76.25032 40.09815
36LA0327	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.06061 40.09527	36LA0949	Prehistoric	-76.20741 40.10641
36LA0328	Prehistoric	-76.08726 40.08306	36LA0951	Prehistoric	-76.0249 40.14018
36LA0329	Prehistoric	-76.06903 40.08489	36LA0952	Prehistoric	-76.03666 40.13944
36LA0330	Prehistoric	-76.07297 40.08608	36LA0955	Prehistoric	-76.15137 40.09732
36LA0340	Prehistoric	-76.10459 40.17443	36LA0959	Prehistoric	-75.96601 40.14943
36LA0341	Prehistoric	-76.11554 40.16906	36LA0964	Prehistoric	-76.01199 40.14668
36LA0342	Prehistoric	-76.11372 40.1673	36LA0978	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.25123 40.05725
36LA0343	Prehistoric	-76.09675 40.08566	36LA0981	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.18815 40.18336
36LA0357	Prehistoric	-76.20022 40.1773	36LA0990	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.34946 40.07382
36LA0358	Prehistoric	-76.23169 40.16627	36LA0991	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.26967 40.07686
36LA0359	Prehistoric	-76.17339 40.18919	36LA0995	Prehistoric	-76.27152 40.08329
36LA0360	Prehistoric	-76.16853 40.13783	36LA0997	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.27044 40.07877
36LA0361	Prehistoric	-76.15163 40.18964	36LA0998	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.26995 40.07916
36LA0362	Prehistoric	-76.17682 40.12915	36LA1002	Prehistoric	-76.18132 40.20244
36LA0363	Prehistoric	-76.1708 40.14288	36LA1003	Prehistoric	-76.20289 40.14207
36LA0364	Prehistoric	-76.19871 40.17694	36LA1004	Prehistoric	-76.14075 40.15217
36LA0373	Prehistoric	-76.22582 40.11226	36LA1005	Prehistoric	-76.14403 40.15106
36LA0374	Prehistoric	-76.14993 40.11811	36LA1006	Prehistoric	-76.26315 40.04692
36LA0375	Prehistoric	-76.22853 40.12466	36LA1007	Prehistoric	-76.23076 40.11686
36LA0376	Prehistoric	-76.2998 40.20662	36LA1008	Prehistoric	-76.21644 40.09965
36LA0377	Prehistoric	-76.09975 40.11182	36LA1011	Prehistoric	-76.05942 40.13758
36LA0378	Prehistoric	-76.00701 40.10752	36LA1012	Prehistoric	-76.04733 40.12584
36LA0381	Prehistoric	-76.11354 40.16464	36LA1013	Prehistoric	-76.05158 40.12791
36LA0386	Prehistoric	-76.09344 40.15123	36LA1014	Prehistoric	-76.04239 40.12981
36LA0387	Prehistoric	-76.10187 40.12652	36LA1015	Prehistoric	-76.04438 40.12649
36LA0391	Prehistoric	-76.11539 40.22388	36LA1016	Prehistoric	-76.04029 40.12638
36LA0393	Prehistoric	-76.10017 40.1533	36LA1017	Prehistoric	-76.03116 40.13887
36LA0394	Prehistoric	-76.11058 40.15082	36LA1018	Prehistoric	-76.03145 40.14088
36LA0395	Prehistoric	-76.11733 40.16846	36LA1019	Prehistoric	-76.02848 40.14276
36LA0396	Prehistoric	-76.10412 40.16862	36LA1020	Prehistoric	-76.02437 40.13274
36LA0397	Prehistoric	-76.11086 40.16934	36LA1021	Prehistoric	-76.01887 40.13453
36LA0398	Prehistoric	-76.11693 40.15357	36LA1022	Prehistoric	-76.01904 40.13677
36LA0399	Prehistoric	-76.1155 40.14767	36LA1023	Prehistoric	-76.02021 40.1377
36LA0400	Prehistoric	-76.09792 40.1518	36LA1024	Prehistoric	-76.02184 40.13516
36LA0401	Prehistoric	-76.04264 40.13812	36LA1025	Prehistoric	-76.00361 40.13156

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LA0403	Prehistoric	-76.25982 40.06296	36LA1026	Prehistoric	-76.00539 40.1274
36LA0404	Prehistoric	-76.26243 40.06089	36LA1029	Prehistoric	-76.10932 40.13768
36LA0405	Prehistoric	-76.25839 40.06095	36LA1030	Prehistoric	-76.0994 40.12716
36LA0406	Prehistoric	-76.25809 40.06934	36LA1034	Prehistoric	-76.09289 40.15907
36LA0407	Prehistoric	-76.25356 40.06958	36LA1035	Prehistoric	-76.08902 40.15672
36LA0408	Prehistoric	-76.25423 40.06156	36LA1037	Prehistoric	-76.09288 40.12705
36LA0409	Prehistoric	-76.25436 40.07127	36LA1038	Prehistoric	-76.07947 40.1463
36LA0410	Prehistoric	-76.26193 40.07214	36LA1041	Prehistoric	-75.99464 40.12044
36LA0411	Prehistoric	-76.29227 40.09521	36LA1042	Prehistoric	-75.99697 40.12098
36LA0412	Prehistoric	-76.29376 40.09466	36LA1043	Prehistoric	-75.99904 40.11964
36LA0413	Prehistoric	-76.29662 40.09588	36LA1044	Prehistoric	-75.99496 40.12197
36LA0414	Prehistoric	-76.29822 40.09519	36LA1045	Prehistoric	-75.99687 40.12288
36LA0415	Prehistoric	-76.29884 40.09619	36LA1046	Prehistoric	-75.98682 40.1202
36LA0416	Prehistoric	-76.30468 40.11359	36LA1047	Prehistoric	-75.98514 40.1182
36LA0417	Prehistoric	-76.30458 40.10949	36LA1048	Prehistoric	-75.9883 40.11666
36LA0418	Prehistoric	-76.3358 40.05949	36LA1049	Prehistoric	-76.10575 40.12193
36LA0419	Prehistoric	-76.33916 40.05765	36LA1050	Prehistoric	-76.10923 40.1236
36LA0420	Prehistoric	-76.33611 40.05749	36LA1051	Prehistoric	-76.10049 40.11263
36LA0421	Prehistoric	-76.27248 40.036	36LA1052	Prehistoric	-76.097 40.11304
36LA0422	Prehistoric	-76.27219 40.03304	36LA1053	Prehistoric	-76.09495 40.1116
36LA0423	Prehistoric	-76.27119 40.03094	36LA1054	Prehistoric	-76.09479 40.11516
36LA0424	Prehistoric	-76.27283 40.02985	36LA1055	Prehistoric	-76.09266 40.11371
36LA0425	Prehistoric	-76.27228 40.02813	36LA1056	Prehistoric	-76.06513 40.12223
36LA0426	Prehistoric	-76.27184 40.02707	36LA1057	Prehistoric	-76.06637 40.12117
36LA0427	Prehistoric	-76.14694 40.10852	36LA1058	Prehistoric	-76.0706 40.12119
36LA0428	Prehistoric	-75.9889 40.14683	36LA1059	Prehistoric	-76.07062 40.11633
36LA0429	Prehistoric	-76.0165 40.11713	36LA1060	Prehistoric	-76.03605 40.11216
36LA0433	Prehistoric	-76.27675 40.053	36LA1061	Prehistoric	-76.04146 40.11215
36LA0435	Prehistoric	-76.08855 40.1079	36LA1062	Prehistoric	-76.04281 40.11068
36LA0436	Prehistoric	-76.08314 40.08303	36LA1063	Prehistoric	-76.03091 40.10542
36LA0439	Prehistoric	-76.24578 40.05705	36LA1064	Prehistoric	-76.03036 40.10744
36LA0440	Prehistoric	-76.24484 40.05599	36LA1065	Prehistoric	-76.03382 40.10291
36LA0441	Prehistoric	-76.24104 40.05532	36LA1066	Prehistoric	-76.03512 40.10714
36LA0442	Prehistoric	-76.2389 40.05562	36LA1067	Prehistoric	-76.02571 40.11997
36LA0443	Prehistoric	-76.2365 40.05627	36LA1068	Prehistoric	-76.02669 40.12319
36LA0444	Prehistoric	-76.24197 40.05313	36LA1069	Prehistoric	-75.92549 40.14011
36LA0445	Prehistoric	-76.23651 40.05458	36LA1070	Prehistoric	-75.92045 40.13924
36LA0446	Prehistoric	-76.24531 40.05239	36LA1071	Prehistoric	-75.98177 40.13314
36LA0447	Prehistoric	-76.24274 40.05231	36LA1072	Prehistoric	-75.98051 40.13423
36LA0448	Prehistoric	-76.24694 40.0496	36LA1073	Prehistoric	-75.98169 40.13483
36LA0449	Prehistoric	-76.24436 40.05044	36LA1074	Prehistoric	-76.17814 40.12932
36LA0450	Prehistoric	-76.24034 40.05192	36LA1086	Prehistoric	-76.34515 39.99218
36LA0451	Prehistoric	-76.23693 40.05252	36LA1088	Prehistoric	-76.25652 40.02023
36LA0452	Prehistoric	-76.23438 40.05335	36LA1089	Prehistoric	-76.25467 40.02023
36LA0453	Prehistoric	-76.23221 40.05238	36LA1090	Prehistoric	-76.29528 40.09625
36LA0454	Prehistoric	-76.23264 40.05489	36LA1094	Prehistoric	-76.3046 40.17007
36LA0455	Prehistoric	-76.23043 40.05344	36LA1095	Prehistoric	-76.35394 40.11892
36LA0457	Prehistoric	-76.24567 40.04804	36LA1096	Prehistoric	-76.3526 40.11767
36LA0458	Prehistoric	-76.24408 40.04849	36LA1098	Prehistoric	-76.27716 40.05058
36LA0459	Prehistoric	-76.2422 40.04935	36LA1099	Prehistoric	-76.26135 40.08484
36LA0460	Prehistoric	-76.2396 40.05027	36LA1100	Prehistoric	-76.33393 40.00992
36LA0461	Prehistoric	-76.23644 40.05078	36LA1107	Prehistoric	-76.33486 40.10534

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LA0462	Prehistoric	-76.24615 40.04583	36LA1108	Prehistoric	-76.33403 40.10283
36LA0463	Prehistoric	-76.24436 40.0463	36LA1109	Prehistoric	-76.33225 40.10291
36LA0464	Prehistoric	-76.24462 40.04504	36LA1110	Prehistoric	-76.31757 40.01285
36LA0465	Prehistoric	-76.24271 40.04617	36LA1111	Prehistoric	-76.35704 40.06301
36LA0466	Prehistoric	-76.24081 40.04791	36LA1112	Prehistoric	-76.34963 40.06439
36LA0467	Prehistoric	-76.24037 40.04361	36LA1113	Prehistoric	-76.35512 40.06529
36LA0468	Prehistoric	-76.24113 40.04489	36LA1114	Prehistoric	-76.22243 40.12826
36LA0469	Prehistoric	-76.24035 40.04593	36LA1117	Prehistoric	-76.24316 40.08405
36LA0470	Prehistoric	-76.23848 40.04593	36LA1118	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.23995 40.08315
36LA0471	Prehistoric	-76.23596 40.04788	36LA1119	Prehistoric	-76.06205 40.10025
36LA0472	Prehistoric	-76.23459 40.04867	36LA1120	Prehistoric	-76.0762 40.08723
36LA0473	Prehistoric	-76.23261 40.04893	36LA1121	Prehistoric	-76.0865 40.08552
36LA0474	Prehistoric	-76.23099 40.04957	36LA1122	Prehistoric	-76.06894 40.06481
36LA0475	Prehistoric	-76.23033 40.05056	36LA1123	Prehistoric	-76.07297 40.08763
36LA0476	Prehistoric	-76.228 40.04871	36LA1127	Prehistoric	-76.35916 39.97883
36LA0477	Prehistoric	-76.22618 40.05204	36LA1138	Prehistoric	-76.29672 40.01886
36LA0478	Prehistoric	-76.23823 40.0444	36LA1140	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.41735 39.9653
36LA0479	Prehistoric	-76.23674 40.04608	36LA1145	Prehistoric	-76.24321 40.00553
36LA0480	Prehistoric	-76.23498 40.04716	36LA1146	Prehistoric	-76.25015 40.10184
36LA0481	Prehistoric	-76.21876 40.05232	36LA1151	Prehistoric	-76.06402 40.09173
36LA0482	Prehistoric	-76.21711 40.05355	36LA1152	Prehistoric	-76.1739 40.05444
36LA0483	Prehistoric	-76.21963 40.05767	36LA1156	Prehistoric	-76.26917 40.06082
36LA0484	Prehistoric	-76.21133 40.05864	36LA1159	Prehistoric	-75.957 40.14152
36LA0485	Prehistoric	-76.20829 40.05702	36LA1160	Prehistoric	-76.38691 40.03433
36LA0486	Prehistoric	-76.20993 40.05441	36LA1161	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.09816 40.07835
36LA0487	Prehistoric	-76.20545 40.05409	36LA1162	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.42266 39.96093
36LA0488	Prehistoric	-76.20307 40.05525	36LA1163	Prehistoric	-76.06267 40.09482
36LA0489	Prehistoric	-76.24722 40.05811	36LA1168	Prehistoric	-76.4179 39.9691
36LA0490	Prehistoric	-76.24486 40.05809	36LA1169	Prehistoric	-76.41433 39.96963
36LA0491	Prehistoric	-76.24356 40.05909	36LA1170	Prehistoric	-76.41559 39.97071
36LA0492	Prehistoric	-76.24345 40.06091	36LA1171	Prehistoric	-76.41779 39.97043
36LA0493	Prehistoric	-76.24209 40.05911	36LA1172	Prehistoric	-76.32817 40.09572
36LA0494	Prehistoric	-76.24116 40.05994	36LA1174	Prehistoric	-76.41365 40.07122
36LA0495	Prehistoric	-76.23867 40.05975	36LA1175	Prehistoric	-76.31222 40.06981
36LA0496	Prehistoric	-76.23812 40.06125	36LA1176	Prehistoric	-76.27903 40.06225
36LA0497	Prehistoric	-76.24101 40.06234	36LA1177	Prehistoric	-76.24647 40.04221
36LA0498	Prehistoric	-76.23935 40.06227	36LA1178	Prehistoric	-76.27434 40.05917
36LA0499	Prehistoric	-76.24066 40.06481	36LA1179	Prehistoric	-76.2815 40.06367
36LA0500	Prehistoric	-76.23926 40.06373	36LA1180	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.34384 40.06267
36LA0501	Prehistoric	-76.23832 40.06337	36LA1193	Prehistoric	-76.18212 40.20762
36LA0502	Prehistoric	-76.23708 40.06324	36LA1195	Prehistoric	-76.16936 40.119
36LA0503	Prehistoric	-76.23536 40.06341	36LA1196	Prehistoric	-76.14817 40.11903
36LA0504	Prehistoric	-76.23871 40.06707	36LA1197	Prehistoric	-76.09451 40.12105
36LA0505	Prehistoric	-76.23655 40.06518	36LA1198	Prehistoric	-76.09673 40.1206
36LA0506	Prehistoric	-76.23387 40.0656	36LA1199	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.09727 40.12208
36LA0507	Prehistoric	-76.23523 40.06761	36LA1200	Prehistoric	-76.09383 40.11885
36LA0508	Prehistoric	-76.2352 40.06992	36LA1201	Prehistoric	-76.09504 40.1195
36LA0509	Prehistoric	-76.23485 40.07165	36LA1202	Prehistoric	-76.0932 40.12053
36LA0510	Prehistoric	-76.2341 40.06833	36LA1203	Prehistoric	-76.09896 40.12415
36LA0511	Prehistoric	-76.23235 40.07013	36LA1204	Prehistoric	-76.01228 40.10569
36LA0512	Prehistoric	-76.23222 40.06733	36LA1205	Prehistoric	-76.11306 40.16853
36LA0513	Prehistoric	-76.23031 40.06755	36LA1206	Prehistoric	-76.11447 40.1699

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LA0514	Prehistoric	-76.2281 40.06249	36LA1207	Prehistoric	-76.10035 40.12556
36LA0515	Prehistoric	-76.22517 40.06293	36LA1208	Prehistoric	-76.11254 40.15136
36LA0516	Prehistoric	-76.23327 40.05812	36LA1209	Prehistoric	-76.1226 40.15378
36LA0517	Prehistoric	-76.22852 40.06005	36LA1211	Prehistoric	-76.08564 40.08424
36LA0518	Prehistoric	-76.22671 40.05804	36LA1212	Prehistoric	-76.08262 40.08395
36LA0519	Prehistoric	-76.221 40.07109	36LA1213	Prehistoric	-76.06778 40.09198
36LA0520	Prehistoric	-76.22122 40.06931	36LA1214	Prehistoric	-76.06731 40.06363
36LA0521	Prehistoric	-76.21815 40.06774	36LA1215	Prehistoric	-76.33042 39.97137
36LA0522	Prehistoric	-76.21726 40.07025	36LA1217	Prehistoric	-76.41473 39.95952
36LA0617	Prehistoric	-76.24856 40.09466	36LA1219	Prehistoric	-76.27364 40.08219
36LA0618	Prehistoric	-76.24844 40.09309	36LA1222	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.16337 40.19597
36LA0619	Prehistoric	-76.24808 40.09186	36LA1223	Prehistoric	-76.34645 39.99725
36LA0620	Prehistoric	-76.2466 40.08918	36LA1229	Prehistoric	-76.07278 40.06613
36LA0621	Prehistoric	-76.24274 40.08873	36LA1230	Prehistoric	-75.99115 40.13719
36LA0622	Prehistoric	-76.24495 40.08989	36LA1235	Prehistoric	-76.13106 40.20714
36LA0623	Prehistoric	-76.24552 40.0919	36LA1236	Prehistoric	-76.16185 40.19429
36LA0624	Prehistoric	-76.24586 40.09393	36LA1245	Prehistoric	-76.11134 40.1632
36LA0625	Prehistoric	-76.24378 40.09383	36LA1246	Prehistoric	-76.07701 40.14923
36LA0626	Prehistoric	-76.24266 40.09215	36LA1248	Prehistoric	-76.2039 40.12034
36LA0627	Prehistoric	-76.24055 40.08992	36LA1249	Prehistoric	-75.89437 40.14091
36LA0628	Prehistoric	-76.23876 40.08923	36LA1250	Prehistoric	-75.93683 40.14595
36LA0629	Prehistoric	-76.23815 40.08783	36LA1260	Prehistoric	-76.2153 40.05396
36LA0630	Prehistoric	-76.23607 40.08852	36LA1261	Prehistoric	-76.05079 40.06101
36LA0631	Prehistoric	-76.23529 40.08967	36LA1262	Prehistoric	-76.05357 40.06331
36LA0632	Prehistoric	-76.23771 40.09083	36LA1263	Prehistoric	-76.07882 40.06804
36LA0633	Prehistoric	-76.23929 40.09135	36LA1269	Prehistoric	-76.41569 39.96221
36LA0634	Prehistoric	-76.23996 40.09252	36LA1299	Prehistoric	-76.41175 39.96484
36LA0635	Prehistoric	-76.24022 40.09414	36LA1300	Prehistoric	-76.04409 40.11266
36LA0636	Prehistoric	-76.23865 40.0954	36LA1307	Prehistoric	-76.06994 40.07284
36LA0637	Prehistoric	-76.24239 40.0955	36LA1311	Prehistoric	-76.27898 40.19759
36LA0638	Prehistoric	-76.23883 40.09668	36LA1313	Prehistoric	-76.26935 39.98052
36LA0639	Prehistoric	-76.24094 40.09685	36LA1315	Prehistoric	-76.23189 40.13608
36LA0640	Prehistoric	-76.24288 40.09737	36LA1317	Prehistoric	-76.04086 40.08419
36LA0641	Prehistoric	-76.24004 40.09784	36LA1329	Prehistoric	-76.2628 40.00064
36LA0642	Prehistoric	-76.24174 40.10034	36LA1330	Prehistoric	-75.90559 40.14104
36LA0643	Prehistoric	-76.23944 40.10063	36LA1331	Prehistoric	-76.11657 40.1578
36LA0644	Prehistoric	-76.24104 40.10134	36LA1337	Prehistoric	-76.37913 40.0852
36LA0645	Prehistoric	-76.24491 40.09901	36LA1338	Prehistoric	-76.37986 40.04626
36LA0646	Prehistoric	-76.24482 40.09991	36LA1339	Prehistoric	-76.37757 40.034
36LA0647	Prehistoric	-76.24197 40.10249	36LA1340	Prehistoric	-76.38678 40.04808
36LA0648	Prehistoric	-76.24397 40.10318	36LA1347	Prehistoric	-76.34952 39.99084
36LA0649	Prehistoric	-76.24508 40.10248	36LA1348	Prehistoric	-76.37123 39.98117
36LA0650	Prehistoric	-76.2461 40.10175	36LA1349	Prehistoric	-76.35452 39.96949
36LA0651	Prehistoric	-76.24748 40.10271	36LA1354	Prehistoric	-76.2577 39.98934
36LA0652	Prehistoric	-76.24653 40.10313	36LA1355	Prehistoric	-76.2559 39.98546
36LA0653	Prehistoric	-76.24433 40.10486	36LA1356	Prehistoric	-76.27365 39.98602
36LA0654	Prehistoric	-76.24609 40.10652	36LA1357	Prehistoric	-76.30462 39.99731
36LA0655	Prehistoric	-76.27022 40.04132	36LA1358	Prehistoric	-76.2657 39.98959
36LA0656	Prehistoric	-76.26899 40.04215	36LA1359	Prehistoric	-76.25061 39.99568
36LA0657	Prehistoric	-76.26671 40.04402	36LA1360	Prehistoric	-76.2535 39.99703
36LA0658	Prehistoric	-76.26492 40.04467	36LA1361	Prehistoric	-76.25532 39.99861
36LA0659	Prehistoric	-76.26886 40.04066	36LA1362	Prehistoric	-76.2575 39.9992

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LA0660	Prehistoric	-76.26755 40.04177	36LA1363	Prehistoric	-76.25098 39.98218
36LA0661	Prehistoric	-76.26555 40.04316	36LA1364	Prehistoric	-76.27087 39.97933
36LA0662	Prehistoric	-76.2666 40.04083	36LA1365	Prehistoric	-76.34763 40.00914
36LA0663	Prehistoric	-76.26324 40.04385	36LA1366	Prehistoric	-76.36109 40.04207
36LA0664	Prehistoric	-76.26033 40.04396	36LA1367	Prehistoric	-76.36977 40.052
36LA0665	Prehistoric	-76.2582 40.04377	36LA1368	Prehistoric	-76.34798 40.05982
36LA0666	Prehistoric	-76.25917 40.04252	36LA1369	Prehistoric	-76.32427 40.10405
36LA0667	Prehistoric	-76.25598 40.04194	36LA1370	Prehistoric	-76.27055 40.02841
36LA0668	Prehistoric	-76.25397 40.04266	36LA1371	Prehistoric	-76.29259 40.09537
36LA0669	Prehistoric	-76.26397 40.04748	36LA1372	Prehistoric	-76.29631 40.08938
36LA0670	Prehistoric	-76.2633 40.04851	36LA1373	Prehistoric	-76.30225 40.00478
36LA0671	Prehistoric	-76.26147 40.04716	36LA1374	Prehistoric	-76.26602 40.00357
36LA0672	Prehistoric	-76.27666 40.04924	36LA1375	Prehistoric	-76.27003 40.01463
36LA0673	Prehistoric	-76.275 40.04872	36LA1376	Prehistoric	-76.25141 40.10236
36LA0674	Prehistoric	-76.27529 40.04775	36LA1382	Prehistoric	-76.36438 40.04652
36LA0675	Prehistoric	-76.27361 40.04827	36LA1383	Prehistoric	-76.28556 39.98616
36LA0676	Prehistoric	-76.27366 40.04696	36LA1384	Prehistoric	-76.28731 39.98804
36LA0677	Prehistoric	-76.27245 40.04664	36LA1388	Prehistoric	-76.27023 40.00361
36LA0678	Prehistoric	-76.27395 40.04595	36LA1389	Prehistoric	-76.26978 40.00725
36LA0679	Prehistoric	-76.27265 40.04513	36LA1390	Prehistoric	-76.27818 39.99635
36LA0680	Prehistoric	-76.27304 40.04061	36LA1391	Prehistoric	-76.27554 39.99846
36LA0681	Prehistoric	-76.29302 40.10716	36LA1393	Prehistoric	-76.20434 40.14212
36LA0682	Prehistoric	-76.2951 40.1072	36LA1403	Prehistoric	-76.05443 40.0969
36LA0683	Prehistoric	-76.29476 40.10802	36LA1404	Prehistoric	-76.08704 40.16372
36LA0684	Prehistoric	-76.29423 40.10981	36LA1422	Prehistoric	-76.40678 39.9693
36LA0685	Prehistoric	-76.29222 40.11057	36LA1424	Prehistoric	-76.13236 40.06624
36LA0686	Prehistoric	-76.29079 40.11179	36LA1426	Prehistoric	-76.24025 40.03648
36LA0687	Prehistoric	-76.29689 40.10852	36LA1429	Prehistoric	-76.21608 40.11593
36LA0688	Prehistoric	-76.29874 40.1086	36LA1432	Prehistoric	-76.39725 39.9687
36LA0689	Prehistoric	-76.30128 40.10846	36LA1433	Prehistoric	-76.1812 40.06741
36LA0690	Prehistoric	-76.30472 40.10745	36LA1436	Prehistoric	-76.24924 39.99205
36LA0691	Prehistoric	-76.30477 40.10849	36LA1438	Prehistoric	-76.25991 39.99226
36LA0692	Prehistoric	-76.30081 40.10983	36LA1448	Prehistoric	-76.42383 39.96017
36LA0693	Prehistoric	-76.29754 40.11003	36LA1454	Prehistoric	-76.38446 40.03869
36LA0694	Prehistoric	-76.29888 40.11127	36LA1461	Prehistoric	-75.91827 40.1515
36LA0695	Prehistoric	-76.29587 40.1108	36LA1462	Prehistoric	-75.98757 40.12169
36LA0696	Prehistoric	-76.29523 40.11212	36LA1463	Prehistoric	-76.01582 40.11494
36LA0697	Prehistoric	-76.29758 40.11246	36LA1464	Prehistoric	-75.96957 40.12807
36LA0698	Prehistoric	-76.29367 40.11316	36LA1465	Prehistoric	-75.92342 40.14654
36LA0699	Prehistoric	-76.29071 40.11297	36LA1466	Prehistoric	-76.02793 40.11456
36LA0700	Prehistoric	-76.29098 40.11487	36LA1467	Prehistoric	-75.91997 40.14994
36LA0701	Prehistoric	-76.29282 40.11483	36LA1468	Prehistoric	-76.0141 40.115
36LA0702	Prehistoric	-76.29571 40.11516	36LA1469	Prehistoric	-76.34001 40.05828
36LA0703	Prehistoric	-76.29774 40.11438	36LA1473	Prehistoric	-76.22263 40.1371
36LA0704	Prehistoric	-76.29959 40.11515	36LA1490	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.21796 40.18334
36LA0705	Prehistoric	-76.30079 40.11348	36LA1500	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.34128 40.0537
36LA0706	Prehistoric	-76.30213 40.11287	36LA1505	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.93393 40.13448
36LA0707	Prehistoric	-76.3025 40.11439	36LA1506	Prehistoric	-76.29223 40.08794
36LA0708	Prehistoric	-76.30173 40.11552			
Watershed 85-Piedmont-Piedmont Upland:					
36LA0084	Prehistoric	-76.37737 39.92485	36LA0322	Prehistoric	-76.00592 40.10577
36LA0091	Prehistoric	-75.97794 40.09912	36LA1182	Prehistoric	-76.37839 39.93104

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LA0242	Prehistoric	-76.38374 39.93731			
Watershed 87-Piedmont-Gettysburg-Newark Lowland:					
36CU0107	Prehistoric	-76.97382 40.15576	36YO0242	Prehistoric	-76.81709 40.19947
36CU0131	Prehistoric	-76.9801 40.15411	36YO0257	Prehistoric	-76.98381 40.15326
36CU0135	Prehistoric	-76.97429 40.1552	36YO0347	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.05156 40.10992
36CU0164	Prehistoric	-76.91067 40.17084	36YO0359	Prehistoric	-77.0147 40.12204
36CU0180	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.91772 40.19707	36YO0383	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.85081 40.20395
36YO0190	Prehistoric	-76.94249 40.16288			
Watershed 88-Piedmont-Gettysburg-Newark Lowland:					
36CH0116	Prehistoric	-75.46432 40.12087	36MG0183	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.38009 40.11434
36CH0295	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.47465 40.11043	36MG0186	Prehistoric	-75.3733 40.11491
36MG0007	Prehistoric	-75.46109 40.10524	36MG0206	Prehistoric	-75.40972 40.10832
36MG0008	Prehistoric	-75.43011 40.11241	36MG0207	Prehistoric	-75.40904 40.10718
36MG0009	Prehistoric	-75.39483 40.12674	36MG0208	Prehistoric	-75.40696 40.10775
36MG0010	Prehistoric	-75.39267 40.11969	36MG0209	Prehistoric	-75.40851 40.10844
36MG0017	Prehistoric	-75.43652 40.1225	36MG0275	Prehistoric	-75.26036 40.19291
36MG0018	Prehistoric	-75.35224 40.1152	36MG0281	Prehistoric	-75.20956 40.1723
36MG0074	Prehistoric	-75.45269 40.11177	36MG0283	Prehistoric	-75.20215 40.13542
36MG0102	Prehistoric	-75.42184 40.11073	36MG0286	Prehistoric	-75.34961 40.11106
36MG0103	Prehistoric	-75.44745 40.11126	36MG0309	Prehistoric	-75.21459 40.13562
36MG0114	Prehistoric	-75.42174 40.10852	36MG0315	Prehistoric	-75.30668 40.18647
36MG0115	Prehistoric	-75.44613 40.10487	36MG0317	Prehistoric	-75.30787 40.18398
36MG0153	Prehistoric	-75.30045 40.20172	36MG0318	Prehistoric	-75.30788 40.18131
36MG0154	Prehistoric	-75.37025 40.11776	36MG0322	Prehistoric	-75.22541 40.20562
36MG0155	Prehistoric	-75.45369 40.11054	36MG0327	Prehistoric	-75.40676 40.10992
36MG0156	Prehistoric	-75.44376 40.11047	36MG0340	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.27899 40.18662
36MG0157	Prehistoric	-75.42567 40.11348	36MG0400	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.42363 40.10442
36MG0158	Prehistoric	-75.40367 40.11747	36MG0435	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.40666 40.10604
36MG0159	Prehistoric	-75.3986 40.11949	36MG0438	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.33987 40.14403
36MG0160	Prehistoric	-75.39333 40.11629	36MG0440	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.29856 40.16213
36MG0171	Prehistoric	-75.36487 40.11469	36MG0441	Prehistoric	-75.45875 40.10193
36MG0172	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.44949 40.10958	36MG0457	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.42193 40.1093
36MG0180	Prehistoric	-75.40766 40.10928			
Watershed 88-Piedmont-Piedmont Lowland:					
36CH/049	Prehistoric	-75.4574 40.07966	36CH0909	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.49211 40.07558
36CH0145	Prehistoric	-75.58001 40.03292	36CH0910	Prehistoric	-75.47025 40.07667
36CH0146	Prehistoric	-75.56537 40.05321	36CH0912	Prehistoric	-75.49446 40.07611
36CH0147	Prehistoric	-75.57821 40.03941	36CH0913	Prehistoric	-75.48407 40.07626
36CH0508	Prehistoric	-75.52417 40.04957	36CH0921	Prehistoric	-75.45177 40.08087
36CH0627	Prehistoric	-75.5149 40.06991	36MG0166	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.21572 40.12548
36CH0628	Prehistoric	-75.51765 40.07009	36MG0185	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.32591 40.10294
36CH0629	Prehistoric	-75.5001 40.05474	36MG0197	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.28556 40.07492
36CH0687	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.44957 40.06979	36MG0282	Prehistoric	-75.20415 40.12609
36CH0690	Prehistoric	-75.55708 40.05138	36MG0288	Prehistoric	-75.20271 40.12611
36CH0764	Prehistoric	-75.58807 40.05193	36MG0289	Prehistoric	-75.20432 40.12708
36CH0859	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.53089 40.07432	36MG0291	Prehistoric	-75.20096 40.11122
36CH0878	Prehistoric	-75.45428 40.08455	36MG0300	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.28515 40.07579
36CH0905	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.45757 40.08012	36MG0323	Prehistoric	-75.19813 40.12342
36CH0906	Prehistoric	-75.45458 40.08035	36MG0335	Prehistoric	-75.20316 40.12869
36CH0907	Prehistoric	-75.48454 40.07659	36MG0412	Prehistoric	-75.42203 40.10318

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36CH0908	Prehistoric	-75.48041 40.07649	36MG0427	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.18963 40.12397
Watershed 88-Piedmont-Piedmont Upland:					
36MG0181	Prehistoric	-75.45354 40.09048	36PH0022	Prehistoric	-75.26165 40.05601
36MG0358	Prehistoric	-75.19523 40.12553	36PH0025	Prehistoric	-75.22443 40.08029
36MG0428	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.19191 40.12605			
Watershed 89-Piedmont-Gettysburg-Newark Lowland:					
36DA0002	Prehistoric	-76.73838 40.17992	36LA1124	Prehistoric	-76.71228 40.13188
36DA0003	Prehistoric	-76.73559 40.15517	36LA1153	Prehistoric	-76.61853 40.1719
36DA0004	Prehistoric	-76.71421 40.15674	36LA1220	Prehistoric	-76.61136 40.18105
36DA0010	Prehistoric	-76.71626 40.16005	36LA1265	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.60344 40.15281
36DA0017	Prehistoric	-76.57121 40.19605	36LA1285	Prehistoric	-76.69113 40.11257
36DA0050	Prehistoric	-76.72414 40.16058	36LA1443	Prehistoric	-76.58831 40.18097
36DA0051	Prehistoric	-76.72336 40.1439	36LA1444	Prehistoric	-76.70644 40.13663
36DA0052	Prehistoric	-76.72322 40.14982	36LA1495	Prehistoric	-76.68836 40.11013
36DA0053	Prehistoric	-76.6139 40.22491	36LE0137	Prehistoric	-76.52985 40.2634
36DA0054	Prehistoric	-76.60415 40.22582	36LE0221	Prehistoric	-76.5852 40.24104
36DA0055	Prehistoric	-76.61544 40.18319	36LE0222	Prehistoric	-76.56798 40.21784
36DA0057	Prehistoric	-76.61882 40.1975	36LE0223	Prehistoric	-76.49386 40.24451
36DA0058	Prehistoric	-76.62771 40.19958	36LE0224	Prehistoric	-76.53607 40.25531
36DA0059	Prehistoric	-76.63214 40.20455	36LE0225	Prehistoric	-76.5225 40.254
36DA0060	Prehistoric	-76.57798 40.1957	36LE0226	Prehistoric	-76.54037 40.24872
36DA0070	Prehistoric	-76.6176 40.23196	36LE0227	Prehistoric	-76.56403 40.20021
36DA0086	Prehistoric	-76.74218 40.17051	36LE0228	Prehistoric	-76.5589 40.22993
36DA0091	Prehistoric	-76.73754 40.18046	36LE0229	Prehistoric	-76.55608 40.23064
36DA0092	Prehistoric	-76.73814 40.17917	36LE0230	Prehistoric	-76.56512 40.24017
36DA0093	Prehistoric	-76.73854 40.17589	36LE0231	Prehistoric	-76.52274 40.24795
36DA0094	Prehistoric	-76.74178 40.16348	36LE0232	Prehistoric	-76.52372 40.23759
36DA0095	Prehistoric	-76.73153 40.17247	36LE0233	Prehistoric	-76.5391 40.21762
36DA0096	Prehistoric	-76.72174 40.15981	36LE0239	Prehistoric	-76.57907 40.22528
36DA0097	Prehistoric	-76.72471 40.15906	36LE0248	Prehistoric	-76.54487 40.22052
36DA0098	Prehistoric	-76.72538 40.14552	36LE0249	Prehistoric	-76.55122 40.20695
36DA0099	Prehistoric	-76.7253 40.13499	36LE0250	Prehistoric	-76.55382 40.22419
36DA0100	Prehistoric	-76.72214 40.13145	36LE0251	Prehistoric	-76.55864 40.20899
36DA0101	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.71823 40.13107	36LE0252	Prehistoric	-76.55074 40.23215
36DA0102	Prehistoric	-76.734 40.16078	36LE0253	Prehistoric	-76.55117 40.24049
36DA0103	Prehistoric	-76.73162 40.15916	36YO0040	Prehistoric	-76.68204 40.08351
36DA0104	Prehistoric	-76.7379 40.15317	36YO0080	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.74524 40.13184
36DA0105	Prehistoric	-76.73699 40.15142	36YO0092	Prehistoric	-76.70593 40.10763
36DA0106	Prehistoric	-76.73305 40.13897	36YO0131	Prehistoric	-76.69603 40.09227
36DA0107	Prehistoric	-76.73367 40.13794	36YO0147	Prehistoric	-76.72783 40.11552
36DA0139	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.73775 40.1293	36YO0151	Prehistoric	-76.68503 40.08502
36DA0146	Prehistoric	-76.72452 40.17799	36YO0171	Prehistoric	-76.748 40.14291
36DA0149	Prehistoric	-76.73521 40.17227	36YO0172	Prehistoric	-76.75396 40.16135
36DA0150	Prehistoric	-76.73919 40.13163	36YO0180	Prehistoric	-76.69365 40.07985
36DA0151	Prehistoric	-76.74143 40.13465	36YO0181	Prehistoric	-76.69423 40.08423
36DA0152	Prehistoric	-76.7311 40.14258	36YO0244	Prehistoric	-76.74569 40.13352
36DA0156	Prehistoric	-76.71671 40.147	36YO0245	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.74611 40.13517
36DA0232	Prehistoric	-76.62834 40.17846	36YO0246	Prehistoric	-76.74778 40.14137
36LA0021	Prehistoric	-76.70763 40.11986	36YO0256	Prehistoric	-76.74882 40.15686
36LA0022	Prehistoric	-76.67402 40.09814	36YO0264	Prehistoric	-76.74939 40.16954
36LA0027	Prehistoric	-76.69403 40.15554	36YO0278	Prehistoric	-76.74969 40.15664

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LA0042	Prehistoric	-76.67866 40.09444	36YO0279	Prehistoric	-76.75253 40.15565
36LA0097	Prehistoric	-76.672 40.09698	36YO0297	Prehistoric	-76.74768 40.13507
36LA0253	Prehistoric	-76.63069 40.117	36YO0298	Prehistoric	-76.74785 40.13655
36LA0437	Prehistoric	-76.71387 40.12759	36YO0299	Prehistoric	-76.74872 40.13846
36LA0885	Prehistoric	-76.68173 40.10637	36YO0300	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.72601 40.12115
36LA0886	Prehistoric	-76.67502 40.09939	36YO0317	Prehistoric	-76.71731 40.11321
36LA0968	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.65441 40.13082	36YO0334	Prehistoric	-76.74897 40.1626
36LA0969	Prehistoric	-76.69698 40.11567			
Watershed 89-Piedmont-Piedmont Lowland:					
36LA0003	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.45741 39.97671	36LA1181	Prehistoric	-76.4727 40.00314
36LA0004	Prehistoric	-76.47052 39.99431	36LA1183	Prehistoric	-76.46897 39.99846
36LA0005	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.66288 40.08255	36LA1228	Prehistoric	-76.63056 40.06859
36LA0006	Prehistoric	-76.47052 39.99571	36LA1256	Prehistoric	-76.46443 39.99003
36LA0007	Prehistoric	-76.46058 39.98078	36LA1256	Prehistoric	-76.4627 39.9887
36LA0008	Prehistoric	-76.46755 39.99435	36LA1257	Prehistoric	-76.45909 39.97578
36LA0009	Prehistoric	-76.45785 39.98062	36LA1258	Prehistoric	-76.47084 40.00347
36LA0010	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.64886 40.07296	36LA1259	Prehistoric	-76.46511 39.98515
36LA0012	Prehistoric	-76.46877 39.99487	36LA1266	Prehistoric	-76.63432 40.0707
36LA0023	Prehistoric	-76.63929 40.06453	36LA1271	Prehistoric	-76.46464 39.99205
36LA0036	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.46374 39.98242	36LA1272	Prehistoric	-76.4631 39.98112
36LA0037	Prehistoric	-76.46309 39.98194	36LA1273	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.45378 39.98482
36LA0039	Prehistoric	-76.66481 40.08514	36LA1274	Prehistoric	-76.46282 39.98308
36LA0040	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.65951 40.07921	36LA1276	Prehistoric	-76.46751 39.99931
36LA0041	Prehistoric	-76.65787 40.06685	36LA1277	Prehistoric	-76.46322 39.99401
36LA0054	Prehistoric	-76.46947 39.99267	36LA1278	Prehistoric	-76.46754 39.99157
36LA0057	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.65956 40.08088	36LA1279	Prehistoric	-76.47285 39.99965
36LA0092	Prehistoric	-76.46586 39.99519	36LA1280	Prehistoric	-76.46576 39.9843
36LA0093	Prehistoric	-76.46572 39.98756	36LA1281	Prehistoric	-76.46898 40.00437
36LA0098	Prehistoric	-76.45679 39.97914	36LA1282	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.47313 40.00072
36LA0099	Prehistoric	-76.61504 40.06489	36LA1283	Prehistoric	-76.47057 40.00095
36LA0101	Prehistoric	-76.46822 39.99074	36LA1284	Prehistoric	-76.47101 40.00294
36LA0102	Prehistoric	-76.45838 39.97465	36LA1291	Prehistoric	-76.47393 40.00057
36LA0111	Prehistoric	-76.45589 39.9693	36LA1301	Prehistoric	-76.43279 40.09074
36LA0183	Prehistoric	-76.45374 39.97002	36LA1322	Prehistoric	-76.47685 40.03049
36LA0186	Prehistoric	-76.47221 39.99832	36LA1323	Prehistoric	-76.4876 40.01739
36LA0191	Prehistoric	-76.47354 40.00128	36LA1324	Prehistoric	-76.49844 40.02774
36LA0205	Prehistoric	-76.44573 39.98172	36LA1325	Prehistoric	-76.4991 40.02699
36LA0239	Prehistoric	-76.46152 39.98536	36LA1326	Prehistoric	-76.49952 40.02656
36LA0254	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.65941 40.08546	36LA1327	Prehistoric	-76.49999 40.02588
36LA0255	Prehistoric	-76.65916 40.08678	36LA1409	Prehistoric	-76.60572 40.06144
36LA0256	Prehistoric	-76.60731 40.06628	36LA1420	Prehistoric	-76.4531 39.99598
36LA0379	Prehistoric	-76.46717 39.98938	36LA1425	Prehistoric	-76.46036 39.99761
36LA0402	Prehistoric	-76.66561 40.07079	36LA1450	Prehistoric	-76.46254 39.98008
36LA0432	Prehistoric	-76.66032 40.0854	36LA1456	Prehistoric	-76.45542 40.09969
36LA0438	Prehistoric	-76.63961 40.06775	36LA1458	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.47161 39.99611
36LA0887	Prehistoric	-76.45317 40.022	36LA1475	Prehistoric	-76.60307 40.05773
36LA0888	Prehistoric	-76.59584 40.05721	36LA1478	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.63992 40.07315
36LA0890	Prehistoric	-76.45668 39.96746	36LA1479	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.63833 40.07322
36LA0929	Prehistoric	-76.64341 40.07195	36LA1480	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.63814 40.07204
36LA0930	Prehistoric	-76.64301 40.07059	36LA1481	Prehistoric	-76.63928 40.07131
36LA0931	Prehistoric	-76.64072 40.07327	36LA1482	Prehistoric	-76.63853 40.0703
36LA0932	Prehistoric	-76.64451 40.07035	36LA1483	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.64061 40.07173

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LA0933	Prehistoric	-76.643 40.06974	36LA1484	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.64128 40.07014
36LA0934	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.45283 39.96863	36LA1485	Prehistoric	-76.64057 40.06908
36LA0943	Prehistoric	-76.45636 39.96815	36LA1496	Prehistoric	-76.61103 40.06195
36LA0957	Prehistoric	-76.52926 40.06854	36LA1498	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.50578 40.03205
36LA0976	Prehistoric	-76.67209 40.07296	36YO0009	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.50056 39.98879
36LA0977	Prehistoric	-76.6329 40.06416	36YO0009	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.50016 39.98883
36LA0993	Prehistoric	-76.4747 40.07081	36YO0113	Prehistoric	-76.65029 40.05905
36LA0994	Prehistoric	-76.47201 40.00033	36YO0170	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.49838 39.97684
36LA0999	Prehistoric	-76.60968 40.0634	36YO0254	Prehistoric	-76.63895 40.05803
36LA1000	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.61931 40.06097	36YO0294	Prehistoric	-76.4958 39.98037
36LA1087	Prehistoric	-76.37156 40.17526	36YO0295	Prehistoric	-76.49005 39.96773
36LA1097	Prehistoric	-76.40293 40.12666	36YO0296	Prehistoric	-76.48865 39.96489
36LA1125	Prehistoric	-76.6618 40.08612	36YO0310	Prehistoric	-76.49492 39.9726
36LA1164	Prehistoric	-76.46459 39.98403	36YO0338	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.49649 39.97767
36LA1165	Prehistoric	-76.46424 39.98335	36YO0340	Prehistoric	-76.49488 39.9749
36LA1166	Prehistoric	-76.46574 39.98348	36YO0351	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.49926 39.98041
36LA1167	Prehistoric	-76.46108 39.98285			
Watershed 89-Piedmont-Piedmont Upland:					
36LA0046	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.45563 39.96676	36LA1421	Prehistoric	-76.45474 39.95561
36LA0048	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.43389 39.94289	36LA1492	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.43536 39.94212
36LA0187	Prehistoric	-76.43978 39.93845	36LA1493	Prehistoric	-76.43353 39.93976
36LA0889	Prehistoric	-76.47421 40.00899	36LA1499	Prehistoric	-76.45202 39.96066
36LA0891	Prehistoric	-76.4494 39.9631	36LA1508	Prehistoric	-76.43455 39.95017
36LA0936	Prehistoric	-76.45072 39.95804	36YO0026	Prehistoric	-76.51315 39.95126
36LA0937	Prehistoric	-76.44808 39.95584	36YO0029	Prehistoric	-76.51278 39.94778
36LA0938	Prehistoric	-76.45817 39.95693	36YO0032	Prehistoric	-76.48333 39.95403
36LA0939	Prehistoric	-76.4559 39.95922	36YO0037	Prehistoric	-76.49544 39.95554
36LA0940	Prehistoric	-76.44858 39.95833	36YO0038	Prehistoric	-76.5006 39.99662
36LA0941	Prehistoric	-76.44752 39.95431	36YO0112	Prehistoric	-76.51667 40.01521
36LA1147	Prehistoric	-76.4457 39.95948	36YO0182	Prehistoric	-76.65006 40.05645
36LA1148	Prehistoric	-76.45122 39.96232	36YO0248	Prehistoric	-76.63393 40.05667
36LA1275	Prehistoric	-76.44325 39.96417	36YO0285	Prehistoric	-76.47662 39.95223
36LA1334	Prehistoric	-76.51622 40.04683	36YO0354	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.48601 39.95982
36LA1335	Prehistoric	-76.47575 40.04044	36YO0394	Prehistoric	-76.61713 40.04989
36LA1336	Prehistoric	-76.48114 40.01418	36YO0431	Prehistoric	-76.39899 39.91298
Watershed 90-Piedmont-Gettysburg-Newark Lowland:					
36BU0343	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.0605 40.16533			
Watershed 90-Piedmont-Piedmont Upland:					
36BU0342	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.02689 40.14548	36MG0363	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.02909 40.13122
36MG0077	Prehistoric	-75.1237 40.11498	36MG0368	Prehistoric	-75.02773 40.1311
36MG0084	Prehistoric	-75.0736 40.1029	36PH0041	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.05732 40.08508
36MG0231	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.02682 40.12982	36PH0054	Prehistoric	-75.02554 40.12829
36MG0284	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.02482 40.1297	36PH0055	Prehistoric	-75.02375 40.12754
36MG0329	Prehistoric	-75.07433 40.09485	36PH0154	Prehistoric	-75.11346 40.04206
Watershed 93-Piedmont-Gettysburg-Newark Lowland:					
36AD0015	Prehistoric	-77.06506 40.0063	36YO0079	Prehistoric	-76.95029 39.94569
36AD0016	Prehistoric	-77.06724 40.0016	36YO0082	Prehistoric	-76.99676 40.00964
36AD0017	Prehistoric	-77.08433 40.00029	36YO0083	Prehistoric	-76.87727 40.06072
36AD0018	Prehistoric	-77.03893 40.00565	36YO0085	Prehistoric	-76.98762 40.01505
36AD0019	Prehistoric	-77.03149 40.00436	36YO0086	Prehistoric	-76.95489 39.97971

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36AD0020	Prehistoric	-77.0347 40.00402	36YO0087	Prehistoric	-76.99202 40.01221
36AD0021	Prehistoric	-77.05517 40.00304	36YO0088	Prehistoric	-76.9986 40.02172
36AD0022	Prehistoric	-77.05162 40.00627	36YO0089	Prehistoric	-76.87816 40.05043
36AD0023	Prehistoric	-77.19413 39.92622	36YO0090	Prehistoric	-76.86275 40.07417
36AD0024	Prehistoric	-77.07356 39.89242	36YO0091	Prehistoric	-76.86253 40.06875
36AD0025	Prehistoric	-77.08343 39.89245	36YO0093	Prehistoric	-76.84507 40.09627
36AD0026	Prehistoric	-77.10906 39.90509	36YO0094	Prehistoric	-76.88602 40.04944
36AD0027	Prehistoric	-77.05142 39.9096	36YO0095	Prehistoric	-76.87212 40.0567
36AD0028	Prehistoric	-77.06634 39.90902	36YO0096	Prehistoric	-76.90072 40.02858
36AD0029	Prehistoric	-77.05918 39.91238	36YO0098	Prehistoric	-76.98652 40.00984
36AD0032	Prehistoric	-77.02317 39.85643	36YO0099	Prehistoric	-76.85694 40.08712
36AD0062	Prehistoric	-77.02333 39.99753	36YO0100	Prehistoric	-76.76209 40.05292
36AD0068	Prehistoric	-77.11852 40.03824	36YO0101	Prehistoric	-76.8697 40.05989
36AD0069	Prehistoric	-77.06544 40.00993	36YO0102	Prehistoric	-76.87751 40.0547
36AD0070	Prehistoric	-77.05708 40.00055	36YO0103	Prehistoric	-76.75808 40.05112
36AD0071	Prehistoric	-77.02845 40.00389	36YO0104	Prehistoric	-76.77092 40.04478
36AD0072	Prehistoric	-77.02464 40.00721	36YO0105	Prehistoric	-76.78117 40.03673
36AD0073	Prehistoric	-77.20419 39.95102	36YO0106	Prehistoric	-76.78533 40.03044
36AD0074	Prehistoric	-76.97087 39.93732	36YO0107	Prehistoric	-76.79635 40.00171
36AD0075	Prehistoric	-77.20639 39.94311	36YO0108	Prehistoric	-76.84004 40.02372
36AD0076	Prehistoric	-77.22526 39.97597	36YO0109	Prehistoric	-76.85547 40.01974
36AD0077	Prehistoric	-77.21657 39.91692	36YO0110	Prehistoric	-76.87167 40.02619
36AD0078	Prehistoric	-77.216 39.94087	36YO0111	Prehistoric	-76.87195 40.02498
36AD0079	Prehistoric	-77.21624 39.9309	36YO0114	Prehistoric	-76.93529 40.00053
36AD0081	Prehistoric	-77.21065 39.92035	36YO0116	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.86803 40.00356
36AD0082	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.19493 39.93591	36YO0117	Prehistoric	-76.92915 39.98466
36AD0083	Prehistoric	-77.17322 39.93563	36YO0119	Prehistoric	-76.88264 40.04937
36AD0084	Prehistoric	-77.15675 39.93754	36YO0121	Prehistoric	-76.88253 40.05696
36AD0085	Prehistoric	-77.15282 39.92639	36YO0123	Prehistoric	-76.8862 40.05066
36AD0086	Prehistoric	-77.1483 39.92492	36YO0125	Prehistoric	-76.92339 40.02142
36AD0087	Prehistoric	-77.16346 39.91584	36YO0126	Prehistoric	-76.89864 40.04874
36AD0088	Prehistoric	-77.15194 39.9011	36YO0127	Prehistoric	-76.89712 40.04652
36AD0089	Prehistoric	-77.13693 39.9127	36YO0128	Prehistoric	-76.8987 39.92544
36AD0090	Prehistoric	-77.13521 39.91107	36YO0129	Prehistoric	-76.89325 40.04006
36AD0091	Prehistoric	-77.1269 39.90901	36YO0130	Prehistoric	-76.79475 39.98877
36AD0092	Prehistoric	-77.12543 39.90755	36YO0132	Prehistoric	-76.86993 40.06583
36AD0093	Prehistoric	-77.12613 39.9016	36YO0133	Prehistoric	-76.88273 40.06138
36AD0094	Prehistoric	-77.00678 39.92656	36YO0134	Prehistoric	-76.79691 39.99109
36AD0095	Prehistoric	-77.12886 39.89763	36YO0136	Prehistoric	-76.99823 40.00855
36AD0096	Prehistoric	-77.07922 39.96852	36YO0139	Prehistoric	-76.92989 40.01461
36AD0097	Prehistoric	-77.10268 39.92368	36YO0140	Prehistoric	-76.9009 40.0423
36AD0098	Prehistoric	-77.12029 39.90657	36YO0141	Prehistoric	-76.90499 40.03553
36AD0099	Prehistoric	-77.08421 39.89628	36YO0142	Prehistoric	-76.87007 40.03229
36AD0100	Prehistoric	-77.08711 39.89389	36YO0143	Prehistoric	-76.87354 40.07186
36AD0101	Prehistoric	-77.10258 39.90379	36YO0144	Prehistoric	-76.87356 40.07266
36AD0102	Prehistoric	-77.08178 39.89598	36YO0145	Prehistoric	-76.87144 40.07361
36AD0103	Prehistoric	-77.05447 39.91223	36YO0146	Prehistoric	-77.00005 40.00888
36AD0104	Prehistoric	-77.14444 39.92104	36YO0148	Prehistoric	-76.7527 40.11067
36AD0105	Prehistoric	-77.15612 39.92903	36YO0149	Prehistoric	-76.88646 40.04783
36AD0106	Prehistoric	-77.15917 39.93688	36YO0150	Prehistoric	-76.89557 40.0402
36AD0107	Prehistoric	-77.12222 39.90012	36YO0152	Prehistoric	-76.87693 40.05894
36AD0108	Prehistoric	-77.14423 39.90134	36YO0153	Prehistoric	-76.89462 40.03853

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36AD0109	Prehistoric	-77.13581 39.92061	36YO0154	Prehistoric	-76.90437 40.03219
36AD0110	Prehistoric	-77.16608 39.93342	36YO0155	Prehistoric	-76.91043 40.031
36AD0111	Prehistoric	-77.04213 39.91296	36YO0156	Prehistoric	-76.90934 40.02807
36AD0112	Prehistoric	-77.04049 39.94504	36YO0157	Prehistoric	-76.90599 40.02417
36AD0113	Prehistoric	-77.0352 39.93888	36YO0158	Prehistoric	-76.93121 40.02724
36AD0114	Prehistoric	-77.01572 39.92385	36YO0159	Prehistoric	-76.93035 40.00637
36AD0115	Prehistoric	-77.00221 39.92958	36YO0160	Prehistoric	-76.95248 40.01422
36AD0117	Prehistoric	-77.24765 39.91151	36YO0161	Prehistoric	-76.96473 40.02807
36AD0118	Prehistoric	-77.24102 39.91105	36YO0162	Prehistoric	-76.9857 40.02774
36AD0121	Prehistoric	-77.30664 39.93206	36YO0163	Prehistoric	-76.97288 40.01536
36AD0123	Prehistoric	-77.27882 39.90938	36YO0164	Prehistoric	-76.90656 40.03926
36AD0124	Prehistoric	-77.14051 39.91574	36YO0165	Prehistoric	-76.87968 40.06151
36AD0125	Prehistoric	-77.14212 39.91189	36YO0166	Prehistoric	-76.92063 40.02769
36AD0126	Prehistoric	-77.13193 39.90774	36YO0167	Prehistoric	-76.97576 40.0026
36AD0130	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.28703 39.91477	36YO0168	Prehistoric	-76.99803 40.00666
36AD0131	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.04817 39.91393	36YO0169	Prehistoric	-76.98385 40.01221
36AD0135	Prehistoric	-77.04689 39.91193	36YO0174	Prehistoric	-77.00609 40.00931
36AD0137	Prehistoric	-77.09185 40.00159	36YO0175	Prehistoric	-76.95031 40.01547
36AD0141	Prehistoric	-77.29621 39.91243	36YO0177	Prehistoric	-76.74265 40.10041
36AD0143	Prehistoric	-77.2884 39.91558	36YO0178	Prehistoric	-76.70724 40.09177
36AD0144	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.26563 39.91952	36YO0179	Prehistoric	-76.70891 40.08857
36AD0145	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.24874 39.92361	36YO0184	Prehistoric	-76.92635 40.00976
36AD0147	Prehistoric	-77.07727 39.9595	36YO0191	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.85709 40.00519
36AD0148	Prehistoric	-77.08833 39.95779	36YO0196	Prehistoric	-76.94175 39.99805
36AD0149	Prehistoric	-77.20132 39.93414	36YO0197	Prehistoric	-76.92331 39.99952
36AD0150	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.21154 39.93203	36YO0198	Prehistoric	-76.92455 39.98412
36AD0151	Prehistoric	-77.20421 39.92409	36YO0199	Prehistoric	-76.89912 39.98767
36AD0152	Prehistoric	-77.31613 39.9316	36YO0200	Prehistoric	-76.8864 39.98208
36AD0157	Prehistoric	-77.05255 40.0087	36YO0201	Prehistoric	-76.95322 39.95195
36AD0159	Prehistoric	-77.1042 40.01181	36YO0202	Prehistoric	-76.96453 39.95039
36AD0160	Prehistoric	-77.10378 40.01183	36YO0203	Prehistoric	-76.96223 39.95032
36AD0161	Prehistoric	-77.10227 40.01187	36YO0204	Prehistoric	-76.96467 39.94534
36AD0162	Prehistoric	-77.10327 40.01115	36YO0205	Prehistoric	-76.9237 39.93089
36AD0163	Prehistoric	-77.0906 40.03081	36YO0206	Prehistoric	-76.90126 39.92291
36AD0164	Prehistoric	-77.10229 40.01053	36YO0207	Prehistoric	-76.78573 39.99383
36AD0165	Prehistoric	-77.10363 40.01256	36YO0208	Prehistoric	-76.78176 39.98833
36AD0167	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.09416 40.00468	36YO0209	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.79511 39.98578
36AD0171	Prehistoric	-77.24868 39.92015	36YO0210	Prehistoric	-76.7832 39.98633
36AD0172	Prehistoric	-77.252 39.92052	36YO0213	Prehistoric	-76.81066 39.97722
36AD0173	Prehistoric	-77.25308 39.92125	36YO0214	Prehistoric	-76.80505 39.97258
36AD0174	Prehistoric	-77.25204 39.9218	36YO0215	Prehistoric	-76.80212 39.96527
36AD0179	Prehistoric	-77.19273 39.93353	36YO0216	Prehistoric	-76.82161 39.96562
36AD0180	Prehistoric	-77.01832 40.01016	36YO0247	Prehistoric	-76.81684 40.09851
36AD0430	Prehistoric	-77.16921 39.89767	36YO0251	Prehistoric	-76.92636 40.0151
36AD0441	Prehistoric	-77.05516 39.87861	36YO0255	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.86589 40.01948
36AD0442	Prehistoric	-77.0794 39.82558	36YO0258	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.79235 40.0169
36AD0443	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.08525 39.861	36YO0259	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.78963 40.01712
36AD0455	Prehistoric	-77.04016 39.86161	36YO0266	Prehistoric	-76.894 40.04807
36AD0486	Prehistoric	-76.9755 39.94195	36YO0267	Prehistoric	-76.93541 40.11717
36AD0510	Prehistoric	-77.28932 39.92528	36YO0268	Prehistoric	-76.96764 40.0264
36AD0521	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.06649 39.87297	36YO0269	Prehistoric	-76.95375 40.11344
36YO0042	Prehistoric	-76.83466 40.1027	36YO0270	Prehistoric	-76.9369 40.11891

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36YO0043	Prehistoric	-76.87429 40.06622	36YO0271	Prehistoric	-76.9353 40.11826
36YO0047	Prehistoric	-76.93599 39.99033	36YO0272	Prehistoric	-76.99257 40.00818
36YO0048	Prehistoric	-76.95004 39.96894	36YO0273	Prehistoric	-76.94067 40.11992
36YO0049	Prehistoric	-76.9929 40.00961	36YO0275	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.81935 40.00561
36YO0050	Prehistoric	-77.00864 40.00154	36YO0276	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.8144 40.00739
36YO0051	Prehistoric	-76.99881 40.00515	36YO0277	Prehistoric	-76.89188 40.04917
36YO0052	Prehistoric	-76.95584 39.88074	36YO0280	Prehistoric	-76.94402 40.11837
36YO0053	Prehistoric	-76.92672 39.99465	36YO0281	Prehistoric	-76.9455 40.10729
36YO0054	Prehistoric	-76.92294 39.99751	36YO0304	Prehistoric	-76.95167 40.11578
36YO0055	Prehistoric	-76.91887 40.01901	36YO0307	Prehistoric	-76.79991 39.96418
36YO0056	Prehistoric	-76.90941 40.02239	36YO0308	Prehistoric	-76.8021 39.96419
36YO0057	Prehistoric	-76.8797 40.05954	36YO0321	Prehistoric	-76.78734 39.98559
36YO0058	Prehistoric	-76.9569 39.95027	36YO0363	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.76255 40.10041
36YO0060	Prehistoric	-76.95105 39.94909	36YO0364	Prehistoric	-76.76409 40.10087
36YO0061	Prehistoric	-76.88807 40.05164	36YO0367	Prehistoric	-76.90215 40.03357
36YO0062	Prehistoric	-76.87585 40.05791	36YO0368	Prehistoric	-76.90268 40.03444
36YO0065	Prehistoric	-76.89609 40.0442	36YO0369	Prehistoric	-76.90357 40.03718
36YO0066	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.98041 40.01142	36YO0370	Prehistoric	-76.89731 40.03727
36YO0067	Prehistoric	-76.99283 40.00646	36YO0371	Prehistoric	-76.89826 40.04195
36YO0068	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.98713 40.00914	36YO0376	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.96864 39.94578
36YO0069	Prehistoric	-76.95098 39.99722	36YO0378	Prehistoric	-76.78244 40.03486
36YO0070	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.95505 39.99982	36YO0386	Prehistoric	-76.70799 40.0993
36YO0071	Prehistoric	-77.00585 40.01194	36YO0391	Prehistoric	-76.9553 39.9862
36YO0072	Prehistoric	-76.81241 40.12065	36YO0398	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.78901 40.04427
36YO0073	Prehistoric	-76.80289 40.11464	36YO0406	Prehistoric	-76.95709 39.98525
36YO0074	Prehistoric	-76.74994 40.10134	36YO0412	Prehistoric	-76.8764 40.14959
36YO0075	Prehistoric	-76.84455 40.09813	36YO0413	Prehistoric	-76.87492 40.14782
36YO0076	Prehistoric	-76.99488 40.00734	36YO0414	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.88523 39.93918
36YO0077	Prehistoric	-76.84876 40.09296	36YO0416	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.00087 40.02604
36YO0078	Prehistoric	-76.94809 39.99554			
Watershed 93-Piedmont-Piedmont Lowland:					
36AD0031	Prehistoric	-77.05326 39.79948	36AD0056	Prehistoric	-77.02324 39.78806
36AD0033	Prehistoric	-77.0528 39.80464	36AD0057	Prehistoric	-77.02076 39.78295
36AD0034	Prehistoric	-77.02913 39.8048	36AD0058	Prehistoric	-77.01934 39.77955
36AD0035	Prehistoric	-77.04121 39.81979	36AD0059	Prehistoric	-77.0188 39.77723
36AD0036	Prehistoric	-77.04284 39.81725	36AD0061	Prehistoric	-77.05667 39.77217
36AD0037	Prehistoric	-77.03856 39.81769	36AD0063	Prehistoric	-77.02293 39.79206
36AD0038	Prehistoric	-77.03719 39.82535	36AD0064	Prehistoric	-77.04941 39.8079
36AD0039	Prehistoric	-77.04905 39.82647	36AD0065	Prehistoric	-77.03344 39.81422
36AD0040	Prehistoric	-77.04277 39.83182	36AD0066	Prehistoric	-77.00118 39.82525
36AD0041	Prehistoric	-77.05503 39.78247	36AD0461	Prehistoric	-77.06085 39.77119
36AD0042	Prehistoric	-77.05672 39.78561	36AD0491	Prehistoric	-77.0202 39.85313
36AD0043	Prehistoric	-77.06119 39.79212	36AD0492	Prehistoric	-77.01747 39.85157
36AD0044	Prehistoric	-77.04659 39.7806	36AD0493	Prehistoric	-77.01913 39.84849
36AD0053	Prehistoric	-77.04718 39.77762	36YO0005	Prehistoric	-76.9769 39.8408
36AD0054	Prehistoric	-77.0382 39.76988	36YO0017	Prehistoric	-76.99762 39.78438
36AD0055	Prehistoric	-77.01637 39.7895	36YO0018	Prehistoric	-76.99831 39.79129
Watershed 93-Piedmont-Piedmont Upland:					
36AD0060	Prehistoric	-77.01128 39.77344	36YO0305	Prehistoric	-76.99061 39.77779
36YO0016	Prehistoric	-76.9827 39.779	36YO0408	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.99351 39.75889

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
Watershed 94-Piedmont-Piedmont Lowland:					
36CH0128	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.62754 40.02962	36CH0630	Prehistoric	-75.59568 40.03693
36CH0195	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.63412 40.01885	36CH0646	Prehistoric	-75.70952 40.014
36CH0196	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.63197 40.01971	36CH0647	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.70986 40.01052
36CH0261	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.62869 40.02668	36CH0648	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.70799 40.01094
36CH0262	Prehistoric	-75.63967 40.02697	36CH0649	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.71046 40.0117
36CH0263	Prehistoric	-75.64516 40.02151	36CH0650	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.61346 40.03221
36CH0326	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.67169 40.01753	36CH0655	Prehistoric	-75.60816 40.03452
36CH0327	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.66303 40.02252	36CH0694	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.62515 40.03041
36CH0328	Prehistoric	-75.65872 40.02332	36CH0699	Prehistoric	-75.90441 39.95678
36CH0329	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.65916 40.02231	36CH0716	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.63074 40.02401
36CH0330	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.65335 40.02327	36CH0717	Prehistoric	-75.63138 40.02282
36CH0331	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.64937 40.02405	36CH0718	Prehistoric	-75.6334 40.02431
36CH0332	Prehistoric	-75.64706 40.02358	36CH0721	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.59936 40.04846
36CH0333	Prehistoric	-75.63835 40.02549	36CH0722	Prehistoric	-75.5986 40.04325
36CH0334	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.63502 40.02737	36CH0723	Prehistoric	-75.59545 40.04181
36CH0335	Prehistoric	-75.63155 40.02816	36CH0724	Prehistoric	-75.59539 40.03919
36CH0336	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.62793 40.02409	36CH0725	Prehistoric	-75.59147 40.03551
36CH0337	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.63611 40.01692	36CH0757	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.63461 40.02132
36CH0338	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.64421 40.01485	36CH0758	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.70823 40.01211
36CH0340	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.70434 40.00658	36CH0759	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.64551 40.01666
36CH0341	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.64459 40.02555	36CH0760	Prehistoric	-75.62611 40.01942
36CH0342	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.58856 40.03361	36CH0763	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.63254 40.02009
36CH0343	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.59128 40.03291	36CH0775	Prehistoric	-75.63423 40.02106
36CH0344	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.60664 40.03147	36CH0776	Prehistoric	-75.63486 40.02133
36CH0345	Prehistoric	-75.60662 40.02707	36CH0777	Prehistoric	-75.63359 40.0214
36CH0346	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.60915 40.02706	36CH0778	Prehistoric	-75.63418 40.02246
36CH0347	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.61823 40.02201	36CH0779	Prehistoric	-75.63485 40.02234
36CH0348	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.62024 40.02374	36CH0780	Prehistoric	-75.63525 40.0219
36CH0349	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.62081 40.02517	36CH0781	Prehistoric	-75.63458 40.0208
36CH0351	Prehistoric	-75.63551 40.03785	36CH0782	Prehistoric	-75.63504 40.02071
36CH0352	Prehistoric	-75.6443 40.0272	36CH0783	Prehistoric	-75.63369 40.02035
36CH0354	Prehistoric	-75.61417 40.0416	36CH0784	Prehistoric	-75.63396 40.02194
36CH0355	Prehistoric	-75.62063 40.03914	36CH0871	Prehistoric	-75.59704 40.0476
36CH0356	Prehistoric	-75.61718 40.03663	36CH0872	Prehistoric	-75.60714 40.04609
36CH0357	Prehistoric	-75.61122 40.0352	36CH0875	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.59955 40.04789
36CH0358	Prehistoric	-75.61336 40.03364	36CH0876	Prehistoric	-75.60033 40.04769
36CH0471	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.86894 39.96729	36CH0877	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.60146 40.0473
36CH0472	Prehistoric	-75.86621 39.96784	36CH0885	Prehistoric	-75.58979 40.05063
36CH0509	Prehistoric	-75.71582 40.0146			
Watershed 94-Piedmont-Piedmont Upland:					
36CH0030	Prehistoric	-75.7185 39.91062	36CH0373	Prehistoric	-75.62591 39.89036
36CH0031	Prehistoric	-75.70544 39.93576	36CH0374	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.62283 39.89443
36CH0034	Prehistoric	-75.90701 39.97128	36CH0375	Prehistoric	-75.91721 40.07875
36CH0062	Prehistoric	-75.7288 39.93305	36CH0376	Prehistoric	-75.89173 40.07204
36CH0064	Prehistoric	-75.92044 40.10954	36CH0377	Prehistoric	-75.91179 40.07756
36CH0065	Prehistoric	-75.89158 40.09226	36CH0378	Prehistoric	-75.87745 40.07173
36CH0066	Prehistoric	-75.89006 40.09107	36CH0379	Prehistoric	-75.86608 40.07288
36CH0067	Prehistoric	-75.90241 40.09614	36CH0430	Prehistoric	-75.87319 40.08353
36CH0068	Prehistoric	-75.937 40.10079	36CH0431	Prehistoric	-75.87487 40.08424
36CH0069	Prehistoric	-75.87159 40.07766	36CH0432	Prehistoric	-75.87386 40.08447

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36CH0085	Prehistoric	-75.65286 39.97013	36CH0433	Prehistoric	-75.85213 40.08257
36CH0086	Prehistoric	-75.64478 39.93637	36CH0438	Prehistoric	-75.90248 40.07251
36CH0087	Prehistoric	-75.62607 39.89947	36CH0444	Prehistoric	-75.64576 39.90381
36CH0088	Prehistoric	-75.62519 39.89692	36CH0445	Prehistoric	-75.67244 39.91842
36CH0089	Prehistoric	-75.62744 39.89575	36CH0446	Prehistoric	-75.65316 39.86753
36CH0090	Prehistoric	-75.62509 39.89516	36CH0447	Prehistoric	-75.74297 39.93946
36CH0091	Prehistoric	-75.63217 39.90773	36CH0448	Prehistoric	-75.61083 39.90024
36CH0092	Prehistoric	-75.6412 39.90525	36CH0449	Prehistoric	-75.61483 39.89846
36CH0093	Prehistoric	-75.65446 39.89933	36CH0462	Prehistoric	-75.85916 40.03515
36CH0094	Prehistoric	-75.65327 39.90924	36CH0463	Prehistoric	-75.85883 40.03388
36CH0095	Prehistoric	-75.65633 39.90715	36CH0464	Prehistoric	-75.85612 40.03356
36CH0096	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.64335 39.91731	36CH0465	Prehistoric	-75.85837 40.03143
36CH0097	Prehistoric	-75.64951 39.91729	36CH0466	Prehistoric	-75.85349 40.02908
36CH0098	Prehistoric	-75.66283 39.91809	36CH0467	Prehistoric	-75.8477 40.02596
36CH0099	Prehistoric	-75.66654 39.92243	36CH0468	Prehistoric	-75.86775 40.00058
36CH0100	Prehistoric	-75.66944 39.92295	36CH0469	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.86898 39.99899
36CH0126	Prehistoric	-75.67374 40.06392	36CH0470	Prehistoric	-75.872 39.99781
36CH0129	Prehistoric	-75.76381 40.13218	36CH0479	Prehistoric	-75.878 40.00297
36CH0130	Prehistoric	-75.77898 40.13747	36CH0483	Prehistoric	-75.93867 40.09313
36CH0131	Prehistoric	-75.90566 40.11835	36CH0486	Prehistoric	-75.69442 39.89161
36CH0132	Prehistoric	-75.87564 40.06652	36CH0487	Prehistoric	-75.76203 40.09305
36CH0133	Prehistoric	-75.87776 40.11654	36CH0494	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.69946 40.09626
36CH0134	Prehistoric	-75.88299 40.11587	36CH0495	Prehistoric	-75.71857 39.97785
36CH0135	Prehistoric	-75.89131 40.09749	36CH0496	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.67717 39.95821
36CH0136	Prehistoric	-75.89158 40.08521	36CH0499	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.65041 39.92645
36CH0137	Prehistoric	-75.88669 40.08472	36CH0502	Prehistoric	-75.81754 40.04423
36CH0138	Prehistoric	-75.90194 40.11012	36CH0503	Prehistoric	-75.7057 40.08745
36CH0139	Prehistoric	-75.91903 40.10631	36CH0511	Prehistoric	-75.9113 40.08009
36CH0140	Prehistoric	-75.91885 40.10837	36CH0512	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.89086 40.07473
36CH0141	Prehistoric	-75.90329 40.10741	36CH0513	Prehistoric	-75.89369 40.08971
36CH0142	Prehistoric	-75.90013 40.09828	36CH0514	Prehistoric	-75.88294 40.10932
36CH0149	Prehistoric	-75.68591 39.92992	36CH0515	Prehistoric	-75.81511 40.10379
36CH0150	Prehistoric	-75.76722 40.09131	36CH0522	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.84733 39.90558
36CH0151	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.76411 40.08424	36CH0523	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.8416 39.9075
36CH0152	Prehistoric	-75.86996 40.08165	36CH0525	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.77546 39.94423
36CH0153	Prehistoric	-75.86851 40.08051	36CH0527	Prehistoric	-75.75672 40.11371
36CH0154	Prehistoric	-75.81438 40.07395	36CH0528	Prehistoric	-75.79373 40.05035
36CH0155	Prehistoric	-75.81064 40.0918	36CH0529	Prehistoric	-75.925 40.07069
36CH0156	Prehistoric	-75.79435 40.12409	36CH0530	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.81673 40.08198
36CH0157	Prehistoric	-75.87392 40.08056	36CH0532	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.76912 40.08584
36CH0158	Prehistoric	-75.86311 40.07067	36CH0533	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.75794 40.08763
36CH0159	Prehistoric	-75.86539 40.1103	36CH0534	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.70868 40.09368
36CH0161	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.61579 39.88902	36CH0535	Prehistoric	-75.74726 40.0891
36CH0162	Prehistoric	-75.62017 39.8981	36CH0536	Prehistoric	-75.88299 40.07495
36CH0163	Prehistoric	-75.61731 39.90099	36CH0537	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.89799 40.07318
36CH0164	Prehistoric	-75.61967 39.90394	36CH0538	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.70349 40.09482
36CH0165	Prehistoric	-75.59615 39.91641	36CH0543	Prehistoric	-75.90877 40.08116
36CH0166	Prehistoric	-75.59951 39.91946	36CH0544	Prehistoric	-75.90865 40.07998
36CH0167	Prehistoric	-75.60125 39.91419	36CH0545	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.90854 40.07916
36CH0177	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.64698 39.91965	36CH0546	Prehistoric	-75.78515 40.11434
36CH0178	Prehistoric	-75.65196 39.92559	36CH0547	Prehistoric	-75.90336 40.11296
36CH0179	Prehistoric	-75.64627 39.92676	36CH0548	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.77762 40.07399

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36CH0180	Prehistoric	-75.63385 39.91847	36CH0549	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.6079 39.89332
36CH0181	Prehistoric	-75.63288 39.92254	36CH0550	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.60405 39.89322
36CH0182	Prehistoric	-75.66334 39.96341	36CH0556	Prehistoric	-75.93512 40.07397
36CH0183	Prehistoric	-75.67841 39.9307	36CH0596	Prehistoric	-75.78574 40.12887
36CH0184	Prehistoric	-75.73159 39.93842	36CH0636	Prehistoric	-75.63448 39.9674
36CH0188	Prehistoric	-75.70587 39.89922	36CH0637	Prehistoric	-75.78143 40.07663
36CH0191	Prehistoric	-75.79064 40.12658	36CH0638	Prehistoric	-75.78086 40.07792
36CH0198	Prehistoric	-75.77758 40.13967	36CH0644	Prehistoric	-75.78336 39.90513
36CH0212	Prehistoric	-75.76301 40.13574	36CH0651	Prehistoric	-75.64236 39.98605
36CH0213	Prehistoric	-75.66869 39.91443	36CH0652	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.66391 39.99739
36CH0214	Prehistoric	-75.6719 39.92083	36CH0658	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.57416 39.91352
36CH0215	Prehistoric	-75.67192 39.9032	36CH0661	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.58319 39.91078
36CH0216	Prehistoric	-75.67762 39.89876	36CH0662	Prehistoric	-75.88868 39.99701
36CH0217	Prehistoric	-75.67951 39.91292	36CH0663	Prehistoric	-75.8889 39.99593
36CH0218	Prehistoric	-75.68334 39.91415	36CH0664	Prehistoric	-75.88896 39.99457
36CH0219	Prehistoric	-75.68951 39.91927	36CH0665	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.84321 40.02939
36CH0220	Prehistoric	-75.68595 39.89868	36CH0667	Prehistoric	-75.66602 40.05882
36CH0221	Prehistoric	-75.68887 39.90445	36CH0668	Prehistoric	-75.66614 40.06073
36CH0222	Prehistoric	-75.69213 39.92479	36CH0669	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.6635 40.06065
36CH0223	Prehistoric	-75.69433 39.92633	36CH0670	Prehistoric	-75.66441 40.06181
36CH0224	Prehistoric	-75.69141 39.88953	36CH0673	Prehistoric	-75.66956 40.0605
36CH0225	Prehistoric	-75.70039 39.90569	36CH0684	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.73049 39.9278
36CH0226	Prehistoric	-75.70166 39.90311	36CH0688	Prehistoric	-75.89384 40.07684
36CH0228	Prehistoric	-75.70374 39.90664	36CH0689	Prehistoric	-75.88746 40.07568
36CH0229	Prehistoric	-75.70996 39.90103	36CH0696	Prehistoric	-75.66545 40.06104
36CH0233	Prehistoric	-75.72905 39.89765	36CH0697	Prehistoric	-75.66448 40.06088
36CH0235	Prehistoric	-75.73689 39.92569	36CH0698	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.82301 39.99982
36CH0236	Prehistoric	-75.73982 39.92866	36CH0703	Prehistoric	-75.66399 39.87881
36CH0238	Prehistoric	-75.62218 39.92378	36CH0704	Prehistoric	-75.66323 39.87806
36CH0239	Prehistoric	-75.57001 39.90204	36CH0705	Prehistoric	-75.66239 39.87671
36CH0240	Prehistoric	-75.57009 39.90066	36CH0706	Prehistoric	-75.66179 39.87401
36CH0241	Prehistoric	-75.57217 39.89756	36CH0707	Prehistoric	-75.66202 39.87101
36CH0242	Prehistoric	-75.5852 39.90552	36CH0708	Prehistoric	-75.66186 39.8696
36CH0243	Prehistoric	-75.60014 39.90809	36CH0709	Prehistoric	-75.66431 39.86823
36CH0244	Prehistoric	-75.61066 39.9054	36CH0710	Prehistoric	-75.66381 39.871
36CH0245	Prehistoric	-75.61075 39.90257	36CH0711	Prehistoric	-75.85915 39.98463
36CH0246	Prehistoric	-75.61312 39.90097	36CH0712	Prehistoric	-75.85994 39.98616
36CH0247	Prehistoric	-75.61688 39.90487	36CH0713	Prehistoric	-75.85736 39.98601
36CH0248	Prehistoric	-75.6222 39.88206	36CH0727	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.62468 39.90019
36CH0258	Prehistoric	-75.60487 39.86366	36CH0728	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.62076 39.9004
36CH0259	Prehistoric	-75.60048 39.8742	36CH0731	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.70703 39.98295
36CH0264	Prehistoric	-75.76873 40.13565	36CH0739	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.75572 39.93492
36CH0265	Prehistoric	-75.88815 40.0718	36CH0740	Prehistoric	-75.89854 40.10063
36CH0266	Prehistoric	-75.92078 40.11343	36CH0741	Prehistoric	-75.89914 40.09434
36CH0267	Prehistoric	-75.91255 40.10741	36CH0742	Prehistoric	-75.93153 40.10707
36CH0268	Prehistoric	-75.90763 40.104	36CH0747	Prehistoric	-75.86848 40.1159
36CH0270	Prehistoric	-75.88747 40.11341	36CH0748	Prehistoric	-75.65957 40.06187
36CH0271	Prehistoric	-75.88507 40.11357	36CH0749	Prehistoric	-75.66019 40.06048
36CH0272	Prehistoric	-75.89857 40.10775	36CH0750	Prehistoric	-75.66264 40.05931
36CH0273	Prehistoric	-75.88162 40.08656	36CH0751	Prehistoric	-75.90976 40.11448
36CH0274	Prehistoric	-75.92351 40.11396	36CH0752	Prehistoric	-75.91263 40.1151
36CH0280	Prehistoric	-75.71976 39.93865	36CH0754	Prehistoric	-75.87753 40.10378

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36CH0281	Prehistoric	-75.63565 39.96352	36CH0755	Prehistoric	-75.88139 40.10254
36CH0282	Prehistoric	-75.63189 39.96388	36CH0756	Prehistoric	-75.88405 40.10365
36CH0283	Prehistoric	-75.64285 39.95817	36CH0761	Prehistoric	-75.66346 39.99601
36CH0284	Prehistoric	-75.67533 39.93685	36CH0768	Prehistoric	-75.70767 40.03874
36CH0285	Prehistoric	-75.67564 39.93507	36CH0774	Prehistoric	-75.63463 39.90606
36CH0286	Prehistoric	-75.66479 39.95541	36CH0817	Prehistoric	-75.90258 39.88341
36CH0287	Prehistoric	-75.65787 39.9672	36CH0832	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.9063 39.89404
36CH0288	Prehistoric	-75.65646 39.92794	36CH0833	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.90489 39.89008
36CH0289	Prehistoric	-75.65206 39.9586	36CH0834	Prehistoric	-75.76437 40.01333
36CH0291	Prehistoric	-75.63105 39.92043	36CH0858	Prehistoric	-75.8235 40.00434
36CH0292	Prehistoric	-75.62705 39.92153	36CH0870	Prehistoric	-75.70678 40.0232
36CH0293	Prehistoric	-75.62644 39.91585	36CH0873	Prehistoric	-75.6156 40.04412
36CH0294	Prehistoric	-75.69566 39.90856	36CH0874	Prehistoric	-75.61731 40.04381
36CH0296	Prehistoric	-75.8732 40.08353	36CH0884	Prehistoric	-75.76012 40.00753
36CH0297	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.87141 40.06802	36DE0006	Prehistoric	-75.59275 39.84124
36CH0298	Prehistoric	-75.81932 40.05661	36DE0007	Prehistoric	-75.58849 39.84452
36CH0299	Prehistoric	-75.80884 40.05968	36DE0010	Prehistoric	-75.58451 39.87262
36CH0300	Prehistoric	-75.77591 40.01159	36DE0011	Prehistoric	-75.58801 39.87037
36CH0311	Prehistoric	-75.57892 39.91984	36DE0012	Prehistoric	-75.549 39.86768
36CH0312	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.60996 39.89052	36DE0013	Prehistoric	-75.59156 39.85814
36CH0313	Prehistoric	-75.59558 39.8759	36DE0014	Prehistoric	-75.58054 39.87142
36CH0319	Prehistoric	-75.78052 40.12547	36DE0047	Prehistoric	-75.55882 39.8874
36CH0320	Prehistoric	-75.78085 40.13829	36DE0084	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.57106 39.87371
36CH0339	Prehistoric	-75.88731 40.07445	36DE0088	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.59216 39.86991
36CH0350	Prehistoric	-75.63591 40.04121	36DE0089	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.54916 39.87373
36CH0353	Prehistoric	-75.86297 40.12643	36DE0109	Prehistoric	-75.58311 39.87374
36CH0359	Prehistoric	-75.60453 40.01883	36DE0123	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.58985 39.87
36CH0360	Prehistoric	-75.6093 40.01957	36LA0169	Prehistoric	-75.96312 40.09079
36CH0361	Prehistoric	-75.60714 40.01665	36LA0170	Prehistoric	-75.94215 40.09263
36CH0362	Prehistoric	-75.6022 40.01651	36LA0912	Prehistoric	-75.97477 40.09126
36CH0365	Prehistoric	-75.85192 40.09762	36LA0913	Prehistoric	-75.97813 40.09165
36CH0367	Prehistoric	-75.86061 40.09944	36LA0962	Prehistoric	-75.96619 40.09091
36CH0368	Prehistoric	-75.82251 40.04095	36LA1139	Prehistoric	-75.98418 40.09223
36CH0369	Prehistoric	-75.77502 40.11664	36LA1210	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.94725 40.09004
36CH0372	Prehistoric	-75.62788 39.89881			
Watershed 96-Piedmont-Piedmont Lowland:					
36CH0081	Prehistoric	-75.96944 39.94957	36LA0871	Prehistoric	-76.06219 39.9271
36CH0504	Prehistoric	-75.97143 39.94328	36LA0872	Prehistoric	-76.06048 39.92781
36CH0505	Prehistoric	-75.97078 39.94336	36LA0873	Prehistoric	-76.06277 39.92539
36CH0506	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.96947 39.94377	36LA0874	Prehistoric	-76.06076 39.92631
36CH0507	Prehistoric	-75.97105 39.94398	36LA0875	Prehistoric	-76.06464 39.92344
36CH0700	Prehistoric	-75.94241 39.9499	36LA0878	Prehistoric	-76.01409 40.05509
36CH0701	Prehistoric	-75.98494 39.94451	36LA0879	Prehistoric	-76.01141 40.05392
36CH0835	Prehistoric	-75.97032 39.94167	36LA0883	Prehistoric	-75.94213 40.03603
36LA0162	Prehistoric	-76.21212 39.98108	36LA1129	Prehistoric	-76.19194 40.00119
36LA0200	Prehistoric	-76.20281 39.99695	36LA1131	Prehistoric	-76.02422 40.02119
36LA0201	Prehistoric	-76.21487 39.98335	36LA1132	Prehistoric	-76.1536 40.01075
36LA0202	Prehistoric	-76.2473 39.96443	36LA1133	Prehistoric	-76.15031 40.00894
36LA0209	Prehistoric	-76.17031 40.00791	36LA1134	Prehistoric	-76.152 40.0049
36LA0210	Prehistoric	-76.13272 40.0081	36LA1135	Prehistoric	-76.14979 40.01168
36LA0214	Prehistoric	-76.16076 39.91847	36LA1137	Prehistoric	-76.21049 39.99188
36LA0216	Prehistoric	-76.29078 39.96826	36LA1184	Prehistoric	-76.15077 39.97908

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LA0217	Prehistoric	-76.25494 39.96542	36LA1186	Prehistoric	-76.15304 39.9764
36LA0220	Prehistoric	-76.22112 39.98153	36LA1241	Prehistoric	-75.96691 40.03227
36LA0225	Prehistoric	-76.25295 39.96972	36LA1264	Prehistoric	-76.06582 40.03717
36LA0226	Prehistoric	-76.2287 39.98163	36LA1267	Prehistoric	-76.26829 39.9649
36LA0228	Prehistoric	-76.22167 39.9825	36LA1288	Prehistoric	-76.19933 39.96633
36LA0229	Prehistoric	-76.22407 39.97827	36LA1289	Prehistoric	-76.19978 39.97118
36LA0230	Prehistoric	-76.24384 39.96104	36LA1296	Prehistoric	-75.99981 39.93832
36LA0231	Prehistoric	-76.23378 39.98769	36LA1297	Prehistoric	-76.00181 39.93685
36LA0232	Prehistoric	-76.19038 39.90739	36LA1303	Prehistoric	-76.15285 39.99147
36LA0233	Prehistoric	-76.1881 39.91096	36LA1304	Prehistoric	-76.13702 39.9747
36LA0264	Prehistoric	-75.94275 40.05092	36LA1305	Prehistoric	-76.14255 39.97457
36LA0265	Prehistoric	-75.94798 40.04772	36LA1308	Prehistoric	-76.09734 40.01617
36LA0266	Prehistoric	-75.95568 40.04093	36LA1309	Prehistoric	-75.95626 40.04642
36LA0267	Prehistoric	-75.95987 40.04133	36LA1310	Prehistoric	-75.99236 39.93953
36LA0268	Prehistoric	-75.95914 40.04311	36LA1314	Prehistoric	-76.23163 39.96451
36LA0269	Prehistoric	-75.95553 40.04825	36LA1332	Prehistoric	-76.12364 39.96896
36LA0270	Prehistoric	-75.95415 40.0518	36LA1333	Prehistoric	-76.01689 40.02102
36LA0271	Prehistoric	-75.96497 40.04108	36LA1377	Prehistoric	-76.15685 39.97604
36LA0272	Prehistoric	-75.96233 40.0403	36LA1378	Prehistoric	-76.1687 39.97193
36LA0275	Prehistoric	-75.95484 40.05475	36LA1379	Prehistoric	-76.17049 39.96909
36LA0333	Prehistoric	-76.17879 39.9086	36LA1380	Prehistoric	-76.18665 39.99801
36LA0334	Prehistoric	-76.18652 39.9852	36LA1381	Prehistoric	-76.19014 39.99586
36LA0350	Prehistoric	-76.08014 39.99528	36LA1385	Prehistoric	-76.04051 40.0539
36LA0351	Prehistoric	-75.947 40.05062	36LA1386	Prehistoric	-75.98731 40.05548
36LA0707	Prehistoric	-76.05908 39.92499	36LA1386	Prehistoric	-75.98727 40.05545
36LA0777	Prehistoric	-76.06157 39.92396	36LA1394	Prehistoric	-76.22278 39.96825
36LA0851	Prehistoric	-76.07149 39.92499	36LA1396	Prehistoric	-75.94732 40.04628
36LA0852	Prehistoric	-76.06954 39.92541	36LA1397	Prehistoric	-75.9597 40.02073
36LA0853	Prehistoric	-76.06885 39.92453	36LA1398	Prehistoric	-75.96053 40.01398
36LA0854	Prehistoric	-76.07119 39.92332	36LA1399	Prehistoric	-75.95718 40.01488
36LA0855	Prehistoric	-76.07421 39.92295	36LA1402	Prehistoric	-76.00072 40.0527
36LA0856	Prehistoric	-76.07377 39.92195	36LA1410	Prehistoric	-76.21999 39.992
36LA0857	Prehistoric	-76.07359 39.92098	36LA1416	Prehistoric	-76.24878 39.95994
36LA0858	Prehistoric	-76.07228 39.91993	36LA1418	Prehistoric	-76.2315 39.96537
36LA0859	Prehistoric	-76.06905 39.92303	36LA1423	Prehistoric	-76.02614 40.0536
36LA0860	Prehistoric	-76.0677 39.92349	36LA1427	Prehistoric	-76.16562 40.00443
36LA0861	Prehistoric	-76.06645 39.92261	36LA1428	Prehistoric	-76.16158 40.01212
36LA0862	Prehistoric	-76.06836 39.92179	36LA1430	Prehistoric	-76.20009 40.00154
36LA0863	Prehistoric	-76.0686 39.91956	36LA1431	Prehistoric	-76.17476 40.00693
36LA0864	Prehistoric	-76.06541 39.92065	36LA1435	Prehistoric	-76.11138 39.99261
36LA0865	Prehistoric	-76.06541 39.91942	36LA1437	Prehistoric	-76.15645 40.00075
36LA0866	Prehistoric	-76.06342 39.91935	36LA1491	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.99253 40.01741
36LA0867	Prehistoric	-76.06757 39.91737	36LA1503	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.0144 39.99115
36LA0870	Prehistoric	-76.06566 39.92547	36LA1510	Prehistoric	-76.21772 39.9889
Watershed 96-Piedmont-Piedmont Upland:					
36CH0017	Prehistoric	-75.90161 39.80497	36LA0573	Prehistoric	-76.1498 39.76254
36CH0021	Prehistoric	-75.89932 39.81346	36LA0574	Prehistoric	-76.15034 39.76306
36CH0025	Prehistoric	-75.90323 39.80158	36LA0575	Prehistoric	-76.14904 39.76342
36CH0077	Prehistoric	-75.89137 39.83204	36LA0576	Prehistoric	-76.15066 39.76361
36CH0079	Prehistoric	-75.98506 39.96086	36LA0577	Prehistoric	-76.14964 39.76491
36CH0080	Prehistoric	-75.98668 39.96104	36LA0578	Prehistoric	-76.14904 39.7661
36CH0082	Prehistoric	-75.98407 39.96181	36LA0579	Prehistoric	-76.15062 39.76537

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36CH0083	Prehistoric	-75.98639 39.96266	36LA0580	Prehistoric	-76.15001 39.76649
36CH0473	Prehistoric	-75.88927 39.85718	36LA0581	Prehistoric	-76.15051 39.767
36CH0488	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.12378 39.72331	36LA0582	Prehistoric	-76.151 39.76611
36CH0516	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.04037 39.79454	36LA0583	Prehistoric	-76.15173 39.76528
36CH0517	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.03802 39.79561	36LA0584	Prehistoric	-76.01389 39.96436
36CH0519	Prehistoric	-75.96076 39.83482	36LA0585	Prehistoric	-76.0153 39.96338
36CH0676	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.8754 39.73526	36LA0586	Prehistoric	-76.01687 39.96344
36CH0743	Prehistoric	-75.91841 40.05854	36LA0587	Prehistoric	-76.01879 39.96275
36CH0861	Prehistoric	-75.93979 39.84718	36LA0588	Prehistoric	-76.02091 39.96318
36CH0862	Prehistoric	-75.96338 39.83311	36LA0589	Prehistoric	-76.01597 39.9623
36CH0863	Prehistoric	-75.96965 39.8292	36LA0590	Prehistoric	-76.01769 39.96251
36CH0864	Prehistoric	-75.97029 39.82896	36LA0591	Prehistoric	-76.01835 39.96167
36CH0865	Prehistoric	-75.97889 39.8245	36LA0592	Prehistoric	-76.01953 39.96202
36CH0866	Prehistoric	-75.98358 39.82321	36LA0593	Prehistoric	-76.02054 39.96205
36CH0869	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.90182 39.84224	36LA0594	Prehistoric	-76.01696 39.96088
36CH0887	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.95979 39.98738	36LA0595	Prehistoric	-76.01437 39.96191
36CH0888	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.95749 39.98277	36LA0596	Prehistoric	-76.01448 39.96085
36CH0890	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.95764 39.98555	36LA0597	Prehistoric	-76.01577 39.96047
36CH0918	Prehistoric	-75.90165 39.83478	36LA0598	Prehistoric	-76.01701 39.96
36CH0920	Prehistoric	-75.98631 39.87863	36LA0599	Prehistoric	-76.01907 39.95902
36CH0923	Prehistoric	-75.92839 39.72857	36LA0600	Prehistoric	-76.02107 39.95976
36LA0002	Prehistoric	-76.36114 39.90646	36LA0601	Prehistoric	-76.0214 39.96039
36LA0011	Prehistoric	-76.34521 39.8731	36LA0602	Prehistoric	-76.02259 39.95905
36LA0015	Prehistoric	-76.18926 39.75107	36LA0603	Prehistoric	-76.02189 39.95854
36LA0016	Prehistoric	-76.18949 39.73482	36LA0604	Prehistoric	-76.0205 39.95799
36LA0017	Prehistoric	-76.16412 39.73788	36LA0605	Prehistoric	-76.02272 39.95735
36LA0018	Prehistoric	-76.14643 39.76545	36LA0606	Prehistoric	-76.01894 39.95773
36LA0019	Prehistoric	-76.10058 39.93184	36LA0607	Prehistoric	-76.01996 39.95742
36LA0038	Prehistoric	-76.1038 39.93867	36LA0608	Prehistoric	-76.02116 39.95717
36LA0076	Prehistoric	-75.96976 40.0815	36LA0609	Prehistoric	-76.02412 39.95838
36LA0103	Prehistoric	-76.29601 39.82242	36LA0610	Prehistoric	-76.0246 39.95967
36LA0107	Prehistoric	-75.96977 40.08316	36LA0611	Prehistoric	-76.02437 39.9614
36LA0115	Prehistoric	-76.35812 39.90508	36LA0612	Prehistoric	-76.02672 39.95874
36LA0117	Prehistoric	-76.36698 39.88745	36LA0613	Prehistoric	-76.02518 39.95767
36LA0121	Prehistoric	-76.02878 39.95809	36LA0614	Prehistoric	-76.02495 39.95696
36LA0122	Prehistoric	-76.02209 39.96139	36LA0615	Prehistoric	-76.0274 39.95704
36LA0123	Prehistoric	-76.01034 39.96141	36LA0616	Prehistoric	-76.0295 39.95687
36LA0124	Prehistoric	-76.01636 39.95847	36LA0818	Prehistoric	-76.0479 39.94553
36LA0136	Prehistoric	-76.01311 39.97682	36LA0819	Prehistoric	-76.04822 39.94446
36LA0137	Prehistoric	-76.01078 39.97759	36LA0820	Prehistoric	-76.04998 39.94547
36LA0138	Prehistoric	-76.01208 39.97784	36LA0821	Prehistoric	-76.04931 39.94375
36LA0139	Prehistoric	-76.07712 39.93717	36LA0822	Prehistoric	-76.05111 39.94334
36LA0140	Prehistoric	-76.07095 39.93072	36LA0823	Prehistoric	-76.05006 39.94207
36LA0141	Prehistoric	-76.01148 39.97578	36LA0824	Prehistoric	-76.05426 39.94267
36LA0142	Prehistoric	-76.00915 39.97211	36LA0825	Prehistoric	-76.05292 39.94202
36LA0143	Prehistoric	-76.00734 39.97055	36LA0826	Prehistoric	-76.05144 39.94133
36LA0144	Prehistoric	-76.00563 39.96979	36LA0827	Prehistoric	-76.05408 39.94026
36LA0145	Prehistoric	-76.00543 39.96717	36LA0828	Prehistoric	-76.05239 39.94003
36LA0146	Prehistoric	-76.07564 39.93562	36LA0829	Prehistoric	-76.05032 39.94021
36LA0147	Prehistoric	-76.07632 39.93926	36LA0830	Prehistoric	-76.04987 39.93951
36LA0148	Prehistoric	-76.07505 39.93941	36LA0831	Prehistoric	-76.05038 39.93846
36LA0149	Prehistoric	-75.94675 40.077	36LA0832	Prehistoric	-76.05011 39.93757

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LA0150	Prehistoric	-75.95547 40.07997	36LA0833	Prehistoric	-76.05235 39.93835
36LA0168	Prehistoric	-75.97316 40.08304	36LA0834	Prehistoric	-76.05388 39.93812
36LA0172	Prehistoric	-76.23043 39.91965	36LA0835	Prehistoric	-76.05277 39.93615
36LA0173	Prehistoric	-76.22099 39.93963	36LA0836	Prehistoric	-76.04984 39.93675
36LA0174	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.23491 39.95369	36LA0837	Prehistoric	-76.04941 39.93541
36LA0175	Prehistoric	-76.22889 39.94162	36LA0838	Prehistoric	-76.04969 39.93433
36LA0176	Prehistoric	-76.24632 39.94559	36LA0839	Prehistoric	-76.05226 39.93427
36LA0178	Prehistoric	-76.26981 39.91278	36LA0840	Prehistoric	-76.05109 39.93355
36LA0179	Prehistoric	-76.26751 39.9166	36LA0841	Prehistoric	-76.05121 39.93229
36LA0180	Prehistoric	-76.25175 39.95013	36LA0842	Prehistoric	-76.05303 39.93217
36LA0181	Prehistoric	-76.29022 39.91735	36LA0843	Prehistoric	-76.05182 39.93112
36LA0182	Prehistoric	-76.33364 39.90188	36LA0844	Prehistoric	-76.076 39.93239
36LA0189	Prehistoric	-76.0175 39.95663	36LA0845	Prehistoric	-76.07499 39.93111
36LA0192	Prehistoric	-76.34857 39.91095	36LA0846	Prehistoric	-76.07373 39.93031
36LA0203	Prehistoric	-76.27675 39.93511	36LA0847	Prehistoric	-76.07238 39.92971
36LA0204	Prehistoric	-76.28325 39.93365	36LA0848	Prehistoric	-76.07168 39.92891
36LA0215	Prehistoric	-76.26722 39.91158	36LA0849	Prehistoric	-76.07169 39.92773
36LA0218	Prehistoric	-76.24842 39.9469	36LA0850	Prehistoric	-76.06973 39.92671
36LA0219	Prehistoric	-76.25258 39.95505	36LA0868	Prehistoric	-76.06725 39.91626
36LA0227	Prehistoric	-76.25225 39.95364	36LA0869	Prehistoric	-76.06659 39.91489
36LA0235	Prehistoric	-76.31529 39.94955	36LA0877	Prehistoric	-76.00511 40.06432
36LA0237	Prehistoric	-76.20174 39.92976	36LA0880	Prehistoric	-76.0008 40.05632
36LA0238	Prehistoric	-76.27661 39.96447	36LA0884	Prehistoric	-75.9471 40.05679
36LA0249	Prehistoric	-76.16499 39.95935	36LA0918	Prehistoric	-76.21095 39.93811
36LA0250	Prehistoric	-76.24477 39.95342	36LA0920	Prehistoric	-76.29273 39.93138
36LA0251	Prehistoric	-76.26428 39.95012	36LA0924	Prehistoric	-75.98713 40.0896
36LA0260	Prehistoric	-76.02055 39.97722	36LA0925	Prehistoric	-75.97424 40.06798
36LA0261	Prehistoric	-76.02014 39.97439	36LA0960	Prehistoric	-75.94807 40.07888
36LA0262	Prehistoric	-76.01956 39.97353	36LA0961	Prehistoric	-75.94487 40.07173
36LA0263	Prehistoric	-76.0178 39.97831	36LA0963	Prehistoric	-75.97745 40.08027
36LA0273	Prehistoric	-75.95158 40.06754	36LA0967	Prehistoric	-76.01236 40.06026
36LA0274	Prehistoric	-75.98459 40.06674	36LA0970	Prehistoric	-76.14902 39.72768
36LA0276	Prehistoric	-75.96624 40.06839	36LA0971	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.097 39.76202
36LA0278	Prehistoric	-75.94087 40.04949	36LA0972	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.09318 39.76475
36LA0279	Prehistoric	-75.93951 40.05483	36LA0973	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.0761 39.77504
36LA0331	Prehistoric	-76.04294 40.05735	36LA0975	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.1112 39.75049
36LA0332	Prehistoric	-76.02166 40.06616	36LA0979	Prehistoric	-76.17382 39.72441
36LA0368	Prehistoric	-76.30405 39.81441	36LA0980	Prehistoric	-76.18612 39.75054
36LA0370	Prehistoric	-75.9697 40.07824	36LA0984	Prehistoric	-76.0245 40.06405
36LA0371	Prehistoric	-75.9872 40.09313	36LA0985	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.98887 40.06633
36LA0372	Prehistoric	-75.987 40.09514	36LA0986	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.9596 40.06846
36LA0430	Prehistoric	-75.99815 39.9643	36LA0987	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.96634 40.06745
36LA0523	Prehistoric	-76.14837 39.77582	36LA0989	Prehistoric	-75.97817 40.06699
36LA0524	Prehistoric	-76.14907 39.77485	36LA0992	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.97964 40.0663
36LA0525	Prehistoric	-76.15094 39.77534	36LA1106	Prehistoric	-75.93882 40.06136
36LA0526	Prehistoric	-76.1501 39.77338	36LA1115	Prehistoric	-76.28592 39.9328
36LA0527	Prehistoric	-76.14835 39.77386	36LA1116	Prehistoric	-76.28585 39.9318
36LA0528	Prehistoric	-76.14538 39.77491	36LA1126	Prehistoric	-76.26107 39.93932
36LA0529	Prehistoric	-76.14539 39.77347	36LA1128	Prehistoric	-76.21794 39.94083
36LA0530	Prehistoric	-76.14871 39.77235	36LA1130	Prehistoric	-76.25202 39.95144
36LA0531	Prehistoric	-76.14811 39.77153	36LA1136	Prehistoric	-76.31264 39.93578
36LA0532	Prehistoric	-76.15086 39.77162	36LA1141	Prehistoric	-76.00768 39.95954

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LA0533	Prehistoric	-76.15089 39.77054	36LA1142	Prehistoric	-76.0246 39.97424
36LA0534	Prehistoric	-76.15106 39.76946	36LA1143	Prehistoric	-76.02527 39.97574
36LA0535	Prehistoric	-76.14905 39.77017	36LA1144	Prehistoric	-76.02842 39.97627
36LA0536	Prehistoric	-76.14782 39.77075	36LA1231	Prehistoric	-76.01659 39.97258
36LA0537	Prehistoric	-76.14459 39.77092	36LA1232	Prehistoric	-76.01124 39.95978
36LA0538	Prehistoric	-76.14366 39.7703	36LA1233	Prehistoric	-76.01442 39.95902
36LA0539	Prehistoric	-76.14941 39.76941	36LA1234	Prehistoric	-76.00247 39.97454
36LA0540	Prehistoric	-76.14682 39.7695	36LA1238	Prehistoric	-75.94705 40.07399
36LA0541	Prehistoric	-76.14504 39.76946	36LA1239	Prehistoric	-75.96503 40.06429
36LA0542	Prehistoric	-76.14378 39.76857	36LA1240	Prehistoric	-75.96673 40.06664
36LA0543	Prehistoric	-76.14591 39.76829	36LA1270	Prehistoric	-76.31532 39.91527
36LA0544	Prehistoric	-76.14725 39.76845	36LA1286	Prehistoric	-76.10819 39.95026
36LA0545	Prehistoric	-76.14846 39.7678	36LA1287	Prehistoric	-76.1082 39.94729
36LA0546	Prehistoric	-76.14949 39.76729	36LA1292	Prehistoric	-76.09884 39.95395
36LA0547	Prehistoric	-76.14861 39.76695	36LA1293	Prehistoric	-76.10752 39.95442
36LA0548	Prehistoric	-76.14786 39.76648	36LA1294	Prehistoric	-76.10405 39.95127
36LA0549	Prehistoric	-76.14647 39.76709	36LA1295	Prehistoric	-76.10856 39.94866
36LA0550	Prehistoric	-76.14445 39.76675	36LA1302	Prehistoric	-76.09487 39.95876
36LA0551	Prehistoric	-76.14369 39.7668	36LA1319	Prehistoric	-75.99457 39.96245
36LA0552	Prehistoric	-76.14258 39.76742	36LA1320	Prehistoric	-75.99791 39.96299
36LA0553	Prehistoric	-76.14268 39.76491	36LA1342	Prehistoric	-76.35825 39.86987
36LA0554	Prehistoric	-76.14341 39.76549	36LA1343	Prehistoric	-76.35308 39.86941
36LA0555	Prehistoric	-76.14366 39.7645	36LA1344	Prehistoric	-76.26452 39.7989
36LA0556	Prehistoric	-76.14489 39.76399	36LA1346	Prehistoric	-76.29387 39.92194
36LA0557	Prehistoric	-76.14487 39.76282	36LA1350	Prehistoric	-76.33249 39.90394
36LA0558	Prehistoric	-76.14381 39.76241	36LA1351	Prehistoric	-76.33154 39.91221
36LA0559	Prehistoric	-76.14287 39.7629	36LA1352	Prehistoric	-76.32533 39.90618
36LA0560	Prehistoric	-76.14728 39.76272	36LA1353	Prehistoric	-76.32637 39.89654
36LA0561	Prehistoric	-76.14628 39.76333	36LA1392	Prehistoric	-76.15098 39.76857
36LA0562	Prehistoric	-76.1462 39.76397	36LA1395	Prehistoric	-75.94774 40.05346
36LA0563	Prehistoric	-76.14625 39.76461	36LA1400	Prehistoric	-75.95719 40.06625
36LA0564	Prehistoric	-76.14709 39.76396	36LA1401	Prehistoric	-75.98712 40.06076
36LA0565	Prehistoric	-76.14746 39.76327	36LA1417	Prehistoric	-76.20531 39.93649
36LA0566	Prehistoric	-76.14883 39.76196	36LA1419	Prehistoric	-76.24442 39.95563
36LA0567	Prehistoric	-76.14836 39.76353	36LA1434	Prehistoric	-76.02724 39.97229
36LA0568	Prehistoric	-76.14849 39.76448	36LA1440	Prehistoric	-76.16772 39.94109
36LA0569	Prehistoric	-76.1477 39.76477	36LA1457	Prehistoric	-76.07958 39.77305
36LA0570	Prehistoric	-76.14755 39.76561	36LA1488	Prehistoric	-76.16573 39.95922
36LA0571	Prehistoric	-76.15365 39.76224	36LA1489	Prehistoric	-76.19773 39.92668
36LA0572	Prehistoric	-76.15219 39.76261			
Watershed 97-Piedmont-Piedmont Lowland:					
36YO0004	Prehistoric	-76.78866 39.91704	36YO0212	Prehistoric	-76.76844 39.98216
36YO0006	Prehistoric	-76.96183 39.83813	36YO0217	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.77679 39.96676
36YO0007	Prehistoric	-76.96704 39.83566	36YO0218	Prehistoric	-76.7912 39.94786
36YO0008	Prehistoric	-76.95919 39.83547	36YO0219	Prehistoric	-76.75512 39.94208
36YO0011	Prehistoric	-76.95683 39.82728	36YO0220	Prehistoric	-76.75353 39.93988
36YO0012	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.7267 39.98988	36YO0221	Prehistoric	-76.77001 39.91827
36YO0015	Prehistoric	-76.96416 39.81077	36YO0222	Prehistoric	-76.80487 39.91968
36YO0020	Prehistoric	-76.95858 39.83333	36YO0223	Prehistoric	-76.79914 39.91067
36YO0021	Prehistoric	-76.96108 39.82818	36YO0224	Prehistoric	-76.81183 39.90203
36YO0022	Prehistoric	-76.95259 39.81889	36YO0225	Prehistoric	-76.87351 39.87339
36YO0023	Prehistoric	-76.95852 39.81384	36YO0226	Prehistoric	-76.74892 39.94349

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36YO0024	Prehistoric	-76.96172 39.81252	36YO0238	Prehistoric	-76.70693 40.00879
36YO0059	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.71494 40.01749	36YO0250	Prehistoric	-76.70492 40.02008
36YO0081	Prehistoric	-76.69101 40.01994	36YO0252	Prehistoric	-76.79941 39.92207
36YO0097	Prehistoric	-76.71156 40.0205	36YO0289	Prehistoric	-76.74626 39.94107
36YO0118	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.75574 39.93787	36YO0314	Prehistoric	-76.8386 39.88183
36YO0120	Prehistoric	-76.75322 39.92805	36YO0315	Prehistoric	-76.83222 39.89738
36YO0122	Prehistoric	-76.77755 39.9693	36YO0316	Prehistoric	-76.85273 39.88018
36YO0124	Prehistoric	-76.7095 40.01328	36YO0318	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.83659 39.89181
36YO0135	Prehistoric	-76.75827 39.94034	36YO0319	Prehistoric	-76.7762 39.96576
36YO0137	Prehistoric	-76.73054 40.0273	36YO0320	Prehistoric	-76.77335 39.96487
36YO0138	Prehistoric	-76.80308 39.91584	36YO0324	Prehistoric	-76.96662 39.83883
36YO0183	Prehistoric	-76.7492 40.01467	36YO0325	Prehistoric	-76.96685 39.83791
36YO0185	Prehistoric	-76.76135 39.92008	36YO0326	Prehistoric	-76.96559 39.83849
36YO0187	Prehistoric	-76.68844 40.0187	36YO0327	Prehistoric	-76.96483 39.83307
36YO0188	Prehistoric	-76.7733 39.96778	36YO0328	Prehistoric	-76.96367 39.83404
36YO0189	Prehistoric	-76.69734 40.01891	36YO0329	Prehistoric	-76.96428 39.83488
36YO0192	Prehistoric	-76.71368 40.01564	36YO0352	Prehistoric	-76.70194 40.01876
36YO0193	Prehistoric	-76.7146 40.01225	36YO0372	Prehistoric	-76.6859 40.01939
36YO0194	Prehistoric	-76.71657 40.01122	36YO0385	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.86551 39.86616
36YO0195	Prehistoric	-76.7489 40.0158	36YO0389	Prehistoric	-76.96848 39.8365
36YO0211	Prehistoric	-76.77543 39.98247	36YO0390	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.72226 40.03003
Watershed 97-Piedmont-Piedmont Upland:					
36YO0003	Prehistoric	-76.70919 39.76997	36YO0283	Prehistoric	-76.69653 39.89964
36YO0013	Prehistoric	-76.75025 39.92458	36YO0293	Prehistoric	-76.75047 39.9325
36YO0063	Prehistoric	-76.64468 40.05684	36YO0366	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.69584 40.01169
36YO0115	Prehistoric	-76.74555 39.89282	36YO0377	Prehistoric	-76.75787 39.9131
36YO0233	Prehistoric	-76.67071 39.93224	36YO0392	Prehistoric	-76.63719 40.04537
36YO0234	Prehistoric	-76.67722 39.94023	36YO0407	Prehistoric	-76.65431 39.93475
36YO0235	Prehistoric	-76.67529 39.91281	36YO0417	Prehistoric	-76.73111 39.86993
36YO0236	Prehistoric	-76.67521 39.91077	36YO0418	Prehistoric	-76.73015 39.86992
36YO0237	Prehistoric	-76.67182 39.90796	36YO0424	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.77428 39.85441
36YO0253	Prehistoric	-76.69644 39.76037			
Watershed 98-Piedmont-Piedmont Upland:					
36CH0160	Prehistoric	-75.57964 39.92944	36CH0844	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.52141 39.93997
36CH0200	Prehistoric	-75.46649 40.01951	36DE0001	Prehistoric	-75.41707 39.91753
36CH0237	Prehistoric	-75.56924 39.92511	36DE0002	Prehistoric	-75.49489 39.95545
36CH0275	Prehistoric	-75.48791 39.96594	36DE0009	Prehistoric	-75.51515 39.85631
36CH0276	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.47443 39.97014	36DE0015	Prehistoric	-75.47421 39.96689
36CH0277	Prehistoric	-75.48762 39.96442	36DE0016	Prehistoric	-75.4757 39.96399
36CH0301	Prehistoric	-75.53309 39.96833	36DE0017	Prehistoric	-75.47775 39.9622
36CH0302	Prehistoric	-75.55909 39.97104	36DE0018	Prehistoric	-75.48957 39.95834
36CH0303	Prehistoric	-75.53963 39.93735	36DE0019	Prehistoric	-75.51461 39.87769
36CH0304	Prehistoric	-75.54019 39.93287	36DE0020	Prehistoric	-75.44013 39.89238
36CH0305	Prehistoric	-75.56464 39.9311	36DE0028	Prehistoric	-75.47182 39.88633
36CH0306	Prehistoric	-75.56593 39.92876	36DE0029	Prehistoric	-75.47792 39.88508
36CH0307	Prehistoric	-75.57037 39.9233	36DE0039	Prehistoric	-75.52807 39.8694
36CH0308	Prehistoric	-75.54919 39.93084	36DE0045	Prehistoric	-75.56047 39.89096
36CH0309	Prehistoric	-75.54752 39.92676	36DE0046	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.55959 39.89012
36CH0310	Prehistoric	-75.5376 39.93689	36DE0048	Prehistoric	-75.50252 39.87213
36CH0314	Prehistoric	-75.55506 39.96666	36DE0049	Prehistoric	-75.52095 39.88157
36CH0315	Prehistoric	-75.52339 39.96828	36DE0055	Prehistoric	-75.40494 40.01679

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36CH0316	Prehistoric	-75.54444 39.9526	36DE0056	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.45255 39.96524
36CH0317	Prehistoric	-75.54001 39.95579	36DE0090	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.51721 39.86787
36CH0457	Prehistoric	-75.5695 40.02531	36DE0091	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.51367 39.86577
36CH0554	Prehistoric	-75.58368 39.95907	36DE0092	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.47991 39.83576
36CH0601	Prehistoric	-75.46643 40.02138	36DE0115	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.49028 39.90088
36CH0604	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.58178 39.92578	36DE0118	Prehistoric	-75.44597 39.90734
36CH0645	Prehistoric	-75.5578 39.93425	36DE0119	Prehistoric	-75.44353 39.90488
36CH0786	Prehistoric	-75.57151 39.95134	36DE0124	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.54431 39.86312
36CH0843	Prehistoric	-75.5239 39.93956	36DE0134	Prehistoric	-75.45852 39.90105

Watershed 101-Piedmont-Piedmont Lowland:

36YO0030	Prehistoric	-76.52527 39.96425	36YO0286	Prehistoric	-76.64461 39.98263
36YO0039	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.49994 39.97219	36YO0335	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.65888 39.98759
36YO0227	Prehistoric	-76.50426 39.98162	36YO0355	Prehistoric	-76.63991 39.98557
36YO0228	Prehistoric	-76.5094 39.97816	36YO0375	Prehistoric	-76.65376 39.9873
36YO0240	Prehistoric	-76.60995 39.99952	36YO0410	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.59449 40.01164
36YO0241	Prehistoric	-76.59798 40.00225	36YO0415	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.6454 39.97635

Watershed 101-Piedmont-Piedmont Upland:

36LA0020	Prehistoric	-76.35083 39.85501	36LA1451	Prehistoric	-76.36866 39.90602
36LA0028	Prehistoric	-76.25201 39.77279	36YO0001	Prehistoric	-76.36003 39.85523
36LA0029	Prehistoric	-76.29853 39.79879	36YO0002	Prehistoric	-76.36062 39.85409
36LA0030	Prehistoric	-76.37967 39.8795	36YO0010	Prehistoric	-76.35948 39.85457
36LA0031	Prehistoric	-76.3779 39.87872	36YO0014	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.37097 39.86068
36LA0032	Prehistoric	-76.37965 39.87734	36YO0019	Prehistoric	-76.53561 40.00945
36LA0033	Prehistoric	-76.37886 39.87582	36YO0025	Prehistoric	-76.52067 39.94795
36LA0034	Prehistoric	-76.32784 39.8197	36YO0027	Prehistoric	-76.51707 39.94552
36LA0035	Prehistoric	-76.29073 39.79727	36YO0028	Prehistoric	-76.5186 39.94462
36LA0043	Prehistoric	-76.27703 39.797	36YO0031	Prehistoric	-76.48692 39.95281
36LA0045	Prehistoric	-76.32047 39.813	36YO0033	Prehistoric	-76.47818 39.93626
36LA0047	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.30296 39.80828	36YO0034	Prehistoric	-76.43751 39.91857
36LA0051	Prehistoric	-76.30867 39.80859	36YO0035	Prehistoric	-76.39443 39.89355
36LA0056	Prehistoric	-76.31474 39.81277	36YO0036	Prehistoric	-76.38401 39.89737
36LA0060	Prehistoric	-76.36609 39.86365	36YO0041	Prehistoric	-76.57363 39.81786
36LA0061	Prehistoric	-76.36397 39.86306	36YO0084	Prehistoric	-76.39473 39.89718
36LA0062	Prehistoric	-76.37657 39.86902	36YO0176	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.59555 39.96773
36LA0063	Prehistoric	-76.34867 39.85459	36YO0186	Prehistoric	-76.35963 39.84469
36LA0064	Prehistoric	-76.38987 39.91977	36YO0229	Prehistoric	-76.3932 39.9065
36LA0065	Prehistoric	-76.3257 39.82036	36YO0230	Prehistoric	-76.38949 39.9039
36LA0066	Prehistoric	-76.37379 39.89804	36YO0231	Prehistoric	-76.39959 39.89997
36LA0067	Prehistoric	-76.30396 39.8022	36YO0232	Prehistoric	-76.39584 39.89603
36LA0068	Prehistoric	-76.29263 39.79666	36YO0249	Prehistoric	-76.45415 39.72513
36LA0069	Prehistoric	-76.29062 39.79884	36YO0282	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.59833 39.96238
36LA0070	Prehistoric	-76.29954 39.80152	36YO0288	Prehistoric	-76.43058 39.83853
36LA0118	Prehistoric	-76.32249 39.81403	36YO0301	Prehistoric	-76.45788 39.92263
36LA0120	Prehistoric	-76.31202 39.8131	36YO0302	Prehistoric	-76.43446 39.9196
36LA0184	Prehistoric	-76.38192 39.91395	36YO0309	Prehistoric	-76.50425 39.98665
36LA0185	Prehistoric	-76.38246 39.91629	36YO0312	Historic	-76.40889 39.89356
36LA0356	Prehistoric	-76.37299 39.92017	36YO0330	Prehistoric	-76.48419 39.94891
36LA0369	Prehistoric	-76.27467 39.80246	36YO0331	Prehistoric	-76.3918 39.82725

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36LA1091	Prehistoric	-76.38205 39.92039	36YO0348	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.67027 39.77346
36LA1092	Prehistoric	-76.38387 39.91718	36YO0349	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.67009 39.77166
36LA1093	Prehistoric	-76.38292 39.91522	36YO0388	Prehistoric	-76.41311 39.74604
36LA1252	Prehistoric	-76.30873 39.80999	36YO0411	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.5956 40.01377
36LA1253	Prehistoric	-76.3144 39.8123	36YO0430	Prehistoric	-76.3999 39.90669
36LA1254	Prehistoric	-76.31345 39.81185	36YO0432	Prehistoric	-76.40102 39.89754
36LA1255	Prehistoric	-76.38365 39.92134	36YO0433	Prehistoric	-76.40033 39.91013
36LA1345	Prehistoric	-76.27974 39.80034	36YO0434	Prehistoric & Historic	-76.39852 39.90549
36LA1449	Prehistoric	-76.37566 39.89679			
Watershed 104-Piedmont-Gettysburg-Newark Lowland:					
36AD0002	Prehistoric	-77.33902 39.89978	36AD0211	Prehistoric	-77.18481 39.84783
36AD0003	Prehistoric	-77.29238 39.89069	36AD0212	Prehistoric	-77.18652 39.84757
36AD0004	Prehistoric	-77.32969 39.85827	36AD0213	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.19097 39.84303
36AD0005	Prehistoric	-77.29198 39.86056	36AD0214	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.19106 39.8438
36AD0006	Prehistoric	-77.2892 39.85834	36AD0215	Prehistoric	-77.18946 39.84586
36AD0007	Prehistoric	-77.29325 39.81723	36AD0216	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.18489 39.84557
36AD0008	Prehistoric	-77.28776 39.81656	36AD0218	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.18593 39.84424
36AD0009	Prehistoric	-77.27531 39.79614	36AD0219	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.18981 39.84302
36AD0010	Prehistoric	-77.32615 39.80331	36AD0221	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.21316 39.84468
36AD0011	Prehistoric	-77.28446 39.76916	36AD0222	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.21405 39.84676
36AD0012	Prehistoric	-77.28396 39.76449	36AD0223	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.21132 39.84792
36AD0013	Prehistoric	-77.28829 39.85479	36AD0225	Prehistoric	-77.2243 39.85286
36AD0014	Prehistoric	-77.36061 39.84672	36AD0227	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.27392 39.82675
36AD0045	Prehistoric	-77.20518 39.81223	36AD0228	Prehistoric	-77.27316 39.82644
36AD0047	Prehistoric	-77.22741 39.84607	36AD0229	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.27647 39.82445
36AD0048	Prehistoric	-77.20606 39.81737	36AD0230	Prehistoric	-77.27455 39.82478
36AD0049	Prehistoric	-77.22055 39.8664	36AD0231	Prehistoric	-77.20465 39.81182
36AD0050	Prehistoric	-77.26437 39.85577	36AD0232	Prehistoric	-77.20514 39.81155
36AD0051	Prehistoric	-77.32483 39.76202	36AD0234	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.20766 39.83933
36AD0052	Prehistoric	-77.35712 39.81684	36AD0235	Prehistoric	-77.22393 39.81242
36AD0067	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.24481 39.81359	36AD0236	Prehistoric	-77.22476 39.81187
36AD0080	Prehistoric	-77.19956 39.78944	36AD0237	Prehistoric	-77.22609 39.8109
36AD0122	Prehistoric	-77.32141 39.90872	36AD0238	Prehistoric	-77.22482 39.81098
36AD0127	Prehistoric	-77.29767 39.73501	36AD0239	Prehistoric	-77.22554 39.81022
36AD0128	Prehistoric	-77.20815 39.7921	36AD0240	Prehistoric	-77.22566 39.80963
36AD0129	Prehistoric	-77.19534 39.83708	36AD0241	Prehistoric	-77.22384 39.81004
36AD0132	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.35632 39.89923	36AD0431	Prehistoric	-77.28874 39.82611
36AD0133	Prehistoric	-77.35465 39.89894	36AD0433	Prehistoric	-77.27938 39.83085
36AD0134	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.35009 39.8985	36AD0434	Prehistoric	-77.28153 39.82816
36AD0136	Prehistoric	-77.31843 39.90674	36AD0435	Prehistoric	-77.26772 39.83146
36AD0138	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.32318 39.90522	36AD0436	Prehistoric	-77.26688 39.82894
36AD0139	Prehistoric	-77.31444 39.90798	36AD0437	Prehistoric	-77.26946 39.82696
36AD0140	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.3068 39.91004	36AD0445	Prehistoric	-77.38107 39.75651
36AD0146	Prehistoric	-77.2927 39.8451	36AD0458	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.34852 39.85215
36AD0155	Prehistoric	-77.22528 39.85701	36AD0459	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.32734 39.85644
36AD0156	Prehistoric	-77.22172 39.85747	36AD0460	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.29114 39.85548
36AD0166	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.20262 39.75509	36AD0463	Prehistoric	-77.29579 39.73582
36AD0168	Prehistoric	-77.32724 39.76695	36AD0465	Prehistoric	-77.29649 39.72534
36AD0169	Prehistoric	-77.32981 39.77105	36AD0466	Prehistoric	-77.28827 39.72618
36AD0170	Prehistoric	-77.32447 39.77047	36AD0468	Prehistoric	-77.28573 39.72478
36AD0182	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.23278 39.85922	36AD0470	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.29285 39.7203
36AD0183	Prehistoric	-77.23185 39.85876	36AD0471	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.28759 39.72892

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36AD0184	Prehistoric	-77.2223 39.8553	36AD0472	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.28583 39.73288
36AD0185	Prehistoric	-77.29199 39.87356	36AD0473	Prehistoric	-77.22603 39.84075
36AD0186	Prehistoric	-77.25435 39.77509	36AD0476	Prehistoric	-77.18476 39.86178
36AD0188	Prehistoric	-77.21327 39.77849	36AD0477	Prehistoric	-77.18611 39.86223
36AD0189	Prehistoric	-77.20761 39.77648	36AD0478	Prehistoric	-77.18736 39.86395
36AD0190	Prehistoric	-77.23568 39.77682	36AD0479	Prehistoric	-77.18416 39.86504
36AD0191	Prehistoric	-77.2035 39.77728	36AD0480	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.19341 39.85984
36AD0194	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.14399 39.77748	36AD0482	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.19558 39.87075
36AD0195	Prehistoric	-77.13072 39.77753	36AD0487	Prehistoric	-77.19481 39.84027
36AD0197	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.10864 39.77723	36AD0488	Prehistoric	-77.19502 39.84271
36AD0198	Prehistoric	-77.16419 39.77633	36AD0490	Prehistoric	-77.19496 39.84592
36AD0199	Prehistoric	-77.13829 39.77744	36AD0495	Prehistoric	-77.28985 39.87597
36AD0203	Prehistoric	-77.25602 39.84024	36AD0496	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.29484 39.8761
36AD0204	Prehistoric	-77.29119 39.73735	36AD0497	Prehistoric	-77.35562 39.89841
36AD0205	Prehistoric	-77.29304 39.86267	36AD0500	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.22078 39.84469
36AD0207	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.18312 39.84784	36AD0501	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.22039 39.84172
36AD0208	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.18113 39.84466	36AD0502	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.21705 39.84206
36AD0209	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.18146 39.8437	36AD0503	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.21827 39.83947
36AD0210	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.18508 39.84699	36AD0504	Prehistoric & Historic	-77.21512 39.83876
Watershed 105-Piedmont-Piedmont Upland:					
36CH0001	Prehistoric	-75.7549 39.76168	36CH0393	Prehistoric	-75.77368 39.72658
36CH0002	Prehistoric	-75.76674 39.74915	36CH0394	Prehistoric	-75.77321 39.72503
36CH0003	Prehistoric	-75.77348 39.74972	36CH0395	Prehistoric	-75.77476 39.7227
36CH0004	Prehistoric	-75.77508 39.75247	36CH0396	Prehistoric	-75.77537 39.72429
36CH0005	Prehistoric	-75.7772 39.75221	36CH0397	Prehistoric	-75.77564 39.72585
36CH0006	Prehistoric	-75.76808 39.75976	36CH0398	Prehistoric	-75.7765 39.72714
36CH0007	Prehistoric	-75.76973 39.76608	36CH0399	Prehistoric	-75.77576 39.72859
36CH0008	Prehistoric	-75.81927 39.73412	36CH0400	Prehistoric	-75.77754 39.73038
36CH0009	Prehistoric	-75.79395 39.7308	36CH0401	Prehistoric	-75.77782 39.73209
36CH0010	Prehistoric	-75.79851 39.72606	36CH0402	Prehistoric	-75.7801 39.73111
36CH0011	Prehistoric	-75.78252 39.74494	36CH0403	Prehistoric	-75.77997 39.73038
36CH0012	Prehistoric	-75.77365 39.77761	36CH0404	Prehistoric	-75.77884 39.7296
36CH0013	Prehistoric	-75.76609 39.75551	36CH0405	Prehistoric	-75.77812 39.72801
36CH0014	Prehistoric	-75.86156 39.81125	36CH0406	Prehistoric	-75.77957 39.72751
36CH0015	Prehistoric	-75.79145 39.73646	36CH0407	Prehistoric	-75.77845 39.72581
36CH0016	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.76584 39.75284	36CH0408	Prehistoric	-75.77719 39.72419
36CH0018	Prehistoric	-75.77416 39.74289	36CH0409	Prehistoric	-75.77669 39.72256
36CH0019	Prehistoric	-75.79703 39.7735	36CH0410	Prehistoric	-75.77851 39.72263
36CH0020	Prehistoric	-75.79641 39.77522	36CH0411	Prehistoric	-75.78049 39.72269
36CH0022	Prehistoric	-75.758 39.77042	36CH0412	Prehistoric	-75.77924 39.72431
36CH0023	Prehistoric	-75.73655 39.78046	36CH0413	Prehistoric	-75.78143 39.72497
36CH0024	Prehistoric	-75.81506 39.73389	36CH0414	Prehistoric	-75.78377 39.72544
36CH0026	Prehistoric	-75.80291 39.7321	36CH0415	Prehistoric	-75.7861 39.72385
36CH0027	Prehistoric	-75.81753 39.73255	36CH0416	Prehistoric	-75.78763 39.72392
36CH0028	Prehistoric	-75.78469 39.8147	36CH0417	Prehistoric	-75.7894 39.72388
36CH0029	Prehistoric	-75.81551 39.73711	36CH0418	Prehistoric	-75.7887 39.72516
36CH0033	Prehistoric	-75.83926 39.81979	36CH0419	Prehistoric	-75.7901 39.72558
36CH0048	Prehistoric	-75.73785 39.78975	36CH0420	Prehistoric	-75.78582 39.7261
36CH0049	Prehistoric	-75.74161 39.78249	36CH0421	Prehistoric	-75.7833 39.72653
36CH0051	Prehistoric	-75.78083 39.82152	36CH0422	Prehistoric	-75.78359 39.72765
36CH0052	Prehistoric	-75.84005 39.81742	36CH0423	Prehistoric	-75.7819 39.72938
36CH0057	Prehistoric	-75.79011 39.73858	36CH0424	Prehistoric	-75.78343 39.73046

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36CH0058	Prehistoric	-75.79591 39.73631	36CH0425	Prehistoric	-75.78425 39.72898
36CH0059	Prehistoric	-75.82029 39.73921	36CH0426	Prehistoric	-75.78516 39.73002
36CH0072	Prehistoric	-75.69899 39.84196	36CH0427	Prehistoric	-75.78765 39.72979
36CH0073	Prehistoric	-75.6652 39.86432	36CH0428	Prehistoric	-75.78971 39.72968
36CH0074	Prehistoric	-75.71042 39.86856	36CH0429	Prehistoric	-75.79081 39.73041
36CH0076	Prehistoric	-75.80616 39.82205	36CH0459	Prehistoric	-75.79443 39.82048
36CH0078	Prehistoric	-75.81709 39.76242	36CH0474	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.86557 39.81052
36CH0168	Prehistoric	-75.73996 39.86766	36CH0475	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.86143 39.80231
36CH0169	Prehistoric	-75.73694 39.8642	36CH0476	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.85889 39.79776
36CH0170	Prehistoric	-75.73207 39.86821	36CH0477	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.85278 39.78602
36CH0171	Prehistoric	-75.72786 39.86026	36CH0478	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.85122 39.78294
36CH0172	Prehistoric	-75.7271 39.8596	36CH0480	Prehistoric	-75.76928 39.75976
36CH0173	Prehistoric	-75.72564 39.87214	36CH0481	Prehistoric	-75.78113 39.75584
36CH0174	Prehistoric	-75.71527 39.87056	36CH0501	Prehistoric	-75.86361 39.80552
36CH0175	Prehistoric	-75.66457 39.85435	36CH0526	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.79626 39.81358
36CH0176	Prehistoric	-75.68027 39.86323	36CH0539	Prehistoric	-75.8278 39.80391
36CH0185	Prehistoric	-75.71209 39.87937	36CH0540	Prehistoric	-75.82173 39.79713
36CH0186	Prehistoric	-75.70789 39.87866	36CH0552	Prehistoric	-75.80477 39.78516
36CH0187	Prehistoric	-75.70077 39.87832	36CH0561	Prehistoric	-75.82267 39.80616
36CH0189	Prehistoric	-75.74205 39.89941	36CH0562	Prehistoric	-75.84045 39.81277
36CH0190	Prehistoric	-75.74716 39.89565	36CH0563	Prehistoric	-75.8317 39.81248
36CH0192	Prehistoric	-75.75481 39.86131	36CH0564	Prehistoric	-75.80483 39.79691
36CH0197	Prehistoric	-75.71323 39.85689	36CH0566	Prehistoric	-75.78542 39.81739
36CH0201	Prehistoric	-75.78981 39.72805	36CH0567	Prehistoric	-75.78218 39.816
36CH0202	Prehistoric	-75.78382 39.84105	36CH0568	Prehistoric	-75.79553 39.80967
36CH0203	Prehistoric	-75.78486 39.84332	36CH0569	Prehistoric	-75.81073 39.8115
36CH0204	Prehistoric	-75.78307 39.84391	36CH0570	Prehistoric	-75.78559 39.83339
36CH0205	Prehistoric	-75.78213 39.84263	36CH0571	Prehistoric	-75.82336 39.85292
36CH0206	Prehistoric	-75.78028 39.84092	36CH0572	Prehistoric	-75.8208 39.79602
36CH0207	Prehistoric	-75.77917 39.84234	36CH0573	Prehistoric	-75.83355 39.79688
36CH0208	Prehistoric	-75.77833 39.84396	36CH0574	Prehistoric	-75.80596 39.82987
36CH0209	Prehistoric	-75.77761 39.84269	36CH0575	Prehistoric	-75.80118 39.81831
36CH0210	Prehistoric	-75.77765 39.84118	36CH0615	Prehistoric	-75.80213 39.8226
36CH0227	Prehistoric	-75.69895 39.87545	36CH0616	Prehistoric	-75.79699 39.82066
36CH0230	Prehistoric	-75.71488 39.88431	36CH0617	Prehistoric	-75.80209 39.81436
36CH0231	Prehistoric	-75.71605 39.88672	36CH0618	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.80433 39.81036
36CH0232	Prehistoric	-75.73322 39.88952	36CH0619	Prehistoric	-75.80132 39.81038
36CH0234	Prehistoric	-75.73878 39.89395	36CH0620	Prehistoric	-75.80674 39.80517
36CH0249	Prehistoric	-75.79891 39.83906	36CH0621	Prehistoric	-75.80374 39.80923
36CH0250	Prehistoric	-75.80632 39.84163	36CH0666	Prehistoric	-75.86451 39.86463
36CH0251	Prehistoric	-75.78546 39.83047	36CH0674	Prehistoric	-75.78106 39.75443
36CH0252	Prehistoric	-75.74996 39.81168	36CH0720	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.86043 39.80147
36CH0253	Prehistoric	-75.77622 39.86545	36CH0753	Prehistoric	-75.78683 39.81665
36CH0254	Prehistoric	-75.78126 39.8611	36CH0787	Prehistoric	-75.86014 39.86583
36CH0255	Prehistoric	-75.76378 39.86881	36CH0792	Prehistoric	-75.84316 39.86087
36CH0256	Prehistoric	-75.76488 39.87182	36CH0794	Prehistoric	-75.84019 39.85988
36CH0257	Prehistoric	-75.78095 39.87363	36CH0795	Prehistoric	-75.83572 39.85851
36CH0366	Prehistoric	-75.74948 39.77918	36CH0796	Prehistoric	-75.80867 39.84563
36CH0370	Prehistoric	-75.77135 39.75966	36CH0797	Prehistoric	-75.80305 39.83991
36CH0371	Prehistoric	-75.77254 39.75912	36CH0800	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.7463 39.80635
36CH0385	Prehistoric	-75.77035 39.73228	36CH0802	Prehistoric	-75.74387 39.80549
36CH0386	Prehistoric	-75.77001 39.73124	36CH0804	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.73744 39.80156

Table A-9. Region 9 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
36CH0387	Prehistoric	-75.77167 39.7304	36CH0807	Prehistoric	-75.71956 39.79629
36CH0388	Prehistoric	-75.77271 39.73093	36CH0809	Prehistoric	-75.72624 39.79498
36CH0389	Prehistoric	-75.7721 39.72921	36CH0810	Prehistoric	-75.72664 39.79785
36CH0390	Prehistoric	-75.7724 39.72789	36CH0882	Prehistoric	-75.82769 39.80786
36CH0391	Prehistoric	-75.77411 39.72831	36CH0891	Prehistoric	-75.76431 39.76929
36CH0392	Prehistoric	-75.77492 39.73016			

Table A-10. Region 10 Archaeological Sites, by Watershed and Physiographic Region

Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates	Site No.	Component	X/Y Coordinates
Watershed 79-Atlantic Coastal Plain-Lowland and Intermediate Upland:					
36BU0172	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.76972 40.13165	36BU0347	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.866 40.12598
36BU0344	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.8805 40.12834	36BU0348	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.85874 40.12479
36BU0346	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.8673 40.12541	36BU0354	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.90099 40.16351
Watershed 80-Atlantic Coastal Plain-Lowland and Intermediate Upland:					
36BU0211	Prehistoric	-74.91177 40.0806	36BU0338	Prehistoric	-74.90135 40.11044
Watershed 88-Atlantic Coastal Plain-Lowland and Intermediate Upland:					
36PH0130	Prehistoric	-75.19754 39.94556			
Watershed 90-Atlantic Coastal Plain-Lowland and Intermediate Upland:					
36PH0023	Prehistoric	-74.98894 40.10927	36PH0131	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.14422 39.947
36PH0024	Prehistoric	-74.9904 40.1097	36PH0137	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.13428 39.96388
36PH0026	Prehistoric & Historic	-74.98195 40.04801	36PH0159	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.13332 39.96746
36PH0056	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.00224 40.0861	36PH0160	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.11642 39.97462
36PH0072	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.15499 39.95684	36PH0162	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.12425 39.97068
Watershed 98-Atlantic Coastal Plain-Lowland and Intermediate Upland:					
36DE0008	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.30983 39.87376	36DE0034	Prehistoric & Historic	-75.36194 39.84492
36DE0026	Prehistoric	-75.3973 39.85525	36DE0057	Prehistoric	-75.351 39.87812

APPENDIX B

TABLES OF ER SURVEYS BY REGION

Table B-1. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 1

ER Numbers				
1979-R001-042	1989-1662-065-C	1993-4193-063-B	2001-2888-125-J	2008-1415-059-C
1980-R001-027-A	1989-1675-003	1993-4317-051-E	2001-3704-125-B	2008-1415-059-D
1980-R001-042	1989-1675-003-A12	1994-0099-065-C	2001-3839-019-C	2008-1415-059-E
1981-0045-051-C	1989-1675-003-HHH	1994-0169-042-A	2001-3842-021-B	2008-1561-007-B
1981-0074-003-B	1989-1675-003-III	1994-0289-009-C	2001-4001-007-B	2008-1571-033-B
1981-0119-042-B	1989-1699-031-B	1994-0393-111	2001-6011-005-B	2008-1608-059-C
1981-0119-042-C	1989-1706-129-E	1994-0545-121	2001-6013-019-B	2008-1729-021-B
1981-0150-042-J	1989-1706-129-F	1994-0576-125-D	2001-6032-111-B	2008-1794-019-B
1981-0150-042-P	1989-1717-005-B	1994-0609-129-B	2001-6047-125-B	2008-1813-003-E
1981-0372-005-I	1989-1725-005-T	1994-0659-051-C	2001-6076-129-B	2008-1853-125-A
1981-0379-042-A	1989-R001-059	1994-0679-003-B	2001-6078-129-G	2008-1853-125-B
1981-0379-042-B	1989-R003-051	1994-0694-007-D	2001-6094-009-B	2008-1887-059-D
1981-0405-035-B	1989-R004-042	1994-0744-063-B	2001-6108-051-B	2008-1903-007-A
1981-0405-035-G	1989-R005-042	1994-0787-063-B	2001-6109-005-C	2008-1996-003-F
1981-0405-035-Z	1989-R006-042	1994-0839-003-B	2001-6112-051-B	2008-2011-125-B
1981-0500-125-A	1989-R007-042	1994-1158-009-E	2001-6113-125-B	2008-2120-051-C
1981-0528-003-B	1989-R009-042	1994-1308-003-B	2001-6114-129-B	2008-2155-003-A
1981-0554-005-I	1989-R011-042	1994-1323-009-C	2001-6169-005-B	2008-2208-027-B
1981-0646-125-E	1989-R012-042	1994-1409-005-B	2001-6213-121-B	2008-2349-059-B
1981-0657-019-A	1990-0020-042-D	1994-1444-003-A	2001-6215-019-B	2008-2349-059-C
1981-0739-007-A	1990-0020-042-E	1994-1452-111-B	2001-8012-111-O	2008-2355-007-B
1981-0819-007-A	1990-0020-042-G	1994-1459-051-C	2001-8029-009-B	2008-2473-042-T
1981-0898-059-A	1990-0040-007-D	1994-1480-033-A	2002-0102-073-C	2008-2512-019-A
1981-0999-051-A	1990-0091-125-C	1994-1496-125-B	2002-0175-111-C	2008-2561-042-B
1981-0999-051-B	1990-0112-042-B	1994-1614-125-B	2002-0175-111-G	2008-2601-003-B
1981-1017-129-D	1990-0112-042-BB	1994-1711-125-A	2002-0176-111-B	2008-2615-129
1981-1103-003-A	1990-0112-042-R	1994-1757-021-G	2002-0204-003-D	2008-2615-129-C
1981-1120-051-BBB	1990-0140-003-C	1994-1765-129-D	2002-0214-019-C	2008-2660-0125-C
1981-1120-051-L	1990-0162-005-J	1994-1828-003-B	2002-0274-042-B	2008-2674-042-C
1981-1120-051-NN	1990-0164-059-H	1994-1913-031-B	2002-0356-005-E	2008-2674-042-D
1981-1136-003-C	1990-0214-129-A	1994-2109-125-C	2002-0676-129-B	2008-6033-031-B
1981-1136-003-J	1990-0251-019-D	1994-2279-033-B	2002-0784-051-C	2008-6047-021-B
1981-1136-003-K	1990-0251-019-H	1994-2280-021-C	2002-0798-019-C	2008-6085-063-B
1981-1176-042-A13	1990-0273-063-S	1994-2285-003-B	2002-0825-129-E	2008-6110-065-B
1981-1176-042-A14	1990-0324-003-J	1994-2333-111-D	2002-1050-051-D	2008-6151-059-B
1981-1176-042-BBB	1990-0364-003-B	1994-2434-125-B	2002-1089-047-D	2008-6167-033-B
1981-1176-042-SS	1990-0366-129-B	1994-2461-125-A12	2002-1212-003-G	2008-6168-051-B
1981-1176-042-UUU	1990-0401-003-B	1994-2461-125-A19	2002-1212-003-M	2008-6168-051-D
1981-1176-042-YYY	1990-0406-033-A	1994-2461-125-FFF	2002-1441-003-C	2008-6184-063-B
1981-1176-051-M	1990-0412-042	1994-2461-125-MMM	2002-1445-059-A	2008-8033-059-A
1981-1248-003-B	1990-0441-065-A	1994-2461-125-NN	2002-1595-125-B	2008-8039-063-B
1981-1301-003-A	1990-0481-021-E	1994-2516-007-B	2002-1601-129-B	2009-0049-003-D
1981-1303-005-A	1990-0543-042-B	1994-2563-021	2002-1742-003-B	2009-0096-003-C
1981-1319-125-B	1990-0600-005-E	1994-2592-111-B	2002-1821-021-D	2009-0113-063-C

Table B-1. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 1

ER Numbers				
1981-1331-129-B	1990-0673-003-A	1994-2718-125-C	2002-1938-007-A	2009-0146-007-B
1981-1336-007-B	1990-0686-042-F	1994-2779-003-B	2002-2255-125-A	2009-0164-059-E
1981-1348-059-A	1990-0686-042-G	1994-2819-125-H	2002-2357-019-A	2009-0164-059-F
1981-1349-125-B	1990-0697-003-E	1994-2867-007-B	2002-2357-019-B	2009-0164-059-H
1981-1352-051-B	1990-0729-005-B	1994-2910-009-E	2002-2548-051-M	2009-0167-059-C
1981-1380-129-A	1990-0742-031-D	1994-3473-042	2002-2717-033-C	2009-0191-051-B
1981-1381-129-B	1990-0753-003-B	1995-0043-059-A	2002-2764-129-B	2009-0199-125-H
1981-1398-042-A	1990-0753-003-J	1995-0212-129-A	2002-6007-065-B	2009-0271-051-B
1981-2000-042-B	1990-0920-003-DDD	1995-0511-125-E	2002-6008-065-B	2009-0278-003-B
1981-2005-042-B	1990-0920-003-GGG	1995-0601-059-C	2002-6012-019-B	2009-0278-003-D
1981-2010-042-B	1990-0920-003-PP	1995-0607-059-A	2002-6063-042-B	2009-0324-059-R
1981-2013-042-B	1990-0920-003-TTT	1995-0644-063-A	2002-6075-125-D	2009-0326-125-B
1981-2014-042-B	1990-0920-003-WWW	1995-0662-129-B	2002-6095-009-F	2009-0326-125-D
1981-2015-042-B	1990-0922-027-B	1995-0688-063-C	2002-6105-065-C	2009-0353-063-B
1981-2016-042-B	1990-0923-003-A	1995-0711-059-A	2002-6150-129-B	2009-0367-003-C
1981-2018-042-B	1990-0934-005-C	1995-0723-063	2002-6154-033-B	2009-0402-033-D
1981-2019-042-B	1990-0958-129-K	1995-0793-003-A	2002-6162-051-B	2009-0449-003-B
1981-2023-042-B	1990-0991-019-C	1995-0797-003-A	2002-8000-021-I	2009-0467-003-A
1981-2034-125-B	1990-1068-007-B	1995-0838-129-E	2002-8000-021-L	2009-0502-019-B
1981-R002-042	1990-1132-019-A	1995-0956-031	2002-8021-129-D	2009-0525-051-B
1981-R002-051	1990-1156-129-E	1995-1000-007-B	2002-8039-051-B	2009-0571-065-A
1981-R003-042	1990-1182-111-C	1995-1040-042	2002-8039-051-H	2009-0647-003-C
1982-0160-013	1990-1225-125	1995-1446-007-A	2002-8042-111-Q	2009-0654-003-B
1982-0178-005-B	1990-1238-042	1995-1748-063-B	2002-8046-003-C	2009-0665-059-B
1982-0633-042-M	1990-1315-033-D	1995-1911-013-G	2002-8053-009-C	2009-0666-129-D
1982-0724-003-A	1990-1362-027-B	1995-2174-125-C	2003-0373-129-B	2009-0669-125-C
1982-0789-007-A	1990-1362-129-A	1995-2257-129-B	2003-0504-033-A	2009-0688-059-B
1982-R001-042	1990-1455-007-A	1995-2457-003-B	2003-0692-042-B	2009-0848-125-B
1983-0066-111-B	1990-1455-007-C	1995-2502-019-C	2003-0692-042-H	2009-0859-051-B
1983-0256-125-A	1990-1480-007-B	1995-2711-005-D	2003-0936-019-B	2009-0943-125-B
1983-0315-059-A	1990-1493-111-C	1995-2874-051-G	2003-0955-003-A	2009-0943-125-E
1983-0340-042	1990-1724-003-A	1995-3046-003-E	2003-1061-019-F	2009-0943-125-G
1983-0340-042-A	1990-1850-003-A	1995-3051-013-A	2003-1088-125-B	2009-0943-125-I
1983-0532-125-D	1990-1897-129-B	1995-3077-003-E	2003-1199-005-C	2009-0944-042-B
1983-0987-031-B	1990-1900-019-D	1995-3106-007-B	2003-1275-042-C	2009-0944-042-C
1983-1194-007-B	1990-1925-051-S	1995-3109-007	2003-1306-042-E	2009-0949-019-B
1983-1257-005-G	1990-1968-007-A	1995-3403-005-B	2003-1580-125-E	2009-1030-042-B
1983-R004-051	1990-2070-003-C	1995-3604-009-EE	2003-1619-005-B	2009-1031-042-C
1984-0001-042-D	1990-2092-129	1995-3604-009-G	2003-1623-129-A	2009-1031-042-F
1984-0129-003-A	1990-2163-007-C	1995-3604-009-K	2003-1651-063-B	2009-1095-111-C
1984-0129-003-B	1990-2163-007-E	1995-3604-009-Q	2003-1652-129-B	2009-1111-019-B
1984-0152-129-B	1990-2163-007-H	1995-3604-009-T	2003-1743-003-D	2009-1127-111-A
1984-0171-042-D	1990-2163-007-K	1995-3604-009-Z	2003-1795-003-G	2009-1162-111-A
1984-0254-129-F	1990-2288-129-A	1995-3646-129-A	2003-1795-003-L	2009-1212-005-B

Table B-1. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 1

ER Numbers				
1984-0254-129-H	1990-2339-005-D	1995-3728-021-B	2003-1888-111-B	2009-1219-111-B
1984-0342-059-XXX	1990-2391-033-A	1995-3845-021	2003-2023-125-B	2009-1264-005-B
1984-0385-003-B	1990-2431-009-B	1995-8053-007	2003-2069-125-J	2009-1291-027-B
1984-0385-003-D	1990-2515-003-D	1996-0031-013-G	2003-2093-129-E	2009-1298-019-B
1984-0392-059-A53	1990-2555-033	1996-0224-042-D	2003-2193-019-C	2009-1398-059-B
1984-0392-059-HHH	1990-2574-051-D	1996-0224-042-L	2003-2251-129-C	2009-1438-051-C
1984-0437-125-C	1990-2648-019-B	1996-0343-033-C	2003-2300-125-B	2009-1482-125-B
1984-0461-042-A	1990-2697-033-B	1996-0484-003-A	2003-2492-033-D	2009-1482-125-C
1984-0744-129	1991-0080-065	1996-0594-129-B	2003-2700-003-C	2009-1503-129-C
1984-0764-051-M	1991-0124-031-B	1996-0701-047-C	2003-2739-059-B	2009-1568-129-B
1984-0764-051-Q	1991-0273-059-B	1996-1105-051-A	2003-2739-059-D	2009-1570-111-D
1984-0777-051-E	1991-0385-125-B	1996-1105-051-B	2003-6010-033-B	2009-1586-125-C
1984-0777-051-L	1991-0464-019-B	1996-1211-042-F	2003-6047-051-B	2009-1589-129-B
1984-0777-051-Q	1991-0464-019-L	1996-1211-042-N	2003-6048-005-B	2009-1666-051-C
1984-0827-042-D	1991-0473-065-A	1996-1211-042-O	2003-6058-059-B	2009-1806-051-A
1984-0827-042-F	1991-0559-005-A	1996-1211-042-Q	2003-6072-033-B	2009-1853-019-B
1984-0873-125-E	1991-0772-042	1996-1211-042-Y	2003-6073-021-B	2009-1938-129-B
1984-0879-021-D	1991-0802-125-C	1996-1335-047-B	2003-6074-021-B	2009-1989-021-C
1984-0984-033-D	1991-1058-003-B	1996-1464-047	2003-6075-129-H	2009-1999-125-B
1984-1015-129-A	1991-1058-003-I	1996-1474-019-B	2003-6089-065-B	2009-2058-042-E
1984-1065-125	1991-1237-059-B	1996-1482-059-J	2003-6158-013-B	2009-2058-042-G
1984-1102-021-B	1991-1245-125-A	1996-1634-051-B	2003-8016-042-H	2009-2058-042-M
1984-1307-003-A	1991-1260-047-L	1996-1772-059-B	2003-8025-063-B	2009-2065-021-B
1984-1506-042	1991-1358-019-F	1996-1797-021-E	2003-8031-059-C	2009-2142-003-B
1984-1506-042-B	1991-1412-129	1996-1798-051-E	2003-8053-129-G	2009-2258-129-C
1984-1506-042-G	1991-1474-007-A	1996-1866-027-D	2003-8053-129-J	2009-2277-125-B
1984-1577-003-A	1991-1517-007-A	1996-1904-059	2004-0259-007-A	2009-2333-125-B
1984-1591-111-B	1991-1661-019-B	1996-1904-059-B	2004-0278-003-A	2009-2367-125-B
1984-1631-003-E	1991-1776-031-B	1996-1904-059-C	2004-0278-003-C	2009-2370-003-C
1984-1638-063-A	1991-1835-063	1996-1904-059-D	2004-0404-003-B	2009-5224-051-B
1984-1638-063-C	1991-1835-063-I	1996-1941-129-C	2004-0404-003-E	2009-6003-125-B
1984-1654-007-B	1991-1835-063-P	1996-2045-042-B	2004-0522-005-C	2009-6005-019-B
1984-1658-059	1991-1892-003-B	1996-2107-129-A	2004-0536-003-C	2009-6006-005-B
1984-1663-125-A	1991-2008-021	1996-2107-129-F	2004-0782-125-E	2009-6039-042-B
1984-1686-129-D	1991-2016-005-B	1996-2107-129-H	2004-0816-073-C	2009-6040-111-B
1984-1826-051-A	1991-2248-042	1996-2107-129-L	2004-0872-021-C	2009-6044-065-B
1984-1899-042	1991-2248-042-GG	1996-2107-129-N	2004-0873-003-D	2009-6072-033-C
1984-1899-042-H	1991-2248-042-GG2	1996-2129-019-D	2004-0912-003-B	2009-6084-125-B
1984-7964-051	1991-2248-042-NN	1996-2162-111-F	2004-0969-019-B	2009-6104-111-B
1985-0066-007-J	1991-2248-042-QQ	1996-2172-003-B	2004-1081-129-D	2009-6113-063-B
1985-0333-005-B	1991-2248-042-S	1996-2283-033-B	2004-1110-019-D	2009-6130-027-B
1985-0364-063-A	1991-2341-065-B	1996-2314-125-C	2004-1125-021-C	2009-6157-059-C
1985-0390-059-A28	1991-2494-003-A	1996-2318-059-E	2004-1309-125-C	2009-6218-125-B
1985-0390-059-A59	1991-2524-129-D	1996-2318-059-O	2004-1360-125-M	2009-6233-021-C

Table B-1. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 1

ER Numbers				
1985-0390-059-B01	1991-2554-003-B	1996-2739-007-B	2004-1394-063-B	2009-8001-003-C
1985-0390-059-B44	1991-2618-129-A	1996-2868-129	2004-1626-042-C	2009-8014-125-K
1985-0390-059-B45	1991-2832-005-C	1996-3058-019-A	2004-1626-042-F	2009-8023-005-A
1985-0390-059-C04	1991-2955-033-A	1996-3088-129-A	2004-1626-042-J	2009-8042-111-A
1985-0390-059-TTT	1991-3010-005-C	1996-3141-033-D	2004-1706-042-O	2009-8043-111-A
1985-0479-111-C	1991-3167-033	1996-8083-042-D	2004-1900-125-D	2009-8053-042-K
1985-0685-007-D	1991-3509-129-A	1996-8135-033-G	2004-2331-059-C	2010-0018-051-B
1985-0751-003-B	1991-3513-125-B	1996-8135-033-Q	2004-2331-059-H	2010-0032-125-B
1985-0783-042-A	1991-3557-121-A	1996-8185-007-B	2004-2421-007-B	2010-0183-042-D
1985-0790-003-G	1991-3627-125-C	1996-8203-033	2004-2421-007-F	2010-0183-042-E
1985-0807-005-D	1991-3653-007-A	1996-8232-007-F	2004-2428-019-B	2010-0196-033-D
1985-1082-003-F	1991-3669-033-H	1996-R003-042	2004-2503-005-C	2010-0220-051-E
1985-1135-009	1991-3814-003-B	1996-R027-042	2004-2844-129-B	2010-0422-129-B
1985-1135-009-C	1991-3929-033-G	1997-0057-065-H	2004-2926-129-B	2010-0465-003-C
1985-1135-009-D	1991-4114-063-F	1997-0081-129-C	2004-2998-003-A	2010-0536-059-B
1985-1220-003-C	1991-4203-129-D	1997-0081-129-E	2004-6004-125-B	2010-0536-059-J
1985-1285-003-A	1991-4210-003-D	1997-0174-007	2004-6010-111-B	2010-0537-005-A
1985-1285-003-H	1991-4256-021	1997-0214-125-D	2004-6015-065-C	2010-0624-042-C
1985-1285-003-O	1991-4316-003	1997-0237-003-F	2004-6033-125-A	2010-0624-042-D
1985-1454-033-A	1991-4334-129-C	1997-0699-009-B	2004-6080-005-B	2010-0720-003-B
1985-1454-033-B	1991-4393-007-B	1997-1107-129-E	2004-6081-129-C	2010-0736-059-JJ
1985-1460-129-B	1991-4453-129-B	1997-1211-042-C	2004-6089-035-C	2010-0886-059-C
1985-1575-021-C	1991-4454-019-G	1997-1313-125-D	2004-6090-129-B	2010-0902-003-B
1985-1634-003-K	1991-4514-007-B	1997-1357-125-D	2004-6109-129-B	2010-0949-125-B
1985-1656-129-F	1991-4531-021-C	1997-1394-125-G	2004-8027-125-F	2010-0967-063-E
1985-1656-129-R	1991-4547-007-D	1997-1540-003-C	2004-8049-005-C	2010-0967-063-G
1985-1688-003-A	1991-4591-065-E	1997-1549-042	2005-0044-003-B	2010-0998-063-C
1985-1695-003	1991-4617-129-E	1997-1549-042-A	2005-0151-003-C	2010-1023-013-C
1985-1695-003-PP	1991-4617-129-U	1997-1555-003-D	2005-0185-125-E	2010-1041-063-B
1985-1806-129-D	1991-4617-129-V	1997-1622-003-C	2005-0391-003-D	2010-1125-033-D
1985-1910-051-E	1992-0101-007-C	1997-1720-003-C	2005-0481-042-C	2010-1138-019-B
1985-1936-129-D	1992-0174-065	1997-1826-003-B	2005-0538-003-C	2010-1139-111-B
1985-1960-005	1992-0237-111-A19	1997-1849-005-F	2005-0606-063-D	2010-1175-051-A
1985-1960-005-C	1992-0279-019-G	1997-1918-051-D	2005-0630-003-E	2010-1223-125-B
1985-1960-005-J	1992-0382-129-C	1997-2006-005-A	2005-0630-003-F	2010-1238-007-A
1986-0011-003-B	1992-0415-051-B	1997-2011-003-B	2005-0925-003-A	2010-1261-007-A
1986-0142-129-C	1992-0423-013	1997-2014-005-B	2005-0973-003-A	2010-1278-073-A
1986-0181-111-B	1992-0480-027-D	1997-2039-007-C	2005-1127-003-E	2010-1284-003-B
1986-0198-129-B	1992-0516-003-D	1997-2220-005-A	2005-1127-003-G	2010-1326-042-J
1986-0199-033-B	1992-0516-003-F	1997-2231-007-C	2005-1209-125-B	2010-1326-042-O
1986-0213-042-B	1992-0547-003-B	1997-6030-003-G	2005-1250-021-B	2010-1387-019-D
1986-0275-005-B	1992-0608-129-D	1997-6040-005-D	2005-1454-059-F	2010-1399-125-B
1986-0457-051-C	1992-0665-042-C	1997-6049-031-B	2005-1591-051-C	2010-1445-129-B
1986-0457-051-G	1992-0670-051-D	1997-6059-007-B	2005-1742-003-D	2010-1445-129-F

Table B-1. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 1

ER Numbers				
1986-0574-003-I	1992-0695-031-F	1997-6099-042	2005-1785-111-E	2010-1507-031-B
1986-0617-051-B	1992-0898-019-B	1997-6139-019-D	2005-1918-003-C	2010-1546-059-C
1986-0668-005-B	1992-0943-007-D	1997-6141-019-B	2005-1976-003-J	2010-1559-125-B
1986-0671-003-A	1992-1024-021-C	1997-6142-019	2005-1996-059-A	2010-1796-042-B
1986-0679-007-B	1992-1024-021-H	1997-8009-003-DD	2005-2123-009-C	2010-1927-027-D
1986-0711-111-H	1992-1024-021-K	1997-8009-003-XX	2005-2124-009-D	2010-1930-063-B
1986-0748-059-A27	1992-1031-003	1997-8030-042-F	2005-2126-009-D	2010-1941-051-B
1986-0767-042-A	1992-1203-005-D	1997-8094-129-C	2005-2468-042-B	2010-2005-003-C
1986-0767-042-C	1992-1204-063	1998-0059-003-D	2005-2468-042-C	2010-2032-042-B
1986-0857-033-A	1992-1210-063-E	1998-0095-059-E	2005-2693-063-C	2010-2034-059-B
1986-0892-033	1992-1212-019-F	1998-0438-003-A	2005-2939-019-B	2010-2035-059-B
1986-0903-005-B	1992-1212-019-G	1998-0472-005-B	2005-3141-059-A	2010-2093-031-C
1986-0938-063	1992-1337-125-E	1998-0495-129-B	2005-6010-051-B	2010-2155-042-B
1986-0938-063-C	1992-1428-003-C	1998-0609-019-B	2005-6035-051-B	2010-2197-125-G
1986-1007-129-C	1992-1437-003-B	1998-0689-042-A	2005-6069-125-B	2010-2241-059-E
1986-1087-065-B	1992-1496-047	1998-0767-003-T	2005-6136-051-B	2010-6016-129-D
1986-1242-003-A	1992-1587-059-C	1998-0773-111-B	2005-8011-125-E	2010-6018-021-B
1986-1242-003-BB	1992-1627-063-D	1998-0809-065-A	2005-8027-121-D	2010-6047-063-B
1986-1242-003-GG	1992-1684-021-GG	1998-0849-111-F	2005-8060-059-C	2010-6106-059-D
1986-1259-125-C	1992-1684-021-RT	1998-0923-031	2006-0079-042-E	2010-8001-125-C
1986-1261-021-B	1992-1684-021-VV	1998-1040-125-H	2006-0079-042-J	2010-8010-042-P
1986-1316-042-E	1992-1686-111-G	1998-1116-003-E	2006-0136-042-D	2010-8048-005-C
1986-1381-073-B	1992-1686-111-L	1998-1154-005-B	2006-0282-007-A	2010-8055-019-B
1986-1381-073-C	1992-1701-063-B	1998-1231-007-C	2006-0300-007-A	2010-8056-005-A
1986-1471-051-J	1992-1719-059	1998-1270-051-B	2006-0517-129-A	2010-8056-005-B
1986-1534-063-D	1992-1721-033-C	1998-1508-125-D	2006-0697-059-B	2010-8057-009-B
1986-1538-019-C	1992-1789-003-D	1998-1585-129-D	2006-0942-042-A	2010-8061-125-B
1986-1550-129-J	1992-1892-129-H	1998-1601-129-A	2006-0952-125-C	2010-8061-125-C
1986-1550-129-K	1992-1977-125-A	1998-1654-129-D	2006-1030-019-A	2010-8064-125-B
1986-1550-129-M	1992-2363-129-C	1998-1730-003-B	2006-1172-033-D	2010-8070-111-B
1986-1550-129-Q	1992-2363-129-H	1998-1792-051-B	2006-1562-065-B	2010-8077-019-D
1986-1550-129-U	1992-2385-003-C	1998-1827-021-L	2006-1562-065-C	2010-8078-019-B
1986-1561-063-D	1992-2459-019-CC	1998-1880-003-C	2006-1622-129-A	2010-8094-065-B
1987-0139-019-B	1992-2484-063-B	1998-1969-021-F	2006-1736-125-B	2010-8096-065-B
1987-0144-111-I	1992-2502-125-C	1998-2016-051-E	2006-1836-021-C	2010-8103-063-A
1987-0145-129-B	1992-2559-063-D	1998-2016-051-H	2006-1938-003-B	2011-0017-021-A
1987-0167-051-B	1992-2668-027	1998-2028-129-B	2006-2178-003-B	2011-0027-007-B
1987-0167-051-D	1992-2668-027-B	1998-2131-042-H	2006-2262-003-B	2011-0027-007-D
1987-0167-051-E	1992-2668-027-C	1998-2287-065-B	2006-2271-003-C	2011-0051-129-C
1987-0167-051-G	1992-2851-051-E	1998-2389-129-F	2006-2271-003-D	2011-0071-051-A
1987-0168-005-B	1992-2851-051-T	1998-2458-005-B	2006-2286-007-B	2011-0078-042-E
1987-0343-042-OO	1992-2935-033-B	1998-2574-129-B	2006-2333-059-AA	2011-0121-059-B
1987-0343-042-PP	1992-2936-047	1998-2574-129-C	2006-2333-059-BB	2011-0122-059-B
1987-0343-042-QQ	1992-2942-047-C	1998-2668-129-E	2006-2333-059-F	2011-0266-129-B

Table B-1. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 1

ER Numbers				
1987-0343-042-UU	1992-2959-019-D	1998-2673-003-D	2006-2333-059-K	2011-0302-003-E
1987-0343-042-WW	1992-2959-019-S	1998-2692-059-B	2006-2333-059-P	2011-0313-033-B
1987-0343-042-Y	1992-2965-059-A	1998-6030-073-B	2006-2730-019-C	2011-0313-033-C
1987-0373-051-C	1992-2969-129-D	1998-6031-007-B	2006-2823-003-O	2011-0331-125-F
1987-0425-005-C	1992-2971-063-B	1998-6083-031-B	2006-3083-042-A	2011-0333-007-A
1987-0430-125-D	1992-2977-059-E	1998-6086-031-B	2006-3265-042-H	2011-0391-021-B
1987-0430-125-K	1992-2978-059-B	1998-6158-063-D	2006-3265-042-J	2011-0393-003-A
1987-0430-125-P	1992-2982-033-C	1998-6159-063-C	2006-3265-042-N	2011-0456-003-C
1987-0430-125-W	1992-3056-003-E	1998-6163-121-D	2006-6003-009-B	2011-0469-111-A
1987-0469-042	1992-3061-042-A	1999-0200-129-B	2006-6054-063-B	2011-0488-031-B
1987-0469-042-A17	1992-3144-033-E	1999-0230-129-C	2006-6080-051-B	2011-0515-129-B
1987-0469-042-AAA	1992-3249-111-C	1999-0328-007-B	2006-6104-129-D	2011-0520-129-C
1987-0469-042-II	1992-3258-111-C	1999-0339-125-B	2006-6123-021-B	2011-0545-059-B
1987-0469-042-RR	1992-3260-111-D	1999-0654-059-E	2006-6127-021-B	2011-0650-042-B
1987-0469-042-TT	1992-3263-111-B	1999-0657-129-C	2006-8014-111-D	2011-0754-059-B
1987-0469-042-VVV	1992-3264-111-C	1999-0813-003-D	2006-8016-063-E	2011-0828-003-D
1987-0469-042-ZZZ	1992-3269-111-C	1999-0873-111-B	2007-0106-125-B	2011-0839-031-B
1987-0482-003-A	1992-3271-009-B	1999-1012-019-B	2007-0183-129-A	2011-0840-031-B
1987-0505-003-A	1992-3348-125-B	1999-1114-003-B	2007-0206-021-A	2011-0869-007-B
1987-0663-033-D	1992-3407-129-I	1999-1207-065	2007-0310-042-D	2011-0903-003-B
1987-0679-129-B	1992-3407-129-J	1999-1214-129-E	2007-0310-042-F	2011-0937-051-A
1987-0701-003-A	1992-3407-129-O	1999-1664-111-C	2007-0349-003-E	2011-1045-019-B
1987-0792-033-B	1992-3424-121-C	1999-2050-129-A	2007-0375-047-D	2011-1094-007-B
1987-0800-121-C	1992-3454-007-C	1999-2197-129-F	2007-0512-033-F	2011-1169-125-B
1987-0879-007-D	1992-3454-007-D	1999-2197-129-G	2007-0532-059-C	2011-1169-125-G
1987-0879-007-E	1992-3461-013-B	1999-2375-019-C	2007-0532-059-E	2011-1176-003-D
1987-1002-042	1992-3462-021-C	1999-2539-129-B	2007-0533-129-D	2011-1242-051-A
1987-1002-042-A39	1992-3482-051-C	1999-2661-003-U	2007-0538-051-B	2011-1267-003-B
1987-1002-042-A83	1992-3500-003-C	1999-2725-111-A	2007-0736-059-CCC	2011-1317-035-A
1987-1002-042-A99	1992-3785-021	1999-2827-019-E	2007-0736-059-EE	2011-1347-003-C
1987-1002-042-AA	1992-3785-021-J	1999-2870-051-B	2007-0736-059-GGG	2011-1394-003-A
1987-1002-042-B17	1992-3785-021-K	1999-2885-005-A	2007-0736-059-HHH	2011-1540-065-B
1987-1002-042-B42	1992-3807-051	1999-2885-005-E	2007-0736-059-JJ	2011-1540-065-C
1987-1002-042-B55	1992-3847-021-E	1999-2885-005-H	2007-0736-059-KKK	2011-1664-003-B
1987-1002-042-B62	1992-3906-063-C	1999-6000-005-B	2007-0736-059-PP	2011-1674-005-A
1987-1002-042-B87	1992-3915-129-A	1999-6001-031-F	2007-0736-059-QQ	2011-1675-059-C
1987-1002-042-B95	1992-4078-019-A	1999-6004-063-B	2007-0736-059-Y	2011-1726-111-A
1987-1002-042-C	1993-0052-051-C	1999-6008-005-C	2007-0736-059-ZZ	2011-1728-051-A
1987-1002-042-C15	1993-0231-065-O	1999-6084-005-B	2007-0793-125-B	2011-1833-033-B
1987-1030-005-C	1993-0232-042	1999-6127-019-D	2007-0842-129-B	2011-1895-051-A
1987-1038-031-C	1993-0246-063-C	1999-6127-019-S	2007-0942-125-B	2011-1942-125-C
1987-1066-065-B	1993-0246-063-V	1999-6127-019-V	2007-0999-003-D	2011-2000-063-A
1987-1201-033-B	1993-0263-125-D	1999-6198-031-B	2007-1017-005-C	2011-2012-063-A
1987-1201-033-G	1993-0389-111-B	1999-8016-063-B	2007-1193-125-C	2011-2021-063-A

Table B-1. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 1

ER Numbers				
1987-1202-033	1993-0406-111-B	1999-8019-059-A	2007-1222-051-C	2011-2053-063-A
1987-1260-007-B	1993-0417-035-B	2000-0010-125-D	2007-1266-021-C	2011-2057-125-C
1987-1583-007-G	1993-0421-021	2000-0181-007-P	2007-1317-042-G	2011-2088-005-A
1987-1584-111-F	1993-0422-009-B	2000-0277-021-D	2007-1333-003-B	2011-2111-003-A
1987-1658-111-B	1993-0437-003-J	2000-0289-063-C	2007-1337-007-B	2011-2220-005-B
1987-1659-047-C	1993-0455-033-B	2000-0337-005-A	2007-1429-059-B	2011-2233-063-B
1987-1853-007-J	1993-0482-003-C	2000-0363-129-B	2007-1461-027-C	2011-2310-059-B
1988-0018-005-B	1993-0482-051-A	2000-0444-111-B	2007-1537-003-E	2011-2361-051-C
1988-0018-005-F	1993-0520-129-D	2000-0653-051-C	2007-1582-019-A	2011-2383-005-B
1988-0018-005-N	1993-0626-042-C	2000-0668-003-E	2007-1708-051-C	2011-2487-042-B
1988-0018-005-W	1993-0653-129-C	2000-0668-003-J	2007-1740-125-D	2011-2487-042-D
1988-0109-129-C	1993-0737-042-A	2000-0702-125-E	2007-1788-019-D	2011-2533-059-B
1988-0204-003-D	1993-0924-063-A	2000-0785-051-D	2007-1847-007-A	2011-8004-125-B
1988-0296-129-C	1993-0973-003-B	2000-0813-021-C	2007-1883-003-D	2011-8004-125-D
1988-0406-042-B	1993-1050-129-I	2000-0841-063-O	2007-1923-007-A	2011-8013-111-C
1988-0493-005-F	1993-1050-129-K	2000-0882-051-G	2007-1969-129-D	2011-8025-031-B
1988-0654-033-C	1993-1118-033-B	2000-0900-121-C	2007-1994-073-A	2011-8028-033-B
1988-0714-125-A	1993-1119-027-B	2000-1037-051-B	2007-2006-129-A	2011-8029-005-C
1988-0716-042-A	1993-1143-009-F	2000-1153-005-C	2007-2160-129-D	2011-8029-005-F
1988-0716-042-B	1993-1170-019-E	2000-1153-005-E	2007-2161-125-C	2011-8043-111-B
1988-0744-051-E	1993-1208-019-B	2000-1371-019-C	2007-2190-007-A	2011-8057-013-A
1988-0773-042-B	1993-1296-033-C	2000-1805-019	2007-2199-005-A	2011-8072-033-B
1988-0773-042-G	1993-1312-129-C	2000-1831-042-P3	2007-2211-129-B	2011-8093-063-B
1988-0873-047	1993-1316-003-B	2000-1831-042-P5	2007-2218-125-C	2011-8097-019-C
1988-0916-129-D	1993-1359-111-B	2000-1831-042-Y	2007-2353-051-E	2012-0020-125-B
1988-0956-035-C	1993-1427-019-C	2000-1845-021-E	2007-2353-051-G	2012-0020-125-C
1988-1027-033-F	1993-1502-129-C	2000-1877-063	2007-2403-033-E	2012-0089-129-B
1988-1213-063-D	1993-1732-059-B	2000-2029-003-D	2007-2421-019-A	2012-0132-033-B
1988-1358-047-E	1993-1734-059-C	2000-2098-051	2007-2446-125-B	2012-0169-042-B
1988-1434-042-F	1993-1961-051-B	2000-2098-051-D	2007-2463-003-B	2012-0182-059-B
1988-1445-005-C	1993-2015-007-U	2000-2098-051-N	2007-2469-125-B	2012-0191-051-B
1988-1558-042-A	1993-2026-003-D	2000-2156-042-D	2007-2580-019-A	2012-0213-125-B
1988-1562-031-B	1993-2113-129-A	2000-2176-125-F	2007-6019-051-B	2012-0218-021-B
1988-1586-042-E	1993-2214-059-A	2000-2176-125-I	2007-6028-021-G	2012-0260-019-A
1988-1615-042-C	1993-2214-059-F	2000-2268-003	2007-6058-005-B	2012-0261-125-B
1988-1643-031-B	1993-2230-059-B	2000-2268-003-F	2007-6059-005-B	2012-0285-129-B
1988-1655-111-K	1993-2270-042-A	2000-2427-007	2007-6060-065-B	2012-0296-125-A
1989-0084-059-E	1993-2270-042-D	2000-2816-033-N	2007-6068-021-C	2012-0298-059-B
1989-0162-125-B	1993-2316-065-E	2000-2961-003-C	2007-6129-063-B	2012-0298-059-D1
1989-0236-003-C	1993-2340-031-D	2000-3048-003-D	2007-8001-021-E	2012-0298-059-D2
1989-0244-051-B	1993-2384-129-C	2000-3199-129-C	2007-8010-125-A	2012-0332-129-A
1989-0297-051-B	1993-2437-063	2000-3237-047	2007-8020-019-A	2012-0397-005-A
1989-0300-007-O	1993-2437-063-C	2000-3300-003	2007-9007-019-B	2012-0397-005-B
1989-0302-047-A	1993-2453-129-B	2000-3357-019-A	2008-0039-031-C	2012-0432-059-B

Table B-1. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 1

ER Numbers				
1989-0344-042-B	1993-2484-063-I	2000-3524-063-B	2008-0077-042-C	2012-0564-129-D
1989-0492-003-C	1993-2484-063-J	2000-3637-019-G	2008-0085-042-B	2012-0605-125-C
1989-0492-003-L	1993-2487-031-H	2000-6096-035-B	2008-0085-042-H	2012-0629-051-B
1989-0492-003-U	1993-2569-005-C	2000-6124-059-B	2008-0171-031-D	2012-0630-051-B
1989-0492-003-X	1993-2598-063-B	2000-6137-009-O	2008-0269-129-B	2012-0690-111-A
1989-0533-042	1993-2630-129-A	2000-6140-063-B	2008-0269-129-I	2012-0691-051-A
1989-0582-051-E	1993-2644-019-B	2000-6175-051-B	2008-0305-051-B	2012-0692-051-A
1989-0607-003-A	1993-2646-129-C	2000-6177-129-B	2008-0308-007-C	2012-0752-051-A
1989-0620-019-B	1993-2661-065-E	2000-6190-051-E	2008-0423-129-B	2012-0757-129-B
1989-0690-125-C	1993-2767-125-F	2000-6190-051-E2	2008-0424-125-B	2012-0823-059-A
1989-0723-063-F	1993-2778-003	2000-6191-051-C	2008-0485-007-C	2012-0850-042-A
1989-0723-063-L	1993-2837-111-D	2000-6201-063-B	2008-0561-129-C	2012-0886-129-A
1989-0768-063-D	1993-2837-111-E	2000-6205-063-A	2008-0564-125-C	2012-0889-129-B
1989-0790-129-A	1993-3026-129-D	2000-8013-125-B	2008-0566-003-C	2012-0916-042-A
1989-0802-003-B	1993-3049-125-A	2000-8037-021-B	2008-0640-042-A	2012-1007-129-A
1989-0849-063-B	1993-3049-125-C	2000-8048-125-B	2008-0669-003-B	2012-1041-051-A
1989-0855-125-D	1993-3078-005-B	2001-0169-003-B	2008-0738-125-D	2012-1058-059-A
1989-0862-051-E	1993-3078-005-E	2001-0258-007-C	2008-0815-019-B	2012-1086-059-A
1989-1024-059-B	1993-3116-125-D	2001-0318-129-H	2008-0875-129-D	2012-1294-051-A
1989-1052-009-E	1993-3161-063-Q	2001-0610-005-E	2008-0880-125-A	2012-1763-059-A
1989-1108-051-B	1993-3203-003-B	2001-1137-007-F	2008-0913-003-C	2012-1764-033-B
1989-1142-003-B	1993-3203-003-F	2001-1204-005-D	2008-0942-129-C	2012-1893-125-B
1989-1275-003-DD	1993-3290-033-G	2001-1219-051-C	2008-0972-059-B	2012-2206-019-B
1989-1292-129-A	1993-3315-031-B	2001-1262-129-E	2008-0986-125-C	2012-2212-129-C
1989-1292-129-B	1993-3357-051-E	2001-1268-125-B	2008-1038-003-A	2012-2386-059-A
1989-1323-059-P	1993-3357-051-G	2001-1401-021-B	2008-1059-019-C	2012-2389-059-A
1989-1329-021-C	1993-3357-051-I	2001-1415-007-A	2008-1061-003-B	2012-2390-003-A
1989-1347-033-A	1993-3905-042-J	2001-1497-019-C	2008-1061-003-C	2012-2419-007-B
1989-1378-042-C	1993-3905-042-R	2001-1823-059-D	2008-1073-003-B	2012-8085-027-B
1989-1378-042-N	1993-3946-042-C	2001-2015-007-C	2008-1085-125-C	2013-0091-051-B
1989-1378-042-U	1993-4041-042-EE	2001-2562-003-B	2008-1101-003-A	2013-0172-129-A
1989-1422-059-C	1993-4056-125-B	2001-2651-019-D	2008-1109-063-C	2013-0174-129-A
1989-1524-003-D	1993-4116-005-D	2001-2666-003-B	2008-1128-125-B	2013-0242-051-B
1989-1533-125-TT	1993-4162-065-D	2001-2690-129-C	2008-1181-003-B	2013-0382-129-B
1989-1586-019-C	1993-4175-125-H	2001-2888-125-G	2008-1256-007-C	2013-0575-051-A
1989-1633-063-E	1993-4193-042-B	2001-2888-125-H	2008-1415-059-A	2013-1445-129-F

Table B-2. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 2

ER Numbers				
1981-0146-047-I	1989-0223-121	1993-1353-123	1998-1728-039	2007-0604-053-B
1981-0513-123-A	1989-0256-039-E	1993-1792-039-C	1998-2208-121-F	2007-1380-053-CD
1981-1097-039-A	1989-0469-039-B	1993-1802-123-C	1998-2322-073-I	2007-1544-085-B
1981-1321-049-B	1989-0485-049-B	1993-1937-019-A	1998-2380-083	2007-1583-039-A
1981-2012-042-B	1989-0489-042	1993-1985-039	1998-6044-073-A	2007-1616-085-B
1981-2020-085-B	1989-0489-042-D	1993-2183-123	1998-6179-085	2007-1617-073-B
1981-R001-049	1989-0609-049-H	1993-2320-049-B	1999-1365-039	2007-1648-049-B
1981-R001-085	1989-0700-073-C	1993-2338-085-C	1999-2146-039-E	2007-1706-085-B
1982-0062-039-A	1989-0948-073-C	1993-2501-039	1999-3071-123-L	2007-1707-039-B
1982-0092-042-B	1989-0949-073-E	1993-2610-085-D	1999-3158-042-C	2007-1720-073-B
1982-0245-042-B	1989-1037-042-D	1993-2633-123-F	1999-6092-073-C	2007-1788-019-D
1982-0245-042-M	1989-1100-007-B	1993-2743-073-C	1999-6092-073-F	2007-1922-039-A
1982-0539-049-A	1989-1221-085-D	1993-2993-039	1999-6195-073-B	2008-0012-049-C
1982-0633-042-B	1989-1234-049-H	1993-3439-047-A	2000-0513-073-C	2008-0273-123-A
1982-0633-042-M	1989-1430-073-B	1993-3504-085-C	2000-0900-121-C	2008-0304-073-B
1983-0102-123-C	1989-1562-049-D	1993-4344-121-A	2000-1126-039-G	2008-0698-007-A
1984-0468-085-B	1989-1562-049-E	1993-R001-047-A	2000-1509-042-G	2008-1079-049-E
1984-0727-049-A	1989-1562-049-F	1994-0041-123-C	2000-1831-042-EE	2008-1157-073-B
1984-0734-085-E	1989-1562-049-V	1994-0169-042-A	2000-1831-042-Z	2008-1900-042-A
1984-1277-085-A	1989-1608-073-E	1994-0255-047-A	2000-2707-049	2008-2075-053-A
1984-1506-042	1989-1678-039-F	1994-0542-121-D	2000-2735-049	2008-2180-123-A
1984-1506-042-B	1989-R001-039	1994-0543-121-G	2000-2946-039-B	2008-2186-12-B
1984-1654-007-B	1989-R008-042	1994-0897-121-B	2000-2948-049	2008-2666-039-A
1984-1790-053-B	1989-R010-042	1994-0929-049-C	2000-3114-123-C	2008-2674-042-C
1985-0036-085-B	1989-R012-042	1994-0929-049-F	2000-3527-085	2008-2674-042-D
1985-0041-085-D	1990-0496-085-A	1994-0929-123	2001-0100-049-B	2008-5159-121-C
1985-0396-121-F	1990-0748-073-D	1994-1393-042-D	2001-1125-123	2008-6005-121-B
1985-1795-085-B	1990-1139-085-B	1994-1395-123-D	2001-1128-073-A	2009-0272-073-D
1986-0490-047-B	1990-1601-121-A	1994-1466-053-N	2001-1164-123-C	2009-0726-039-B
1986-0525-085-BB	1990-1849-073-B	1994-1759-042-F	2001-1821-073-G	2009-1191-053-B
1986-0525-085-E	1990-2025-049-B	1994-1829-073-D	2001-3150-039-C	2009-1330-039-C
1986-0641-019-E	1990-2385-121-B	1994-2797-047	2001-3249-085-B	2009-1515-053-B
1986-0819-121-B	1990-2403-049-B	1994-2933-039-A	2001-4036-039-C	2009-6052-073-B
1986-0961-121-B	1991-0024-123-C	1994-3252-073	2001-6041-073-B59	2009-6052-073-F
1986-1112-085-G	1991-0426-121-B	1994-3336-039-E	2001-6201-073-B	2010-0652-042-B
1986-1316-042-AA	1991-0679-073-F	1994-4561-053-A	2001-6269-121-B	2010-0903-042-A
1986-1316-042-E	1991-0951-042-A	1995-0908-123-B	2002-1456-053-D	2010-1269-085-A
1986-1316-042-Z	1991-2187-123-B	1995-0991-121	2002-1555-085-E	2010-1366-085-A
1986-1336-039-C	1991-3146-085-E	1995-3108-047-D	2002-1555-085-H	2010-1501-047-A
1986-1377-123-A	1991-3339-083-E	1995-3546-085-B	2002-1730-123-A	2010-1695-073-A
1986-1381-073-B	1991-3891-047	1995-3548-042	2002-2548-053-J	2010-8015-121-B
1986-1381-073-C	1991-4602-047-D	1995-8025-049	2002-6006-123-K	2010-9029-123-B
1986-1511-053-A	1992-0174-065	1996-0174-047-E	2002-6012-019-B	2011-0384-065-B
1986-1512-123-A	1992-1513-049-G	1996-0880-123-C	2002-6161-047-C	2011-0650-042-B
1987-0006-047-B	1992-1988-085-A	1996-1335-047-B	2003-0160-121-C	2011-1037-019-B
1987-0527-049-D	1992-2175-039-B	1996-1705-047	2003-0401-049-C	2011-1148-031-A
1987-0570-047-A	1992-2258-085-B	1996-1756-085-A	2003-0723-073-A	2011-1447-039-B
1987-0571-053-A	1992-2942-047-C	1996-2354-049-H	2003-0723-073-B	2011-1667-121-A
1987-0615-053-B	1992-3034-123-E	1996-8134-049	2003-1021-085-C	2011-1968-047-B
1987-0800-121-C	1992-3034-123-G	1996-8186-073-B	2003-1727-073-H	2011-2339-053-A
1987-1153-047-A	1992-3109-053	1996-8227-073-V	2003-1727-073-N	2011-2363-073-C
1987-1220-121-B	1992-3251-121-D	1996-8227-073-W	2003-8041-039-D	2011-2407-083-B
1987-1364-053-D	1992-3259-019-B	1997-0309-123	2004-0834-121-C	2011-8109-085-A

Table B-2. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 2

ER Numbers				
1987-1388-121-C	1992-3354-053-B	1997-0399-049-B	2004-1612-039-B	2012-0012-047-B
1987-1553-121-M	1992-3399-039-C	1997-0399-049-C	2004-2258-123-C	2012-0056-123-A
1987-R001-053-A	1992-4006-047-A	1997-0934-049	2004-6045-073-C	2012-0317-047-A
1988-0001-085-D	1993-0497-039	1997-0934-049-F	2005-2553-083-A	2012-0429-047-A
1988-0278-083-D	1993-0621-047-E	1997-0943-039-B	2005-6026-039-B	2012-1269-073-A
1988-0773-042	1993-0644-039-F	1997-1143-121-C	2005-6051-047-B	2012-1270-085-A
1988-0773-042-F	1993-0674-049-E	1997-1958-123-C	2006-0475-123-C	2012-1272-039-A
1988-1128-047-B	1993-0737-042-A	1997-2602-042-F	2006-2264-039-B	2012-1725-053-B
1988-1314-085-B	1993-0757-047-G	1997-2777-039	2006-3083-042-A	2012-1745-047-A
1988-1466-049-B	1993-0942-039-C	1997-8010-073-F	2006-6051-073-D	2012-2206-019-B
1988-1476-047-B	1993-1015-073-DE	1998-0923-031	2006-8065-039-D	2012-2210-083-B
1988-1507-049	1993-1015-073-I	1998-1648-123-A	2007-0458-047-C	2012-2428-042-A
1989-0175-039-C	1993-1336-053-B			

Table B-3. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 3

ER Numbers				
1981-0162-049	1988-0645-049-U	1992-0858-049-HH	1997-0399-049-C	2002-2304-049-B
1981-0576-049	1988-0645-049-V	1992-0858-049-S	1997-1232-049	2003-0401-049-C
1981-1198-049	1989-0113-049-D	1992-0858-049-Z	1997-2863-049-B	2003-0547-042-C
1981-R001-049	1989-1313-049-A	1992-1513-049-K	1998-0631-042	2003-0621-049-B
1982-0079-049-A	1989-1313-049-B	1992-1513-049-L	1998-1911-049-D	2003-1216-049-D
1983-0728-049-A	1990-0903-049-A	1992-2941-049-L	1999-2093-049-B	2005-1128-049-B
1983-1201-049-A	1990-2025-049-B	1993-2458-049-B	2000-1831-042-JJ3	2007-0007-049-A
1984-0241-049-A	1990-2025-049-C	1993-3288-049-F	2000-2388-049-D	2007-0596-049-B
1984-0845-049-KK	1991-0008-049-B	1993-3288-049-O	2001-3250-049-B	2007-2154-049-B
1984-1208-049-C	1991-2241-049-D	1994-1749-049-C	2001-8019-049-E	2008-0012-049-C
1984-1425-049-F	1991-2490-049	1995-1072-049	2001-8019-049-E	2008-6013-049-B
1984-1774-049-E	1991-3496-049-B	1995-2417-049-K	2001-8019-049-J	2009-0817-049-E
1985-0555-049-B	1991-4020-049-C	1995-8025-049	2002-1851-049-B	2010-0478-049-B
1987-0527-049-D	1991-4062-049-E	1996-2354-049-H	2002-1853-049-B	2011-0337-049-B
1987-0528-049-C	1992-0858-049	1997-0307-049	2002-1981-049-C	2011-2180-049-B
1987-0529-049-F	1992-0858-049-EE			

Table B-4. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 4

ER Numbers				
1980-R001-027-A	1988-1532-013-N	1993-0932-027-G	1999-1775-057-C	2006-0903-027-G
1980-R001-042	1989-0035-027-E	1993-0953-027-B	1999-2221-042-B	2006-0903-027-J
1981-0028-061-BB	1989-0399-027-B	1993-1115-035-B	1999-2727-027-E	2006-1072-055-B
1981-0028-061-Q	1989-0478-027-C	1993-1212-087-E	1999-2744-013-E	2006-1375-055-A
1981-0028-061-S	1989-0519-013-B	1993-1212-087-H	1999-5024-087-L	2006-2651-009-D
1981-0102-061-B	1989-0528-061-C	1993-1273-009-A	1999-6165-027-D	2006-2651-009-E
1981-0119-042-A	1989-0586-027-B	1993-1278-042-I	1999-8002-009-A	2006-6075-009-B
1981-0119-042-B	1989-1120-009-B	1993-2319-013-E	2000-1180-009-G	2006-6100-013-B
1981-0156-027-B	1989-1148-035-D	1993-2438-013-N	2000-1831-042-HH	2006-6129-009-B
1981-0405-035-B	1989-1597-027-M	1993-2646-129-C	2000-1831-042-JJ1	2006-6137-013-B
1981-0405-035-G	1989-1597-027-R	1993-2925-009-D	2000-1831-042-JJ5	2006-6142-009-B
1981-0405-035-LLL	1990-0153-067-B	1993-3415-061-C	2000-1831-042-P4	2007-0219-027-B
1981-0468-087	1990-0175-027-F	1993-3844-061-D	2000-1831-042-P6	2007-0951-013-B
1981-0468-087-A	1990-0278-027-C	1993-4041-042-EE	2000-1831-042-P8	2007-1095-057-C
1981-1183-061-B	1990-0325-061-E	1993-4377-013-B	2000-1831-042-U	2007-1317-042-M
1981-1311-013-B	1990-0479-027-B	1994-0188-009-C	2000-2140-061-B	2007-1359-027-B
1981-1320-009-B	1990-0527-087-C	1994-0229-027-B	2000-2156-042-D	2007-1623-009-E
1981-2039-027-B	1990-0543-042	1994-0323-027-N	2000-2888-013-D	2007-1623-009-V
1981-R003-042	1990-0543-042-B	1994-0323-027-Q	2000-2888-013-M	2007-6003-027-B
1982-0160-013	1990-0572-027-E	1994-0323-027-S	2000-6073-027	2007-6045-009-B
1982-0160-013-BB	1990-0922-027-B	1994-0607-061-C	2000-6073-027-E	2007-6088-013-B
1982-0160-013-S	1990-0968-061-B	1994-0607-061-I	2000-6073-027-F	2007-6108-087-B
1982-0219-061-B	1990-1016-061-C	1994-0607-061-N	2000-6093-109-B	2008-0067-087-E
1982-0339-035-B	1990-1023-067-C	1994-0607-061-O	2000-6096-035-B	2008-0085-042-H
1982-0339-035-C	1990-1121-061-B	1994-0673-009-J	2000-8028-013-D	2008-0640-042-A
1982-0648-042	1990-1362-027-B	1994-0673-009-OO	2000-8030-009-B	2008-0869-013-B
1982-0796-061-B	1990-1661-027-B	1994-0673-009-YY	2001-0367-027-E	2008-1984-027-D
1982-0796-061-C	1990-1915-055-J	1994-0841-009-E	2001-0650-027	2008-2544-087-C
1983-0424-061	1990-2350-009-D	1994-1006-061-B	2001-0766-009-E	2008-2617-027-B
1983-0424-061-A	1991-0801-013-B	1994-1406-057-A	2001-2310-013-F	2008-6082-057-B
1983-0424-061-EE	1991-0820-009-B	1994-1428-061-B	2001-2550-061-C	2008-6118-009-B
1983-0424-061-H	1991-1106-087-D	1994-1758-057-H	2001-6164-013-B	2008-6143-013-B
1983-0424-061-HHH	1991-1522-009-A	1994-1818-009-B	2001-6242-061-B	2008-6164-061-B
1983-0424-061-JJJ	1991-1835-063-I	1994-1943-013-B	2001-6243-061-B	2008-6166-061-B
1983-0424-061-SS	1991-2248-042	1994-2222-027-C	2001-6244-061-B	2008-6177-035-B
1983-0424-061-T	1991-2248-042-D	1994-2280-021-C	2001-6260-061-A	2008-8029-027-D
1983-0424-061-W	1991-2248-042-M	1994-2751-009-B	2001-6261-061-B	2009-0046-027-C
1983-0424-061-WW	1991-2576-042-D	1994-3287-009-E	2001-6262-061-B	2009-0123-061-A
1983-0526-013-B	1991-2694-027-CC	1994-3473-042	2001-8002-009-A	2009-0344-009-B
1984-0012-109-B	1991-3409-061-E	1995-0160-061-D	2001-8004-061-B	2009-0549-009-B
1984-0171-042-I	1991-3410-061-F	1995-0764-009-E	2002-0031-013-B	2009-0724-061-A
1984-0379-027-F	1991-3495-013-B	1995-0996-061-G	2002-0037-109-C	2009-1306-027-C
1984-0439-027-C	1991-3553-055-B	1995-0996-061-L	2002-0274-042-B	2009-1350-013-B
1984-0678-009-C	1992-0352-013-F	1995-0996-061-S	2002-0385-009-D	2009-1372-027-B
1984-0736-087-C	1992-0423-013	1995-1911-013-G	2002-6140-061-B	2009-1444-035-F

Table B-4. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 4

ER Numbers				
1984-0818-027	1992-0591-061-G	1995-2067-061-B	2002-6184-013-B	2009-1989-021-C
1984-1248-042-B	1992-0842-013-D	1995-2637-009-B	2002-6204-067-B	2009-5094-067-B
1984-1268-009-B	1992-1263-027-G	1996-0224-042-L	2002-8003-061-O1	2009-6008-055-D
1984-1532-009-B	1992-1442-087	1996-0441-027	2003-0692-042-C	2009-6026-009-B
1984-1899-042	1992-1442-087-X	1996-0513-057-F	2003-1030-027-E	2009-6045-013-D
1984-1899-042-H	1992-1504-027-B	1996-0624-057-D	2003-1084-061-F	2009-6134-009-B
1985-0058-061-A	1992-1710-063-B	1996-0708-119-A	2003-1150-013-C	2009-6198-027-B
1985-0250-027-P	1992-1826-055-F	1996-0855-009-P	2003-2119-009-D	2009-6224-042-B
1985-0250-027-R	1992-2001-042-A	1996-1105-051-B	2003-2142-027-D	2009-6235-061-B
1985-1135-009	1992-2031-057-C	1996-1211-042-F	2003-2256-027-B	2009-9017-027-D
1985-1135-009-C	1992-2668-027-B	1996-2045-042-B	2003-2561-087-C	2010-0183-042-D
1985-1197-035-G	1992-2668-027-C	1996-2683-009-B	2003-6009-099-B	2010-0220-051-E
1985-1571-027-B	1992-2758-009-C	1996-2683-009-D	2004-0362-057-C	2010-1028-009-G
1985-1571-027-H	1992-2974-087-H	1996-8010-013-A	2004-0683-009-C	2010-1028-009-H
1985-1718-027-B	1992-2986-027-B	1996-8056-057-B	2004-1125-021-C	2010-1028-009-M
1986-0297-061-B	1992-2994-027-D	1996-8083-042-D	2004-1244-087-B	2010-1028-009-O
1986-0297-061-C	1992-3012-067-C	1996-8113-061-B	2004-1706-042-BB	2010-1143-055-B
1986-0484-057-B	1992-3070-061-C	1996-8206-013-B	2004-1706-042-J	2010-1183-061-B
1986-0751-042-E	1992-3254-057-B	1997-1271-009-F	2004-1706-042-O	2010-1326-042-L
1986-0767-042	1992-3255-013-D	1997-1271-009-I	2004-1706-042-S	2010-1326-042-N
1986-0767-042-A	1992-3257-013-F	1997-2793-027	2004-5104-067-C	2010-2023-027-B
1986-0767-042-C	1992-3262-009-E	1997-2806-009-LL	2004-6038-061-B	2010-6090-013-A
1986-1229-009-C	1992-3265-061-C	1997-2806-009-Y	2004-6089-035-C	2011-0112-057-B
1986-1623-013-C	1992-3266-061-E	1997-8013-042-AA	2004-8044-013-B	2011-0534-027-B
1987-0343-042-UU	1992-3267-061-F	1997-8013-042-D	2005-2122-009-C	2011-0566-061-E
1987-0343-042-WW	1992-3268-061-D	1997-8030-042-F	2005-2148-055-B	2011-0566-061-F
1987-0405-035-B	1992-3272-061-B	1997-8058-061-B	2005-2802-009-B	2011-0912-009-A
1987-0744-061-B	1992-3460-009-B	1998-0072-087-F	2005-6033-027-B	2011-1027-081-A
1987-1002-042-A99	1993-0232-042	1998-0082-013-D	2005-6033-027-C	2011-1200-013-C
1987-1400-009-H	1993-0232-042-A11	1998-0978-013-D	2005-6047-027-B	2011-1366-027-C
1987-1421-027-B	1993-0232-042-AAA	1998-1013-035-F	2005-6087-061-B	2011-1640-027-B
1987-1599-061-E	1993-0234-009-H	1998-1099-061-B	2005-6117-061-B	2011-8011-061-C
1988-0079-081-B	1993-0246-063-C	1998-1099-061-C	2005-6176-087-B	2011-8022-009-B
1988-0081-057-D	1993-0418-027-B	1998-1854-061-B	2005-8013-061-B	2011-8070-087-B
1988-0226-009-D	1993-0419-061-C	1998-2172-027-D	2006-0136-042-D	2011-8104-027-B
1988-0420-061-A	1993-0649-057	1998-6164-067-L	2006-0523-099-B	2011-8127-009-B
1988-0663-013-C	1993-0649-057-E	1998-6166-067-D	2006-0731-027-L	2011-8147-027-B
1988-0670-009-D	1993-0653-129-C	1999-0390-027-D	2006-0731-027-N	2013-0441-027-A
1988-1415-042-A	1993-0735-027-E	1999-0658-027-D		

Table B-5. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 5

ER Numbers				
1981-0119-042-A	1987-1440-097-C	1992-3781-099-B	1998-8021-097-B	2005-5254-093-B
1981-0119-042-B	1987-1463-119-B	1992-3801-081	1999-0319-097-D	2005-6160-119-B
1981-0167-043-B	1987-1547-097-B	1992-4035-081-C	1999-2098-043-B	2006-0017-042-A
1981-0405-035-B	1987-1674-043-C	1993-0377-043-B	1999-2767-119	2006-0017-042-E
1981-0405-035-E	1988-0079-081-B	1993-1116-081-B	1999-2780-037-I	2006-0192-042-H
1981-0405-035-G	1988-0092-107-E	1993-1192-025-H	1999-5169-037-F	2006-0571-067-E
1981-0434-042	1988-0100-079-B	1993-1276-081-B	1999-6052-081-B	2006-0973-093-B
1981-0434-042-V	1988-0353-107-C	1993-1276-081-D	1999-6058-037	2006-0973-093-H
1981-0658-079-B	1988-0353-107-E	1993-1346-081-B	1999-6061-097-C	2006-1582-025-B
1981-0658-079-C	1988-0634-043	1993-1763-107	1999-6062-097-C	2006-1582-025-C
1981-0658-079-HH	1988-0856-081-H	1993-2092-037-E	1999-6063-093-B	2006-5048-037-D
1981-0658-079-N	1988-0959-037-F	1993-2363-107-D	1999-6069-119-A	2006-7001-042-B
1981-0685-079-Q	1988-0959-037-O	1993-3128-081-C	1999-6154-097	2007-0223-025-K
1981-0759-043-B	1988-0962-093	1993-3196-079-D	1999-8000-042	2007-0735-081-B
1981-0787-093-B	1988-1019-079-B	1993-3393-107-C	1999-8001-097-B	2007-0815-042-C
1981-1204-037-A	1988-1021-079-B	1993-3461-097-F	1999-8027-037	2007-0839-081-A
1981-1307-037-A	1988-1024-079-D	1993-3544-119-E	1999-8027-037-E	2007-1793-081-B
1981-1318-107-B	1988-1139-043	1993-3639-037-B	2000-1302-119	2007-2565-119-B
1981-1328-119-A	1988-1139-043-BBB	1993-3764-079-D	2000-1788-093-B	2007-6036-109-B
1981-1350-097-B	1988-1139-043-FFF	1993-4042-097-B	2000-1788-093-C	2007-6105-037-B
1981-1366-097-B	1988-1139-043-LL	1993-4122-081-E	2000-2156-042-D	2008-1420-099-C
1981-2026-042-B	1988-1139-043-P	1993-4207-107-D	2000-2297-025-D	2008-1443-097-C
1982-0043-093	1988-1326-097-B	1993-4375-079-F	2000-2337-099-D	2008-1443-097-G
1982-0139-093-B	1988-1612-093-J	1994-0040-099-B	2000-6002-081	2008-1830-081-B
1982-0293-037-B	1989-0038-079-R	1994-0177-097-B	2000-6096-035-B	2008-1830-081-H
1982-0648-042	1989-0181-042-D	1994-0414-081-B	2000-6150-081-B	2008-1839-081-F
1982-0648-042-A09	1989-0381-042	1994-0414-081-E	2000-6173-097-G	2008-1872-081-C
1982-0648-042-A27	1989-0381-042-A	1994-0465-097-B	2000-6173-097-H	2008-1873-081-C
1982-0648-042-A30	1989-0381-042-SS	1994-0775-042-C	2000-6173-097-L	2008-1947-097-D
1982-0648-042-A32	1989-0381-042-WW	1994-1060-093-D	2000-6260-043-B	2008-2038-081-C
1982-0648-042-A36	1989-0635-109	1994-1528-097-E	2000-6279-099-D	2008-2623-119-B
1982-0648-042-A40	1989-0695-107-D	1994-1536-079-C	2000-6298-081-B	2008-6022-081-B
1982-0648-042-A41	1989-1270-025-F	1994-1819-097-C	2000-8002-099-H	2008-6028-037-B
1982-0648-042-A47	1989-1566-067	1994-1997-119	2000-8007-097-E	2008-6191-079-B
1982-0648-042-C	1989-1630-119-A	1994-1997-119-K	2001-1026-037-B	2008-8008-035-A
1982-0648-042-KKK	1989-1630-119-N	1994-2380-079-B	2001-1103-043-D	2008-8044-081-D
1982-0648-042-LL	1989-1710-043	1994-2473-079-B	2001-1263-097-E	2009-0009-097-C
1982-0648-042-OOO	1990-0025-035-B	1994-2764-037-B	2001-2122-081	2009-0260-093-B
1982-0669-109-H	1990-0087-079-E	1994-2876-109-D	2001-2208-081-A	2009-0592-042-K
1982-0669-109-P	1990-0216-081-F	1994-3253-081-C	2001-2774-079-M	2009-0646-097-B
1982-0801-042-R	1990-0225-107-B	1994-3538-097-E	2001-3040-099-C	2009-1029-099-H
1982-R002-042	1990-0588-079-D	1994-3538-097-G	2001-3713-037-B	2009-1050-099-C
1983-0030-081-B	1990-0630-037-D	1994-3538-097-I	2001-6067-037-B	2009-1741-109-A
1983-0403-025	1990-0635-079-NNN	1995-0070-079	2001-6068-081-E	2009-2221-081-C
1983-0403-025-D	1990-1023-067-C	1995-1034-081-B	2001-6276-043-B	2009-2332-097-B
1983-0683-081-B	1990-1275-037-B	1995-1882-081	2002-0037-109-C	2009-5119-037-B
1983-1183-042-D	1990-1283-037-B	1995-1882-081-H	2002-0233-081-D	2009-6043-109-B
1983-2000-037-A	1990-1477-081-C	1995-2362-043	2002-0233-081-J	2009-6118-043-B
1984-0177-119-C	1990-2229-037-F	1995-2476-099-C	2002-0274-042-B	2009-6163-109-B
1984-0178-037-A	1990-2392-079-B	1995-2570-079-E	2002-0287-079-G	2009-6165-099-B
1984-0179-042-B	1990-2400-109-C	1996-0276-079-G	2002-0287-079-M	2009-6202-067-B
1984-0180-093-B	1990-2499-097-A	1996-0276-079-H	2002-0353-079-F	2009-6213-099-B
1984-0182-037	1991-0289-097-G	1996-0276-079-K	2002-0878-035-C	2009-6229-097-B

Table B-5. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 5

ER Numbers				
1984-0497-097-B	1991-0331-119-E	1996-1912-037-B	2002-1306-109-B	2010-0195-097-B
1984-0502-081	1991-0399-037-C	1996-1961-109-F	2002-2550-109-E	2010-0616-037-C
1984-0731-037	1991-1178-042	1996-2299-035-C	2002-5274-081-F	2010-1137-043-C
1984-0961-042-C	1991-1186-097-C	1996-2315-042-D	2002-6058-109-I	2010-1271-081-B
1984-1321-097-B	1991-1312-079-D	1996-2315-042-F	2002-6126-043-B	2010-1324-067-C
1984-1508-079	1991-1594-109-B	1996-2315-042-H	2003-0070-079-D	2010-1630-081-C
1984-1508-079-QQ	1991-1602-097-G	1996-8055-119-D	2003-0087-079-E	2010-1630-081-D
1984-1803-107-B	1991-1719-109-B	1996-8085-081-H	2003-0250-025-C	2010-1630-081-H
1984-1899-042	1991-2397-037-B	1996-8119-093	2003-0524-079-D	2010-1797-081-C
1985-0091-109-A	1991-2740-043-C	1997-0968-119-N	2003-1297-081-B	2010-1801-081-B
1985-0322-042-C	1991-3046-075-S	1997-0968-119-P	2003-2427-097-C	2010-2070-081-B
1985-0322-042-G	1991-3046-075-V	1997-1030-042	2003-2428-097-C	2010-5269-109-E
1985-0397-097-C	1991-3254-081-C	1997-1045-109-C	2003-2781-099-C	2010-6083-079-B
1985-0530-081-B	1991-3517-079-D	1997-1414-081-F	2003-5019-099-C	2010-8087-081-B
1985-0589-097-BB	1991-3988-079-H	1997-1549-042	2003-6023-081-B	2011-0065-107-A
1985-0589-097-X	1991-4245-107-B	1997-1556-037-C	2003-6029-081-E	2011-0077-081-C
1985-0641-081-J	1991-4550-119-C	1997-1670-081-C	2003-6029-081-F	2011-0359-081-B
1985-0771-099-A	1992-0203-109-G	1997-2553-037	2003-6040-099-B	2011-0447-037-B
1985-0842-107-B	1992-0588-119-B	1997-2852-081-I	2003-6042-099-B	2011-0622-042-B
1986-0246-037-B	1992-0647-109-F	1997-6002-109-C	2003-6044-043-G	2011-0739-107-B
1986-0517-107-C	1992-1469-081-E	1997-6003-081-D	2003-6097-099-C	2011-0898-081-E
1986-0767-042	1992-1586-107-B	1997-6019-109-C	2003-6143-107-B	2011-0975-097-B
1986-0767-042-A	1992-1588-081-B	1997-8006-093-C	2003-6161-025-J	2011-1068-081-F
1986-1103-099-C	1992-2180-107-E	1998-1388-081-H	2003-6190-099-B	2011-1240-042-B
1986-1285-119-C	1992-2313-079-B	1998-1793-081-B	2004-0356-097-B	2011-1676-081-B
1986-1299-037-D	1992-2454-037-G	1998-1797-097-F	2004-0697-119-E	2011-1840-081-B
1986-1325-109-C	1992-2490-042-C	1998-2241-042-C	2004-1042-079-C	2011-2248-042-B
1986-1612-119-D	1992-2492-107-D	1998-2284-097-E	2004-2225-079-B	2011-2439-081-B
1987-0047-043	1992-2526-037-A	1998-6073-097-C	2004-2453-037-B	2011-2563-081-B
1987-0234-109-D	1992-3029-081-A	1998-6140-119-H	2004-6060-079-B	2011-8048-119-A
1987-0400-081-D	1992-3189-043-D	1998-6140-119-N	2004-6067-109-B	2012-0671-081-B
1987-0610-107-C	1992-3290-081-F	1998-6141-081	2004-6089-035-C	2012-1332-081-A
1987-0936-119-B	1992-3441-081-D	1998-6164-067-L	2004-8007-099-B	2012-1546-081-B
1987-0989-107-B	1992-3536-037-J	1998-6166-067-D	2005-0539-109-C	2012-1729-043-A
1987-1143-079-B	1992-3536-037-N	1998-8019-107	2005-2364-025-A	2013-8009-079-A
1987-1219-097-B				

Table B-6. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 6

ER Numbers				
1981-0086-083-A	1990-0112-042-B	1997-6021-113	2009-1974-105-B	2011-1530-117-B
1981-0149-117	1990-0112-042-G	1997-6025-015-F	2009-2033-042-B	2011-1574-081-B
1981-0950-042-A	1990-0180-083	1998-6063-081-D	2009-2181-083-C	2011-1608-081-A
1981-1374-083-B	1990-0482-105-A	1998-6130-117-B	2009-6194-105-B	2011-1779-042-A
1981-2041-083-B	1990-0482-105-B	1999-1329-105-G	2009-6195-083-B	2011-1779-042-D
1981-2041-083-C	1990-0482-105-C	1999-1329-105-H	2009-6199-105-B	2011-1819-117-B
1982-0648-042	1990-0482-105-E	1999-1329-105-I	2010-0035-083-B	2011-1839-081-B
1982-0648-042-A09	1990-0699-083-D	2000-0828-113	2010-0183-042-D	2011-1866-081-B
1982-0648-042-A12	1990-0922-027-B	2000-1831-042-JJ4	2010-0183-042-E	2011-1980-015-C
1982-0648-042-A15	1990-1784-105-E	2000-6184-083-C	2010-0740-081-B	2011-1980-015-E
1982-0648-042-A30	1991-1047-105-B	2000-8019-081	2010-0741-081-B	2011-2019-105-E
1982-0648-042-A41	1991-2652-023-H	2001-0883-083-A	2010-0917-042-U	2011-2020-117-D
1982-0648-042-DD	1991-2942-083-K	2001-2547-023-C	2010-1271-081-B	2011-2046-081-B
1982-0648-042-II	1991-3429-083-A	2001-3696-083-C	2010-1274-081-D	2011-2122-015-A
1982-0648-042-KK	1991-3744-083-G	2001-3955-105-C	2010-1413-042-B	2011-2230-081-C
1982-0648-042-KKK	1992-0073-123-J	2001-3955-105-E	2010-1631-042-B	2011-2246-113-B
1982-0648-042-LL	1992-0121-105	2001-3955-105-F	2010-1673-117-B	2011-2248-042-B
1982-0648-042-NNN	1992-0121-105-E	2001-6189-081-B	2010-1755-081-B	2011-2265-113-B
1982-0648-042-OOO	1992-0248-083-G	2001-6190-081	2010-1792-117-D	2011-2265-113-D
1982-0648-042-PP	1992-1609-081-A	2002-0257-105-C	2010-1797-081-C	2011-2303-015-B
1982-0648-042-Q	1992-1643-105	2002-0257-105-E	2010-1797-081-D	2011-2304-042-B
1983-0819-117-B	1992-1757-035-G	2002-2666-105-B	2010-1801-081-B	2011-2331-113-B
1983-1128-083-D	1992-2939-083-C	2003-0114-117-B	2010-1936-042-B	2011-2358-117-B
1984-0137-117-D	1992-2981-105-C	2003-2029-042-D	2010-1936-042-D	2011-2401-042-B
1984-0502-081	1992-2985-105-B	2003-2029-042-K	2010-2032-042-B	2011-2401-042-H
1984-1082-081-B	1992-3521-083-A	2003-2029-042-O	2010-2038-081-B	2011-2504-113-B
1984-1506-042	1992-3843-083	2003-6057-035-B	2010-2039-035-A	2011-2507-117-B
1984-1506-042-B	1992-4067-105-F	2004-1706-042-O	2010-2070-081-B	2011-2514-117-A
1984-1563-035-B	1993-0226-083	2004-2329-105-B	2010-2070-081-C	2011-2514-117-G
1984-1899-042	1993-0382-023-B	2004-2329-105-F	2010-2174-105-D	2011-2524-081-B
1985-1783-042-B	1993-0426-105-C	2004-2330-105-B	2010-2282-105-B	2011-8031-117-D
1985-1783-042-E	1993-0456-105-B	2005-2455-083-C	2010-2306-117-B	2011-8045-105-B
1986-0422-083-D	1993-0939-117	2005-3139-083-D	2010-2306-117-D	2011-8046-105-B
1986-0858-033-A	1993-1122-023-B	2005-6073-117-C	2010-2309-105-B	2011-8133-117-B
1986-0959-117-B	1993-1453-083-C	2005-6143-117-B	2010-2327-117-C	2012-0021-131-B
1986-1085-081	1993-1665-105-B	2005-6150-117-B	2011-0041-105-B	2012-0044-105-B
1986-1262-033-B	1993-2221-083-C	2006-6035-131-B	2011-0053-105-C	2012-0044-105-C
1986-1312-042-B	1993-2221-083-F	2007-0500-023-D	2011-0077-081-C	2012-0051-081-B
1986-1455-042-B	1994-0174-117-A	2007-0524-083-B	2011-0289-105-B	2012-0109-105-A
1986-1512-123-A	1994-0259-042	2007-0697-042-A	2011-0297-081-D	2012-0250-083-B
1986-1542-042	1994-1884-105-B	2007-0697-042-C	2011-0596-113-D	2012-0357-081-B
1987-0547-083-D	1994-1884-105-G	2007-0697-042-G	2011-0622-042-B	2012-0378-117-B
1987-0547-083-E	1994-2480-117-B	2007-0697-042-H	2011-0622-042-D	2012-0381-117-A
1987-0547-083-F	1994-2655-081-C	2007-0697-042-M	2011-0649-081-C	2012-0416-081-B
1987-1069-083-B	1994-3250-035-C	2007-2194-083-B	2011-0803-117-B	2012-0450-015-C
1987-1194-117-D	1995-0927-042-C	2008-0785-117-B	2011-0866-117-B	2012-0498-117-B
1987-1338-081-B	1996-0332-117-A	2008-1058-105-B	2011-1026-081-A	2012-0499-117-B
1987-1557-042-B	1996-0332-117-H	2008-1174-105-D	2011-1068-081-C	2012-0857-081-C
1988-0561-023-E	1996-1215-117-D	2008-1830-081-H	2011-1068-081-F	2012-0961-015-B
1988-0775-113-B	1996-1464-047	2008-1840-035-A	2011-1353-015-A	2012-0961-015-C
1988-1129-023-C	1996-2359-105-C	2008-2473-042-T	2011-1353-015-D	2012-1189-117-A
1988-1558-042-A	1996-8131-083	2009-0041-083-A	2011-1354-015-A	2012-1189-117-B
1988-1559-105-C	1996-8202-023-J	2009-0625-083-E	2011-1355-015-A	2012-1249-117-B

Table B-6. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 6

ER Numbers				
1989-0174-083-E	1997-0054-081	2009-0625-083-F	2011-1406-042-D	2012-1494-105-B
1989-0227-117-H	1997-0657-105-D	2009-0922-042-C	2011-1422-117-A	2012-1617-015-A
1989-0650-105-C	1997-1358-105	2009-0990-117-C	2011-1456-042-B	2012-2108-113-B
1989-0968-117-C	1997-2018-117-QQ	2009-1715-117-F	2011-1456-042-J	2012-2355-035-B
1989-1273-105-C	1997-2018-117-X	2009-1896-105-A	2011-1456-042-K	2012-2405-081-B
1990-0079-117-A	1997-2535-117-A	2009-1941-117-B	2011-1513-117-B	

Table B-7. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 7

ER Numbers				
1981-0122-069-B	1993-0939-117-PP	2001-2145-103-D	2010-1631-042-B	2011-2328-042-B
1981-0149-117	1993-0939-117-VV	2001-6030-127-B	2010-1661-117-B	2011-2329-015-B
1981-0434-042	1993-1131-127-B	2001-6136-079-B	2010-1673-117-B	2011-2330-015-A
1981-0434-042-Z	1993-1271-089-B	2001-6157-103-B	2010-1737-117-B	2011-2330-015-C
1981-0555-079-A	1993-1345-015-E	2001-6160-079-C	2010-1791-117-C	2011-2331-113-B
1981-0555-079-O	1993-1398-069-E	2001-6163-127-B	2010-1792-117-D	2011-2331-113-C
1981-0658-079-C	1993-1398-069-I	2001-6180-103-B	2010-1936-042-B	2011-2346-015-A
1981-0950-042-A	1993-1425-069-C	2001-6194-117-A	2010-1936-042-F	2011-2347-015-A
1981-0950-042-B	1993-1466-015-M	2001-8001-115	2010-2102-015-B	2011-2377-015-A
1981-1090-015-B	1993-1739-069-A	2001-8010-069-N	2010-2162-117-B	2011-2397-015-B
1981-1325-103-B	1993-1909-069-B	2001-8018-127-B	2010-2172-015-C	2011-2403-015-C
1981-1376-079-B	1993-2318-079-C	2002-1106-127-C	2010-2172-015-E	2011-2440-015-B
1981-1377-115-B	1993-2331-089-E	2002-1625-089-F	2010-2184-115-D	2011-2442-115-C
1981-2025-042-B	1993-2342-015-B	2002-1626-103-B	2010-2184-115-E	2011-2444-042-C
1982-0051-127-E	1993-2451-103-D	2002-2557-131-B	2010-2184-115-F	2011-2445-015-B
1982-0161-103-CCC	1993-2573-069-C	2002-6019-127-B	2010-2255-117-B	2011-2446-015-B
1982-0161-103-DDD	1993-2573-069-F	2002-6031-103-B	2010-2326-042-B	2011-2452-115-B
1982-0161-103-JJ	1993-2947-117-A	2002-6033-069-B	2010-2327-117-C	2011-2452-115-D
1982-0161-103-OO	1993-2947-117-C	2002-6091-127-B	2010-6007-117-B	2011-2456-015-B
1982-0161-103-RRR	1993-3063-115-G	2002-6101-117-B	2010-6008-117-B	2011-2466-115-B
1982-0161-103-SS	1993-3344-015-E	2002-8011-079-H	2010-6032-015-B	2011-2473-015-B
1982-0513-015-B	1993-3501-127-C	2002-8033-103-B	2010-6078-115-G	2011-2485-015-B
1982-0648-042-A32	1993-3636-131-G	2002-8043-103-I	2010-6078-115-I	2011-2485-015-D
1982-0648-042-C	1993-4041-042-DD	2003-0524-079-D	2010-8076-131-A	2011-2489-117-B
1982-0648-042-O	1994-0064-113-C	2003-0644-089-B	2010-8080-131-A	2011-2504-113-B
1983-1020-069-B	1994-0068-127-E	2003-0966-127-B	2010-8082-131-A	2011-2529-015-C
1983-1020-069-J	1994-0157-015-C	2003-2174-079-I	2011-0078-042-B	2011-5122-117-B
1983-1020-069-L	1994-0174-117-A	2003-6007-127-B	2011-0229-115-B	2011-8050-115-C
1984-0171-042-C	1994-0241-115-B	2003-6066-103-B	2011-0315-117-C	2012-0018-015-B
1984-0319-131-A	1994-0259-042	2003-6069-103-B	2011-0315-117-E	2012-0042-015-B
1984-0545-079-D	1994-0259-042-C	2003-8020-115-C	2011-0370-089-B	2012-0043-015-C
1984-0778-117-B	1994-0500-015-A	2004-0262-117-D	2011-0385-042-B	2012-0043-015-E
1984-0931-089-D	1994-0702-103-F	2004-0647-089-C	2011-0399-015-A	2012-0106-131-A
1984-1212-015-A	1994-0982-079-H	2004-1073-103-D	2011-0400-015-A	2012-0111-131-B
1984-1263-069-C	1994-1045-089-E	2004-1444-103-B	2011-0401-015-A	2012-0124-117-B
1984-1834-115-F	1994-1057-117	2004-3050-042-C	2011-0402-115-B	2012-0183-015-B
1984-1912-069-B	1994-1057-117-G	2004-6002-079-B	2011-0631-115-B	2012-0192-131-A
1985-1182-015-F	1994-1427-079-A	2004-6052-127-B	2011-0679-042-B	2012-0192-131-B
1985-1265-079-N	1994-1430-015-B	2004-6057-131-B	2011-0692-015-A	2012-0193-115-B
1986-0367-025-A	1994-1433-079-E	2004-6071-015-B	2011-0729-115-B	2012-0194-115-B
1986-0606-079-D	1994-1486-069-B	2004-6096-115-B	2011-0803-117-B	2012-0195-115-B
1986-0861-069-D	1994-1500-127-D	2004-6101-115-B	2011-0817-115-A	2012-0202-015-B
1986-0959-117-B	1994-1706-127-D	2005-0485-127-D	2011-0818-042-A	2012-0204-113-C
1986-1457-117	1994-2681-127-C	2005-0670-127-E	2011-0819-131-A	2012-0263-115-B
1987-0189-069-D	1994-2854-079-A	2005-1509-127-B	2011-0846-015-A	2012-0266-015-B
1987-0189-069-E	1994-3026-069-A	2005-1880-127-A	2011-0855-015-B	2012-0293-015-A
1987-0310-131	1994-3373-103-D	2005-2325-089-E	2011-0866-117-B	2012-0299-015-B
1987-0313-131-B	1995-0370-103-H	2005-2325-089-G	2011-0867-117-B	2012-0315-015-B
1987-0313-131-D	1995-0507-089-A	2005-2364-025-A	2011-0943-015-A	2012-0369-015-B
1987-0335-131-E	1995-2026-115	2005-2364-025-D	2011-1060-115-B	2012-0369-015-C
1987-0335-131-J	1995-2330-015-I	2005-2820-103-C	2011-1079-015-B	2012-0370-115-A
1987-0403-015-D	1995-2438-103-D	2005-3108-103-C	2011-1088-015-A	2012-0378-117-B
1987-0403-015-H	1995-2724-069	2005-6028-115-B	2011-1208-015-B	2012-0409-015-B

Table B-7. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 7

ER Numbers				
1987-0598-089-B	1995-2724-069-B	2005-6029-115-B	2011-1294-015-A	2012-0423-015-A
1987-0599-089-B	1995-3179-127-B	2005-6030-115-B	2011-1295-042-A	2012-0450-015-C
1987-1016-069	1995-3519-089-C	2005-6080-115-B	2011-1295-042-D	2012-0485-015-B
1987-1016-069-P	1995-3519-089-E	2005-6111-127-B	2011-1301-117-C	2012-0488-015-C
1987-1016-069-R	1995-8003-127-C	2005-6112-127-B	2011-1350-015-A	2012-0528-115-B
1987-1016-069-S	1995-8037-015-D	2005-6113-127-B	2011-1352-015-A	2012-0566-115-B
1987-1149-069-A02	1995-8046-131-A	2005-6119-131-B	2011-1353-015-A	2012-0567-115-B
1987-1662-079-B	1996-0249-103-B	2005-6120-131-B	2011-1353-015-D	2012-0568-115-B
1987-1663-131-B	1996-0332-117-A	2005-6149-015-C	2011-1354-015-A	2012-0569-115-B
1988-0172-131-C	1996-0332-117-EE	2005-6156-127-B	2011-1355-015-A	2012-0571-115-C
1988-0358-127-E	1996-0332-117-F	2006-0017-042-A	2011-1356-015-A	2012-0572-115-B
1988-0373-015-B	1996-0332-117-H	2006-0111-089-B	2011-1359-015-A	2012-0573-115-B
1988-0376-079-C	1996-0332-117-L	2006-0420-089-C	2011-1360-015-A	2012-0575-115-B
1988-0437-042	1996-0977-131-B	2006-0452-015-B	2011-1362-015-A	2012-0576-115-B
1988-0476-127-B	1996-1890-117	2006-0452-015-G	2011-1365-117-B	2012-0577-115-B
1988-0516-079-S	1996-1924-015-E	2006-0452-015-M	2011-1365-117-E	2012-0588-115-A
1988-0532-069-B	1996-2887-069-D	2006-0452-015-N	2011-1396-015-A	2012-0615-042-B
1988-1307-015-D	1996-8116-015-A	2006-0452-015-O	2011-1406-042-D	2012-0618-015-A
1988-1329-127-C	1996-8183-115-K	2006-0888-089-C	2011-1413-015-A	2012-0622-015-C
1988-1330-127-A	1997-0460-025-H	2006-0923-131-F	2011-1416-015-A	2012-0635-115-B
1988-1333-131-B	1997-0560-127-D	2006-1124-069-B	2011-1418-015-A	2012-0639-115-B
1988-1333-131-D	1997-0991-079-C	2006-1451-103-C	2011-1419-015-A	2012-0653-115-B
1988-1338-131-B	1997-2018-117-C	2006-1997-115-B	2011-1420-015-A	2012-0712-117-B
1988-1341-127-D	1997-2018-117-QQ	2006-2358-127-E	2011-1421-015-A	2012-0713-115-A
1988-1365-131-D	1997-2019-079-A	2006-2460-069-B	2011-1422-117-A	2012-0817-015-C
1988-1501-025-A	1997-2182-042-T	2006-6033-131-B	2011-1456-042-B	2012-0831-115-A
1989-0038-079-G	1997-2182-042-U	2006-6034-131-C	2011-1456-042-D	2012-0871-115-B
1989-0038-079-O	1997-6010-015	2006-6034-131-E	2011-1456-042-F	2012-0872-015-B
1989-0073-115-B	1997-6023-015-D	2006-6035-131-B	2011-1471-015-A	2012-0891-015-B
1989-0122-079-B	1997-6024-015-D	2006-6060-089-B	2011-1472-015-A	2012-0899-079-C
1989-0227-117-F	1997-6035-015-E	2006-6117-079-B	2011-1473-015-B	2012-0911-115-C
1989-0473-015-A	1997-6063-117-B	2006-7001-042-B	2011-1474-115-A	2012-0913-115-C
1989-0529-069-B	1997-6154-117-D	2006-7002-042-B	2011-1513-117-B	2012-0933-117-B
1989-0968-117-C	1997-6181-127-D	2006-7002-042-C	2011-1532-015-A	2012-0944-115-A
1989-1346-042-A	1997-8034-115-B	2006-7002-042-D	2011-1541-015-A	2012-0958-042-B
1989-1382-115-B	1997-8045-089-B	2006-7002-042-E	2011-1544-015-A	2012-0993-015-A
1989-1421-015	1997-8077-117-D	2007-0728-089-A	2011-1547-015-A	2012-1030-115-A
1989-1536-117	1997-8090-127-A	2007-0815-103-C	2011-1604-015-B	2012-1031-015-B
1989-1644-089-F	1998-0300-069	2007-0815-103-D	2011-1607-015-A	2012-1036-117-B
1990-0084-079-K	1998-0612-117	2007-0817-103-B	2011-1631-015-A	2012-1136-115-B
1990-0084-117-B	1998-0631-042	2007-1478-042-J	2011-1652-015-A	2012-1137-015-B
1990-0625-089-M	1998-1499-089-E	2007-1809-117-A	2011-1679-015-A	2012-1140-115-B
1990-0735-131	1998-1499-089-I	2007-2023-117-C	2011-1680-015-A	2012-1170-115-B
1990-0735-131-F	1998-1721-015-I	2007-2053-089-B	2011-1708-015-A	2012-1171-015-B
1990-0735-131-X	1998-2336-115	2007-2330-069-D	2011-1711-115-A	2012-1192-115-A
1990-0974-089-B	1998-2497-042-P	2007-6161-115-B	2011-1712-115-A	2012-1192-115-B
1990-1149-103-C	1998-6065-089-C	2008-0217-115-C	2011-1719-015-A	2012-1235-115-A
1990-1743-089-B	1998-6065-089-D	2008-1758-115-D	2011-1729-015-A	2012-1249-117-B
1990-1862-131-F	1998-6169-079-C	2008-1758-115-H	2011-1759-115-A	2012-1254-015-A
1990-2651-089-D	1998-8011-103-K	2008-1758-115-I	2011-1767-015-E	2012-1307-115-B
1991-1620-089-C	1998-8011-103-N	2008-1758-115-J	2011-1775-015-A	2012-1312-015-A
1991-2503-127-D	1998-8011-103-Q	2008-1758-115-N	2011-1776-115-B	2012-1344-015-A
1991-3123-115-E	1998-8011-103-S	2008-1758-115-O	2011-1778-015-A	2012-1346-115-A

Table B-7. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 7

ER Numbers				
1991-3217-117-G	1998-8011-103-U	2008-1758-115-P	2011-1778-015-E	2012-1352-015-B
1991-3485-127-B	1999-0647-117-B	2008-1758-115-V	2011-1818-131-B	2012-1353-015-A
1991-3586-131-C	1999-0648-117	2008-2068-131-E	2011-1819-117-B	2012-1354-015-A
1991-3586-131-E	1999-0827-042	2008-2473-042-DD	2011-1845-015-A	2012-1370-015-F
1991-3835-117	1999-1868-127-I	2008-2473-042-F	2011-1866-117-B	2012-1374-015-A
1991-4007-103-A	1999-1887-089-E	2008-2473-042-T	2011-1870-015-B	2012-1375-015-A
1991-4323-117-B	1999-1921-117-G	2008-2473-042-Z	2011-1910-079-A	2012-1388-015-C
1992-0467-069-C	1999-2170-025	2008-2587-117-C	2011-1951-015-A	2012-1393-115-B
1992-0475-079-B	1999-2646-089-B	2008-6043-117-C	2011-1971-015-A	2012-1420-115-B
1992-0486-089-D	1999-2708-089-D	2008-6155-069-B	2011-1973-042-A	2012-1450-015-B
1992-0774-079-D	1999-6028-131-C	2008-6157-069-B	2011-1973-042-D	2012-1455-015-B
1992-1446-127-K	1999-6048-015-B	2008-6192-115-B	2011-2025-015-B	2012-1481-015-B
1992-1492-115	1999-6056-015-M	2008-6220-042-B	2011-2025-015-C	2012-1483-115-B
1992-1570-115-C	1999-6072-117	2009-0261-015-B	2011-2028-015-A	2012-1550-015-B
1992-1689-115-F	1999-6156-115-C	2009-0554-069-C	2011-2061-015-A	2012-1700-115-A
1992-1690-079-D	1999-6191-127-B	2009-0592-042-K	2011-2085-015-C	2012-1719-113-B
1992-1692-115-E	1999-6192-127-B	2009-0592-042-S	2011-2089-015-A	2012-1723-015-A
1992-2000-115-E	1999-8028-015-D	2009-0717-115-B	2011-2097-115-B	2012-1726-115-A
1992-2009-089	2000-0881-042-E	2009-0922-042-C	2011-2122-015-A	2012-1767-015-B
1992-2190-089-B	2000-0881-042-H	2009-1636-127-D	2011-2125-117-B	2012-1768-042-B
1992-2190-089-RR	2000-0881-042-K	2009-1754-103-F	2011-2131-015-B	2012-1779-015-A
1992-2270-015-B	2000-0890-103-M	2009-1825-117-B	2011-2133-015-D	2012-1818-015-B
1992-2441-117-F	2000-0890-103-S	2009-1897-042-B	2011-2138-042-A	2012-1852-015-B
1992-2931-117-C	2000-1364-069	2009-1937-079-B	2011-2144-042-A	2012-1947-015-B
1992-2932-117-C	2000-2478-015-F	2009-1941-117-B	2011-2144-042-C	2012-1949-015-B
1992-2933-127-D	2000-2502-103-C	2009-1942-117-B	2011-2146-015-B	2012-1984-042-A
1992-2938-127-B	2000-2539-131-F	2009-6011-115-B	2011-2147-131-B	2012-2044-115-B
1992-3133-079-D	2000-2985-103-A	2009-6042-015-B	2011-2148-015-B	2012-2112-115-B
1992-3148-015-D	2000-3202-015-I	2009-6047-015-B	2011-2148-015-C	2012-2114-115-B
1992-3585-131-B	2000-6202-115-B	2009-6188-015-B	2011-2173-015-A	2012-2182-115-A
1992-3655-127-B	2000-8022-115-C	2009-6230-069-B	2011-2207-015-C	2012-2184-115-A
1992-3784-079-J	2000-8029-015-O	2010-0223-117-D	2011-2208-015-C	2012-2241-115-A
1992-3857-103-B	2000-8029-015-V	2010-0493-015-B	2011-2221-015-B	2012-2312-015-A
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1992-3857-103-D	2000-8047-127-J	2010-0961-015-B	2011-2223-015-B	2012-2464-117-B
1992-3857-103-DD	2001-0001-015-A	2010-1005-117-C	2011-2236-115-C	2012-2487-015-B
1992-3857-103-E	2001-0001-015-C	2010-1120-015-B	2011-2246-113-B	2012-2506-015-B
1992-3857-103-U	2001-0404-115-A	2010-1120-015-C	2011-2253-131-B	2012-2551-115-A
1993-0195-015-A	2001-0416-089	2010-1120-015-E	2011-2263-042-B	2012-2597-115-A
1993-0307-079-E	2001-0942-015-E	2010-1150-015-A	2011-2265-113-B	2012-2661-115-A
1993-0400-115-C	2001-0942-015-F	2010-1413-042-B	2011-2271-015-A	2013-0193-115-A
1993-0454-131-E	2001-0942-015-G	2010-1461-117-B	2011-2275-015-D	2013-0195-115-A
1993-0846-131-C	2001-0942-015-J	2010-1506-042-D	2011-2275-015-E	2013-0243-115-A
1993-0846-131-F	2001-1413-015-A	2010-1554-042-EE	2011-2276-015-B	2013-0443-115-A
1993-0846-131-L	2001-1414-015-A	2010-1554-042-F	2011-2277-015-A	2013-0542-131-A
1993-0939-117	2001-1415-015-A	2010-1554-042-O	2011-2303-015-B	2013-0846-079-A
1993-0939-117-JJ	2001-1417-015-A	2010-1560-117-B	2011-2325-015-B	2013-8013-015-B
1993-0939-117-MM				

Table B-8. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 8

ER Numbers				
1981-0021-077-B	1990-1898-055-B	1994-0286-043-D	1999-3110-095-I	2005-6056-077-E
1981-0119-042-B	1990-1911-055-C	1994-0287-011-C	1999-3141-011	2005-6127-043-B
1981-0119-042-C	1990-1915-055-J	1994-0380-043-A	1999-3184-011-A	2005-6154-041-B
1981-0153-055-A	1990-2078-095-A	1994-0394-077-C	1999-6045-041-B	2005-6162-077-B
1981-0231-042-B	1990-2232-075-E	1994-0511-011	1999-6161-041-B	2005-8017-043-C
1981-0231-107-B	1990-2263-055-B	1994-0709-011	2000-0173-017-B	2005-8017-043-H
1981-0247-077-A	1990-2264-011-B	1994-0798-107-C	2000-0196-075-K	2005-8036-077-C
1981-0267-077-B	1990-2266-095-C	1994-0806-075-A	2000-0835-011	2005-8043-077-E
1981-0267-077-C	1990-2298-075-B	1994-0839-107-BB	2000-1022-041-G	2005-8061-041-B
1981-0267-077-L	1990-2621-042-B	1994-0839-107-P	2000-1238-011-G	2006-0017-042-E
1981-0267-077-M	1990-2621-042-E	1994-0908-077-J	2000-1831-042-GG	2006-0136-042-D
1981-0342-043-B	1990-2887-043	1994-1429-011-D	2000-1831-042-JJ2	2006-0461-011-B
1981-0352-043-B	1991-0014-055-C	1994-1537-055-C	2000-1831-042-P	2006-0497-095-C
1981-0433-089-B	1991-0135-041-B	1994-1635-011-E	2000-1831-042-P1	2006-0532-043-B
1981-0483-041-D	1991-0150-055-B	1994-1635-011-G	2000-1831-042-P10	2006-0558-041-B
1981-0682-011-A	1991-0223-042-D	1994-1663-055-A	2000-1831-042-P2	2006-0681-055-B
1981-0686-025	1991-0296-043-D	1994-1808-077-B	2000-1831-042-P7	2006-0735-089-B
1981-1306-041-B	1991-0370-077-G	1994-2003-107-G	2000-1831-042-UU	2006-0807-075-C
1981-1347-075-B	1991-0370-077-H	1994-2050-077-C	2000-1831-042-WW	2006-1020-041-B
1981-1351-055-B	1991-0445-055-C	1994-2096-095-K	2000-1837-011-B	2006-1072-055-B
1981-2010-042-B	1991-0492-055-D	1994-2155-055-BB	2000-2156-042-D	2006-1072-055-D
1982-0050-011-B	1991-0663-055-B	1994-2155-055-GG	2000-2323-075-D	2006-1096-043-B
1982-0190-011-I	1991-0720-011-B	1994-2155-055-HH	2000-2500-107-G	2006-1280-089-A
1982-0358-055	1991-0918-055	1994-2155-055-K	2000-2889-055-C	2006-1477-042-C
1982-0648-042-A41	1991-1053-011-B	1994-2155-055-TT	2000-2889-055-G	2006-1491-041-B
1982-0648-042-CCC	1991-1411-077-B	1994-2384-095-I	2000-2889-055-H	2006-1521-095-D
1982-0648-042-O	1991-1411-077-C	1994-2484-075-D	2000-3004-041-C	2006-1553-041-B
1982-0648-042-VV	1991-1907-055-C	1994-3302-107-B	2000-3536-055-D	2006-1553-041-E
1982-0648-042-XXX	1991-2007-075-F	1994-3313-077-B	2000-3633-089-B	2006-1700-043-D
1982-R002-042	1991-2080-011-A	1994-3331-077-F	2000-3641-089-B	2006-2040-055-B
1983-0530-095-B	1991-2184-095-B	1995-0077-075-A	2000-3643-043-G	2006-2622-077-B
1983-0907-043-B	1991-2248-042-KK	1995-0089-055-A	2000-6122-041-C	2006-2665-011-A
1983-0976-077-G	1991-2276-055	1995-0305-011-B	2000-6213-001-B	2006-6016-011-B
1984-0171-042-G	1991-2343-095-D	1995-0449-011-B	2000-6213-001-D	2006-6039-095-B
1984-0171-042-I	1991-2469-095-B	1995-0549-055	2000-6216-055-B	2006-6056-055-B
1984-0316-001-A	1991-2558-095-C	1995-0968-077-B	2000-6217-041-C	2006-6077-095-C
1984-0415-043-E	1991-2716-011-D	1995-1017-011-E	2000-6218-001-C	2006-6077-095-D
1984-0908-055-C	1991-3042-055-C	1995-1097-041	2000-6220-041-C	2006-6121-089-B
1984-0966-077-W	1991-3046-075-J	1995-1224-107-M	2000-6263-043-C	2006-6124-041-B
1984-1083-077-JJ	1991-3046-075-Q	1995-1246-042-C	2000-6264-075-B	2006-8007-017-E
1984-1105-077-C	1991-3046-075-S	1995-1589-041	2000-6265-075	2006-8045-042-B
1984-1147-011	1991-3046-075-V	1995-1997-011-D	2000-6278-075-B	2007-0047-011-D
1984-1244-041-C	1991-3282-011	1995-2047-011	2000-6295-075-C	2007-0223-025-K
1984-1641-095-B	1991-3338-025	1995-2260-095-B	2000-8006-107-A	2007-0492-055-C
1984-1899-042	1991-3338-025-B	1995-2260-095-J	2001-0399-041-D	2007-0590-095-D
1984-1899-042-H	1991-3553-055-B	1995-2647-075-B	2001-0521-095-E	2007-0601-077-B
1985-0042-011-T	1991-3698-011-B	1995-2731-089-C	2001-1526-043-J	2007-0767-075-C
1985-0214-025-B	1991-3875-011-C	1995-2896-077-B	2001-2409-055-E	2007-0840-011-D
1985-1523-011-FF	1991-4218-011-B	1995-2903-055-E	2001-2502-001-B	2007-0893-089-C
1985-1523-011-N	1991-4320-089-B	1995-3573-075-J	2001-2891-095-E	2007-1211-011-C
1985-1871-075-E	1991-4322-095-D	1995-3824-077-B	2001-2924-095-C	2007-1334-133-B
1985-1871-075-J	1991-4354-107-E	1995-3846-077-R	2001-3391-011-E	2007-1354-043-F
1986-0367-025-A	1991-4383-075-B	1995-8049-095-C	2001-3453-095-F	2007-1560-043-B

Table B-8. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 8

ER Numbers				
1986-0410-077-C	1991-4525-055-C	1996-0295-041-D	2001-3578-055-B	2007-1713-089-E
1986-0410-077-H	1992-0022-011-C	1996-0779-011-F	2001-3644-011-C	2007-1761-041-B
1986-0410-077-J	1992-0052-095-D	1996-0875-041	2001-3644-011-D	2007-1761-041-C
1986-0713-089-E	1992-0126-107-F	1996-1071-011	2001-4109-095-C	2007-1903-075-C
1986-0717-089-C	1992-0131-011-B	1996-1166-011-E	2001-6087-077-B	2007-2327-075-D
1986-0767-042-A	1992-0252-011	1996-1211-042-F	2001-6135-043-G	2007-2368-041-C
1986-0848-055	1992-0375-055-C	1996-1211-042-M	2001-6171-095-B	2007-2431-075-D
1986-1319-077-D	1992-0388-011-D	1996-1211-042-O	2001-6247-077-C	2007-2558-089-A
1987-0054-011	1992-0444-025-D	1996-1444-089-D	2002-0274-042-B	2007-6102-075-A
1987-0065-095-C	1992-0444-025-G	1996-2045-042-B	2002-0312-089-B	2007-6144-077-B
1987-0085-041	1992-0659-055	1996-2153-095-B	2002-0468-095-F	2007-6145-077-B
1987-0100-041-D	1992-0705-095-L	1996-2199-095-C	2002-0890-043-E	2007-6147-089-B
1987-0147-011-E	1992-0736-075-D	1996-2315-042-D	2002-0895-041-D	2007-6155-055-E
1987-0147-011-SS	1992-0760-089-C	1996-2315-042-F	2002-1134-075-D	2007-8032-043-E
1987-0169-095-D	1992-0852-075-D	1996-2315-042-H	2002-1625-089-F	2008-0007-041-C
1987-0343-042-UU	1992-0852-075-E	1996-3074-041	2002-1648-095-B	2008-0085-042-H
1987-0354-011-G	1992-0911-025-A	1996-8132-077-B	2002-1711-041-C	2008-0582-089-B
1987-0354-011-J	1992-1308-077-F	1996-8136-011-A	2002-1711-041-D	2008-0695-011-F
1987-0589-011-E	1992-1344-075-A	1996-8147-095	2002-2412-055-N	2008-0784-043-C
1987-0593-077-C	1992-1383-075-B	1996-8207-055	2002-2470-075-D	2008-1211-041-B
1987-0596-077-B	1992-1465-011-E	1996-8250-077-C	2002-2572-095-B	2008-1687-077-C
1987-1023-011-B	1992-1742-011-E	1996-R015-042	2002-2591-025-E	2008-1781-041-B
1987-1145-055-C	1992-1763-041-C	1996-R016-042	2002-2681-011-C	2008-1990-095-A
1987-1299-095-B	1992-1877-043-C	1996-R017-042	2002-2681-011-D	2008-2163-011-E
1987-1410-041-YY	1992-2009-089	1996-R018-042	2002-6089-011-E	2008-6067-075-B
1987-1513-089-A	1992-2010-089-F	1996-R019-042	2002-6124-043-B	2008-6075-133-B
1987-1525-055-H	1992-2075-011-D	1996-R020-042	2002-6166-041-B	2008-6146-075-B
1987-1525-055-I	1992-2166-075-B	1996-R021-042	2002-8029-075-J	2008-6160-075-B
1988-0130-077-C	1992-2190-089-B	1996-R022-042	2003-0244-077-B	2008-6175-075-B
1988-0200-025-D	1992-2190-089-RR	1996-R023-042	2003-0317-043-C	2008-6196-107-B
1988-0224-095-E	1992-2195-011-F	1996-R024-042	2003-0317-043-E	2008-6199-011-B
1988-0224-095-FF	1992-2265-025	1996-R025-042	2003-0486-077-E	2008-6216-077-B
1988-0318-011-C	1992-2464-011-B	1996-R026-042	2003-0486-077-F	2008-6224-055-B
1988-0479-025	1992-2527-055-J	1997-0041-055-EE	2003-0544-075-D	2009-0247-075-B
1988-0479-025-C	1992-2669-011	1997-0096-095-C	2003-0544-075-I	2009-0475-041-C
1988-0481-042-B	1992-2713-077-B	1997-0769-042	2003-0692-042-L	2009-0574-011-B
1988-0481-042-E	1992-2739-055-B	1997-1057-075-B	2003-0738-077-C	2009-1096-043-B
1988-0636-095-E	1992-2739-055-D	1997-1222-089-K	2003-0792-095-E	2009-1165-075-A
1988-0636-095-K	1992-2752-011-C	1997-1244-011-I	2003-0880-055-C	2009-1483-077-B
1988-0636-095-L	1992-2848-095-E	1997-1480-089-C	2003-1200-089-D	2009-1650-043-C
1988-0636-095-M	1992-2848-095-I	1997-1485-089-D	2003-1220-077-F	2009-1684-095-C
1988-0636-095-O	1992-3028-025-I	1997-1549-042-A	2003-1239-041-C	2009-1800-011-B
1988-0644-043-B	1992-3092-095-C	1997-1557-011-C	2003-1391-043-B	2009-1897-042-B
1988-0735-025-B	1992-3295-011-F	1997-1658-077-J	2003-1459-075-M	2009-6020-077-D
1988-0887-011-C	1992-3303-077-C	1997-1807-077-C	2003-1495-025-D	2009-6101-055-B
1988-0904-095-B	1992-3307-095-B	1997-2182-042-MM	2003-1495-025-L	2009-6116-055-B
1988-1240-077-D	1992-3452-043-B	1997-2182-042-T	2003-1882-043-G	2009-6117-041-B
1988-1240-077-E	1992-3643-042-B	1997-2182-042-U	2003-1887-089-B	2009-6126-055-B
1988-1427-089-I	1992-3782-011-B	1997-2182-042-V	2003-1906-011-B	2009-6127-055-B
1988-1506-017-E	1992-4042-041-E	1997-2686-077-S	2003-2135-095-B	2009-6167-075-B
1988-1663-043-C	1992-4042-041-F	1997-2686-077-X	2003-2742-095-D	2009-8056-055-C
1988-1663-043-D	1993-0290-075-A	1997-2771-075	2003-5019-099-C	2010-0250-042-C
1989-0698-055-N	1993-0317-075-F	1997-6027-077-F	2003-8024-011-D	2010-0250-042-F

Table B-8. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 8

ER Numbers				
1989-0753-077-C	1993-0375-089-D	1997-6149-017-D	2004-0021-077-B	2010-0310-077-B
1989-0753-077-O	1993-0523-095-E	1997-6149-017-O	2004-0102-095-B	2010-0528-043-C
1989-0767-041-G	1993-0535-011-C	1997-8047-011-B	2004-0177-095-A	2010-0737-075-B
1989-0848-001-B	1993-1180-043-B	1997-8048-011-C	2004-0269-077-F	2010-0763-055-B
1989-1092-011-B	1993-1358-095-B	1997-8049-011-B	2004-0594-043-D	2010-0827-095-B
1989-1184-043-B	1993-1390-089-B	1997-8091-011-C	2004-0647-089-C	2010-0990-107-B
1989-1188-075-B	1993-1695-077-C	1997-8095-043	2004-0860-095-F	2010-1029-025-B
1989-1646-107-C	1993-1731-011-E	1998-0070-095-C	2004-1763-055-B	2010-1143-055-B
1989-1711-077-J	1993-1844-041-E	1998-0138-075-C	2004-2325-055-C	2010-1143-055-C
1989-1717-005-B	1993-1892-077-C	1998-0221-011-E	2004-2530-089-E	2010-1301-095-B
1990-0128-042-D	1993-2067-011-B	1998-0289-011-D	2004-2801-077-B	2010-1326-042-G
1990-0129-095-C	1993-2076-133-O	1998-0355-011	2004-2802-043-C	2010-1370-077-B
1990-0282-077	1993-2076-133-P	1998-0355-011-G	2004-2941-055-B	2010-2024-041-B
1990-0282-077-B	1993-2365-055-D	1998-1031-089-H	2004-3163-043-R	2010-2052-075-C
1990-0282-077-EEE	1993-2365-055-E	1998-1055-095-H	2004-5117-095-C	2010-2254-043-B
1990-0282-077-FFF	1993-2365-055-K	1998-1177-077-E	2004-6023-089-B	2010-2324-077-D
1990-0282-077-GGG	1993-2365-055-M	1998-2054-043-E	2004-8003-075-D	2010-6107-077-B
1990-0282-077-JJJ	1993-2442-025-F	1998-2145-077-B	2004-8018-011-E	2010-8052-095-A
1990-0282-077-L	1993-2535-095-B	1998-2289-011-C	2004-8021-095-E	2010-8060-075-A
1990-0282-077-RR	1993-2535-095-E	1998-2329-077	2004-8038-011-E	2010-8095-077-B
1990-0282-077-YY	1993-2792-041-B	1998-2525-011-II	2005-0021-095-C	2011-0519-095-A
1990-0432-095-B	1993-2847-043-C	1998-2525-011-P	2005-0420-011-B	2011-1030-042-A
1990-0555-042-H	1993-3010-055-D	1998-2528-055-B	2005-0463-077-C	2011-1240-042-D
1990-0555-042-I	1993-3193-043-D	1998-6011-107-G	2005-0625-089-I	2011-1240-042-G
1990-0674-041-B	1993-3283-095-D	1998-6038-077-B	2005-0735-089-B	2011-1333-089-B
1990-0717-041-D	1993-3394-025	1998-6067-095-C	2005-0879-089-H	2011-1364-041-B
1990-0749-011-F	1993-3596-077-F	1998-8001-055-G	2005-1069-055-C	2011-1367-011-B
1990-0752-041-F	1993-3652-043-B	1998-8011-103-U	2005-1387-055-B	2011-1705-043-C
1990-0833-075-D	1993-3707-011	1999-0013-042-H	2005-1792-011-B	2011-1828-043-B
1990-0833-075-J	1993-3708-077-B	1999-0156-041-B	2005-1948-041-C	2011-2181-041-B
1990-0853-011-B	1993-3957-043-C	1999-0156-041-L	2005-2091-077-C	2011-2248-041-B
1990-0902-133-C	1993-4035-095-F	1999-0323-041-YY	2005-2267-043-F	2011-2298-041-C
1990-0985-011-B	1993-4041-042-DD	1999-0736-077-E	2005-2465-043-B	2011-2357-011-A
1990-1010-055-B	1993-4058-041-F	1999-0758-095-D	2005-2467-095-C	2011-8008-107-B
1990-1085-075-B	1993-4058-041-G	1999-0843-042	2005-2467-095-D	2011-8145-011-B
1990-1254-055-A03	1993-4068-095-H	1999-0852-011-E	2005-2467-095-I	2012-0333-011-A
1990-1254-055-C	1993-4206-107-G	1999-1473-055-D	2005-2520-075-B	2012-0334-011-A
1990-1323-043-B	1994-0061-075	1999-2191-043-H	2005-2568-011-C	2012-0336-011-A
1990-1421-075-E	1994-0062-041-C	1999-2611-075	2005-2703-041-F	2012-0339-011-A
1990-1527-055-II	1994-0063-043-B	1999-2811-043-H	2005-6008-095-B	2012-0340-011-A
1990-1618-041-B	1994-0071-043	1999-3110-095-E	2005-6034-041-B	2012-1063-043-C
1990-1838-077-B	1994-0102-089-D	1999-3110-095-G	2005-6048-077-B	2012-1733-041-A
1990-1892-043-F	1994-0117-095-C			

Table B-9. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 9

ER Numbers				
1947-0001-045	1990-0379-071-H	1993-4041-042-Q	1998-2699-017-D	2004-2319-042-E
1981-0087-133-E	1990-0400-071-A	1993-4059-017-J	1998-6005-045-B	2004-2319-042-H
1981-0109-001-A	1990-0400-071-B	1993-4179-017-O	1998-6006-045	2004-2802-043-C
1981-0109-001-B	1990-0497-071	1993-4217-091-F	1998-6066-011-B	2004-6032-017-B
1981-0283-043-B	1990-0497-071-B	1993-4335-029-E	1998-6091-091-B	2004-6049-091-C
1981-0300-071	1990-0497-071-T	1994-0010-029-D	1998-8014-071-C	2004-6069-029-B
1981-0382-017-B	1990-0543-042	1994-0039-071-B	1998-8028-091	2004-6070-133-B
1981-0858-001-C	1990-0621-091	1994-0061-075	1999-0013-042-H	2004-6084-091-D
1981-0878-091	1990-0621-091-GG	1994-0288-001-B	1999-0250-133-C	2004-6103-017-B
1981-0888-017-B	1990-0621-091-YY	1994-0356-091-D	1999-0278-029	2004-6107-042-B
1981-0975-071-A	1990-0626-071-C	1994-0365-017-I	1999-0284-017-E	2004-6112-017-E
1981-1300-001-B	1990-0798-091-E	1994-0579-029-B	1999-0753-043-B	2004-6116-091-D
1981-1309-017-C	1990-0902-133-C	1994-0649-133-C	1999-0843-042	2004-6120-017-F
1981-1310-017-B	1990-0979-071-A	1994-0715-071-A	1999-0843-042-M	2004-6124-017-E
1981-1310-017-F	1990-1012-071-C	1994-0759-017-F	1999-0843-042-N	2004-6126-091-D
1981-1312-017-B	1990-1374-133-G	1994-0940-029-B	1999-1160-091	2004-6131-029-B
1981-1322-133-B	1990-1393-071-D	1994-1021-001-A	1999-1399-101-A	2004-8001-029-D
1981-1337-071-B	1990-1446-071-G	1994-1100-029-C	1999-1500-091	2004-8011-017-H
1981-1339-071-B	1990-1586-071-B	1994-1325-017-B	1999-1514-017-J	2004-8037-091-E
1981-1357-045-B	1990-1643-133-B	1994-1337-017-D	1999-1519-029-W	2004-8046-029-C
1981-1367-091-B	1990-1702-017-F	1994-1340-011-A	1999-1709-071-A	2004-8051-091-A
1981-1368-091-B	1990-1729-001-E	1994-1412-045-E	1999-1862-045-C	2004-8051-091-E
1981-1369-091-B	1990-1800-029-D	1994-1458-091-C	1999-1885-017-H	2005-0032-091-A
1981-1370-091-B	1990-1930-071-E	1994-1458-091-J	1999-2190-133-C	2005-0413-029-A
1981-1373-075-A	1990-1944-029-B	1994-1605-001-L	1999-2354-001-B	2005-0413-029-C
1981-1378-017-B	1990-2005-091-B	1994-1611-133-C	1999-2414-017-E	2005-0782-029-G
1981-1383-071-B	1990-2061-042-D	1994-1623-029	1999-2468-001-F	2005-1019-071-B
1981-1384-071-B	1990-2117-029-A	1994-1649-133-B	1999-2584-029-F	2005-1709-133-B
1981-1385-071-B	1990-2139-071	1994-1669-029-D	1999-2858-091	2005-2319-091-B
1981-1386-071-A	1990-2146-011-B	1994-1710-091-A	1999-2981-042	2005-2319-091-C
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1982-0375-071	1990-2714-001-C	1994-2418-133-B	2000-0456-029-E	2005-6055-029-D
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1982-0773-042-B	1991-0089-091-C	1994-2567-133-B	2000-0773-017	2005-6060-133-B
1982-0815-071-A	1991-0237-071-A	1994-2567-133-E	2000-0780-011-D	2005-6104-029-B
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1983-0723-001-I	1991-0361-001-S	1994-2628-041-G	2000-0987-071-B	2005-6163-133-B
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1983-0869-011	1991-0406-029-G	1994-2768-017-C	2000-1482-001-C	2005-8003-091-C

Table B-9. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 9

ER Numbers				
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1985-0468-029-LL	1991-3731-029-B	1995-1361-029	2001-1500-029-G	2007-0600-029-C
1985-0468-029-NN	1991-3747-133-P	1995-1622-133-B	2001-2311-017-A	2007-0724-075-A
1985-0468-029-QQ	1991-3878-029-G	1995-1742-101-G	2001-2503-045-E	2007-1196-101-E
1985-0468-029-S	1991-3931-071-C	1995-1822-029-C	2001-2925-029-C	2007-1334-133-B
1985-0726-133	1991-3993-071-B	1995-1964-029-C	2001-2938-133-F	2007-1454-043-E
1985-0819-133-D	1991-3993-071-C	1995-2047-011	2001-2955-045-B	2007-1842-045-C
1985-0950-042-D	1991-4071-001-F	1995-2047-011-G	2001-2998-091-H	2007-2108-017-B
1985-1039-091-B	1991-4085-071-C	1995-2093-071-C	2001-3164-133-C	2007-2129-029-C
1985-1255-071-B	1991-4195-071	1995-2107-133-B	2001-3164-133-Q	2007-2295-091-B
1985-1268-091	1991-4202-091-C	1995-2108-045-E	2001-3435-029-B	2007-2338-071-E

Table B-9. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 9

ER Numbers				
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1985-1871-075-E	1992-0304-017-G	1995-2788-091-H	2001-6277-075-C	2007-6035-029-D
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1987-0877-091-C	1992-3180-001-D	1996-1700-091-B	2002-6141-029-B	2008-2160-091-A
1987-0928-091-A	1992-3195-071-B	1996-1794-042-A	2002-6142-091-B	2008-6008-133-B
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1987-0928-091-H	1992-3325-045-G	1996-1858-001-C	2002-6181-017-B	2008-6074-071-B
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1987-0957-042	1992-3445-071-C	1996-2158-001-D	2002-8001-133-A	2008-6161-071-B
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1987-1000-071-A	1992-3625-133-I	1996-2193-029-F	2002-8009-029-B	2008-6182-133-B
1987-1047-071-C	1992-3758-071-B	1996-2257-001	2002-8010-045-A	2008-6182-133-E
1987-1047-071-D	1992-3883-091-B	1996-2362-029-E	2002-8013-091-A	2008-6207-133-B
1987-1047-071-F	1992-3898-091-M	1996-2409-001-D	2002-8018-091-B	2008-6208-133-B
1987-1078-133-B	1992-3905-133-D	1996-2473-017-I	2002-8023-091-B	2008-6209-071-B
1987-1160-029-B	1992-3993-029-D	1996-2537-045	2002-8027-091-B	2008-6217-017-B
1987-1172-017-J	1992-4021-017-I	1996-2596-091	2002-8029-075-J	2008-6226-071-B
1987-1172-017-S	1992-4021-017-K	1996-2995-091-B	2002-8034-045-B	2008-8004-091-C

Table B-9. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 9

ER Numbers				
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1987-1472-091-A	1993-0567-071-C	1996-8074-029-B	2002-8051-001-H	2009-1753-017-B
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1989-1184-042	1993-3138-029-C	1997-8083-091	2003-8023-071-G	2010-8005-045-A
1989-1419-071-A	1993-3139-029-D	1998-0052-043-C	2003-8042-133-G	2010-8006-029-D
1989-1513-011-B	1993-3140-029-B	1998-0443-017-B	2003-8054-029-D	2010-9000-017-D
1989-1620-077-D	1993-3149-029	1998-0561-029	2004-0033-091-D	2011-0212-042-C
1989-1636-029-B	1993-3211-029	1998-0917-091	2004-0033-091-E	2011-0212-042-E
1989-1637-133-F	1993-3276-001-B	1998-0959-091	2004-0235-133-B	2011-0543-043-E
1989-1639-045-F	1993-3433-071-E	1998-1124-091	2004-0307-091-G	2011-0833-071-D

Table B-9. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 9

ER Numbers				
1989-1645-011-B	1993-3470-017-C	1998-1413-091-E	2004-0311-029-B	2011-1007-071-B
1989-1645-011-C	1993-3610-029	1998-1456-133-B	2004-0363-071-D	2011-1444-091-B
1989-1650-017-K	1993-3709-091-D	1998-1571-029-A	2004-0567-017-E	2011-1668-071-D
1989-1667-029-B	1993-3710-091-D	1998-1668-017-D	2004-0570-011-B	2011-1907-071-B
1989-1711-077-B	1993-3771-071-C	1998-1871-042	2004-0665-091-B	2011-2255-133-C
1989-1711-077-J	1993-3774-133-C	1998-2181-017-D	2004-0902-042-D	2011-2461-071-D
1989-R013-042	1993-3834-091-B	1998-2359-071-A	2004-0990-043-D	2011-8141-045-A
1990-0113-001	1993-3905-042-J	1998-2440-091	2004-1103-091-C	2012-0335-011-A
1990-0113-001-E	1993-3905-042-R	1998-2594-043-D	2004-1416-133-B	2012-8122-029-B
1990-0341-029-C	1993-4038-029-GG	1998-2594-043-F	2004-1629-001-B	2013-0727-091-A
1990-0352-017-F	1993-4041-042-DD	1998-2656-043-B	2004-1760-029-D	2013-0811-091-A
1990-0365-133-B				

Table B-10. ER Surveys on File at PHMC within Region 10

ER Numbers				
1981-0672-045-D	1984-1096-101-D	1989-1293-045-B	1993-3814-101-D	2001-8007-101-L
1981-0672-045-P	1984-1099-042-EE	1989-1365-101-B	1993-3944-017-C	2002-8008-017-E
1981-1304-045-B	1984-1099-042-R	1989-1365-101-C	1994-0467-101-A	2002-8012-017-B
1981-1313-101-A	1984-1099-042-W	1989-1382-101	1994-1057-042-M	2003-6121-101-D
1981-1314-101-B	1984-1099-042-X	1989-1392-101-F	1994-1150-045	2003-8014-101-J
1981-1316-101-B	1984-1352-101-E	1989-1392-101-Z	1995-1170-101-G	2004-0295-045-E
1981-1324-101-B	1984-1560-045-B	1989-1639-045-F	1995-1742-101-G	2004-0297-045-C
1981-1353-045-B	1984-1708-042-B	1990-2441-045-C	1995-3347-101-A	2004-1357-045-C
1981-1358-045-B	1985-0080-017-B	1990-2498-101-MM	1996-0301-101-D	2004-2831-017-F
1981-2030-042-B	1985-0269-101-B	1991-0428-101-A	1996-0645-101-I	2004-2932-017-B
1982-0072-017-B	1985-0688-101-D	1991-0804-017-A	1996-0645-101-L	2006-0405-017-B
1982-0133-101	1985-0803-101-D	1991-0858-017-A	1996-0645-101-M	2006-8034-101-B
1982-0133-101-F	1985-1680-101-X	1991-1105-017-P	1996-1253-101-C	2007-0154-101-C
1982-0133-101-W	1986-0022-017-B	1991-1105-017-Q	1997-6109-045-E	2007-0722-101-C
1982-0230-101-D	1987-0957-042	1991-1105-042-M	1998-0782-017-J	2007-2107-017-A
1982-0230-101-O	1987-0957-042-B	1991-1754-042-B	1998-2301-042	2007-6074-045-B
1983-0055-045-B	1987-1230-017-B	1992-2487-101-O	1998-2301-042-B	2007-8002-101-B
1983-0685-101-B	1987-1591-101-B	1993-0123-101-D	1998-2425-101-C	2008-1042-101-C
1983-1152-101-D	1988-0211-101-E	1993-0509-045-B	1999-2124-101-D	2008-8020-101-F
1984-0265-101-D	1988-0271-101-C	1993-0956-101-DD	2000-0434-017-E	2009-0512-045-C
1984-0265-101-E	1988-0300-101-F	1993-0956-101-V	2000-1831-042-BB	2009-0655-101-KK
1984-0265-101-LL	1988-0592-101-B	1993-0983-101-B90	2000-1831-042-P9	2009-1698-101-B
1984-0265-101-O	1988-1269-017-D	1993-0983-101-B95	2000-1958-101-C	2010-2181-045-B
1984-0743-101-C	1988-1269-017-J	1993-0983-101-C12	2000-2032-101-B	2011-1855-045-H
1984-0822-017-L	1989-0653-101-A	1993-1891-101-C	2000-2573-045-F	PHMC-0002-045
1984-0822-017-M	1989-0943-101-C	1993-2618-101	2000-2966-101-A	PHMC-0003-045
1984-0822-017-N	1989-0943-101-E	1993-2618-101-R	2001-0109-101-A	